

Patterned Selfie Fractions

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Abstract

By selfie fractions, we understand that a fraction, where numerator and denominators are represented by same digits, with basic operation. This paper brings patterned selfie fractions. Patterned selfie fractions are understand as selfie fractions extendable in symmetric way. This work is with repeated digits.

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1 Introduction

Kieth [2, 3] for the first gave an idea of **dottable fraction**. It is a proper fraction where multiplication signs can be inserted into numerator and denominator, and the resulting fraction is equal to the original. Keith's [2, 3] idea was only with multiplication. For the first time, we extended it to other operations also, such as, with **addition, multiplication, potentiation**, etc. separately or jointly. We can think all of them together also. See below some examples studied by author [5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

1.1 Selfie Fraction

• Addable Fractions

$$\frac{96}{352} = \frac{9+6}{3+52}, \frac{182}{6734} = \frac{18+2}{6+734}, \text{ etc.} \quad (1)$$

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• **Subtractable Fractions**

$$\frac{204}{357} = \frac{20-4}{35-7}, \frac{726}{1089} = \frac{72-6}{108-9}, \text{ etc.} \quad (2)$$

• **Dottable Fraction**

$$\frac{13}{624} = \frac{1 \times 3}{6 \times 24}, \frac{416}{728} = \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8}, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

• **Dottable with Potentiation Fractions**

$$\frac{95}{342} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}, \frac{728}{1456} = \frac{7^2 \times 8}{14 \times 56}, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

• **Mixed Fractions: All Operations**

$$\frac{4980}{5312} = \frac{4-9+80}{5 \times (3+1)^2}, \frac{3249}{5168} = \frac{(3+2^4) \times 9}{(5-1) \times 68}, \text{ etc.} \quad (5)$$

Observing the examples given in (1) - (5), the numerator and denominator follows the same order of digits in both sides of each fraction separated by operations. These type of fractions, we call **Selfie fractions**. There are two situations. One when all digits appearing in each fraction are distinct and second, when there are repetitions of digits. Initially, we shall work with distinct digits. Due to big number of fractions, the repetition of digits shall be dealt elsewhere. The idea of **equivalent e fractions** is explained below.

1.2 Equivalent Selfie Fractions

Above we have given *selfie fractions* with single value in each case. There are many fractions, that can be written in more than one way, for example,

• **Addable**

$$\frac{1453}{2906} := \frac{1+453}{2+906} = \frac{145+3}{290+6} = \frac{1+45+3}{2+90+6}$$

• **Subtractable**

$$\frac{932}{1864} := \frac{9-32}{18-64} = \frac{93-2}{186-4}$$

• **Dottable and Addable**

$$\frac{1680}{59472} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 80}{59 \times 4 \times 72} = \frac{1+6+8+0}{59+472}$$

• **Dottable, Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{302}{8154} := \frac{30 \times 2}{81 \times 5 \times 4} = \frac{3+02}{81+54} = \frac{3-02}{81-54}.$$

• **Symmetric Addable and Subtractable**

$$\frac{645}{1290} := \frac{6-45}{12-90} = \frac{6+45}{12+90}.$$

• **Dottable and Addable together**

$$\frac{284}{639} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 4}{6 + 39} = \frac{28 + 4}{6 \times (3 + 9)}.$$

• **Mixed - All Operations**

$$\frac{73842}{90516} := \frac{7-3 \times (8-4^2)}{9 \times 05-1-6} = \frac{7 \times (3+8) + 4^2}{90+(5-1) \times 6} = \frac{738+4+2}{905+1+6}.$$

Equivalent expression given in equation (8), let us classify it as *symmetric equivalent fraction*. In this case we just change plus with minus and vice-versa. There are many fractions *double symmetric equivalent fraction* too. In this paper, we shall work with *equivalent fractions* given in equations (6)-(10). Below are few examples of equivalent fractions with all operations:

$$\frac{15}{240} := \frac{1^5}{2^4+0} = \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{42}{1785} := \frac{4^2}{17 \times 8 \times 5} = \frac{4-2}{17 \times 85}$$

$$\frac{95}{3420} := \frac{9-5}{(3 \times 4)^{2+0}} = \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{163}{7824} := \frac{1^{63}}{7 \times 8-2 \times 4} = \frac{16-3}{78 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{189}{4725} := \frac{1^{89}}{4-7 \times (2-5)} = \frac{1-8+9}{47-2+5} = \frac{18-9}{(47-2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{206}{3914} := \frac{2-0 \times 6}{39-1^4} = \frac{2+06}{(39-1) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{384}{9216} := \frac{3 \times (8-4)}{9 \times 2 \times 16} = \frac{3 \times 8-4}{(9^2-1) \times 6} = \frac{3^{8-4}}{9 \times 216}$$

$$\frac{624}{1950} := \frac{(6-2) \times 4}{1^9 \times 50} = \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{142}{69580} := \frac{1^{42}}{6 \times 95-80} = \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(6 \times 9-5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{149}{36207} := \frac{1^{49}}{3^{6 \times 2}-07} = \frac{1-4+9}{3^6 \times (2+0 \times 7)}$$

$$\frac{172}{63984} := \frac{1^7 \times 2}{6 \times (39-8) \times 4} = \frac{1 \times 7-2}{6^3 \times 9-84}$$

$$\frac{173}{29064} := \frac{1^{73}}{(-2+9) \times 06 \times 4} = \frac{1 \times 7-3}{2 \times (90-6) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{1975}{6320} := \frac{1^{97} \times 5}{6 \times 3-2+0} = \frac{(19-7) \times 5}{6 \times 32+0}$$

$$\frac{2457}{8190} := \frac{(2-4+5)^7}{81 \times 90} = \frac{2 \times 4 \times 57}{8 \times 190}$$

$$\frac{4256}{83790} := \frac{4 \times (2 \times 5-6)}{(8-3) \times 7 \times 9+0} = \frac{4 \times 2^5 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 7 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{5608}{79213} := \frac{(-5+6) \times 08}{7 \times 9 \times 2-13} = \frac{56+0 \times 8}{792-1^3}$$

$$\frac{7690}{13842} := \frac{7-6+9+0}{1 \times 3 \times (8-4+2)} = \frac{(7-6) \times 90}{(1 \times 3^{8-4} \times 2)}$$

$$\frac{9246}{37185} := \frac{92-46}{37 \times 1^8 \times 5} = \frac{9 \times 2 \times 46}{37 \times 18 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{21480}{73569} := \frac{(2-1+4) \times 8+0}{73-5+69} = \frac{2-1^4 \times 80}{7-3+5 \times 6 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{67284}{90513} := \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2 \times (8-4)}{90 \times 5-1+3} = \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2^{8-4}}{905-1^3}$$

Let's consider two selfie fractions of type $\frac{11}{1089} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10+89}$ and $\frac{11}{10989} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10+989}$. We observe that there is symmetric among these two selfie fraction. This symmetry allows us to extend the fraction for higher digits. This type of fractions, we call **patterned selfie fractions**. Below is a good list of **patterned selfie fractions** in two and three digits numerators, where in some cases there is a repetition of digits. For study on selfie fractions with repeated and non repeated digits refer Taneja [16, 17, 18, 19].

Remark 1.1. *The following remarks are considered:*

- Numerator is always less than denominator;
- Repetition of digits are allowed.

2 Patterned Selfie Fractions

2.1 Two Digits Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 1. \quad & \frac{11}{1089} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 89} \\
 & \frac{11}{10989} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 989} \\
 & \frac{11}{109989} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 9989} \\
 & \frac{11}{1099989} := \frac{1 \times 1}{10 + 99989}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5. \quad & \frac{11}{165} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{11}{1650} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{11}{16500} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{11}{165000} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9. \quad & \frac{11}{33} := \frac{1 + 1}{3 + 3} \\
 & \frac{11}{363} := \frac{1 + 1}{3 + 63} \\
 & \frac{11}{3663} := \frac{1 + 1}{3 + 663} \\
 & \frac{11}{36663} := \frac{1 + 1}{3 + 6663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2. \quad & \frac{11}{110} := \frac{1 \times 1}{1 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{11}{1100} := \frac{1 \times 1}{1 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{11}{11000} := \frac{1 \times 1}{1 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{11}{110000} := \frac{1 \times 1}{1 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6. \quad & \frac{11}{22} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{11}{220} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{11}{2200} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{11}{22000} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 10. \quad & \frac{11}{396} := \frac{1 + 1}{(3 + 9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{11}{3960} := \frac{1 + 1}{(3 + 9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{11}{39600} := \frac{1 + 1}{(3 + 9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{11}{396000} := \frac{1 + 1}{(3 + 9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3. \quad & \frac{11}{121} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 21} \\
 & \frac{11}{1221} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 221} \\
 & \frac{11}{12221} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 2221} \\
 & \frac{11}{122221} := \frac{1 + 1}{1 + 22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7. \quad & \frac{11}{242} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 42} \\
 & \frac{11}{2442} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 442} \\
 & \frac{11}{24442} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 4442} \\
 & \frac{11}{244442} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 + 44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11. \quad & \frac{11}{44} := \frac{1 + 1}{4 + 4} \\
 & \frac{11}{484} := \frac{1 + 1}{4 + 84} \\
 & \frac{11}{4884} := \frac{1 + 1}{4 + 884} \\
 & \frac{11}{48884} := \frac{1 + 1}{4 + 8884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4. \quad & \frac{11}{1386} := \frac{1 \times 1}{(13 + 8) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{11}{13860} := \frac{1 \times 1}{(13 + 8) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{11}{138600} := \frac{1 \times 1}{(13 + 8) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{11}{1386000} := \frac{1 \times 1}{(13 + 8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8. \quad & \frac{11}{264} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{11}{2640} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{11}{26400} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{11}{264000} := \frac{1 + 1}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12. \quad & \frac{12}{10908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 0908} \\
 & \frac{12}{1090908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 090908} \\
 & \frac{12}{109090908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 09090908} \\
 & \frac{12}{10909090908} := \frac{1^2}{1 + 0909090908}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$13. \quad \frac{12}{1188} := \frac{1^2}{11+88}$$

$$\frac{12}{11988} := \frac{1^2}{11+988}$$

$$\frac{12}{119988} := \frac{1^2}{11+9988}$$

$$\frac{12}{1199988} := \frac{1^2}{11+99988}$$

$$18. \quad \frac{12}{24} := \frac{1+2}{2+4}$$

$$\frac{12}{264} := \frac{1+2}{2+64}$$

$$\frac{12}{2664} := \frac{1+2}{2+664}$$

$$\frac{12}{26664} := \frac{1+2}{2+6664}$$

$$23. \quad \frac{13}{1287} := \frac{1^3}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{13}{12987} := \frac{1^3}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{13}{129987} := \frac{1^3}{12+9987}$$

$$\frac{13}{1299987} := \frac{1^3}{12+99987}$$

$$14. \quad \frac{12}{120} := \frac{1 \times 2}{1 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{12}{1200} := \frac{1 \times 2}{1 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{12}{12000} := \frac{1 \times 2}{1 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{12}{120000} := \frac{1 \times 2}{1 \times 20000}$$

$$19. \quad \frac{12}{384} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{12}{3840} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{12}{38400} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{12}{384000} := \frac{1+2}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$24. \quad \frac{13}{130} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{13}{1300} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{13}{13000} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{13}{130000} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times 30000}$$

$$15. \quad \frac{12}{1296} := \frac{1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{12}{12960} := \frac{1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{12}{129600} := \frac{1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{12}{1296000} := \frac{1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$20. \quad \frac{12}{396} := \frac{1+2}{3+96}$$

$$\frac{12}{3996} := \frac{1+2}{3+996}$$

$$\frac{12}{39996} := \frac{1+2}{3+9996}$$

$$25. \quad \frac{13}{143} := \frac{1+3}{1+43}$$

$$\frac{13}{1443} := \frac{1+3}{1+443}$$

$$\frac{13}{14443} := \frac{1+3}{1+4443}$$

$$\frac{13}{144443} := \frac{1+3}{1+44443}$$

$$16. \quad \frac{12}{132} := \frac{1+2}{1+32}$$

$$\frac{12}{1332} := \frac{1+2}{1+332}$$

$$\frac{12}{13332} := \frac{1+2}{1+3332}$$

$$\frac{12}{133332} := \frac{1+2}{1+33332}$$

$$21. \quad \frac{12}{594} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5+94}$$

$$\frac{12}{5994} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5+994}$$

$$\frac{12}{59994} := \frac{1 \times 2}{5+9994}$$

$$17. \quad \frac{12}{216} := \frac{1^2}{(2+1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{12}{2160} := \frac{1^2}{(2+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{12}{21600} := \frac{1^2}{(2+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{12}{216000} := \frac{1^2}{(2+1) \times 6000}$$

$$22. \quad \frac{13}{1248} := \frac{1^3}{1 \times 2 \times 48}$$

$$\frac{13}{12480} := \frac{1^3}{1 \times 2 \times 480}$$

$$\frac{13}{124800} := \frac{1^3}{1 \times 2 \times 4800}$$

$$\frac{13}{1248000} := \frac{1^3}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}$$

$$26. \quad \frac{13}{156} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(1+5) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{13}{1560} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(1+5) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{13}{15600} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(1+5) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{13}{156000} := \frac{1 \times 3}{(1+5) \times 6000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27. \quad & \frac{13}{195} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{13}{1950} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times (9 \times 50)} \\
 & \frac{13}{19500} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times (9 \times 500)} \\
 & \frac{13}{195000} := \frac{1 \times 3}{1 \times (9 \times 5000)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28. \quad & \frac{13}{208} := \frac{1^3}{2 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{13}{2080} := \frac{1^3}{2 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{13}{20800} := \frac{1^3}{2 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{13}{208000} := \frac{1^3}{2 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29. \quad & \frac{13}{286} := \frac{1+3}{2+86} \\
 & \frac{13}{2886} := \frac{1+3}{2+886} \\
 & \frac{13}{28886} := \frac{1+3}{2+8886} \\
 & \frac{13}{288886} := \frac{1+3}{2+88886}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 30. \quad & \frac{13}{325} := \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{13}{3250} := \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{13}{32500} := \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{13}{325000} := \frac{1 \times 3}{3 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31. \quad & \frac{13}{429} := \frac{1^3}{4+29} \\
 & \frac{13}{4329} := \frac{1^3}{4+329} \\
 & \frac{13}{43329} := \frac{1^3}{4+3329} \\
 & \frac{13}{433329} := \frac{1^3}{4+33329}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32. \quad & \frac{13}{832} := \frac{1+3}{8 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{13}{8320} := \frac{1+3}{8 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{13}{83200} := \frac{1+3}{8 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{13}{832000} := \frac{1+3}{8 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33. \quad & \frac{13}{858} := \frac{1^3}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{13}{8658} := \frac{1^3}{8+658} \\
 & \frac{13}{86658} := \frac{1^3}{8+6658} \\
 & \frac{13}{866658} := \frac{1^3}{8+66658}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34. \quad & \frac{13}{936} := \frac{1^3}{(9+3) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{13}{9360} := \frac{1^3}{(9+3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{13}{93600} := \frac{1^3}{(9+3) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{13}{936000} := \frac{1^3}{(9+3) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35. \quad & \frac{14}{1365} := \frac{1 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{14}{13650} := \frac{1 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{14}{136500} := \frac{1 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{14}{1365000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36. \quad & \frac{14}{1386} := \frac{1^4}{13+86} \\
 & \frac{14}{13986} := \frac{1^4}{13+986} \\
 & \frac{14}{139986} := \frac{1^4}{13+9986} \\
 & \frac{14}{1399986} := \frac{1^4}{13+99986}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37. \quad & \frac{14}{140} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{14}{1400} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{14}{14000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{14}{140000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38. \quad & \frac{14}{154} := \frac{1+4}{1+54} \\
 & \frac{14}{1554} := \frac{1+4}{1+554} \\
 & \frac{14}{15554} := \frac{1+4}{1+5554} \\
 & \frac{14}{155554} := \frac{1+4}{1+55554}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39. \quad & \frac{14}{168} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{14}{1680} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{14}{16800} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{14}{168000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{1 \times 6 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40. \quad & \frac{14}{224} := \frac{1^4}{2 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{14}{2240} := \frac{1^4}{2 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{14}{22400} := \frac{1^4}{2 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{14}{224000} := \frac{1^4}{2 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$41. \quad \frac{14}{448} := \frac{1 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{14}{4480} := \frac{1 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{14}{44800} := \frac{1 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{14}{448000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{4 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$46. \quad \frac{15}{150} := \frac{1 \times 5}{1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{15}{1500} := \frac{1 \times 5}{1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{15}{15000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{1 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{15}{150000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{1 \times 50000}$$

$$51. \quad \frac{15}{24} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{15}{240} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{15}{2400} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{15}{24000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2 \times 4000}$$

$$42. \quad \frac{14}{63} := \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{14}{630} := \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{14}{6300} := \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{14}{63000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{6 \times 3000}$$

$$47. \quad \frac{15}{1575} := \frac{1 \times 5}{15 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{15}{15750} := \frac{1 \times 5}{15 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{15}{157500} := \frac{1 \times 5}{15 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{15}{1575000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{15 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$52. \quad \frac{15}{25} := \frac{1+5}{2 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{15}{250} := \frac{1+5}{2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{15}{2500} := \frac{1+5}{2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{15}{25000} := \frac{1+5}{2 \times 5000}$$

$$43. \quad \frac{14}{784} := \frac{1 \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{14}{7840} := \frac{1 \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{14}{78400} := \frac{1 \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{14}{784000} := \frac{1 \times 4}{7 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$48. \quad \frac{15}{165} := \frac{1+5}{1+65}$$

$$\frac{15}{1665} := \frac{1+5}{1+665}$$

$$\frac{15}{16665} := \frac{1+5}{1+6665}$$

$$\frac{15}{166665} := \frac{1+5}{1+66665}$$

$$53. \quad \frac{15}{27} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2+7}$$

$$\frac{15}{297} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2+97}$$

$$\frac{15}{2997} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2+997}$$

$$\frac{15}{29997} := \frac{1 \times 5}{2+9997}$$

$$44. \quad \frac{15}{1470} := \frac{1^5}{14 \times 7 + 0}$$

$$\frac{15}{14700} := \frac{1^5}{14 \times 70 + 0}$$

$$\frac{15}{147000} := \frac{1^5}{14 \times 700 + 0}$$

$$\frac{15}{1470000} := \frac{1^5}{14 \times 7000 + 0}$$

$$49. \quad \frac{15}{168} := \frac{1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{15}{1680} := \frac{1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{15}{16800} := \frac{1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{15}{168000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 8000}$$

$$45. \quad \frac{15}{1485} := \frac{1^5}{14+85}$$

$$\frac{15}{14985} := \frac{1^5}{14+985}$$

$$\frac{15}{149985} := \frac{1^5}{14+9985}$$

$$\frac{15}{1499985} := \frac{1^5}{14+99985}$$

$$50. \quad \frac{15}{1815} := \frac{1^5}{1+8 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{15}{18015} := \frac{1^5}{1+80 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{15}{180015} := \frac{1^5}{1+800 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{15}{1800015} := \frac{1^5}{1+8000 \times 15}$$

$$54. \quad \frac{15}{480} := \frac{1^5}{4 \times (8+0)}$$

$$\frac{15}{4800} := \frac{1^5}{4 \times (80+0)}$$

$$\frac{15}{48000} := \frac{1^5}{4 \times (800+0)}$$

$$\frac{15}{480000} := \frac{1^5}{4 \times (8000+0)}$$

$$55. \quad \frac{15}{525} := \frac{1^5}{5 \times (2+5)}$$

$$\frac{15}{5250} := \frac{1^5}{(5+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{15}{52500} := \frac{1^5}{(5+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{15}{525000} := \frac{1^5}{(5+2) \times 5000}$$

$$59. \quad \frac{16}{14848} := \frac{1^6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{16}{148480} := \frac{1^6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{16}{1484800} := \frac{1^6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{16}{14848000} := \frac{1^6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 8000}$$

$$64. \quad \frac{16}{528} := \frac{1^6}{5+28}$$

$$\frac{16}{5328} := \frac{1^6}{5+328}$$

$$\frac{16}{53328} := \frac{1^6}{5+3328}$$

$$\frac{16}{533328} := \frac{1^6}{5+33328}$$

$$56. \quad \frac{15}{735} := \frac{1 \times 5}{7 \times 35}$$

$$\frac{15}{7350} := \frac{1 \times 5}{7 \times 350}$$

$$\frac{15}{73500} := \frac{1 \times 5}{7 \times 3500}$$

$$\frac{15}{735000} := \frac{1 \times 5}{7 \times 35000}$$

$$60. \quad \frac{16}{1584} := \frac{1^6}{15+84}$$

$$\frac{16}{15984} := \frac{1^6}{15+984}$$

$$\frac{16}{159984} := \frac{1^6}{15+9984}$$

$$\frac{16}{1599984} := \frac{1^6}{15+99984}$$

$$65. \quad \frac{16}{64} := \frac{1 \times 6}{6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{16}{640} := \frac{1 \times 6}{6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{16}{6400} := \frac{1 \times 6}{6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{16}{64000} := \frac{1 \times 6}{6 \times 4000}$$

$$57. \quad \frac{16}{1056} := \frac{1^6}{10+56}$$

$$\frac{16}{10656} := \frac{1^6}{10+656}$$

$$\frac{16}{106656} := \frac{1^6}{10+6656}$$

$$\frac{16}{1066656} := \frac{1^6}{10+66656}$$

$$61. \quad \frac{16}{160} := \frac{1 \times 6}{1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{16}{1600} := \frac{1 \times 6}{1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{16}{16000} := \frac{1 \times 6}{1 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{16}{160000} := \frac{1 \times 6}{1 \times 60000}$$

$$66. \quad \frac{17}{1088} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 08 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{17}{10880} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 08 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{17}{108800} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 08 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{17}{1088000} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 08 \times 8000}$$

$$58. \quad \frac{16}{128} := \frac{1^6}{1^2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{16}{1280} := \frac{1^6}{1^2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{16}{12800} := \frac{1^6}{1^2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{16}{128000} := \frac{1^6}{1^2 \times 8000}$$

$$62. \quad \frac{16}{176} := \frac{1+6}{1+76}$$

$$\frac{16}{1776} := \frac{1+6}{1+776}$$

$$\frac{16}{17776} := \frac{1+6}{1+7776}$$

$$\frac{16}{177776} := \frac{1+6}{1+77776}$$

$$67. \quad \frac{17}{1224} := \frac{1+7}{12^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{17}{12240} := \frac{1+7}{(12^2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{17}{122400} := \frac{1+7}{(12^2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{17}{1224000} := \frac{1+7}{(12^2) \times 4000}$$

$$63. \quad \frac{16}{256} := \frac{1+6}{2 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{16}{2560} := \frac{1+6}{2 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{16}{25600} := \frac{1+6}{2 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{16}{256000} := \frac{1+6}{2 \times 56000}$$

$$68. \quad \frac{17}{1275} := \frac{1^7}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{17}{12750} := \frac{1^7}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{17}{127500} := \frac{1^7}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{17}{1275000} := \frac{1^7}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5000}$$

$$69. \quad \frac{17}{1326} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 3 \times 26}$$

$$\frac{17}{13260} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 3 \times 260}$$

$$\frac{17}{132600} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 3 \times 2600}$$

$$\frac{17}{1326000} := \frac{1^7}{1 \times 3 \times 26000}$$

$$70. \quad \frac{17}{1445} := \frac{1^7}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{17}{14450} := \frac{1^7}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{17}{144500} := \frac{1^7}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{17}{1445000} := \frac{1^7}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5000}$$

$$71. \quad \frac{17}{1683} := \frac{1^7}{16+83}$$

$$\frac{17}{16983} := \frac{1^7}{16+983}$$

$$\frac{17}{169983} := \frac{1^7}{16+9983}$$

$$\frac{17}{1699983} := \frac{1^7}{16+99983}$$

$$72. \quad \frac{17}{170} := \frac{1 \times 7}{1 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{17}{1700} := \frac{1 \times 7}{1 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{17}{17000} := \frac{1 \times 7}{1 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{17}{170000} := \frac{1 \times 7}{1 \times 70000}$$

$$73. \quad \frac{17}{187} := \frac{1+7}{1+87}$$

$$\frac{17}{1887} := \frac{1+7}{1+887}$$

$$\frac{17}{18887} := \frac{1+7}{1+8887}$$

$$\frac{17}{188887} := \frac{1+7}{1+88887}$$

$$74. \quad \frac{17}{306} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{17}{3060} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{17}{30600} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{17}{306000} := \frac{1^7}{3 \times 06000}$$

$$75. \quad \frac{17}{816} := \frac{1^7}{8 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{17}{8160} := \frac{1^7}{8 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{17}{81600} := \frac{1^7}{8 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{17}{816000} := \frac{1^7}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$76. \quad \frac{17}{85} := \frac{1+7}{8 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{17}{850} := \frac{1+7}{8 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{17}{8500} := \frac{1+7}{8 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{17}{85000} := \frac{1+7}{8 \times 5000}$$

$$77. \quad \frac{18}{1152} := \frac{1^8}{(1+1)^5 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{18}{11520} := \frac{1^8}{(1+1)^5 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{18}{115200} := \frac{1^8}{(1+1)^5 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{18}{1152000} := \frac{1^8}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}$$

$$78. \quad \frac{18}{12288} := \frac{1+8}{(1+2) \times 2^8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{18}{122880} := \frac{1+8}{(1+2) \times 2^8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{18}{1228800} := \frac{1+8}{(1+2) \times 2^8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{18}{12288000} := \frac{1+8}{(1+2) \times 2^8 \times 8000}$$

$$79. \quad \frac{18}{1296} := \frac{1+8}{12 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{18}{12960} := \frac{1+8}{12 \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{18}{129600} := \frac{1+8}{12 \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{18}{1296000} := \frac{1+8}{12 \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$80. \quad \frac{18}{1352} := \frac{1+8}{13 \times 52}$$

$$\frac{18}{13520} := \frac{1+8}{13 \times 520}$$

$$\frac{18}{135200} := \frac{1+8}{13 \times 5200}$$

$$81. \quad \frac{18}{1782} := \frac{1^8}{17+82}$$

$$\frac{18}{17982} := \frac{1^8}{17+982}$$

$$\frac{18}{179982} := \frac{1^8}{17+9982}$$

$$\frac{18}{1799982} := \frac{1^8}{17+99982}$$

$$82. \quad \frac{18}{180} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{18}{1800} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{18}{18000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{18}{180000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 80000}$$

$$83. \quad \frac{18}{198} := \frac{1+8}{1+98}$$

$$\frac{18}{1998} := \frac{1+8}{1+998}$$

$$\frac{18}{19998} := \frac{1+8}{1+9998}$$

$$\frac{18}{199998} := \frac{1+8}{1+99998}$$

$$88. \quad \frac{18}{378} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{18}{3780} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{18}{37800} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{18}{378000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 8000}$$

$$93. \quad \frac{19}{1197} := \frac{1^9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{19}{11970} := \frac{1^9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{19}{119700} := \frac{1^9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{19}{1197000} := \frac{1^9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}$$

$$84. \quad \frac{18}{216} := \frac{1^8}{2 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{18}{2160} := \frac{1^8}{2 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{18}{21600} := \frac{1^8}{2 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{18}{216000} := \frac{1^8}{2 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$89. \quad \frac{18}{432} := \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{18}{4320} := \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{18}{43200} := \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{18}{432000} := \frac{1^8}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$94. \quad \frac{19}{1254} := \frac{1^9}{12+54}$$

$$\frac{19}{12654} := \frac{1^9}{12+654}$$

$$\frac{19}{126654} := \frac{1^9}{12+6654}$$

$$\frac{19}{1266654} := \frac{1^9}{12+66654}$$

$$85. \quad \frac{18}{252} := \frac{1^8}{(2+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{18}{2520} := \frac{1^8}{(2+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{18}{25200} := \frac{1^8}{(2+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{18}{252000} := \frac{1^8}{(2+5) \times 2000}$$

$$90. \quad \frac{18}{45} := \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{18}{450} := \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{18}{4500} := \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{18}{45000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{4 \times 5000}$$

$$95. \quad \frac{19}{1368} := \frac{1^9}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{19}{13680} := \frac{1^9}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{19}{136800} := \frac{1^9}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{19}{1368000} := \frac{1^9}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8000}$$

$$86. \quad \frac{18}{288} := \frac{1 \times 8}{2 \times 8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{18}{2880} := \frac{1 \times 8}{2 \times 8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{18}{28800} := \frac{1 \times 8}{2 \times 8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{18}{288000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{2 \times 8 \times 8000}$$

$$91. \quad \frac{18}{648} := \frac{1 \times 8}{6 \times 48}$$

$$\frac{18}{6480} := \frac{1 \times 8}{6 \times 480}$$

$$\frac{18}{64800} := \frac{1 \times 8}{6 \times 4800}$$

$$\frac{18}{648000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{6 \times 48000}$$

$$87. \quad \frac{18}{36} := \frac{1+8}{3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{18}{360} := \frac{1+8}{3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{18}{3600} := \frac{1+8}{3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{18}{36000} := \frac{1+8}{3 \times 6000}$$

$$92. \quad \frac{19}{1045} := \frac{1^9}{10+45}$$

$$\frac{19}{10545} := \frac{1^9}{10+545}$$

$$\frac{19}{105545} := \frac{1^9}{10+5545}$$

$$\frac{19}{1055545} := \frac{1^9}{10+55545}$$

$$96. \quad \frac{19}{1463} := \frac{1^9}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{19}{14763} := \frac{1^9}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{19}{147763} := \frac{1^9}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{19}{1477763} := \frac{1^9}{14+77763}$$

$$97. \quad \frac{19}{1672} := \frac{1^9}{16+72}$$

$$\frac{19}{16872} := \frac{1^9}{16+872}$$

$$\frac{19}{168872} := \frac{1^9}{16+8872}$$

$$\frac{19}{1688872} := \frac{1^9}{16+88872}$$

$$101. \quad \frac{19}{627} := \frac{1^9}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{19}{6327} := \frac{1^9}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{19}{63327} := \frac{1^9}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{19}{633327} := \frac{1^9}{6+33327}$$

$$106. \quad \frac{21}{1365} := \frac{2+1}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{21}{13650} := \frac{2+1}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{21}{136500} := \frac{2+1}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$98. \quad \frac{19}{1881} := \frac{1^9}{18+81}$$

$$\frac{19}{18981} := \frac{1^9}{18+981}$$

$$\frac{19}{189981} := \frac{1^9}{18+9981}$$

$$\frac{19}{1899981} := \frac{1^9}{18+99981}$$

$$102. \quad \frac{19}{836} := \frac{1^9}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{19}{8436} := \frac{1^9}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{19}{84436} := \frac{1^9}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{19}{844436} := \frac{1^9}{8+44436}$$

$$107. \quad \frac{21}{210} := \frac{2 \times 1}{2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{21}{2100} := \frac{2 \times 1}{2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{21}{21000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{2 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{21}{210000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{2 \times 10000}$$

$$99. \quad \frac{19}{190} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{19}{1900} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{19}{19000} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{19}{190000} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 90000}$$

$$103. \quad \frac{19}{95} := \frac{1 \times 9}{9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{19}{950} := \frac{1 \times 9}{9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{19}{9500} := \frac{1 \times 9}{9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{19}{95000} := \frac{1 \times 9}{9 \times 5000}$$

$$108. \quad \frac{21}{231} := \frac{2+1}{2+31}$$

$$\frac{21}{2331} := \frac{2+1}{2+331}$$

$$\frac{21}{23331} := \frac{2+1}{2+3331}$$

$$\frac{21}{233331} := \frac{2+1}{2+33331}$$

$$100. \quad \frac{19}{2109} := \frac{1^9}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{19}{21109} := \frac{1^9}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{19}{211109} := \frac{1^9}{2+11109}$$

$$\frac{19}{2111109} := \frac{1^9}{2+111109}$$

$$104. \quad \frac{21}{1155} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 55}$$

$$\frac{21}{11550} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 550}$$

$$\frac{21}{115500} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 5500}$$

$$\frac{21}{1155000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 55000}$$

$$109. \quad \frac{21}{315} := \frac{2+1}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{21}{3150} := \frac{2+1}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{21}{31500} := \frac{2+1}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{21}{315000} := \frac{2+1}{3 \times 15000}$$

$$105. \quad \frac{21}{126} := \frac{2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{21}{1260} := \frac{2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{21}{12600} := \frac{2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{21}{126000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$110. \quad \frac{21}{385} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{21}{3850} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{21}{38500} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{21}{385000} := \frac{2+1}{(3+8) \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 111. \quad & \frac{21}{448} := \frac{2+1}{(4+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{21}{4480} := \frac{2+1}{(4+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{21}{44800} := \frac{2+1}{(4+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{21}{448000} := \frac{2+1}{(4+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 116. \quad & \frac{21}{756} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{21}{7560} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{21}{75600} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{21}{756000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{(7+5) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 120. \quad & \frac{22}{242} := \frac{2^2}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{22}{2442} := \frac{2^2}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{22}{24442} := \frac{2^2}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{22}{244442} := \frac{2^2}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 112. \quad & \frac{21}{462} := \frac{2+1}{4+62} \\
 & \frac{21}{4662} := \frac{2+1}{4+662} \\
 & \frac{21}{46662} := \frac{2+1}{4+6662} \\
 & \frac{21}{466662} := \frac{2+1}{4+66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 117. \quad & \frac{22}{121} := \frac{2^2}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{22}{1221} := \frac{2^2}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{22}{12221} := \frac{2^2}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{22}{122221} := \frac{2^2}{1+22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 121. \quad & \frac{22}{264} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{22}{2640} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{22}{26400} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{22}{264000} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 113. \quad & \frac{21}{525} := \frac{2 \times 1}{5 \times 2 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{21}{5250} := \frac{2 \times 1}{5 \times 2 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{21}{52500} := \frac{2 \times 1}{5 \times 2 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{21}{525000} := \frac{2 \times 1}{5 \times 2 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 118. \quad & \frac{22}{165} := \frac{2^2}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{22}{1650} := \frac{2^2}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{22}{16500} := \frac{2^2}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{22}{165000} := \frac{2^2}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 122. \quad & \frac{22}{363} := \frac{2^2}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{22}{3663} := \frac{2^2}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{22}{36663} := \frac{2^2}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{22}{366663} := \frac{2^2}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 114. \quad & \frac{21}{63} := \frac{2+1}{6+3} \\
 & \frac{21}{693} := \frac{2+1}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{21}{6993} := \frac{2+1}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{21}{69993} := \frac{2+1}{6+9993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 119. \quad & \frac{22}{220} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{22}{2200} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{22}{22000} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{22}{220000} := \frac{2^2}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 123. \quad & \frac{22}{44} := \frac{2^2}{4+4} \\
 & \frac{22}{484} := \frac{2^2}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{22}{4884} := \frac{2^2}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{22}{48884} := \frac{2^2}{4+8884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 115. \quad & \frac{21}{735} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{21}{7350} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{21}{73500} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{21}{735000} := \frac{2+1}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$124. \quad \frac{23}{1449} := \frac{2^3}{14 \times 4 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{23}{14490} := \frac{2^3}{14 \times 4 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{23}{144900} := \frac{2^3}{14 \times 4 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{23}{1449000} := \frac{2^3}{14 \times 4 \times 9000}$$

$$129. \quad \frac{24}{150} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{24}{1500} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{24}{15000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{24}{150000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{1 \times 50000}$$

$$134. \quad \frac{24}{384} := \frac{2+4}{3 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{24}{3840} := \frac{2+4}{3 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{24}{38400} := \frac{2+4}{3 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{24}{384000} := \frac{2+4}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$125. \quad \frac{23}{230} := \frac{2 \times 3}{2 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{23}{2300} := \frac{2 \times 3}{2 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{23}{23000} := \frac{2 \times 3}{2 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{23}{230000} := \frac{2 \times 3}{2 \times 30000}$$

$$130. \quad \frac{24}{168} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{24}{1680} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{24}{16800} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{24}{168000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{(1+6) \times 8000}$$

$$135. \quad \frac{24}{36} := \frac{2+4}{3+6}$$

$$\frac{24}{396} := \frac{2+4}{3+96}$$

$$\frac{24}{3996} := \frac{2+4}{3+996}$$

$$\frac{24}{39996} := \frac{2+4}{3+9996}$$

$$126. \quad \frac{23}{253} := \frac{2+3}{2+53}$$

$$\frac{23}{2553} := \frac{2+3}{2+553}$$

$$\frac{23}{25553} := \frac{2+3}{2+5553}$$

$$\frac{23}{255553} := \frac{2+3}{2+55553}$$

$$131. \quad \frac{24}{240} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{24}{2400} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{24}{24000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{24}{240000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2 \times 40000}$$

$$136. \quad \frac{24}{48} := \frac{2^4}{4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{24}{480} := \frac{2^4}{4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{24}{4800} := \frac{2^4}{4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{24}{48000} := \frac{2^4}{4 \times 8000}$$

$$127. \quad \frac{24}{132} := \frac{2+4}{1+32}$$

$$\frac{24}{1332} := \frac{2+4}{1+332}$$

$$\frac{24}{13332} := \frac{2+4}{1+3332}$$

$$\frac{24}{133332} := \frac{2+4}{1+33332}$$

$$132. \quad \frac{24}{264} := \frac{2+4}{2+64}$$

$$\frac{24}{2664} := \frac{2+4}{2+664}$$

$$\frac{24}{26664} := \frac{2+4}{2+6664}$$

$$\frac{24}{266664} := \frac{2+4}{2+66664}$$

$$137. \quad \frac{24}{675} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{24}{6750} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{24}{67500} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{24}{675000} := \frac{2^4}{6 \times 75000}$$

$$128. \quad \frac{24}{147} := \frac{2^4}{14 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{24}{1470} := \frac{2^4}{14 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{24}{14700} := \frac{2^4}{14 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{24}{147000} := \frac{2^4}{14 \times 7000}$$

$$133. \quad \frac{24}{27} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2+7}$$

$$\frac{24}{297} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2+97}$$

$$\frac{24}{2997} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2+997}$$

$$\frac{24}{29997} := \frac{2 \times 4}{2+9997}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 138. \quad & \frac{24}{735} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 35} \\
 & \frac{24}{7350} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 350} \\
 & \frac{24}{73500} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{24}{735000} := \frac{2 \times 4}{7 \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 143. \quad & \frac{25}{375} := \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{25}{3750} := \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{25}{37500} := \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{25}{375000} := \frac{2+5}{3 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 148. \quad & \frac{27}{150} := \frac{2+7}{1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{27}{1500} := \frac{2+7}{1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{27}{15000} := \frac{2+7}{1 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{27}{150000} := \frac{2+7}{1 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 139. \quad & \frac{24}{972} := \frac{2^4}{9 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{24}{9720} := \frac{2^4}{9 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{24}{97200} := \frac{2^4}{9 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{24}{972000} := \frac{2^4}{9 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 144. \quad & \frac{26}{143} := \frac{2+6}{1+43} \\
 & \frac{26}{1443} := \frac{2+6}{1+443} \\
 & \frac{26}{14443} := \frac{2+6}{1+4443} \\
 & \frac{26}{144443} := \frac{2+6}{1+44443}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 149. \quad & \frac{27}{168} := \frac{2+7}{(1+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{27}{1680} := \frac{2+7}{(1+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{27}{16800} := \frac{2+7}{(1+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{27}{168000} := \frac{2+7}{(1+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 140. \quad & \frac{25}{165} := \frac{2 \times 5}{1+65} \\
 & \frac{25}{1665} := \frac{2 \times 5}{1+665} \\
 & \frac{25}{16665} := \frac{2 \times 5}{1+6665} \\
 & \frac{25}{166665} := \frac{2 \times 5}{1+66665}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 145. \quad & \frac{26}{260} := \frac{2 \times 6}{2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{26}{2600} := \frac{2 \times 6}{2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{26}{26000} := \frac{2 \times 6}{2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{26}{260000} := \frac{2 \times 6}{2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 150. \quad & \frac{27}{240} := \frac{2+7}{2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{27}{2400} := \frac{2+7}{2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{27}{24000} := \frac{2+7}{2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{27}{240000} := \frac{2+7}{2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 141. \quad & \frac{25}{250} := \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{25}{2500} := \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{25}{25000} := \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{25}{250000} := \frac{2 \times 5}{2 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 146. \quad & \frac{26}{286} := \frac{2+6}{2+86} \\
 & \frac{26}{2886} := \frac{2+6}{2+886} \\
 & \frac{26}{28886} := \frac{2+6}{2+8886} \\
 & \frac{26}{288886} := \frac{2+6}{2+88886}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 151. \quad & \frac{27}{270} := \frac{2 \times 7}{2 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{27}{2700} := \frac{2 \times 7}{2 \times 700}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 142. \quad & \frac{25}{275} := \frac{2+5}{2+75} \\
 & \frac{25}{2775} := \frac{2+5}{2+775} \\
 & \frac{25}{27775} := \frac{2+5}{2+7775} \\
 & \frac{25}{277775} := \frac{2+5}{2+77775}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 147. \quad & \frac{26}{65} := \frac{2 \times 6}{6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{26}{650} := \frac{2 \times 6}{6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{26}{6500} := \frac{2 \times 6}{6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{26}{65000} := \frac{2 \times 6}{6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 152. \quad & \frac{27}{297} := \frac{2+7}{2+97} \\
 & \frac{27}{2997} := \frac{2+7}{2+997} \\
 & \frac{27}{29997} := \frac{2+7}{2+9997} \\
 & \frac{27}{299997} := \frac{2+7}{2+99997}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$153. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{27}{735} &:= \frac{2+7}{7 \times 35} \\ \frac{27}{7350} &:= \frac{2+7}{7 \times 350} \\ \frac{27}{73500} &:= \frac{2+7}{7 \times 3500} \\ \frac{27}{735000} &:= \frac{2+7}{7 \times 35000} \end{aligned}$$

$$158. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{29}{290} &:= \frac{2 \times 9}{2 \times 90} \\ \frac{29}{2900} &:= \frac{2 \times 9}{2 \times 900} \\ \frac{29}{29000} &:= \frac{2 \times 9}{2 \times 9000} \\ \frac{29}{290000} &:= \frac{2 \times 9}{2 \times 90000} \end{aligned}$$

$$163. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{341} &:= \frac{3+1}{3+41} \\ \frac{31}{3441} &:= \frac{3+1}{3+441} \\ \frac{31}{34441} &:= \frac{3+1}{3+4441} \\ \frac{31}{344441} &:= \frac{3+1}{3+44441} \end{aligned}$$

$$154. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{27}{756} &:= \frac{2 \times 7}{7 \times 56} \\ \frac{27}{7560} &:= \frac{2 \times 7}{7 \times 560} \\ \frac{27}{75600} &:= \frac{2 \times 7}{7 \times 5600} \\ \frac{27}{756000} &:= \frac{2 \times 7}{7 \times 56000} \end{aligned}$$

$$159. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{124} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 4} \\ \frac{31}{1240} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 40} \\ \frac{31}{12400} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 400} \\ \frac{31}{124000} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$164. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{62} &:= \frac{3+1}{6+2} \\ \frac{31}{682} &:= \frac{3+1}{6+82} \\ \frac{31}{6882} &:= \frac{3+1}{6+882} \\ \frac{31}{68882} &:= \frac{3+1}{6+8882} \end{aligned}$$

$$155. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{28}{126} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{12 \times 6} \\ \frac{28}{1260} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{12 \times 60} \\ \frac{28}{12600} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{12 \times 600} \\ \frac{28}{126000} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{12 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

$$160. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{1395} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \frac{31}{13950} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 50} \\ \frac{31}{139500} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 500} \\ \frac{31}{1395000} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

$$165. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{868} &:= \frac{3+1}{(8+6) \times 8} \\ \frac{31}{8680} &:= \frac{3+1}{(8+6) \times 80} \end{aligned}$$

$$156. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{28}{154} &:= \frac{2+8}{1+54} \\ \frac{28}{1554} &:= \frac{2+8}{1+554} \\ \frac{28}{15554} &:= \frac{2+8}{1+5554} \\ \frac{28}{155554} &:= \frac{2+8}{1+55554} \end{aligned}$$

$$161. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{217} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(2+1) \times 7} \\ \frac{31}{2170} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(2+1) \times 70} \\ \frac{31}{21700} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(2+1) \times 700} \\ \frac{31}{217000} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{(2+1) \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

$$166. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{32}{128} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 8} \\ \frac{32}{1280} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 80} \\ \frac{32}{12800} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 800} \\ \frac{32}{128000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$157. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{28}{280} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{2 \times 80} \\ \frac{28}{2800} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{2 \times 800} \\ \frac{28}{28000} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{2 \times 8000} \\ \frac{28}{280000} &:= \frac{2 \times 8}{2 \times 80000} \end{aligned}$$

$$162. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{31}{310} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{3 \times 10} \\ \frac{31}{3100} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{3 \times 100} \\ \frac{31}{31000} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{3 \times 1000} \\ \frac{31}{310000} &:= \frac{3 \times 1}{3 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

$$167. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{32}{320} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{3 \times 20} \\ \frac{32}{3200} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{3 \times 200} \\ \frac{32}{32000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{3 \times 2000} \\ \frac{32}{320000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2}{3 \times 20000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 183. \quad & \frac{34}{374} := \frac{3+4}{3+74} \\
 & \frac{34}{3774} := \frac{3+4}{3+774} \\
 & \frac{34}{37774} := \frac{3+4}{3+7774} \\
 & \frac{34}{377774} := \frac{3+4}{3+77774}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 188. \quad & \frac{35}{385} := \frac{3+5}{3+85} \\
 & \frac{35}{3885} := \frac{3+5}{3+885} \\
 & \frac{35}{38885} := \frac{3+5}{3+8885} \\
 & \frac{35}{388885} := \frac{3+5}{3+88885}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 193. \quad & \frac{36}{198} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1+98} \\
 & \frac{36}{1998} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1+998} \\
 & \frac{36}{19998} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1+9998} \\
 & \frac{36}{199998} := \frac{3 \times 6}{1+99998}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 184. \quad & \frac{34}{476} := \frac{3 \times 4}{4 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{34}{4760} := \frac{3 \times 4}{4 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{34}{47600} := \frac{3 \times 4}{4 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{34}{476000} := \frac{3 \times 4}{4 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 189. \quad & \frac{35}{448} := \frac{3 \times 5}{4 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{35}{4480} := \frac{3 \times 5}{4 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{35}{44800} := \frac{3 \times 5}{4 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{35}{448000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{4 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 194. \quad & \frac{36}{264} := \frac{3+6}{2+64} \\
 & \frac{36}{2664} := \frac{3+6}{2+664} \\
 & \frac{36}{26664} := \frac{3+6}{2+6664} \\
 & \frac{36}{266664} := \frac{3+6}{2+66664}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 185. \quad & \frac{35}{175} := \frac{3 \times 5}{1 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{35}{1750} := \frac{3 \times 5}{1 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{35}{17500} := \frac{3 \times 5}{1 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{35}{175000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{1 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 190. \quad & \frac{35}{945} := \frac{3 \times 5}{9 \times 45} \\
 & \frac{35}{9450} := \frac{3 \times 5}{9 \times 450} \\
 & \frac{35}{94500} := \frac{3 \times 5}{9 \times 4500} \\
 & \frac{35}{945000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{9 \times 45000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 195. \quad & \frac{36}{360} := \frac{3 \times 6}{3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{36}{3600} := \frac{3 \times 6}{3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{36}{36000} := \frac{3 \times 6}{3 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{36}{360000} := \frac{3 \times 6}{3 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 186. \quad & \frac{35}{189} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{35}{1890} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{35}{18900} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{35}{189000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{(1+8) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 191. \quad & \frac{36}{132} := \frac{3+6}{1+32} \\
 & \frac{36}{1332} := \frac{3+6}{1+332} \\
 & \frac{36}{13332} := \frac{3+6}{1+3332} \\
 & \frac{36}{133332} := \frac{3+6}{1+33332}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 196. \quad & \frac{36}{384} := \frac{3+6}{3 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{36}{3840} := \frac{3+6}{3 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{36}{38400} := \frac{3+6}{3 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{36}{384000} := \frac{3+6}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 187. \quad & \frac{35}{350} := \frac{3 \times 5}{3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{35}{3500} := \frac{3 \times 5}{3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{35}{35000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{35}{350000} := \frac{3 \times 5}{3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 192. \quad & \frac{36}{1352} := \frac{3 \times 6}{13 \times 52} \\
 & \frac{36}{13520} := \frac{3 \times 6}{13 \times 520} \\
 & \frac{36}{135200} := \frac{3 \times 6}{13 \times 5200} \\
 & \frac{36}{1352000} := \frac{3 \times 6}{13 \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 197. \quad & \frac{36}{396} := \frac{3+6}{3+96} \\
 & \frac{36}{3996} := \frac{3+6}{3+996} \\
 & \frac{36}{39996} := \frac{3+6}{3+9996} \\
 & \frac{36}{399996} := \frac{3+6}{3+99996}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 198. \quad & \frac{37}{148} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{37}{1480} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{37}{14800} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{37}{148000} := \frac{3+7}{(1+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 203. \quad & \frac{39}{1248} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{39}{12480} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{39}{124800} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{39}{1248000} := \frac{3+9}{12 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 208. \quad & \frac{39}{637} := \frac{3 \times 9}{63 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{39}{6370} := \frac{3 \times 9}{63 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{39}{63700} := \frac{3 \times 9}{63 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{39}{637000} := \frac{3 \times 9}{63 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 199. \quad & \frac{37}{370} := \frac{3 \times 7}{3 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{37}{3700} := \frac{3 \times 7}{3 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{37}{37000} := \frac{3 \times 7}{3 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{37}{370000} := \frac{3 \times 7}{3 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 204. \quad & \frac{39}{143} := \frac{3+9}{1+43} \\
 & \frac{39}{1443} := \frac{3+9}{1+443} \\
 & \frac{39}{14443} := \frac{3+9}{1+4443} \\
 & \frac{39}{144443} := \frac{3+9}{1+44443}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 209. \quad & \frac{39}{832} := \frac{3+9}{8 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{39}{8320} := \frac{3+9}{8 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{39}{83200} := \frac{3+9}{8 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{39}{832000} := \frac{3+9}{8 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 200. \quad & \frac{38}{380} := \frac{3 \times 8}{3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{38}{3800} := \frac{3 \times 8}{3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{38}{38000} := \frac{3 \times 8}{3 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{38}{380000} := \frac{3 \times 8}{3 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 205. \quad & \frac{39}{286} := \frac{3+9}{2+86} \\
 & \frac{39}{2886} := \frac{3+9}{2+886} \\
 & \frac{39}{28886} := \frac{3+9}{2+8886} \\
 & \frac{39}{288886} := \frac{3+9}{2+88886}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 210. \quad & \frac{39}{975} := \frac{3 \times 9}{9 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{39}{9750} := \frac{3 \times 9}{9 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{39}{97500} := \frac{3 \times 9}{9 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{39}{975000} := \frac{3 \times 9}{9 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 201. \quad & \frac{38}{475} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{38}{4750} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{38}{47500} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{38}{475000} := \frac{3 \times 8}{4 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 206. \quad & \frac{39}{351} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3^5 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{39}{3510} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3^5 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{39}{35100} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3^5 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{39}{351000} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3^5 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 211. \quad & \frac{41}{1025} := \frac{4 \times 1}{10 \times 2 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{41}{10250} := \frac{4 \times 1}{10 \times 2 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{41}{102500} := \frac{4 \times 1}{10 \times 2 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{41}{1025000} := \frac{4 \times 1}{10 \times 2 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 202. \quad & \frac{38}{798} := \frac{3 \times 8}{7 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{38}{7980} := \frac{3 \times 8}{7 \times 9 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{38}{79800} := \frac{3 \times 8}{7 \times 9 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{38}{798000} := \frac{3 \times 8}{7 \times 9 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 207. \quad & \frac{39}{390} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{39}{3900} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{39}{39000} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{39}{390000} := \frac{3 \times 9}{3 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 212. \quad & \frac{41}{1148} := \frac{4 \times 1}{1 \times 14 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{41}{11480} := \frac{4 \times 1}{1 \times 14 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{41}{114800} := \frac{4 \times 1}{1 \times 14 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{41}{1148000} := \frac{4 \times 1}{1 \times 14 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$213. \quad \frac{41}{1435} := \frac{4+1}{(1+4) \times 35}$$

$$\frac{41}{14350} := \frac{4+1}{(1+4) \times 350}$$

$$\frac{41}{143500} := \frac{4+1}{(1+4) \times 3500}$$

$$\frac{41}{1435000} := \frac{4+1}{(1+4) \times 35000}$$

$$218. \quad \frac{42}{1365} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 65}$$

$$\frac{42}{13650} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 650}$$

$$\frac{42}{136500} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{42}{1365000} := \frac{4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 65000}$$

$$223. \quad \frac{42}{231} := \frac{4+2}{2+31}$$

$$\frac{42}{2331} := \frac{4+2}{2+331}$$

$$\frac{42}{23331} := \frac{4+2}{2+3331}$$

$$\frac{42}{233331} := \frac{4+2}{2+33331}$$

$$214. \quad \frac{41}{328} := \frac{4+1}{(3+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{41}{3280} := \frac{4+1}{(3+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{41}{32800} := \frac{4+1}{(3+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{41}{328000} := \frac{4+1}{(3+2) \times 8000}$$

$$219. \quad \frac{42}{147} := \frac{4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{42}{1470} := \frac{4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{42}{14700} := \frac{4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{42}{147000} := \frac{4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 7000}$$

$$224. \quad \frac{42}{315} := \frac{4+2}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{42}{3150} := \frac{4+2}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{42}{31500} := \frac{4+2}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$215. \quad \frac{41}{410} := \frac{4 \times 1}{4 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{41}{4100} := \frac{4 \times 1}{4 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{41}{41000} := \frac{4 \times 1}{4 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{41}{410000} := \frac{4 \times 1}{4 \times 10000}$$

$$220. \quad \frac{42}{1848} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{42}{18480} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{42}{184800} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{42}{1848000} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 8000}$$

$$225. \quad \frac{42}{385} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{42}{3850} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{42}{38500} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{42}{385000} := \frac{4+2}{(3+8) \times 5000}$$

$$216. \quad \frac{41}{451} := \frac{4+1}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{41}{4551} := \frac{4+1}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{41}{45551} := \frac{4+1}{4+5551}$$

$$\frac{41}{455551} := \frac{4+1}{4+55551}$$

$$221. \quad \frac{42}{18844} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 84) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{42}{188440} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 84) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{42}{1884400} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 84) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{42}{18844000} := \frac{4+2}{(1+8 \times 84) \times 4000}$$

$$217. \quad \frac{42}{126} := \frac{4+2}{(1+2) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{42}{1260} := \frac{4+2}{(1+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{42}{12600} := \frac{4+2}{(1+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{42}{126000} := \frac{4+2}{(1+2) \times 6000}$$

$$222. \quad \frac{42}{189} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{42}{1890} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{42}{18900} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{42}{189000} := \frac{4^2}{1 \times 8 \times 9000}$$

$$226. \quad \frac{42}{420} := \frac{4 \times 2}{4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{42}{4200} := \frac{4 \times 2}{4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{42}{42000} := \frac{4 \times 2}{4 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{42}{420000} := \frac{4 \times 2}{4 \times 20000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 227. \quad & \frac{42}{448} := \frac{4+2}{(4+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{42}{4480} := \frac{4+2}{(4+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{42}{44800} := \frac{4+2}{(4+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{42}{448000} := \frac{4+2}{(4+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 232. \quad & \frac{42}{945} := \frac{4 \times 2}{9 \times 4 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{42}{9450} := \frac{4 \times 2}{9 \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{42}{94500} := \frac{4 \times 2}{9 \times 4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{42}{945000} := \frac{4 \times 2}{9 \times 4 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 237. \quad & \frac{44}{165} := \frac{4+4}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{44}{1650} := \frac{4+4}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{44}{16500} := \frac{4+4}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{44}{165000} := \frac{4+4}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 228. \quad & \frac{42}{462} := \frac{4+2}{4+62} \\
 & \frac{42}{4662} := \frac{4+2}{4+662} \\
 & \frac{42}{46662} := \frac{4+2}{4+6662} \\
 & \frac{42}{466662} := \frac{4+2}{4+66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 233. \quad & \frac{43}{430} := \frac{4 \times 3}{4 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{43}{4300} := \frac{4 \times 3}{4 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{43}{43000} := \frac{4 \times 3}{4 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{43}{430000} := \frac{4 \times 3}{4 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 238. \quad & \frac{44}{198} := \frac{4 \times 4}{1 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{44}{1980} := \frac{4 \times 4}{1 \times 9 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{44}{19800} := \frac{4 \times 4}{1 \times 9 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{44}{198000} := \frac{4 \times 4}{1 \times 9 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 229. \quad & \frac{42}{63} := \frac{4+2}{6+3} \\
 & \frac{42}{693} := \frac{4+2}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{42}{6993} := \frac{4+2}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{42}{69993} := \frac{4+2}{6+9993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 234. \quad & \frac{43}{473} := \frac{4+3}{4+73} \\
 & \frac{43}{4773} := \frac{4+3}{4+773} \\
 & \frac{43}{47773} := \frac{4+3}{4+7773} \\
 & \frac{43}{477773} := \frac{4+3}{4+77773}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 239. \quad & \frac{44}{220} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{44}{2200} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{44}{22000} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{44}{220000} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 230. \quad & \frac{42}{735} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{42}{7350} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{42}{73500} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{42}{735000} := \frac{4+2}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 235. \quad & \frac{43}{688} := \frac{4+3}{(6+8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{43}{6880} := \frac{4+3}{(6+8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{43}{68800} := \frac{4+3}{(6+8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{43}{688000} := \frac{4+3}{(6+8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 240. \quad & \frac{44}{242} := \frac{4+4}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{44}{2442} := \frac{4+4}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{44}{24442} := \frac{4+4}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{44}{244442} := \frac{4+4}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 231. \quad & \frac{42}{84} := \frac{4^2}{8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{42}{840} := \frac{4^2}{8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{42}{8400} := \frac{4^2}{8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{42}{84000} := \frac{4^2}{8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 236. \quad & \frac{44}{121} := \frac{4+4}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{44}{1221} := \frac{4+4}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{44}{12221} := \frac{4+4}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{44}{122221} := \frac{4+4}{1+22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 241. \quad & \frac{44}{264} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{44}{2640} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{44}{26400} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{44}{264000} := \frac{4+4}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 242. \quad & \frac{44}{363} := \frac{4+4}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{44}{3663} := \frac{4+4}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{44}{36663} := \frac{4+4}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{44}{366663} := \frac{4+4}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 247. \quad & \frac{45}{125} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{45}{1250} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{45}{12500} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{45}{125000} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 252. \quad & \frac{45}{378} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{45}{3780} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{45}{37800} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{45}{378000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{3 \times 7 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 243. \quad & \frac{44}{396} := \frac{4+4}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{44}{3960} := \frac{4+4}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{44}{39600} := \frac{4+4}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{44}{396000} := \frac{4+4}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 248. \quad & \frac{45}{16675} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 667 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{45}{166750} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 667 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{45}{1667500} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 667 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{45}{16675000} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 667 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 253. \quad & \frac{45}{450} := \frac{4 \times 5}{4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{45}{4500} := \frac{4 \times 5}{4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{45}{45000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{4 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{45}{450000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{4 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 244. \quad & \frac{44}{440} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{44}{4400} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{44}{44000} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{44}{440000} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 249. \quad & \frac{45}{175} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{45}{1750} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{45}{17500} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{45}{175000} := \frac{4+5}{1 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 254. \quad & \frac{45}{495} := \frac{4+5}{4+95} \\
 & \frac{45}{4995} := \frac{4+5}{4+995} \\
 & \frac{45}{49995} := \frac{4+5}{4+9995} \\
 & \frac{45}{499995} := \frac{4+5}{4+99995}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 245. \quad & \frac{44}{484} := \frac{4+4}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{44}{4884} := \frac{4+4}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{44}{48884} := \frac{4+4}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{44}{488884} := \frac{4+4}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 250. \quad & \frac{45}{180} := \frac{4 \times 5}{1 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{45}{1800} := \frac{4 \times 5}{1 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{45}{18000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{1 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{45}{180000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{1 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 255. \quad & \frac{45}{648} := \frac{4 \times 5}{6 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{45}{6480} := \frac{4 \times 5}{6 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{45}{64800} := \frac{4 \times 5}{6 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{45}{648000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{6 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 246. \quad & \frac{44}{495} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{44}{4950} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{44}{49500} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{44}{495000} := \frac{4 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 251. \quad & \frac{45}{288} := \frac{4 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{45}{2880} := \frac{4 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{45}{28800} := \frac{4 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{45}{288000} := \frac{4 \times 5}{2 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 256. \quad & \frac{46}{253} := \frac{4+6}{2+53} \\
 & \frac{46}{2553} := \frac{4+6}{2+553} \\
 & \frac{46}{25553} := \frac{4+6}{2+5553} \\
 & \frac{46}{255553} := \frac{4+6}{2+55553}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 257. \quad \frac{46}{460} := \frac{4 \times 6}{4 \times 60} \\
 \frac{46}{4600} := \frac{4 \times 6}{4 \times 600} \\
 \frac{46}{46000} := \frac{4 \times 6}{4 \times 6000} \\
 \frac{46}{460000} := \frac{4 \times 6}{4 \times 60000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 262. \quad \frac{48}{264} := \frac{4+8}{2+64} \\
 \frac{48}{2664} := \frac{4+8}{2+664} \\
 \frac{48}{26664} := \frac{4+8}{2+6664} \\
 \frac{48}{266664} := \frac{4+8}{2+66664}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 267. \quad \frac{48}{972} := \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 72} \\
 \frac{48}{9720} := \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 720} \\
 \frac{48}{97200} := \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 7200} \\
 \frac{48}{972000} := \frac{4 \times 8}{9 \times 72000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 258. \quad \frac{47}{470} := \frac{4 \times 7}{4 \times 70} \\
 \frac{47}{4700} := \frac{4 \times 7}{4 \times 700} \\
 \frac{47}{47000} := \frac{4 \times 7}{4 \times 7000} \\
 \frac{47}{470000} := \frac{4 \times 7}{4 \times 70000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 263. \quad \frac{48}{384} := \frac{4+8}{3 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 \frac{48}{3840} := \frac{4+8}{3 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 \frac{48}{38400} := \frac{4+8}{3 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 \frac{48}{384000} := \frac{4+8}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 268. \quad \frac{49}{490} := \frac{4 \times 9}{4 \times 90} \\
 \frac{49}{4900} := \frac{4 \times 9}{4 \times 900} \\
 \frac{49}{49000} := \frac{4 \times 9}{4 \times 9000} \\
 \frac{49}{490000} := \frac{4 \times 9}{4 \times 90000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 259. \quad \frac{47}{846} := \frac{4 \times 7}{84 \times 6} \\
 \frac{47}{8460} := \frac{4 \times 7}{84 \times 60} \\
 \frac{47}{84600} := \frac{4 \times 7}{84 \times 600} \\
 \frac{47}{846000} := \frac{4 \times 7}{84 \times 6000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 264. \quad \frac{48}{396} := \frac{4+8}{3+96} \\
 \frac{48}{3996} := \frac{4+8}{3+996} \\
 \frac{48}{39996} := \frac{4+8}{3+9996} \\
 \frac{48}{399996} := \frac{4+8}{3+99996}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 269. \quad \frac{49}{98} := \frac{4 \times 9}{9 \times 8} \\
 \frac{49}{980} := \frac{4 \times 9}{9 \times 80} \\
 \frac{49}{9800} := \frac{4 \times 9}{9 \times 800} \\
 \frac{49}{98000} := \frac{4 \times 9}{9 \times 8000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 260. \quad \frac{48}{132} := \frac{4+8}{1+32} \\
 \frac{48}{1332} := \frac{4+8}{1+332} \\
 \frac{48}{13332} := \frac{4+8}{1+3332} \\
 \frac{48}{133332} := \frac{4+8}{1+33332}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 265. \quad \frac{48}{480} := \frac{4 \times 8}{4 \times 80} \\
 \frac{48}{4800} := \frac{4 \times 8}{4 \times 800} \\
 \frac{48}{48000} := \frac{4 \times 8}{4 \times 8000} \\
 \frac{48}{480000} := \frac{4 \times 8}{4 \times 80000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 270. \quad \frac{51}{1275} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 \frac{51}{12750} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 \frac{51}{127500} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 \frac{51}{1275000} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 261. \quad \frac{48}{147} := \frac{4 \times 8}{14 \times 7} \\
 \frac{48}{1470} := \frac{4 \times 8}{14 \times 70} \\
 \frac{48}{14700} := \frac{4 \times 8}{14 \times 700} \\
 \frac{48}{147000} := \frac{4 \times 8}{14 \times 7000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 266. \quad \frac{48}{675} := \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 75} \\
 \frac{48}{6750} := \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 750} \\
 \frac{48}{67500} := \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 7500} \\
 \frac{48}{675000} := \frac{4 \times 8}{6 \times 75000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 271. \quad \frac{51}{1326} := \frac{5+1}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 \frac{51}{13260} := \frac{5+1}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 \frac{51}{132600} := \frac{5+1}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 \frac{51}{1326000} := \frac{5+1}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{array}$$

$$272. \quad \frac{51}{1428} := \frac{5 \times 1}{(1+4) \times 28}$$

$$\frac{51}{14280} := \frac{5 \times 1}{(1+4) \times 280}$$

$$\frac{51}{142800} := \frac{5 \times 1}{(1+4) \times 2800}$$

$$\frac{51}{1428000} := \frac{5 \times 1}{(1+4) \times 28000}$$

$$277. \quad \frac{51}{561} := \frac{5+1}{5+61}$$

$$\frac{51}{5661} := \frac{5+1}{5+661}$$

$$\frac{51}{56661} := \frac{5+1}{5+6661}$$

$$\frac{51}{566661} := \frac{5+1}{5+66661}$$

$$282. \quad \frac{52}{156} := \frac{5 \times 2}{1 \times 5 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{52}{1560} := \frac{5 \times 2}{1 \times 5 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{52}{15600} := \frac{5 \times 2}{1 \times 5 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{52}{156000} := \frac{5 \times 2}{1 \times 5 \times 6000}$$

$$273. \quad \frac{51}{153} := \frac{5 \times 1}{1 \times 5 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{51}{1530} := \frac{5 \times 1}{1 \times 5 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{51}{15300} := \frac{5 \times 1}{1 \times 5 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{51}{153000} := \frac{5 \times 1}{1 \times 5 \times 3000}$$

$$278. \quad \frac{51}{595} := \frac{5+1}{(5+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{51}{5950} := \frac{5+1}{(5+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{51}{59500} := \frac{5+1}{(5+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{51}{595000} := \frac{5+1}{(5+9) \times 5000}$$

$$283. \quad \frac{52}{1872} := \frac{5+2}{18 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{52}{18720} := \frac{5+2}{18 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{52}{187200} := \frac{5+2}{18 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{52}{1872000} := \frac{5+2}{18 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$274. \quad \frac{51}{1734} := \frac{5+1}{17 \times 3 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{51}{17340} := \frac{5+1}{17 \times 3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{51}{173400} := \frac{5+1}{17 \times 3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{51}{1734000} := \frac{5+1}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}$$

$$279. \quad \frac{51}{612} := \frac{5+1}{6 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{51}{6120} := \frac{5+1}{6 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{51}{61200} := \frac{5+1}{6 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{51}{612000} := \frac{5+1}{6 \times 12000}$$

$$284. \quad \frac{52}{520} := \frac{5 \times 2}{5 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{52}{5200} := \frac{5 \times 2}{5 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{52}{52000} := \frac{5 \times 2}{5 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{52}{520000} := \frac{5 \times 2}{5 \times 20000}$$

$$275. \quad \frac{51}{17374} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{51}{173740} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{51}{1737400} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{51}{17374000} := \frac{5+1}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}$$

$$280. \quad \frac{51}{748} := \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{51}{7480} := \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{51}{74800} := \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{51}{748000} := \frac{5+1}{(7+4) \times 8000}$$

$$285. \quad \frac{52}{572} := \frac{5+2}{5+72}$$

$$\frac{52}{5772} := \frac{5+2}{5+772}$$

$$\frac{52}{57772} := \frac{5+2}{5+7772}$$

$$\frac{52}{577772} := \frac{5+2}{5+77772}$$

$$276. \quad \frac{51}{510} := \frac{5 \times 1}{5 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{51}{5100} := \frac{5 \times 1}{5 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{51}{51000} := \frac{5 \times 1}{5 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{51}{510000} := \frac{5 \times 1}{5 \times 10000}$$

$$281. \quad \frac{52}{1456} := \frac{5 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 56}$$

$$\frac{52}{14560} := \frac{5 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 560}$$

$$\frac{52}{145600} := \frac{5 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{52}{1456000} := \frac{5 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 56000}$$

$$286. \quad \frac{53}{1484} := \frac{5 \times 3}{(1+4) \times 84}$$

$$\frac{53}{14840} := \frac{5 \times 3}{(1+4) \times 840}$$

$$\frac{53}{148400} := \frac{5 \times 3}{(1+4) \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{53}{1484000} := \frac{5 \times 3}{(1+4) \times 84000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 287. \quad & \frac{53}{159} := \frac{5 \times 3}{1 \times 5 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{53}{1590} := \frac{5 \times 3}{1 \times 5 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{53}{15900} := \frac{5 \times 3}{1 \times 5 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{53}{159000} := \frac{5 \times 3}{1 \times 5 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 292. \quad & \frac{54}{120} := \frac{5+4}{1 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{54}{1200} := \frac{5+4}{1 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{54}{12000} := \frac{5+4}{1 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{54}{120000} := \frac{5+4}{1 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 297. \quad & \frac{55}{165} := \frac{5+5}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{55}{1650} := \frac{5+5}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{55}{16500} := \frac{5+5}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{55}{165000} := \frac{5+5}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 288. \quad & \frac{53}{265} := \frac{5+3}{(2+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{53}{2650} := \frac{5+3}{(2+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{53}{26500} := \frac{5+3}{(2+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{53}{265000} := \frac{5+3}{(2+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 293. \quad & \frac{54}{540} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{54}{5400} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{54}{54000} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{54}{540000} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 298. \quad & \frac{55}{220} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{55}{2200} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{55}{22000} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{55}{220000} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 289. \quad & \frac{53}{424} := \frac{5+3}{(4^2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{53}{4240} := \frac{5+3}{(4^2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{53}{42400} := \frac{5+3}{(4^2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{53}{424000} := \frac{5+3}{(4^2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 294. \quad & \frac{54}{567} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 6 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{54}{5670} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 6 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{54}{56700} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 6 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{54}{567000} := \frac{5 \times 4}{5 \times 6 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 299. \quad & \frac{55}{242} := \frac{5+5}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{55}{2442} := \frac{5+5}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{55}{24442} := \frac{5+5}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{55}{244442} := \frac{5+5}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 290. \quad & \frac{53}{530} := \frac{5 \times 3}{5 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{53}{5300} := \frac{5 \times 3}{5 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{53}{53000} := \frac{5 \times 3}{5 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{53}{530000} := \frac{5 \times 3}{5 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 295. \quad & \frac{54}{594} := \frac{5+4}{5+94} \\
 & \frac{54}{5994} := \frac{5+4}{5+994} \\
 & \frac{54}{59994} := \frac{5+4}{5+9994} \\
 & \frac{54}{599994} := \frac{5+4}{5+99994}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 300. \quad & \frac{55}{264} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{55}{2640} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{55}{26400} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{55}{264000} := \frac{5+5}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 291. \quad & \frac{53}{583} := \frac{5+3}{5+83} \\
 & \frac{53}{5883} := \frac{5+3}{5+883} \\
 & \frac{53}{58883} := \frac{5+3}{5+8883} \\
 & \frac{53}{588883} := \frac{5+3}{5+88883}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 296. \quad & \frac{55}{121} := \frac{5+5}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{55}{1221} := \frac{5+5}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{55}{12221} := \frac{5+5}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{55}{122221} := \frac{5+5}{1+22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 301. \quad & \frac{55}{363} := \frac{5+5}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{55}{3663} := \frac{5+5}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{55}{36663} := \frac{5+5}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{55}{366663} := \frac{5+5}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 302. \quad & \frac{55}{396} := \frac{5+5}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{55}{3960} := \frac{5+5}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{55}{39600} := \frac{5+5}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{55}{396000} := \frac{5+5}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 307. \quad & \frac{57}{1368} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{57}{13680} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{57}{136800} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{57}{1368000} := \frac{5+7}{1 \times 36 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 312. \quad & \frac{61}{610} := \frac{6 \times 1}{6 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{61}{6100} := \frac{6 \times 1}{6 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{61}{61000} := \frac{6 \times 1}{6 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{61}{610000} := \frac{6 \times 1}{6 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 303. \quad & \frac{55}{484} := \frac{5+5}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{55}{4884} := \frac{5+5}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{55}{48884} := \frac{5+5}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{55}{488884} := \frac{5+5}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 308. \quad & \frac{57}{570} := \frac{5 \times 7}{5 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{57}{5700} := \frac{5 \times 7}{5 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{57}{57000} := \frac{5 \times 7}{5 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{57}{570000} := \frac{5 \times 7}{5 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 313. \quad & \frac{61}{671} := \frac{6+1}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{61}{6771} := \frac{6+1}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{61}{67771} := \frac{6+1}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{61}{677771} := \frac{6+1}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 304. \quad & \frac{55}{550} := \frac{5 \times 5}{5 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{55}{5500} := \frac{5 \times 5}{5 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{55}{55000} := \frac{5 \times 5}{5 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{55}{550000} := \frac{5 \times 5}{5 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 309. \quad & \frac{58}{580} := \frac{5 \times 8}{5 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{58}{5800} := \frac{5 \times 8}{5 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{58}{58000} := \frac{5 \times 8}{5 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{58}{580000} := \frac{5 \times 8}{5 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 314. \quad & \frac{61}{976} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(9+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{61}{9760} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(9+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{61}{97600} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(9+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{61}{976000} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(9+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 305. \quad & \frac{56}{112} := \frac{5+6}{11 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{56}{1120} := \frac{5+6}{11 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{56}{11200} := \frac{5+6}{11 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{56}{112000} := \frac{5+6}{11 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 310. \quad & \frac{59}{590} := \frac{5 \times 9}{5 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{59}{5900} := \frac{5 \times 9}{5 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{59}{59000} := \frac{5 \times 9}{5 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{59}{590000} := \frac{5 \times 9}{5 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 315. \quad & \frac{62}{124} := \frac{6 \times 2}{1 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{62}{1240} := \frac{6 \times 2}{1 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{62}{12400} := \frac{6 \times 2}{1 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{62}{124000} := \frac{6 \times 2}{1 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 306. \quad & \frac{56}{560} := \frac{5 \times 6}{5 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{56}{5600} := \frac{5 \times 6}{5 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{56}{56000} := \frac{5 \times 6}{5 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{56}{560000} := \frac{5 \times 6}{5 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 311. \quad & \frac{61}{244} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(2+4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{61}{2440} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(2+4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{61}{24400} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(2+4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{61}{244000} := \frac{6 \times 1}{(2+4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 316. \quad & \frac{62}{1395} := \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{62}{13950} := \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{62}{139500} := \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{62}{1395000} := \frac{6+2}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 317. \quad & \frac{62}{155} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{62}{1550} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{62}{15500} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{62}{155000} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(1+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 322. \quad & \frac{62}{682} := \frac{6+2}{6+82} \\
 & \frac{62}{6882} := \frac{6+2}{6+882} \\
 & \frac{62}{68882} := \frac{6+2}{6+8882} \\
 & \frac{62}{688882} := \frac{6+2}{6+88882}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 327. \quad & \frac{63}{168} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{63}{1680} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{63}{16800} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{63}{168000} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 6 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 318. \quad & \frac{62}{186} := \frac{6^2}{18 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{62}{1860} := \frac{6^2}{18 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{62}{18600} := \frac{6^2}{18 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{62}{186000} := \frac{6^2}{18 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 323. \quad & \frac{62}{868} := \frac{6+2}{(8+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{62}{8680} := \frac{6+2}{(8+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{62}{86800} := \frac{6+2}{(8+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{62}{868000} := \frac{6+2}{(8+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 328. \quad & \frac{63}{231} := \frac{6+3}{2+31} \\
 & \frac{63}{2331} := \frac{6+3}{2+331} \\
 & \frac{63}{23331} := \frac{6+3}{2+3331} \\
 & \frac{63}{233331} := \frac{6+3}{2+33331}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 319. \quad & \frac{62}{248} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(2+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{62}{2480} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(2+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{62}{24800} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(2+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{62}{248000} := \frac{6 \times 2}{(2+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 324. \quad & \frac{63}{126} := \frac{6+3}{12+6} \\
 & \frac{63}{1260} := \frac{6+3}{(1+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{63}{12600} := \frac{6+3}{(1+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{63}{126000} := \frac{6+3}{(1+2) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 329. \quad & \frac{63}{315} := \frac{6+3}{3 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{63}{3150} := \frac{6+3}{3 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{63}{385} := \frac{6+3}{(3+8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{63}{3850} := \frac{6+3}{(3+8) \times 50}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 320. \quad & \frac{62}{341} := \frac{6+2}{3+41} \\
 & \frac{62}{3441} := \frac{6+2}{3+441} \\
 & \frac{62}{34441} := \frac{6+2}{3+4441} \\
 & \frac{62}{344441} := \frac{6+2}{3+44441}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 325. \quad & \frac{63}{1365} := \frac{6+3}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{63}{13650} := \frac{6+3}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{63}{136500} := \frac{6+3}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{63}{1365000} := \frac{6+3}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 330. \quad & \frac{63}{448} := \frac{6 \times 3}{4 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{63}{4480} := \frac{6 \times 3}{4 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{63}{44800} := \frac{6 \times 3}{4 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{63}{448000} := \frac{6 \times 3}{4 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 321. \quad & \frac{62}{620} := \frac{6 \times 2}{6 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{62}{6200} := \frac{6 \times 2}{6 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{62}{62000} := \frac{6 \times 2}{6 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{62}{620000} := \frac{6 \times 2}{6 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 326. \quad & \frac{63}{140} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{63}{1400} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{63}{14000} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{63}{140000} := \frac{6 \times 3}{1 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 331. \quad & \frac{63}{462} := \frac{6+3}{4+62} \\
 & \frac{63}{4662} := \frac{6+3}{4+662} \\
 & \frac{63}{46662} := \frac{6+3}{4+6662} \\
 & \frac{63}{466662} := \frac{6+3}{4+66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 332. \quad & \frac{63}{630} := \frac{6 \times 3}{6 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{63}{63} := \frac{6 \times 3}{6 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{6300}{63} := \frac{6 \times 300}{6 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{63000}{63} := \frac{6 \times 3000}{6 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{630000}{63} := \frac{6 \times 30000}{6 \times 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 337. \quad & \frac{64}{352} := \frac{6+4}{3+52} \\
 & \frac{64}{64} := \frac{6+4}{6+4} \\
 & \frac{3552}{64} := \frac{3+552}{6+4} \\
 & \frac{35552}{64} := \frac{3+5552}{6+4} \\
 & \frac{355552}{64} := \frac{3+55552}{6+4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 342. \quad & \frac{66}{121} := \frac{6+6}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{66}{66} := \frac{6+6}{6+6} \\
 & \frac{1221}{66} := \frac{1+221}{6+6} \\
 & \frac{12221}{66} := \frac{1+2221}{6+6} \\
 & \frac{122221}{66} := \frac{1+22221}{6+6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 333. \quad & \frac{63}{693} := \frac{6+3}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{63}{6993} := \frac{6+3}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{63}{69993} := \frac{6+3}{6+9993} \\
 & \frac{63}{699993} := \frac{6+3}{6+99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 338. \quad & \frac{64}{640} := \frac{6 \times 4}{6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{64}{6400} := \frac{6 \times 4}{6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{64}{64000} := \frac{6 \times 4}{6 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{64}{640000} := \frac{6 \times 4}{6 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 343. \quad & \frac{66}{165} := \frac{6+6}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{66}{1650} := \frac{6+6}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{66}{16500} := \frac{6+6}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{66}{165000} := \frac{6+6}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 334. \quad & \frac{63}{735} := \frac{6+3}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{63}{7350} := \frac{6+3}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{63}{73500} := \frac{6+3}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{63}{735000} := \frac{6+3}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 339. \quad & \frac{65}{1248} := \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{65}{12480} := \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{65}{124800} := \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{65}{1248000} := \frac{6 \times 5}{12 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 344. \quad & \frac{66}{220} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{66}{2200} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{66}{22000} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{66}{220000} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 335. \quad & \frac{63}{784} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{63}{7840} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{63}{78400} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{63}{784000} := \frac{6 \times 3}{7 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 340. \quad & \frac{65}{260} := \frac{6 \times 5}{2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{65}{2600} := \frac{6 \times 5}{2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{65}{26000} := \frac{6 \times 5}{2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{65}{260000} := \frac{6 \times 5}{2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 345. \quad & \frac{66}{242} := \frac{6+6}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{66}{2442} := \frac{6+6}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{66}{24442} := \frac{6+6}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{66}{244442} := \frac{6+6}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 336. \quad & \frac{64}{160} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{64}{1600} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{64}{16000} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{64}{160000} := \frac{6 \times 4}{1 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 341. \quad & \frac{65}{650} := \frac{6 \times 5}{6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{65}{6500} := \frac{6 \times 5}{6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{65}{65000} := \frac{6 \times 5}{6 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{65}{650000} := \frac{6 \times 5}{6 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 346. \quad & \frac{66}{264} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{66}{2640} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{66}{26400} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{66}{264000} := \frac{6+6}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 347. \quad & \frac{66}{275} := \frac{6 \times 6}{2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{66}{2750} := \frac{6 \times 6}{2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{66}{27500} := \frac{6 \times 6}{2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{66}{275000} := \frac{6 \times 6}{2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 352. \quad & \frac{67}{670} := \frac{6 \times 7}{6 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{67}{6700} := \frac{6 \times 7}{6 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{67}{67000} := \frac{6 \times 7}{6 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{67}{670000} := \frac{6 \times 7}{6 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 357. \quad & \frac{69}{368} := \frac{6 \times 9}{36 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{69}{3680} := \frac{6 \times 9}{36 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{69}{36800} := \frac{6 \times 9}{36 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{69}{368000} := \frac{6 \times 9}{36 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 348. \quad & \frac{66}{363} := \frac{6+6}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{66}{3663} := \frac{6+6}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{66}{36663} := \frac{6+6}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{66}{366663} := \frac{6+6}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 353. \quad & \frac{68}{1275} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{68}{12750} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{68}{127500} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{68}{1275000} := \frac{6 \times 8}{12 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 358. \quad & \frac{69}{690} := \frac{6 \times 9}{6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{69}{6900} := \frac{6 \times 9}{6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{69}{69000} := \frac{6 \times 9}{6 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{69}{690000} := \frac{6 \times 9}{6 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 349. \quad & \frac{66}{396} := \frac{6+6}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{66}{3960} := \frac{6+6}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{66}{39600} := \frac{6+6}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{66}{396000} := \frac{6+6}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 354. \quad & \frac{68}{374} := \frac{6+8}{3+74} \\
 & \frac{68}{3774} := \frac{6+8}{3+774} \\
 & \frac{68}{37774} := \frac{6+8}{3+7774} \\
 & \frac{68}{377774} := \frac{6+8}{3+77774}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 359. \quad & \frac{71}{355} := \frac{7+1}{(3+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{71}{3550} := \frac{7+1}{(3+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{71}{35500} := \frac{7+1}{(3+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{71}{355000} := \frac{7+1}{(3+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 350. \quad & \frac{66}{484} := \frac{6+6}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{66}{4884} := \frac{6+6}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{66}{48884} := \frac{6+6}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{66}{488884} := \frac{6+6}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 355. \quad & \frac{68}{680} := \frac{6 \times 8}{6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{68}{6800} := \frac{6 \times 8}{6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{68}{68000} := \frac{6 \times 8}{6 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{68}{680000} := \frac{6 \times 8}{6 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 360. \quad & \frac{71}{426} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{71}{4260} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{71}{42600} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{71}{426000} := \frac{7+1}{4 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 351. \quad & \frac{66}{660} := \frac{6 \times 6}{6 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{66}{6600} := \frac{6 \times 6}{6 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{66}{66000} := \frac{6 \times 6}{6 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{66}{660000} := \frac{6 \times 6}{6 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 356. \quad & \frac{69}{253} := \frac{6+9}{2+53} \\
 & \frac{69}{2553} := \frac{6+9}{2+553} \\
 & \frac{69}{25553} := \frac{6+9}{2+5553} \\
 & \frac{69}{255553} := \frac{6+9}{2+55553}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 361. \quad & \frac{71}{710} := \frac{7 \times 1}{7 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{71}{7100} := \frac{7 \times 1}{7 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{71}{71000} := \frac{7 \times 1}{7 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{71}{710000} := \frac{7 \times 1}{7 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 362. \quad & \frac{71}{781} := \frac{7+1}{7+81} \\
 & \frac{71}{7881} := \frac{7+1}{7+881} \\
 & \frac{71}{78881} := \frac{7+1}{7+8881} \\
 & \frac{71}{788881} := \frac{7+1}{7+88881}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 367. \quad & \frac{72}{720} := \frac{7 \times 2}{7 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{72}{7200} := \frac{7 \times 2}{7 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{72}{72000} := \frac{7 \times 2}{7 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{72}{720000} := \frac{7 \times 2}{7 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 372. \quad & \frac{76}{760} := \frac{7 \times 6}{7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{76}{7600} := \frac{7 \times 6}{7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{76}{76000} := \frac{7 \times 6}{7 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{76}{760000} := \frac{7 \times 6}{7 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 363. \quad & \frac{72}{128} := \frac{7+2}{1 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{72}{1280} := \frac{7+2}{1 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{72}{12800} := \frac{7+2}{1 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{72}{128000} := \frac{7+2}{1 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 368. \quad & \frac{72}{792} := \frac{7+2}{7+92} \\
 & \frac{72}{7992} := \frac{7+2}{7+992} \\
 & \frac{72}{79992} := \frac{7+2}{7+9992} \\
 & \frac{72}{799992} := \frac{7+2}{7+99992}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 373. \quad & \frac{77}{121} := \frac{7+7}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{77}{1221} := \frac{7+7}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{77}{12221} := \frac{7+7}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{77}{122221} := \frac{7+7}{1+22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 364. \quad & \frac{72}{1296} := \frac{7+2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{72}{12960} := \frac{7+2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{72}{129600} := \frac{7+2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{72}{1296000} := \frac{7+2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 369. \quad & \frac{73}{730} := \frac{7 \times 3}{7 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{73}{7300} := \frac{7 \times 3}{7 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{73}{73000} := \frac{7 \times 3}{7 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{73}{730000} := \frac{7 \times 3}{7 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 374. \quad & \frac{77}{165} := \frac{7+7}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{77}{1650} := \frac{7+7}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{77}{16500} := \frac{7+7}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{77}{165000} := \frac{7+7}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 365. \quad & \frac{72}{576} := \frac{7+2}{(5+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{72}{5760} := \frac{7+2}{(5+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{72}{57600} := \frac{7+2}{(5+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{72}{576000} := \frac{7+2}{(5+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 370. \quad & \frac{74}{740} := \frac{7 \times 4}{7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{74}{7400} := \frac{7 \times 4}{7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{74}{74000} := \frac{7 \times 4}{7 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{74}{740000} := \frac{7 \times 4}{7 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 375. \quad & \frac{77}{220} := \frac{7+7}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{77}{2200} := \frac{7+7}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{77}{22000} := \frac{7+7}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{77}{220000} := \frac{7+7}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 366. \quad & \frac{72}{672} := \frac{7+2}{6 \times 7 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{72}{6720} := \frac{7+2}{6 \times 7 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{72}{67200} := \frac{7+2}{6 \times 7 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{72}{672000} := \frac{7+2}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 371. \quad & \frac{75}{750} := \frac{7 \times 5}{7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{75}{7500} := \frac{7 \times 5}{7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{75}{75000} := \frac{7 \times 5}{7 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{75}{750000} := \frac{7 \times 5}{7 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 376. \quad & \frac{77}{242} := \frac{7+7}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{77}{2442} := \frac{7+7}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{77}{24442} := \frac{7+7}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{77}{244442} := \frac{7+7}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 377. \quad & \frac{77}{363} := \frac{7+7}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{77}{3663} := \frac{7+7}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{77}{36663} := \frac{7+7}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{77}{366663} := \frac{7+7}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 382. \quad & \frac{78}{156} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{78}{1560} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{78}{15600} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{78}{156000} := \frac{7+8}{1 \times 5 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 387. \quad & \frac{81}{1125} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{81}{11250} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{81}{112500} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 12500}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 378. \quad & \frac{77}{396} := \frac{7+7}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{77}{3960} := \frac{7+7}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{77}{39600} := \frac{7+7}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{77}{396000} := \frac{7+7}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 383. \quad & \frac{78}{520} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{78}{5200} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{78}{52000} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{78}{520000} := \frac{7+8}{5 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 388. \quad & \frac{81}{1197} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{81}{11970} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{81}{119700} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{81}{1197000} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 379. \quad & \frac{77}{484} := \frac{7+7}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{77}{4884} := \frac{7+7}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{77}{48884} := \frac{7+7}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{77}{488884} := \frac{7+7}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 384. \quad & \frac{78}{780} := \frac{7 \times 8}{7 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{78}{7800} := \frac{7 \times 8}{7 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{78}{78000} := \frac{7 \times 8}{7 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{78}{780000} := \frac{7 \times 8}{7 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 389. \quad & \frac{81}{135} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{81}{1350} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{81}{13500} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{81}{135000} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 380. \quad & \frac{77}{770} := \frac{7 \times 7}{7 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{77}{7700} := \frac{7 \times 7}{7 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{77}{77000} := \frac{7 \times 7}{7 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{77}{770000} := \frac{7 \times 7}{7 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 385. \quad & \frac{79}{1264} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{79}{12640} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{79}{126400} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{79}{1264000} := \frac{7+9}{1 \times 2^6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 390. \quad & \frac{81}{1368} := \frac{8+1}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{81}{13680} := \frac{8+1}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{81}{136800} := \frac{8+1}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{81}{1368000} := \frac{8+1}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 381. \quad & \frac{78}{1456} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 56} \\
 & \frac{78}{14560} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 560} \\
 & \frac{78}{145600} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{78}{1456000} := \frac{7+8}{(1+4) \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 386. \quad & \frac{79}{790} := \frac{7 \times 9}{7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{79}{7900} := \frac{7 \times 9}{7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{79}{79000} := \frac{7 \times 9}{7 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{79}{790000} := \frac{7 \times 9}{7 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 391. \quad & \frac{81}{144} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{81}{1440} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{81}{14400} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{81}{144000} := \frac{8+1}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 392. \quad \frac{81}{1485} &:= \frac{8+1}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 \frac{81}{14850} &:= \frac{8+1}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 \frac{81}{148500} &:= \frac{8+1}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 \frac{81}{1485000} &:= \frac{8+1}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 397. \quad \frac{81}{810} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{8 \times 10} \\
 \frac{81}{8100} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{8 \times 100} \\
 \frac{81}{81000} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{8 \times 1000} \\
 \frac{81}{810000} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{8 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 402. \quad \frac{82}{328} &:= \frac{8^2}{32 \times 8} \\
 \frac{82}{3280} &:= \frac{8^2}{32 \times 80} \\
 \frac{82}{32800} &:= \frac{8^2}{32 \times 800} \\
 \frac{82}{328000} &:= \frac{8^2}{32 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 393. \quad \frac{81}{243} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 3} \\
 \frac{81}{2430} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 30} \\
 \frac{81}{24300} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 300} \\
 \frac{81}{243000} &:= \frac{8 \times 1}{2 \times 4 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 398. \quad \frac{81}{891} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+91} \\
 \frac{81}{8991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+991} \\
 \frac{81}{89991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+9991} \\
 \frac{81}{899991} &:= \frac{8+1}{8+99991}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 403. \quad \frac{82}{451} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+51} \\
 \frac{82}{4551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+551} \\
 \frac{82}{45551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+5551} \\
 \frac{82}{455551} &:= \frac{8+2}{4+55551}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 394. \quad \frac{81}{324} &:= \frac{8+1}{3^2 \times 4} \\
 \frac{81}{3240} &:= \frac{8+1}{3^2 \times 40} \\
 \frac{81}{32400} &:= \frac{8+1}{3^2 \times 400} \\
 \frac{81}{324000} &:= \frac{8+1}{3^2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 399. \quad \frac{82}{1435} &:= \frac{8+2}{(1+4) \times 35} \\
 \frac{82}{14350} &:= \frac{8+2}{(1+4) \times 350} \\
 \frac{82}{143500} &:= \frac{8+2}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\
 \frac{82}{1435000} &:= \frac{8+2}{(1+4) \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 404. \quad \frac{82}{820} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{8 \times 20} \\
 \frac{82}{8200} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{8 \times 200} \\
 \frac{82}{82000} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{8 \times 2000} \\
 \frac{82}{820000} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{8 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 395. \quad \frac{81}{585} &:= \frac{8+1}{(5+8) \times 5} \\
 \frac{81}{5850} &:= \frac{8+1}{(5+8) \times 50} \\
 \frac{81}{58500} &:= \frac{8+1}{(5+8) \times 500} \\
 \frac{81}{585000} &:= \frac{8+1}{(5+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 400. \quad \frac{82}{1476} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(1+47) \times 6} \\
 \frac{82}{14760} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(1+47) \times 60} \\
 \frac{82}{147600} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(1+47) \times 600} \\
 \frac{82}{1476000} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{(1+47) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 405. \quad \frac{83}{249} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 9} \\
 \frac{83}{2490} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 90} \\
 \frac{83}{24900} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 900} \\
 \frac{83}{249000} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 396. \quad \frac{81}{729} &:= \frac{8+1}{(7+2) \times 9} \\
 \frac{81}{7290} &:= \frac{8+1}{(7+2) \times 90} \\
 \frac{81}{72900} &:= \frac{8+1}{(7+2) \times 900} \\
 \frac{81}{729000} &:= \frac{8+1}{(7+2) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 401. \quad \frac{82}{246} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{2 \times 4 \times 6} \\
 \frac{82}{2460} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{2 \times 4 \times 60} \\
 \frac{82}{24600} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{2 \times 4 \times 600} \\
 \frac{82}{246000} &:= \frac{8 \times 2}{2 \times 4 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 406. \quad \frac{83}{332} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{3 \times 32} \\
 \frac{83}{3320} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{3 \times 320} \\
 \frac{83}{33200} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{3 \times 3200} \\
 \frac{83}{332000} &:= \frac{8 \times 3}{3 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$407. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{83}{830} := \frac{8 \times 3}{8 \times 30} \\ \frac{83}{83} := \frac{8 \times 3}{8 \times 3} \\ \frac{8300}{83} := \frac{8 \times 300}{8 \times 3} \\ \frac{83000}{83} := \frac{8 \times 3000}{8 \times 3} \\ \frac{830000}{83} := \frac{8 \times 30000}{8 \times 3} \end{array}$$

$$412. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{385} := \frac{8+4}{(3+8) \times 5} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{3850}{84} := \frac{(3+8) \times 50}{8+4} \\ \frac{38500}{84} := \frac{(3+8) \times 500}{8+4} \\ \frac{385000}{84} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5000}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$417. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{85}{1224} := \frac{8 \times 5}{12^2 \times 4} \\ \frac{85}{85} := \frac{8 \times 5}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{12240}{85} := \frac{12^2 \times 40}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{122400}{85} := \frac{12^2 \times 400}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{1224000}{85} := \frac{12^2 \times 4000}{8 \times 5} \end{array}$$

$$408. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{126} := \frac{8+4}{(1+2) \times 6} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{1260}{84} := \frac{(1+2) \times 60}{8+4} \\ \frac{12600}{84} := \frac{(1+2) \times 600}{8+4} \\ \frac{126000}{84} := \frac{(1+2) \times 6000}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$413. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{448} := \frac{8+4}{(4+4) \times 8} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{4480}{84} := \frac{(4+4) \times 80}{8+4} \\ \frac{44800}{84} := \frac{(4+4) \times 800}{8+4} \\ \frac{448000}{84} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8000}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$418. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{85}{187} := \frac{8 \times 5}{1+87} \\ \frac{85}{85} := \frac{8 \times 5}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{1887}{85} := \frac{1+887}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{18887}{85} := \frac{1+8887}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{188887}{85} := \frac{1+88887}{8 \times 5} \end{array}$$

$$409. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{189} := \frac{8 \times 4}{1 \times 8 \times 9} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8 \times 4}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{1890}{84} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 90}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{18900}{84} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 900}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{189000}{84} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9000}{8 \times 4} \end{array}$$

$$414. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{462} := \frac{8+4}{4+62} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{4662}{84} := \frac{4+662}{8+4} \\ \frac{46662}{84} := \frac{4+6662}{8+4} \\ \frac{466662}{84} := \frac{4+66662}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$419. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{85}{850} := \frac{8 \times 5}{8 \times 50} \\ \frac{85}{85} := \frac{8 \times 5}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{8500}{85} := \frac{8 \times 500}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{85000}{85} := \frac{8 \times 5000}{8 \times 5} \\ \frac{850000}{85} := \frac{8 \times 50000}{8 \times 5} \end{array}$$

$$410. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{231} := \frac{8+4}{2+31} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{2331}{84} := \frac{2+331}{8+4} \\ \frac{23331}{84} := \frac{2+3331}{8+4} \\ \frac{233331}{84} := \frac{2+33331}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$415. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{693} := \frac{8+4}{6+93} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{6993}{84} := \frac{6+993}{8+4} \\ \frac{69993}{84} := \frac{6+9993}{8+4} \\ \frac{699993}{84} := \frac{6+99993}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$420. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{86}{473} := \frac{8+6}{4+73} \\ \frac{86}{86} := \frac{8+6}{8+6} \\ \frac{4773}{86} := \frac{4+773}{8+6} \\ \frac{47773}{86} := \frac{4+7773}{8+6} \\ \frac{477773}{86} := \frac{4+77773}{8+6} \end{array}$$

$$411. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{315} := \frac{8+4}{3 \times 15} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8+4}{8+4} \\ \frac{3150}{84} := \frac{3 \times 150}{8+4} \\ \frac{31500}{84} := \frac{3 \times 1500}{8+4} \\ \frac{315000}{84} := \frac{3 \times 15000}{8+4} \end{array}$$

$$416. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{84}{840} := \frac{8 \times 4}{8 \times 40} \\ \frac{84}{84} := \frac{8 \times 4}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{8400}{84} := \frac{8 \times 400}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{84000}{84} := \frac{8 \times 4000}{8 \times 4} \\ \frac{840000}{84} := \frac{8 \times 40000}{8 \times 4} \end{array}$$

$$421. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{86}{688} := \frac{8 \times 6}{6 \times 8 \times 8} \\ \frac{86}{86} := \frac{8 \times 6}{8 \times 6} \\ \frac{6880}{86} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 80}{8 \times 6} \\ \frac{68800}{86} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 800}{8 \times 6} \\ \frac{688000}{86} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 8000}{8 \times 6} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 422. \quad & \frac{86}{860} := \frac{8 \times 6}{8 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{86}{8600} := \frac{8 \times 6}{8 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{86}{86000} := \frac{8 \times 6}{8 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{86}{860000} := \frac{8 \times 6}{8 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 427. \quad & \frac{88}{220} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{88}{2200} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{88}{22000} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{88}{220000} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 432. \quad & \frac{88}{484} := \frac{8+8}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{88}{4884} := \frac{8+8}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{88}{48884} := \frac{8+8}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{88}{488884} := \frac{8+8}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 423. \quad & \frac{87}{145} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{87}{1450} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{87}{14500} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{87}{145000} := \frac{8+7}{(1+4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 428. \quad & \frac{88}{242} := \frac{8+8}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{88}{2442} := \frac{8+8}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{88}{24442} := \frac{8+8}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{88}{244442} := \frac{8+8}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 433. \quad & \frac{88}{880} := \frac{8 \times 8}{8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{88}{8800} := \frac{8 \times 8}{8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{88}{88000} := \frac{8 \times 8}{8 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{88}{880000} := \frac{8 \times 8}{8 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 424. \quad & \frac{87}{870} := \frac{8 \times 7}{8 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{87}{8700} := \frac{8 \times 7}{8 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{87}{87000} := \frac{8 \times 7}{8 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{87}{870000} := \frac{8 \times 7}{8 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 429. \quad & \frac{88}{264} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{88}{2640} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{88}{26400} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{88}{264000} := \frac{8+8}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 434. \quad & \frac{89}{890} := \frac{8 \times 9}{8 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{89}{8900} := \frac{8 \times 9}{8 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{89}{89000} := \frac{8 \times 9}{8 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{89}{890000} := \frac{8 \times 9}{8 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 425. \quad & \frac{88}{121} := \frac{8+8}{1+21} \\
 & \frac{88}{1221} := \frac{8+8}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{88}{12221} := \frac{8+8}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{88}{122221} := \frac{8+8}{1+22221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 430. \quad & \frac{88}{363} := \frac{8+8}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{88}{3663} := \frac{8+8}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{88}{36663} := \frac{8+8}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{88}{366663} := \frac{8+8}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 435. \quad & \frac{91}{182} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(1+8) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{91}{1820} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(1+8) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{91}{18200} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(1+8) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{91}{182000} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(1+8) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 426. \quad & \frac{88}{165} := \frac{8+8}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{88}{1650} := \frac{8+8}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{88}{16500} := \frac{8+8}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{88}{165000} := \frac{8+8}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 431. \quad & \frac{88}{396} := \frac{8 \times 8}{3 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{88}{3960} := \frac{8 \times 8}{3 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{88}{39600} := \frac{8 \times 8}{3 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{88}{396000} := \frac{8 \times 8}{3 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 436. \quad & \frac{91}{273} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{91}{2730} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{91}{27300} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{91}{273000} := \frac{9 \times 1}{(2+7) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 437. \quad \frac{91}{364} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 4} \\
 \frac{91}{3640} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 40} \\
 \frac{91}{36400} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 400} \\
 \frac{91}{364000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(3+6) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 442. \quad \frac{91}{819} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 \frac{91}{8190} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 \frac{91}{81900} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 900} \\
 \frac{91}{819000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 447. \quad \frac{92}{368} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 8} \\
 \frac{92}{3680} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 80} \\
 \frac{92}{36800} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 800} \\
 \frac{92}{368000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 438. \quad \frac{91}{455} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(4+5) \times 5} \\
 \frac{91}{4550} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(4+5) \times 50} \\
 \frac{91}{45500} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(4+5) \times 500} \\
 \frac{91}{455000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(4+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 443. \quad \frac{91}{910} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{9 \times 10} \\
 \frac{91}{9100} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{9 \times 100} \\
 \frac{91}{91000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{9 \times 1000} \\
 \frac{91}{910000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 448. \quad \frac{92}{920} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{9 \times 20} \\
 \frac{92}{9200} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{9 \times 200} \\
 \frac{92}{92000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{9 \times 2000} \\
 \frac{92}{920000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{9 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 439. \quad \frac{91}{546} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 6} \\
 \frac{91}{5460} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 60} \\
 \frac{91}{54600} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 600} \\
 \frac{91}{546000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 444. \quad \frac{92}{1472} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 72} \\
 \frac{92}{14720} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 720} \\
 \frac{92}{147200} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 7200} \\
 \frac{92}{1472000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 449. \quad \frac{93}{186} &:= \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 6} \\
 \frac{93}{1860} &:= \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 60} \\
 \frac{93}{18600} &:= \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 600} \\
 \frac{93}{186000} &:= \frac{9 \times 3}{(1+8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 440. \quad \frac{91}{637} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 7} \\
 \frac{91}{6370} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 70} \\
 \frac{91}{63700} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 700} \\
 \frac{91}{637000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(6+3) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 445. \quad \frac{92}{184} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 4} \\
 \frac{92}{1840} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 40} \\
 \frac{92}{18400} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 400} \\
 \frac{92}{184000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(1+8) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 441. \quad \frac{91}{728} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 8} \\
 \frac{91}{7280} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 80} \\
 \frac{91}{72800} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 800} \\
 \frac{91}{728000} &:= \frac{9 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 446. \quad \frac{92}{276} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(2+7) \times 6} \\
 \frac{92}{2760} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(2+7) \times 60} \\
 \frac{92}{27600} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(2+7) \times 600} \\
 \frac{92}{276000} &:= \frac{9 \times 2}{(2+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 450. \quad \frac{93}{341} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+41} \\
 \frac{93}{3441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+441} \\
 \frac{93}{34441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+4441} \\
 \frac{93}{344441} &:= \frac{9+3}{3+44441}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$451. \quad \frac{93}{682} := \frac{9+3}{6+82}$$

$$\frac{93}{6882} := \frac{9+3}{6+882}$$

$$\frac{93}{68882} := \frac{9+3}{6+8882}$$

$$\frac{93}{688882} := \frac{9+3}{6+88882}$$

$$456. \quad \frac{95}{1425} := \frac{9+5}{1 \times 42 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{95}{14250} := \frac{9+5}{1 \times 42 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{95}{142500} := \frac{9+5}{1 \times 42 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{95}{1425000} := \frac{9+5}{1 \times 42 \times 5000}$$

$$461. \quad \frac{96}{960} := \frac{9 \times 6}{9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{96}{9600} := \frac{9 \times 6}{9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{96}{96000} := \frac{9 \times 6}{9 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{96}{960000} := \frac{9 \times 6}{9 \times 60000}$$

$$452. \quad \frac{93}{868} := \frac{9+3}{(8+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{93}{8680} := \frac{9+3}{(8+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{93}{86800} := \frac{9+3}{(8+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{93}{868000} := \frac{9+3}{(8+6) \times 8000}$$

$$457. \quad \frac{95}{190} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{95}{1900} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{95}{19000} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{95}{190000} := \frac{9 \times 5}{1 \times 90000}$$

$$462. \quad \frac{97}{970} := \frac{9 \times 7}{9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{97}{9700} := \frac{9 \times 7}{9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{97}{97000} := \frac{9 \times 7}{9 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{97}{970000} := \frac{9 \times 7}{9 \times 70000}$$

$$453. \quad \frac{93}{930} := \frac{9 \times 3}{9 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{93}{9300} := \frac{9 \times 3}{9 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{93}{93000} := \frac{9 \times 3}{9 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{93}{930000} := \frac{9 \times 3}{9 \times 30000}$$

$$458. \quad \frac{95}{342} := \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{95}{3420} := \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{95}{34200} := \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{95}{342000} := \frac{9 \times 5}{3^4 \times 2000}$$

$$463. \quad \frac{98}{490} := \frac{9 \times 8}{4 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{98}{4900} := \frac{9 \times 8}{4 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{98}{49000} := \frac{9 \times 8}{4 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{98}{490000} := \frac{9 \times 8}{4 \times 90000}$$

$$454. \quad \frac{94}{188} := \frac{9 \times 4}{(1+8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{94}{1880} := \frac{9 \times 4}{(1+8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{94}{18800} := \frac{9 \times 4}{(1+8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{94}{188000} := \frac{9 \times 4}{(1+8) \times 8000}$$

$$459. \quad \frac{95}{950} := \frac{9 \times 5}{9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{95}{9500} := \frac{9 \times 5}{9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{95}{95000} := \frac{9 \times 5}{9 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{95}{950000} := \frac{9 \times 5}{9 \times 50000}$$

$$464. \quad \frac{98}{980} := \frac{9 \times 8}{9 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{98}{9800} := \frac{9 \times 8}{9 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{98}{98000} := \frac{9 \times 8}{9 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{98}{980000} := \frac{9 \times 8}{9 \times 80000}$$

$$455. \quad \frac{94}{940} := \frac{9 \times 4}{9 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{94}{9400} := \frac{9 \times 4}{9 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{94}{94000} := \frac{9 \times 4}{9 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{94}{940000} := \frac{9 \times 4}{9 \times 40000}$$

$$460. \quad \frac{96}{352} := \frac{9+6}{3+52}$$

$$\frac{96}{3552} := \frac{9+6}{3+552}$$

$$\frac{96}{35552} := \frac{9+6}{3+5552}$$

$$\frac{96}{355552} := \frac{9+6}{3+55552}$$

$$465. \quad \frac{99}{121} := \frac{9+9}{1+21}$$

$$\frac{99}{1221} := \frac{9+9}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{99}{12221} := \frac{9+9}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{99}{122221} := \frac{9+9}{1+22221}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 466. \quad & \frac{99}{165} := \frac{9+9}{1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{99}{1650} := \frac{9+9}{1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{99}{16500} := \frac{9+9}{1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{99}{165000} := \frac{9+9}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 467. \quad & \frac{99}{220} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{99}{2200} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{99}{22000} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{99}{220000} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 468. \quad & \frac{99}{242} := \frac{9+9}{2+42} \\
 & \frac{99}{2442} := \frac{9+9}{2+442} \\
 & \frac{99}{24442} := \frac{9+9}{2+4442} \\
 & \frac{99}{244442} := \frac{9+9}{2+44442}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 469. \quad & \frac{99}{264} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{99}{2640} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{99}{26400} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{99}{264000} := \frac{9+9}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 470. \quad & \frac{99}{363} := \frac{9+9}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{99}{3663} := \frac{9+9}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{99}{36663} := \frac{9+9}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{99}{366663} := \frac{9+9}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 471. \quad & \frac{99}{396} := \frac{9+9}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{99}{3960} := \frac{9+9}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{99}{39600} := \frac{9+9}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{99}{396000} := \frac{9+9}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 472. \quad & \frac{99}{484} := \frac{9+9}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{99}{4884} := \frac{9+9}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{99}{48884} := \frac{9+9}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{99}{488884} := \frac{9+9}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 473. \quad & \frac{99}{990} := \frac{9 \times 9}{9 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{99}{9900} := \frac{9 \times 9}{9 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{99}{99000} := \frac{9 \times 9}{9 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{99}{990000} := \frac{9 \times 9}{9 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Three Digits Numerator

$$\begin{aligned}
 1. \quad & \frac{101}{1010} := \frac{10 \times 1}{10 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{101}{10100} := \frac{10 \times 1}{10 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{101}{101000} := \frac{10 \times 1}{10 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{101}{1010000} := \frac{10 \times 1}{10 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2. \quad & \frac{101}{1111} := \frac{10+1}{11 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{101}{11110} := \frac{10+1}{11 \times 110} \\
 & \frac{101}{111100} := \frac{10+1}{11 \times 1100} \\
 & \frac{101}{1111000} := \frac{10+1}{11 \times 11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3. \quad & \frac{101}{11211} := \frac{1+01}{11+11} \\
 & \frac{101}{112110} := \frac{1+01}{11+110} \\
 & \frac{101}{1121100} := \frac{1+01}{11+1100} \\
 & \frac{101}{11211000} := \frac{1+01}{11+11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4. \quad \frac{101}{1212} := \frac{1+01}{1 \times 2 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{101}{12120} := \frac{1+01}{1 \times 2 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{101}{121200} := \frac{1+01}{1 \times 2 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{101}{1212000} := \frac{1+01}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}$$

$$9. \quad \frac{102}{1020} := \frac{10 \times 2}{10 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{102}{10200} := \frac{10 \times 2}{10 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{102}{102000} := \frac{10 \times 2}{10 \times 2000}$$

$$14. \quad \frac{102}{1292} := \frac{1+02}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{102}{12920} := \frac{1+02}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{102}{129200} := \frac{1+02}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{102}{1292000} := \frac{1+02}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}$$

$$5. \quad \frac{101}{1313} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^3 \times 13}$$

$$\frac{101}{13130} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^3 \times 130}$$

$$\frac{101}{131300} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^3 \times 1300}$$

$$\frac{101}{1313000} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^3 \times 13000}$$

$$10. \quad \frac{102}{1122} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 1 \times 22}$$

$$\frac{102}{11220} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 1 \times 220}$$

$$\frac{102}{112200} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 1 \times 2200}$$

$$\frac{102}{1122000} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 1 \times 22000}$$

$$15. \quad \frac{102}{1326} := \frac{10+2}{13 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{102}{13260} := \frac{10+2}{13 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{102}{132600} := \frac{10+2}{13 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{102}{1326000} := \frac{10+2}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$6. \quad \frac{101}{1414} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^4 \times 14}$$

$$\frac{101}{14140} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^4 \times 140}$$

$$\frac{101}{141400} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^4 \times 1400}$$

$$\frac{101}{1414000} := \frac{1 \times 01}{1^4 \times 14000}$$

$$11. \quad \frac{102}{1122} := \frac{1+02}{11+22}$$

$$\frac{102}{11322} := \frac{1+02}{11+322}$$

$$\frac{102}{113322} := \frac{1+02}{11+3322}$$

$$16. \quad \frac{102}{1428} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^4 \times 28}$$

$$\frac{102}{14280} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^4 \times 280}$$

$$\frac{102}{142800} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^4 \times 2800}$$

$$\frac{102}{1428000} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^4 \times 28000}$$

$$7. \quad \frac{101}{202} := \frac{1+01}{2 \times 02}$$

$$\frac{101}{2020} := \frac{1+01}{2 \times 020}$$

$$\frac{101}{20200} := \frac{1+01}{2 \times 0200}$$

$$\frac{101}{202000} := \frac{1+01}{2 \times 02000}$$

$$12. \quad \frac{102}{1224} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^2 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{102}{12240} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^2 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{102}{122400} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^2 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{102}{1224000} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^2 \times 24000}$$

$$17. \quad \frac{102}{153} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^5 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{102}{1530} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^5 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{102}{15300} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^5 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{102}{153000} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1^5 \times 3000}$$

$$8. \quad \frac{102}{1020} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 0+20}$$

$$\frac{102}{10200} := \frac{1 \times 02}{1 \times 0+200}$$

$$13. \quad \frac{102}{1275} := \frac{10+2}{1 \times 2 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{102}{12750} := \frac{10+2}{1 \times 2 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{102}{127500} := \frac{10+2}{1 \times 2 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{102}{1275000} := \frac{10+2}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}$$

$$18. \quad \frac{102}{255} := \frac{10 \times 2}{2 \times 5 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{102}{2550} := \frac{10 \times 2}{2 \times 5 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{102}{25500} := \frac{10 \times 2}{2 \times 5 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{102}{255000} := \frac{10 \times 2}{2 \times 5 \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 19. \quad \frac{102}{3570} &:= \frac{1+02}{3 \times 5 \times 7+0} \\
 \frac{102}{35700} &:= \frac{1+02}{3 \times 5 \times 70+0} \\
 \frac{102}{357000} &:= \frac{1+02}{3 \times 5 \times 700+0} \\
 \frac{102}{3570000} &:= \frac{1+02}{3 \times 5 \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24. \quad \frac{102}{612} &:= \frac{10+2}{6 \times 12} \\
 \frac{102}{6120} &:= \frac{10+2}{6 \times 120} \\
 \frac{102}{61200} &:= \frac{10+2}{6 \times 1200} \\
 \frac{102}{612000} &:= \frac{10+2}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29. \quad \frac{103}{1133} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+33} \\
 \frac{103}{11433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+433} \\
 \frac{103}{114433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+4433} \\
 \frac{103}{1144433} &:= \frac{1+03}{11+44433}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20. \quad \frac{102}{510} &:= \frac{1^{02}}{5 \times 1+0} \\
 \frac{102}{5100} &:= \frac{1^{02}}{5 \times 10+0} \\
 \frac{102}{51000} &:= \frac{1^{02}}{5 \times 100+0} \\
 \frac{102}{510000} &:= \frac{1^{02}}{5 \times 1000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 25. \quad \frac{102}{748} &:= \frac{10+2}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 \frac{102}{7480} &:= \frac{10+2}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 \frac{102}{74800} &:= \frac{10+2}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 \frac{102}{748000} &:= \frac{10+2}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 30. \quad \frac{103}{1236} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 \frac{103}{12360} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 \frac{103}{123600} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 \frac{103}{1236000} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21. \quad \frac{102}{561} &:= \frac{1 \times 02}{(5+6) \times 1} \\
 \frac{102}{5610} &:= \frac{1 \times 02}{(5+6) \times 10} \\
 \frac{102}{56100} &:= \frac{1 \times 02}{(5+6) \times 100} \\
 \frac{102}{561000} &:= \frac{1 \times 02}{(5+6) \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26. \quad \frac{102}{952} &:= \frac{1+02}{(9+5) \times 2} \\
 \frac{102}{9520} &:= \frac{1+02}{(9+5) \times 20} \\
 \frac{102}{95200} &:= \frac{1+02}{(9+5) \times 200} \\
 \frac{102}{952000} &:= \frac{1+02}{(9+5) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31. \quad \frac{103}{1339} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^3 \times 39} \\
 \frac{103}{13390} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^3 \times 390} \\
 \frac{103}{133900} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^3 \times 3900} \\
 \frac{103}{1339000} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^3 \times 39000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 22. \quad \frac{102}{561} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+61} \\
 \frac{102}{5661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+661} \\
 \frac{102}{56661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+6661} \\
 \frac{102}{566661} &:= \frac{10+2}{5+66661}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27. \quad \frac{103}{1030} &:= \frac{10 \times 3}{10 \times 30} \\
 \frac{103}{10300} &:= \frac{10 \times 3}{10 \times 300} \\
 \frac{103}{103000} &:= \frac{10 \times 3}{10 \times 3000} \\
 \frac{103}{1030000} &:= \frac{10 \times 3}{10 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32. \quad \frac{103}{1442} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^4 \times 42} \\
 \frac{103}{14420} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^4 \times 420} \\
 \frac{103}{144200} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^4 \times 4200} \\
 \frac{103}{1442000} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1^4 \times 42000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23. \quad \frac{102}{595} &:= \frac{10+2}{(5+9) \times 50} \\
 \frac{102}{5950} &:= \frac{10+2}{(5+9) \times 500} \\
 \frac{102}{59500} &:= \frac{10+2}{(5+9) \times 5000} \\
 \frac{102}{595000} &:= \frac{10+2}{(5+9) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 28. \quad \frac{103}{1133} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 1 \times 33} \\
 \frac{103}{11330} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 1 \times 330} \\
 \frac{103}{113300} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 1 \times 3300} \\
 \frac{103}{1133000} &:= \frac{1 \times 03}{1 \times 1 \times 33000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33. \quad \frac{104}{1040} &:= \frac{10 \times 4}{10 \times 40} \\
 \frac{104}{10400} &:= \frac{10 \times 4}{10 \times 400} \\
 \frac{104}{104000} &:= \frac{10 \times 4}{10 \times 4000} \\
 \frac{104}{1040000} &:= \frac{10 \times 4}{10 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34. \quad & \frac{104}{1144} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1 \times 1 \times 44} \\
 & \frac{104}{11440} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1 \times 1 \times 440} \\
 & \frac{104}{114400} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1 \times 1 \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{104}{1144000} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1 \times 1 \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39. \quad & \frac{104}{156} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^5 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{104}{1560} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^5 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{104}{15600} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^5 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{104}{156000} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^5 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44. \quad & \frac{105}{12768} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 76 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{105}{127680} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 76 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{105}{1276800} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 76 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{105}{12768000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 76 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35. \quad & \frac{104}{1144} := \frac{1+04}{11+44} \\
 & \frac{104}{11544} := \frac{1+04}{11+544} \\
 & \frac{104}{115544} := \frac{1+04}{11+5544} \\
 & \frac{104}{1155544} := \frac{1+04}{11+55544}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40. \quad & \frac{104}{572} := \frac{10+4}{5+72} \\
 & \frac{104}{5772} := \frac{10+4}{5+772} \\
 & \frac{104}{57772} := \frac{10+4}{5+7772} \\
 & \frac{104}{577772} := \frac{10+4}{5+77772}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 45. \quad & \frac{105}{1302} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{105}{13020} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{105}{130200} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{105}{1302000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 36. \quad & \frac{104}{1248} := \frac{1 \times 04}{\times 1 \times 2 + 4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{104}{12480} := \frac{1 \times (04)}{(1 \times 2 + 4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{104}{124800} := \frac{1 \times (04)}{(1 \times 2 + 4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{104}{1248000} := \frac{1 \times (04)}{(1 \times 2 + 4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 41. \quad & \frac{105}{1050} := \frac{10 \times 5}{10 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{105}{10500} := \frac{10 \times 5}{10 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{105}{105000} := \frac{10 \times 5}{10 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{105}{1050000} := \frac{10 \times 5}{10 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46. \quad & \frac{105}{1344} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{105}{13440} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{105}{134400} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{105}{1344000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 37. \quad & \frac{104}{1352} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^3 \times 52} \\
 & \frac{104}{13520} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^3 \times 520} \\
 & \frac{104}{135200} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^3 \times 5200} \\
 & \frac{104}{1352000} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^3 \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 42. \quad & \frac{105}{1225} := \frac{1+05}{(12+2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{105}{12250} := \frac{1+05}{(12+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{105}{122500} := \frac{1+05}{(12+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{105}{1225000} := \frac{1+05}{(12+2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47. \quad & \frac{105}{1365} := \frac{10+5}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{105}{13650} := \frac{10+5}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{105}{136500} := \frac{10+5}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{105}{1365000} := \frac{10+5}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38. \quad & \frac{104}{1456} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^4 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{104}{14560} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^4 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{104}{145600} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^4 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{104}{1456000} := \frac{1 \times 04}{1^4 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 43. \quad & \frac{105}{126} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{105}{1260} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{105}{12600} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{105}{126000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48. \quad & \frac{105}{1386} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{105}{13860} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{105}{138600} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{105}{1386000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$49. \quad \frac{105}{14280} := \frac{1^{05}}{(1+4^2) \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{142800} := \frac{1^{05}}{(1+4^2) \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{1428000} := \frac{1^{05}}{(1+4^2) \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{14280000} := \frac{1^{05}}{(1+4^2) \times 8000+0}$$

$$54. \quad \frac{105}{231} := \frac{10+5}{2+31}$$

$$\frac{105}{2331} := \frac{10+5}{2+331}$$

$$\frac{105}{23331} := \frac{10+5}{2+3331}$$

$$\frac{105}{233331} := \frac{10+5}{2+33331}$$

$$59. \quad \frac{105}{5250} := \frac{1^{05}}{5 \times 2 \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{52500} := \frac{1^{05}}{5 \times 2 \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{525000} := \frac{1^{05}}{5 \times 2 \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{5250000} := \frac{1^{05}}{5 \times 2 \times 5000+0}$$

$$50. \quad \frac{105}{147} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^4 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{105}{1470} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{105}{14700} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{105}{147000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$55. \quad \frac{105}{280} := \frac{1+05}{2 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{2800} := \frac{1+05}{2 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{28000} := \frac{1+05}{2 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{280000} := \frac{1+05}{2 \times 8000+0}$$

$$60. \quad \frac{105}{693} := \frac{10+5}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{105}{6993} := \frac{10+5}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{105}{69993} := \frac{10+5}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{105}{699993} := \frac{10+5}{6+99993}$$

$$51. \quad \frac{105}{168} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{105}{1680} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{105}{16800} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{105}{168000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^6 \times 8000}$$

$$56. \quad \frac{105}{315} := \frac{10+5}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{105}{3150} := \frac{10+5}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{105}{31500} := \frac{10+5}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{105}{315000} := \frac{10+5}{3 \times 15000}$$

$$61. \quad \frac{105}{735} := \frac{10+5}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{105}{7350} := \frac{10+5}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{105}{73500} := \frac{10+5}{7 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{105}{735000} := \frac{10+5}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$52. \quad \frac{105}{189} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{105}{1890} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{105}{18900} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{105}{189000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{1^8 \times 9000}$$

$$57. \quad \frac{105}{448} := \frac{10+5}{(4+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{105}{4480} := \frac{10+5}{(4+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{105}{44800} := \frac{10+5}{(4+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{105}{448000} := \frac{10+5}{(4+4) \times 8000}$$

$$53. \quad \frac{105}{210} := \frac{1^{05}}{2 \times 1+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{2100} := \frac{1^{05}}{2 \times 10+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{21000} := \frac{1^{05}}{2 \times 100+0}$$

$$\frac{105}{210000} := \frac{1^{05}}{2 \times 1000+0}$$

$$58. \quad \frac{105}{462} := \frac{10+5}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{105}{4662} := \frac{10+5}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{105}{46662} := \frac{10+5}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{105}{466662} := \frac{10+5}{4+66662}$$

$$62. \quad \frac{105}{924} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(9+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{105}{9240} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(9+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{105}{92400} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(9+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{105}{924000} := \frac{1 \times 05}{(9+2) \times 4000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63. \quad & \frac{106}{1060} := \frac{10 \times 6}{10 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{106}{10600} := \frac{10 \times 6}{10 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{106}{106000} := \frac{10 \times 6}{10 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{106}{1060000} := \frac{10 \times 6}{10 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68. \quad & \frac{106}{265} := \frac{10+6}{(2+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{106}{2650} := \frac{10+6}{(2+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{106}{26500} := \frac{10+6}{(2+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{106}{265000} := \frac{10+6}{(2+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 73. \quad & \frac{107}{1177} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1 \times 1 \times 77} \\
 & \frac{107}{11770} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1 \times 1 \times 770} \\
 & \frac{107}{117700} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1 \times 1 \times 7700} \\
 & \frac{107}{1177000} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1 \times 1 \times 77000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64. \quad & \frac{106}{1272} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^2 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{106}{12720} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^2 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{106}{127200} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^2 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{106}{1272000} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^2 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69. \quad & \frac{106}{371} := \frac{1 \times 06}{3 \times 7 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{106}{3710} := \frac{1 \times 06}{3 \times 7 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{106}{37100} := \frac{1 \times 06}{3 \times 7 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{106}{371000} := \frac{1 \times 06}{3 \times 7 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 74. \quad & \frac{107}{1177} := \frac{1+07}{11+77} \\
 & \frac{107}{11877} := \frac{1+07}{11+877} \\
 & \frac{107}{118877} := \frac{1+07}{11+8877} \\
 & \frac{107}{1188877} := \frac{1+07}{11+88877}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65. \quad & \frac{106}{1378} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^3 \times 78} \\
 & \frac{106}{13780} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^3 \times 780} \\
 & \frac{106}{137800} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^3 \times 7800} \\
 & \frac{106}{1378000} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^3 \times 78000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 70. \quad & \frac{106}{424} := \frac{10+6}{4^2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{106}{4240} := \frac{10+6}{4^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{106}{42400} := \frac{10+6}{4^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{106}{424000} := \frac{10+6}{4^2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 75. \quad & \frac{107}{1391} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1^3 \times 91} \\
 & \frac{107}{13910} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1^3 \times 910} \\
 & \frac{107}{139100} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1^3 \times 9100} \\
 & \frac{107}{1391000} := \frac{1 \times 07}{1^3 \times 91000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66. \quad & \frac{106}{1484} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^4 \times 84} \\
 & \frac{106}{14840} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^4 \times 840} \\
 & \frac{106}{148400} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^4 \times 8400} \\
 & \frac{106}{1484000} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^4 \times 84000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 71. \quad & \frac{106}{583} := \frac{10+6}{5+83} \\
 & \frac{106}{5883} := \frac{10+6}{5+883} \\
 & \frac{106}{58883} := \frac{10+6}{5+8883} \\
 & \frac{106}{588883} := \frac{10+6}{5+88883}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76. \quad & \frac{107}{535} := \frac{1+07}{(5+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{107}{5350} := \frac{1+07}{(5+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{107}{53500} := \frac{1+07}{(5+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{107}{535000} := \frac{1+07}{(5+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67. \quad & \frac{106}{159} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^5 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{106}{1590} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^5 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{106}{15900} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^5 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{106}{159000} := \frac{1 \times 06}{1^5 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 72. \quad & \frac{107}{1070} := \frac{10 \times 7}{10 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{107}{10700} := \frac{10 \times 7}{10 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{107}{107000} := \frac{10 \times 7}{10 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{107}{1070000} := \frac{10 \times 7}{10 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77. \quad & \frac{107}{642} := \frac{1+07}{6+42} \\
 & \frac{107}{6420} := \frac{1+07}{6 \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{107}{64200} := \frac{1+07}{6 \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{107}{642000} := \frac{1+07}{6 \times 4 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$78. \quad \frac{108}{1080} := \frac{10 \times 8}{10 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{108}{10800} := \frac{10 \times 8}{10 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{108}{108000} := \frac{10 \times 8}{10 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{108}{1080000} := \frac{10 \times 8}{10 \times 80000}$$

$$83. \quad \frac{108}{1485} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(14+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{108}{14850} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(14+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{108}{148500} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(14+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{108}{1485000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(14+8) \times 5000}$$

$$88. \quad \frac{108}{594} := \frac{10+8}{5+94}$$

$$\frac{108}{5994} := \frac{10+8}{5+994}$$

$$\frac{108}{59994} := \frac{10+8}{5+9994}$$

$$\frac{108}{599994} := \frac{10+8}{5+99994}$$

$$79. \quad \frac{108}{1188} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 88}$$

$$\frac{108}{11880} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 880}$$

$$\frac{108}{118800} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 8800}$$

$$\frac{108}{1188000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 88000}$$

$$84. \quad \frac{108}{162} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{108}{1620} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{108}{16200} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{108}{162000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1 \times 6 \times 2000}$$

$$89. \quad \frac{109}{1090} := \frac{10 \times 9}{10 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{109}{10900} := \frac{10 \times 9}{10 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{109}{109000} := \frac{10 \times 9}{10 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{109}{1090000} := \frac{10 \times 9}{10 \times 90000}$$

$$80. \quad \frac{108}{1188} := \frac{1+8}{11+88}$$

$$\frac{108}{11988} := \frac{1+8}{11+988}$$

$$\frac{108}{119988} := \frac{1+8}{11+9988}$$

$$\frac{108}{1199988} := \frac{1+8}{11+99988}$$

$$85. \quad \frac{108}{216} := \frac{1+8}{(2+1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{108}{2160} := \frac{1+8}{(2+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{108}{21600} := \frac{1+8}{(2+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{108}{216000} := \frac{1+8}{(2+1) \times 6000}$$

$$90. \quad \frac{109}{1199} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 99}$$

$$\frac{109}{11990} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 990}$$

$$\frac{109}{119900} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 9900}$$

$$\frac{109}{1199000} := \frac{1 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}$$

$$81. \quad \frac{108}{120} := \frac{10+8}{1 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{108}{1200} := \frac{10+8}{1 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{108}{12000} := \frac{10+8}{1 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{108}{120000} := \frac{10+8}{1 \times 20000}$$

$$86. \quad \frac{108}{243} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(2+4) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{108}{2430} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(2+4) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{108}{24300} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(2+4) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{108}{243000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{(2+4) \times 3000}$$

$$91. \quad \frac{109}{545} := \frac{1 \times 9}{(5+4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{109}{5450} := \frac{1 \times 9}{(5+4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{109}{54500} := \frac{1 \times 9}{(5+4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{109}{545000} := \frac{1 \times 9}{(5+4) \times 5000}$$

$$82. \quad \frac{108}{1296} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1^2 \times 96}$$

$$\frac{108}{12960} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1^2 \times 960}$$

$$\frac{108}{129600} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1^2 \times 9600}$$

$$\frac{108}{1296000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{1^2 \times 96000}$$

$$87. \quad \frac{108}{324} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{108}{3240} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{108}{32400} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{108}{324000} := \frac{1 \times 8}{3 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$92. \quad \frac{110}{1089} := \frac{1 \times 10}{10+89}$$

$$\frac{110}{10989} := \frac{1 \times 10}{10+989}$$

$$\frac{110}{109989} := \frac{1 \times 10}{10+9989}$$

$$\frac{110}{1099989} := \frac{1 \times 10}{10+99989}$$

$$93. \quad \frac{110}{1815} := \frac{1+1+0}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{110}{18315} := \frac{1+1+0}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{110}{183315} := \frac{1+1+0}{18+3315}$$

$$\frac{110}{1833315} := \frac{1+1+0}{18+33315}$$

$$98. \quad \frac{111}{1221} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+21}$$

$$\frac{111}{12321} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+321}$$

$$\frac{111}{123321} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+3321}$$

$$\frac{111}{1233321} := \frac{1+1+1}{12+33321}$$

$$103. \quad \frac{111}{5550} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{5+5) \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{55500} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{5+5) \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{555000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{5+5) \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{5550000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{5+5) \times 5000+0}$$

$$94. \quad \frac{110}{605} := \frac{1+1+0}{6+05}$$

$$\frac{110}{6105} := \frac{1+1+0}{6+105}$$

$$\frac{110}{61105} := \frac{1+1+0}{6+1105}$$

$$\frac{110}{611105} := \frac{1+1+0}{6+11105}$$

$$99. \quad \frac{111}{1332} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{111}{13320} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{111}{133200} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{111}{1332000} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$104. \quad \frac{111}{814} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+14}$$

$$\frac{111}{8214} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+214}$$

$$\frac{111}{82214} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+2214}$$

$$\frac{111}{822214} := \frac{1+1+1}{8+22214}$$

$$95. \quad \frac{111}{1110} := \frac{1 \times 11}{1 \times 110}$$

$$\frac{111}{11100} := \frac{1 \times 11}{1 \times 1100}$$

$$\frac{111}{111000} := \frac{1 \times 11}{1 \times 11000}$$

$$\frac{111}{1110000} := \frac{1 \times 11}{1 \times 110000}$$

$$100. \quad \frac{111}{1480} := \frac{1+(1+1)}{(1+4) \times (8+0)}$$

$$\frac{111}{14800} := \frac{1+(1+1)}{(1+4) \times (80+0)}$$

$$\frac{111}{148000} := \frac{1+(1+1)}{(1+4) \times (800+0)}$$

$$\frac{111}{1480000} := \frac{1+(1+1)}{(1+4) \times (8000+0)}$$

$$105. \quad \frac{111}{9990} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{9+9 \times 9+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{99900} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{9+9 \times 90+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{999000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{9+9 \times 900+0}$$

$$\frac{111}{9990000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 1}{9+9 \times 9000+0}$$

$$96. \quad \frac{111}{1184} := \frac{1+1+1}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{111}{11840} := \frac{1+1+1}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{111}{118400} := \frac{1+1+1}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{111}{1184000} := \frac{1+1+1}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$101. \quad \frac{111}{185} := \frac{1+1+1}{1^8 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{111}{1850} := \frac{1+1+1}{1^8 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{111}{18500} := \frac{1+1+1}{1^8 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{111}{185000} := \frac{1+1+1}{1^8 \times 5000}$$

$$106. \quad \frac{112}{1120} := \frac{11 \times 2}{11 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{112}{11200} := \frac{11 \times 2}{11 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{112}{112000} := \frac{11 \times 2}{11 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{112}{1120000} := \frac{11 \times 2}{11 \times 20000}$$

$$97. \quad \frac{111}{1221} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{1 \times 22 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{111}{12210} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{1 \times 22 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{111}{122100} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{1 \times 22 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{111}{1221000} := \frac{1+1 \times 1}{1 \times 22 \times 1000}$$

$$102. \quad \frac{111}{407} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+07}$$

$$\frac{111}{4107} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+107}$$

$$\frac{111}{41107} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+1107}$$

$$\frac{111}{411107} := \frac{1+1+1}{4+11107}$$

$$107. \quad \frac{112}{1176} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{112}{11760} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{112}{117600} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{112}{1176000} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

$$108. \quad \frac{112}{1232} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{112}{12432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{112}{124432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{112}{1244432} := \frac{1+1+2}{12+44432}$$

$$113. \quad \frac{112}{924} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{112}{9324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{112}{93324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{112}{933324} := \frac{1+1+2}{9+33324}$$

$$118. \quad \frac{113}{5650} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{56500} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{565000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{5650000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 5000 + 0}$$

$$109. \quad \frac{112}{1344} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{112}{13440} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{112}{134400} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{112}{1344000} := \frac{1+1+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$114. \quad \frac{113}{1130} := \frac{11 \times 3}{11 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{113}{11300} := \frac{11 \times 3}{11 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{113}{113000} := \frac{11 \times 3}{11 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{113}{1130000} := \frac{11 \times 3}{11 \times 30000}$$

$$119. \quad \frac{114}{1026} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{(10+2) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{114}{10260} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{(10+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{114}{102600} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{(10+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{114}{1026000} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{(10+2) \times 6000}$$

$$110. \quad \frac{112}{308} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{112}{3108} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+108}$$

$$\frac{112}{31108} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+1108}$$

$$\frac{112}{311108} := \frac{1+1+2}{3+11108}$$

$$115. \quad \frac{113}{1243} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+43}$$

$$\frac{113}{12543} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+543}$$

$$\frac{113}{125543} := \frac{1+1+3}{12+5543}$$

$$120. \quad \frac{114}{1140} := \frac{11 \times 4}{11 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{114}{11400} := \frac{11 \times 4}{11 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{114}{114000} := \frac{11 \times 4}{11 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{114}{1140000} := \frac{11 \times 4}{11 \times 40000}$$

$$111. \quad \frac{112}{336} := \frac{1 \times 12}{(3+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{112}{3360} := \frac{1 \times 12}{(3+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{112}{33600} := \frac{1 \times 12}{(3+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{112}{336000} := \frac{1 \times 12}{(3+3) \times 6000}$$

$$116. \quad \frac{113}{1356} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^3+5) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{113}{13560} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^3+5) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{113}{135600} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^3+5) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{113}{1356000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^3+5) \times 6000}$$

$$121. \quad \frac{114}{1197} := \frac{1+1+4}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{114}{11970} := \frac{1+1+4}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{114}{119700} := \frac{1+1+4}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{114}{1197000} := \frac{1+1+4}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}$$

$$112. \quad \frac{112}{616} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{112}{6216} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{112}{62216} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{112}{622216} := \frac{1+1+2}{6+22216}$$

$$117. \quad \frac{113}{4520} := \frac{1^{13}}{4 \times 5 \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{45200} := \frac{1^{13}}{4 \times 5 \times 20 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{452000} := \frac{1^{13}}{4 \times 5 \times 200 + 0}$$

$$\frac{113}{4520000} := \frac{1^{13}}{4 \times 5 \times 2000 + 0}$$

$$122. \quad \frac{114}{1254} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{114}{12540} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{114}{125400} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 4000}$$

$$123. \quad \frac{114}{1368} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{1^3 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{114}{13680} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{1^3 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{114}{136800} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{1^3 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{114}{1368000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{1^3 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$124. \quad \frac{114}{1425} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{114}{14250} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{114}{142500} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{114}{1425000} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 25000}$$

$$125. \quad \frac{114}{1463} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{114}{14763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{114}{147763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{114}{1477763} := \frac{1+1+4}{14+77763}$$

$$126. \quad \frac{114}{1482} := \frac{1+1^4}{(1+4+8) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{114}{14820} := \frac{1+1^4}{(1+4+8) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{114}{148200} := \frac{1+1^4}{(1+4+8) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{114}{1482000} := \frac{1+1^4}{(1+4+8) \times 2000}$$

$$127. \quad \frac{114}{1672} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+72}$$

$$\frac{114}{16872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+872}$$

$$\frac{114}{168872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+8872}$$

$$\frac{114}{1688872} := \frac{1+1+4}{16+88872}$$

$$128. \quad \frac{114}{209} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+09}$$

$$\frac{114}{2109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{114}{21109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{114}{211109} := \frac{1+1+4}{2+11109}$$

$$129. \quad \frac{114}{228} := \frac{(1+1)^4}{2 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{114}{2280} := \frac{(1+1)^4}{2 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{114}{22800} := \frac{(1+1)^4}{2 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{114}{228000} := \frac{(1+1)^4}{2 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$130. \quad \frac{114}{2850} := \frac{1+1^4}{(2+8) \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{114}{28500} := \frac{1+1^4}{(2+8) \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{114}{285000} := \frac{1+1^4}{(2+8) \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{114}{2850000} := \frac{1+1^4}{(2+8) \times 5000+0}$$

$$131. \quad \frac{114}{342} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{3 \times 4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{114}{3420} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{3 \times 4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{114}{34200} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{3 \times 4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{114}{342000} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4}{3 \times 4 \times 2000}$$

$$132. \quad \frac{114}{418} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{114}{4218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{114}{42218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{114}{422218} := \frac{1+1+4}{4+22218}$$

$$133. \quad \frac{114}{513} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(5+1) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{114}{5130} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(5+1) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{114}{51300} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(5+1) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{114}{513000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 4}{(5+1) \times 3000}$$

$$134. \quad \frac{114}{627} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{114}{6327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{114}{63327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{114}{633327} := \frac{1+1+4}{6+33327}$$

$$135. \quad \frac{114}{836} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{114}{8436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{114}{84436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{114}{844436} := \frac{1+1+4}{8+44436}$$

$$136. \quad \frac{115}{1150} := \frac{11 \times 5}{11 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{115}{11500} := \frac{11 \times 5}{11 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{115}{115000} := \frac{11 \times 5}{11 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{115}{1150000} := \frac{11 \times 5}{11 \times 50000}$$

$$137. \frac{115}{1173} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{115}{11730} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{11730}{115} := \frac{1 \times 17 \times 300}{1 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{11730}{115} := \frac{1 \times 17 \times 300}{1 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{11730}{11730} := \frac{1 \times 17 \times 3000}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}$$

$$142. \frac{115}{3450} := \frac{1+1^5}{3 \times 4 \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{34500} := \frac{1+1^5}{3 \times 4 \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{345000} := \frac{1+1^5}{3 \times 4 \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{3450000} := \frac{1+1^5}{3 \times 4 \times 5000+0}$$

$$147. \frac{116}{1392} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{116}{13920} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{116}{139200} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{116}{1392000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$138. \frac{115}{1242} := \frac{1 \times 15}{(1+2)^4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{115}{12420} := \frac{1 \times 15}{(1+2)^4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{115}{124200} := \frac{1 \times 15}{(1+2)^4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{115}{1242000} := \frac{1 \times 15}{(1+2)^4 \times 2000}$$

$$143. \frac{115}{460} := \frac{1 \times 1+5}{4 \times 6+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{4600} := \frac{1 \times 1+5}{4 \times 60+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{46000} := \frac{1 \times 1+5}{4 \times 600+0}$$

$$\frac{115}{460000} := \frac{1 \times 1+5}{4 \times 6000+0}$$

$$148. \frac{116}{1421} := \frac{1 \times 16}{14^2 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{116}{14210} := \frac{1 \times 16}{14^2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{116}{142100} := \frac{1 \times 16}{14^2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{116}{1421000} := \frac{1 \times 16}{14^2 \times 1000}$$

$$139. \frac{115}{1265} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+65}$$

$$\frac{115}{12765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+765}$$

$$\frac{115}{127765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+7765}$$

$$\frac{115}{1277765} := \frac{1+1+5}{12+77765}$$

$$144. \frac{115}{759} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+59}$$

$$\frac{115}{7659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+659}$$

$$\frac{115}{76659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+6659}$$

$$\frac{115}{766659} := \frac{(1+1) \times 5}{7+66659}$$

$$149. \frac{116}{145} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{116}{1450} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{116}{14500} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{116}{145000} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 5000}$$

$$140. \frac{115}{1380} := \frac{1+1^5}{(1 \times 3 \times 8+0)}$$

$$\frac{115}{13800} := \frac{1+1^5}{(1 \times 3 \times 80+0)}$$

$$\frac{115}{138000} := \frac{1+1^5}{(1 \times 3 \times 800+0)}$$

$$\frac{115}{1380000} := \frac{1+1^5}{(1 \times 3 \times 8000+0)}$$

$$145. \frac{116}{1160} := \frac{11 \times 6}{11 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{116}{11600} := \frac{11 \times 6}{11 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{116}{116000} := \frac{11 \times 6}{11 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{116}{1160000} := \frac{11 \times 6}{11 \times 60000}$$

$$150. \frac{116}{232} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{2 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{116}{2320} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{2 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{116}{23200} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{2 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{116}{232000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 6}{2 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$141. \frac{115}{161} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{1+6 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{115}{1610} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 10}$$

$$\frac{115}{16100} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 100}$$

$$\frac{115}{161000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+6) \times 1000}$$

$$146. \frac{116}{1218} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 21 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{116}{12180} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 21 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{116}{121800} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 21 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{116}{1218000} := \frac{1 \times 16}{1 \times 21 \times 8000}$$

$$151. \frac{116}{319} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+19}$$

$$\frac{116}{3219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+219}$$

$$\frac{116}{32219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+2219}$$

$$\frac{116}{322219} := \frac{1+1+6}{3+22219}$$

$$152. \quad \frac{116}{435} := \frac{1 \times 16}{4 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{116}{4350} := \frac{1 \times 16}{4 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{116}{43500} := \frac{1 \times 16}{4 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{116}{435000} := \frac{1 \times 16}{4 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$157. \quad \frac{116}{986} := \frac{(1+1) \times 6}{(9+8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{116}{9860} := \frac{(1+1) \times 6}{(9+8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{116}{98600} := \frac{(1+1) \times 6}{(9+8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{116}{986000} := \frac{(1+1) \times 6}{(9+8) \times 6000}$$

$$162. \quad \frac{117}{1287} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+2+8) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{117}{12870} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+2+8) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{117}{128700} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+2+8) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{117}{1287000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+2+8) \times 7000}$$

$$153. \quad \frac{116}{464} := \frac{(1+1)^6}{4 \times 64}$$

$$\frac{116}{4640} := \frac{(1+1)^6}{4 \times 640}$$

$$\frac{116}{46400} := \frac{(1+1)^6}{4 \times 6400}$$

$$\frac{116}{464000} := \frac{(1+1)^6}{4 \times 64000}$$

$$158. \quad \frac{117}{1053} := \frac{1+1^7}{(1+05) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{117}{10530} := \frac{1+1^7}{(1+05) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{117}{105300} := \frac{1+1^7}{(1+05) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{117}{1053000} := \frac{1+1^7}{(1+05) \times 3000}$$

$$163. \quad \frac{117}{1287} := \frac{1+1+7}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{117}{12987} := \frac{1+1+7}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{117}{129987} := \frac{1+1+7}{12+9987}$$

$$154. \quad \frac{116}{580} := \frac{1+1+6}{5 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{116}{5800} := \frac{1+1+6}{5 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{116}{58000} := \frac{1+1+6}{5 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{116}{580000} := \frac{1+1+6}{5 \times 8000+0}$$

$$159. \quad \frac{117}{1144} := \frac{1+17}{11 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{117}{11440} := \frac{1+17}{11 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{117}{114400} := \frac{1+17}{11 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{117}{1144000} := \frac{1+17}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$164. \quad \frac{117}{1352} := \frac{1+17}{(1+3) \times 52}$$

$$\frac{117}{13520} := \frac{1+17}{(1+3) \times 520}$$

$$\frac{117}{135200} := \frac{1+17}{(1+3) \times 5200}$$

$$\frac{117}{1352000} := \frac{1+17}{(1+3) \times 52000}$$

$$155. \quad \frac{116}{638} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+38}$$

$$\frac{116}{6438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+438}$$

$$\frac{116}{64438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+4438}$$

$$\frac{116}{644438} := \frac{1+1+6}{6+44438}$$

$$160. \quad \frac{117}{1170} := \frac{11 \times 7}{11 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{117}{11700} := \frac{11 \times 7}{11 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{117}{117000} := \frac{11 \times 7}{11 \times 7000}$$

$$165. \quad \frac{117}{1456} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{117}{14560} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{117}{145600} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{117}{1456000} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}$$

$$156. \quad \frac{116}{957} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+57}$$

$$\frac{116}{9657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+657}$$

$$\frac{116}{96657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+6657}$$

$$\frac{116}{966657} := \frac{1+1+6}{9+66657}$$

$$161. \quad \frac{117}{1248} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 24 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{117}{12480} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 24 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{117}{124800} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 24 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{117}{1248000} := \frac{1+17}{1 \times 24 \times 8000}$$

$$166. \quad \frac{117}{208} := \frac{1+1+7}{2 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{117}{2080} := \frac{1+1+7}{2 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{117}{20800} := \frac{1+1+7}{2 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{117}{208000} := \frac{1+1+7}{2 \times 08000}$$

$$167. \quad \frac{117}{2340} := \frac{1^{17}}{(2+3) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{23400} := \frac{1^{17}}{(2+3) \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{234000} := \frac{1^{17}}{(2+3) \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{2340000} := \frac{1^{17}}{(2+3) \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$172. \quad \frac{117}{4680} := \frac{1+1^7}{(4+6) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{46800} := \frac{1+1^7}{(4+6) \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{468000} := \frac{1+1^7}{(4+6) \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{117}{4680000} := \frac{1+1^7}{(4+6) \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$177. \quad \frac{118}{1298} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{118}{12980} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{118}{129800} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{118}{1298000} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 8000}$$

$$168. \quad \frac{117}{273} := \frac{1+17}{2 \times 7 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{117}{2730} := \frac{1+17}{2 \times 7 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{117}{27300} := \frac{1+17}{2 \times 7 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{117}{273000} := \frac{1+17}{2 \times 7 \times 3000}$$

$$173. \quad \frac{117}{624} := \frac{1+1+7}{6 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{117}{6240} := \frac{1+1+7}{6 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{117}{62400} := \frac{1+1+7}{6 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{117}{624000} := \frac{1+1+7}{6 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$178. \quad \frac{118}{1416} := \frac{1+1^8}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{118}{14160} := \frac{1+1^8}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{118}{141600} := \frac{1+1^8}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{118}{1416000} := \frac{1+1^8}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$169. \quad \frac{117}{325} := \frac{1+1+7}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{117}{3250} := \frac{1+1+7}{(3+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{117}{32500} := \frac{1+1+7}{(3+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{117}{325000} := \frac{1+1+7}{(3+2) \times 5000}$$

$$174. \quad \frac{117}{728} := \frac{1+17}{7 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{117}{7280} := \frac{1+17}{7 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{117}{72800} := \frac{1+17}{7 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{117}{728000} := \frac{1+17}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$179. \quad \frac{118}{590} := \frac{1 \times 1 + 8}{5 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\frac{118}{5900} := \frac{1 \times 1 + 8}{5 \times 90 + 0}$$

$$\frac{118}{59000} := \frac{1 \times 1 + 8}{5 \times 900 + 0}$$

$$\frac{118}{590000} := \frac{1 \times 1 + 8}{5 \times 9000 + 0}$$

$$170. \quad \frac{117}{416} := \frac{1+17}{4 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{117}{4160} := \frac{1+17}{4 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{117}{41600} := \frac{1+17}{4 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{117}{416000} := \frac{1+17}{4 \times 16000}$$

$$175. \quad \frac{117}{936} := \frac{1+1+7}{(9+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{117}{9360} := \frac{1+1+7}{(9+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{117}{93600} := \frac{1+1+7}{(9+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{117}{936000} := \frac{1+1+7}{(9+3) \times 6000}$$

$$171. \quad \frac{117}{429} := \frac{1+1+7}{4+29}$$

$$\frac{117}{4329} := \frac{1+1+7}{4+329}$$

$$\frac{117}{43329} := \frac{1+1+7}{4+3329}$$

$$\frac{117}{433329} := \frac{1+1+7}{4+33329}$$

$$176. \quad \frac{118}{1180} := \frac{11 \times 8}{11 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{118}{11800} := \frac{11 \times 8}{11 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{118}{118000} := \frac{11 \times 8}{11 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{118}{1180000} := \frac{11 \times 8}{11 \times 80000}$$

$$180. \quad \frac{118}{649} := \frac{1+1+8}{6+49}$$

$$\frac{118}{6549} := \frac{1+1+8}{6+549}$$

$$\frac{118}{65549} := \frac{1+1+8}{6+5549}$$

$$\frac{118}{655549} := \frac{1+1+8}{6+55549}$$

$$181. \quad \frac{118}{944} := \frac{1 \times 18}{9 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{118}{9440} := \frac{1 \times 18}{9 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{118}{94400} := \frac{1 \times 18}{9 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{118}{944000} := \frac{1 \times 18}{9 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$186. \quad \frac{121}{1210} := \frac{12 \times 1}{12 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{121}{12100} := \frac{12 \times 1}{12 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{121}{121000} := \frac{12 \times 1}{12 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{121}{1210000} := \frac{12 \times 1}{12 \times 10000}$$

$$191. \quad \frac{121}{220} := \frac{1+21}{2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{121}{2200} := \frac{1+21}{2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{121}{22000} := \frac{1+21}{2 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{121}{220000} := \frac{1+21}{2 \times 20000}$$

$$182. \quad \frac{119}{1309} := \frac{1+1^9}{13+09}$$

$$\frac{119}{13209} := \frac{1+1^9}{13+209}$$

$$\frac{119}{132209} := \frac{1+1^9}{13+2209}$$

$$\frac{119}{1322209} := \frac{1+1^9}{13+22209}$$

$$187. \quad \frac{121}{1221} := \frac{1+21}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{121}{12221} := \frac{1+21}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{121}{122221} := \frac{1+21}{1+22221}$$

$$\frac{121}{1222221} := \frac{1+21}{1+222221}$$

$$192. \quad \frac{121}{242} := \frac{1+21}{2+42}$$

$$\frac{121}{2442} := \frac{1+21}{2+442}$$

$$\frac{121}{24442} := \frac{1+21}{2+4442}$$

$$\frac{121}{244442} := \frac{1+21}{2+44442}$$

$$183. \quad \frac{119}{238} := \frac{1+19}{(2+3) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{119}{2380} := \frac{1+19}{(2+3) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{119}{23800} := \frac{1+19}{(2+3) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{119}{238000} := \frac{1+19}{(2+3) \times 8000}$$

$$188. \quad \frac{121}{1331} := \frac{1+2 \times 1}{1 \times 33 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{121}{13310} := \frac{1+2 \times 1}{1 \times 33 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{121}{133100} := \frac{1+2 \times 1}{1 \times 33 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{121}{1331000} := \frac{1+2 \times 1}{1 \times 33 \times 1000}$$

$$193. \quad \frac{121}{363} := \frac{1+21}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{121}{3663} := \frac{1+21}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{121}{36663} := \frac{1+21}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{121}{366663} := \frac{1+21}{3+66663}$$

$$184. \quad \frac{120}{594} := \frac{1 \times 20}{5+94}$$

$$\frac{120}{5994} := \frac{1 \times 20}{5+994}$$

$$\frac{120}{59994} := \frac{1 \times 20}{5+9994}$$

$$\frac{120}{599994} := \frac{1 \times 20}{5+99994}$$

$$189. \quad \frac{121}{1452} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{(1^4+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{121}{14520} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{(1^4+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{121}{145200} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{(1^4+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{121}{1452000} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{(1^4+5) \times 2000}$$

$$185. \quad \frac{121}{1089} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{10^8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{121}{10890} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{10^8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{121}{108900} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{10^8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{121}{1089000} := \frac{1^2 \times 1}{10^8 \times 9000}$$

$$190. \quad \frac{121}{165} := \frac{1+21}{1 \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{121}{1650} := \frac{1+21}{1 \times 6 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{121}{16500} := \frac{1+21}{1 \times 6 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{121}{165000} := \frac{1+21}{1 \times 6 \times 5000}$$

$$194. \quad \frac{121}{396} := \frac{1+21}{(3+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{121}{3960} := \frac{1+21}{(3+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{121}{39600} := \frac{1+21}{(3+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{121}{396000} := \frac{1+21}{(3+9) \times 6000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 195. \quad & \frac{121}{484} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(4+8) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{121}{4840} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(4+8) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{121}{48400} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(4+8) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{121}{484000} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(4+8) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 200. \quad & \frac{122}{305} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{3 \times 05} \\
 & \frac{122}{3050} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{3 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{122}{30500} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{3 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{122}{305000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{3 \times 05000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 205. \quad & \frac{123}{1230} := \frac{12 \times 3}{12 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{123}{12300} := \frac{12 \times 3}{12 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{123}{123000} := \frac{12 \times 3}{12 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{123}{1230000} := \frac{12 \times 3}{12 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 196. \quad & \frac{121}{847} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(8+4) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{121}{8470} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(8+4) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{121}{84700} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(8+4) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{121}{847000} := \frac{12 \times 1}{(8+4) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 201. \quad & \frac{122}{488} := \frac{12 \times 2}{(4+8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{122}{4880} := \frac{12 \times 2}{(4+8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{122}{48800} := \frac{12 \times 2}{(4+8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{122}{488000} := \frac{12 \times 2}{(4+8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 206. \quad & \frac{123}{1312} := \frac{1 + (2+3)}{(1+31) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{123}{13120} := \frac{1 + (2+3)}{(1+31) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{123}{131200} := \frac{1 + (2+3)}{(1+31) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{123}{1312000} := \frac{1 + (2+3)}{(1+31) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 197. \quad & \frac{122}{1220} := \frac{12 \times 2}{12 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{122}{12200} := \frac{12 \times 2}{12 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{122}{122000} := \frac{12 \times 2}{12 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{122}{1220000} := \frac{12 \times 2}{12 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 202. \quad & \frac{122}{5490} := \frac{1 \times (2^2)}{5 \times 4 \times 9 + 0} \\
 & \frac{122}{54900} := \frac{1 \times (2^2)}{5 \times 4 \times 90 + 0} \\
 & \frac{122}{549000} := \frac{1 \times (2^2)}{5 \times 4 \times 900 + 0} \\
 & \frac{122}{5490000} := \frac{1 \times (2^2)}{5 \times 4 \times 9000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 207. \quad & \frac{123}{1353} := \frac{1+2+3}{13+53} \\
 & \frac{123}{13653} := \frac{1+2+3}{13+653} \\
 & \frac{123}{136653} := \frac{1+2+3}{13+6653} \\
 & \frac{123}{1366653} := \frac{1+2+3}{13+66653}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 198. \quad & \frac{122}{1464} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^4 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{122}{14640} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^4 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{122}{146400} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^4 \times 6 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{122}{1464000} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^4 \times 6 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 203. \quad & \frac{122}{671} := \frac{12+2}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{122}{6771} := \frac{12+2}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{122}{67771} := \frac{12+2}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{122}{677771} := \frac{12+2}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 199. \quad & \frac{122}{183} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^8 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{122}{1830} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^8 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{122}{18300} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^8 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{122}{183000} := \frac{1^2 \times 2}{1^8 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 204. \quad & \frac{122}{915} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{9 \times 1 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{122}{9150} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{9 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{122}{91500} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{9 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{122}{915000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2}{9 \times 1 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 208. \quad & \frac{123}{1435} := \frac{12+3}{(1+4) \times 35} \\
 & \frac{123}{14350} := \frac{12+3}{(1+4) \times 350} \\
 & \frac{123}{143500} := \frac{12+3}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{123}{1435000} := \frac{12+3}{(1+4) \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$209. \quad \frac{123}{1476} := \frac{1+23}{(1+47) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{123}{14760} := \frac{1+23}{(1+47) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{123}{147600} := \frac{1+23}{(1+47) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{123}{1476000} := \frac{1+23}{(1+47) \times 6000}$$

$$214. \quad \frac{123}{328} := \frac{12+3}{(3+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{123}{3280} := \frac{12+3}{(3+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{123}{32800} := \frac{12+3}{(3+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{123}{328000} := \frac{12+3}{(3+2) \times 8000}$$

$$219. \quad \frac{123}{984} := \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{123}{9840} := \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{123}{98400} := \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{123}{984000} := \frac{12 \times 3}{9 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$210. \quad \frac{123}{164} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{1^6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{123}{1640} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{1^6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{123}{16400} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{1^6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{123}{164000} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{1^6 \times 4000}$$

$$215. \quad \frac{123}{369} := \frac{(1+2)^3}{(3+6) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{123}{3690} := \frac{(1+2)^3}{(3+6) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{123}{36900} := \frac{(1+2)^3}{(3+6) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{123}{369000} := \frac{(1+2)^3}{(3+6) \times 9000}$$

$$220. \quad \frac{124}{1023} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+23}$$

$$\frac{124}{10323} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+323}$$

$$\frac{124}{103323} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+3323}$$

$$\frac{124}{1033323} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{10+33323}$$

$$211. \quad \frac{123}{205} := \frac{1+2+3}{2 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{123}{2050} := \frac{1+2+3}{2 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{123}{20500} := \frac{1+2+3}{2 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{123}{205000} := \frac{1+2+3}{2 \times 05000}$$

$$216. \quad \frac{123}{451} := \frac{12+3}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{123}{4551} := \frac{12+3}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{123}{45551} := \frac{12+3}{4+5551}$$

$$\frac{123}{455551} := \frac{12+3}{4+55551}$$

$$221. \quad \frac{124}{1116} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+11) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{124}{11160} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+11) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{124}{111600} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+11) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{124}{1116000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1+11) \times 6000}$$

$$212. \quad \frac{123}{246} := \frac{1+23}{2 \times 4 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{123}{2460} := \frac{1+23}{2 \times 4 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{123}{24600} := \frac{1+23}{2 \times 4 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{123}{246000} := \frac{1+23}{2 \times 4 \times 6000}$$

$$217. \quad \frac{123}{615} := \frac{1+2+3}{6 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{123}{6150} := \frac{1+2+3}{6 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{123}{61500} := \frac{1+2+3}{6 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{123}{615000} := \frac{1+2+3}{6 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$213. \quad \frac{123}{2870} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{(2+8) \times 7+0}$$

$$\frac{123}{28700} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{(2+8) \times 70+0}$$

$$\frac{123}{287000} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{(2+8) \times 700+0}$$

$$\frac{123}{2870000} := \frac{1^2 \times 3}{(2+8) \times 7000+0}$$

$$218. \quad \frac{123}{820} := \frac{1+23}{8 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{123}{8200} := \frac{1+23}{8 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{123}{82000} := \frac{1+23}{8 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{123}{820000} := \frac{1+23}{8 \times 20000}$$

$$222. \quad \frac{124}{1240} := \frac{12 \times 4}{12 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{124}{12400} := \frac{12 \times 4}{12 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{124}{124000} := \frac{12 \times 4}{12 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{124}{1240000} := \frac{12 \times 4}{12 \times 40000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 223. \quad & \frac{124}{13764} := \frac{1+2+4}{13+764} \\
 & \frac{124}{137764} := \frac{1+2+4}{13+7764} \\
 & \frac{124}{1377764} := \frac{1+2+4}{13+77764} \\
 & \frac{124}{13777764} := \frac{1+2+4}{13+777764}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 228. \quad & \frac{124}{217} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{2 \times 1 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{124}{2170} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{2 \times 1 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{124}{21700} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{2 \times 1 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{124}{217000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{2 \times 1 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 233. \quad & \frac{124}{620} := \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{124}{6200} := \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{124}{62000} := \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{124}{620000} := \frac{1 \times 24}{6 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 224. \quad & \frac{124}{1395} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{124}{13950} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{124}{139500} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{124}{1395000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 229. \quad & \frac{124}{248} := \frac{12 \times 4}{2 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{124}{2480} := \frac{12 \times 4}{2 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{124}{24800} := \frac{12 \times 4}{2 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{124}{248000} := \frac{12 \times 4}{2 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 234. \quad & \frac{124}{682} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6+82} \\
 & \frac{124}{6882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6+882} \\
 & \frac{124}{68882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6+8882} \\
 & \frac{124}{688882} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{6+88882}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 225. \quad & \frac{124}{1488} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{124}{14880} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{124}{148800} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{124}{1488000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 230. \quad & \frac{124}{310} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{3 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{124}{3100} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{3 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{124}{31000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{3 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{124}{310000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 4}{3 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 235. \quad & \frac{124}{868} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{(8+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{124}{8680} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{(8+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{124}{86800} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{(8+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{124}{868000} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{(8+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 226. \quad & \frac{124}{155} := \frac{1 \times 24}{(1+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{124}{1550} := \frac{1 \times 24}{(1+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{124}{15500} := \frac{1 \times 24}{(1+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{124}{155000} := \frac{1 \times 24}{(1+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 231. \quad & \frac{124}{341} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+41} \\
 & \frac{124}{3441} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+441} \\
 & \frac{124}{34441} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+4441} \\
 & \frac{124}{344441} := \frac{1 \times 2^4}{3+44441}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 227. \quad & \frac{124}{186} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{1^8 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{124}{1860} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{1^8 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{124}{18600} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{1^8 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{124}{186000} := \frac{1^2 \times 4}{1^8 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 232. \quad & \frac{124}{434} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(4+3) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{124}{4340} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(4+3) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{124}{43400} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(4+3) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{124}{434000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 4}{(4+3) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 236. \quad & \frac{125}{1375} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{125}{13750} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{125}{137500} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{125}{1375000} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$237. \quad \frac{125}{175} := \frac{1 \times 25}{1 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{125}{1750} := \frac{1 \times 25}{1 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{125}{17500} := \frac{1 \times 25}{1 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{125}{175000} := \frac{1 \times 25}{1 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$238. \quad \frac{125}{250} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{2 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{125}{2500} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{2 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{125}{25000} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{2 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{125}{250000} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{2 \times 5000 + 0}$$

$$239. \quad \frac{125}{495} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 95}$$

$$\frac{125}{4995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 995}$$

$$\frac{125}{49995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 9995}$$

$$\frac{125}{499995} := \frac{1 \times 25}{4 + 99995}$$

$$240. \quad \frac{125}{625} := \frac{1+2+5}{(6+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{125}{6250} := \frac{1+2+5}{(6+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{125}{62500} := \frac{1+2+5}{(6+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{125}{625000} := \frac{1+2+5}{(6+2) \times 5000}$$

$$241. \quad \frac{125}{825} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8+25}$$

$$\frac{125}{8325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8+325}$$

$$\frac{125}{83325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8+3325}$$

$$\frac{125}{833325} := \frac{1^2 \times 5}{8+33325}$$

$$242. \quad \frac{126}{1008} := \frac{1^{26}}{1 \times 008}$$

$$\frac{126}{10080} := \frac{1^{26}}{1 \times 0080}$$

$$\frac{126}{100800} := \frac{1^{26}}{1 \times 00800}$$

$$\frac{126}{1008000} := \frac{1^{26}}{1 \times 008000}$$

$$243. \quad \frac{126}{1050} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{126}{10500} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{126}{105000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 05000}$$

$$\frac{126}{1050000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 050000}$$

$$244. \quad \frac{126}{1152} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+1)^5 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{126}{11520} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+1)^5 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{126}{115200} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+1)^5 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{126}{1152000} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}$$

$$245. \quad \frac{126}{1155} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 55}$$

$$\frac{126}{11550} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 550}$$

$$\frac{126}{115500} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}$$

$$\frac{126}{1155000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}$$

$$246. \quad \frac{126}{1176} := \frac{1+2+6}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{126}{11760} := \frac{1+2+6}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{126}{117600} := \frac{1+2+6}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{126}{1176000} := \frac{1+2+6}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 6000}$$

$$247. \quad \frac{126}{1260} := \frac{1 \times 26}{1 \times 260}$$

$$\frac{126}{12600} := \frac{1 \times 26}{1 \times 2600}$$

$$\frac{126}{126000} := \frac{1 \times 26}{1 \times 26000}$$

$$\frac{126}{1260000} := \frac{1 \times 26}{1 \times 260000}$$

$$248. \quad \frac{126}{1296} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+2+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{126}{12960} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+2+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{126}{129600} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+2+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{126}{1296000} := \frac{1^2+6}{(1+2+9) \times 6000}$$

$$249. \quad \frac{126}{1302} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+30) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{126}{13020} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+30) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{126}{130200} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+30) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{126}{1302000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+30) \times 2000}$$

$$250. \quad \frac{126}{1344} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{126}{13440} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{126}{134400} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{126}{1344000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$254. \quad \frac{126}{147} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^4 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{126}{1470} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{126}{14700} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{126}{147000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$258. \quad \frac{126}{216} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{2 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{126}{2160} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{2 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{126}{21600} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{2 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{126}{216000} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{2 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$251. \quad \frac{126}{1365} := \frac{12 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{126}{13650} := \frac{12 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{126}{136500} := \frac{12 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{126}{1365000} := \frac{12 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}$$

$$255. \quad \frac{126}{168} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{126}{1680} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{126}{16800} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{126}{168000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^6 \times 8000}$$

$$259. \quad \frac{126}{224} := \frac{1 + 26}{2 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{126}{2240} := \frac{1 + 26}{2 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{126}{22400} := \frac{1 + 26}{2 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{126}{224000} := \frac{1 + 26}{2 \times 24000}$$

$$252. \quad \frac{126}{1386} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{126}{13860} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{126}{138600} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{126}{1386000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$256. \quad \frac{126}{189} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{126}{1890} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{126}{18900} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{126}{189000} := \frac{1^2 \times 6}{1^8 \times 9000}$$

$$260. \quad \frac{126}{231} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 31}$$

$$\frac{126}{2331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 331}$$

$$\frac{126}{23331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 3331}$$

$$\frac{126}{233331} := \frac{12 + 6}{2 + 33331}$$

$$253. \quad \frac{126}{1428} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(1 + 4^2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{126}{14280} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(1 + 4^2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{126}{142800} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(1 + 4^2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{126}{1428000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(1 + 4^2) \times 8000}$$

$$257. \quad \frac{126}{210} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{126}{2100} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{126}{21000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{2 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{126}{210000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{2 \times 10000}$$

$$261. \quad \frac{126}{252} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{(2 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{126}{2520} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{(2 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{126}{25200} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{(2 + 5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{126}{252000} := \frac{1^2 + 6}{(2 + 5) \times 2000}$$

$$262. \quad \frac{126}{280} := \frac{12 \times 6}{2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{126}{2800} := \frac{12 \times 6}{2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{126}{28000} := \frac{12 \times 6}{2 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{126}{280000} := \frac{12 \times 6}{2 \times 80000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 263. \quad & \frac{126}{315} := \frac{12+6}{3 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{126}{3150} := \frac{12+6}{3 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{126}{31500} := \frac{12+6}{3 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{126}{315000} := \frac{12+6}{3 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 268. \quad & \frac{126}{693} := \frac{12+6}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{126}{6993} := \frac{12+6}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{126}{69993} := \frac{12+6}{6+9993} \\
 & \frac{126}{699993} := \frac{12+6}{6+99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 273. \quad & \frac{127}{254} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(2+5) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{127}{2540} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(2+5) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{127}{25400} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(2+5) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{127}{254000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(2+5) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 264. \quad & \frac{126}{432} := \frac{1^2+6}{4 \times 3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{126}{4320} := \frac{1^2+6}{4 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{126}{43200} := \frac{1^2+6}{4 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{126}{432000} := \frac{1^2+6}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 269. \quad & \frac{126}{735} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{126}{7350} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{126}{73500} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{126}{735000} := \frac{12+6}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 274. \quad & \frac{127}{381} := \frac{1^2+7}{3 \times 8 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{127}{3810} := \frac{1^2+7}{3 \times 8 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{127}{38100} := \frac{1^2+7}{3 \times 8 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{127}{381000} := \frac{1^2+7}{3 \times 8 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 265. \quad & \frac{126}{448} := \frac{12+6}{(4+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{126}{4480} := \frac{12+6}{(4+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{126}{44800} := \frac{12+6}{(4+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{126}{448000} := \frac{12+6}{(4+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 270. \quad & \frac{126}{756} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(7+5) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{126}{7560} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(7+5) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{126}{75600} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(7+5) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{126}{756000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{(7+5) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 275. \quad & \frac{127}{508} := \frac{1+2+7}{5 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{127}{5080} := \frac{1+2+7}{5 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{127}{50800} := \frac{1+2+7}{5 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{127}{508000} := \frac{1+2+7}{5 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 266. \quad & \frac{126}{462} := \frac{12+6}{4+62} \\
 & \frac{126}{4662} := \frac{12+6}{4+662} \\
 & \frac{126}{46662} := \frac{12+6}{4+6662} \\
 & \frac{126}{466662} := \frac{12+6}{4+66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 271. \quad & \frac{127}{1270} := \frac{12 \times 7}{12 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{127}{12700} := \frac{12 \times 7}{12 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{127}{127000} := \frac{12 \times 7}{12 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{127}{1270000} := \frac{12 \times 7}{12 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 276. \quad & \frac{127}{635} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{127}{6350} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{127}{63500} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{127}{635000} := \frac{1 \times (2+7)}{(6+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 267. \quad & \frac{126}{525} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{5 \times 2 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{126}{5250} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{5 \times 2 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{126}{52500} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{5 \times 2 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{126}{525000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6}{5 \times 2 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 272. \quad & \frac{127}{1397} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(13+9) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{127}{13970} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(13+9) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{127}{139700} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(13+9) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{127}{1397000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{(13+9) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$277. \quad \frac{127}{762} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{7 \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{127}{7620} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{7 \times 6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{127}{76200} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{7 \times 6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{127}{762000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 7}{7 \times 6 \times 2000}$$

$$282. \quad \frac{128}{256} := \frac{12 \times 8}{2^5 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{128}{2560} := \frac{12 \times 8}{2^5 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{128}{25600} := \frac{12 \times 8}{2^5 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{128}{256000} := \frac{12 \times 8}{2^5 \times 6000}$$

$$287. \quad \frac{128}{792} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 92}$$

$$\frac{128}{7992} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 992}$$

$$\frac{128}{79992} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 9992}$$

$$\frac{128}{799992} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{7 + 99992}$$

$$278. \quad \frac{128}{1024} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 8}{10 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{128}{10240} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 8}{10 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{128}{102400} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 8}{10 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{128}{1024000} := \frac{1 \times 2 + 8}{10 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$283. \quad \frac{128}{320} := \frac{(1+2) \times 8}{3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{128}{3200} := \frac{(1+2) \times 8}{3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{128}{32000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 8}{3 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{128}{320000} := \frac{(1+2) \times 8}{3 \times 20000}$$

$$288. \quad \frac{129}{1032} := \frac{1^{29}}{(1+03) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{129}{10320} := \frac{1^{29}}{(1+03) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{129}{103200} := \frac{1^{29}}{(1+03) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{129}{1032000} := \frac{1^{29}}{(1+03) \times 2000}$$

$$279. \quad \frac{128}{1056} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 56}$$

$$\frac{128}{10656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 656}$$

$$\frac{128}{106656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 6656}$$

$$\frac{128}{1066656} := \frac{1^2 \times 8}{10 + 66656}$$

$$284. \quad \frac{128}{352} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 52}$$

$$\frac{128}{3552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 552}$$

$$\frac{128}{35552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 5552}$$

$$\frac{128}{355552} := \frac{12 + 8}{3 + 55552}$$

$$289. \quad \frac{129}{1075} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{1 \times 075}$$

$$\frac{129}{10750} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{1 \times 0750}$$

$$\frac{129}{107500} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{1 \times 07500}$$

$$\frac{129}{1075000} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{1 \times 075000}$$

$$280. \quad \frac{128}{1280} := \frac{12 \times 8}{12 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{128}{12800} := \frac{12 \times 8}{12 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{128}{128000} := \frac{12 \times 8}{12 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{128}{1280000} := \frac{12 \times 8}{12 \times 80000}$$

$$285. \quad \frac{128}{672} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{128}{6720} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{128}{67200} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{128}{672000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$290. \quad \frac{129}{1204} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(1+20) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{129}{12040} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(1+20) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{129}{120400} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(1+20) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{129}{1204000} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(1+20) \times 4000}$$

$$281. \quad \frac{128}{1296} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{128}{12960} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{128}{129600} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{128}{1296000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$286. \quad \frac{128}{784} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{128}{7840} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{128}{78400} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{128}{784000} := \frac{12 \times 8}{7 \times 84000}$$

$$291. \quad \frac{129}{1290} := \frac{12 \times 9}{12 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{129}{12900} := \frac{12 \times 9}{12 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{129}{129000} := \frac{12 \times 9}{12 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{129}{1290000} := \frac{12 \times 9}{12 \times 90000}$$

$$292. \quad \frac{129}{172} := \frac{1+2+9}{(1+7) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{129}{1720} := \frac{1+2+9}{(1+7) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{129}{17200} := \frac{1+2+9}{(1+7) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{129}{172000} := \frac{1+2+9}{(1+7) \times 2000}$$

$$293. \quad \frac{129}{215} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{2 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{129}{2150} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{2 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{129}{21500} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{2 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{129}{215000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{2 \times 15000}$$

$$294. \quad \frac{129}{2580} := \frac{1^2+9}{25 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{129}{25800} := \frac{1^2+9}{25 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{129}{258000} := \frac{1^2+9}{25 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{129}{2580000} := \frac{1^2+9}{25 \times 8000+0}$$

$$295. \quad \frac{129}{344} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{129}{3440} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{129}{34400} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{129}{344000} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 9}{3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$296. \quad \frac{129}{473} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4+7) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{129}{4730} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4+7) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{129}{47300} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4+7) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{129}{473000} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(4+7) \times 3000}$$

$$297. \quad \frac{129}{473} := \frac{12+9}{4+73}$$

$$\frac{129}{4773} := \frac{12+9}{4+773}$$

$$\frac{129}{47773} := \frac{12+9}{4+7773}$$

$$\frac{129}{477773} := \frac{12+9}{4+77773}$$

$$298. \quad \frac{129}{516} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(5+1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{129}{5160} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(5+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{129}{51600} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(5+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{129}{516000} := \frac{1^2 \times 9}{(5+1) \times 6000}$$

$$299. \quad \frac{129}{645} := \frac{1^2+9}{(6+4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{129}{6450} := \frac{1^2+9}{(6+4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{129}{64500} := \frac{1^2+9}{(6+4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{129}{645000} := \frac{1^2+9}{(6+4) \times 5000}$$

$$300. \quad \frac{129}{688} := \frac{12+9}{(6+8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{129}{6880} := \frac{12+9}{(6+8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{129}{68800} := \frac{12+9}{(6+8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{129}{688000} := \frac{12+9}{(6+8) \times 8000}$$

$$301. \quad \frac{130}{1365} := \frac{1+3+0}{1+36+5}$$

$$\frac{130}{14365} := \frac{1+3+0}{1+436+5}$$

$$\frac{130}{144365} := \frac{1+3+0}{1+4436+5}$$

$$\frac{130}{1444365} := \frac{1+3+0}{1+44436+5}$$

$$302. \quad \frac{131}{1048} := \frac{1+3+1}{(1+04) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{131}{10480} := \frac{1+3+1}{(1+04) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{131}{104800} := \frac{1+3+1}{(1+04) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{131}{1048000} := \frac{1+3+1}{(1+04) \times 8000}$$

$$303. \quad \frac{131}{1179} := \frac{13+1}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{131}{11790} := \frac{13+1}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{131}{117900} := \frac{13+1}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{131}{1179000} := \frac{13+1}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9000}$$

$$304. \quad \frac{131}{1310} := \frac{13 \times 1}{13 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{131}{13100} := \frac{13 \times 1}{13 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{131}{131000} := \frac{13 \times 1}{13 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{131}{1310000} := \frac{13 \times 1}{13 \times 10000}$$

$$305. \quad \frac{131}{1441} := \frac{1+3 \times 1}{1 \times 44 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{131}{14410} := \frac{1+3 \times 1}{1 \times 44 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{131}{144100} := \frac{1+3 \times 1}{1 \times 44 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{131}{1441000} := \frac{1+3 \times 1}{1 \times 44 \times 1000}$$

$$310. \quad \frac{132}{1320} := \frac{1 \times 32}{1 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{132}{13200} := \frac{1 \times 32}{1 \times 3200}$$

$$\frac{132}{132000} := \frac{1 \times 32}{1 \times 32000}$$

$$315. \quad \frac{132}{264} := \frac{1+32}{2+64}$$

$$\frac{132}{2664} := \frac{1+32}{2+664}$$

$$\frac{132}{26664} := \frac{1+32}{2+6664}$$

$$306. \quad \frac{131}{5240} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{5 \times 24 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{52400} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{5 \times 240 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{524000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{5 \times 2400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{5240000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{5 \times 24000 + 0}$$

$$311. \quad \frac{132}{1332} := \frac{1+32}{1+332}$$

$$\frac{132}{13332} := \frac{1+32}{1+3332}$$

$$\frac{132}{133332} := \frac{1+32}{1+33332}$$

$$\frac{132}{1333332} := \frac{1+32}{1+333332}$$

$$316. \quad \frac{132}{352} := \frac{1+3+2}{(3+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{132}{3520} := \frac{1+3+2}{(3+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{132}{35200} := \frac{1+3+2}{(3+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{132}{352000} := \frac{1+3+2}{(3+5) \times 2000}$$

$$307. \quad \frac{131}{6550} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{6 \times 5 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{65500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{6 \times 5 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{655000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{6 \times 5 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{6550000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 1}{6 \times 5 \times 5000 + 0}$$

$$312. \quad \frac{132}{1408} := \frac{1^3+2}{1 \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{132}{14080} := \frac{1^3+2}{1 \times 4 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{132}{140800} := \frac{1^3+2}{1 \times 4 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{132}{1408000} := \frac{1^3+2}{1 \times 4 \times 08000}$$

$$317. \quad \frac{132}{384} := \frac{1+32}{3 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{132}{3840} := \frac{1+32}{3 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{132}{38400} := \frac{1+32}{3 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{132}{384000} := \frac{1+32}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$308. \quad \frac{131}{9170} := \frac{1^3 \times 1}{(9+1) \times 7 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{91700} := \frac{1^3 \times 1}{(9+1) \times 70 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{917000} := \frac{1^3 \times 1}{(9+1) \times 700 + 0}$$

$$\frac{131}{9170000} := \frac{1^3 \times 1}{(9+1) \times 7000 + 0}$$

$$313. \quad \frac{132}{1452} := \frac{1+3+2}{14+52}$$

$$\frac{132}{14652} := \frac{1+3+2}{14+652}$$

$$\frac{132}{146652} := \frac{1+3+2}{14+6652}$$

$$\frac{132}{1466652} := \frac{1+3+2}{14+66652}$$

$$309. \quad \frac{132}{1188} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{1 \times 18 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{132}{11880} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{1 \times 18 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{132}{118800} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{1 \times 18 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{132}{1188000} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{1 \times 18 \times 8000}$$

$$314. \quad \frac{132}{264} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(2+6) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{132}{2640} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(2+6) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{132}{26400} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(2+6) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{132}{264000} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(2+6) \times 4000}$$

$$318. \quad \frac{132}{396} := \frac{1+32}{3+96}$$

$$\frac{132}{3996} := \frac{1+32}{3+996}$$

$$\frac{132}{39996} := \frac{1+32}{3+9996}$$

$$\frac{132}{399996} := \frac{1+32}{3+99996}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 319. \quad & \frac{132}{5280} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 2}{5^2 \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{52800} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 2}{5^2 \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{528000} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 2}{5^2 \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{5280000} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 2}{5^2 \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 324. \quad & \frac{132}{858} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{8 \times (5+8)} \\
 & \frac{132}{8580} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(8+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{132}{85800} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(8+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{132}{858000} := \frac{(1+3)^2}{(8+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 328. \quad & \frac{133}{1368} := \frac{1+3^3}{1 \times 36 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{133}{13680} := \frac{1+3^3}{1 \times 36 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{133}{136800} := \frac{1+3^3}{1 \times 36 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{133}{1368000} := \frac{1+3^3}{1 \times 36 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 320. \quad & \frac{132}{550} := \frac{1+3+2}{5 \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{5500} := \frac{1+3+2}{5 \times 50 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{55000} := \frac{1+3+2}{5 \times 500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{132}{550000} := \frac{1+3+2}{5 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 325. \quad & \frac{133}{1045} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{133}{10545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{133}{105545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{133}{1055545} := \frac{1+3+3}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 329. \quad & \frac{133}{1463} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{(1+4+6) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{133}{14630} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{(1+4+6) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{133}{146300} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{(1+4+6) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{133}{1463000} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{(1+4+6) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 321. \quad & \frac{132}{616} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(6+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{132}{6160} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(6+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{132}{61600} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(6+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{132}{616000} := \frac{1 \times 3^2}{(6+1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 326. \quad & \frac{133}{1064} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{1 \times 06 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{133}{10640} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{1 \times 06 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{133}{106400} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{1 \times 06 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{133}{1064000} := \frac{1^3 \times 3}{1 \times 06 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 330. \quad & \frac{133}{1463} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{133}{14763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{133}{147763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{133}{1477763} := \frac{1+3+3}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 322. \quad & \frac{132}{726} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+26} \\
 & \frac{132}{7326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+326} \\
 & \frac{132}{73326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+3326} \\
 & \frac{132}{733326} := \frac{1+3+2}{7+33326}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 327. \quad & \frac{133}{1330} := \frac{13 \times 3}{13 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{133}{13300} := \frac{13 \times 3}{13 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{133}{133000} := \frac{13 \times 3}{13 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{133}{1330000} := \frac{13 \times 3}{13 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 331. \quad & \frac{133}{209} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+09} \\
 & \frac{133}{2109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+109} \\
 & \frac{133}{21109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+1109} \\
 & \frac{133}{211109} := \frac{1+3+3}{2+11109}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 323. \quad & \frac{132}{825} := \frac{1 \times 32}{8 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{132}{8250} := \frac{1 \times 32}{8 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{132}{82500} := \frac{1 \times 32}{8 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{132}{825000} := \frac{1 \times 32}{8 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 332. \quad & \frac{133}{418} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+18} \\
 & \frac{133}{4218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+218} \\
 & \frac{133}{42218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+2218} \\
 & \frac{133}{422218} := \frac{1+3+3}{4+22218}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 333. \quad & \frac{133}{532} := \frac{1^3 + 3}{(5+3) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{133}{5320} := \frac{1^3 + 3}{(5+3) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{133}{53200} := \frac{1^3 + 3}{(5+3) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{133}{532000} := \frac{1^3 + 3}{(5+3) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 338. \quad & \frac{134}{1340} := \frac{13 \times 4}{13 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{134}{13400} := \frac{13 \times 4}{13 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{134}{134000} := \frac{13 \times 4}{13 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{134}{1340000} := \frac{13 \times 4}{13 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 342. \quad & \frac{134}{536} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(5+3) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{134}{5360} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(5+3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{134}{53600} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(5+3) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{134}{536000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(5+3) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 334. \quad & \frac{133}{627} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{133}{6327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{133}{63327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{133}{633327} := \frac{1+3+3}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 339. \quad & \frac{134}{1474} := \frac{1^3 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{134}{14740} := \frac{1^3 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{134}{147400} := \frac{1^3 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{134}{1474000} := \frac{1^3 \times 4}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 343. \quad & \frac{134}{737} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+37} \\
 & \frac{134}{7437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+437} \\
 & \frac{134}{74437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+4437} \\
 & \frac{134}{744437} := \frac{1+3+4}{7+44437}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 335. \quad & \frac{133}{665} := \frac{(1+3) \times 3}{(6+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{133}{6650} := \frac{(1+3) \times 3}{(6+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{133}{66500} := \frac{(1+3) \times 3}{(6+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{133}{665000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 3}{(6+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 340. \quad & \frac{134}{268} := \frac{(1+3)^4}{2^6 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{134}{2680} := \frac{(1+3)^4}{2^6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{134}{26800} := \frac{(1+3)^4}{2^6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{134}{268000} := \frac{(1+3)^4}{2^6 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 344. \quad & \frac{135}{1080} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 08 + 0} \\
 & \frac{135}{10800} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 080 + 0} \\
 & \frac{135}{108000} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 0800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{135}{1080000} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 08000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 336. \quad & \frac{133}{836} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+36} \\
 & \frac{133}{8436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+436} \\
 & \frac{133}{84436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+4436} \\
 & \frac{133}{844436} := \frac{1+3+3}{8+44436}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 341. \quad & \frac{134}{335} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(3+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{134}{3350} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(3+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{134}{33500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(3+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{134}{335000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4}{(3+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 345. \quad & \frac{135}{1125} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{135}{11250} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{135}{112500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{135}{1125000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 337. \quad & \frac{134}{1206} := \frac{1+3+4}{12 \times 06} \\
 & \frac{134}{12060} := \frac{1+3+4}{12 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{134}{120600} := \frac{1+3+4}{12 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{134}{1206000} := \frac{1+3+4}{12 \times 06000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 346. \quad & \frac{135}{1188} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(1+1) \times 88} \\
 & \frac{135}{11880} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(1+1) \times 880} \\
 & \frac{135}{118800} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(1+1) \times 8800} \\
 & \frac{135}{1188000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(1+1) \times 88000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 347. \quad & \frac{135}{1215} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{12 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{135}{12150} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{12 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{135}{121500} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{12 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{135}{1215000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{12 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 348. \quad & \frac{135}{1296} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{135}{12960} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{135}{129600} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{135}{1296000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 349. \quad & \frac{135}{1350} := \frac{13 \times 5}{13 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{135}{13500} := \frac{13 \times 5}{13 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{135}{135000} := \frac{13 \times 5}{13 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{135}{1350000} := \frac{13 \times 5}{13 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 350. \quad & \frac{135}{144} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{135}{1440} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{135}{14400} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{135}{144000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 351. \quad & \frac{135}{1470} := \frac{1+3+5}{14 \times 7+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{14700} := \frac{1+3+5}{14 \times 70+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{147000} := \frac{1+3+5}{14 \times 700+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{1470000} := \frac{1+3+5}{14 \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 352. \quad & \frac{135}{1485} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{135}{14850} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{135}{148500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{135}{1485000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 353. \quad & \frac{135}{1485} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+85} \\
 & \frac{135}{14985} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+985} \\
 & \frac{135}{149985} := \frac{1+3+5}{14+9985}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 354. \quad & \frac{135}{1620} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 6 \times 2+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{16200} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 6 \times 20+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{162000} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 6 \times 200+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{1620000} := \frac{1^{35}}{1 \times 6 \times 2000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 355. \quad & \frac{135}{1665} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+6 \times 6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{135}{16650} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+6 \times 6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{135}{166500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+6 \times 6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{135}{1665000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+6 \times 6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 356. \quad & \frac{135}{180} := \frac{1^3+5}{1 \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{1800} := \frac{1^3+5}{1 \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{18000} := \frac{1^3+5}{1 \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{180000} := \frac{1^3+5}{1 \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 357. \quad & \frac{135}{1815} := \frac{1+3+5}{1+8 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{135}{18015} := \frac{1+3+5}{1+80 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{135}{180015} := \frac{1+3+5}{1+800 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{135}{1800015} := \frac{1+3+5}{1+8000 \times 15}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 358. \quad & \frac{135}{216} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{2 \times 16} \\
 & \frac{135}{2160} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{2 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{135}{21600} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{2 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{135}{216000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{2 \times 16000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 359. \quad & \frac{135}{2880} := \frac{1^3+5}{2 \times 8 \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{28800} := \frac{1^3+5}{2 \times 8 \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{288000} := \frac{1^3+5}{2 \times 8 \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{135}{2880000} := \frac{1^3+5}{2 \times 8 \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 360. \quad & \frac{135}{297} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{135}{2970} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{135}{29700} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{135}{297000} := \frac{1 \times 35}{(2+9) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$361. \quad \frac{135}{324} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{3^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{135}{3240} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{3^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{135}{32400} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{3^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{135}{324000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{3^2 \times 4000}$$

$$362. \quad \frac{135}{375} := \frac{13+5}{(3+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{135}{3750} := \frac{13+5}{(3+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{135}{37500} := \frac{13+5}{(3+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{135}{375000} := \frac{13+5}{(3+7) \times 5000}$$

$$363. \quad \frac{135}{450} := \frac{1^3+5}{4 \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{4500} := \frac{1^3+5}{4 \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{45000} := \frac{1^3+5}{4 \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{450000} := \frac{1^3+5}{4 \times 5000+0}$$

$$364. \quad \frac{135}{480} := \frac{1+3+5}{4 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{4800} := \frac{1+3+5}{4 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{48000} := \frac{1+3+5}{4 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{480000} := \frac{1+3+5}{4 \times 8000+0}$$

$$365. \quad \frac{135}{486} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{135}{4860} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{135}{48600} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{135}{486000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 5}{(4+8) \times 6000}$$

$$366. \quad \frac{135}{525} := \frac{1+3+5}{(5+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{135}{5250} := \frac{1+3+5}{(5+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{135}{52500} := \frac{1+3+5}{(5+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{135}{525000} := \frac{1+3+5}{(5+2) \times 5000}$$

$$367. \quad \frac{135}{540} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 4+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{5400} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 40+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{54000} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 400+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{540000} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 4000+0}$$

$$368. \quad \frac{135}{5670} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 6 \times 7+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{56700} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 6 \times 70+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{567000} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 6 \times 700+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{5670000} := \frac{1^3 \times 5}{5 \times 6 \times 7000+0}$$

$$369. \quad \frac{135}{585} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(5+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{135}{5850} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(5+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{135}{58500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(5+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{135}{585000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(5+8) \times 5000}$$

$$370. \quad \frac{135}{6480} := \frac{1^3+5}{6 \times 48+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{64800} := \frac{1^3+5}{6 \times 480+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{648000} := \frac{1^3+5}{6 \times 4800+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{6480000} := \frac{1^3+5}{6 \times 48000+0}$$

$$371. \quad \frac{135}{729} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7+2) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{135}{7290} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7+2) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{135}{72900} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7+2) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{135}{729000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{(7+2) \times 9000}$$

$$372. \quad \frac{135}{8640} := \frac{1 \times 3+5}{8 \times 64+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{86400} := \frac{1 \times 3+5}{8 \times 640+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{864000} := \frac{1 \times 3+5}{8 \times 6400+0}$$

$$\frac{135}{8640000} := \frac{1 \times 3+5}{8 \times 64000+0}$$

$$373. \quad \frac{135}{891} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+91}$$

$$\frac{135}{8991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+991}$$

$$\frac{135}{89991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+9991}$$

$$\frac{135}{899991} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 5}{8+99991}$$

$$374. \quad \frac{136}{1088} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6}{(10+8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{136}{10880} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6}{(10+8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{136}{108800} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6}{(10+8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{136}{1088000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6}{(10+8) \times 8000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 375. \quad & \frac{136}{1275} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 75} \\
 & \frac{136}{12750} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 750} \\
 & \frac{136}{127500} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{136}{1275000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 380. \quad & \frac{136}{544} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(5+4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{136}{5440} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(5+4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{136}{54400} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(5+4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{136}{544000} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(5+4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 385. \quad & \frac{137}{274} := \frac{(1+3) \times 7}{2 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{137}{2740} := \frac{(1+3) \times 7}{2 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{137}{27400} := \frac{(1+3) \times 7}{2 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{137}{274000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 7}{2 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 376. \quad & \frac{136}{1360} := \frac{13 \times 6}{13 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{136}{13600} := \frac{13 \times 6}{13 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{136}{136000} := \frac{13 \times 6}{13 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{136}{1360000} := \frac{13 \times 6}{13 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 381. \quad & \frac{136}{748} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+48} \\
 & \frac{136}{7548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+548} \\
 & \frac{136}{75548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+5548} \\
 & \frac{136}{755548} := \frac{1+3+6}{7+55548}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 386. \quad & \frac{138}{1104} := \frac{1^{38}}{(1+1) \times 04} \\
 & \frac{138}{11040} := \frac{1^{38}}{(1+1) \times 040} \\
 & \frac{138}{110400} := \frac{1^{38}}{(1+1) \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{138}{1104000} := \frac{1^{38}}{(1+1) \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 377. \quad & \frac{136}{1479} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{136}{14790} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{136}{147900} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{136}{1479000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 382. \quad & \frac{136}{816} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(8+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{136}{8160} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(8+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{136}{81600} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(8+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{136}{816000} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(8+1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 387. \quad & \frac{138}{1150} := \frac{1+(3+8)}{(1+1) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{138}{11500} := \frac{1+(3+8)}{(1+1) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{138}{115000} := \frac{1+(3+8)}{(1+1) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{138}{1150000} := \frac{1+(3+8)}{(1+1) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 378. \quad & \frac{136}{272} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(2+7) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{136}{2720} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(2+7) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{136}{27200} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(2+7) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{136}{272000} := \frac{1 \times 3 + 6}{(2+7) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 383. \quad & \frac{136}{918} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{9 \times 18} \\
 & \frac{136}{9180} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{9 \times 180} \\
 & \frac{136}{91800} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{9 \times 1800} \\
 & \frac{136}{918000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{9 \times 18000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 379. \quad & \frac{136}{459} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(4+5) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{136}{4590} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(4+5) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{136}{45900} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(4+5) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{136}{459000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 6}{(4+5) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 384. \quad & \frac{137}{1370} := \frac{13 \times 7}{13 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{137}{13700} := \frac{13 \times 7}{13 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{137}{137000} := \frac{13 \times 7}{13 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{137}{1370000} := \frac{13 \times 7}{13 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 388. \quad & \frac{138}{1288} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 28 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{138}{12880} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 28 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{138}{128800} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 28 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{138}{1288000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 28 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 389. \quad & \frac{138}{1380} := \frac{13 \times 8}{13 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{138}{13800} := \frac{13 \times 8}{13 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{138}{138000} := \frac{13 \times 8}{13 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{138}{1380000} := \frac{13 \times 8}{13 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 390. \quad & \frac{138}{1472} := \frac{1^3 + 8}{(1+47) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{138}{14720} := \frac{1^3 + 8}{(1+47) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{138}{147200} := \frac{1^3 + 8}{(1+47) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{138}{1472000} := \frac{1^3 + 8}{(1+47) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 391. \quad & \frac{138}{184} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{138}{1840} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{138}{18400} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{138}{184000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 392. \quad & \frac{138}{345} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{3 \times 4 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{138}{3450} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{3 \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{138}{34500} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{3 \times 4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{138}{345000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 8}{3 \times 4 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 393. \quad & \frac{138}{621} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{6^2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{138}{6210} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{6^2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{138}{62100} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{6^2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{138}{621000} := \frac{1^3 \times 8}{6^2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 394. \quad & \frac{139}{1251} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{(1+2)^5 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{139}{12510} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{(1+2)^5 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{139}{125100} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{(1+2)^5 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{139}{1251000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{(1+2)^5 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 395. \quad & \frac{139}{1390} := \frac{13 \times 9}{13 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{139}{13900} := \frac{13 \times 9}{13 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{139}{139000} := \frac{13 \times 9}{13 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{139}{1390000} := \frac{13 \times 9}{13 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 396. \quad & \frac{139}{1529} := \frac{1^3 \times 9}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{139}{15290} := \frac{1^3 \times 9}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{139}{152900} := \frac{1^3 \times 9}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{139}{1529000} := \frac{1^3 \times 9}{(1+5 \times 2) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 397. \quad & \frac{139}{278} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{139}{2780} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{139}{27800} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{139}{278000} := \frac{(1+3) \times 9}{(2+7) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 398. \quad & \frac{139}{973} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{9 \times 7 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{139}{9730} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{9 \times 7 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{139}{97300} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{9 \times 7 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{139}{973000} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 9}{9 \times 7 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 399. \quad & \frac{140}{1232} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+32} \\
 & \frac{140}{12432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+432} \\
 & \frac{140}{124432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+4432} \\
 & \frac{140}{1244432} := \frac{1+4+0}{12+44432}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 400. \quad & \frac{140}{308} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+08} \\
 & \frac{140}{3108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+108} \\
 & \frac{140}{31108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+1108} \\
 & \frac{140}{311108} := \frac{1+4+0}{3+11108}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 401. \quad & \frac{140}{616} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{140}{6216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{140}{62216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{140}{622216} := \frac{1+4+0}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 402. \quad & \frac{140}{924} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{140}{9324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{140}{93324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{140}{933324} := \frac{1+4+0}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$403. \quad \frac{141}{1034} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+34}$$

$$\frac{141}{10434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+434}$$

$$\frac{141}{104434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+4434}$$

$$\frac{141}{1044434} := \frac{1+4+1}{10+44434}$$

$$408. \quad \frac{141}{188} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{141}{1880} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{141}{18800} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{141}{188000} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^8 \times 8000}$$

$$413. \quad \frac{142}{1420} := \frac{14 \times 2}{14 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{142}{14200} := \frac{14 \times 2}{14 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{142}{142000} := \frac{14 \times 2}{14 \times 2000}$$

$$404. \quad \frac{141}{1128} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 1}{(1+1+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{141}{11280} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 1}{(1+1+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{141}{112800} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 1}{(1+1+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{141}{1128000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 1}{(1+1+2) \times 8000}$$

$$409. \quad \frac{141}{235} := \frac{1+41}{2 \times 35}$$

$$\frac{141}{2350} := \frac{1+41}{2 \times 350}$$

$$\frac{141}{23500} := \frac{1+41}{2 \times 3500}$$

$$\frac{141}{235000} := \frac{1+41}{2 \times 35000}$$

$$414. \quad \frac{142}{1562} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+62}$$

$$\frac{142}{15762} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+762}$$

$$\frac{142}{157762} := \frac{1+4+2}{15+7762}$$

$$405. \quad \frac{141}{1269} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{141}{12690} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{141}{126900} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{141}{1269000} := \frac{1+4+1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000}$$

$$410. \quad \frac{141}{517} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+17}$$

$$\frac{141}{5217} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+217}$$

$$\frac{141}{52217} := \frac{1+4+1}{5+2217}$$

$$415. \quad \frac{142}{213} := \frac{1 \times 42}{21 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{142}{2130} := \frac{1 \times 42}{21 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{142}{21300} := \frac{1 \times 42}{21 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{142}{213000} := \frac{1 \times 42}{21 \times 3000}$$

$$406. \quad \frac{141}{1410} := \frac{14 \times 1}{14 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{141}{14100} := \frac{14 \times 1}{14 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{141}{141000} := \frac{14 \times 1}{14 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{141}{1410000} := \frac{14 \times 1}{14 \times 10000}$$

$$411. \quad \frac{142}{1136} := \frac{1+4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 36}$$

$$\frac{142}{11360} := \frac{1+4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 360}$$

$$\frac{142}{113600} := \frac{1+4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 3600}$$

$$\frac{142}{1136000} := \frac{1+4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 36000}$$

$$416. \quad \frac{142}{2840} := \frac{1^4 \times 2}{(2+8) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{28400} := \frac{1^4 \times 2}{(2+8) \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{284000} := \frac{1^4 \times 2}{(2+8) \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{2840000} := \frac{1^4 \times 2}{(2+8) \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$407. \quad \frac{141}{1551} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+51}$$

$$\frac{141}{15651} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+651}$$

$$\frac{141}{156651} := \frac{1+4+1}{15+6651}$$

$$412. \quad \frac{142}{1278} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{142}{12780} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{142}{127800} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{142}{1278000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 2}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 8000}$$

$$417. \quad \frac{142}{355} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{(3+5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{142}{3550} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{(3+5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{142}{35500} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{(3+5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{142}{355000} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{(3+5) \times 5000}$$

$$418. \quad \frac{142}{426} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{4 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{142}{4260} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{4 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{142}{42600} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{4 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{142}{426000} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{4 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$423. \quad \frac{143}{1144} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{1 \times 14 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{143}{11440} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{1 \times 14 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{143}{114400} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{1 \times 14 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{143}{1144000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{1 \times 14 \times 4000}$$

$$428. \quad \frac{143}{1443} := \frac{1 + 43}{1 + 443}$$

$$\frac{143}{14443} := \frac{1 + 43}{1 + 4443}$$

$$\frac{143}{144443} := \frac{1 + 43}{1 + 44443}$$

$$\frac{143}{1444443} := \frac{1 + 43}{1 + 444443}$$

$$419. \quad \frac{142}{5680} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 2}{5 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{56800} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 2}{5 \times 6 \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{568000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 2}{5 \times 6 \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{142}{5680000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 2}{5 \times 6 \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$424. \quad \frac{143}{1248} := \frac{1 + 43}{12 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{143}{12480} := \frac{1 + 43}{12 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{143}{124800} := \frac{1 + 43}{12 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{143}{1248000} := \frac{1 + 43}{12 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$429. \quad \frac{143}{1573} := \frac{1 + 4 + 3}{15 + 73}$$

$$\frac{143}{15873} := \frac{1 + 4 + 3}{15 + 873}$$

$$\frac{143}{158873} := \frac{1 + 4 + 3}{15 + 8873}$$

$$\frac{143}{1588873} := \frac{1 + 4 + 3}{15 + 88873}$$

$$420. \quad \frac{142}{781} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7 + 81}$$

$$\frac{142}{7881} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7 + 881}$$

$$\frac{142}{78881} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7 + 8881}$$

$$\frac{142}{788881} := \frac{1 \times 4^2}{7 + 88881}$$

$$425. \quad \frac{143}{1287} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{(1^2 + 8) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{143}{12870} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{(1^2 + 8) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{143}{128700} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{(1^2 + 8) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{143}{1287000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{(1^2 + 8) \times 7000}$$

$$430. \quad \frac{143}{2860} := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2 + 8) \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{143}{28600} := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2 + 8) \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{143}{286000} := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2 + 8) \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{143}{2860000} := \frac{1^4 \times 3}{(2 + 8) \times 6000 + 0}$$

$$421. \quad \frac{143}{1089} := \frac{1 + (4 \times 3)}{10 + 89}$$

$$\frac{143}{10989} := \frac{1 + (4 \times 3)}{10 + 989}$$

$$\frac{143}{109989} := \frac{1 + (4 \times 3)}{10 + 9989}$$

$$\frac{143}{1099989} := \frac{1 + (4 \times 3)}{10 + 99989}$$

$$426. \quad \frac{143}{1386} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{(13 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{143}{13860} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{(13 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{143}{138600} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{(13 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{143}{1386000} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{(13 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$431. \quad \frac{143}{286} := \frac{1 + 43}{2 + 86}$$

$$\frac{143}{2886} := \frac{1 + 43}{2 + 886}$$

$$\frac{143}{28886} := \frac{1 + 43}{2 + 8886}$$

$$\frac{143}{288886} := \frac{1 + 43}{2 + 88886}$$

$$422. \quad \frac{143}{1100} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{1 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{143}{11000} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{1 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{143}{110000} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{1 \times 10000}$$

$$\frac{143}{1100000} := \frac{1 + 4 \times 3}{1 \times 100000}$$

$$427. \quad \frac{143}{1430} := \frac{14 \times 3}{14 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{143}{14300} := \frac{14 \times 3}{14 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{143}{143000} := \frac{14 \times 3}{14 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{143}{1430000} := \frac{14 \times 3}{14 \times 30000}$$

$$432. \quad \frac{143}{550} := \frac{1+4^3}{5 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{143}{5500} := \frac{1+4^3}{5 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{143}{55000} := \frac{1+4^3}{5 \times 5000}$$

$$437. \quad \frac{144}{1280} := \frac{14+4}{1 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{144}{12800} := \frac{14+4}{1 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{144}{128000} := \frac{14+4}{1 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$442. \quad \frac{144}{1485} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{144}{14850} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{144}{148500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$433. \quad \frac{143}{715} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{7 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{143}{7150} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{7 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{143}{71500} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 3}{7 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$438. \quad \frac{144}{1296} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(1+2+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{144}{12960} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(1+2+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{144}{129600} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(1+2+9) \times 600}$$

$$443. \quad \frac{144}{1782} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17+82}$$

$$\frac{144}{17982} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17+982}$$

$$\frac{144}{179982} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{17+9982}$$

$$434. \quad \frac{143}{832} := \frac{1+43}{8 \times 32}$$

$$\frac{143}{8320} := \frac{1+43}{8 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{143}{83200} := \frac{1+43}{8 \times 3200}$$

$$439. \quad \frac{144}{1350} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{144}{13500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{144}{135000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$444. \quad \frac{144}{216} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{2 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{144}{2160} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{2 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{144}{21600} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{2 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$435. \quad \frac{144}{1056} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+56}$$

$$\frac{144}{10656} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+656}$$

$$\frac{144}{106656} := \frac{1+4+4}{10+6656}$$

$$440. \quad \frac{144}{1368} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{144}{13680} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{144}{136800} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$445. \quad \frac{144}{252} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(2+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{144}{2520} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(2+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{144}{25200} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{(2+5) \times 200}$$

$$436. \quad \frac{144}{1152} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(1+15) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{144}{11520} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(1+15) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{144}{115200} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(1+15) \times 200}$$

$$441. \quad \frac{144}{1440} := \frac{1 \times 44}{1 \times 440}$$

$$\frac{144}{14400} := \frac{1 \times 44}{1 \times 4400}$$

$$\frac{144}{144000} := \frac{1 \times 44}{1 \times 44000}$$

$$446. \quad \frac{144}{2880} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(2+8) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{144}{28800} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(2+8) \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{144}{288000} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(2+8) \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{144}{2880000} := \frac{1^4 \times 4}{(2+8) \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$451. \quad \frac{144}{672} := \frac{14+4}{6 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{144}{6720} := \frac{14+4}{6 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{144}{67200} := \frac{14+4}{6 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{144}{672000} := \frac{14+4}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$456. \quad \frac{145}{1218} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{145}{12180} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{145}{121800} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{145}{1218000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 8000}$$

$$447. \quad \frac{144}{324} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{3^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{144}{3240} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{3^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{144}{32400} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{3^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{144}{324000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{3^2 \times 4000}$$

$$452. \quad \frac{144}{729} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{144}{7290} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{144}{72900} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{144}{729000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 9000}$$

$$457. \quad \frac{145}{1421} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{14^2 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{145}{14210} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{14^2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{145}{142100} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{14^2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{145}{1421000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{14^2 \times 1000}$$

$$448. \quad \frac{144}{432} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{144}{4320} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{4 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{144}{43200} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{4 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{144}{432000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 4}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$453. \quad \frac{144}{792} := \frac{14+4}{7+92}$$

$$\frac{144}{7992} := \frac{14+4}{7+992}$$

$$\frac{144}{79992} := \frac{14+4}{7+9992}$$

$$\frac{144}{799992} := \frac{14+4}{7+99992}$$

$$458. \quad \frac{145}{1450} := \frac{14 \times 5}{14 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{145}{14500} := \frac{14 \times 5}{14 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{145}{145000} := \frac{14 \times 5}{14 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{145}{1450000} := \frac{14 \times 5}{14 \times 50000}$$

$$449. \quad \frac{144}{576} := \frac{14+4}{(5+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{144}{5760} := \frac{14+4}{(5+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{144}{57600} := \frac{14+4}{(5+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{144}{576000} := \frac{14+4}{(5+7) \times 6000}$$

$$454. \quad \frac{144}{891} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8+91}$$

$$\frac{144}{8991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8+991}$$

$$\frac{144}{89991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8+9991}$$

$$\frac{144}{899991} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{8+99991}$$

$$459. \quad \frac{145}{232} := \frac{1+4+5}{2^3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{145}{2320} := \frac{1+4+5}{2^3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{145}{23200} := \frac{1+4+5}{2^3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{145}{232000} := \frac{1+4+5}{2^3 \times 2000}$$

$$450. \quad \frac{144}{585} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(5+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{144}{5850} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(5+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{144}{58500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(5+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{144}{585000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4}{(5+8) \times 5000}$$

$$455. \quad \frac{145}{1160} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{145}{11600} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{145}{116000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 16000}$$

$$\frac{145}{1160000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 160000}$$

$$460. \quad \frac{145}{290} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 5}{2 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\frac{145}{2900} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 5}{2 \times 90 + 0}$$

$$\frac{145}{29000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 5}{2 \times 900 + 0}$$

$$\frac{145}{290000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 5}{2 \times 9000 + 0}$$

$$461. \quad \frac{145}{319} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+19}$$

$$\frac{145}{3219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+219}$$

$$\frac{145}{32219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+2219}$$

$$\frac{145}{322219} := \frac{1+4+5}{3+22219}$$

$$466. \quad \frac{146}{1095} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 09 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{146}{10950} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 09 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{146}{109500} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 09 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{146}{1095000} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 09 \times 5000}$$

$$470. \quad \frac{147}{1050} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{147}{10500} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{147}{105000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1 \times 05000}$$

$$\frac{147}{1050000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1 \times 050000}$$

$$462. \quad \frac{145}{435} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{4 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{145}{4350} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{4 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{145}{43500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{4 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{145}{435000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 5}{4 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$467. \quad \frac{146}{1168} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{146}{11680} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{146}{116800} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{146}{1168000} := \frac{1^4 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$471. \quad \frac{147}{1078} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+78}$$

$$\frac{147}{10878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+878}$$

$$\frac{147}{108878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+8878}$$

$$\frac{147}{1088878} := \frac{1+4+7}{10+88878}$$

$$463. \quad \frac{145}{580} := \frac{1+4+5}{5 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{145}{5800} := \frac{1+4+5}{5 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{145}{58000} := \frac{1+4+5}{5 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{145}{580000} := \frac{1+4+5}{5 \times 8000+0}$$

$$468. \quad \frac{146}{1460} := \frac{14 \times 6}{14 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{146}{14600} := \frac{14 \times 6}{14 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{146}{146000} := \frac{14 \times 6}{14 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{146}{1460000} := \frac{14 \times 6}{14 \times 60000}$$

$$472. \quad \frac{147}{1260} := \frac{14+7}{(1+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{147}{12600} := \frac{14+7}{(1+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{147}{126000} := \frac{14+7}{(1+2) \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{147}{1260000} := \frac{14+7}{(1+2) \times 60000}$$

$$464. \quad \frac{145}{638} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+38}$$

$$\frac{145}{6438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+438}$$

$$\frac{145}{64438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+4438}$$

$$\frac{145}{644438} := \frac{1+4+5}{6+44438}$$

$$469. \quad \frac{146}{292} := \frac{1+4+6}{(2+9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{146}{2920} := \frac{1+4+6}{(2+9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{146}{29200} := \frac{1+4+6}{(2+9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{146}{292000} := \frac{1+4+6}{(2+9) \times 2000}$$

$$473. \quad \frac{147}{1302} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1+30) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{147}{13020} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1+30) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{147}{130200} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1+30) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{147}{1302000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1+30) \times 2000}$$

$$465. \quad \frac{145}{725} := \frac{1 \times 4+5}{(7+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{145}{7250} := \frac{1 \times 4+5}{(7+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{145}{72500} := \frac{1 \times 4+5}{(7+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{145}{725000} := \frac{1 \times 4+5}{(7+2) \times 5000}$$

$$474. \quad \frac{147}{1323} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 7}{(1 + 32) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{147}{13230} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 7}{(1 + 32) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{147}{132300} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 7}{(1 + 32) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{147}{1323000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 7}{(1 + 32) \times 3000}$$

$$478. \quad \frac{147}{1470} := \frac{14 \times 7}{14 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{147}{14700} := \frac{14 \times 7}{14 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{147}{147000} := \frac{14 \times 7}{14 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{147}{1470000} := \frac{14 \times 7}{14 \times 70000}$$

$$483. \quad \frac{147}{315} := \frac{14 + 7}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{147}{3150} := \frac{14 + 7}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{147}{31500} := \frac{14 + 7}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{147}{315000} := \frac{14 + 7}{3 \times 15000}$$

$$475. \quad \frac{147}{1344} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{147}{13440} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{147}{134400} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{147}{1344000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$479. \quad \frac{147}{168} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{147}{1680} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{147}{16800} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{147}{168000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^6 \times 8000}$$

$$484. \quad \frac{147}{385} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{147}{3850} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{147}{38500} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{147}{385000} := \frac{14 + 7}{(3 + 8) \times 5000}$$

$$476. \quad \frac{147}{1365} := \frac{14 + 7}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{147}{13650} := \frac{14 + 7}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{147}{136500} := \frac{14 + 7}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{147}{1365000} := \frac{14 + 7}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}$$

$$480. \quad \frac{147}{189} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{147}{1890} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{147}{18900} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{147}{189000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{1^8 \times 9000}$$

$$485. \quad \frac{147}{420} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{147}{4200} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{147}{42000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{4 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{147}{420000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{4 \times 20000}$$

$$477. \quad \frac{147}{1386} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{147}{13860} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{147}{138600} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{147}{1386000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$481. \quad \frac{147}{231} := \frac{14 + 7}{2 + 31}$$

$$\frac{147}{2331} := \frac{14 + 7}{2 + 331}$$

$$\frac{147}{23331} := \frac{14 + 7}{2 + 3331}$$

$$\frac{147}{233331} := \frac{14 + 7}{2 + 33331}$$

$$486. \quad \frac{147}{448} := \frac{14 + 7}{(4 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{147}{4480} := \frac{14 + 7}{(4 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{147}{44800} := \frac{14 + 7}{(4 + 4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{147}{448000} := \frac{14 + 7}{(4 + 4) \times 8000}$$

$$482. \quad \frac{147}{245} := \frac{1 + 47}{2^4 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{147}{2450} := \frac{1 + 47}{2^4 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{147}{24500} := \frac{1 + 47}{2^4 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{147}{245000} := \frac{1 + 47}{2^4 \times 5000}$$

$$487. \quad \frac{147}{462} := \frac{14 + 7}{4 + 62}$$

$$\frac{147}{4662} := \frac{14 + 7}{4 + 662}$$

$$\frac{147}{46662} := \frac{14 + 7}{4 + 6662}$$

$$\frac{147}{466662} := \frac{14 + 7}{4 + 66662}$$

$$488. \quad \frac{147}{480} := \frac{14 \times 7}{4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{147}{4800} := \frac{14 \times 7}{4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{147}{48000} := \frac{14 \times 7}{4 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{147}{480000} := \frac{14 \times 7}{4 \times 80000}$$

$$489. \quad \frac{147}{525} := \frac{(1+4) \times 7}{5 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{147}{5250} := \frac{(1+4) \times 7}{5 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{147}{52500} := \frac{(1+4) \times 7}{5 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{147}{525000} := \frac{(1+4) \times 7}{5 \times 25000}$$

$$490. \quad \frac{147}{539} := \frac{1 + (4+7)}{5 + 39}$$

$$\frac{147}{5439} := \frac{1 + (4+7)}{5 + 439}$$

$$\frac{147}{54439} := \frac{1 + (4+7)}{5 + 4439}$$

$$\frac{147}{544439} := \frac{1 + (4+7)}{5 + 44439}$$

$$491. \quad \frac{147}{5880} := \frac{1^4 + 7}{5 \times 8 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{147}{58800} := \frac{1^4 + 7}{5 \times 8 \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{147}{588000} := \frac{1^4 + 7}{5 \times 8 \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{147}{5880000} := \frac{1^4 + 7}{5 \times 8 \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$492. \quad \frac{147}{693} := \frac{14+7}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{147}{6993} := \frac{14+7}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{147}{69993} := \frac{14+7}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{147}{699993} := \frac{14+7}{6+99993}$$

$$493. \quad \frac{147}{735} := \frac{14+7}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{147}{7350} := \frac{14+7}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{147}{73500} := \frac{14+7}{7 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{147}{735000} := \frac{14+7}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$494. \quad \frac{147}{924} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(9+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{147}{9240} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(9+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{147}{92400} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(9+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{147}{924000} := \frac{1^4 \times 7}{(9+2) \times 4000}$$

$$495. \quad \frac{147}{945} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{9 \times 4 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{147}{9450} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{9 \times 4 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{147}{94500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{9 \times 4 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{147}{945000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 7}{9 \times 4 \times 5000}$$

$$496. \quad \frac{147}{972} := \frac{14 \times 7}{9 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{147}{9720} := \frac{14 \times 7}{9 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{147}{97200} := \frac{14 \times 7}{9 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{147}{972000} := \frac{14 \times 7}{9 \times 72000}$$

$$497. \quad \frac{148}{1184} := \frac{1^4 + 8}{1 \times 18 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{148}{11840} := \frac{1^4 + 8}{1 \times 18 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{148}{118400} := \frac{1^4 + 8}{1 \times 18 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{148}{1184000} := \frac{1^4 + 8}{1 \times 18 \times 4000}$$

$$498. \quad \frac{148}{1295} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{(12+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{148}{12950} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{(12+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{148}{129500} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{(12+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{148}{1295000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{(12+9) \times 5000}$$

$$499. \quad \frac{148}{1480} := \frac{14 \times 8}{14 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{148}{14800} := \frac{14 \times 8}{14 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{148}{148000} := \frac{14 \times 8}{14 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{148}{1480000} := \frac{14 \times 8}{14 \times 80000}$$

$$500. \quad \frac{148}{185} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{148}{1850} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{148}{18500} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{148}{185000} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 8 \times 5000}$$

$$501. \quad \frac{148}{296} := \frac{1+4 \times 8}{(2+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{148}{2960} := \frac{1+4 \times 8}{(2+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{148}{29600} := \frac{1+4 \times 8}{(2+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{148}{296000} := \frac{1+4 \times 8}{(2+9) \times 6000}$$

$$502. \quad \frac{148}{333} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{3 \times 3 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{148}{3330} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{3 \times 3 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{148}{33300} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{3 \times 3 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{148}{333000} := \frac{1 \times 4 + 8}{3 \times 3 \times 3000}$$

$$507. \quad \frac{150}{297} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2 + 97}$$

$$\frac{150}{2997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2 + 997}$$

$$\frac{150}{29997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2 + 9997}$$

$$\frac{150}{299997} := \frac{1 \times 50}{2 + 99997}$$

$$512. \quad \frac{151}{4530} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{4 \times 5 \times 3 + 0}$$

$$\frac{151}{45300} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{4 \times 5 \times 30 + 0}$$

$$\frac{151}{453000} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{4 \times 5 \times 300 + 0}$$

$$\frac{151}{4530000} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{4 \times 5 \times 3000 + 0}$$

$$503. \quad \frac{148}{666} := \frac{1 \times 48}{6 \times 6 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{148}{6660} := \frac{1 \times 48}{6 \times 6 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{148}{66600} := \frac{1 \times 48}{6 \times 6 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{148}{666000} := \frac{1 \times 48}{6 \times 6 \times 6000}$$

$$508. \quad \frac{151}{1057} := \frac{15 \times 1}{(10 + 5) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{151}{10570} := \frac{15 \times 1}{(10 + 5) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{151}{105700} := \frac{15 \times 1}{(10 + 5) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{151}{1057000} := \frac{15 \times 1}{(10 + 5) \times 7000}$$

$$513. \quad \frac{151}{604} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 1}{6 \times 04}$$

$$\frac{151}{6040} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 1}{6 \times 040}$$

$$\frac{151}{60400} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 1}{6 \times 0400}$$

$$\frac{151}{604000} := \frac{1 + 5 \times 1}{6 \times 04000}$$

$$504. \quad \frac{149}{1192} := \frac{14 + 9}{(1 + 1) \times 92}$$

$$\frac{149}{11920} := \frac{14 + 9}{(1 + 1) \times 920}$$

$$\frac{149}{119200} := \frac{14 + 9}{(1 + 1) \times 9200}$$

$$\frac{149}{1192000} := \frac{14 + 9}{(1 + 1) \times 92000}$$

$$509. \quad \frac{151}{1208} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{1 \times 2 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{151}{12080} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{1 \times 2 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{151}{120800} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{1 \times 2 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{151}{1208000} := \frac{1^5 + 1}{1 \times 2 \times 08000}$$

$$514. \quad \frac{152}{1216} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{152}{12160} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{152}{121600} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{152}{1216000} := \frac{1^5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 16000}$$

$$505. \quad \frac{149}{1341} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{1 \times 3^4 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{149}{13410} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{1 \times 3^4 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{149}{134100} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{1 \times 3^4 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{149}{1341000} := \frac{1^4 \times 9}{1 \times 3^4 \times 1000}$$

$$510. \quad \frac{151}{1359} := \frac{15 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{151}{13590} := \frac{15 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{151}{135900} := \frac{15 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{151}{1359000} := \frac{15 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 9000}$$

$$506. \quad \frac{149}{1490} := \frac{14 \times 9}{14 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{149}{14900} := \frac{14 \times 9}{14 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{149}{149000} := \frac{14 \times 9}{14 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{149}{1490000} := \frac{14 \times 9}{14 \times 90000}$$

$$511. \quad \frac{151}{1661} := \frac{1 + 5 + 1}{16 + 61}$$

$$\frac{151}{16761} := \frac{1 + 5 + 1}{16 + 761}$$

$$\frac{151}{167761} := \frac{1 + 5 + 1}{16 + 7761}$$

$$\frac{151}{1677761} := \frac{1 + 5 + 1}{16 + 77761}$$

$$515. \quad \frac{152}{1254} := \frac{1 + 5 + 2}{12 + 54}$$

$$\frac{152}{12654} := \frac{1 + 5 + 2}{12 + 654}$$

$$\frac{152}{126654} := \frac{1 + 5 + 2}{12 + 6654}$$

$$\frac{152}{1266654} := \frac{1 + 5 + 2}{12 + 66654}$$

$$516. \quad \frac{152}{1368} := \frac{1+5+2}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{152}{13680} := \frac{1+5+2}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{152}{136800} := \frac{1+5+2}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{152}{1368000} := \frac{1+5+2}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}$$

$$521. \quad \frac{152}{627} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{152}{6327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{152}{63327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{152}{633327} := \frac{1+5+2}{6+33327}$$

$$525. \quad \frac{153}{1071} := \frac{1^{53}}{1 \times 07 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{153}{10710} := \frac{1^{53}}{1 \times 07 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{153}{107100} := \frac{1^{53}}{1 \times 07 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{153}{1071000} := \frac{1^{53}}{1 \times 07 \times 1000}$$

$$517. \quad \frac{152}{1881} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+81}$$

$$\frac{152}{18981} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+981}$$

$$\frac{152}{189981} := \frac{1+5+2}{18+9981}$$

$$522. \quad \frac{152}{836} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{152}{8360} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{152}{83600} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{152}{836000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{(8+3) \times 6000}$$

$$526. \quad \frac{153}{1088} := \frac{1+5+3}{1 \times 08 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{153}{10880} := \frac{1+5+3}{1 \times 08 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{153}{108800} := \frac{1+5+3}{1 \times 08 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{153}{1088000} := \frac{1+5+3}{1 \times 08 \times 8000}$$

$$518. \quad \frac{152}{209} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+09}$$

$$\frac{152}{2109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{152}{21109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{152}{211109} := \frac{1+5+2}{2+11109}$$

$$523. \quad \frac{152}{912} := \frac{1^5+2}{9 \times 1 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{152}{9120} := \frac{1^5+2}{9 \times 1 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{152}{91200} := \frac{1^5+2}{9 \times 1 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{152}{912000} := \frac{1^5+2}{9 \times 1 \times 2000}$$

$$527. \quad \frac{153}{1122} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 22}$$

$$\frac{153}{11220} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 220}$$

$$\frac{153}{112200} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 2200}$$

$$\frac{153}{1122000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 22000}$$

$$519. \quad \frac{152}{418} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{152}{4218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{152}{42218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{152}{422218} := \frac{1+5+2}{4+22218}$$

$$524. \quad \frac{153}{1020} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 020}$$

$$\frac{153}{10200} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 0200}$$

$$\frac{153}{102000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 020000}$$

$$528. \quad \frac{153}{1224} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^2 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{153}{12240} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^2 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{153}{122400} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^2 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{153}{1224000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^2 \times 24000}$$

$$520. \quad \frac{152}{608} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{6 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{152}{6080} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{6 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{152}{60800} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{6 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{152}{608000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 2}{6 \times 08000}$$

$$\frac{153}{1020000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1 \times 0200000}$$

$$529. \quad \frac{153}{1275} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 2 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{153}{12750} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 2 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{153}{127500} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 2 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{153}{1275000} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}$$

$$530. \quad \frac{153}{1326} := \frac{15+3}{13 \times (2 \times 6)}$$

$$\frac{153}{13260} := \frac{15+3}{13 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{153}{132600} := \frac{15+3}{13 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{153}{1326000} := \frac{15+3}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$535. \quad \frac{153}{17374} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{153}{173740} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{153}{1737400} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{153}{17374000} := \frac{15+3}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}$$

$$540. \quad \frac{153}{476} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{153}{4760} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{153}{47600} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{153}{476000} := \frac{1+53}{4 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

$$531. \quad \frac{153}{1428} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^4 \times 28}$$

$$\frac{153}{14280} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^4 \times 280}$$

$$\frac{153}{142800} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^4 \times 2800}$$

$$\frac{153}{1428000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{1^4 \times 28000}$$

$$536. \quad \frac{153}{2550} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{2 \times 5 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{153}{25500} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{2 \times 5 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{153}{255000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{2 \times 5 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{153}{2550000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{2 \times 5 \times 5000 + 0}$$

$$541. \quad \frac{153}{510} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3}{5 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{153}{5100} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3}{5 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{153}{51000} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3}{5 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{153}{510000} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 3}{5 \times 10000}$$

$$532. \quad \frac{153}{1445} := \frac{1+5+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{153}{14450} := \frac{1+5+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{153}{144500} := \frac{1+5+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{153}{1445000} := \frac{1+5+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5000}$$

$$537. \quad \frac{153}{306} := \frac{1+5+3}{3 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{153}{3060} := \frac{1+5+3}{3 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{153}{30600} := \frac{1+5+3}{3 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{153}{306000} := \frac{1+5+3}{3 \times 06000}$$

$$542. \quad \frac{153}{561} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{(5+6) \times 1}$$

$$\frac{153}{5610} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{(5+6) \times 10}$$

$$\frac{153}{56100} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{(5+6) \times 100}$$

$$\frac{153}{561000} := \frac{1^5 \times 3}{(5+6) \times 1000}$$

$$533. \quad \frac{153}{1683} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+83}$$

$$\frac{153}{16983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+983}$$

$$\frac{153}{169983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+9983}$$

$$\frac{153}{1699983} := \frac{1+5+3}{16+99983}$$

$$538. \quad \frac{153}{340} := \frac{1+53}{3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{153}{3400} := \frac{1+53}{3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{153}{34000} := \frac{1+53}{3 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{153}{340000} := \frac{1+53}{3 \times 40000}$$

$$534. \quad \frac{153}{1734} := \frac{15+3}{17 \times 3 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{153}{17340} := \frac{15+3}{17 \times 3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{153}{173400} := \frac{15+3}{17 \times 3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{153}{1734000} := \frac{15+3}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}$$

$$539. \quad \frac{153}{357} := \frac{15 \times 3}{3 \times 5 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{153}{3570} := \frac{15 \times 3}{3 \times 5 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{153}{35700} := \frac{15 \times 3}{3 \times 5 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{153}{357000} := \frac{15 \times 3}{3 \times 5 \times 7000}$$

$$543. \quad \frac{153}{561} := \frac{15+3}{5+61}$$

$$\frac{153}{5661} := \frac{15+3}{5+661}$$

$$\frac{153}{56661} := \frac{15+3}{5+6661}$$

$$\frac{153}{566661} := \frac{15+3}{5+66661}$$

$$544. \quad \frac{153}{595} := \frac{15+3}{(5+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{153}{5950} := \frac{15+3}{(5+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{153}{59500} := \frac{15+3}{(5+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{153}{595000} := \frac{15+3}{(5+9) \times 5000}$$

$$549. \quad \frac{154}{231} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{2 \times 3 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{154}{2310} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{2 \times 3 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{154}{23100} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{2 \times 3 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{154}{231000} := \frac{1^5 \times 4}{2 \times 3 \times 1000}$$

$$554. \quad \frac{155}{1023} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{10+23}$$

$$\frac{155}{10323} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{10+323}$$

$$\frac{155}{103323} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{10+3323}$$

$$\frac{155}{1033323} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{10+33323}$$

$$545. \quad \frac{153}{612} := \frac{15+3}{6 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{153}{6120} := \frac{15+3}{6 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{153}{61200} := \frac{15+3}{6 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{153}{612000} := \frac{15+3}{6 \times 12000}$$

$$550. \quad \frac{154}{616} := \frac{(1+5) \times 4}{6 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{154}{6160} := \frac{(1+5) \times 4}{6 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{154}{61600} := \frac{(1+5) \times 4}{6 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{154}{616000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 4}{6 \times 16000}$$

$$555. \quad \frac{155}{1116} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1+11) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{155}{11160} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1+11) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{155}{111600} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1+11) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{155}{1116000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1+11) \times 6000}$$

$$546. \quad \frac{153}{748} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{153}{7480} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{153}{74800} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{153}{748000} := \frac{15+3}{(7+4) \times 8000}$$

$$551. \quad \frac{154}{693} := \frac{1+5+4}{(6+9) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{154}{6930} := \frac{1+(5+4)}{(6+9) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{154}{69300} := \frac{1+(5+4)}{(6+9) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{154}{693000} := \frac{1+(5+4)}{(6+9) \times 3000}$$

$$556. \quad \frac{155}{1240} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{155}{12400} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{155}{124000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{155}{1240000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}$$

$$547. \quad \frac{153}{816} := \frac{1+5+3}{8 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{153}{8160} := \frac{1+5+3}{8 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{153}{81600} := \frac{1+5+3}{8 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{153}{816000} := \frac{1+5+3}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$552. \quad \frac{154}{847} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+47}$$

$$\frac{154}{8547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+547}$$

$$\frac{154}{85547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+5547}$$

$$\frac{154}{855547} := \frac{1+5+4}{8+55547}$$

$$557. \quad \frac{155}{1395} := \frac{15+5}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{155}{13950} := \frac{15+5}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{155}{139500} := \frac{15+5}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{155}{1395000} := \frac{15+5}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}$$

$$548. \quad \frac{154}{1554} := \frac{1+54}{1+554}$$

$$\frac{154}{15554} := \frac{1+54}{1+5554}$$

$$\frac{154}{155554} := \frac{1+54}{1+55554}$$

$$\frac{154}{1555554} := \frac{1+54}{1+555554}$$

$$553. \quad \frac{154}{924} := \frac{1 \times 54}{9^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{154}{9240} := \frac{1 \times 54}{9^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{154}{92400} := \frac{1 \times 54}{9^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{154}{924000} := \frac{1 \times 54}{9^2 \times 4000}$$

$$558. \quad \frac{155}{1488} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{155}{14880} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{155}{148800} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{155}{1488000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8000}$$

$$559. \quad \frac{155}{186} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{1^8 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{155}{1860} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{1^8 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{155}{18600} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{1^8 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{155}{186000} := \frac{1^5 \times 5}{1^8 \times 6000}$$

$$560. \quad \frac{155}{217} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{2 \times 1 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{155}{2170} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{2 \times 1 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{155}{21700} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{2 \times 1 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{155}{217000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{2 \times 1 \times 7000}$$

$$561. \quad \frac{155}{248} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{(2+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{155}{2480} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{(2+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{155}{24800} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{(2+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{155}{248000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{(2+4) \times 8000}$$

$$562. \quad \frac{155}{341} := \frac{15 + 5}{3 + 41}$$

$$\frac{155}{3441} := \frac{15 + 5}{3 + 441}$$

$$\frac{155}{34441} := \frac{15 + 5}{3 + 4441}$$

$$\frac{155}{344441} := \frac{15 + 5}{3 + 44441}$$

$$563. \quad \frac{155}{434} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(4+3) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{155}{4340} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(4+3) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{155}{43400} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(4+3) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{155}{434000} := \frac{1 \times 5 + 5}{(4+3) \times 4000}$$

$$564. \quad \frac{155}{620} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{155}{6200} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{155}{62000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{6 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{155}{620000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 5}{6 \times 20000}$$

$$565. \quad \frac{155}{682} := \frac{15 + 5}{6 + 82}$$

$$\frac{155}{6882} := \frac{15 + 5}{6 + 882}$$

$$\frac{155}{68882} := \frac{15 + 5}{6 + 8882}$$

$$\frac{155}{688882} := \frac{15 + 5}{6 + 88882}$$

$$566. \quad \frac{156}{1040} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 040}$$

$$\frac{156}{10400} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 0400}$$

$$\frac{156}{104000} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 04000}$$

$$\frac{156}{1040000} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 040000}$$

$$567. \quad \frac{156}{1144} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 44}$$

$$\frac{156}{11440} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 440}$$

$$\frac{156}{114400} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 4400}$$

$$\frac{156}{1144000} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1 \times 1 \times 44000}$$

$$568. \quad \frac{156}{1248} := \frac{1 + 5 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 48}$$

$$\frac{156}{12480} := \frac{1 + 5 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 480}$$

$$\frac{156}{124800} := \frac{1 + 5 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 4800}$$

$$\frac{156}{1248000} := \frac{1 + 5 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}$$

$$569. \quad \frac{156}{1300} := \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{156}{13000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{156}{130000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 30000}$$

$$\frac{156}{1300000} := \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 300000}$$

$$570. \quad \frac{156}{1352} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^3 \times 52}$$

$$\frac{156}{13520} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^3 \times 520}$$

$$\frac{156}{135200} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^3 \times 5200}$$

$$\frac{156}{1352000} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^3 \times 52000}$$

$$571. \quad \frac{156}{1456} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{156}{14560} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{156}{145600} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{156}{1456000} := \frac{1^5 \times 6}{1^4 \times 56000}$$

$$572. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{195} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \frac{156}{1950} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 9 \times 50} \\ \frac{156}{19500} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 9 \times 500} \\ \frac{156}{195000} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{1 \times 9 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

$$573. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{208} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{2 \times 08} \\ \frac{156}{2080} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{2 \times 080} \\ \frac{156}{20800} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{2 \times 0800} \end{aligned}$$

$$574. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{312} &:= \frac{1+5 \times 6}{31 \times 2} \\ \frac{156}{3120} &:= \frac{1+5 \times 6}{31 \times 20} \\ \frac{156}{31200} &:= \frac{1+5 \times 6}{31 \times 200} \\ \frac{156}{312000} &:= \frac{1+5 \times 6}{31 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

$$575. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{325} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{3 \times 25} \\ \frac{156}{3250} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{3 \times 250} \\ \frac{156}{32500} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{3 \times 2500} \\ \frac{156}{325000} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 6}{3 \times 25000} \end{aligned}$$

$$576. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{429} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{4+29} \\ \frac{156}{4329} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{4+329} \\ \frac{156}{43329} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{4+3329} \\ \frac{156}{433329} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{4+33329} \end{aligned}$$

$$577. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{520} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6}{5 \times 20} \\ \frac{156}{5200} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6}{5 \times 200} \\ \frac{156}{52000} &:= \frac{1 \times 5 \times 6}{5 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

$$578. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{572} &:= \frac{15+6}{5+72} \\ \frac{156}{5772} &:= \frac{15+6}{5+772} \\ \frac{156}{57772} &:= \frac{15+6}{5+7772} \\ \frac{156}{577772} &:= \frac{15+6}{5+77772} \end{aligned}$$

$$579. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{156}{624} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{6 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \frac{156}{6240} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{6 \times 2 \times 40} \\ \frac{156}{62400} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{6 \times 2 \times 400} \\ \frac{156}{624000} &:= \frac{1+5+6}{6 \times 2 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$580. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{157}{1256} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{1^2 \times 56} \\ \frac{157}{12560} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{1^2 \times 560} \\ \frac{157}{125600} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{1^2 \times 5600} \\ \frac{157}{1256000} &:= \frac{1^5 \times 7}{1^2 \times 56000} \end{aligned}$$

$$581. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{157}{314} &:= \frac{1^5+7}{(3+1) \times 4} \\ \frac{157}{3140} &:= \frac{1^5+7}{(3+1) \times 40} \\ \frac{157}{31400} &:= \frac{1^5+7}{(3+1) \times 400} \\ \frac{157}{314000} &:= \frac{1^5+7}{(3+1) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$582. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{157}{628} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 28} \\ \frac{157}{6280} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 280} \\ \frac{157}{62800} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 2800} \\ \frac{157}{628000} &:= \frac{(1+5) \times 7}{6 \times 28000} \end{aligned}$$

$$583. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{157}{942} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+7}{9 \times 4 \times 2} \\ \frac{157}{9420} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+7}{9 \times 4 \times 20} \\ \frac{157}{94200} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+7}{9 \times 4 \times 200} \end{aligned}$$

$$584. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{158}{1264} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+8}{1 \times 26 \times 4} \\ \frac{158}{12640} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+8}{1 \times 26 \times 40} \\ \frac{158}{126400} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+8}{1 \times 26 \times 400} \\ \frac{158}{1264000} &:= \frac{1 \times 5+8}{1 \times 26 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$585. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{158}{316} &:= \frac{1^5+8}{3 \times 1 \times 6} \\ \frac{158}{3160} &:= \frac{1^5+8}{3 \times 1 \times 60} \\ \frac{158}{31600} &:= \frac{1^5+8}{3 \times 1 \times 600} \\ \frac{158}{316000} &:= \frac{1^5+8}{3 \times 1 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

$$586. \quad \frac{158}{632} := \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{158}{6320} := \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{158}{63200} := \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{158}{632000} := \frac{1^5 + 8}{6 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$590. \quad \frac{159}{1272} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^2 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{159}{12720} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^2 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{159}{127200} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^2 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{159}{1272000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^2 \times 72000}$$

$$594. \quad \frac{159}{371} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{3 \times 7 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{159}{3710} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{3 \times 7 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{159}{37100} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{3 \times 7 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{159}{371000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{3 \times 7 \times 1000}$$

$$587. \quad \frac{158}{869} := \frac{1 + 5 + 8}{8 + 69}$$

$$\frac{158}{8769} := \frac{1 + 5 + 8}{8 + 769}$$

$$\frac{158}{87769} := \frac{1 + 5 + 8}{8 + 7769}$$

$$\frac{158}{87769} := \frac{1 + 5 + 8}{8 + 7769}$$

$$591. \quad \frac{159}{1325} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{159}{13250} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{159}{132500} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{159}{1325000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 25000}$$

$$595. \quad \frac{159}{424} := \frac{15 + 9}{4^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{159}{4240} := \frac{15 + 9}{4^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{159}{42400} := \frac{15 + 9}{4^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{159}{424000} := \frac{15 + 9}{4^2 \times 4000}$$

$$588. \quad \frac{159}{1060} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{159}{10600} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{159}{106000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 06000}$$

$$\frac{159}{1060000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 060000}$$

$$592. \quad \frac{159}{1378} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^3 \times 78}$$

$$\frac{159}{13780} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^3 \times 780}$$

$$\frac{159}{137800} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^3 \times 7800}$$

$$\frac{159}{1378000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^3 \times 78000}$$

$$596. \quad \frac{159}{530} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 9}{5 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{159}{5300} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 9}{5 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{159}{53000} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 9}{5 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{159}{530000} := \frac{1 \times 5 \times 9}{5 \times 30000}$$

$$589. \quad \frac{159}{1166} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 66}$$

$$\frac{159}{11660} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 660}$$

$$\frac{159}{116600} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 6600}$$

$$\frac{159}{1166000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 66000}$$

$$593. \quad \frac{159}{1484} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^4 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{159}{14840} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^4 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{159}{148400} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^4 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{159}{1484000} := \frac{1^5 \times 9}{1^4 \times 84000}$$

$$597. \quad \frac{159}{583} := \frac{15 + 9}{5 + 83}$$

$$\frac{159}{5883} := \frac{15 + 9}{5 + 883}$$

$$\frac{159}{58883} := \frac{15 + 9}{5 + 8883}$$

$$598. \quad \frac{159}{636} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 9}{6 \times 36}$$

$$\frac{159}{6360} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 9}{6 \times 360}$$

$$\frac{159}{63600} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 9}{6 \times 3600}$$

$$\frac{159}{636000} := \frac{(1 + 5) \times 9}{6 \times 36000}$$

$$599. \quad \frac{161}{1127} := \frac{1^6+1}{1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{161}{11270} := \frac{1^6+1}{1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{161}{112700} := \frac{1^6+1}{1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{161}{1127000} := \frac{1^6+1}{1 \times 1 \times 2 \times 7000}$$

$$600. \quad \frac{161}{1150} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{161}{11500} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{161}{115000} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{161}{1150000} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}$$

$$601. \quad \frac{161}{1173} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 17 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{161}{11730} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 17 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{161}{117300} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 17 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{161}{1173000} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}$$

$$602. \quad \frac{161}{1288} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{161}{12880} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{161}{128800} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{161}{1288000} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 8 \times 8000}$$

$$603. \quad \frac{161}{1449} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{161}{14490} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{161}{144900} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{161}{1449000} := \frac{16 \times 1}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 9000}$$

$$604. \quad \frac{161}{1495} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{(1 \times 4 + 9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{161}{14950} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{(1 \times 4 + 9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{161}{149500} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{(1 \times 4 + 9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{161}{1495000} := \frac{1+6 \times 1}{(1 \times 4 + 9) \times 5000}$$

$$605. \quad \frac{161}{15295} := \frac{16+1}{(15+2) \times 95}$$

$$\frac{161}{152950} := \frac{16+1}{(15+2) \times 950}$$

$$\frac{161}{1529500} := \frac{16+1}{(15+2) \times 9500}$$

$$\frac{161}{15295000} := \frac{16+1}{(15+2) \times 95000}$$

$$606. \quad \frac{161}{322} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 1}{3 \times 2 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{161}{3220} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 1}{3 \times 2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{161}{32200} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 1}{3 \times 2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{161}{322000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 1}{3 \times 2 \times 2000}$$

$$607. \quad \frac{161}{6440} := \frac{1^6 \times 1}{(6+4) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{161}{64400} := \frac{1^6 \times 1}{(6+4) \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{161}{644000} := \frac{1^6 \times 1}{(6+4) \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{161}{6440000} := \frac{1^6 \times 1}{(6+4) \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$608. \quad \frac{161}{805} := \frac{1+6+1}{8 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{161}{8050} := \frac{1+6+1}{8 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{161}{80500} := \frac{1+6+1}{8 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{161}{805000} := \frac{1+6+1}{8 \times 05000}$$

$$609. \quad \frac{162}{1080} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{162}{10800} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{162}{108000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 08000}$$

$$\frac{162}{1080000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 080000}$$

$$610. \quad \frac{162}{1125} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 125}$$

$$\frac{162}{11250} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 1250}$$

$$\frac{162}{112500} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 12500}$$

$$\frac{162}{1125000} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 125000}$$

$$611. \quad \frac{162}{1134} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{(1+13) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{162}{11340} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{(1+13) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{162}{113400} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{(1+13) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{162}{1134000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{(1+13) \times 4000}$$

$$612. \quad \frac{162}{1152} := \frac{1+6+2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{162}{11520} := \frac{1+6+2}{(1+1)^5 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{162}{115200} := \frac{1+6+2}{(1+1)^5 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{162}{1152000} := \frac{1+6+2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}$$

$$613. \quad \frac{162}{1188} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 88}$$

$$\frac{162}{11880} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 880}$$

$$\frac{162}{118800} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 8800}$$

$$\frac{162}{1188000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 88000}$$

$$618. \quad \frac{162}{1368} := \frac{16+2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{162}{13680} := \frac{16+2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{162}{136800} := \frac{16+2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{162}{1368000} := \frac{16+2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

$$623. \quad \frac{162}{1575} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{162}{15750} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{162}{157500} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{162}{1575000} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$614. \quad \frac{162}{1197} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 19 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{162}{11970} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 19 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{162}{119700} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 19 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{162}{1197000} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}$$

$$619. \quad \frac{162}{13797} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 2)}{(137+9) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{162}{137970} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 2)}{(137+9) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{162}{1379700} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 2)}{(137+9) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{162}{13797000} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 2)}{(137+9) \times 7000}$$

$$624. \quad \frac{162}{216} := \frac{1+6+2}{2 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{162}{2160} := \frac{1+6+2}{2 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{162}{21600} := \frac{1+6+2}{2 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{162}{216000} := \frac{1+6+2}{2 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$615. \quad \frac{162}{1215} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{12 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{162}{12150} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{12 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{162}{121500} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{12 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{162}{1215000} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{12 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$620. \quad \frac{162}{1440} := \frac{1+62}{14 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{162}{14400} := \frac{1+62}{14 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{162}{144000} := \frac{1+62}{14 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{162}{1440000} := \frac{1+62}{14 \times 40000}$$

$$625. \quad \frac{162}{225} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{2 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{162}{2250} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{2 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{162}{22500} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{2 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{162}{225000} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{2 \times 25000}$$

$$616. \quad \frac{162}{1296} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1^2 \times 96}$$

$$\frac{162}{12960} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1^2 \times 960}$$

$$\frac{162}{129600} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1^2 \times 9600}$$

$$\frac{162}{1296000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{1^2 \times 96000}$$

$$621. \quad \frac{162}{1458} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{(1 \times 4+5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{162}{14580} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{(1 \times 4+5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{162}{145800} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{(1 \times 4+5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{162}{1458000} := \frac{1 \times 6+2}{(1 \times 4+5) \times 8000}$$

$$626. \quad \frac{162}{243} := \frac{16 \times 2}{2^4 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{162}{2430} := \frac{16 \times 2}{2^4 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{162}{24300} := \frac{16 \times 2}{2^4 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{162}{243000} := \frac{16 \times 2}{2^4 \times 3000}$$

$$617. \quad \frac{162}{1350} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{162}{13500} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{162}{135000} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{162}{1350000} := \frac{16+2}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}$$

$$622. \quad \frac{162}{1485} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{(14+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{162}{14850} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{(14+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{162}{148500} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{(14+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{162}{1485000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{(14+8) \times 5000}$$

$$627. \quad \frac{162}{252} := \frac{1+6+2}{(2+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{162}{2520} := \frac{1+6+2}{(2+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{162}{25200} := \frac{1+6+2}{(2+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{162}{252000} := \frac{1+6+2}{(2+5) \times 2000}$$

$$628. \quad \frac{162}{324} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{3 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{162}{3240} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{3 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{162}{32400} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{3 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{162}{324000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 2}{3 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$633. \quad \frac{162}{729} := \frac{16+2}{(7+2) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{162}{7290} := \frac{16+2}{(7+2) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{162}{72900} := \frac{16+2}{(7+2) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{162}{729000} := \frac{16+2}{(7+2) \times 9000}$$

$$638. \quad \frac{164}{1230} := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{1^2 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{164}{12300} := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{1^2 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{164}{123000} := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{1^2 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{164}{1230000} := \frac{1^6 \times 4}{1^2 \times 30000}$$

$$629. \quad \frac{162}{405} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{4 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{162}{4050} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{4 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{162}{40500} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{4 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{162}{405000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 2}{4 \times 05000}$$

$$634. \quad \frac{162}{864} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{8 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{162}{8640} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{8 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{162}{86400} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{8 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{162}{864000} := \frac{1 \times 6^2}{8 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$639. \quad \frac{164}{1312} := \frac{1^{64}}{(1+3 \times 1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{164}{13120} := \frac{1^{64}}{(1+3 \times 1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{164}{131200} := \frac{1^{64}}{(1+3 \times 1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{164}{1312000} := \frac{1^{64}}{(1+3 \times 1) \times 2000}$$

$$630. \quad \frac{162}{432} := \frac{1+6+2}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{162}{4320} := \frac{1+6+2}{4 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{162}{43200} := \frac{1+6+2}{4 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{162}{432000} := \frac{1+6+2}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$635. \quad \frac{162}{891} := \frac{16+2}{8+91}$$

$$\frac{162}{8991} := \frac{16+2}{8+991}$$

$$\frac{162}{89991} := \frac{16+2}{8+9991}$$

$$631. \quad \frac{162}{585} := \frac{16+2}{(5+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{162}{5850} := \frac{16+2}{(5+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{162}{58500} := \frac{16+2}{(5+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{162}{585000} := \frac{16+2}{(5+8) \times 5000}$$

$$636. \quad \frac{163}{326} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{163}{3260} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{163}{32600} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{163}{326000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$640. \quad \frac{164}{1435} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{14 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{164}{14350} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{14 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{164}{143500} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{14 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{164}{1435000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{14 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$632. \quad \frac{162}{6480} := \frac{1^6 \times 2}{(6+4) \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{162}{64800} := \frac{1^6 \times 2}{(6+4) \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{162}{648000} := \frac{1^6 \times 2}{(6+4) \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{162}{6480000} := \frac{1^6 \times 2}{(6+4) \times 8000+0}$$

$$637. \quad \frac{163}{815} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 3}{(8+1) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{163}{8150} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 3}{(8+1) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{163}{81500} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 3}{(8+1) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{163}{815000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 3}{(8+1) \times 5000}$$

$$641. \quad \frac{164}{246} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2^4 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{164}{2460} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2^4 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{164}{24600} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2^4 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{164}{246000} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2^4 \times 6000}$$

$$642. \quad \frac{164}{287} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times 8 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{164}{2870} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times 8 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{164}{28700} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times 8 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{164}{287000} := \frac{1 \times 64}{2 \times 8 \times 7000}$$

$$643. \quad \frac{164}{328} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{164}{3280} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{164}{32800} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{164}{328000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{3 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$644. \quad \frac{164}{451} := \frac{16+4}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{164}{4551} := \frac{16+4}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{164}{45551} := \frac{16+4}{4+5551}$$

$$\frac{164}{455551} := \frac{16+4}{4+55551}$$

$$645. \quad \frac{164}{492} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{164}{4920} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{164}{49200} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{164}{492000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{4 \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$646. \quad \frac{164}{615} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{164}{6150} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{164}{61500} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{164}{615000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 15000}$$

$$647. \quad \frac{165}{1155} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1+1+5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{165}{11550} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1+1+5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{115500} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1+1+5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{1155000} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1+1+5) \times 5000}$$

$$648. \quad \frac{165}{1221} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{165}{12221} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{165}{122221} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+22221}$$

$$\frac{165}{1222221} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{1+222221}$$

$$649. \quad \frac{165}{1320} := \frac{1^{65}}{(1+3) \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{13200} := \frac{1^{65}}{(1+3) \times 20 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{132000} := \frac{1^{65}}{(1+3) \times 200 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{1320000} := \frac{1^{65}}{(1+3) \times 2000 + 0}$$

$$650. \quad \frac{165}{1375} := \frac{1+6+5}{(13+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{165}{13750} := \frac{1+6+5}{(13+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{137500} := \frac{1+6+5}{(13+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{1375000} := \frac{1+6+5}{(13+7) \times 5000}$$

$$651. \quad \frac{165}{1470} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 \times 7 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{14700} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 \times 70 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{147000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 \times 700 + 0}$$

$$\frac{165}{1470000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 \times 7000 + 0}$$

$$652. \quad \frac{165}{1485} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1^4+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{165}{14850} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1^4+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{148500} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1^4+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{1485000} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(1^4+8) \times 5000}$$

$$653. \quad \frac{165}{1485} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 + 85}$$

$$\frac{165}{14985} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 + 985}$$

$$\frac{165}{149985} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 + 9985}$$

$$\frac{165}{1499985} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{14 + 99985}$$

$$654. \quad \frac{165}{1665} := \frac{1+65}{1+665}$$

$$\frac{165}{16665} := \frac{1+65}{1+6665}$$

$$\frac{165}{166665} := \frac{1+65}{1+66665}$$

$$\frac{165}{1666665} := \frac{1+65}{1+666665}$$

$$655. \quad \frac{165}{1875} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{(18+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{165}{18750} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{(18+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{187500} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{(18+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{1875000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 5}{(18+7) \times 5000}$$

656.

$$\frac{165}{18975} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(18+97) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{165}{189750} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(18+97) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{1897500} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(18+97) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{18975000} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{(18+97) \times 5000}$$

657.

$$\frac{165}{220} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{165}{2200} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{165}{22000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{165}{220000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2 \times 20000}$$

658.

$$\frac{165}{242} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+42}$$

$$\frac{165}{2442} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+442}$$

$$\frac{165}{24442} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+4442}$$

$$\frac{165}{244442} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{2+44442}$$

659.

$$\frac{165}{250} := \frac{1+65}{2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{2500} := \frac{1+65}{2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{25000} := \frac{1+65}{2 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{165}{250000} := \frac{1+65}{2 \times 50000}$$

660.

$$\frac{165}{264} := \frac{16 \times 5}{2 \times 64}$$

$$\frac{165}{2640} := \frac{16 \times 5}{2 \times 640}$$

$$\frac{165}{26400} := \frac{16 \times 5}{2 \times 6400}$$

$$\frac{165}{264000} := \frac{16 \times 5}{2 \times 64000}$$

661.

$$\frac{165}{363} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{165}{3663} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{165}{36663} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{165}{366663} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{3+66663}$$

662.

$$\frac{165}{440} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 4+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{4400} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 40+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{44000} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 400+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{440000} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 4000+0}$$

663.

$$\frac{165}{480} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{4 \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{4800} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{4 \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{48000} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{4 \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{480000} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{4 \times 8000+0}$$

664.

$$\frac{165}{484} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{165}{4884} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{165}{48884} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{165}{488884} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 5}{4+88884}$$

665.

$$\frac{165}{4950} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 9 \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{49500} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 9 \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{495000} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 9 \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{4950000} := \frac{1^6+5}{4 \times 9 \times 5000+0}$$

666.

$$\frac{165}{525} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{(5+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{165}{5250} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{(5+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{165}{52500} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{(5+2) \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{165}{525000} := \frac{1 \times 6+5}{(5+2) \times 50000}$$

667.

$$\frac{165}{5940} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{5 \times 9 \times 4+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{59400} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{5 \times 9 \times 40+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{594000} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{5 \times 9 \times 400+0}$$

$$\frac{165}{5940000} := \frac{1^6 \times 5}{5 \times 9 \times 4000+0}$$

668.

$$\frac{166}{1328} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{166}{13280} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{166}{132800} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{166}{1328000} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

669.

$$\frac{166}{1826} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(1+8+2) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{166}{18260} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(1+8+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{166}{182600} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(1+8+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{166}{1826000} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(1+8+2) \times 6000}$$

$$670. \quad \frac{166}{249} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 6}{(2+4) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{166}{2490} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 6}{(2+4) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{166}{24900} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 6}{(2+4) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{166}{249000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 6}{(2+4) \times 9000}$$

$$671. \quad \frac{166}{332} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(3+3) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{166}{3320} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(3+3) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{166}{33200} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(3+3) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{166}{332000} := \frac{1^6 \times 6}{(3+3) \times 2000}$$

$$672. \quad \frac{166}{498} := \frac{16 \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{166}{4980} := \frac{16 \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{166}{49800} := \frac{16 \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{166}{498000} := \frac{16 \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 8000}$$

$$673. \quad \frac{166}{664} := \frac{1 \times 66}{66 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{166}{6640} := \frac{1 \times 66}{66 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{166}{66400} := \frac{1 \times 66}{66 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{166}{664000} := \frac{1 \times 66}{66 \times 4000}$$

$$674. \quad \frac{167}{1336} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7}{1 \times 336}$$

$$\frac{167}{13360} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7}{1 \times 3360}$$

$$\frac{167}{133600} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7}{1 \times 33600}$$

$$\frac{167}{1336000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 7}{1 \times 336000}$$

$$675. \quad \frac{167}{1837} := \frac{1^6 \times 7}{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{167}{18370} := \frac{1^6 \times 7}{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{167}{183700} := \frac{1^6 \times 7}{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{167}{1837000} := \frac{1^6 \times 7}{(1 \times 8 + 3) \times 7000}$$

$$676. \quad \frac{168}{1050} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{168}{10500} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{168}{105000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 05000}$$

$$\frac{168}{1050000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 050000}$$

$$677. \quad \frac{168}{1155} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 55}$$

$$\frac{168}{11550} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 550}$$

$$\frac{168}{115500} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}$$

$$\frac{168}{1155000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}$$

$$678. \quad \frac{168}{1188} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11 + 88}$$

$$\frac{168}{11888} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11 + 988}$$

$$\frac{168}{118888} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11 + 9988}$$

$$\frac{168}{1188888} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{11 + 99988}$$

$$679. \quad \frac{168}{1260} := \frac{16 + 8}{(1+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{168}{12600} := \frac{16 + 8}{(1+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{168}{126000} := \frac{16 + 8}{(1+2) \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{168}{1260000} := \frac{16 + 8}{(1+2) \times 60000}$$

$$680. \quad \frac{168}{1296} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{168}{12960} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{168}{129600} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{168}{1296000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$681. \quad \frac{168}{1302} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+30) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{168}{13020} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+30) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{168}{130200} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+30) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{168}{1302000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+30) \times 2000}$$

$$682. \quad \frac{168}{1344} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{168}{13440} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{168}{134400} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{168}{1344000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$683. \quad \frac{168}{1365} := \frac{16 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{168}{13650} := \frac{16 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{168}{136500} := \frac{16 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{168}{1365000} := \frac{16 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}$$

$$684. \quad \frac{168}{1386} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{168}{13860} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{168}{138600} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{168}{1386000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$688. \quad \frac{168}{216} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{(2 + 1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{168}{2160} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{(2 + 1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{168}{21600} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{(2 + 1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{168}{216000} := \frac{1 \times 6 + 8}{(2 + 1) \times 6000}$$

$$693. \quad \frac{168}{385} := \frac{16 + 8}{(3 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{168}{3850} := \frac{16 + 8}{(3 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{168}{38500} := \frac{16 + 8}{(3 + 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{168}{385000} := \frac{16 + 8}{(3 + 8) \times 5000}$$

$$685. \quad \frac{168}{1400} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{1 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{168}{14000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{1 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{168}{140000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{1 \times 40000}$$

$$\frac{168}{1400000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{1 \times 400000}$$

$$689. \quad \frac{168}{231} := \frac{16 + 8}{2 + 31}$$

$$\frac{168}{2331} := \frac{16 + 8}{2 + 331}$$

$$\frac{168}{23331} := \frac{16 + 8}{2 + 3331}$$

$$\frac{168}{233331} := \frac{16 + 8}{2 + 33331}$$

$$694. \quad \frac{168}{448} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{168}{4480} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{168}{44800} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{168}{448000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{4 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$686. \quad \frac{168}{1470} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{168}{14700} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{168}{147000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{168}{1470000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^4 \times 70000}$$

$$690. \quad \frac{168}{240} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{168}{2400} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{168}{24000} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{168}{240000} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 \times 40000}$$

$$695. \quad \frac{168}{462} := \frac{16 + 8}{4 + 62}$$

$$\frac{168}{4662} := \frac{16 + 8}{4 + 662}$$

$$\frac{168}{46662} := \frac{16 + 8}{4 + 6662}$$

$$\frac{168}{466662} := \frac{16 + 8}{4 + 66662}$$

$$687. \quad \frac{168}{189} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{168}{1890} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{168}{18900} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{168}{189000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{1^8 \times 9000}$$

$$691. \quad \frac{168}{297} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 + 97}$$

$$\frac{168}{2997} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 + 997}$$

$$\frac{168}{29997} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 + 9997}$$

$$\frac{168}{299997} := \frac{(1 + 6) \times 8}{2 + 99997}$$

$$696. \quad \frac{168}{560} := \frac{1^6 + 8}{5 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{168}{5600} := \frac{1^6 + 8}{5 \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{168}{56000} := \frac{1^6 + 8}{5 \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{168}{560000} := \frac{1^6 + 8}{5 \times 6000 + 0}$$

$$692. \quad \frac{168}{315} := \frac{16 + 8}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{168}{3150} := \frac{16 + 8}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{168}{31500} := \frac{16 + 8}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{168}{315000} := \frac{16 + 8}{3 \times 15000}$$

$$697. \quad \frac{168}{630} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 8)}{6 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{168}{6300} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 8)}{6 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{168}{63000} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 8)}{6 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{168}{630000} := \frac{1 \times (6 \times 8)}{6 \times 30000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 698. \quad & \frac{168}{693} := \frac{16+8}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{168}{6993} := \frac{16+8}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{168}{69993} := \frac{16+8}{6+9993} \\
 & \frac{168}{699993} := \frac{16+8}{6+99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 703. \quad & \frac{169}{676} := \frac{(1+6) \times 9}{6 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{169}{6760} := \frac{(1+6) \times 9}{6 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{169}{67600} := \frac{(1+6) \times 9}{6 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{169}{676000} := \frac{(1+6) \times 9}{6 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 708. \quad & \frac{171}{1197} := \frac{1+7+1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{171}{11970} := \frac{1+7+1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{171}{119700} := \frac{1+7+1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{171}{1197000} := \frac{1+7+1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 699. \quad & \frac{168}{735} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{168}{7350} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{168}{73500} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{168}{735000} := \frac{16+8}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 704. \quad & \frac{170}{1785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+78+5} \\
 & \frac{170}{18785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+878+5} \\
 & \frac{170}{188785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+8878+5} \\
 & \frac{170}{1888785} := \frac{1+7+0}{1+88878+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 709. \quad & \frac{171}{1254} := \frac{17+1}{(1+2^5) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{171}{12540} := \frac{17+1}{(1+2^5) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{171}{125400} := \frac{17+1}{(1+2^5) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{171}{1254000} := \frac{17+1}{(1+2^5) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 700. \quad & \frac{168}{784} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{168}{7840} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{168}{78400} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{168}{784000} := \frac{1 \times 6 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 705. \quad & \frac{170}{935} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+35} \\
 & \frac{170}{9435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+435} \\
 & \frac{170}{94435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+4435} \\
 & \frac{170}{944435} := \frac{1+7+0}{9+44435}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 710. \quad & \frac{171}{1254} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+54} \\
 & \frac{171}{12654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+654} \\
 & \frac{171}{126654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+6654} \\
 & \frac{171}{1266654} := \frac{1+7+1}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 701. \quad & \frac{168}{924} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(9+2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{168}{9240} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(9+2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{168}{92400} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(9+2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{168}{924000} := \frac{1^6 \times 8}{(9+2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 706. \quad & \frac{171}{1026} := \frac{1^7+1}{1 \times 02 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{171}{10260} := \frac{1^7+1}{1 \times 02 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{171}{102600} := \frac{1^7+1}{1 \times 02 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{171}{1026000} := \frac{1^7+1}{1 \times 02 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 702. \quad & \frac{169}{1352} := \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(1+35) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{169}{13520} := \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(1+35) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{169}{135200} := \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(1+35) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{169}{1352000} := \frac{1^6 \times 9}{(1+35) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 707. \quad & \frac{171}{1045} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{171}{10545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{171}{105545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{171}{1055545} := \frac{1+7+1}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 711. \quad & \frac{171}{1368} := \frac{17+1}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{171}{13680} := \frac{17+1}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{171}{136800} := \frac{17+1}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{171}{1368000} := \frac{17+1}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$712. \quad \frac{171}{1463} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{171}{14763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{171}{147763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{171}{1477763} := \frac{1+7+1}{14+77763}$$

$$717. \quad \frac{171}{418} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{171}{4218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{171}{42218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{171}{422218} := \frac{1+7+1}{4+22218}$$

$$722. \quad \frac{172}{344} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2}{(3+4) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{172}{3440} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2}{(3+4) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{172}{34400} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2}{(3+4) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{172}{344000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 2}{(3+4) \times 4000}$$

$$713. \quad \frac{171}{1881} := \frac{1+7 \times 1}{1 \times 88 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{171}{18810} := \frac{1+7 \times 1}{1 \times 88 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{171}{188100} := \frac{1+7 \times 1}{1 \times 88 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{171}{1881000} := \frac{1+7 \times 1}{1 \times 88 \times 1000}$$

$$718. \quad \frac{171}{494} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{171}{4940} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{171}{49400} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{171}{494000} := \frac{17+1}{(4+9) \times 4000}$$

$$723. \quad \frac{172}{645} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 45}$$

$$\frac{172}{6450} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 450}$$

$$\frac{172}{64500} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 4500}$$

$$\frac{172}{645000} := \frac{1 \times 72}{6 \times 45000}$$

$$714. \quad \frac{171}{1881} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+81}$$

$$\frac{171}{18981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+981}$$

$$\frac{171}{189981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+9981}$$

$$\frac{171}{1899981} := \frac{1+7+1}{18+99981}$$

$$719. \quad \frac{171}{627} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{171}{6327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{171}{63327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{171}{633327} := \frac{1+7+1}{6+33327}$$

$$724. \quad \frac{172}{946} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+46}$$

$$\frac{172}{9546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+546}$$

$$\frac{172}{95546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+5546}$$

$$\frac{172}{955546} := \frac{1+7+2}{9+55546}$$

$$715. \quad \frac{171}{209} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+09}$$

$$\frac{171}{2109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{171}{21109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{171}{211109} := \frac{1+7+1}{2+11109}$$

$$720. \quad \frac{172}{1032} := \frac{1+7+2}{10 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{172}{10320} := \frac{1+7+2}{10 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{172}{103200} := \frac{1+7+2}{10 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{172}{1032000} := \frac{1+7+2}{10 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$725. \quad \frac{173}{1038} := \frac{1^7+3}{1 \times 03 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{173}{10380} := \frac{1^7+3}{1 \times 03 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{173}{103800} := \frac{1^7+3}{1 \times 03 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{173}{1038000} := \frac{1^7+3}{1 \times 03 \times 8000}$$

$$716. \quad \frac{171}{342} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 1}{(3+4) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{171}{3420} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 1}{(3+4) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{171}{34200} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 1}{(3+4) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{171}{342000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 1}{(3+4) \times 2000}$$

$$721. \quad \frac{172}{1376} := \frac{1+7 \times 2}{(13+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{172}{13760} := \frac{1+7 \times 2}{(13+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{172}{137600} := \frac{1+7 \times 2}{(13+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{172}{1376000} := \frac{1+7 \times 2}{(13+7) \times 6000}$$

$$726. \quad \frac{173}{1211} := \frac{1^7 \times 3}{1 \times 21 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{173}{12110} := \frac{1^7 \times 3}{1 \times 21 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{173}{121100} := \frac{1^7 \times 3}{1 \times 21 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{173}{1211000} := \frac{1^7 \times 3}{1 \times 21 \times 1000}$$

727.

$$\frac{173}{1384} := \frac{1^7+3}{1^3 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{173}{13840} := \frac{1^7+3}{1^3 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{173}{138400} := \frac{1^7+3}{1^3 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{173}{1384000} := \frac{1^7+3}{1^3 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

732.

$$\frac{174}{232} := \frac{1+7+4}{2^3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{174}{2320} := \frac{1+7+4}{2^3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{174}{23200} := \frac{1+7+4}{2^3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{174}{232000} := \frac{1+7+4}{2^3 \times 2000}$$

737.

$$\frac{174}{638} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+38}$$

$$\frac{174}{6438} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+438}$$

$$\frac{174}{64438} := \frac{1+7+4}{6+4438}$$

728.

$$\frac{173}{346} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 3}{(3+4) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{173}{3460} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 3}{(3+4) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{173}{34600} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 3}{(3+4) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{173}{346000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 3}{(3+4) \times 6000}$$

733.

$$\frac{174}{319} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+19}$$

$$\frac{174}{3219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+219}$$

$$\frac{174}{32219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+2219}$$

$$\frac{174}{322219} := \frac{1+7+4}{3+22219}$$

738.

$$\frac{174}{957} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+57}$$

$$\frac{174}{9657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+657}$$

$$\frac{174}{96657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+6657}$$

$$\frac{174}{966657} := \frac{1+7+4}{9+66657}$$

729.

$$\frac{174}{1200} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{1 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{174}{12000} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{1 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{174}{120000} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{1 \times 20000}$$

$$\frac{174}{1200000} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{1 \times 200000}$$

734.

$$\frac{174}{348} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 4}{(3+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{174}{3480} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 4}{(3+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{174}{34800} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 4}{(3+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{174}{348000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 4}{(3+4) \times 8000}$$

739.

$$\frac{175}{12250} := \frac{1^{75}}{(12+2) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{122500} := \frac{1^{75}}{(12+2) \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{1225000} := \frac{1^{75}}{(12+2) \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{12250000} := \frac{1^{75}}{(12+2) \times 5000 + 0}$$

730.

$$\frac{174}{1276} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+76}$$

$$\frac{174}{12876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+876}$$

$$\frac{174}{128876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+8876}$$

$$\frac{174}{1288876} := \frac{1+7+4}{12+88876}$$

735.

$$\frac{174}{580} := \frac{1+7+4}{5 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{5800} := \frac{1+7+4}{5 \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{58000} := \frac{1+7+4}{5 \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{580000} := \frac{1+7+4}{5 \times 8000 + 0}$$

731.

$$\frac{174}{13920} := \frac{1^{74}}{(1+39) \times 2 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{139200} := \frac{1^{74}}{(1+39) \times 20 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{1392000} := \frac{1^{74}}{(1+39) \times 200 + 0}$$

$$\frac{174}{13920000} := \frac{1^{74}}{(1+39) \times 2000 + 0}$$

736.

$$\frac{174}{594} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+94}$$

$$\frac{174}{5994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+994}$$

$$\frac{174}{59994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+9994}$$

$$\frac{174}{599994} := \frac{1+7 \times 4}{5+99994}$$

740.

$$\frac{175}{1250} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{1 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{175}{12500} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{1 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{175}{125000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{1 \times 25000}$$

$$\frac{175}{1250000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{1 \times 250000}$$

$$741. \quad \frac{175}{1400} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{1 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{14000} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{1 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{140000} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{1 \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$\frac{175}{1400000} := \frac{1^7 \times 5}{1 \times 40000 + 0}$$

$$746. \quad \frac{175}{495} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4 + 95}$$

$$\frac{175}{4995} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4 + 995}$$

$$\frac{175}{49995} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4 + 9995}$$

$$\frac{175}{499995} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 5}{4 + 99995}$$

$$751. \quad \frac{176}{1826} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{(1+82) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{176}{18326} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{(1+832) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{176}{183326} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{(1+8332) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{176}{1833326} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{(1+83332) \times 6}$$

$$742. \quad \frac{175}{189} := \frac{1 \times 75}{(1+8) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{175}{1890} := \frac{1 \times 75}{(1+8) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{175}{18900} := \frac{1 \times 75}{(1+8) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{175}{189000} := \frac{1 \times 75}{(1+8) \times 9000}$$

$$747. \quad \frac{175}{945} := \frac{1 \times 75}{9 \times 45}$$

$$\frac{175}{9450} := \frac{1 \times 75}{9 \times 450}$$

$$\frac{175}{94500} := \frac{1 \times 75}{9 \times 4500}$$

$$\frac{175}{945000} := \frac{1 \times 75}{9 \times 45000}$$

$$752. \quad \frac{176}{256} := \frac{1+76}{2 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{176}{2560} := \frac{1+76}{2 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{176}{25600} := \frac{1+76}{2 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{176}{256000} := \frac{1+76}{2 \times 56000}$$

$$743. \quad \frac{175}{350} := \frac{1 \times 75}{3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{175}{3500} := \frac{1 \times 75}{3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{175}{35000} := \frac{1 \times 75}{3 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{175}{350000} := \frac{1 \times 75}{3 \times 50000}$$

$$748. \quad \frac{176}{1375} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{1 \times 375}$$

$$\frac{176}{13750} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{1 \times 3750}$$

$$\frac{176}{137500} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{1 \times 37500}$$

$$\frac{176}{1375000} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{1 \times 375000}$$

$$753. \quad \frac{176}{330} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{3 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{176}{3300} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{3 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{176}{33000} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{3 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{176}{330000} := \frac{(1+7) \times 6}{3 \times 30000}$$

$$744. \quad \frac{175}{385} := \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+85}$$

$$\frac{175}{3885} := \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+885}$$

$$\frac{175}{38885} := \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+8885}$$

$$\frac{175}{388885} := \frac{(1+7) \times 5}{3+88885}$$

$$749. \quad \frac{176}{1408} := \frac{1+7+6}{14 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{176}{14080} := \frac{1+7+6}{14 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{176}{140800} := \frac{1+7+6}{14 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{176}{1408000} := \frac{1+7+6}{14 \times 08000}$$

$$754. \quad \frac{176}{704} := \frac{1^7+6}{7 \times 04}$$

$$\frac{176}{7040} := \frac{1^7+6}{7 \times 040}$$

$$\frac{176}{70400} := \frac{1^7+6}{7 \times 0400}$$

$$\frac{176}{704000} := \frac{1^7+6}{7 \times 04000}$$

$$745. \quad \frac{175}{448} := \frac{1 \times 75}{4 \times 48}$$

$$\frac{175}{4480} := \frac{1 \times 75}{4 \times 480}$$

$$\frac{175}{44800} := \frac{1 \times 75}{4 \times 4800}$$

$$\frac{175}{448000} := \frac{1 \times 75}{4 \times 48000}$$

$$750. \quad \frac{176}{1776} := \frac{1+76}{1+776}$$

$$\frac{176}{17776} := \frac{1+76}{1+7776}$$

$$\frac{176}{177776} := \frac{1+76}{1+77776}$$

$$\frac{176}{1777776} := \frac{1+76}{1+777776}$$

$$755. \quad \frac{176}{768} := \frac{1+76}{7 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{176}{7680} := \frac{1+76}{7 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{176}{76800} := \frac{1+76}{7 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{176}{768000} := \frac{1+76}{7 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$756. \quad \frac{176}{968} := \frac{1+7+6}{9+68}$$

$$\frac{176}{9768} := \frac{1+7+6}{9+768}$$

$$\frac{176}{97768} := \frac{1+7+6}{9+7768}$$

$$\frac{176}{977768} := \frac{1+7+6}{9+77768}$$

$$761. \quad \frac{178}{1068} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{1 \times 06 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{178}{10680} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{1 \times 06 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{178}{106800} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{1 \times 06 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{178}{1068000} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{1 \times 06 \times 8000}$$

$$765. \quad \frac{178}{445} := \frac{1+7+8}{(4+4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{178}{4450} := \frac{1+7+8}{(4+4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{178}{44500} := \frac{1+7+8}{(4+4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{178}{445000} := \frac{1+7+8}{(4+4) \times 5000}$$

$$757. \quad \frac{177}{1180} := \frac{17+7}{(1+1) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{177}{11800} := \frac{17+7}{(1+1) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{177}{118000} := \frac{17+7}{(1+1) \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{177}{1180000} := \frac{17+7}{(1+1) \times 80000}$$

$$762. \quad \frac{178}{1335} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{178}{13350} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{178}{133500} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{178}{1335000} := \frac{1^7 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$766. \quad \frac{178}{979} := \frac{1+7+8}{9+79}$$

$$\frac{178}{9879} := \frac{1+7+8}{9+879}$$

$$\frac{178}{98879} := \frac{1+7+8}{9+8879}$$

$$\frac{178}{988879} := \frac{1+7+8}{9+88879}$$

$$758. \quad \frac{177}{1416} := \frac{1^7+7}{1 \times 4 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{177}{14160} := \frac{1^7+7}{1 \times 4 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{177}{141600} := \frac{1^7+7}{1 \times 4 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{177}{1416000} := \frac{1^7+7}{1 \times 4 \times 16000}$$

$$763. \quad \frac{178}{1424} := \frac{1 \times 7+8}{(1+4) \times 24}$$

$$\frac{178}{14240} := \frac{1 \times 7+8}{(1+4) \times 240}$$

$$\frac{178}{142400} := \frac{1 \times 7+8}{(1+4) \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{178}{1424000} := \frac{1 \times 7+8}{(1+4) \times 24000}$$

$$767. \quad \frac{179}{1432} := \frac{1 \times 7+9}{1 \times 4 \times 32}$$

$$\frac{179}{14320} := \frac{1 \times 7+9}{1 \times 4 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{179}{143200} := \frac{1 \times 7+9}{1 \times 4 \times 3200}$$

$$\frac{179}{1432000} := \frac{1 \times 7+9}{1 \times 4 \times 32000}$$

$$759. \quad \frac{177}{649} := \frac{1+7+7}{6+49}$$

$$\frac{177}{6549} := \frac{1+7+7}{6+549}$$

$$\frac{177}{65549} := \frac{1+7+7}{6+5549}$$

$$\frac{177}{655549} := \frac{1+7+7}{6+55549}$$

$$764. \quad \frac{178}{267} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 8}{2 \times 6 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{178}{2670} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 8}{2 \times 6 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{178}{26700} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 8}{2 \times 6 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{178}{267000} := \frac{1 \times 7 \times 8}{2 \times 6 \times 7000}$$

$$768. \quad \frac{179}{895} := \frac{(1+7) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{179}{8950} := \frac{(1+7) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{179}{89500} := \frac{(1+7) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{179}{895000} := \frac{(1+7) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 5000}$$

$$760. \quad \frac{177}{708} := \frac{1 \times 7+7}{7 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{177}{7080} := \frac{1 \times 7+7}{7 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{177}{70800} := \frac{1 \times 7+7}{7 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{177}{708000} := \frac{1 \times 7+7}{7 \times 08000}$$

$$769. \quad \frac{181}{1267} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{(1 \times 2+6) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{181}{12670} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{(1 \times 2+6) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{181}{126700} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{(1 \times 2+6) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{181}{1267000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{(1 \times 2+6) \times 7000}$$

$$770. \quad \frac{181}{1448} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{1 \times (4+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{181}{14480} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{1 \times (4+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{181}{144800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{1 \times (4+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{181}{1448000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 1}{1 \times (4+4) \times 8000}$$

$$775. \quad \frac{182}{1365} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{182}{13650} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{182}{136500} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{182}{1365000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 5000}$$

$$780. \quad \frac{182}{637} := \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times 3 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{182}{6370} := \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times 3 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{182}{63700} := \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times 3 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{182}{637000} := \frac{18 \times 2}{6 \times 3 \times 7000}$$

$$771. \quad \frac{181}{362} := \frac{18 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{181}{3620} := \frac{18 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{181}{36200} := \frac{18 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{181}{362000} := \frac{18 \times 1}{3 \times 6 \times 2000}$$

$$776. \quad \frac{182}{1554} := \frac{1+8^2}{1+554}$$

$$\frac{182}{15554} := \frac{1+8^2}{1+5554}$$

$$\frac{182}{155554} := \frac{1+8^2}{1+55554}$$

$$\frac{182}{1555554} := \frac{1+8^2}{1+555554}$$

$$781. \quad \frac{182}{728} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(7+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{182}{7280} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(7+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{182}{72800} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(7+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{182}{728000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(7+2) \times 8000}$$

$$772. \quad \frac{181}{543} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{181}{5430} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{181}{54300} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{181}{543000} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 3000}$$

$$777. \quad \frac{182}{364} := \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{182}{3640} := \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{182}{36400} := \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{182}{364000} := \frac{18 \times 2}{3 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$782. \quad \frac{182}{819} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{182}{8190} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{182}{81900} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{182}{819000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 9000}$$

$$773. \quad \frac{181}{724} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{181}{7240} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{181}{72400} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{181}{724000} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{(7+2) \times 4000}$$

$$778. \quad \frac{182}{455} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(4+5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{182}{4550} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(4+5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{182}{45500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(4+5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{182}{455000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(4+5) \times 5000}$$

$$774. \quad \frac{181}{905} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{9 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{181}{9050} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{9 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{181}{90500} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{9 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{181}{905000} := \frac{1+8 \times 1}{9 \times 05000}$$

$$779. \quad \frac{182}{546} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(5+4) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{182}{5460} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(5+4) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{182}{54600} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(5+4) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{182}{546000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{(5+4) \times 6000}$$

$$783. \quad \frac{182}{910} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{9 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{182}{9100} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{9 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{182}{91000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{9 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{182}{910000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 2}{9 \times 10000}$$

$$784. \quad \frac{183}{1098} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 09 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{183}{10980} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 09 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{183}{109800} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 09 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{183}{1098000} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 09 \times 8000}$$

$$789. \quad \frac{183}{366} := \frac{18 \times 3}{3 \times 6 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{183}{3660} := \frac{18 \times 3}{3 \times 6 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{183}{36600} := \frac{18 \times 3}{3 \times 6 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{183}{366000} := \frac{18 \times 3}{3 \times 6 \times 6000}$$

$$794. \quad \frac{184}{1012} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10+12}$$

$$\frac{184}{10212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10+212}$$

$$\frac{184}{102212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10+2212}$$

$$\frac{184}{1022212} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{10+22212}$$

$$785. \quad \frac{183}{1220} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{1^2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{183}{12200} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{1^2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{183}{122000} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{1^2 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{183}{1220000} := \frac{1^8 \times 3}{1^2 \times 20000}$$

$$790. \quad \frac{183}{427} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{4 \times 2 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{183}{4270} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{4 \times 2 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{183}{42700} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{4 \times 2 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{183}{427000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{4 \times 2 \times 7000}$$

$$795. \quad \frac{184}{1242} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1+24+2}$$

$$\frac{184}{12742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1+274+2}$$

$$\frac{184}{127742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1+2774+2}$$

$$\frac{184}{1277742} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{1+27774+2}$$

$$786. \quad \frac{183}{1281} := \frac{1^8+3}{1 \times 28 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{183}{12810} := \frac{1^8+3}{1 \times 28 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{183}{128100} := \frac{1^8+3}{1 \times 28 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{183}{1281000} := \frac{1^8+3}{1 \times 28 \times 1000}$$

$$791. \quad \frac{183}{671} := \frac{18+3}{6+71}$$

$$\frac{183}{6771} := \frac{18+3}{6+771}$$

$$\frac{183}{67771} := \frac{18+3}{6+7771}$$

$$\frac{183}{677771} := \frac{18+3}{6+77771}$$

$$796. \quad \frac{184}{1288} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 28 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{184}{12880} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 28 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{184}{128800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 28 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{184}{1288000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 28 \times 8000}$$

$$787. \quad \frac{183}{1464} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{183}{14640} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{183}{146400} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{183}{1464000} := \frac{1+8+3}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$792. \quad \frac{183}{915} := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{9 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{183}{9150} := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{9 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{183}{91500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{9 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{183}{915000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 3}{9 \times 15000}$$

$$788. \quad \frac{183}{244} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{183}{2440} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{183}{24400} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{183}{244000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 3}{2 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$793. \quad \frac{184}{1012} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{(10+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{184}{10120} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{(10+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{184}{101200} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{(10+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{184}{1012000} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{(10+1) \times 2000}$$

$$797. \quad \frac{184}{1380} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{184}{13800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{184}{138000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{184}{1380000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 3 \times 80000}$$

$$798. \quad \frac{184}{1472} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{184}{14720} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{184}{147200} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{184}{1472000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 72000}$$

$$803. \quad \frac{184}{920} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{184}{9200} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{184}{92000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{184}{920000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 20000}$$

$$808. \quad \frac{184}{506} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+06}$$

$$\frac{184}{5106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+106}$$

$$\frac{184}{51106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+1106}$$

$$\frac{184}{511106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+11106}$$

$$799. \quad \frac{184}{276} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{184}{2760} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{184}{27600} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{184}{276000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 6000}$$

$$804. \quad \frac{184}{1472} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{184}{14720} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{184}{147200} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{184}{1472000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 72000}$$

$$809. \quad \frac{184}{920} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{184}{9200} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{184}{92000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{184}{920000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{9 \times 20000}$$

$$800. \quad \frac{184}{345} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 45}$$

$$\frac{184}{3450} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 450}$$

$$\frac{184}{34500} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 4500}$$

$$\frac{184}{345000} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 45000}$$

$$805. \quad \frac{184}{276} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{184}{2760} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{184}{27600} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{184}{276000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 4}{(2+7) \times 6000}$$

$$810. \quad \frac{185}{1184} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{185}{11840} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{185}{118400} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{185}{1184000} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$801. \quad \frac{184}{368} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{184}{3680} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{184}{36800} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{184}{368000} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$806. \quad \frac{184}{345} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 45}$$

$$\frac{184}{3450} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 450}$$

$$\frac{184}{34500} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 4500}$$

$$\frac{184}{345000} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 45000}$$

$$802. \quad \frac{184}{506} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+06}$$

$$\frac{184}{5106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+106}$$

$$\frac{184}{51106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+1106}$$

$$\frac{184}{511106} := \frac{1^8 \times 4}{5+11106}$$

$$807. \quad \frac{184}{368} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{184}{3680} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{184}{36800} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{184}{368000} := \frac{18 \times 4}{3 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$811. \quad \frac{185}{1221} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12+21}$$

$$\frac{185}{12321} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12+321}$$

$$\frac{185}{123321} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{12+3321}$$

$$812. \quad \frac{185}{1369} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(1+36) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{185}{13690} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(1+36) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{185}{136900} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(1+36) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{185}{1369000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(1+36) \times 9000}$$

$$813. \quad \frac{185}{1480} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{185}{14800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{185}{148000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{185}{1480000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$814. \quad \frac{185}{259} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(2+5) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{185}{2590} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(2+5) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{185}{25900} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(2+5) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{185}{259000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{(2+5) \times 9000}$$

$$815. \quad \frac{185}{333} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{3^3 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{185}{3330} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{3^3 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{185}{33300} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{3^3 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{185}{333000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{3^3 \times 3000}$$

$$816. \quad \frac{185}{407} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4+07}$$

$$\frac{185}{4107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4+107}$$

$$\frac{185}{41107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4+1107}$$

$$\frac{185}{411107} := \frac{1^8 \times 5}{4+11107}$$

$$817. \quad \frac{185}{6660} := \frac{1^8 + 5}{6 \times 6 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{185}{66600} := \frac{1^8 + 5}{6 \times 6 \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{185}{666000} := \frac{1^8 + 5}{6 \times 6 \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{185}{6660000} := \frac{1^8 + 5}{6 \times 6 \times 6000 + 0}$$

$$818. \quad \frac{185}{925} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{9 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{185}{9250} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{9 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{185}{92500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{9 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{185}{925000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 5}{9 \times 25000}$$

$$819. \quad \frac{186}{1023} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10+23}$$

$$\frac{186}{10323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10+323}$$

$$\frac{186}{103323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10+3323}$$

$$\frac{186}{1033323} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{10+33323}$$

$$820. \quad \frac{186}{1116} := \frac{1^{86}}{1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{186}{11160} := \frac{1^{86}}{1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{186}{111600} := \frac{1^{86}}{1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{186}{1116000} := \frac{1^{86}}{1 \times 1 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$821. \quad \frac{186}{1240} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{1^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{186}{12400} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{1^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{186}{124000} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{1^2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{186}{1240000} := \frac{1^8 \times 6}{1^2 \times 40000}$$

$$822. \quad \frac{186}{1395} := \frac{18+6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{186}{13950} := \frac{18+6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{186}{139500} := \frac{18+6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{186}{1395000} := \frac{18+6}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}$$

$$823. \quad \frac{186}{1488} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{1 \times 48 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{186}{14880} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{1 \times 48 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{186}{148800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{1 \times 48 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{186}{1488000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{1 \times 48 \times 8000}$$

$$824. \quad \frac{186}{248} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{2 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{186}{2480} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{2 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{186}{24800} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{2 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{186}{248000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{2 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$825. \quad \frac{186}{279} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{(2+7) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{186}{2790} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{(2+7) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{186}{27900} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{(2+7) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{186}{279000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{(2+7) \times 9000}$$

$$826. \quad \frac{186}{341} := \frac{18+6}{3+41}$$

$$\frac{186}{3441} := \frac{18+6}{3+441}$$

$$\frac{186}{34441} := \frac{18+6}{3+4441}$$

$$\frac{186}{344441} := \frac{18+6}{3+44441}$$

$$831. \quad \frac{186}{930} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{9 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{186}{9300} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{9 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{186}{93000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{9 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{186}{930000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 6}{9 \times 30000}$$

$$836. \quad \frac{187}{935} := \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 35}$$

$$\frac{187}{9350} := \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 350}$$

$$\frac{187}{93500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 3500}$$

$$\frac{187}{935000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 7}{9 \times 35000}$$

$$827. \quad \frac{186}{372} := \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{186}{3720} := \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{186}{37200} := \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{186}{372000} := \frac{18 \times 6}{3 \times 72000}$$

$$832. \quad \frac{187}{1122} := \frac{1^{87}}{(1 \times 1 + 2) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{187}{11220} := \frac{1^{87}}{(1 \times 1 + 2) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{187}{112200} := \frac{1^{87}}{(1 \times 1 + 2) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{187}{1122000} := \frac{1^{87}}{(1 \times 1 + 2) \times 2000}$$

$$837. \quad \frac{188}{1034} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 34}$$

$$\frac{188}{10434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 434}$$

$$\frac{188}{104434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 4434}$$

$$\frac{188}{1044434} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{10 + 44434}$$

$$828. \quad \frac{186}{465} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{4 \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{186}{4650} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{4 \times 6 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{186}{46500} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{4 \times 6 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{186}{465000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 6}{4 \times 6 \times 5000}$$

$$833. \quad \frac{187}{1224} := \frac{1+87}{12^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{187}{12240} := \frac{1+87}{12^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{187}{122400} := \frac{1+87}{12^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{187}{1224000} := \frac{1+87}{12^2 \times 4000}$$

$$838. \quad \frac{188}{1128} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 12 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{188}{11280} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 12 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{188}{112800} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 12 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{188}{1128000} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 12 \times 8000}$$

$$829. \quad \frac{186}{682} := \frac{18+6}{6+82}$$

$$\frac{186}{6882} := \frac{18+6}{6+882}$$

$$\frac{186}{68882} := \frac{18+6}{6+8882}$$

$$\frac{186}{688882} := \frac{18+6}{6+88882}$$

$$834. \quad \frac{187}{1887} := \frac{1+87}{1+887}$$

$$\frac{187}{18887} := \frac{1+87}{1+8887}$$

$$\frac{187}{188887} := \frac{1+87}{1+88887}$$

$$\frac{187}{1888887} := \frac{1+87}{1+888887}$$

$$839. \quad \frac{188}{1269} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{188}{12690} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{188}{126900} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{188}{1269000} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 9000}$$

$$830. \quad \frac{186}{868} := \frac{18+6}{(8+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{186}{8680} := \frac{18+6}{(8+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{186}{86800} := \frac{18+6}{(8+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{186}{868000} := \frac{18+6}{(8+6) \times 8000}$$

$$835. \quad \frac{187}{850} := \frac{1+87}{8 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{187}{8500} := \frac{1+87}{8 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{187}{85000} := \frac{1+87}{8 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{187}{850000} := \frac{1+87}{8 \times 50000}$$

$$840. \quad \frac{188}{1551} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15+51}$$

$$\frac{188}{15651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15+651}$$

$$\frac{188}{156651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15+6651}$$

$$\frac{188}{1566651} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{15+66651}$$

$$841. \quad \frac{188}{423} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{(4+2) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{188}{4230} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{(4+2) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{188}{42300} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{(4+2) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{188}{423000} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{(4+2) \times 3000}$$

$$842. \quad \frac{188}{517} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5+17}$$

$$\frac{188}{5217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5+217}$$

$$\frac{188}{52217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5+2217}$$

$$\frac{188}{522217} := \frac{1^8 \times 8}{5+22217}$$

$$843. \quad \frac{188}{846} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{(8+4) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{188}{8460} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{(8+4) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{188}{84600} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{(8+4) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{188}{846000} := \frac{1 \times 8 + 8}{(8+4) \times 6000}$$

$$844. \quad \frac{188}{940} := \frac{(1+8) \times 8}{9 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{188}{9400} := \frac{(1+8) \times 8}{9 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{188}{94000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 8}{9 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{188}{940000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 8}{9 \times 40000}$$

$$845. \quad \frac{189}{1050} := \frac{1+89}{10 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{189}{10500} := \frac{1+89}{10 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{189}{105000} := \frac{1+89}{10 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{189}{1050000} := \frac{1+89}{10 \times 50000}$$

$$846. \quad \frac{189}{1155} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 55}$$

$$\frac{189}{11550} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 550}$$

$$\frac{189}{115500} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}$$

$$\frac{189}{1155000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}$$

$$847. \quad \frac{189}{1260} := \frac{1+8+9}{1 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{189}{12600} := \frac{1+8+9}{1 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{189}{126000} := \frac{1+8+9}{1 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{189}{1260000} := \frac{1+8+9}{1 \times 2 \times 60000}$$

$$848. \quad \frac{189}{1302} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+30) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{189}{13020} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+30) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{189}{130200} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+30) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{189}{1302000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+30) \times 2000}$$

$$849. \quad \frac{189}{1344} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{189}{13440} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{189}{134400} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{189}{1344000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$850. \quad \frac{189}{1365} := \frac{18+9}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{189}{13650} := \frac{18+9}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{189}{136500} := \frac{18+9}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{189}{1365000} := \frac{18+9}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}$$

$$851. \quad \frac{189}{1386} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{189}{13860} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{189}{138600} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{189}{1386000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$852. \quad \frac{189}{1428} := \frac{1+8+9}{(1+4^2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{189}{14280} := \frac{1+8+9}{(1+4^2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{189}{142800} := \frac{1+8+9}{(1+4^2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{189}{1428000} := \frac{1+8+9}{(1+4^2) \times 8000}$$

$$853. \quad \frac{189}{1470} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{189}{14700} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{189}{147000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{189}{1470000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{1^4 \times 70000}$$

$$854. \quad \frac{189}{210} := \frac{1+8+9}{2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{189}{2100} := \frac{1+8+9}{2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{189}{21000} := \frac{1+8+9}{2 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{189}{210000} := \frac{1+8+9}{2 \times 10000}$$

$$855. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{231} := \frac{18+9}{2+31} \\ \frac{189}{2331} := \frac{18+9}{2+331} \\ \frac{189}{23331} := \frac{18+9}{2+3331} \\ \frac{189}{233331} := \frac{18+9}{2+33331} \end{array}$$

$$860. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{525} := \frac{1+8+9}{5 \times 2 \times 5} \\ \frac{189}{5250} := \frac{1+8+9}{5 \times 2 \times 50} \\ \frac{189}{52500} := \frac{1+8+9}{5 \times 2 \times 500} \\ \frac{189}{525000} := \frac{1+8+9}{5 \times 2 \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$865. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{896} := \frac{18 \times 9}{8 \times 96} \\ \frac{189}{8960} := \frac{18 \times 9}{8 \times 960} \\ \frac{189}{89600} := \frac{18 \times 9}{8 \times 9600} \\ \frac{189}{896000} := \frac{18 \times 9}{8 \times 96000} \end{array}$$

$$856. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{315} := \frac{18+9}{3 \times 15} \\ \frac{189}{3150} := \frac{18+9}{3 \times 150} \\ \frac{189}{31500} := \frac{18+9}{3 \times 1500} \\ \frac{189}{315000} := \frac{18+9}{3 \times 15000} \end{array}$$

$$861. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{693} := \frac{18+9}{6+93} \\ \frac{189}{6993} := \frac{18+9}{6+993} \\ \frac{189}{69993} := \frac{18+9}{6+9993} \\ \frac{189}{699993} := \frac{18+9}{6+99993} \end{array}$$

$$866. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{924} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(9+2) \times 4} \\ \frac{189}{9240} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(9+2) \times 40} \\ \frac{189}{92400} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(9+2) \times 400} \\ \frac{189}{924000} := \frac{1^8 \times 9}{(9+2) \times 4000} \end{array}$$

$$857. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{350} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{3 \times 50} \\ \frac{189}{3500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{3 \times 500} \\ \frac{189}{35000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{3 \times 5000} \\ \frac{189}{350000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{3 \times 50000} \end{array}$$

$$862. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{735} := \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\ \frac{189}{7350} := \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\ \frac{189}{73500} := \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\ \frac{189}{735000} := \frac{18+9}{7 \times 3 \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$867. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{945} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{9 \times 45} \\ \frac{189}{9450} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{9 \times 450} \\ \frac{189}{94500} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{9 \times 4500} \\ \frac{189}{945000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{9 \times 45000} \end{array}$$

$$858. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{448} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{4 \times 48} \\ \frac{189}{4480} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{4 \times 480} \\ \frac{189}{44800} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{4 \times 4800} \\ \frac{189}{448000} := \frac{(1+8) \times 9}{4 \times 48000} \end{array}$$

$$863. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{756} := \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 6} \\ \frac{189}{7560} := \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 60} \\ \frac{189}{75600} := \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 600} \\ \frac{189}{756000} := \frac{1+8+9}{(7+5) \times 6000} \end{array}$$

$$868. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{190}{1045} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+45} \\ \frac{190}{10545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+545} \\ \frac{190}{105545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+5545} \\ \frac{190}{1055545} := \frac{1+9+0}{10+55545} \end{array}$$

$$859. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{462} := \frac{18+9}{4+62} \\ \frac{189}{4662} := \frac{18+9}{4+662} \\ \frac{189}{46662} := \frac{18+9}{4+6662} \\ \frac{189}{466662} := \frac{18+9}{4+66662} \end{array}$$

$$864. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{189}{840} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9}{8 \times 40} \\ \frac{189}{8400} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9}{8 \times 400} \\ \frac{189}{84000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9}{8 \times 4000} \\ \frac{189}{840000} := \frac{1 \times 8 \times 9}{8 \times 40000} \end{array}$$

$$869. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{190}{1254} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+54} \\ \frac{190}{12654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+654} \\ \frac{190}{126654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+6654} \\ \frac{190}{1266654} := \frac{1+9+0}{12+66654} \end{array}$$

$$870. \quad \frac{190}{1463} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{190}{14763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{190}{147763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{190}{1477763} := \frac{1+9+0}{14+77763}$$

$$875. \quad \frac{190}{836} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{190}{8436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{190}{84436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{190}{844436} := \frac{1+9+0}{8+44436}$$

$$880. \quad \frac{192}{1280} := \frac{1+9+2}{1^2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{192}{12800} := \frac{1+9+2}{1^2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{192}{128000} := \frac{1+9+2}{1^2 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{192}{1280000} := \frac{1+9+2}{1^2 \times 80000}$$

$$871. \quad \frac{190}{1881} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+81}$$

$$\frac{190}{18981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+981}$$

$$\frac{190}{189981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+9981}$$

$$\frac{190}{1899981} := \frac{1+9+0}{18+99981}$$

$$876. \quad \frac{191}{1337} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{191}{13370} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{191}{133700} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{191}{1337000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 7000}$$

$$881. \quad \frac{192}{1344} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{(1+34) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{192}{13440} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{(1+34) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{192}{134400} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{(1+34) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{192}{1344000} := \frac{(1+9) \times 2}{(1+34) \times 4000}$$

$$872. \quad \frac{190}{209} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+09}$$

$$\frac{190}{2109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+109}$$

$$\frac{190}{21109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+1109}$$

$$\frac{190}{211109} := \frac{1+9+0}{2+11109}$$

$$877. \quad \frac{191}{382} := \frac{1+9+1}{(3+8) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{191}{3820} := \frac{1+9+1}{(3+8) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{191}{38200} := \frac{1+9+1}{(3+8) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{191}{382000} := \frac{1+9+1}{(3+8) \times 2000}$$

$$882. \quad \frac{192}{528} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+28}$$

$$\frac{192}{5328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+328}$$

$$\frac{192}{53328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+3328}$$

$$\frac{192}{533328} := \frac{1+9+2}{5+33328}$$

$$873. \quad \frac{190}{418} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{190}{4218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{190}{42218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{190}{422218} := \frac{1+9+0}{4+22218}$$

$$878. \quad \frac{192}{1056} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+56}$$

$$\frac{192}{10656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+656}$$

$$\frac{192}{106656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+6656}$$

$$\frac{192}{1066656} := \frac{1+9+2}{10+66656}$$

$$883. \quad \frac{192}{704} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+04}$$

$$\frac{192}{7104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+104}$$

$$\frac{192}{71104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+1104}$$

$$\frac{192}{711104} := \frac{1^9+2}{7+11104}$$

$$874. \quad \frac{190}{627} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{190}{6327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{190}{63327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{190}{633327} := \frac{1+9+0}{6+33327}$$

$$879. \quad \frac{192}{1152} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{1 \times (1+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{192}{11520} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{1 \times (1+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{192}{115200} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{1 \times (1+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{192}{1152000} := \frac{1^9 \times 2}{1 \times (1+5) \times 2000}$$

$$884. \quad \frac{194}{1067} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+67}$$

$$\frac{194}{10767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+767}$$

$$\frac{194}{107767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+7767}$$

$$\frac{194}{1077767} := \frac{1+9+4}{10+77767}$$

$$885. \quad \frac{194}{1164} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{194}{11640} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{194}{116400} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{194}{1164000} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$886. \quad \frac{194}{1261} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 26 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{194}{12610} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 26 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{194}{126100} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 26 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{194}{1261000} := \frac{1^9 \times 4}{1 \times 26 \times 1000}$$

$$887. \quad \frac{194}{1358} := \frac{(1+9) \times 4}{1 \times 35 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{194}{13580} := \frac{(1+9) \times 4}{1 \times 35 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{194}{135800} := \frac{(1+9) \times 4}{1 \times 35 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{194}{1358000} := \frac{(1+9) \times 4}{1 \times 35 \times 8000}$$

$$888. \quad \frac{194}{1455} := \frac{1+9+4}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{194}{14550} := \frac{1+9+4}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{194}{145500} := \frac{1+9+4}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{194}{1455000} := \frac{1+9+4}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 5000}$$

$$889. \quad \frac{195}{1144} := \frac{1+9+5}{(1+1) \times 44}$$

$$\frac{195}{11440} := \frac{1+9+5}{(1+1) \times 440}$$

$$\frac{195}{114400} := \frac{1+9+5}{(1+1) \times 4400}$$

$$\frac{195}{1144000} := \frac{1+9+5}{(1+1) \times 44000}$$

$$890. \quad \frac{195}{1287} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{195}{12987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{195}{129987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+9987}$$

$$\frac{195}{1299987} := \frac{1+9+5}{12+99987}$$

$$891. \quad \frac{195}{1300} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{1 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{195}{13000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{1 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{195}{130000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{1 \times 30000}$$

$$\frac{195}{1300000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{1 \times 300000}$$

$$892. \quad \frac{195}{1365} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(1^3+6) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{195}{13650} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(1^3+6) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{195}{136500} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(1^3+6) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{195}{1365000} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(1^3+6) \times 5000}$$

$$893. \quad \frac{195}{208} := \frac{1+9+5}{2 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{195}{2080} := \frac{1+9+5}{2 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{195}{20800} := \frac{1+9+5}{2 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{195}{208000} := \frac{1+9+5}{2 \times 08000}$$

$$894. \quad \frac{195}{312} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(3+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{195}{3120} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(3+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{195}{31200} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(3+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{195}{312000} := \frac{1^9 \times 5}{(3+1) \times 2000}$$

$$895. \quad \frac{195}{325} := \frac{1+95}{32 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{195}{3250} := \frac{1+95}{32 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{195}{32500} := \frac{1+95}{32 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{195}{325000} := \frac{1+95}{32 \times 5000}$$

$$896. \quad \frac{195}{429} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+29}$$

$$\frac{195}{4329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+329}$$

$$\frac{195}{43329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+3329}$$

$$\frac{195}{433329} := \frac{1+9+5}{4+33329}$$

$$897. \quad \frac{195}{624} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{195}{6240} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{195}{62400} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{195}{624000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 5}{6 \times 24000}$$

$$898. \quad \frac{195}{715} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+15}$$

$$\frac{195}{7215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+215}$$

$$\frac{195}{72215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+2215}$$

$$\frac{195}{722215} := \frac{1^9+5}{7+22215}$$

$$899. \quad \frac{195}{780} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 5}{7 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{195}{7800} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 5}{7 \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{195}{78000} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 5}{7 \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{195}{780000} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 5}{7 \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$900. \quad \frac{195}{858} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{8 + 58}$$

$$\frac{195}{8658} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{8 + 658}$$

$$\frac{195}{86658} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{8 + 6658}$$

$$\frac{195}{866658} := \frac{1 + 9 + 5}{8 + 66658}$$

$$901. \quad \frac{196}{1078} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{10 + 78}$$

$$\frac{196}{10878} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{10 + 878}$$

$$\frac{196}{108878} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{10 + 8878}$$

$$\frac{196}{1088878} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{10 + 88878}$$

$$902. \quad \frac{196}{1120} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{(1 + 1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{196}{11200} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{(1 + 1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{196}{112000} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{(1 + 1) \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{196}{1120000} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{(1 + 1) \times 20000}$$

$$903. \quad \frac{196}{1176} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{196}{11760} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{196}{117600} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{196}{1176000} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

$$904. \quad \frac{196}{1344} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{196}{13440} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{196}{134400} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{196}{1344000} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$905. \quad \frac{196}{1372} := \frac{1^9 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{196}{13720} := \frac{1^9 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{196}{137200} := \frac{1^9 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{196}{1372000} := \frac{1^9 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$906. \quad \frac{196}{1512} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 + 51 + 2}$$

$$\frac{196}{15512} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 + 551 + 2}$$

$$\frac{196}{155512} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 + 5551 + 2}$$

$$\frac{196}{1555512} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{1 + 55551 + 2}$$

$$907. \quad \frac{196}{245} := \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{196}{2450} := \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{196}{24500} := \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{196}{245000} := \frac{1 \times 96}{24 \times 5000}$$

$$908. \quad \frac{196}{308} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{3 + 08}$$

$$\frac{196}{3108} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{3 + 108}$$

$$\frac{196}{31108} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{3 + 1108}$$

$$\frac{196}{311108} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{3 + 11108}$$

$$909. \quad \frac{196}{539} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{5 + 39}$$

$$\frac{196}{5439} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{5 + 439}$$

$$\frac{196}{54439} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{5 + 4439}$$

$$\frac{196}{544439} := \frac{1 + 9 + 6}{5 + 44439}$$

$$910. \quad \frac{196}{616} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{6 + 16}$$

$$\frac{196}{6216} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{6 + 216}$$

$$\frac{196}{62216} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{6 + 2216}$$

$$\frac{196}{622216} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{6 + 22216}$$

$$911. \quad \frac{196}{784} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 6}{(7 + 8) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{196}{7840} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 6}{(7 + 8) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{196}{78400} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 6}{(7 + 8) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{196}{784000} := \frac{1 \times 9 + 6}{(7 + 8) \times 4000}$$

$$912. \quad \frac{196}{924} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{9 + 24}$$

$$\frac{196}{9324} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{9 + 324}$$

$$\frac{196}{93324} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{9 + 3324}$$

$$\frac{196}{933324} := \frac{1^9 + 6}{9 + 33324}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 913. \quad & \frac{197}{985} := \frac{1+97}{98 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{197}{9850} := \frac{1+97}{98 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{197}{98500} := \frac{1+97}{98 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{197}{985000} := \frac{1+97}{98 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 918. \quad & \frac{198}{1352} := \frac{1+98}{13 \times 52} \\
 & \frac{198}{13520} := \frac{1+98}{13 \times 520} \\
 & \frac{198}{135200} := \frac{1+98}{13 \times 5200} \\
 & \frac{198}{1352000} := \frac{1+98}{13 \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 922. \quad & \frac{198}{352} := \frac{1^9+8}{(3+5) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{198}{3520} := \frac{1^9+8}{(3+5) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{198}{35200} := \frac{1^9+8}{(3+5) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{198}{352000} := \frac{1^9+8}{(3+5) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 914. \quad & \frac{198}{1089} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+89} \\
 & \frac{198}{10989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+989} \\
 & \frac{198}{109989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+9989} \\
 & \frac{198}{1099989} := \frac{1+9+8}{10+99989}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 919. \quad & \frac{198}{1386} := \frac{1+9+8}{(13+8) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{198}{13860} := \frac{1+9+8}{(13+8) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{198}{138600} := \frac{1+9+8}{(13+8) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{198}{1386000} := \frac{1+9+8}{(13+8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 923. \quad & \frac{198}{360} := \frac{1+98}{3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{198}{3600} := \frac{1+98}{3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{198}{36000} := \frac{1+98}{3 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{198}{360000} := \frac{1+98}{3 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 915. \quad & \frac{198}{1100} := \frac{1+9+8}{1 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{198}{11000} := \frac{1+9+8}{1 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{198}{110000} := \frac{1+9+8}{1 \times 10000} \\
 & \frac{198}{1100000} := \frac{1+9+8}{1 \times 100000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 920. \quad & \frac{198}{1452} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+52} \\
 & \frac{198}{14652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+652} \\
 & \frac{198}{146652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+6652} \\
 & \frac{198}{1466652} := \frac{1^9+8}{14+66652}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 924. \quad & \frac{198}{440} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 8}{4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{198}{4400} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 8}{4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{198}{44000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 8}{4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{198}{440000} := \frac{1 \times 9 \times 8}{4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 916. \quad & \frac{198}{1296} := \frac{1+98}{12 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{198}{12960} := \frac{1+98}{12 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{198}{129600} := \frac{1+98}{12 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{198}{1296000} := \frac{1+98}{12 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 921. \quad & \frac{198}{1485} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{198}{14850} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{198}{148500} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{198}{1485000} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 925. \quad & \frac{198}{495} := \frac{19 \times 8}{4 \times 95} \\
 & \frac{198}{4950} := \frac{19 \times 8}{4 \times 950} \\
 & \frac{198}{49500} := \frac{19 \times 8}{4 \times 9500} \\
 & \frac{198}{495000} := \frac{19 \times 8}{4 \times 95000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 917. \quad & \frac{198}{1320} := \frac{1^9+8}{1 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{198}{13200} := \frac{1^9+8}{1 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{198}{132000} := \frac{1^9+8}{1 \times 3 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{198}{1320000} := \frac{1^9+8}{1 \times 3 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 926. \quad & \frac{198}{550} := \frac{1^9+8}{5 \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \frac{198}{5500} := \frac{1^9+8}{5 \times 50 + 0} \\
 & \frac{198}{55000} := \frac{1^9+8}{5 \times 500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{198}{550000} := \frac{1^9+8}{5 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

927.

$$\frac{198}{726} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7 + 26}$$

$$\frac{198}{7326} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7 + 326}$$

$$\frac{198}{73326} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7 + 3326}$$

$$\frac{198}{733326} := \frac{1^9 + 8}{7 + 33326}$$

932.

$$\frac{202}{1010} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1 \times 010}$$

$$\frac{202}{10100} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1 \times 0100}$$

$$\frac{202}{101000} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1 \times 010000}$$

937.

$$\frac{202}{1414} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^4 \times 14}$$

$$\frac{202}{14140} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^4 \times 140}$$

$$\frac{202}{141400} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^4 \times 1400}$$

928.

$$\frac{198}{792} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{198}{7920} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{198}{79200} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{198}{792000} := \frac{1^9 \times 8}{(7 + 9) \times 2000}$$

933.

$$\frac{202}{1111} := \frac{20 + 2}{11 \times 11}$$

$$\frac{202}{11110} := \frac{20 + 2}{11 \times 110}$$

$$\frac{202}{111100} := \frac{20 + 2}{11 \times 1100}$$

$$\frac{202}{1111000} := \frac{20 + 2}{11 \times 11000}$$

938.

$$\frac{203}{1015} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{(1 + 01) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{203}{10150} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{(1 + 01) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{203}{101500} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{(1 + 01) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{203}{1015000} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 3}{(1 + 01) \times 5000}$$

929.

$$\frac{199}{995} := \frac{1 \times 99}{99 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{199}{9950} := \frac{1 \times 99}{99 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{199}{99500} := \frac{1 \times 99}{99 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{199}{995000} := \frac{1 \times 99}{99 \times 5000}$$

934.

$$\frac{202}{1111} := \frac{2^{02}}{11 + 11}$$

$$\frac{202}{11211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11 + 211}$$

$$\frac{202}{112211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11 + 2211}$$

$$\frac{202}{1122211} := \frac{2^{02}}{11 + 22211}$$

939.

$$\frac{203}{1421} := \frac{2 \times 03}{1 \times 42 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{203}{14210} := \frac{2 \times 03}{1 \times (42 \times 10)}$$

$$\frac{203}{142100} := \frac{2 \times 03}{1 \times (42 \times 100)}$$

$$\frac{203}{1421000} := \frac{2 \times 03}{1 \times (42 \times 1000)}$$

930.

$$\frac{201}{1072} := \frac{2 + 01}{(1 + 07) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{201}{10720} := \frac{2 + 01}{(1 + 07) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{201}{107200} := \frac{2 + 01}{(1 + 07) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{201}{1072000} := \frac{2 + 01}{(1 + 07) \times 2000}$$

935.

$$\frac{202}{1212} := \frac{2^{02}}{1 \times 2 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{202}{12120} := \frac{2^{02}}{1 \times 2 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{202}{121200} := \frac{2^{02}}{1 \times 2 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{202}{1212000} := \frac{2^{02}}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}$$

931.

$$\frac{201}{1206} := \frac{20 \times 1}{1 \times 20 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{201}{12060} := \frac{20 \times 1}{1 \times 20 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{201}{120600} := \frac{20 \times 1}{1 \times 20 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{201}{1206000} := \frac{20 \times 1}{1 \times 20 \times 6000}$$

936.

$$\frac{202}{1313} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^3 \times 13}$$

$$\frac{202}{13130} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^3 \times 130}$$

$$\frac{202}{131300} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^3 \times 1300}$$

$$\frac{202}{1313000} := \frac{2 + 0 \times 2}{1^3 \times 13000}$$

940.

$$\frac{204}{1122} := \frac{2 \times 04}{11 \times 2 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{204}{11220} := \frac{2 \times 04}{11 \times 2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{204}{112200} := \frac{2 \times 04}{11 \times 2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{204}{1122000} := \frac{2 \times 04}{11 \times 2 \times 2000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 941. \quad & \frac{204}{1122} := \frac{2+04}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{204}{11322} := \frac{2+04}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{204}{113322} := \frac{2+04}{11+3322} \\
 & \frac{204}{1133322} := \frac{2+04}{11+33322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 946. \quad & \frac{204}{1428} := \frac{2 \times 04}{(1+4+2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{204}{14280} := \frac{2 \times 04}{(1+4+2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{204}{142800} := \frac{2 \times 04}{(1+4+2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{204}{1428000} := \frac{2 \times 04}{(1+4+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 951. \quad & \frac{204}{510} := \frac{2+0 \times 4}{5 \times 1+0} \\
 & \frac{204}{5100} := \frac{2+0 \times 4}{5 \times 10+0} \\
 & \frac{204}{51000} := \frac{2+0 \times 4}{5 \times 100+0} \\
 & \frac{204}{510000} := \frac{2+0 \times 4}{5 \times 1000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 942. \quad & \frac{204}{1224} := \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times 2 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{204}{12240} := \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times 2 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{204}{122400} := \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times 2 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{204}{1224000} := \frac{2 \times 04}{1 \times 2 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 947. \quad & \frac{204}{1734} := \frac{20+4}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{204}{17340} := \frac{20+4}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{204}{173400} := \frac{20+4}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{204}{1734000} := \frac{20+4}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 952. \quad & \frac{204}{561} := \frac{20+4}{5+61} \\
 & \frac{204}{5661} := \frac{20+4}{5+661} \\
 & \frac{204}{56661} := \frac{20+4}{5+6661} \\
 & \frac{204}{566661} := \frac{20+4}{5+66661}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 943. \quad & \frac{204}{1275} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{204}{12750} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{204}{127500} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{204}{1275000} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 948. \quad & \frac{204}{17374} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{204}{173740} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{204}{1737400} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{204}{17374000} := \frac{20+4}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 953. \quad & \frac{204}{612} := \frac{20+4}{6 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{204}{6120} := \frac{20+4}{6 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{204}{61200} := \frac{20+4}{6 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{204}{612000} := \frac{20+4}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 944. \quad & \frac{204}{1292} := \frac{2+04}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{204}{12920} := \frac{2+04}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{204}{129200} := \frac{2+04}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{204}{1292000} := \frac{2+04}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 949. \quad & \frac{204}{408} := \frac{2^{04}}{4 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{204}{4080} := \frac{2^{04}}{4 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{204}{40800} := \frac{2^{04}}{4 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{204}{408000} := \frac{2^{04}}{4 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 954. \quad & \frac{204}{714} := \frac{2 \times 04}{7 \times 1 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{204}{7140} := \frac{2 \times 04}{7 \times 1 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{204}{71400} := \frac{2 \times 04}{7 \times 1 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{204}{714000} := \frac{2 \times 04}{7 \times 1 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 945. \quad & \frac{204}{1326} := \frac{20+4}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{204}{13260} := \frac{20+4}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{204}{132600} := \frac{20+4}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{204}{1326000} := \frac{20+4}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 950. \quad & \frac{204}{459} := \frac{20 \times 4}{4 \times 5 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{204}{4590} := \frac{20 \times 4}{4 \times 5 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{204}{45900} := \frac{20 \times 4}{4 \times 5 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{204}{459000} := \frac{20 \times 4}{4 \times 5 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 955. \quad & \frac{204}{748} := \frac{20+4}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{204}{7480} := \frac{20+4}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{204}{74800} := \frac{20+4}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{204}{748000} := \frac{20+4}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$956. \quad \frac{204}{918} := \frac{2^{04}}{9 \times 1 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{204}{9180} := \frac{2^{04}}{9 \times 1 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{204}{91800} := \frac{2^{04}}{9 \times 1 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{204}{918000} := \frac{2^{04}}{9 \times 1 \times 8000}$$

$$961. \quad \frac{205}{14350} := \frac{205}{(1+4) \times 350}$$

$$\frac{205}{143500} := \frac{205}{(1+4) \times 3500}$$

$$\frac{205}{1435000} := \frac{205}{(1+4) \times 35000}$$

$$966. \quad \frac{205}{1435} := \frac{20+5206}{(1+4) \times 1336} := \frac{2 \times 06}{1 \times 2 \times 36}$$

$$\frac{206}{12360} := \frac{2 \times 06}{1 \times 2 \times 360}$$

$$\frac{206}{123600} := \frac{2 \times 06}{1 \times 2 \times 3600}$$

$$\frac{206}{1236000} := \frac{2 \times 06}{1 \times 2 \times 36000}$$

$$957. \quad \frac{204}{952} := \frac{2+04}{(9+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{204}{9520} := \frac{2+04}{(9+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{204}{95200} := \frac{2+04}{(9+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{204}{952000} := \frac{2+04}{(9+5) \times 2000}$$

$$962. \quad \frac{205}{1476} := \frac{2 \times 05}{(1+4+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{205}{14760} := \frac{2 \times 05}{(1+4+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{205}{147600} := \frac{2 \times 05}{(1+4+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{205}{1476000} := \frac{2 \times 05}{(1+4+7) \times 6000}$$

$$967. \quad \frac{206}{515} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(5+1) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{206}{5150} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(5+1) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{206}{51500} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(5+1) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{206}{515000} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(5+1) \times 5000}$$

$$958. \quad \frac{205}{1025} := \frac{2+0 \times 5}{1 \times 02 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{205}{10250} := \frac{2+0 \times 5}{1 \times 02 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{205}{102500} := \frac{2+0 \times 5}{1 \times 02 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{205}{1025000} := \frac{2+0 \times 5}{1 \times 02 \times 5000}$$

$$963. \quad \frac{205}{451} := \frac{20+5}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{205}{4551} := \frac{20+5}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{205}{45551} := \frac{20+5}{4+5551}$$

$$968. \quad \frac{206}{824} := \frac{2^{06}}{8^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{206}{8240} := \frac{2^{06}}{8^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{206}{82400} := \frac{2^{06}}{8^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{206}{824000} := \frac{2^{06}}{8^2 \times 4000}$$

$$959. \quad \frac{205}{1230} := \frac{2 \times 05}{1 \times 2 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{205}{12300} := \frac{2 \times 05}{1 \times 2 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{205}{123000} := \frac{2 \times 05}{1 \times 2 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{205}{1230000} := \frac{2 \times 05}{1 \times 2 \times 30000}$$

$$964. \quad \frac{206}{1133} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(1+1) \times 33}$$

$$\frac{206}{11330} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(1+1) \times 330}$$

$$\frac{206}{113300} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(1+1) \times 3300}$$

$$\frac{206}{1133000} := \frac{2 \times 06}{(1+1) \times 33000}$$

$$969. \quad \frac{207}{1150} := \frac{20+7}{1 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{207}{11500} := \frac{20+7}{1 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{207}{115000} := \frac{20+7}{1 \times 15000}$$

$$960. \quad \frac{205}{1353} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+53}$$

$$\frac{205}{13653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+653}$$

$$\frac{205}{136653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+6653}$$

$$\frac{205}{1366653} := \frac{2 \times 05}{13+66653}$$

$$965. \quad \frac{206}{1133} := \frac{2+06}{11+33}$$

$$\frac{206}{11433} := \frac{2+06}{11+433}$$

$$\frac{206}{114433} := \frac{2+06}{11+4433}$$

$$\frac{206}{1144433} := \frac{2+06}{11+44433}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 970. \quad & \frac{207}{1173} := \frac{2+07}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{207}{11730} := \frac{2+07}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{207}{117300} := \frac{2+07}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{207}{1173000} := \frac{2+07}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 975. \quad & \frac{208}{13520} := \frac{2+0 \times 8}{13 \times 5 \times 2+0} \\
 & \frac{208}{135200} := \frac{2+0 \times 8}{13 \times 5 \times 20+0} \\
 & \frac{208}{1352000} := \frac{2+0 \times 8}{13 \times 5 \times 200+0} \\
 & \frac{208}{13520000} := \frac{2+0 \times 8}{13 \times 5 \times 2000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 980. \quad & \frac{208}{858} := \frac{2 \times 08}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{208}{8658} := \frac{2 \times 08}{8+658} \\
 & \frac{208}{86658} := \frac{2 \times 08}{8+6658} \\
 & \frac{208}{866658} := \frac{2 \times 08}{8+66658}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 971. \quad & \frac{207}{1242} := \frac{2 \times 07}{1 \times 2 \times 42} \\
 & \frac{207}{12420} := \frac{2 \times 07}{1 \times 2 \times 420} \\
 & \frac{207}{124200} := \frac{2 \times 07}{1 \times 2 \times 4200} \\
 & \frac{207}{1242000} := \frac{2 \times 07}{1 \times 2 \times 42000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 976. \quad & \frac{208}{429} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+29} \\
 & \frac{208}{4329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+329} \\
 & \frac{208}{43329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+3329} \\
 & \frac{208}{433329} := \frac{2 \times 08}{4+33329}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 981. \quad & \frac{209}{1045} := \frac{2+09}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{209}{10545} := \frac{2+09}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{209}{105545} := \frac{2+09}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{209}{1055545} := \frac{2+09}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 972. \quad & \frac{207}{828} := \frac{2^{07}}{8^2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{207}{8280} := \frac{2^{07}}{8^2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{207}{82800} := \frac{2^{07}}{8^2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{207}{828000} := \frac{2^{07}}{8^2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 977. \quad & \frac{208}{572} := \frac{20+8}{5+72} \\
 & \frac{208}{5772} := \frac{20+8}{5+772} \\
 & \frac{208}{57772} := \frac{20+8}{5+7772} \\
 & \frac{208}{577772} := \frac{20+8}{5+77772}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 982. \quad & \frac{209}{1197} := \frac{2+09}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{209}{11970} := \frac{2+09}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{209}{119700} := \frac{2+09}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{209}{1197000} := \frac{2+09}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 973. \quad & \frac{208}{1144} := \frac{2 \times 08}{(1+1) \times 44} \\
 & \frac{208}{11440} := \frac{2 \times 08}{(1+1) \times 440} \\
 & \frac{208}{114400} := \frac{2 \times 08}{(1+1) \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{208}{1144000} := \frac{2 \times 08}{(1+1) \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 978. \quad & \frac{208}{624} := \frac{2 \times 08}{6 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{208}{6240} := \frac{2 \times 08}{6 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{208}{62400} := \frac{2 \times 08}{6 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{208}{624000} := \frac{2 \times 08}{6 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 983. \quad & \frac{209}{1254} := \frac{2 \times 09}{1 \times 2 \times 54} \\
 & \frac{209}{12540} := \frac{2 \times 09}{1 \times 2 \times 540} \\
 & \frac{209}{125400} := \frac{2 \times 09}{1 \times 2 \times 5400} \\
 & \frac{209}{1254000} := \frac{2 \times 09}{1 \times 2 \times 54000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 974. \quad & \frac{208}{1248} := \frac{2 \times 08}{1 \times 2 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{208}{12480} := \frac{2 \times 08}{1 \times 2 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{208}{124800} := \frac{2 \times 08}{1 \times 2 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{208}{1248000} := \frac{2 \times 08}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 979. \quad & \frac{208}{832} := \frac{2^{08}}{8^3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{208}{8320} := \frac{2^{08}}{8^3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{208}{83200} := \frac{2^{08}}{8^3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{208}{832000} := \frac{2^{08}}{8^3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 984. \quad & \frac{209}{1254} := \frac{2+09}{12+54} \\
 & \frac{209}{12654} := \frac{2+09}{12+654} \\
 & \frac{209}{126654} := \frac{2+09}{12+6654} \\
 & \frac{209}{1266654} := \frac{2+09}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 985. \quad & \frac{209}{1368} := \frac{2+09}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{209}{13680} := \frac{2+09}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{209}{136800} := \frac{2+09}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{209}{1368000} := \frac{2+09}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 990. \quad & \frac{209}{627} := \frac{2+09}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{209}{6327} := \frac{2+09}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{209}{63327} := \frac{2+09}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{209}{633327} := \frac{2+09}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 995. \quad & \frac{211}{1477} := \frac{21 \times 1}{(14+7) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{211}{14770} := \frac{21 \times 1}{(14+7) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{211}{147700} := \frac{21 \times 1}{(14+7) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{211}{1477000} := \frac{21 \times 1}{(14+7) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 986. \quad & \frac{209}{1463} := \frac{2+09}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{209}{14763} := \frac{2+09}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{209}{147763} := \frac{2+09}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{209}{1477763} := \frac{2+09}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 991. \quad & \frac{209}{836} := \frac{2+09}{8+36} \\
 & \frac{209}{8436} := \frac{2+09}{8+436} \\
 & \frac{209}{84436} := \frac{2+09}{8+4436} \\
 & \frac{209}{844436} := \frac{2+09}{8+44436}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 996. \quad & \frac{212}{1166} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(1+1) \times 66} \\
 & \frac{212}{11660} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(1+1) \times 660} \\
 & \frac{212}{116600} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(1+1) \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{212}{1166000} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(1+1) \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 987. \quad & \frac{209}{1672} := \frac{2+09}{16+72} \\
 & \frac{209}{16872} := \frac{2+09}{16+872} \\
 & \frac{209}{168872} := \frac{2+09}{16+8872} \\
 & \frac{209}{1688872} := \frac{2+09}{16+88872}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 992. \quad & \frac{210}{1155} := \frac{2+10}{11+55} \\
 & \frac{210}{11655} := \frac{2+10}{11+655} \\
 & \frac{210}{116655} := \frac{2+10}{11+6655} \\
 & \frac{210}{1166655} := \frac{2+10}{11+66655}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 997. \quad & \frac{212}{1272} := \frac{2 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{212}{12720} := \frac{2 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{212}{127200} := \frac{2 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{212}{1272000} := \frac{2 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 988. \quad & \frac{209}{4180} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(4+1) \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{209}{41800} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(4+1) \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{209}{418000} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(4+1) \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{209}{4180000} := \frac{2+0 \times 9}{(4+1) \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 993. \quad & \frac{210}{1225} := \frac{2+10}{(12+2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{210}{12250} := \frac{2+10}{(12+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{210}{122500} := \frac{2+10}{(12+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{210}{1225000} := \frac{2+10}{(12+2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 998. \quad & \frac{212}{1325} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{212}{13250} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{212}{132500} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{212}{1325000} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 989. \quad & \frac{209}{418} := \frac{2+09}{4+18} \\
 & \frac{209}{4218} := \frac{2+09}{4+218} \\
 & \frac{209}{42218} := \frac{2+09}{4+2218} \\
 & \frac{209}{422218} := \frac{2+09}{4+22218}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 994. \quad & \frac{211}{1266} := \frac{2 \times 11}{1 \times 2 \times 66} \\
 & \frac{211}{12660} := \frac{2 \times 11}{1 \times 2 \times 660} \\
 & \frac{211}{126600} := \frac{2 \times 11}{1 \times 2 \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{211}{1266000} := \frac{2 \times 11}{1 \times 2 \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$999. \quad \frac{212}{14840} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{(1+4) \times 84 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{148400} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{(1+4) \times 840 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{1484000} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{(1+4) \times 8400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{14840000} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{(1+4) \times 84000 + 0}$$

$$1004. \quad \frac{213}{1065} := \frac{2+1+3}{1 \times 06 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{213}{10650} := \frac{2+1+3}{1 \times 06 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{213}{106500} := \frac{2+1+3}{1 \times 06 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{213}{1065000} := \frac{2+1+3}{1 \times 06 \times 5000}$$

$$1009. \quad \frac{213}{2840} := \frac{2+1^3}{(2+8) \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{28400} := \frac{2+1^3}{(2+8) \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{284000} := \frac{2+1^3}{(2+8) \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{2840000} := \frac{2+1^3}{(2+8) \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$1000. \quad \frac{212}{1749} := \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+49}$$

$$\frac{212}{17649} := \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+649}$$

$$\frac{212}{176649} := \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+6649}$$

$$\frac{212}{1766649} := \frac{2^{1+2}}{17+66649}$$

$$1005. \quad \frac{213}{1136} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{(1+1)^3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{213}{11360} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{(1+1)^3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{213}{113600} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{(1+1)^3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{213}{1136000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{(1+1)^3 \times 6000}$$

$$1010. \quad \frac{213}{355} := \frac{21+3}{(3+5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{213}{3550} := \frac{21+3}{(3+5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{213}{35500} := \frac{21+3}{(3+5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{213}{355000} := \frac{21+3}{(3+5) \times 5000}$$

$$1001. \quad \frac{212}{530} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{5 \times 3 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{5300} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{5 \times 30 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{53000} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{5 \times 300 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{530000} := \frac{2 \times (1+2)}{5 \times 3000 + 0}$$

$$1006. \quad \frac{213}{1278} := \frac{2 \times 13}{1 \times 2 \times 78}$$

$$\frac{213}{12780} := \frac{2 \times 13}{1 \times 2 \times 780}$$

$$\frac{213}{127800} := \frac{2 \times 13}{1 \times 2 \times 7800}$$

$$\frac{213}{1278000} := \frac{2 \times 13}{1 \times 2 \times 78000}$$

$$1011. \quad \frac{213}{426} := \frac{21+3}{4 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{213}{4260} := \frac{21+3}{4 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{213}{42600} := \frac{21+3}{4 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{213}{426000} := \frac{21+3}{4 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$1002. \quad \frac{212}{848} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(8+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{212}{8480} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(8+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{212}{84800} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(8+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{212}{848000} := \frac{2 \times 12}{(8+4) \times 8000}$$

$$1007. \quad \frac{213}{1420} := \frac{21 \times 3}{1 \times 420}$$

$$\frac{213}{14200} := \frac{21 \times 3}{1 \times 4200}$$

$$\frac{213}{142000} := \frac{21 \times 3}{1 \times 42000}$$

$$\frac{213}{1420000} := \frac{21 \times 3}{1 \times 420000}$$

$$1003. \quad \frac{212}{9540} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{9 \times 5 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{95400} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{9 \times 5 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{954000} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{9 \times 5 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{212}{9540000} := \frac{2^{1 \times 2}}{9 \times 5 \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$1008. \quad \frac{213}{1491} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(1+4+9) \times 1}$$

$$\frac{213}{14910} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(1+4+9) \times 10}$$

$$\frac{213}{149100} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(1+4+9) \times 100}$$

$$\frac{213}{1491000} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{(1+4+9) \times 1000}$$

$$1012. \quad \frac{213}{5680} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{56800} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{568000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{213}{5680000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 3}{5 \times 6 \times 8000 + 0}$$

1013.

$$\frac{213}{639} := \frac{(2+1)^3}{(6+3) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{213}{6390} := \frac{(2+1)^3}{(6+3) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{213}{63900} := \frac{(2+1)^3}{(6+3) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{213}{639000} := \frac{(2+1)^3}{(6+3) \times 9000}$$

1018.

$$\frac{214}{1284} := \frac{2 \times 14}{1 \times 2 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{214}{12840} := \frac{2 \times 14}{1 \times 2 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{214}{128400} := \frac{2 \times 14}{1 \times 2 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{214}{1284000} := \frac{2 \times 14}{1 \times 2 \times 84000}$$

1023.

$$\frac{214}{642} := \frac{21 \times 4}{6 \times 42}$$

$$\frac{214}{6420} := \frac{21 \times 4}{6 \times 420}$$

$$\frac{214}{64200} := \frac{21 \times 4}{6 \times 4200}$$

$$\frac{214}{642000} := \frac{21 \times 4}{6 \times 42000}$$

1014.

$$\frac{213}{781} := \frac{21+3}{7+81}$$

$$\frac{213}{7881} := \frac{21+3}{7+881}$$

$$\frac{213}{78881} := \frac{21+3}{7+8881}$$

$$\frac{213}{788881} := \frac{21+3}{7+88881}$$

1019.

$$\frac{214}{1391} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{1 \times 39 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{214}{13910} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{1 \times 39 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{214}{139100} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{1 \times 39 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{214}{1391000} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{1 \times 39 \times 1000}$$

1024.

$$\frac{214}{8560} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{8 \times 5 \times 6+0}$$

$$\frac{214}{85600} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{8 \times 5 \times 60+0}$$

$$\frac{214}{856000} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{8 \times 5 \times 600+0}$$

1015.

$$\frac{213}{8520} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{8 \times 5 \times 2+0}$$

$$\frac{213}{85200} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{8 \times 5 \times 20+0}$$

$$\frac{213}{852000} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{8 \times 5 \times 200+0}$$

$$\frac{213}{8520000} := \frac{2 \times 1^3}{8 \times 5 \times 2000+0}$$

1020.

$$\frac{214}{321} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3^2 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{214}{3210} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3^2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{214}{32100} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3^2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{214}{321000} := \frac{2+1 \times 4}{3^2 \times 1000}$$

1025.

$$\frac{214}{963} := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{214}{9630} := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{214}{96300} := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{214}{963000} := \frac{2 \times (1+4)}{(9+6) \times 3000}$$

1016.

$$\frac{214}{1177} := \frac{2 \times 14}{(1+1) \times 77}$$

$$\frac{214}{11770} := \frac{2 \times 14}{(1+1) \times 770}$$

$$\frac{214}{117700} := \frac{2 \times 14}{(1+1) \times 7700}$$

$$\frac{214}{1177000} := \frac{2 \times 14}{(1+1) \times 77000}$$

1021.

$$\frac{214}{428} := \frac{2^{1+4}}{4 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{214}{4280} := \frac{2^{1+4}}{4 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{214}{42800} := \frac{2^{1+4}}{4 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{214}{428000} := \frac{2^{1+4}}{4 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

1017.

$$\frac{214}{1177} := \frac{2+14}{11+77}$$

$$\frac{214}{11877} := \frac{2+14}{11+877}$$

$$\frac{214}{118877} := \frac{2+14}{11+8877}$$

$$\frac{214}{1188877} := \frac{2+14}{11+88877}$$

1022.

$$\frac{214}{535} := \frac{2+14}{(5+3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{214}{5350} := \frac{2+14}{(5+3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{214}{53500} := \frac{2+14}{(5+3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{214}{535000} := \frac{2+14}{(5+3) \times 5000}$$

1026.

$$\frac{215}{1075} := \frac{2+1 \times 5}{1 \times 07 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{215}{10750} := \frac{2+1 \times 5}{1 \times 07 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{215}{107500} := \frac{2+1 \times 5}{1 \times 07 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{215}{1075000} := \frac{2+1 \times 5}{1 \times 07 \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1027. \quad & \frac{215}{1204} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(1+20) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{215}{12040} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(1+20) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{215}{120400} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(1+20) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{215}{1204000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(1+20) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1032. \quad & \frac{215}{860} := \frac{2 \times (1+5)}{8 \times 6 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{8600} := \frac{2 \times (1+5)}{8 \times 60 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{86000} := \frac{2 \times (1+5)}{8 \times 600 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{860000} := \frac{2 \times (1+5)}{8 \times 6000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1037. \quad & \frac{216}{1280} := \frac{21+6}{1 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{216}{12800} := \frac{21+6}{1 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{216}{128000} := \frac{21+6}{1 \times 2 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{216}{1280000} := \frac{21+6}{1 \times 2 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1028. \quad & \frac{215}{1290} := \frac{2 \times 15}{1 \times 2 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{215}{12900} := \frac{2 \times 15}{1 \times 2 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{215}{129000} := \frac{2 \times 15}{1 \times 2 \times 90000} \\
 & \frac{215}{1290000} := \frac{2 \times 15}{1 \times 2 \times 900000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1033. \quad & \frac{216}{1152} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+1)^5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{216}{11520} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+1)^5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{216}{115200} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+1)^5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{216}{1152000} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1038. \quad & \frac{216}{1296} := \frac{2 \times 16}{1 \times 2 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{216}{12960} := \frac{2 \times 16}{1 \times 2 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{216}{129600} := \frac{2 \times 16}{1 \times 2 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{216}{1296000} := \frac{2 \times 16}{1 \times 2 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1029. \quad & \frac{215}{344} := \frac{2 \times 15}{3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{215}{3440} := \frac{2 \times 15}{3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{215}{34400} := \frac{2 \times 15}{3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{215}{344000} := \frac{2 \times 15}{3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1034. \quad & \frac{216}{1188} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+1) \times 88} \\
 & \frac{216}{11880} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+1) \times 880} \\
 & \frac{216}{118800} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+1) \times 8800} \\
 & \frac{216}{1188000} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+1) \times 88000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1039. \quad & \frac{216}{1350} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{216}{13500} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{216}{135000} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{216}{1350000} := \frac{2 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1030. \quad & \frac{215}{516} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(5+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{215}{5160} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(5+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{215}{51600} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(5+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{215}{516000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 5}{(5+1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1035. \quad & \frac{216}{1188} := \frac{2+16}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{216}{11988} := \frac{2+16}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{216}{119988} := \frac{2+16}{11+9988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1040. \quad & \frac{216}{1440} := \frac{2+1^6}{(1+4) \times 4 + 0} \\
 & \frac{216}{14400} := \frac{2+1^6}{(1+4) \times 40 + 0} \\
 & \frac{216}{144000} := \frac{2+1^6}{(1+4) \times 400 + 0} \\
 & \frac{216}{1440000} := \frac{2+1^6}{(1+4) \times 4000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1031. \quad & \frac{215}{6880} := \frac{2+15}{68 \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{68800} := \frac{2+15}{68 \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{688000} := \frac{2+15}{68 \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{215}{6880000} := \frac{2+15}{68 \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1036. \quad & \frac{216}{1215} := \frac{2 \times 16}{12 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{216}{12150} := \frac{2 \times 16}{12 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{216}{121500} := \frac{2 \times 16}{12 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{216}{1215000} := \frac{2 \times 16}{12 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

1041.

$$\frac{216}{243} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{24 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{216}{2430} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{24 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{216}{24300} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{24 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{216}{243000} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{24 \times 3000}$$

1046.

$$\frac{216}{648} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{6 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{216}{6480} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{6 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{216}{64800} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{6 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{216}{648000} := \frac{2^{1 \times 6}}{6 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

1051.

$$\frac{217}{1302} := \frac{2+1+7}{1 \times 30 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{217}{13020} := \frac{2+1+7}{1 \times 30 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{217}{130200} := \frac{2+1+7}{1 \times 30 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{217}{1302000} := \frac{2+1+7}{1 \times 30 \times 2000}$$

1042.

$$\frac{216}{252} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(2+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{216}{2520} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(2+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{216}{25200} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 6}{(2+5) \times 2000}$$

1047.

$$\frac{216}{672} := \frac{21+6}{6 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{216}{6720} := \frac{21+6}{6 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{216}{67200} := \frac{21+6}{6 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{216}{672000} := \frac{21+6}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

1052.

$$\frac{217}{1395} := \frac{21+7}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{217}{13950} := \frac{21+7}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{217}{139500} := \frac{21+7}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{217}{1395000} := \frac{21+7}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}$$

1043.

$$\frac{216}{486} := \frac{2^{1+6}}{48 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{216}{4860} := \frac{2^{1+6}}{48 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{216}{48600} := \frac{2^{1+6}}{48 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{216}{486000} := \frac{2^{1+6}}{48 \times 6000}$$

1048.

$$\frac{217}{1085} := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(1+08) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{217}{10850} := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(1+08) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{217}{108500} := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(1+08) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{217}{1085000} := \frac{2+1 \times 7}{(1+08) \times 5000}$$

1053.

$$\frac{217}{1488} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{217}{14880} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{217}{148800} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{217}{1488000} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8000}$$

1044.

$$\frac{216}{540} := \frac{2+1 \times 6}{5 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{216}{5400} := \frac{2+1 \times 6}{5 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{216}{54000} := \frac{2+1 \times 6}{5 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{216}{540000} := \frac{2+1 \times 6}{5 \times 4000 + 0}$$

1049.

$$\frac{217}{1116} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+11) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{217}{11160} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+11) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{217}{111600} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+11) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{217}{1116000} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(1+11) \times 6000}$$

1045.

$$\frac{216}{576} := \frac{21+6}{(5+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{216}{5760} := \frac{21+6}{(5+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{216}{57600} := \frac{21+6}{(5+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{216}{576000} := \frac{21+6}{(5+7) \times 6000}$$

1050.

$$\frac{217}{1240} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{217}{12400} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{217}{124000} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{217}{1240000} := \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}$$

1054.

$$\frac{217}{310} := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{3 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{217}{3100} := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{3 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{217}{31000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{3 \times 1000}$$

$$\frac{217}{310000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 7}{3 \times 10000}$$

$$1055. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{341} &:= \frac{21+7}{3+41} \\ \frac{217}{3441} &:= \frac{21+7}{3+441} \\ \frac{217}{34441} &:= \frac{21+7}{3+4441} \\ \frac{217}{344441} &:= \frac{21+7}{3+44441} \end{aligned}$$

$$1060. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{868} &:= \frac{21+7}{(8+6) \times 8} \\ \frac{217}{8680} &:= \frac{21+7}{(8+6) \times 80} \\ \frac{217}{86800} &:= \frac{21+7}{(8+6) \times 800} \\ \frac{217}{868000} &:= \frac{21+7}{(8+6) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1065. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{763} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times 6 \times 3} \\ \frac{218}{7630} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times 6 \times 30} \\ \frac{218}{76300} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times 6 \times 300} \\ \frac{218}{763000} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{7 \times 6 \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1056. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{434} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(4+3) \times 4} \\ \frac{217}{4340} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(4+3) \times 40} \\ \frac{217}{43400} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(4+3) \times 400} \\ \frac{217}{434000} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 7}{(4+3) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1061. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{1090} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 090} \\ \frac{218}{10900} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 0900} \\ \frac{218}{109000} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 09000} \\ \frac{218}{1090000} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 090000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1066. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{981} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 8}{9 \times 8 \times 1} \\ \frac{218}{9810} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 8}{9 \times 8 \times 10} \\ \frac{218}{98100} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 8}{9 \times 8 \times 100} \\ \frac{218}{981000} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 8}{9 \times 8 \times 1000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1057. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{651} &:= \frac{2+1+7}{6 \times 5 \times 1} \\ \frac{217}{6510} &:= \frac{2+1+7}{6 \times 5 \times 10} \\ \frac{217}{65100} &:= \frac{2+1+7}{6 \times 5 \times 100} \\ \frac{217}{651000} &:= \frac{2+1+7}{6 \times 5 \times 1000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1062. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{1199} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\ \frac{218}{11990} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\ \frac{218}{119900} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\ \frac{218}{1199000} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1067. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{219}{1168} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 8} \\ \frac{219}{11680} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 80} \\ \frac{219}{116800} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 800} \\ \frac{219}{1168000} &:= \frac{2 \times 1 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1058. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{682} &:= \frac{21+7}{6+82} \\ \frac{217}{6882} &:= \frac{21+7}{6+882} \\ \frac{217}{68882} &:= \frac{21+7}{6+8882} \\ \frac{217}{688882} &:= \frac{21+7}{6+88882} \end{aligned}$$

$$1063. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{436} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times 3 \times 6} \\ \frac{218}{4360} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times 3 \times 60} \\ \frac{218}{43600} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times 3 \times 600} \\ \frac{218}{436000} &:= \frac{2 \times 18}{4 \times 3 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1068. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{219}{1241} &:= \frac{2+1^9}{(1+2^4) \times 1} \\ \frac{219}{12410} &:= \frac{2+1^9}{(1+2^4) \times 10} \\ \frac{219}{124100} &:= \frac{2+1^9}{(1+2^4) \times 100} \\ \frac{219}{1241000} &:= \frac{2+1^9}{(1+2^4) \times 1000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1059. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{217}{775} &:= \frac{21 \times 7}{7 \times 75} \\ \frac{217}{7750} &:= \frac{21 \times 7}{7 \times 750} \\ \frac{217}{77500} &:= \frac{21 \times 7}{7 \times 7500} \\ \frac{217}{775000} &:= \frac{21 \times 7}{7 \times 75000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1064. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{218}{545} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{(5+4) \times 5} \\ \frac{218}{5450} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{(5+4) \times 50} \\ \frac{218}{54500} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{(5+4) \times 500} \\ \frac{218}{545000} &:= \frac{2 \times (1+8)}{(5+4) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1069.

$$\frac{219}{1314} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{1 \times 3 \times 1 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{219}{13140} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{1 \times 3 \times 1 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{219}{131400} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{1 \times 3 \times 1 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{219}{1314000} := \frac{2 \times 1^9}{1 \times 3 \times 1 \times 4000}$$

1073.

$$\frac{219}{803} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+03}$$

$$\frac{219}{8103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+103}$$

$$\frac{219}{81103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+1103}$$

$$\frac{219}{811103} := \frac{2+1^9}{8+11103}$$

1077.

$$\frac{220}{1815} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{220}{18315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{220}{183315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+3315}$$

$$\frac{220}{1833315} := \frac{2^{2+0}}{18+33315}$$

1070.

$$\frac{219}{1606} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+06}$$

$$\frac{219}{16206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+206}$$

$$\frac{219}{162206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+2206}$$

$$\frac{219}{1622206} := \frac{2+1^9}{16+22206}$$

1074.

$$\frac{219}{949} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(9+4) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{219}{9490} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(9+4) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{219}{94900} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(9+4) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{219}{949000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(9+4) \times 9000}$$

1078.

$$\frac{220}{242} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+42}$$

$$\frac{220}{2442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+442}$$

$$\frac{220}{24442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+4442}$$

$$\frac{220}{244442} := \frac{2 \times 20}{2+44442}$$

1071.

$$\frac{219}{292} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{2 \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{219}{2920} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{2 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{219}{29200} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{2 \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{219}{292000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{2 \times 9 \times 2000}$$

1075.

$$\frac{220}{1221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{220}{12221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{220}{122221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+22221}$$

$$\frac{220}{1222221} := \frac{2 \times 20}{1+222221}$$

1079.

$$\frac{220}{363} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{220}{3663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{220}{36663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{220}{366663} := \frac{2 \times 20}{3+66663}$$

1080.

$$\frac{220}{484} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{220}{4884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{220}{48884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{220}{488884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+88884}$$

1072.

$$\frac{219}{365} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{219}{3650} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{219}{36500} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{219}{365000} := \frac{(2+1) \times 9}{(3+6) \times 5000}$$

1076.

$$\frac{220}{1155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+15+5}$$

$$\frac{220}{12155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+215+5}$$

$$\frac{220}{122155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+2215+5}$$

$$\frac{220}{1222155} := \frac{2^2+0}{1+22215+5}$$

1081.

$$\frac{220}{48884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{220}{488884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+88884}$$

$$\frac{220}{4888884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+888884}$$

$$\frac{220}{48888884} := \frac{2 \times 20}{4+8888884}$$

1082.

$$\frac{220}{605} := \frac{2^2+0}{6+05}$$

$$\frac{220}{6105} := \frac{2^2+0}{6+105}$$

$$\frac{220}{61105} := \frac{2^2+0}{6+1105}$$

$$\frac{220}{611105} := \frac{2^2+0}{6+11105}$$

1086.

$$\frac{222}{1221} := \frac{2+2^2}{12+21}$$

$$\frac{222}{12321} := \frac{2+2^2}{12+321}$$

$$\frac{222}{123321} := \frac{2+2^2}{12+3321}$$

$$\frac{222}{1233321} := \frac{2+2^2}{12+33321}$$

1090.

$$\frac{222}{407} := \frac{2+2^2}{4+07}$$

$$\frac{222}{4107} := \frac{2+2^2}{4+107}$$

$$\frac{222}{41107} := \frac{2+2^2}{4+1107}$$

$$\frac{222}{411107} := \frac{2+2^2}{4+11107}$$

1083.

$$\frac{221}{1326} := \frac{2 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{221}{13260} := \frac{2 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{221}{132600} := \frac{2 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{221}{1326000} := \frac{2 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 3 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

1087.

$$\frac{222}{1258} := \frac{2+22}{(12+5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{222}{12580} := \frac{2+22}{(12+5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{222}{125800} := \frac{2+22}{(12+5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{222}{1258000} := \frac{2+22}{(12+5) \times 8000}$$

1091.

$$\frac{222}{444} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{(4+4) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{222}{4440} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{(4+4) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{222}{44400} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{(4+4) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{222}{444000} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{(4+4) \times 4000}$$

1084.

$$\frac{221}{442} := \frac{2^{2+1}}{(4+4) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{221}{4420} := \frac{2^{2+1}}{(4+4) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{221}{44200} := \frac{2^{2+1}}{(4+4) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{221}{442000} := \frac{2^{2+1}}{(4+4) \times 2000}$$

1088.

$$\frac{222}{1332} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{1 \times 3 \times 32}$$

$$\frac{222}{13320} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{1 \times 3 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{222}{133200} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{1 \times 3 \times 3200}$$

$$\frac{222}{1332000} := \frac{2^{2 \times 2}}{1 \times 3 \times 32000}$$

1092.

$$\frac{222}{814} := \frac{2+2^2}{8+14}$$

$$\frac{222}{8214} := \frac{2+2^2}{8+214}$$

$$\frac{222}{82214} := \frac{2+2^2}{8+2214}$$

$$\frac{222}{822214} := \frac{2+2^2}{8+22214}$$

1085.

$$\frac{222}{1184} := \frac{2+2 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{222}{11840} := \frac{2+2 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{222}{118400} := \frac{2+2 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{222}{1184000} := \frac{2+2 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

1089.

$$\frac{222}{1480} := \frac{2+2^2}{(1+4) \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{222}{14800} := \frac{2+2^2}{(1+4) \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{222}{148000} := \frac{2+2^2}{(1+4) \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{222}{1480000} := \frac{2+2^2}{(1+4) \times 8000+0}$$

1093.

$$\frac{223}{1115} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+11) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{223}{11150} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+11) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{223}{111500} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+11) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{223}{1115000} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+11) \times 5000}$$

$$1094. \quad \frac{223}{1338} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{223}{223} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 3}{2 \times 2 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{13380}{223} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 80}{2 \times 2 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{133800}{223} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 800}{2 \times 2 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{1338000}{223} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 3 \times 8000}{2 \times 2 \times 3}$$

$$1095. \quad \frac{224}{1120} := \frac{2+2+4}{(1+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2+2+4}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{11200}{224} := \frac{(1+1) \times 200}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{112000}{224} := \frac{(1+1) \times 2000}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{1120000}{224} := \frac{(1+1) \times 20000}{2+2+4}$$

$$1096. \quad \frac{224}{1176} := \frac{22 \times 4}{11 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{22 \times 4}{22 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{11760}{224} := \frac{11 \times 7 \times 60}{22 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{117600}{224} := \frac{11 \times 7 \times 600}{22 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{1176000}{224} := \frac{11 \times 7 \times 6000}{22 \times 4}$$

$$1097. \quad \frac{224}{1260} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(1+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{12600}{224} := \frac{(1+2) \times 600}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{126000}{224} := \frac{(1+2) \times 6000}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{1260000}{224} := \frac{(1+2) \times 60000}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$1098. \quad \frac{224}{1344} := \frac{2+2+4}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2+2+4}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{13440}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{134400}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{1344000}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}{2+2+4}$$

$$1099. \quad \frac{224}{1365} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{13650}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 650}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{136500}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 6500}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{1365000}{224} := \frac{1 \times 3 \times 65000}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$1100. \quad \frac{224}{1386} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 4}{13+86}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 4}{2 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{13986}{224} := \frac{13+986}{2 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{139986}{224} := \frac{13+9986}{2 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{1399986}{224} := \frac{13+99986}{2 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$1101. \quad \frac{224}{1400} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{1 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{2^{2+4}}$$

$$\frac{14000}{224} := \frac{1 \times 4000}{2^{2+4}}$$

$$\frac{140000}{224} := \frac{1 \times 40000}{2^{2+4}}$$

$$\frac{1400000}{224} := \frac{1 \times 400000}{2^{2+4}}$$

$$1102. \quad \frac{224}{231} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2+31}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{2331}{224} := \frac{2+331}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{23331}{224} := \frac{2+3331}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{233331}{224} := \frac{2+33331}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$1103. \quad \frac{224}{308} := \frac{2+2+4}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2+2+4}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{3108}{224} := \frac{3+108}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{31108}{224} := \frac{3+1108}{2+2+4}$$

$$\frac{311108}{224} := \frac{3+11108}{2+2+4}$$

$$1104. \quad \frac{224}{315} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{3150}{224} := \frac{3 \times 150}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{31500}{224} := \frac{3 \times 1500}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{315000}{224} := \frac{3 \times 15000}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$1105. \quad \frac{224}{385} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{224}{3850} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(3+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{224}{38500} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(3+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{224}{385000} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(3+8) \times 5000}$$

$$1106. \quad \frac{224}{448} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(4+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{224}{4480} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(4+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{224}{44800} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(4+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{224}{448000} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{(4+4) \times 8000}$$

$$1107. \quad \frac{224}{462} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{224}{224} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{4662}{224} := \frac{4+662}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{46662}{224} := \frac{4+6662}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\frac{466662}{224} := \frac{4+66662}{2 \times 2^4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1108. \quad & \frac{224}{560} := \frac{2 \times (2+4)}{5 \times 6+0} \\
 & \frac{224}{5600} := \frac{2 \times (2+4)}{5 \times 60+0} \\
 & \frac{224}{56000} := \frac{2 \times (2+4)}{5 \times 600+0} \\
 & \frac{224}{560000} := \frac{2 \times (2+4)}{5 \times 6000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1112. \quad & \frac{224}{784} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{7 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{224}{7840} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{7 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{224}{78400} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{7 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{224}{784000} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{7 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1117. \quad & \frac{225}{1375} := \frac{2+2+5}{(1+3+7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{225}{13750} := \frac{(2+2+5)}{(1+3+7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{225}{137500} := \frac{(2+2+5)}{(1+3+7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{225}{1375000} := \frac{(2+2+5)}{(1+3+7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1109. \quad & \frac{224}{616} := \frac{2+2+4}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{224}{6216} := \frac{2+2+4}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{224}{62216} := \frac{2+2+4}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{224}{622216} := \frac{2+2+4}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1113. \quad & \frac{224}{924} := \frac{2+2+4}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{224}{9324} := \frac{2+2+4}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{224}{93324} := \frac{2+2+4}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{224}{933324} := \frac{2+2+4}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1118. \quad & \frac{225}{15875} := \frac{2+2+5}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{225}{158750} := \frac{2+2+5}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{225}{1587500} := \frac{2+2+5}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{225}{15875000} := \frac{2+2+5}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1110. \quad & \frac{224}{630} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{6 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{224}{6300} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{6 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{224}{63000} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{6 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{224}{630000} := \frac{2^{2+4}}{6 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1114. \quad & \frac{225}{1125} := \frac{2+2 \times 5}{1 \times 12 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{225}{11250} := \frac{2+2 \times 5}{1 \times 12 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{225}{112500} := \frac{2+2 \times 5}{1 \times 12 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{225}{1125000} := \frac{2+2 \times 5}{1 \times 12 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1119. \quad & \frac{225}{250} := \frac{2+2+5}{2 \times 5+0} \\
 & \frac{225}{2500} := \frac{2+2+5}{2 \times 50+0} \\
 & \frac{225}{25000} := \frac{2+2+5}{2 \times 500+0} \\
 & \frac{225}{250000} := \frac{2+2+5}{2 \times 5000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1111. \quad & \frac{224}{735} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{7 \times (3 \times 5)} \\
 & \frac{224}{7350} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{7 \times (3 \times 50)} \\
 & \frac{224}{73500} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{7 \times (3 \times 500)} \\
 & \frac{224}{735000} := \frac{2 \times 2^4}{7 \times (3 \times 5000)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1115. \quad & \frac{225}{1250} := \frac{2+25}{(1+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{225}{12500} := \frac{2+25}{(1+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{225}{125000} := \frac{2+25}{(1+2) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{225}{1250000} := \frac{2+25}{(1+2) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1120. \quad & \frac{225}{324} := \frac{2 \times 25}{3 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{225}{3240} := \frac{2 \times 25}{3 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{225}{32400} := \frac{2 \times 25}{3 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{225}{324000} := \frac{2 \times 25}{3 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1116. \quad & \frac{225}{1296} := \frac{2 \times 25}{(1+2) \times 96} \\
 & \frac{225}{12960} := \frac{2 \times 25}{(1+2) \times 960} \\
 & \frac{225}{129600} := \frac{2 \times 25}{(1+2) \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{225}{1296000} := \frac{2 \times 25}{(1+2) \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1121. \quad & \frac{225}{6875} := \frac{2+2+5}{(6 \times 8+7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{225}{68750} := \frac{2+2+5}{(6 \times 8+7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{225}{687500} := \frac{2+2+5}{(6 \times 8+7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{225}{6875000} := \frac{2+2+5}{(6 \times 8+7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1122. \quad \frac{225}{825} := \frac{2+2+5}{8+25}$$

$$\frac{225}{8325} := \frac{2+2+5}{8+325}$$

$$\frac{225}{83325} := \frac{2+2+5}{8+3325}$$

$$\frac{225}{833325} := \frac{2+2+5}{8+33325}$$

$$1127. \quad \frac{227}{454} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{(4+5) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{227}{4540} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{(4+5) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{227}{45400} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{(4+5) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{227}{454000} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{(4+5) \times 4000}$$

$$1132. \quad \frac{228}{1368} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{228}{13680} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{228}{136800} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{228}{1368000} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$1123. \quad \frac{225}{864} := \frac{2 \times 25}{8 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{225}{8640} := \frac{2 \times 25}{8 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{225}{86400} := \frac{2 \times 25}{8 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{225}{864000} := \frac{2 \times 25}{8 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$1128. \quad \frac{227}{681} := \frac{2+2 \times 7}{6 \times 8 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{227}{6810} := \frac{2+2 \times 7}{6 \times 8 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{227}{68100} := \frac{2+2 \times 7}{6 \times 8 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{227}{681000} := \frac{2+2 \times 7}{6 \times 8 \times 1000}$$

$$1133. \quad \frac{228}{1425} := \frac{2 \times 28}{14 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{228}{14250} := \frac{2 \times 28}{14 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{228}{142500} := \frac{2 \times 28}{14 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{228}{1425000} := \frac{2 \times 28}{14 \times 25000}$$

$$1124. \quad \frac{226}{1130} := \frac{2+2^6}{11 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{226}{11300} := \frac{2+2^6}{11 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{226}{113000} := \frac{2+2^6}{11 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{226}{1130000} := \frac{2+2^6}{11 \times 30000}$$

$$1129. \quad \frac{227}{908} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{9 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{227}{9080} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{9 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{227}{90800} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{9 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{227}{908000} := \frac{2 \times (2+7)}{9 \times 08000}$$

$$1134. \quad \frac{228}{1463} := \frac{2+2+8}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{228}{14763} := \frac{2+2+8}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{228}{147763} := \frac{2+2+8}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{228}{1477763} := \frac{2+2+8}{14+77763}$$

$$1125. \quad \frac{226}{1243} := \frac{2+2+6}{12+43}$$

$$\frac{226}{12543} := \frac{2+2+6}{12+543}$$

$$\frac{226}{125543} := \frac{2+2+6}{12+5543}$$

$$\frac{226}{1255543} := \frac{2+2+6}{12+55543}$$

$$1130. \quad \frac{228}{1197} := \frac{2+2+8}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{228}{11970} := \frac{2+2+8}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{228}{119700} := \frac{2+2+8}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{228}{1197000} := \frac{2+2+8}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}$$

$$1135. \quad \frac{228}{1672} := \frac{2+2+8}{16+72}$$

$$\frac{228}{16872} := \frac{2+2+8}{16+872}$$

$$\frac{228}{168872} := \frac{2+2+8}{16+8872}$$

$$\frac{228}{1688872} := \frac{2+2+8}{16+88872}$$

$$1126. \quad \frac{226}{1356} := \frac{2+26}{1 \times 3 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{226}{13560} := \frac{2+26}{1 \times 3 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{226}{135600} := \frac{2+26}{1 \times 3 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{226}{1356000} := \frac{2+26}{1 \times 3 \times 56000}$$

$$1131. \quad \frac{228}{1254} := \frac{2+2+8}{12+54}$$

$$\frac{228}{12654} := \frac{2+2+8}{12+654}$$

$$\frac{228}{126654} := \frac{2+2+8}{12+6654}$$

$$\frac{228}{1266654} := \frac{2+2+8}{12+66654}$$

$$1136. \quad \frac{228}{418} := \frac{2+2+8}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{228}{4218} := \frac{2+2+8}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{228}{42218} := \frac{2+2+8}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{228}{422218} := \frac{2+2+8}{4+22218}$$

$$1137. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{608} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{6 \times 08} \\ \frac{228}{6080} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{6 \times 080} \\ \frac{228}{60800} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{6 \times 0800} \\ \frac{228}{608000} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{6 \times 08000} \end{array}$$

$$1142. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{836} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{(8+3) \times 6} \\ \frac{228}{8360} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{(8+3) \times 60} \\ \frac{228}{83600} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{(8+3) \times 600} \\ \frac{228}{836000} := \frac{2+2 \times 8}{(8+3) \times 6000} \end{array}$$

$$1147. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{230}{1725} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 0}{(1 \times 7 + 2) \times 5} \\ \frac{230}{17250} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 0}{(1 \times 7 + 2) \times 50} \\ \frac{230}{172500} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 0}{(1 \times 7 + 2) \times 500} \\ \frac{230}{1725000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 0}{(1 \times 7 + 2) \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$1138. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{627} := \frac{2+2+8}{6+27} \\ \frac{228}{6327} := \frac{2+2+8}{6+327} \\ \frac{228}{63327} := \frac{2+2+8}{6+3327} \\ \frac{228}{633327} := \frac{2+2+8}{6+33327} \end{array}$$

$$1143. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{836} := \frac{2+2+8}{8+36} \\ \frac{228}{8436} := \frac{2+2+8}{8+436} \\ \frac{228}{84436} := \frac{2+2+8}{8+4436} \\ \frac{228}{844436} := \frac{2+2+8}{8+44436} \end{array}$$

$$1148. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{230}{17595} := \frac{2^3 + 0}{17+595} \\ \frac{230}{175595} := \frac{2^3 + 0}{17+5595} \\ \frac{230}{1755595} := \frac{2^3 + 0}{17+55595} \\ \frac{230}{17555595} := \frac{2^3 + 0}{17+555595} \end{array}$$

$$1139. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{6384} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(6^3 + 8) \times 4} \\ \frac{228}{63840} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(6^3 + 8) \times 40} \\ \frac{228}{638400} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(6^3 + 8) \times 400} \\ \frac{228}{6384000} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 8}{(6^3 + 8) \times 4000} \end{array}$$

$$1144. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{229}{458} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{(4+5) \times 8} \\ \frac{229}{4580} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{(4+5) \times 80} \\ \frac{229}{45800} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{(4+5) \times 800} \\ \frac{229}{458000} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{(4+5) \times 8000} \end{array}$$

$$1149. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{230}{506} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+06} \\ \frac{230}{5106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+106} \\ \frac{230}{51106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+1106} \\ \frac{230}{511106} := \frac{2+3+0}{5+11106} \end{array}$$

$$1140. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{6688} := \frac{2+2+8}{(6 \times 6 + 8) \times 8} \\ \frac{228}{66880} := \frac{2+2+8}{(6 \times 6 + 8) \times 80} \\ \frac{228}{668800} := \frac{2+2+8}{(6 \times 6 + 8) \times 800} \\ \frac{228}{6688000} := \frac{2+2+8}{(6 \times 6 + 8) \times 8000} \end{array}$$

$$1145. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{229}{916} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{9 \times 16} \\ \frac{229}{9160} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{9 \times 160} \\ \frac{229}{91600} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{9 \times 1600} \\ \frac{229}{916000} := \frac{2 \times 2 \times 9}{9 \times 16000} \end{array}$$

$$1150. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{231}{1232} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{1^2 \times 32} \\ \frac{231}{12320} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{1^2 \times 320} \\ \frac{231}{123200} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{1^2 \times 3200} \\ \frac{231}{1232000} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 1}{1^2 \times 32000} \end{array}$$

$$1141. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{228}{6745} := \frac{2+2+8}{(67+4) \times 5} \\ \frac{228}{67450} := \frac{2+2+8}{(67+4) \times 50} \\ \frac{228}{674500} := \frac{2+2+8}{(67+4) \times 500} \\ \frac{228}{6745000} := \frac{2+2+8}{(67+4) \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$1146. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{230}{1012} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+12} \\ \frac{230}{10212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+212} \\ \frac{230}{102212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+2212} \\ \frac{230}{1022212} := \frac{2+3+0}{10+22212} \end{array}$$

$$1151. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{231}{1365} := \frac{2+31}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\ \frac{231}{13650} := \frac{2+31}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\ \frac{231}{136500} := \frac{2+31}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\ \frac{231}{1365000} := \frac{2+31}{1 \times 3 \times 65000} \end{array}$$

$$1152. \quad \frac{231}{1386} := \frac{23+1}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{231}{13860} := \frac{23+1}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{231}{138600} := \frac{23+1}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{231}{1386000} := \frac{23+1}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6000}$$

$$1157. \quad \frac{231}{462} := \frac{2+31}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{231}{4662} := \frac{2+31}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{231}{46662} := \frac{2+31}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{231}{466662} := \frac{2+31}{4+66662}$$

$$1162. \quad \frac{232}{1218} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{1 \times 21 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{232}{12180} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{1 \times 21 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{232}{121800} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{1 \times 21 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{232}{1218000} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{1 \times 21 \times 8000}$$

$$1153. \quad \frac{231}{1485} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(1^4 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{231}{14850} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(1^4 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{231}{148500} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(1^4 + 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{231}{1485000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{(1^4 + 8) \times 5000}$$

$$1158. \quad \frac{231}{5940} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{5 \times 9 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{231}{59400} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{5 \times 9 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{231}{594000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{5 \times 9 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{231}{5940000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 1}{5 \times 9 \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$1163. \quad \frac{232}{1392} := \frac{23 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 92}$$

$$\frac{232}{13920} := \frac{23 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 920}$$

$$\frac{232}{139200} := \frac{23 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 9200}$$

$$\frac{232}{1392000} := \frac{23 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 92000}$$

$$1154. \quad \frac{231}{315} := \frac{2+31}{3 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{231}{3150} := \frac{2+31}{3 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{231}{31500} := \frac{2+31}{3 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{231}{315000} := \frac{2+31}{3 \times 15000}$$

$$1159. \quad \frac{231}{693} := \frac{2+31}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{231}{6993} := \frac{2+31}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{231}{69993} := \frac{2+31}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{231}{699993} := \frac{2+31}{6+99993}$$

$$1164. \quad \frac{232}{1421} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{14^2 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{232}{14210} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{14^2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{232}{142100} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{14^2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{232}{1421000} := \frac{2^{3+2}}{14^2 \times 1000}$$

$$1155. \quad \frac{231}{385} := \frac{2+31}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{231}{3850} := \frac{2+31}{(3+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{231}{38500} := \frac{2+31}{(3+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{231}{385000} := \frac{2+31}{(3+8) \times 5000}$$

$$1160. \quad \frac{231}{735} := \frac{2+31}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{231}{7350} := \frac{2+31}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{231}{73500} := \frac{2+31}{7 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{231}{735000} := \frac{2+31}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$1165. \quad \frac{232}{1450} := \frac{2+3 \times 2}{1^4 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{232}{14500} := \frac{2+3 \times 2}{1^4 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{232}{145000} := \frac{2+3 \times 2}{1^4 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{232}{1450000} := \frac{2+3 \times 2}{1^4 \times 50000}$$

$$1156. \quad \frac{231}{462} := \frac{23+1}{4 \times 6 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{231}{4620} := \frac{23+1}{4 \times 6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{231}{46200} := \frac{23+1}{4 \times 6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{231}{462000} := \frac{23+1}{4 \times 6 \times 2000}$$

$$1161. \quad \frac{232}{1160} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{232}{11600} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{232}{116000} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{232}{1160000} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 60000}$$

$$1166. \quad \frac{232}{319} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+19}$$

$$\frac{232}{3219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+219}$$

$$\frac{232}{32219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+2219}$$

$$\frac{232}{322219} := \frac{2^3 \times 2}{3+22219}$$

$$1167. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{232}{348} &:= \frac{2 \times 32}{3 \times 4 \times 8} \\ \frac{232}{3480} &:= \frac{2 \times 32}{3 \times 4 \times 80} \\ \frac{232}{34800} &:= \frac{2 \times 32}{3 \times 4 \times 800} \\ \frac{232}{348000} &:= \frac{2 \times 32}{3 \times 4 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1172. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{233}{1165} &:= \frac{2 \times 33}{11 \times 6 \times 5} \\ \frac{233}{11650} &:= \frac{2 \times 33}{11 \times 6 \times 50} \\ \frac{233}{116500} &:= \frac{2 \times 33}{11 \times 6 \times 500} \\ \frac{233}{1165000} &:= \frac{2 \times 33}{11 \times 6 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1177. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1170} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 70} \\ \frac{234}{11700} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 700} \\ \frac{234}{117000} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 7000} \\ \frac{234}{1170000} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 70000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1168. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{232}{435} &:= \frac{2^{3+2}}{4 \times 3 \times 5} \\ \frac{232}{4350} &:= \frac{2^{3+2}}{4 \times 3 \times 50} \\ \frac{232}{43500} &:= \frac{2^{3+2}}{4 \times 3 \times 500} \\ \frac{232}{435000} &:= \frac{2^{3+2}}{4 \times 3 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1173. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{233}{1398} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+3)}{1^3 \times 9 \times 8} \\ \frac{233}{13980} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+3)}{1^3 \times 9 \times 80} \\ \frac{233}{139800} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+3)}{1^3 \times 9 \times 800} \\ \frac{233}{1398000} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+3)}{1^3 \times 9 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1178. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1248} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 8} \\ \frac{234}{12480} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 80} \\ \frac{234}{124800} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 800} \\ \frac{234}{1248000} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1169. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{232}{580} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{5 \times 8+0} \\ \frac{232}{5800} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{5 \times 80+0} \\ \frac{232}{58000} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{5 \times 800+0} \\ \frac{232}{580000} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{5 \times 8000+0} \end{aligned}$$

$$1174. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1040} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times 040} \\ \frac{234}{10400} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times 0400} \\ \frac{234}{104000} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times 04000} \\ \frac{234}{1040000} &:= \frac{2+3+4}{1 \times 040000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1179. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1287} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(1+2+8) \times 7} \\ \frac{234}{12870} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(1+2+8) \times 70} \\ \frac{234}{128700} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(1+2+8) \times 700} \\ \frac{234}{1287000} &:= \frac{2 \times (3+4)}{(1+2+8) \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1170. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{232}{638} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+38} \\ \frac{232}{6438} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+438} \\ \frac{232}{64438} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+4438} \\ \frac{232}{644438} &:= \frac{2^3 \times 2}{6+44438} \end{aligned}$$

$$1175. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1053} &:= \frac{2 \times 3+4}{(10+5) \times 3} \\ \frac{234}{10530} &:= \frac{2 \times 3+4}{(10+5) \times 30} \\ \frac{234}{105300} &:= \frac{2 \times 3+4}{(10+5) \times 300} \\ \frac{234}{1053000} &:= \frac{2 \times 3+4}{(10+5) \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1171. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{232}{928} &:= \frac{(2 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 2 \times 8} \\ \frac{232}{9280} &:= \frac{(2 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 2 \times 80} \\ \frac{232}{92800} &:= \frac{(2 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 2 \times 800} \\ \frac{232}{928000} &:= \frac{(2 \times 3)^2}{9 \times 2 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1176. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1144} &:= \frac{2+34}{11 \times 4 \times 4} \\ \frac{234}{11440} &:= \frac{2+34}{11 \times 4 \times 40} \\ \frac{234}{114400} &:= \frac{2+34}{11 \times 4 \times 400} \\ \frac{234}{1144000} &:= \frac{2+34}{11 \times 4 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1180. \quad \begin{aligned} \frac{234}{1352} &:= \frac{23+4}{1 \times 3 \times 52} \\ \frac{234}{13520} &:= \frac{23+4}{1 \times 3 \times 520} \\ \frac{234}{135200} &:= \frac{23+4}{1 \times 3 \times 5200} \\ \frac{234}{1352000} &:= \frac{23+4}{1 \times 3 \times 52000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1181. \quad \frac{234}{1456} := \frac{2+34}{1 \times 4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{234}{14560} := \frac{2+34}{1 \times 4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{234}{145600} := \frac{2+34}{1 \times 4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{234}{1456000} := \frac{2+34}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}$$

$$1182. \quad \frac{234}{273} := \frac{2+34}{2 \times 7 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{234}{2730} := \frac{2+34}{2 \times 7 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{234}{27300} := \frac{2+34}{2 \times 7 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{234}{273000} := \frac{2+34}{2 \times 7 \times 3000}$$

$$1183. \quad \frac{234}{312} := \frac{23+4}{3 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{234}{3120} := \frac{23+4}{3 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{234}{31200} := \frac{23+4}{3 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{234}{312000} := \frac{23+4}{3 \times 12000}$$

$$1184. \quad \frac{234}{351} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{3 \times 5 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{234}{3510} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{3 \times 5 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{234}{35100} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{3 \times 5 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{234}{351000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 4}{3 \times 5 \times 1000}$$

$$1185. \quad \frac{234}{390} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{3 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{234}{3900} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{3 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{234}{39000} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{3 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{234}{390000} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{3 \times 90000}$$

$$1186. \quad \frac{234}{416} := \frac{2+34}{4 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{234}{4160} := \frac{2+34}{4 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{234}{41600} := \frac{2+34}{4 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{234}{416000} := \frac{2+34}{4 \times 16000}$$

$$1187. \quad \frac{234}{624} := \frac{2^3 + 4}{(6+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{234}{6240} := \frac{2^3 + 4}{(6+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{234}{62400} := \frac{2^3 + 4}{(6+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{234}{624000} := \frac{2^3 + 4}{(6+2) \times 4000}$$

$$1188. \quad \frac{234}{637} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{63 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{234}{6370} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{63 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{234}{63700} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{63 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{234}{637000} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{63 \times 7000}$$

$$1189. \quad \frac{234}{676} := \frac{23+4}{(6+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{234}{6760} := \frac{23+4}{(6+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{234}{67600} := \frac{23+4}{(6+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{234}{676000} := \frac{23+4}{(6+7) \times 6000}$$

$$1190. \quad \frac{234}{728} := \frac{2+34}{7 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{234}{7280} := \frac{2+34}{7 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{234}{72800} := \frac{2+34}{7 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{234}{728000} := \frac{2+34}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$1191. \quad \frac{234}{975} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{9 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{234}{9750} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{9 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{234}{97500} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{9 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{234}{975000} := \frac{2 \times 3^4}{9 \times 75000}$$

$$1192. \quad \frac{235}{1034} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+34}$$

$$\frac{235}{10340} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+340}$$

$$\frac{235}{103400} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+3400}$$

$$\frac{235}{1034000} := \frac{2+3+5}{10+34000}$$

$$1193. \quad \frac{235}{1175} := \frac{2+3 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{235}{11750} := \frac{2+3 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{235}{117500} := \frac{2+3 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{235}{1175000} := \frac{2+3 \times 5}{1 \times 17 \times 5000}$$

$$1194. \quad \frac{235}{1269} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{(12+6) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{235}{12690} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{(12+6) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{235}{126900} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{(12+6) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{235}{1269000} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5}{(12+6) \times 9000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1195. \quad & \frac{235}{1551} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+51} \\
 & \frac{235}{15651} := \frac{2+3+5}{15+651} \\
 & \frac{156651}{235} := \frac{15+6651}{2+3+5} \\
 & \frac{156651}{156651} := \frac{15+6651}{15+6651}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1200. \quad & \frac{236}{1475} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 6}{1^4 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{14750}{236} := \frac{1^4 \times 750}{2 \times 3 + 6} \\
 & \frac{147500}{236} := \frac{1^4 \times 7500}{2 \times 3 + 6} \\
 & \frac{1475000}{236} := \frac{1^4 \times 75000}{2 \times 3 + 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1205. \quad & \frac{236}{944} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6}{9 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{9440}{236} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 40}{2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{94400}{236} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 400}{2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{944000}{236} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 4000}{2 \times 3 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1196. \quad & \frac{235}{423} := \frac{2 \times 35}{42 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{4230}{235} := \frac{42 \times 30}{2 \times 35} \\
 & \frac{42300}{235} := \frac{42 \times 300}{2 \times 35} \\
 & \frac{423000}{235} := \frac{42 \times 3000}{2 \times 35}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1201. \quad & \frac{236}{295} := \frac{2 \times 36}{2 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{2950}{236} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 50}{2 \times 36} \\
 & \frac{29500}{236} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 500}{2 \times 36} \\
 & \frac{295000}{236} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 5000}{2 \times 36}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1206. \quad & \frac{237}{1264} := \frac{2+3+7}{1^2 \times 64} \\
 & \frac{12640}{237} := \frac{1^2 \times 640}{2+3+7} \\
 & \frac{126400}{237} := \frac{1^2 \times 6400}{2+3+7} \\
 & \frac{1264000}{237} := \frac{1^2 \times 64000}{2+3+7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1197. \quad & \frac{235}{517} := \frac{2+3+5}{5+17} \\
 & \frac{5217}{235} := \frac{5+217}{2+3+5} \\
 & \frac{52217}{235} := \frac{5+2217}{2+3+5} \\
 & \frac{52217}{52217} := \frac{5+2217}{5+2217}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1202. \quad & \frac{236}{472} := \frac{2+3+6}{(4+7) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{4720}{236} := \frac{(4+7) \times 20}{2+3+6} \\
 & \frac{47200}{236} := \frac{(4+7) \times 200}{2+3+6} \\
 & \frac{472000}{236} := \frac{(4+7) \times 2000}{2+3+6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1207. \quad & \frac{238}{1088} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{1 \times 08 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{10880}{238} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 80}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{108800}{238} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 800}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{1088000}{238} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 8000}{2 \times 3 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1198. \quad & \frac{236}{1180} := \frac{2 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 180} \\
 & \frac{11800}{236} := \frac{1 \times 1800}{2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{118000}{236} := \frac{1 \times 18000}{2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{1180000}{236} := \frac{1 \times 180000}{2 \times 3 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1203. \quad & \frac{236}{590} := \frac{2 \times (3+6)}{5 \times 9 + 0} \\
 & \frac{5900}{236} := \frac{5 \times 90 + 0}{2 \times (3+6)} \\
 & \frac{59000}{236} := \frac{5 \times 900 + 0}{2 \times (3+6)} \\
 & \frac{590000}{236} := \frac{5 \times 9000 + 0}{2 \times (3+6)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1208. \quad & \frac{238}{1224} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1+2) \times 24} \\
 & \frac{12240}{238} := \frac{(1+2) \times 240}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{122400}{238} := \frac{(1+2) \times 2400}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{1224000}{238} := \frac{(1+2) \times 24000}{2 \times 3 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1199. \quad & \frac{236}{1416} := \frac{2^3 + 6}{14 \times 1 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{14160}{236} := \frac{2^3 + 6}{14 \times 1 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{141600}{236} := \frac{2^3 + 6}{14 \times 1 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{1416000}{236} := \frac{2^3 + 6}{14 \times 1 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1204. \quad & \frac{236}{649} := \frac{2+3 \times 6}{6+49} \\
 & \frac{6549}{236} := \frac{6+549}{2+3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{65549}{236} := \frac{6+5549}{2+3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{655549}{236} := \frac{6+55549}{2+3 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1209. \quad & \frac{238}{1275} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{12750}{238} := \frac{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{127500}{238} := \frac{(1+2 \times 7) \times 500}{2 \times 3 + 8} \\
 & \frac{1275000}{238} := \frac{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5000}{2 \times 3 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1210. \quad \frac{238}{1326} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 26}$$

$$\frac{238}{13260} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 260}$$

$$\frac{238}{132600} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 2600}$$

$$\frac{238}{1326000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 26000}$$

$$1215. \quad \frac{240}{1485} := \frac{2^4 + 0}{14 + 85}$$

$$\frac{240}{14985} := \frac{2^4 + 0}{14 + 985}$$

$$\frac{240}{149985} := \frac{2^4 + 0}{14 + 9985}$$

$$1220. \quad \frac{242}{1221} := \frac{2 + 42}{1 + 221}$$

$$\frac{242}{12221} := \frac{2 + 42}{1 + 2221}$$

$$\frac{242}{122221} := \frac{2 + 42}{1 + 22221}$$

$$1211. \quad \frac{238}{1445} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{238}{14450} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{238}{144500} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{238}{1445000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5000}$$

$$1216. \quad \frac{240}{1575} := \frac{2 \times 40}{15 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{240}{15750} := \frac{2 \times 40}{15 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{240}{157500} := \frac{2 \times 40}{15 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{240}{1575000} := \frac{2 \times 40}{15 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$1221. \quad \frac{242}{1331} := \frac{2 + 4 + 2}{13 + 31}$$

$$\frac{242}{13431} := \frac{2 + 4 + 2}{13 + 431}$$

$$\frac{242}{134431} := \frac{2 + 4 + 2}{13 + 4431}$$

$$1212. \quad \frac{238}{306} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{3 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{238}{3060} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{3 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{238}{30600} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{3 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{238}{306000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{3 \times 06000}$$

$$1217. \quad \frac{240}{297} := \frac{2 \times 40}{2 + 97}$$

$$\frac{240}{2997} := \frac{2 \times 40}{2 + 997}$$

$$\frac{240}{29997} := \frac{2 \times 40}{2 + 9997}$$

$$1222. \quad \frac{242}{264} := \frac{2 + 42}{2 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{242}{2640} := \frac{2 + 42}{2 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{242}{26400} := \frac{2 + 42}{2 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$1213. \quad \frac{238}{5950} := \frac{(2+3)^8}{5^9 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{238}{59500} := \frac{(2+3)^8}{5^9 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{238}{595000} := \frac{(2+3)^8}{5^9 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$1218. \quad \frac{241}{482} := \frac{2^{4+1}}{4 \times 8 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{241}{4820} := \frac{2^{4+1}}{4 \times 8 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{241}{48200} := \frac{2^{4+1}}{4 \times 8 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{241}{482000} := \frac{2^{4+1}}{4 \times 8 \times 2000}$$

$$1214. \quad \frac{238}{816} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{8 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{238}{8160} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{8 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{238}{81600} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{8 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{238}{816000} := \frac{2 \times 3 + 8}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$1219. \quad \frac{242}{1089} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{242}{10890} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{242}{108900} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{242}{1089000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 9000}$$

$$1223. \quad \frac{242}{363} := \frac{(2+4)^2}{3 \times 6 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{242}{3630} := \frac{(2+4)^2}{3 \times 6 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{242}{36300} := \frac{(2+4)^2}{3 \times 6 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{242}{363000} := \frac{(2+4)^2}{3 \times 6 \times 3000}$$

$$1224. \quad \frac{242}{363} := \frac{2+42}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{242}{3663} := \frac{2+42}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{242}{36663} := \frac{2+42}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{242}{366663} := \frac{2+42}{3+66663}$$

$$1225. \quad \frac{242}{396} := \frac{2+42}{(3+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{242}{3960} := \frac{2+42}{(3+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{242}{39600} := \frac{2+42}{(3+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{242}{396000} := \frac{2+42}{(3+9) \times 6000}$$

$$1226. \quad \frac{242}{484} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{4 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{242}{4840} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{4 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{242}{48400} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{4 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{242}{484000} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{4 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$1227. \quad \frac{242}{484} := \frac{2+42}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{242}{4884} := \frac{2+42}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{242}{48884} := \frac{2+42}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{242}{488884} := \frac{2+42}{4+88884}$$

$$1228. \quad \frac{242}{605} := \frac{2 \times (4+2)}{6 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{242}{6050} := \frac{2 \times (4+2)}{6 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{242}{60500} := \frac{2 \times (4+2)}{6 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{242}{605000} := \frac{2 \times (4+2)}{6 \times 05000}$$

$$1229. \quad \frac{242}{726} := \frac{2+4^2}{(7+2) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{242}{7260} := \frac{2+4^2}{(7+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{242}{72600} := \frac{2+4^2}{(7+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{242}{726000} := \frac{2+4^2}{(7+2) \times 6000}$$

$$1230. \quad \frac{242}{847} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{8 \times 4 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{242}{8470} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{8 \times 4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{242}{84700} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{8 \times 4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{242}{847000} := \frac{2^{4+2}}{8 \times 4 \times 7000}$$

$$1231. \quad \frac{243}{1080} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{243}{10800} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{243}{108000} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 08000}$$

$$1232. \quad \frac{243}{1188} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 88}$$

$$\frac{243}{11880} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 880}$$

$$\frac{243}{118800} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1 \times 1 \times 8800}$$

$$1233. \quad \frac{243}{1197} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 19 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{243}{11970} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 19 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{243}{119700} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 19 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{243}{1197000} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}$$

$$1234. \quad \frac{243}{1215} := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+2) \times 15}$$

$$\frac{243}{12150} := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+2) \times 150}$$

$$\frac{243}{121500} := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+2) \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{243}{1215000} := \frac{2+4+3}{(1+2) \times 15000}$$

$$1235. \quad \frac{243}{1296} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1^2 \times 96}$$

$$\frac{243}{12960} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1^2 \times 960}$$

$$\frac{243}{129600} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1^2 \times 9600}$$

$$\frac{243}{1296000} := \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{1^2 \times 96000}$$

$$1236. \quad \frac{243}{1350} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{243}{13500} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{243}{135000} := \frac{24+3}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$1237. \quad \frac{243}{1368} := \frac{24+3}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{243}{13680} := \frac{24+3}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{243}{136800} := \frac{24+3}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{243}{1368000} := \frac{24+3}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

1238.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{1440} &:= \frac{24+3}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\ \frac{243}{14400} &:= \frac{24+3}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\ \frac{243}{144000} &:= \frac{24+3}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\ \frac{243}{1440000} &:= \frac{24+3}{1 \times 4 \times 40000} \end{aligned}$$

1243.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{5670} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 6 \times 7+0} \\ \frac{243}{56700} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 6 \times 70+0} \\ \frac{243}{567000} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 6 \times 700+0} \\ \frac{243}{5670000} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 6 \times 7000+0} \end{aligned}$$

1248.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{1220} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{(1+2) \times 20} \\ \frac{244}{12200} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{(1+2) \times 200} \\ \frac{244}{122000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{(1+2) \times 2000} \\ \frac{244}{1220000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{(1+2) \times 20000} \end{aligned}$$

1239.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{1485} &:= \frac{24+3}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\ \frac{243}{14850} &:= \frac{24+3}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\ \frac{243}{148500} &:= \frac{24+3}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\ \frac{243}{1485000} &:= \frac{24+3}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1244.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{585} &:= \frac{24+3}{(5+8) \times 5} \\ \frac{243}{5850} &:= \frac{24+3}{(5+8) \times 50} \\ \frac{243}{58500} &:= \frac{24+3}{(5+8) \times 500} \\ \frac{243}{585000} &:= \frac{24+3}{(5+8) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1249.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{1464} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4} \\ \frac{244}{14640} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 40} \\ \frac{244}{146400} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 400} \\ \frac{244}{1464000} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1240.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{324} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \frac{243}{3240} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 40} \\ \frac{243}{32400} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 400} \\ \frac{243}{324000} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 3}{3 \times 2 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1245.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{729} &:= \frac{24+3}{(7+2) \times 9} \\ \frac{243}{7290} &:= \frac{24+3}{(7+2) \times 90} \\ \frac{243}{72900} &:= \frac{24+3}{(7+2) \times 900} \\ \frac{243}{729000} &:= \frac{24+3}{(7+2) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

1250.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{305} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{3 \times 05} \\ \frac{244}{3050} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{3 \times 050} \\ \frac{244}{30500} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{3 \times 0500} \\ \frac{244}{305000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{3 \times 05000} \end{aligned}$$

1241.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{432} &:= \frac{24 \times 3}{4 \times 32} \\ \frac{243}{4320} &:= \frac{24 \times 3}{4 \times 320} \\ \frac{243}{43200} &:= \frac{24 \times 3}{4 \times 3200} \\ \frac{243}{432000} &:= \frac{24 \times 3}{4 \times 32000} \end{aligned}$$

1246.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{810} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{8 \times 10} \\ \frac{243}{8100} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{8 \times 100} \\ \frac{243}{81000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{8 \times 1000} \\ \frac{243}{810000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 3}{8 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

1251.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{427} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 2 \times 7} \\ \frac{244}{4270} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 2 \times 70} \\ \frac{244}{42700} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 2 \times 700} \\ \frac{244}{427000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4 \times 4}{4 \times 2 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

1242.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{540} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 4+0} \\ \frac{243}{5400} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 40+0} \\ \frac{243}{54000} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 400+0} \\ \frac{243}{540000} &:= \frac{2+4+3}{5 \times 4000+0} \end{aligned}$$

1247.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{243}{891} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+91} \\ \frac{243}{8991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+991} \\ \frac{243}{89991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+9991} \\ \frac{243}{899991} &:= \frac{24+3}{8+99991} \end{aligned}$$

1252.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{610} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{6 \times 10} \\ \frac{244}{6100} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{6 \times 100} \\ \frac{244}{61000} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{6 \times 1000} \\ \frac{244}{610000} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{6 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

1253.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{671} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+71} \\ \frac{244}{6771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+771} \\ \frac{244}{67771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+7771} \\ \frac{244}{677771} &:= \frac{24+4}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

1258.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{245}{686} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 5}{6 \times (8+6)} \\ \frac{245}{6860} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 5}{(6+8) \times 60} \\ \frac{245}{68600} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 5}{(6+8) \times 600} \\ \frac{245}{686000} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 5}{(6+8) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1263.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1353} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+53} \\ \frac{246}{13653} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+653} \\ \frac{246}{136653} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{13+6653} \end{aligned}$$

1254.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{915} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{9 \times 1 \times 5} \\ \frac{244}{9150} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{9 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \frac{244}{91500} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{9 \times 1 \times 500} \\ \frac{244}{915000} &:= \frac{2 \times 4+4}{9 \times 1 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1259.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{245}{875} &:= \frac{2^4+5}{(8+7) \times 5} \\ \frac{245}{8750} &:= \frac{2^4+5}{(8+7) \times 50} \\ \frac{245}{87500} &:= \frac{2^4+5}{(8+7) \times 500} \\ \frac{245}{875000} &:= \frac{2^4+5}{(8+7) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1264.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1435} &:= \frac{24+6}{(1+4) \times 35} \\ \frac{246}{14350} &:= \frac{24+6}{(1+4) \times 350} \\ \frac{246}{143500} &:= \frac{24+6}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\ \frac{246}{1435000} &:= \frac{24+6}{(1+4) \times 35000} \end{aligned}$$

1255.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{244}{976} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{(9+7) \times 6} \\ \frac{244}{9760} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{(9+7) \times 60} \\ \frac{244}{97600} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{(9+7) \times 600} \\ \frac{244}{976000} &:= \frac{(2+4) \times 4}{(9+7) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1260.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{245}{980} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{9 \times 8+0} \\ \frac{245}{9800} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{9 \times 80+0} \\ \frac{245}{98000} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{9 \times 800+0} \\ \frac{245}{980000} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{9 \times 8000+0} \end{aligned}$$

1265.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1476} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+4+7) \times 6} \\ \frac{246}{14760} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+4+7) \times 60} \\ \frac{246}{147600} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+4+7) \times 600} \\ \frac{246}{1476000} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+4+7) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1256.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{245}{1225} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 5}{1 \times 22 \times 5} \\ \frac{245}{12250} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 5}{1 \times 22 \times 50} \\ \frac{245}{122500} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 5}{1 \times 22 \times 500} \\ \frac{245}{1225000} &:= \frac{2+4 \times 5}{1 \times 22 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1261.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1230} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{1 \times 2 \times 30} \\ \frac{246}{12300} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{1 \times 2 \times 300} \\ \frac{246}{123000} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{1 \times 2 \times 3000} \\ \frac{246}{1230000} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{1 \times 2 \times 30000} \end{aligned}$$

1257.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{245}{490} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{4 \times 9+0} \\ \frac{245}{4900} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{4 \times 90+0} \\ \frac{245}{49000} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{4 \times 900+0} \\ \frac{245}{490000} &:= \frac{2 \times (4+5)}{4 \times 9000+0} \end{aligned}$$

1262.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{1312} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+31) \times 2} \\ \frac{246}{13120} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+31) \times 20} \\ \frac{246}{131200} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+31) \times 200} \\ \frac{246}{1312000} &:= \frac{2+4+6}{(1+31) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1266.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{246}{287} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 6}{2 \times 8 \times 7} \\ \frac{246}{2870} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 6}{2 \times 8 \times 70} \\ \frac{246}{28700} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 6}{2 \times 8 \times 700} \\ \frac{246}{287000} &:= \frac{2^4 \times 6}{2 \times 8 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1267. \quad \frac{246}{328} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{246}{3280} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{246}{32800} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{246}{328000} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{3 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$1272. \quad \frac{247}{1045} := \frac{2+4+7}{10+45}$$

$$\frac{247}{10545} := \frac{2+4+7}{10+545}$$

$$\frac{247}{105545} := \frac{2+4+7}{10+5545}$$

$$1277. \quad \frac{247}{1463} := \frac{2+4+7}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{247}{14763} := \frac{2+4+7}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{247}{147763} := \frac{2+4+7}{14+7763}$$

$$1268. \quad \frac{246}{451} := \frac{24+6}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{246}{4551} := \frac{24+6}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{246}{45551} := \frac{24+6}{4+5551}$$

$$\frac{246}{455551} := \frac{24+6}{4+55551}$$

$$1273. \quad \frac{247}{1197} := \frac{2+4+7}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{247}{11970} := \frac{2+4+7}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{247}{119700} := \frac{2+4+7}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$1278. \quad \frac{247}{418} := \frac{2+4+7}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{247}{4218} := \frac{2+4+7}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{247}{42218} := \frac{2+4+7}{4+2218}$$

$$1269. \quad \frac{246}{492} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{246}{4920} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{246}{49200} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{246}{492000} := \frac{(2+4) \times 6}{4 \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$1274. \quad \frac{247}{1235} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 7}{(12+3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{247}{12350} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 7}{(12+3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{247}{123500} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 7}{(12+3) \times 500}$$

$$1279. \quad \frac{247}{627} := \frac{2+4+7}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{247}{6327} := \frac{2+4+7}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{247}{63327} := \frac{2+4+7}{6+3327}$$

$$1270. \quad \frac{246}{615} := \frac{2+4+6}{6 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{246}{6150} := \frac{2+4+6}{6 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{246}{61500} := \frac{2+4+6}{6 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{246}{615000} := \frac{2+4+6}{6 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$1275. \quad \frac{247}{1254} := \frac{2+4+7}{12+54}$$

$$\frac{247}{12654} := \frac{2+4+7}{12+654}$$

$$\frac{247}{126654} := \frac{2+4+7}{12+6654}$$

$$1280. \quad \frac{247}{836} := \frac{2+4+7}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{247}{8436} := \frac{2+4+7}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{247}{84436} := \frac{2+4+7}{8+4436}$$

$$1271. \quad \frac{246}{820} := \frac{2+46}{8 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{246}{8200} := \frac{2+46}{8 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{246}{82000} := \frac{2+46}{8 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{246}{820000} := \frac{2+46}{8 \times 20000}$$

$$1276. \quad \frac{247}{1368} := \frac{2+4+7}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{247}{13680} := \frac{2+4+7}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{247}{136800} := \frac{2+4+7}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{247}{1368000} := \frac{2+4+7}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8000}$$

$$1281. \quad \frac{248}{1116} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(1+11) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{248}{11160} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(1+11) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{248}{111600} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(1+11) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{248}{1116000} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(1+11) \times 6000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1282. \quad & \frac{248}{1240} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{248}{12400} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{248}{124000} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{248}{1240000} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1287. \quad & \frac{248}{341} := \frac{24 + 8}{3 + 41} \\
 & \frac{248}{3441} := \frac{24 + 8}{3 + 441} \\
 & \frac{248}{34441} := \frac{24 + 8}{3 + 4441} \\
 & \frac{248}{344441} := \frac{24 + 8}{3 + 44441}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1292. \quad & \frac{248}{682} := \frac{24 + 8}{6 + 82} \\
 & \frac{248}{6882} := \frac{24 + 8}{6 + 882} \\
 & \frac{248}{68882} := \frac{24 + 8}{6 + 8882} \\
 & \frac{248}{688882} := \frac{24 + 8}{6 + 88882}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1283. \quad & \frac{248}{13764} := \frac{2 + 4 + 8}{13 + 764} \\
 & \frac{248}{137764} := \frac{2 + 4 + 8}{13 + 7764} \\
 & \frac{248}{1377764} := \frac{2 + 4 + 8}{13 + 77764} \\
 & \frac{248}{13777764} := \frac{2 + 4 + 8}{13 + 777764}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1288. \quad & \frac{248}{434} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(4 + 3) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{248}{4340} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(4 + 3) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{248}{43400} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(4 + 3) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{248}{434000} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 8}{(4 + 3) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1293. \quad & \frac{248}{868} := \frac{24 + 8}{(8 + 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{248}{8680} := \frac{24 + 8}{(8 + 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{248}{86800} := \frac{24 + 8}{(8 + 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{248}{868000} := \frac{24 + 8}{(8 + 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1284. \quad & \frac{248}{1395} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{248}{13950} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{248}{139500} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{248}{1395000} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1289. \quad & \frac{248}{465} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{4 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{248}{4650} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{4 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{248}{46500} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{4 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{248}{465000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{4 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1294. \quad & \frac{249}{1245} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2^4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{249}{12450} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2^4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{249}{124500} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2^4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{249}{1245000} := \frac{2 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2^4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1285. \quad & \frac{248}{1488} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 48 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{248}{14880} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 48 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{248}{148800} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 48 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{248}{1488000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 48 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1290. \quad & \frac{248}{496} := \frac{24 \times 8}{4 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{248}{4960} := \frac{24 \times 8}{4 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{248}{49600} := \frac{24 \times 8}{4 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{248}{496000} := \frac{24 \times 8}{4 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1295. \quad & \frac{249}{1328} := \frac{2 + 4 + 9}{(1 + 3^2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{249}{13280} := \frac{2 + 4 + 9}{(1 + 3^2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{249}{132800} := \frac{2 + 4 + 9}{(1 + 3^2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{249}{1328000} := \frac{2 + 4 + 9}{(1 + 3^2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1286. \quad & \frac{248}{310} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{3 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{248}{3100} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{3 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{248}{31000} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{3 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{248}{310000} := \frac{2 \times (4 + 8)}{3 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1291. \quad & \frac{248}{620} := \frac{(2 + 4) \times 8}{6 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{248}{6200} := \frac{(2 + 4) \times 8}{6 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{248}{62000} := \frac{(2 + 4) \times 8}{6 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{248}{620000} := \frac{(2 + 4) \times 8}{6 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1296. \quad & \frac{249}{332} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{3 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{249}{3320} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{3 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{249}{33200} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{3 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{249}{332000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{3 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1297. \quad & \frac{249}{415} := \frac{2+4+9}{(4+1) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{249}{4150} := \frac{2+4+9}{(4+1) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{249}{41500} := \frac{2+4+9}{(4+1) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{249}{415000} := \frac{2+4+9}{(4+1) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1302. \quad & \frac{250}{13875} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(13 \times 8 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{138750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(13 \times 8 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{1387500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(13 \times 8 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{13875000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(13 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1307. \quad & \frac{250}{17875} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{178750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{1787500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{17875000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1298. \quad & \frac{249}{498} := \frac{2^4 \times 9}{4 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{249}{4980} := \frac{2^4 \times 9}{4 \times 9 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{249}{49800} := \frac{2^4 \times 9}{4 \times 9 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{249}{498000} := \frac{2^4 \times 9}{4 \times 9 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1303. \quad & \frac{250}{15875} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(15 \times 8 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{158750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(15 \times 8 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{1587500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(15 \times 8 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{15875000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(15 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1308. \quad & \frac{250}{18375} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{183750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{1837500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{18375000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1299. \quad & \frac{249}{830} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{8 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{249}{8300} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{8 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{249}{83000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{8 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{249}{830000} := \frac{2 \times 4 \times 9}{8 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1304. \quad & \frac{250}{1625} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{16250} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{162500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{1625000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1309. \quad & \frac{250}{1875} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{18750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{187500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{1875000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1300. \quad & \frac{249}{996} := \frac{24 \times 9}{9 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{249}{9960} := \frac{24 \times 9}{9 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{249}{99600} := \frac{24 \times 9}{9 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{249}{996000} := \frac{24 \times 9}{9 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1305. \quad & \frac{250}{1575} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 57 + 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{16575} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 657 + 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{166575} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 6657 + 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{1666575} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{1 + 66657 + 5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1301. \quad & \frac{250}{1375} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 3 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{13750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 3 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{137500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 3 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{1375000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(1 + 3 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1306. \quad & \frac{250}{1665} := \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 665} \\
 & \frac{250}{16665} := \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 6665} \\
 & \frac{250}{166665} := \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 66665} \\
 & \frac{250}{1666665} := \frac{2 \times 50}{1 + 666665}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1310. \quad & \frac{250}{18875} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 \times 8 + 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{250}{188750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 \times 8 + 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{250}{1887500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 \times 8 + 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{250}{18875000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{(18 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1311. \quad & \frac{250}{825} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 25} \\
 & \frac{250}{8325} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 325} \\
 & \frac{250}{83325} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 3325} \\
 & \frac{250}{833325} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 0}{8 + 33325}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1316. \quad & \frac{251}{753} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 1)}{(7 + 5) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{251}{7530} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 1)}{(7 + 5) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{251}{75300} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 1)}{(7 + 5) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{251}{753000} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 1)}{(7 + 5) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1321. \quad & \frac{252}{1155} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 55} \\
 & \frac{252}{11550} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 550} \\
 & \frac{252}{115500} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 5500} \\
 & \frac{252}{1155000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1312. \quad & \frac{251}{1004} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 04} \\
 & \frac{251}{10040} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 040} \\
 & \frac{251}{100400} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{251}{1004000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1317. \quad & \frac{252}{1008} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 2}{10 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{252}{10080} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 2}{10 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{252}{100800} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 2}{10 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{252}{1008000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 2}{10 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1322. \quad & \frac{252}{1176} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{252}{11760} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{252}{117600} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{252}{1176000} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1313. \quad & \frac{251}{1004} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 04} \\
 & \frac{251}{10040} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 040} \\
 & \frac{251}{100400} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{251}{1004000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{10 \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1318. \quad & \frac{252}{1050} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{252}{10500} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{252}{105000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 05000} \\
 & \frac{252}{1050000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1 \times 050000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1323. \quad & \frac{252}{1260} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{252}{12600} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{252}{126000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{252}{1260000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{1^2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1314. \quad & \frac{251}{11044} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 44} \\
 & \frac{251}{110440} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 440} \\
 & \frac{251}{1104400} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{251}{11044000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1319. \quad & \frac{252}{1120} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{(1 + 1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{252}{11200} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{(1 + 1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{252}{112000} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{(1 + 1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{252}{1120000} := \frac{2 + 5 + 2}{(1 + 1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1324. \quad & \frac{252}{1296} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 2 + 9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{252}{12960} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 2 + 9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{252}{129600} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 2 + 9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{252}{1296000} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 2 + 9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1315. \quad & \frac{251}{1255} := \frac{25 + 1}{(1 + 25) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{251}{12550} := \frac{25 + 1}{(1 + 25) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{251}{125500} := \frac{25 + 1}{(1 + 25) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{251}{1255000} := \frac{25 + 1}{(1 + 25) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1320. \quad & \frac{252}{1152} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 1)^5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{252}{11520} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 1)^5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{252}{115200} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 1)^5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{252}{1152000} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 2)}{(1 + 1)^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1325. \quad & \frac{252}{1302} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{(1 + 30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{252}{13020} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{(1 + 30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{252}{130200} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{(1 + 30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{252}{1302000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 2}{(1 + 30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1326. \quad \frac{252}{1344} := \frac{2+5+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{252}{13440} := \frac{2+5+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{252}{134400} := \frac{2+5+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{252}{1344000} := \frac{2+5+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$1327. \quad \frac{252}{1365} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{252}{13650} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{252}{136500} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{252}{1365000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^3 \times 65000}$$

$$1328. \quad \frac{252}{1386} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{252}{13860} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{252}{138600} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{252}{1386000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$1329. \quad \frac{252}{1470} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{252}{14700} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{252}{147000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{252}{1470000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{1^4 \times 70000}$$

$$1330. \quad \frac{252}{308} := \frac{2+5+2}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{252}{3108} := \frac{2+5+2}{3+108}$$

$$\frac{252}{31108} := \frac{2+5+2}{3+1108}$$

$$\frac{252}{311108} := \frac{2+5+2}{3+11108}$$

$$1331. \quad \frac{252}{315} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{252}{3150} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{252}{31500} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{252}{315000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{3 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$1332. \quad \frac{252}{336} := \frac{2+5^2}{(3+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{252}{3360} := \frac{2+5^2}{(3+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{252}{33600} := \frac{2+5^2}{(3+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{252}{336000} := \frac{2+5^2}{(3+3) \times 6000}$$

$$1333. \quad \frac{252}{432} := \frac{2 \times (5+2)}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{252}{4320} := \frac{2 \times (5+2)}{4 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{252}{43200} := \frac{2 \times (5+2)}{4 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{252}{432000} := \frac{2 \times (5+2)}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$1334. \quad \frac{252}{504} := \frac{(2 \times 5)^2}{50 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{252}{5040} := \frac{(2 \times 5)^2}{50 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{252}{50400} := \frac{(2 \times 5)^2}{50 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{252}{504000} := \frac{(2 \times 5)^2}{50 \times 4000}$$

$$1335. \quad \frac{252}{616} := \frac{2+5+2}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{252}{6216} := \frac{2+5+2}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{252}{62216} := \frac{2+5+2}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{252}{622216} := \frac{2+5+2}{6+22216}$$

$$1336. \quad \frac{252}{720} := \frac{(2+5)^2}{7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{252}{7200} := \frac{(2+5)^2}{7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{252}{72000} := \frac{(2+5)^2}{7 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{252}{720000} := \frac{(2+5)^2}{7 \times 20000}$$

$$1337. \quad \frac{252}{924} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(9+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{252}{9240} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(9+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{252}{92400} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(9+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{252}{924000} := \frac{2+5 \times 2}{(9+2) \times 4000}$$

$$1338. \quad \frac{252}{924} := \frac{2+5+2}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{252}{9324} := \frac{2+5+2}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{252}{93324} := \frac{2+5+2}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{252}{933324} := \frac{2+5+2}{9+33324}$$

$$1339. \quad \frac{253}{1012} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3}{10 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{253}{10120} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3}{10 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{253}{101200} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3}{10 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{253}{1012000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 3}{10 \times 12000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1340. \quad & \frac{253}{1265} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 3}{(1 + 2 \times 6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{253}{12650} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 3}{(1 + 2 \times 6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{253}{126500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 3}{(1 + 2 \times 6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{253}{1265000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 3}{(1 + 2 \times 6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1345. \quad & \frac{255}{1020} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 5}{10 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{255}{10200} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 5}{10 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{255}{102000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 5}{10 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{255}{1020000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 5}{10 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1350. \quad & \frac{255}{1428} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 28} \\
 & \frac{255}{14280} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 280} \\
 & \frac{255}{142800} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 2800} \\
 & \frac{255}{1428000} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 28000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1341. \quad & \frac{254}{1016} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4}{10 \times 16} \\
 & \frac{254}{10160} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4}{10 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{254}{101600} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4}{10 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{254}{1016000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 4}{10 \times 16000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1346. \quad & \frac{255}{1088} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 08 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{255}{10880} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 08 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{255}{108800} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 08 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{255}{1088000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 08 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1351. \quad & \frac{255}{1445} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{255}{14450} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{255}{144500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{255}{1445000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1342. \quad & \frac{254}{1270} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 4}{1^2 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{254}{12700} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 4}{1^2 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{254}{127000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 4}{1^2 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{254}{1270000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 4}{1^2 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1347. \quad & \frac{255}{1224} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{12 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{255}{12240} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{12 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{255}{122400} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{12 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{255}{1224000} := \frac{2 \times (5 + 5)}{12 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1352. \quad & \frac{255}{1683} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 83} \\
 & \frac{255}{16983} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 983} \\
 & \frac{255}{169983} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 9983} \\
 & \frac{255}{1699983} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 99983}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1343. \quad & \frac{254}{1397} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{(13 + 9) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{254}{13970} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{(13 + 9) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{254}{139700} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{(13 + 9) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{254}{1397000} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{(13 + 9) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1348. \quad & \frac{255}{1275} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{255}{12750} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{255}{127500} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{255}{1275000} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1353. \quad & \frac{255}{1734} := \frac{25 + 5}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{255}{17340} := \frac{25 + 5}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{255}{173400} := \frac{25 + 5}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{255}{1734000} := \frac{25 + 5}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1344. \quad & \frac{254}{762} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{7 \times 6 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{254}{7620} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{7 \times 6 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{254}{76200} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{7 \times 6 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{254}{762000} := \frac{(2 + 5) \times 4}{7 \times 6 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1349. \quad & \frac{255}{1326} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 3 \times 26} \\
 & \frac{255}{13260} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 3 \times 260} \\
 & \frac{255}{132600} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 3 \times 2600} \\
 & \frac{255}{1326000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 3 \times 26000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1354. \quad & \frac{255}{17374} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{255}{173740} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{255}{1737400} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{255}{17374000} := \frac{25 + 5}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1355. \quad & \frac{255}{306} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{3 \times 06} \\
 & \frac{255}{3060} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{3 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{255}{30600} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{3 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{255}{306000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{3 \times 06000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1360. \quad & \frac{255}{714} := \frac{(2+5) \times 5}{7 \times 14} \\
 & \frac{255}{7140} := \frac{(2+5) \times 5}{7 \times 140} \\
 & \frac{255}{71400} := \frac{(2+5) \times 5}{7 \times 1400} \\
 & \frac{255}{714000} := \frac{(2+5) \times 5}{7 \times 14000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1365. \quad & \frac{255}{935} := \frac{2+5+5}{9+35} \\
 & \frac{255}{9435} := \frac{2+5+5}{9+435} \\
 & \frac{255}{94435} := \frac{2+5+5}{9+4435} \\
 & \frac{255}{944435} := \frac{2+5+5}{9+44435}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1356. \quad & \frac{255}{408} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{4 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{255}{4080} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{4 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{255}{40800} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{4 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{255}{408000} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{4 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1361. \quad & \frac{255}{748} := \frac{25+5}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{255}{7480} := \frac{25+5}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{255}{74800} := \frac{25+5}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{255}{748000} := \frac{25+5}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1366. \quad & \frac{256}{1024} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6}{10 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{256}{10240} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6}{10 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{256}{102400} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6}{10 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{256}{1024000} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 6}{10 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1357. \quad & \frac{255}{561} := \frac{25+5}{5+61} \\
 & \frac{255}{5661} := \frac{25+5}{5+661} \\
 & \frac{255}{56661} := \frac{25+5}{5+6661} \\
 & \frac{255}{566661} := \frac{25+5}{5+66661}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1362. \quad & \frac{255}{816} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{8 \times 1 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{255}{8160} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{8 \times 1 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{255}{81600} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{8 \times 1 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{255}{816000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 5}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1367. \quad & \frac{256}{1056} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 56} \\
 & \frac{256}{10656} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 656} \\
 & \frac{256}{106656} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 6656} \\
 & \frac{256}{1066656} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{10 + 66656}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1358. \quad & \frac{255}{595} := \frac{25+5}{(5+9) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{255}{5950} := \frac{25+5}{(5+9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{255}{59500} := \frac{25+5}{(5+9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{255}{595000} := \frac{25+5}{(5+9) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1363. \quad & \frac{255}{850} := \frac{2+5+5}{8 \times 5+0} \\
 & \frac{255}{8500} := \frac{2+5+5}{8 \times 50+0} \\
 & \frac{255}{85000} := \frac{2+5+5}{8 \times 500+0} \\
 & \frac{255}{850000} := \frac{2+5+5}{8 \times 5000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1368. \quad & \frac{256}{1280} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{12 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{256}{12800} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{12 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{256}{128000} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{12 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{256}{1280000} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{12 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1359. \quad & \frac{255}{612} := \frac{25+5}{6 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{255}{6120} := \frac{25+5}{6 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{255}{61200} := \frac{25+5}{6 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{255}{612000} := \frac{25+5}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1364. \quad & \frac{255}{918} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{9 \times 1 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{255}{9180} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{9 \times 1 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{255}{91800} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{9 \times 1 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{255}{918000} := \frac{2 \times (5+5)}{9 \times 1 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1369. \quad & \frac{256}{1296} := \frac{2+5 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{256}{12960} := \frac{2+5 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{256}{129600} := \frac{2+5 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{256}{1296000} := \frac{2+5 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1370. \quad \frac{256}{1584} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 84}$$

$$\frac{256}{15984} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 984}$$

$$\frac{256}{159984} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 9984}$$

$$\frac{256}{1599984} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 6}{15 + 99984}$$

$$1375. \quad \frac{256}{792} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 92}$$

$$\frac{256}{7992} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 992}$$

$$\frac{256}{79992} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{7 + 9992}$$

$$1380. \quad \frac{258}{1290} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1^2 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{258}{12900} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1^2 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{258}{129000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1^2 \times 9000}$$

$$1371. \quad \frac{256}{1776} := \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 776}$$

$$\frac{256}{17776} := \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 7776}$$

$$\frac{256}{177776} := \frac{2 \times 56}{1 + 77776}$$

$$1376. \quad \frac{257}{1028} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 7}{10 \times 28}$$

$$\frac{257}{10280} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 7}{10 \times 280}$$

$$\frac{257}{102800} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 7}{10 \times 2800}$$

$$1381. \quad \frac{258}{473} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{(4 + 7) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{258}{4730} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{(4 + 7) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{258}{47300} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{(4 + 7) \times 300}$$

$$1372. \quad \frac{256}{672} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{256}{6720} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{256}{67200} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{256}{672000} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$1377. \quad \frac{257}{1285} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 7}{(1 + 2 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{257}{12850} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 7}{(1 + 2 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{257}{128500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 7}{(1 + 2 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{257}{1285000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 7}{(1 + 2 \times 8) \times 5000}$$

$$1382. \quad \frac{258}{473} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 73}$$

$$\frac{258}{4773} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 773}$$

$$\frac{258}{47773} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{4 + 7773}$$

$$1373. \quad \frac{256}{768} := \frac{2 \times 56}{7 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{256}{7680} := \frac{2 \times 56}{7 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{256}{76800} := \frac{2 \times 56}{7 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{256}{768000} := \frac{2 \times 56}{7 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$1378. \quad \frac{258}{1032} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 8}{10 \times 32}$$

$$\frac{258}{10320} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 8}{10 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{258}{103200} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 8}{10 \times 3200}$$

$$1383. \quad \frac{258}{688} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{(6 + 8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{258}{6880} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{(6 + 8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{258}{68800} := \frac{2 + 5 \times 8}{(6 + 8) \times 800}$$

$$1374. \quad \frac{256}{784} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{256}{7840} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{256}{78400} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{256}{784000} := \frac{2^5 \times 6}{7 \times 84000}$$

$$1379. \quad \frac{258}{1075} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 075}$$

$$\frac{258}{10750} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 0750}$$

$$\frac{258}{107500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 07500}$$

$$1384. \quad \frac{258}{946} := \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 46}$$

$$\frac{258}{9546} := \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 546}$$

$$\frac{258}{95546} := \frac{2 + 5 + 8}{9 + 5546}$$

$$1385. \quad \frac{259}{1036} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 9}{10 \times 36}$$

$$\frac{259}{10360} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 9}{10 \times 360}$$

$$\frac{259}{103600} := \frac{2 \times 5 \times 9}{10 \times 3600}$$

$$1390. \quad \frac{260}{1365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+36+5}$$

$$\frac{260}{14365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+436+5}$$

$$\frac{260}{144365} := \frac{2+6+0}{1+4436+5}$$

$$1395. \quad \frac{261}{1305} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 1}{13 \times 05}$$

$$\frac{261}{13050} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 1}{13 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{261}{130500} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 1}{13 \times 05000}$$

$$1386. \quad \frac{259}{1258} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(12+5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{259}{12580} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(12+5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{259}{125800} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(12+5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{259}{1258000} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(12+5) \times 8000}$$

$$1391. \quad \frac{260}{15925} := \frac{2+6+0}{(1+5+92) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{260}{159250} := \frac{2+6+0}{(1+5+92) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{260}{1592500} := \frac{2+6+0}{(1+5+92) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{260}{15925000} := \frac{2+6+0}{(1+5+92) \times 5000}$$

$$1396. \quad \frac{261}{725} := \frac{2+61}{7 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{261}{7250} := \frac{2+61}{7 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{261}{72500} := \frac{2+61}{7 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{261}{725000} := \frac{2+61}{7 \times 25000}$$

$$1387. \quad \frac{259}{1295} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{259}{12950} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{259}{129500} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{259}{1295000} := \frac{2 \times 5 + 9}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 5000}$$

$$1392. \quad \frac{260}{715} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+15}$$

$$\frac{260}{7215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+215}$$

$$\frac{260}{72215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+2215}$$

$$\frac{260}{722215} := \frac{2+6+0}{7+22215}$$

$$1397. \quad \frac{261}{986} := \frac{26+1}{(9+8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{261}{9860} := \frac{26+1}{(9+8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{261}{98600} := \frac{26+1}{(9+8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{261}{986000} := \frac{26+1}{(9+8) \times 6000}$$

$$1388. \quad \frac{259}{333} := \frac{(2+5) \times 9}{3^3 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{259}{3330} := \frac{(2+5) \times 9}{3^3 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{259}{33300} := \frac{(2+5) \times 9}{3^3 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{259}{333000} := \frac{(2+5) \times 9}{3^3 \times 3000}$$

$$1393. \quad \frac{261}{1044} := \frac{2 \times (6+1)}{(10+4) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{261}{10440} := \frac{2 \times (6+1)}{(10+4) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{261}{104400} := \frac{2 \times (6+1)}{(10+4) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{261}{1044000} := \frac{2 \times (6+1)}{(10+4) \times 4000}$$

$$1389. \quad \frac{259}{666} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(6+6) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{259}{6660} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(6+6) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{259}{66600} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(6+6) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{259}{666000} := \frac{2 \times (5+9)}{(6+6) \times 6000}$$

$$1394. \quad \frac{261}{1160} := \frac{26+1}{(1+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{261}{11600} := \frac{26+1}{(1+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{261}{116000} := \frac{26+1}{(1+1) \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{261}{1160000} := \frac{26+1}{(1+1) \times 60000}$$

$$1398. \quad \frac{262}{1048} := \frac{26+2}{(10+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{262}{10480} := \frac{26+2}{(10+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{262}{104800} := \frac{26+2}{(10+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{262}{1048000} := \frac{26+2}{(10+4) \times 8000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1399. \quad & \frac{262}{1179} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{262}{11790} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{262}{117900} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{262}{1179000} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1404. \quad & \frac{264}{1188} := \frac{(2+6) \times 4}{1 \times 18 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{264}{11880} := \frac{(2+6) \times 4}{1 \times 18 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{264}{118800} := \frac{(2+6) \times 4}{1 \times 18 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{264}{1188000} := \frac{(2+6) \times 4}{1 \times 18 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1409. \quad & \frac{264}{363} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+63} \\
 & \frac{264}{3663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+663} \\
 & \frac{264}{36663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+6663} \\
 & \frac{264}{366663} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{3+66663}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1400. \quad & \frac{262}{1441} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+41} \\
 & \frac{262}{14541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+541} \\
 & \frac{262}{145541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+5541} \\
 & \frac{262}{1455541} := \frac{2+6+2}{14+55541}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1405. \quad & \frac{264}{1221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{264}{12221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{264}{122221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+22221} \\
 & \frac{264}{1222221} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{1+222221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1410. \quad & \frac{264}{384} := \frac{2+64}{3 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{264}{3840} := \frac{2+64}{3 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{264}{38400} := \frac{2+64}{3 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{264}{384000} := \frac{2+64}{3 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1401. \quad & \frac{262}{393} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 2}{(3+9) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{262}{3930} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 2}{(3+9) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{262}{39300} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 2}{(3+9) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{262}{393000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 2}{(3+9) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1406. \quad & \frac{264}{1320} := \frac{2+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{264}{13200} := \frac{2+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{264}{132000} := \frac{2+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{264}{1320000} := \frac{2+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1411. \quad & \frac{264}{396} := \frac{2+64}{3+96} \\
 & \frac{264}{3996} := \frac{2+64}{3+996} \\
 & \frac{264}{39996} := \frac{2+64}{3+9996} \\
 & \frac{264}{399996} := \frac{2+64}{3+99996}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1402. \quad & \frac{262}{524} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{(5+2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{262}{5240} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{(5+2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{262}{52400} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{(5+2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{262}{524000} := \frac{2+6 \times 2}{(5+2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1407. \quad & \frac{264}{1332} := \frac{2+64}{1+332} \\
 & \frac{264}{13332} := \frac{2+64}{1+3332} \\
 & \frac{264}{133332} := \frac{2+64}{1+33332} \\
 & \frac{264}{1333332} := \frac{2+64}{1+333332}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1412. \quad & \frac{264}{396} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{(3+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{264}{3960} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{(3+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{264}{39600} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{(3+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{264}{396000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{(3+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1403. \quad & \frac{263}{526} := \frac{2+63}{5 \times 26} \\
 & \frac{263}{5260} := \frac{2+63}{5 \times 260} \\
 & \frac{263}{52600} := \frac{2+63}{5 \times 2600} \\
 & \frac{263}{526000} := \frac{2+63}{5 \times 26000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1408. \quad & \frac{264}{1452} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+52} \\
 & \frac{264}{14652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+652} \\
 & \frac{264}{146652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+6652} \\
 & \frac{264}{1466652} := \frac{2+6+4}{14+66652}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1413. \quad & \frac{264}{396} := \frac{2+64}{3+96} \\
 & \frac{264}{3996} := \frac{2+64}{3+996} \\
 & \frac{264}{39996} := \frac{2+64}{3+9996} \\
 & \frac{264}{399996} := \frac{2+64}{3+99996}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1414. \quad \frac{264}{484} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{4 + 84} \\
 \frac{264}{4884} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{4 + 884} \\
 \frac{264}{48884} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{4 + 8884} \\
 \frac{264}{488884} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 4}{4 + 88884}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1419. \quad \frac{265}{1325} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 5}{1 \times 32 \times 5} \\
 \frac{265}{13250} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 5}{1 \times 32 \times 50} \\
 \frac{265}{132500} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 5}{1 \times 32 \times 500} \\
 \frac{265}{1325000} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 5}{1 \times 32 \times 5000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1424. \quad \frac{266}{1045} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{10 + 45} \\
 \frac{266}{10545} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{10 + 545} \\
 \frac{266}{105545} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{10 + 5545} \\
 \frac{266}{1055545} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{10 + 55545}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1415. \quad \frac{264}{550} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{5 \times 5 + 0} \\
 \frac{264}{5500} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{5 \times 50 + 0} \\
 \frac{264}{55000} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{5 \times 500 + 0} \\
 \frac{264}{550000} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{5 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1420. \quad \frac{265}{1378} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 78} \\
 \frac{265}{13780} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 780} \\
 \frac{265}{137800} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 7800} \\
 \frac{265}{1378000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 78000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1425. \quad \frac{266}{1197} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 \frac{266}{11970} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 \frac{266}{119700} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 \frac{266}{1197000} := \frac{2 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1416. \quad \frac{264}{726} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{7 + 26} \\
 \frac{264}{7326} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{7 + 326} \\
 \frac{264}{73326} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{7 + 3326} \\
 \frac{264}{733326} := \frac{2 + 6 + 4}{7 + 33326}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1421. \quad \frac{265}{1484} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 84} \\
 \frac{265}{14840} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 840} \\
 \frac{265}{148400} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 8400} \\
 \frac{265}{1484000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 84000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1426. \quad \frac{266}{1260} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{(1 + 2) \times 60} \\
 \frac{266}{12600} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{(1 + 2) \times 600} \\
 \frac{266}{126000} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{(1 + 2) \times 6000} \\
 \frac{266}{1260000} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{(1 + 2) \times 60000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1417. \quad \frac{264}{825} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(8 + 2) \times 5} \\
 \frac{264}{8250} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(8 + 2) \times 50} \\
 \frac{264}{82500} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(8 + 2) \times 500} \\
 \frac{264}{825000} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 4}{(8 + 2) \times 5000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1422. \quad \frac{265}{424} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{4 \times 24} \\
 \frac{265}{4240} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{4 \times 240} \\
 \frac{265}{42400} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{4 \times 2400} \\
 \frac{265}{424000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 5}{4 \times 24000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1427. \quad \frac{266}{1330} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 30} \\
 \frac{266}{13300} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 300} \\
 \frac{266}{133000} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 3000} \\
 \frac{266}{1330000} := \frac{2 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 3 \times 30000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1418. \quad \frac{264}{858} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 5) \times 8} \\
 \frac{264}{8580} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 5) \times 80} \\
 \frac{264}{85800} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 5) \times 800} \\
 \frac{264}{858000} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 4}{(8 + 5) \times 8000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1423. \quad \frac{265}{583} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 5}{5 + 83} \\
 \frac{265}{5883} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 5}{5 + 883} \\
 \frac{265}{58883} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 5}{5 + 8883} \\
 \frac{265}{588883} := \frac{(2 + 6) \times 5}{5 + 88883}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
 1428. \quad \frac{266}{1365} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 \frac{266}{13650} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 \frac{266}{136500} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\
 \frac{266}{1365000} := \frac{2 + 6 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1429. \quad & \frac{266}{1368} := \frac{2+6+6}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{266}{13680} := \frac{2+6+6}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{266}{136800} := \frac{2+6+6}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{266}{1368000} := \frac{2+6+6}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1434. \quad & \frac{266}{418} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+18} \\
 & \frac{266}{4218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+218} \\
 & \frac{266}{42218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+2218} \\
 & \frac{266}{422218} := \frac{2+6+6}{4+22218}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1439. \quad & \frac{266}{665} := \frac{2 \times 66}{66 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{266}{6650} := \frac{2 \times 66}{66 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{266}{66500} := \frac{2 \times 66}{66 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{266}{665000} := \frac{2 \times 66}{66 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1430. \quad & \frac{266}{1463} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{266}{14763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{266}{147763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{266}{1477763} := \frac{2+6+6}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1435. \quad & \frac{266}{448} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{(4+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{266}{4480} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{(4+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{266}{44800} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{(4+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{266}{448000} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{(4+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1440. \quad & \frac{266}{693} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{266}{6993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{266}{69993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+9993} \\
 & \frac{266}{699993} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{6+99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1431. \quad & \frac{266}{1672} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+72} \\
 & \frac{266}{16872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+872} \\
 & \frac{266}{168872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+8872} \\
 & \frac{266}{1688872} := \frac{2+6+6}{16+88872}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1436. \quad & \frac{266}{456} := \frac{2^6+6}{4 \times 5 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{266}{4560} := \frac{2^6+6}{4 \times 5 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{266}{45600} := \frac{2^6+6}{4 \times 5 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{266}{456000} := \frac{2^6+6}{4 \times 5 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1441. \quad & \frac{266}{735} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{266}{7350} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{266}{73500} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{266}{735000} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1432. \quad & \frac{266}{315} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{3 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{266}{3150} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{3 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{266}{31500} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{3 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{266}{315000} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{3 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1437. \quad & \frac{266}{462} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+62} \\
 & \frac{266}{4662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+662} \\
 & \frac{266}{46662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+6662} \\
 & \frac{266}{466662} := \frac{2+6 \times 6}{4+66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1442. \quad & \frac{267}{1335} := \frac{26+7}{1 \times 33 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{267}{13350} := \frac{26+7}{1 \times 33 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{267}{133500} := \frac{26+7}{1 \times 33 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{267}{1335000} := \frac{26+7}{1 \times 33 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1433. \quad & \frac{266}{399} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 6}{(3+9) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{266}{3990} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 6}{(3+9) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{266}{39900} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 6}{(3+9) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{266}{399000} := \frac{2 \times 6 \times 6}{(3+9) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1438. \quad & \frac{266}{627} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{266}{6327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{266}{63327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{266}{633327} := \frac{2+6+6}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1443. \quad & \frac{268}{1206} := \frac{2+6+8}{12 \times 06} \\
 & \frac{268}{12060} := \frac{2+6+8}{12 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{268}{120600} := \frac{2+6+8}{12 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{268}{1206000} := \frac{2+6+8}{12 \times 06000}
 \end{aligned}$$

1444.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{268}{1474} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{14+74} \\ \frac{268}{14874} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{14+874} \\ \frac{268}{148874} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{14+8874} \\ \frac{268}{1488874} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{14+88874} \end{aligned}$$

1445.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{268}{737} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{7+37} \\ \frac{268}{7437} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{7+437} \\ \frac{268}{74437} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{7+4437} \\ \frac{268}{744437} &:= \frac{2+6+8}{7+44437} \end{aligned}$$

1446.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{269}{1345} &:= \frac{26+9}{(1+34) \times 5} \\ \frac{269}{13450} &:= \frac{26+9}{(1+34) \times 50} \\ \frac{269}{134500} &:= \frac{26+9}{(1+34) \times 500} \\ \frac{269}{1345000} &:= \frac{26+9}{(1+34) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1447.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{271}{1084} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 4} \\ \frac{271}{10840} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 40} \\ \frac{271}{108400} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 400} \\ \frac{271}{1084000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1448.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{271}{1355} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 + 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 5} \\ \frac{271}{13550} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 + 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 50} \\ \frac{271}{135500} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 + 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 500} \\ \frac{271}{1355000} &:= \frac{2 \times 7 + 1}{1 \times 3 \times 5 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1449.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{271}{542} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 2} \\ \frac{271}{5420} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 20} \\ \frac{271}{54200} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 200} \\ \frac{271}{542000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(5+4) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1450.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{271}{813} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 3} \\ \frac{271}{8130} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 30} \\ \frac{271}{81300} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 300} \\ \frac{271}{813000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 1}{(8+1) \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

1451.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1088} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 8} \\ \frac{272}{10880} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 80} \\ \frac{272}{108800} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 800} \\ \frac{272}{1088000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 08 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1452.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1224} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 24} \\ \frac{272}{12240} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 240} \\ \frac{272}{122400} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 2400} \\ \frac{272}{1224000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 24000} \end{aligned}$$

1453.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1275} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5} \\ \frac{272}{12750} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50} \\ \frac{272}{127500} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 500} \\ \frac{272}{1275000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1454.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1280} &:= \frac{2+7^2}{(1+2) \times 80} \\ \frac{272}{12800} &:= \frac{2+7^2}{(1+2) \times 800} \\ \frac{272}{128000} &:= \frac{2+7^2}{(1+2) \times 8000} \\ \frac{272}{1280000} &:= \frac{2+7^2}{(1+2) \times 80000} \end{aligned}$$

1455.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1326} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 26} \\ \frac{272}{13260} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 260} \\ \frac{272}{132600} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 2600} \\ \frac{272}{1326000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 26000} \end{aligned}$$

1456.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1445} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5} \\ \frac{272}{14450} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 50} \\ \frac{272}{144500} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 500} \\ \frac{272}{1445000} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1457.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{272}{1683} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+83} \\ \frac{272}{16983} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+983} \\ \frac{272}{169983} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+9983} \\ \frac{272}{1699983} &:= \frac{2+7 \times 2}{16+99983} \end{aligned}$$

$$1458. \quad \frac{272}{306} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{3 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{272}{3060} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{3 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{272}{30600} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{3 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{272}{306000} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{3 \times 06000}$$

$$1463. \quad \frac{273}{1144} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{11 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{273}{11440} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{11 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{273}{114400} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{11 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{273}{1144000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$1468. \quad \frac{273}{1456} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{273}{14560} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{273}{145600} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{273}{1456000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}$$

$$1459. \quad \frac{272}{320} := \frac{2+7^2}{3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{272}{3200} := \frac{2+7^2}{3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{272}{32000} := \frac{2+7^2}{3 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{272}{320000} := \frac{2+7^2}{3 \times 20000}$$

$$1464. \quad \frac{273}{1248} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 24 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{273}{12480} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 24 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{273}{124800} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 24 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{273}{1248000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 24 \times 8000}$$

$$1469. \quad \frac{273}{416} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{273}{4160} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{273}{41600} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{273}{416000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{4 \times 16000}$$

$$1460. \quad \frac{272}{544} := \frac{2 \times (7+2)}{(5+4) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{272}{5440} := \frac{2 \times (7+2)}{(5+4) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{272}{54400} := \frac{2 \times (7+2)}{(5+4) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{272}{544000} := \frac{2 \times (7+2)}{(5+4) \times 4000}$$

$$1465. \quad \frac{273}{1274} := \frac{2+7+3}{1 \times 2 \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{273}{12740} := \frac{2+7+3}{1 \times 2 \times 7 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{273}{127400} := \frac{2+7+3}{1 \times 2 \times 7 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{273}{1274000} := \frac{2+7+3}{1 \times 2 \times 7 \times 4000}$$

$$1470. \quad \frac{273}{455} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(4+5) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{273}{4550} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(4+5) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{273}{45500} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(4+5) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{273}{455000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(4+5) \times 5000}$$

$$1461. \quad \frac{272}{816} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{272}{8160} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{272}{81600} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{272}{816000} := \frac{2+7 \times 2}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$1466. \quad \frac{273}{1352} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 52}$$

$$\frac{273}{13520} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 520}$$

$$\frac{273}{135200} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 5200}$$

$$\frac{273}{1352000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 52000}$$

$$1471. \quad \frac{273}{546} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(5+4) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{273}{5460} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(5+4) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{273}{54600} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(5+4) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{273}{546000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(5+4) \times 6000}$$

$$1462. \quad \frac{273}{1092} := \frac{2+7 \times 3}{1 \times 092}$$

$$\frac{273}{10920} := \frac{2+7 \times 3}{1 \times 0920}$$

$$\frac{273}{109200} := \frac{2+7 \times 3}{1 \times 09200}$$

$$\frac{273}{1092000} := \frac{2+7 \times 3}{1 \times 092000}$$

$$1467. \quad \frac{273}{1365} := \frac{(2+7)^3}{1 \times 3^6 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{273}{13650} := \frac{(2+7)^3}{1 \times 3^6 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{273}{136500} := \frac{(2+7)^3}{1 \times 3^6 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{273}{1365000} := \frac{(2+7)^3}{1 \times 3^6 \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1472. \quad & \frac{273}{637} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(6+3) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{273}{6370} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(6+3) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{273}{63700} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(6+3) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{273}{637000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(6+3) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1477. \quad & \frac{274}{548} := \frac{(2+7) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{274}{5480} := \frac{(2+7) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{274}{54800} := \frac{(2+7) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{274}{548000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1482. \quad & \frac{276}{1472} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{276}{14720} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{276}{147200} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{276}{1472000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1473. \quad & \frac{273}{728} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{7 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{273}{7280} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{7 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{273}{72800} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{7 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{273}{728000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 3}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1478. \quad & \frac{275}{1375} := \frac{2+7 \times 5}{1 \times 37 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{275}{13750} := \frac{2+7 \times 5}{1 \times 37 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{275}{137500} := \frac{2+7 \times 5}{1 \times 37 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{275}{1375000} := \frac{2+7 \times 5}{1 \times 37 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1483. \quad & \frac{276}{368} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{(3+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{276}{3680} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{(3+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{276}{36800} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{(3+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{276}{368000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{(3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1474. \quad & \frac{273}{819} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{273}{8190} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{273}{81900} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(8+1) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{273}{819000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{(8+1) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1479. \quad & \frac{275}{375} := \frac{2+75}{3 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{275}{3750} := \frac{2+75}{3 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{275}{37500} := \frac{2+75}{3 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{275}{375000} := \frac{2+75}{3 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1484. \quad & \frac{276}{575} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{5 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{276}{5750} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{5 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{276}{57500} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{5 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{276}{575000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 6}{5 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1475. \quad & \frac{273}{910} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{273}{9100} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{273}{91000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{9 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{273}{910000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 3}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1480. \quad & \frac{275}{660} := \frac{2 \times 75}{6 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{275}{6600} := \frac{2 \times 75}{6 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{275}{66000} := \frac{2 \times 75}{6 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{275}{660000} := \frac{2 \times 75}{6 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1485. \quad & \frac{276}{920} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{9 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{276}{9200} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{9 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{276}{92000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{9 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{276}{920000} := \frac{(2+7) \times 6}{9 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1476. \quad & \frac{274}{1370} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{274}{13700} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{274}{137000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{274}{1370000} := \frac{2 \times 7 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1481. \quad & \frac{276}{1104} := \frac{2 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 104} \\
 & \frac{276}{11040} := \frac{2 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 1040} \\
 & \frac{276}{110400} := \frac{2 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 10400} \\
 & \frac{276}{1104000} := \frac{2 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 104000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1486. \quad & \frac{277}{1385} := \frac{2+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 85} \\
 & \frac{277}{13850} := \frac{2+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 850} \\
 & \frac{277}{138500} := \frac{2+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 8500} \\
 & \frac{277}{1385000} := \frac{2+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 85000}
 \end{aligned}$$

1487.

$$\frac{277}{554} := \frac{(2^7)+7}{5 \times 54}$$

$$\frac{277}{5540} := \frac{(2^7)+7}{5 \times 540}$$

$$\frac{277}{55400} := \frac{(2^7)+7}{5 \times 5400}$$

$$\frac{277}{554000} := \frac{(2^7)+7}{5 \times 54000}$$

1491.

$$\frac{279}{1116} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1+11) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{279}{11160} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1+11) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{279}{111600} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1+11) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{279}{1116000} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1+11) \times 6000}$$

1496.

$$\frac{279}{434} := \frac{2+7+9}{(4+3) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{279}{4340} := \frac{2+7+9}{(4+3) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{279}{43400} := \frac{2+7+9}{(4+3) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{279}{434000} := \frac{2+7+9}{(4+3) \times 4000}$$

1488.

$$\frac{278}{1251} := \frac{2^7+8}{12 \times 51}$$

$$\frac{278}{12510} := \frac{2^7+8}{12 \times 510}$$

$$\frac{278}{125100} := \frac{2^7+8}{12 \times 5100}$$

$$\frac{278}{1251000} := \frac{2^7+8}{12 \times 51000}$$

1492.

$$\frac{279}{1240} := \frac{2+7+9}{1 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{279}{12400} := \frac{2+7+9}{1 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{279}{124000} := \frac{2+7+9}{1 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{279}{1240000} := \frac{2+7+9}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}$$

1497.

$$\frac{279}{682} := \frac{27+9}{6+82}$$

$$\frac{279}{6882} := \frac{27+9}{6+882}$$

$$\frac{279}{68882} := \frac{27+9}{6+8882}$$

$$\frac{279}{688882} := \frac{27+9}{6+88882}$$

1489.

$$\frac{278}{556} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(5+5) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{278}{5560} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(5+5) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{278}{55600} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(5+5) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{278}{556000} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(5+5) \times 6000}$$

1493.

$$\frac{279}{1395} := \frac{27+9}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{279}{13950} := \frac{27+9}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{279}{139500} := \frac{27+9}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{279}{1395000} := \frac{27+9}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}$$

1498.

$$\frac{279}{868} := \frac{2+7+9}{8+6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{279}{8680} := \frac{2+7+9}{(8+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{279}{86800} := \frac{2+7+9}{(8+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{279}{868000} := \frac{2+7+9}{(8+6) \times 8000}$$

1494.

$$\frac{279}{1488} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{279}{14880} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{279}{148800} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{279}{1488000} := \frac{2+7+9}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 8000}$$

1499.

$$\frac{279}{930} := \frac{2+79}{9 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{279}{9300} := \frac{2+79}{9 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{279}{93000} := \frac{2+79}{9 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{279}{930000} := \frac{2+79}{9 \times 30000}$$

1490.

$$\frac{278}{695} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(6+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{278}{6950} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(6+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{278}{69500} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(6+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{278}{695000} := \frac{2 \times (7+8)}{(6+9) \times 5000}$$

1495.

$$\frac{279}{341} := \frac{27+9}{3+41}$$

$$\frac{279}{3441} := \frac{27+9}{3+441}$$

$$\frac{279}{34441} := \frac{27+9}{3+4441}$$

$$\frac{279}{344441} := \frac{27+9}{3+44441}$$

1500.

$$\frac{280}{1155} := \frac{2 \times 8+0}{11+55}$$

$$\frac{280}{11655} := \frac{2 \times 8+0}{11+655}$$

$$\frac{280}{116655} := \frac{2 \times 8+0}{11+6655}$$

$$\frac{280}{1166655} := \frac{2 \times 8+0}{11+66655}$$

$$1501. \quad \frac{280}{1232} := \frac{2+8+0}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{280}{12432} := \frac{2+8+0}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{280}{124432} := \frac{2+8+0}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{280}{1244432} := \frac{2+8+0}{12+44432}$$

$$1506. \quad \frac{281}{562} := \frac{2+8+1}{(5+6) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{281}{5620} := \frac{2+8+1}{(5+6) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{281}{56200} := \frac{2+8+1}{(5+6) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{281}{562000} := \frac{2+8+1}{(5+6) \times 2000}$$

$$1511. \quad \frac{282}{1316} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{(13+1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{282}{13160} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{(13+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{282}{131600} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{(13+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{282}{1316000} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{(13+1) \times 6000}$$

$$1502. \quad \frac{280}{1848} := \frac{2+8+0}{18+48}$$

$$\frac{280}{18648} := \frac{2+8+0}{18+648}$$

$$\frac{280}{186648} := \frac{2+8+0}{18+6648}$$

$$\frac{280}{1866648} := \frac{2+8+0}{18+66648}$$

$$1507. \quad \frac{282}{1034} := \frac{2+8+2}{10+34}$$

$$\frac{282}{10434} := \frac{2+8+2}{10+434}$$

$$\frac{282}{104434} := \frac{2+8+2}{10+4434}$$

$$\frac{282}{1044434} := \frac{2+8+2}{10+44434}$$

$$1512. \quad \frac{282}{1551} := \frac{2+8+2}{15+51}$$

$$\frac{282}{15651} := \frac{2+8+2}{15+651}$$

$$\frac{282}{156651} := \frac{2+8+2}{15+6651}$$

$$\frac{282}{1566651} := \frac{2+8+2}{15+66651}$$

$$1503. \quad \frac{280}{308} := \frac{2+8+0}{3+08}$$

$$\frac{280}{3108} := \frac{2+8+0}{3+108}$$

$$\frac{280}{31108} := \frac{2+8+0}{3+1108}$$

$$\frac{280}{311108} := \frac{2+8+0}{3+11108}$$

$$1508. \quad \frac{282}{1128} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 128}$$

$$\frac{282}{11280} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 1280}$$

$$\frac{282}{112800} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 12800}$$

$$\frac{282}{1128000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 128000}$$

$$1513. \quad \frac{282}{423} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{4^2 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{282}{4230} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{4^2 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{282}{42300} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{4^2 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{282}{423000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 2}{4^2 \times 3000}$$

$$1504. \quad \frac{280}{616} := \frac{2+8+0}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{280}{6216} := \frac{2+8+0}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{280}{62216} := \frac{2+8+0}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{280}{622216} := \frac{2+8+0}{6+22216}$$

$$1509. \quad \frac{282}{1175} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{282}{11750} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{282}{117500} := \frac{2+8 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 7500}$$

$$1514. \quad \frac{282}{517} := \frac{2+8+2}{5+17}$$

$$\frac{282}{5217} := \frac{2+8+2}{5+217}$$

$$\frac{282}{52217} := \frac{2+8+2}{5+2217}$$

$$\frac{282}{522217} := \frac{2+8+2}{5+22217}$$

$$1505. \quad \frac{280}{924} := \frac{2+8+0}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{280}{9324} := \frac{2+8+0}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{280}{93324} := \frac{2+8+0}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{280}{933324} := \frac{2+8+0}{9+33324}$$

$$1510. \quad \frac{282}{1269} := \frac{2 \times 8^2}{1 \times 2^6 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{282}{12690} := \frac{2 \times 8^2}{1 \times 2^6 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{282}{126900} := \frac{2 \times 8^2}{1 \times 2^6 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{282}{1269000} := \frac{2 \times 8^2}{1 \times 2^6 \times 9000}$$

$$1515. \quad \frac{284}{1420} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + 4}{(1+4) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{284}{14200} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + 4}{(1+4) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{284}{142000} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + 4}{(1+4) \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{284}{1420000} := \frac{(2 \times 8) + 4}{(1+4) \times 20000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1516. \quad & \frac{284}{1491} := \frac{2 \times (8+4)}{14 \times 9 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{284}{14910} := \frac{2 \times (8+4)}{14 \times 9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{284}{149100} := \frac{2 \times (8+4)}{14 \times 9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{284}{1491000} := \frac{2 \times (8+4)}{14 \times 9 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1521. \quad & \frac{285}{1026} := \frac{2 \times 85}{102 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{285}{10260} := \frac{2 \times 85}{102 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{285}{102600} := \frac{2 \times 85}{102 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{285}{1026000} := \frac{2 \times 85}{102 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1526. \quad & \frac{285}{1463} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{285}{14763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{285}{147763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{285}{1477763} := \frac{2+8+5}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1517. \quad & \frac{284}{1562} := \frac{2+8+4}{15+62} \\
 & \frac{284}{15762} := \frac{2+8+4}{15+762} \\
 & \frac{284}{157762} := \frac{2+8+4}{15+7762} \\
 & \frac{284}{1577762} := \frac{2+8+4}{15+77762}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1522. \quad & \frac{285}{1045} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{285}{10545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{285}{105545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{285}{1055545} := \frac{2+8+5}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1527. \quad & \frac{285}{418} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+18} \\
 & \frac{285}{4218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+218} \\
 & \frac{285}{42218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+2218} \\
 & \frac{285}{422218} := \frac{2+8+5}{4+22218}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1518. \quad & \frac{284}{355} := \frac{28+4}{(3+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{284}{3550} := \frac{28+4}{(3+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{284}{35500} := \frac{28+4}{(3+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{284}{355000} := \frac{28+4}{(3+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1523. \quad & \frac{285}{1197} := \frac{2+8+5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{285}{11970} := \frac{2+8+5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{285}{119700} := \frac{2+8+5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{285}{1197000} := \frac{2+8+5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1528. \quad & \frac{285}{456} := \frac{28 \times 5}{4 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{285}{4560} := \frac{28 \times 5}{4 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{285}{45600} := \frac{28 \times 5}{4 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{285}{456000} := \frac{28 \times 5}{4 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1519. \quad & \frac{284}{426} := \frac{2 \times 84}{42 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{284}{4260} := \frac{2 \times 84}{42 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{284}{42600} := \frac{2 \times 84}{42 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{284}{426000} := \frac{2 \times 84}{42 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1524. \quad & \frac{285}{1254} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+54} \\
 & \frac{285}{12654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+654} \\
 & \frac{285}{126654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+6654} \\
 & \frac{285}{1266654} := \frac{2+8+5}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1529. \quad & \frac{285}{475} := \frac{28+5}{(4+7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{285}{4750} := \frac{28+5}{(4+7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{285}{47500} := \frac{28+5}{(4+7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{285}{475000} := \frac{28+5}{(4+7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1520. \quad & \frac{284}{781} := \frac{28+4}{7+81} \\
 & \frac{284}{7881} := \frac{28+4}{7+881} \\
 & \frac{284}{78881} := \frac{28+4}{7+8881} \\
 & \frac{284}{788881} := \frac{28+4}{7+88881}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1525. \quad & \frac{285}{1425} := \frac{2+8 \times 5}{1 \times 42 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{285}{14250} := \frac{2+8 \times 5}{1 \times 42 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{285}{142500} := \frac{2+8 \times 5}{1 \times 42 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{285}{1425000} := \frac{2+8 \times 5}{1 \times 42 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1530. \quad & \frac{285}{627} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{285}{6327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{285}{63327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{285}{633327} := \frac{2+8+5}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1531. \quad \frac{285}{684} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{285}{6840} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{285}{68400} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{285}{684000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 5}{6 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$1536. \quad \frac{286}{1443} := \frac{2+86}{1+443}$$

$$\frac{286}{14443} := \frac{2+86}{1+4443}$$

$$\frac{286}{144443} := \frac{2+86}{1+44443}$$

$$1541. \quad \frac{286}{624} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{6 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{286}{6240} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{6 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{286}{62400} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{6 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{286}{624000} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{6 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$1532. \quad \frac{285}{836} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+36}$$

$$\frac{285}{8436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+436}$$

$$\frac{285}{84436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+4436}$$

$$\frac{285}{844436} := \frac{2+8+5}{8+44436}$$

$$1537. \quad \frac{286}{1573} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+73}$$

$$\frac{286}{15873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+873}$$

$$\frac{286}{158873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+8873}$$

$$\frac{286}{1588873} := \frac{2+8+6}{15+88873}$$

$$1542. \quad \frac{286}{715} := \frac{2+8+6}{(7+1) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{286}{7150} := \frac{2+8+6}{(7+1) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{286}{71500} := \frac{2+8+6}{(7+1) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{286}{715000} := \frac{2+8+6}{(7+1) \times 5000}$$

$$1533. \quad \frac{286}{1144} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(1+1) \times 44}$$

$$\frac{286}{11440} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(1+1) \times 440}$$

$$\frac{286}{114400} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(1+1) \times 4400}$$

$$\frac{286}{1144000} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(1+1) \times 44000}$$

$$1538. \quad \frac{286}{325} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{286}{3250} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(3+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{286}{32500} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(3+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{286}{325000} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{(3+2) \times 5000}$$

$$1543. \quad \frac{286}{832} := \frac{2+86}{8 \times 32}$$

$$\frac{286}{8320} := \frac{2+86}{8 \times 320}$$

$$\frac{286}{83200} := \frac{2+86}{8 \times 3200}$$

$$\frac{286}{832000} := \frac{2+86}{8 \times 32000}$$

$$1534. \quad \frac{286}{1248} := \frac{2+86}{12 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{286}{12480} := \frac{2+86}{12 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{286}{124800} := \frac{2+86}{12 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{286}{1248000} := \frac{2+86}{12 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$1539. \quad \frac{286}{429} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 6}{4^2 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{286}{4290} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 6}{4^2 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{286}{42900} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 6}{4^2 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{286}{429000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 6}{4^2 \times 9000}$$

$$1544. \quad \frac{286}{858} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8+58}$$

$$\frac{286}{8658} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8+658}$$

$$\frac{286}{86658} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{8+6658}$$

$$1535. \quad \frac{286}{1287} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12+87}$$

$$\frac{286}{12987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12+987}$$

$$\frac{286}{129987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12+9987}$$

$$\frac{286}{1299987} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{12+99987}$$

$$1540. \quad \frac{286}{429} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4+29}$$

$$\frac{286}{4329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4+329}$$

$$\frac{286}{43329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4+3329}$$

$$\frac{286}{433329} := \frac{2 \times 8 + 6}{4+33329}$$

$$1545. \quad \frac{287}{1025} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{10 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{287}{10250} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{10 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{287}{102500} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{10 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{287}{1025000} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{10 \times 25000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1546. \quad & \frac{287}{1148} := \frac{2 \times (8+7)}{(1+14) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{287}{11480} := \frac{2 \times (8+7)}{(1+14) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{287}{114800} := \frac{2 \times (8+7)}{(1+14) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{287}{1148000} := \frac{2 \times (8+7)}{(1+14) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1551. \quad & \frac{288}{1125} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{288}{11250} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{288}{112500} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{288}{1125000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1556. \quad & \frac{288}{1368} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{288}{13680} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{288}{136800} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{288}{1368000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1547. \quad & \frac{287}{1435} := \frac{28+7}{(1+4) \times 35} \\
 & \frac{287}{14350} := \frac{28+7}{(1+4) \times 350} \\
 & \frac{287}{143500} := \frac{28+7}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{287}{1435000} := \frac{28+7}{(1+4) \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1552. \quad & \frac{288}{1197} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{288}{11970} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{288}{119700} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{288}{1197000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1557. \quad & \frac{288}{1440} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{288}{14400} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{288}{144000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{288}{1440000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1548. \quad & \frac{287}{451} := \frac{28+7}{4+51} \\
 & \frac{287}{4551} := \frac{28+7}{4+551} \\
 & \frac{287}{45551} := \frac{28+7}{4+5551} \\
 & \frac{287}{455551} := \frac{28+7}{4+55551}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1553. \quad & \frac{288}{1280} := \frac{28+8}{1 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{288}{12800} := \frac{28+8}{1 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{288}{128000} := \frac{28+8}{1 \times 2 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{288}{1280000} := \frac{28+8}{1 \times 2 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1558. \quad & \frac{288}{1485} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{288}{14850} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{288}{148500} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{288}{1485000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1549. \quad & \frac{287}{574} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{5 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{287}{5740} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{5 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{287}{57400} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{5 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{287}{574000} := \frac{(2+8) \times 7}{5 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1554. \quad & \frac{288}{1296} := \frac{28+8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{288}{12960} := \frac{28+8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{288}{129600} := \frac{28+8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{288}{1296000} := \frac{28+8}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1559. \quad & \frac{288}{324} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{3^2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{288}{3240} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{3^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{288}{32400} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{3^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{288}{324000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{3^2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1550. \quad & \frac{288}{1056} := \frac{2+8+8}{10+56} \\
 & \frac{288}{10656} := \frac{2+8+8}{10+656} \\
 & \frac{288}{106656} := \frac{2+8+8}{10+6656} \\
 & \frac{288}{1066656} := \frac{2+8+8}{10+66656}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1555. \quad & \frac{288}{1350} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{288}{13500} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{288}{135000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{288}{1350000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1560. \quad & \frac{288}{378} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{288}{3780} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{288}{37800} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{288}{378000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{3 \times 7 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1561. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{450} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{4 \times 50} \\ \frac{288}{4500} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{4 \times 500} \\ \frac{288}{45000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{4 \times 5000} \\ \frac{288}{450000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{4 \times 50000} \end{array}$$

$$1566. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{729} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{72+9} \\ \frac{288}{7290} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(7+2) \times 90} \\ \frac{288}{72900} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(7+2) \times 900} \\ \frac{288}{729000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(7+2) \times 9000} \end{array}$$

$$1571. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{561} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+61} \\ \frac{289}{5661} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+661} \\ \frac{289}{56661} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+6661} \\ \frac{289}{566661} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{5+66661} \end{array}$$

$$1562. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{528} := \frac{2+8+8}{5+28} \\ \frac{288}{5328} := \frac{2+8+8}{5+328} \\ \frac{288}{53328} := \frac{2+8+8}{5+3328} \\ \frac{288}{533328} := \frac{2+8+8}{5+33328} \end{array}$$

$$1567. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{756} := \frac{(2+8) \times 8}{7 \times 5 \times 6} \\ \frac{288}{7560} := \frac{(2+8) \times 8}{7 \times 5 \times 60} \\ \frac{288}{75600} := \frac{(2+8) \times 8}{7 \times 5 \times 600} \\ \frac{288}{756000} := \frac{(2+8) \times 8}{7 \times 5 \times 6000} \end{array}$$

$$1572. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{595} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(5+9) \times 5} \\ \frac{289}{5950} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(5+9) \times 50} \\ \frac{289}{59500} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(5+9) \times 500} \\ \frac{289}{595000} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(5+9) \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$1563. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{576} := \frac{28+8}{(5+7) \times 6} \\ \frac{288}{5760} := \frac{28+8}{(5+7) \times 60} \\ \frac{288}{57600} := \frac{28+8}{(5+7) \times 600} \\ \frac{288}{576000} := \frac{28+8}{(5+7) \times 6000} \end{array}$$

$$1568. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{1275} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\ \frac{289}{12750} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\ \frac{289}{127500} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\ \frac{289}{1275000} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{1 \times 2 \times 75000} \end{array}$$

$$1573. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{612} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{6 \times 12} \\ \frac{289}{6120} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{6 \times 120} \\ \frac{289}{61200} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{6 \times 1200} \\ \frac{289}{612000} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{6 \times 12000} \end{array}$$

$$1564. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{585} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(5+8) \times 5} \\ \frac{288}{5850} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(5+8) \times 50} \\ \frac{288}{58500} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(5+8) \times 500} \\ \frac{288}{585000} := \frac{2 \times (8+8)}{(5+8) \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$1569. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{1326} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\ \frac{289}{13260} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \frac{289}{132600} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\ \frac{289}{1326000} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{13 \times 2 \times 6000} \end{array}$$

$$1574. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{748} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(7+4) \times 8} \\ \frac{289}{7480} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(7+4) \times 80} \\ \frac{289}{74800} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(7+4) \times 800} \\ \frac{289}{748000} := \frac{2 \times (8+9)}{(7+4) \times 8000} \end{array}$$

$$1565. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{288}{648} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{6 \times 48} \\ \frac{288}{6480} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{6 \times 480} \\ \frac{288}{64800} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{6 \times 4800} \\ \frac{288}{648000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 8}{6 \times 48000} \end{array}$$

$$1570. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{289}{1445} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9}{144 \times 5} \\ \frac{289}{14450} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9}{144 \times 50} \\ \frac{289}{144500} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9}{144 \times 500} \\ \frac{289}{1445000} := \frac{2 \times 8 \times 9}{144 \times 5000} \end{array}$$

$$1575. \quad \begin{array}{l} \frac{291}{1164} := \frac{2+9+1}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 4} \\ \frac{291}{11640} := \frac{2+9+1}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 40} \\ \frac{291}{116400} := \frac{2+9+1}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 400} \\ \frac{291}{1164000} := \frac{2+9+1}{(1+1) \times 6 \times 4000} \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1576. \quad & \frac{291}{1455} := \frac{2+9 \times 1}{1^4 \times 55} \\
 & \frac{291}{14550} := \frac{2+9 \times 1}{1^4 \times 550} \\
 & \frac{291}{145500} := \frac{2+9 \times 1}{1^4 \times 5500} \\
 & \frac{291}{1455000} := \frac{2+9 \times 1}{1^4 \times 55000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1581. \quad & \frac{294}{1225} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4}{12 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{294}{12250} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4}{12 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{294}{122500} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4}{12 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{294}{1225000} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 4}{12 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1586. \quad & \frac{297}{1350} := \frac{(2+9) \times 7}{1 \times 350} \\
 & \frac{297}{13500} := \frac{(2+9) \times 7}{1 \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{297}{135000} := \frac{(2+9) \times 7}{1 \times 35000} \\
 & \frac{297}{1350000} := \frac{(2+9) \times 7}{1 \times 350000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1577. \quad & \frac{292}{365} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{292}{3650} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{292}{36500} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{292}{365000} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(3+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1582. \quad & \frac{294}{1323} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 4}{(1+32) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{294}{13230} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 4}{(1+32) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{294}{132300} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 4}{(1+32) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{294}{1323000} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 4}{(1+32) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1587. \quad & \frac{297}{1485} := \frac{2 \times (9+7)}{1 \times 4 \times 8 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{297}{14850} := \frac{2 \times (9+7)}{1 \times 4 \times 8 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{297}{148500} := \frac{2 \times (9+7)}{1 \times 4 \times 8 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{297}{1485000} := \frac{2 \times (9+7)}{1 \times 4 \times 8 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1578. \quad & \frac{292}{949} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(9+4) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{292}{9490} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(9+4) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{292}{94900} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(9+4) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{292}{949000} := \frac{2 \times 9 \times 2}{(9+4) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1583. \quad & \frac{295}{1475} := \frac{2+9 \times 5}{1 \times 47 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{295}{14750} := \frac{2+9 \times 5}{1 \times 47 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{295}{147500} := \frac{2+9 \times 5}{1 \times 47 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{295}{1475000} := \frac{2+9 \times 5}{1 \times 47 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1588. \quad & \frac{297}{735} := \frac{2+97}{7 \times 35} \\
 & \frac{297}{7350} := \frac{2+97}{7 \times 350} \\
 & \frac{297}{73500} := \frac{2+97}{7 \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{297}{735000} := \frac{2+97}{7 \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1579. \quad & \frac{293}{1465} := \frac{2 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{293}{14650} := \frac{2 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{293}{146500} := \frac{2 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{293}{1465000} := \frac{2 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1584. \quad & \frac{297}{1188} := \frac{29+7}{1 \times 18 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{297}{11880} := \frac{29+7}{1 \times 18 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{297}{118800} := \frac{29+7}{1 \times 18 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{297}{1188000} := \frac{29+7}{1 \times 18 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1589. \quad & \frac{297}{825} := \frac{2+9+7}{(8+2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{297}{8250} := \frac{2+9+7}{(8+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{297}{82500} := \frac{2+9+7}{(8+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{297}{825000} := \frac{2+9+7}{(8+2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1580. \quad & \frac{294}{1176} := \frac{2+9 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 76} \\
 & \frac{294}{11760} := \frac{2+9 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 760} \\
 & \frac{294}{117600} := \frac{2+9 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 7600} \\
 & \frac{294}{1176000} := \frac{2+9 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 76000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1585. \quad & \frac{297}{1320} := \frac{2+9+7}{(1+3) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{297}{13200} := \frac{2+9+7}{(1+3) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{297}{132000} := \frac{2+9+7}{(1+3) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{297}{1320000} := \frac{2+9+7}{(1+3) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1590. \quad & \frac{299}{1196} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 9}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{299}{11960} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 9}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{299}{119600} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 9}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{299}{1196000} := \frac{2 \times 9 + 9}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1591. \quad \frac{301}{1204} := \frac{3^{01}}{(1+2+0) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{301}{12040} := \frac{3^{01}}{(1+2+0) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{301}{120400} := \frac{3^{01}}{(1+2+0) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{301}{1204000} := \frac{3^{01}}{(1+2+0) \times 4000}$$

$$1595. \quad \frac{302}{4530} := \frac{3^{02}}{45 \times 3 + 0}$$

$$\frac{302}{45300} := \frac{3^{02}}{45 \times 30 + 0}$$

$$\frac{302}{453000} := \frac{3^{02}}{45 \times 300 + 0}$$

$$\frac{302}{4530000} := \frac{3^{02}}{45 \times 3000 + 0}$$

$$1600. \quad \frac{303}{1313} := \frac{3 \times 03}{1 \times 3 \times 13}$$

$$\frac{303}{13130} := \frac{3 \times 03}{1 \times 3 \times 130}$$

$$\frac{303}{131300} := \frac{3 \times 03}{1 \times 3 \times 1300}$$

$$\frac{303}{1313000} := \frac{3 \times 03}{1 \times 3 \times 13000}$$

$$1592. \quad \frac{302}{10570} := \frac{3+0 \times 2}{(10+5) \times 7 + 0}$$

$$\frac{302}{105700} := \frac{3+0 \times 2}{(10+5) \times 70 + 0}$$

$$\frac{302}{1057000} := \frac{3+0 \times 2}{(10+5) \times 700 + 0}$$

$$1596. \quad \frac{303}{1010} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1 \times 010}$$

$$\frac{303}{10100} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1 \times 0100}$$

$$\frac{303}{101000} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1 \times 01000}$$

$$1601. \quad \frac{303}{1414} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1^4 \times 14}$$

$$\frac{303}{14140} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1^4 \times 140}$$

$$\frac{303}{141400} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1^4 \times 1400}$$

$$\frac{303}{1414000} := \frac{3+0 \times 3}{1^4 \times 14000}$$

$$1593. \quad \frac{302}{1208} := \frac{3 \times 02}{(1+2+0) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{302}{12080} := \frac{3 \times 02}{(1+2+0) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{302}{120800} := \frac{3 \times 02}{(1+2+0) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{302}{1208000} := \frac{3 \times 02}{(1+2+0) \times 8000}$$

$$1597. \quad \frac{303}{1111} := \frac{30+3}{11 \times 11}$$

$$\frac{303}{11110} := \frac{30+3}{11 \times 110}$$

$$\frac{303}{111100} := \frac{30+3}{11 \times 1100}$$

$$1602. \quad \frac{303}{909} := \frac{3^{03}}{9 \times 09}$$

$$\frac{303}{9090} := \frac{3^{03}}{9 \times 090}$$

$$\frac{303}{90900} := \frac{3^{03}}{9 \times 0900}$$

$$\frac{303}{909000} := \frac{3^{03}}{9 \times 09000}$$

$$1594. \quad \frac{302}{1359} := \frac{30+2}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{302}{13590} := \frac{30+2}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{302}{135900} := \frac{30+2}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{302}{1359000} := \frac{30+2}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9000}$$

$$1598. \quad \frac{303}{1111} := \frac{3+03}{11+11}$$

$$\frac{303}{11211} := \frac{3+03}{11+211}$$

$$\frac{303}{112211} := \frac{3+03}{11+2211}$$

$$1603. \quad \frac{304}{1216} := \frac{3+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{304}{12160} := \frac{3+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{304}{121600} := \frac{3+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{304}{1216000} := \frac{3+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$1599. \quad \frac{303}{1212} := \frac{3+03}{1 \times 2 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{303}{12120} := \frac{3+03}{1 \times 2 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{303}{121200} := \frac{3+03}{1 \times 2 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{303}{1212000} := \frac{3+03}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}$$

$$1604. \quad \frac{305}{1220} := \frac{3 \times 05}{(1+2) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{305}{12200} := \frac{3 \times 05}{(1+2) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{305}{122000} := \frac{3 \times 05}{(1+2) \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{305}{1220000} := \frac{3 \times 05}{(1+2) \times 20000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1605. \quad & \frac{305}{610} := \frac{3+0 \times 5}{6 \times 1+0} \\
 & \frac{305}{6100} := \frac{3+0 \times 5}{6 \times 10+0} \\
 & \frac{305}{61000} := \frac{3+0 \times 5}{6 \times 100+0} \\
 & \frac{305}{610000} := \frac{3+0 \times 5}{6 \times 1000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1610. \quad & \frac{306}{1224} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+2) \times 24} \\
 & \frac{306}{12240} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+2) \times 240} \\
 & \frac{306}{122400} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+2) \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{306}{1224000} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+2) \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1615. \quad & \frac{306}{1683} := \frac{3 \times 06}{16+83} \\
 & \frac{306}{16983} := \frac{3 \times 06}{16+983} \\
 & \frac{306}{169983} := \frac{3 \times 06}{16+9983}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1606. \quad & \frac{305}{671} := \frac{30+5}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{305}{6771} := \frac{30+5}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{305}{67771} := \frac{30+5}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{305}{677771} := \frac{30+5}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1611. \quad & \frac{306}{1275} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{306}{12750} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{306}{127500} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{306}{1275000} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1616. \quad & \frac{306}{1734} := \frac{30+6}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{306}{17340} := \frac{30+6}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{306}{173400} := \frac{30+6}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{306}{1734000} := \frac{30+6}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1607. \quad & \frac{305}{915} := \frac{3 \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{305}{9150} := \frac{3 \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{305}{91500} := \frac{3 \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{305}{915000} := \frac{3 \times 05}{9 \times 1 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1612. \quad & \frac{306}{1292} := \frac{3+06}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{306}{12920} := \frac{3+06}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{306}{129200} := \frac{3+06}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{306}{1292000} := \frac{3+06}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1617. \quad & \frac{306}{17374} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{306}{173740} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{306}{1737400} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{306}{17374000} := \frac{30+6}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1608. \quad & \frac{306}{1088} := \frac{30 \times 6}{10 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{306}{10880} := \frac{30 \times 6}{10 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{306}{108800} := \frac{30 \times 6}{10 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{306}{1088000} := \frac{30 \times 6}{10 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1613. \quad & \frac{306}{1326} := \frac{30+6}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{306}{13260} := \frac{30+6}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{306}{132600} := \frac{30+6}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{306}{1326000} := \frac{30+6}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1618. \quad & \frac{306}{3570} := \frac{3+06}{3 \times 5 \times 7+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{35700} := \frac{3+06}{3 \times 5 \times 70+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{357000} := \frac{3+06}{3 \times 5 \times 700+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{3570000} := \frac{3+06}{3 \times 5 \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1609. \quad & \frac{306}{1122} := \frac{3+06}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{306}{11322} := \frac{3+06}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{306}{113322} := \frac{3+06}{11+3322} \\
 & \frac{306}{1133322} := \frac{3+06}{11+33322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1614. \quad & \frac{306}{1445} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{306}{14450} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{306}{144500} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{306}{1445000} := \frac{3 \times 06}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1619. \quad & \frac{306}{5100} := \frac{3+0 \times 6}{5 \times 10+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{51000} := \frac{3+0 \times 6}{5 \times 100+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{510000} := \frac{3+0 \times 6}{5 \times 1000+0} \\
 & \frac{306}{5100000} := \frac{3+0 \times 6}{5 \times 10000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

1620.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{561} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+61} \\ \frac{306}{5661} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+661} \\ \frac{306}{56661} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+6661} \\ \frac{306}{566661} &:= \frac{30+6}{5+66661} \end{aligned}$$

1625.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{307}{1228} &:= \frac{3 \times 07}{(1+2) \times 28} \\ \frac{307}{12280} &:= \frac{3 \times 07}{(1+2) \times 280} \\ \frac{307}{122800} &:= \frac{3 \times 07}{(1+2) \times 2800} \\ \frac{307}{1228000} &:= \frac{3 \times 07}{(1+2) \times 28000} \end{aligned}$$

1630.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1344} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\ \frac{308}{13440} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\ \frac{308}{134400} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\ \frac{308}{1344000} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1621.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{595} &:= \frac{30+6}{(5+9) \times 5} \\ \frac{306}{5950} &:= \frac{30+6}{(5+9) \times 50} \\ \frac{306}{59500} &:= \frac{30+6}{(5+9) \times 500} \\ \frac{306}{595000} &:= \frac{30+6}{(5+9) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1626.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1120} &:= \frac{3+08}{(1+1) \times 20} \\ \frac{308}{11200} &:= \frac{3+08}{(1+1) \times 200} \\ \frac{308}{112000} &:= \frac{3+08}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\ \frac{308}{1120000} &:= \frac{3+08}{(1+1) \times 20000} \end{aligned}$$

1631.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{616} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+16} \\ \frac{308}{6216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+216} \\ \frac{308}{62216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+2216} \\ \frac{308}{622216} &:= \frac{3+08}{6+22216} \end{aligned}$$

1622.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{612} &:= \frac{30+6}{6 \times 12} \\ \frac{306}{6120} &:= \frac{30+6}{6 \times 120} \\ \frac{306}{61200} &:= \frac{30+6}{6 \times 1200} \\ \frac{306}{612000} &:= \frac{30+6}{6 \times 12000} \end{aligned}$$

1627.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1176} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\ \frac{308}{11760} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\ \frac{308}{117600} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\ \frac{308}{1176000} &:= \frac{3+08}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1632.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{924} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{9 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \frac{308}{9240} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{9 \times 2 \times 40} \\ \frac{308}{92400} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{9 \times 2 \times 400} \\ \frac{308}{924000} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{9 \times 2 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1623.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{748} &:= \frac{30+6}{(7+4) \times 8} \\ \frac{306}{7480} &:= \frac{30+6}{(7+4) \times 80} \\ \frac{306}{74800} &:= \frac{30+6}{(7+4) \times 800} \\ \frac{306}{748000} &:= \frac{30+6}{(7+4) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1628.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1232} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{(1+2) \times 32} \\ \frac{308}{12320} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{(1+2) \times 320} \\ \frac{308}{123200} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{(1+2) \times 3200} \\ \frac{308}{1232000} &:= \frac{3 \times 08}{(1+2) \times 32000} \end{aligned}$$

1633.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{309}{1133} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{11 \times 3 \times 3} \\ \frac{309}{11330} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{11 \times 3 \times 30} \\ \frac{309}{113300} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{11 \times 3 \times 300} \\ \frac{309}{1133000} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{11 \times 3 \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

1624.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{306}{952} &:= \frac{3+06}{(9+5) \times 2} \\ \frac{306}{9520} &:= \frac{3+06}{(9+5) \times 20} \\ \frac{306}{95200} &:= \frac{3+06}{(9+5) \times 200} \\ \frac{306}{952000} &:= \frac{3+06}{(9+5) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1629.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{308}{1232} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+32} \\ \frac{308}{12432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+432} \\ \frac{308}{124432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+4432} \\ \frac{308}{1244432} &:= \frac{3+08}{12+44432} \end{aligned}$$

1634.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{309}{1133} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+33} \\ \frac{309}{11433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+433} \\ \frac{309}{114433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+4433} \\ \frac{309}{1144433} &:= \frac{3+09}{11+44433} \end{aligned}$$

1635.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{309}{1236} &:= \frac{3+09}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6} \\ \frac{309}{12360} &:= \frac{3+09}{1 \times 2^3 \times 60} \\ \frac{309}{123600} &:= \frac{3+09}{1 \times 2^3 \times 600} \\ \frac{309}{1236000} &:= \frac{3+09}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1640.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1248} &:= \frac{31 \times 2}{1 \times 248} \\ \frac{312}{12480} &:= \frac{31 \times 2}{1 \times 2480} \\ \frac{312}{124800} &:= \frac{31 \times 2}{1 \times 24800} \end{aligned}$$

1645.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{520} &:= \frac{3+1+2}{5 \times 2+0} \\ \frac{312}{5200} &:= \frac{3+1+2}{5 \times 20+0} \\ \frac{312}{52000} &:= \frac{3+1+2}{5 \times 200+0} \\ \frac{312}{520000} &:= \frac{3+1+2}{5 \times 2000+0} \end{aligned}$$

1636.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{309}{1339} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{1 \times 3 \times 39} \\ \frac{309}{13390} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{1 \times 3 \times 390} \\ \frac{309}{133900} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{1 \times 3 \times 3900} \\ \frac{309}{1339000} &:= \frac{3 \times 09}{1 \times 3 \times 39000} \end{aligned}$$

1641.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1352} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{1 \times 3 \times 52} \\ \frac{312}{13520} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{1 \times 3 \times 520} \\ \frac{312}{135200} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{1 \times 3 \times 5200} \end{aligned}$$

1646.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{624} &:= \frac{(3+1)^2}{(6+2) \times 4} \\ \frac{312}{6240} &:= \frac{(3+1)^2}{(6+2) \times 40} \\ \frac{312}{62400} &:= \frac{(3+1)^2}{(6+2) \times 400} \end{aligned}$$

1637.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{310}{1705} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+05} \\ \frac{310}{17205} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+205} \\ \frac{310}{172205} &:= \frac{3+1+0}{17+2205} \end{aligned}$$

1642.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1365} &:= \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(1^3+6) \times 5} \\ \frac{312}{13650} &:= \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(1^3+6) \times 50} \\ \frac{312}{136500} &:= \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(1^3+6) \times 500} \\ \frac{312}{1365000} &:= \frac{(3+1) \times 2}{(1^3+6) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1647.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{676} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{(6+7) \times 6} \\ \frac{312}{6760} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{(6+7) \times 60} \\ \frac{312}{67600} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{(6+7) \times 600} \\ \frac{312}{676000} &:= \frac{3 \times 12}{(6+7) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1638.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{311}{1244} &:= \frac{3 \times 11}{(1+2) \times 44} \\ \frac{311}{12440} &:= \frac{3 \times 11}{(1+2) \times 440} \\ \frac{311}{124400} &:= \frac{3 \times 11}{(1+2) \times 4400} \\ \frac{311}{1244000} &:= \frac{3 \times 11}{(1+2) \times 44000} \end{aligned}$$

1643.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1456} &:= \frac{3^{1+2}}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 6} \\ \frac{312}{14560} &:= \frac{3^{1+2}}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 60} \\ \frac{312}{145600} &:= \frac{3^{1+2}}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 600} \\ \frac{312}{1456000} &:= \frac{3^{1+2}}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1639.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1144} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+44} \\ \frac{312}{11544} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+544} \\ \frac{312}{115544} &:= \frac{3+12}{11+5544} \end{aligned}$$

1644.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{312}{1872} &:= \frac{3+1 \times 2}{(1 \times 8+7) \times 2} \\ \frac{312}{18720} &:= \frac{3+1 \times 2}{(1 \times 8+7) \times 20} \\ \frac{312}{187200} &:= \frac{3+1 \times 2}{(1 \times 8+7) \times 200} \\ \frac{312}{1872000} &:= \frac{3+1 \times 2}{(1 \times 8+7) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1648.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{313}{1252} &:= \frac{3+13}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2} \\ \frac{313}{12520} &:= \frac{3+13}{1 \times 2^5 \times 20} \\ \frac{313}{125200} &:= \frac{3+13}{1 \times 2^5 \times 200} \\ \frac{313}{1252000} &:= \frac{3+13}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1649.

$$\frac{313}{939} := \frac{3^{1+3}}{9 \times 3 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{313}{9390} := \frac{3^{1+3}}{9 \times 3 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{313}{93900} := \frac{3^{1+3}}{9 \times 3 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{313}{939000} := \frac{3^{1+3}}{9 \times 3 \times 9000}$$

1653.

$$\frac{315}{1050} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{315}{10500} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{315}{105000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 05000}$$

1658.

$$\frac{315}{1344} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{315}{13440} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{315}{134400} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{315}{1344000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

1650.

$$\frac{314}{1413} := \frac{3+1^4}{(1+4+1) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{314}{14130} := \frac{3+1^4}{(1+4+1) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{314}{141300} := \frac{3+1^4}{(1+4+1) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{314}{1413000} := \frac{3+1^4}{(1+4+1) \times 3000}$$

1654.

$$\frac{315}{1155} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 55}$$

$$\frac{315}{11550} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 550}$$

$$\frac{315}{115500} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}$$

1659.

$$\frac{315}{1365} := \frac{3 \times 15}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{315}{13650} := \frac{3 \times 15}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{315}{136500} := \frac{3 \times 15}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

1651.

$$\frac{314}{1727} := \frac{3+1+4}{17+27}$$

$$\frac{314}{17427} := \frac{3+1+4}{17+427}$$

$$\frac{314}{174427} := \frac{3+1+4}{17+4427}$$

$$\frac{314}{1744427} := \frac{3+1+4}{17+44427}$$

1655.

$$\frac{315}{1225} := \frac{3+15}{(12+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{315}{12250} := \frac{3+15}{(12+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{315}{122500} := \frac{3+15}{(12+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{315}{1225000} := \frac{3+15}{(12+2) \times 5000}$$

1660.

$$\frac{315}{1386} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{315}{13860} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{315}{138600} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{315}{1386000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

1652.

$$\frac{314}{7850} := \frac{3^{14}}{(7+8) \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{314}{78500} := \frac{3^{14}}{(7+8) \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{314}{785000} := \frac{3^{14}}{(7+8) \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{314}{7850000} := \frac{3^{14}}{(7+8) \times 5000 + 0}$$

1656.

$$\frac{315}{1260} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{315}{12600} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{315}{126000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^2 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{315}{1260000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^2 \times 60000}$$

1661.

$$\frac{315}{1400} := \frac{3+1+5}{1 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{14000} := \frac{3+1+5}{1 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{140000} := \frac{3+1+5}{1 \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{1400000} := \frac{3+1+5}{1 \times 40000 + 0}$$

1657.

$$\frac{315}{1302} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+30) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{315}{13020} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+30) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{315}{130200} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+30) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{315}{1302000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+30) \times 2000}$$

1662.

$$\frac{315}{14280} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{(1+4^2) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{142800} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{(1+4^2) \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{1428000} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{(1+4^2) \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{315}{14280000} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{(1+4^2) \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$1663. \quad \frac{315}{1470} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{315}{14700} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{315}{147000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{315}{1470000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{1^4 \times 70000}$$

$$1668. \quad \frac{315}{630} := \frac{3+1+5}{6 \times 3+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{6300} := \frac{3+1+5}{6 \times 30+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{63000} := \frac{3+1+5}{6 \times 300+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{630000} := \frac{3+1+5}{6 \times 3000+0}$$

$$1673. \quad \frac{316}{1343} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 34 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{316}{13430} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 34 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{316}{134300} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 34 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{316}{1343000} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 34 \times 3000}$$

$$1664. \quad \frac{315}{385} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(3+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{315}{3850} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(3+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{315}{38500} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(3+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{315}{385000} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(3+8) \times 5000}$$

$$1669. \quad \frac{315}{693} := \frac{3 \times 15}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{315}{6993} := \frac{3 \times 15}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{315}{69993} := \frac{3 \times 15}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{315}{699993} := \frac{3 \times 15}{6+99993}$$

$$1674. \quad \frac{316}{1422} := \frac{3+1^6}{(1+4 \times 2) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{316}{14220} := \frac{3+1^6}{(1+4 \times 2) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{316}{142200} := \frac{3+1^6}{(1+4 \times 2) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{316}{1422000} := \frac{3+1^6}{(1+4 \times 2) \times 2000}$$

$$1665. \quad \frac{315}{448} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(4+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{315}{4480} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(4+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{315}{44800} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(4+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{315}{448000} := \frac{3 \times 15}{(4+4) \times 8000}$$

$$1670. \quad \frac{315}{735} := \frac{3 \times 15}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{315}{7350} := \frac{3 \times 15}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{315}{73500} := \frac{3 \times 15}{7 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{315}{735000} := \frac{3 \times 15}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$1675. \quad \frac{316}{1738} := \frac{3+1+6}{17+38}$$

$$\frac{316}{17538} := \frac{3+1+6}{17+538}$$

$$\frac{316}{175538} := \frac{3+1+6}{17+5538}$$

$$\frac{316}{1755538} := \frac{3+1+6}{17+55538}$$

$$1666. \quad \frac{315}{462} := \frac{3 \times 15}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{315}{4662} := \frac{3 \times 15}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{315}{46662} := \frac{3 \times 15}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{315}{466662} := \frac{3 \times 15}{4+66662}$$

$$1671. \quad \frac{315}{924} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{315}{9240} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{315}{92400} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{315}{924000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 5}{(9+2) \times 4000}$$

$$1667. \quad \frac{315}{5250} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{5 \times 2 \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{52500} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{5 \times 2 \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{525000} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{5 \times 2 \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{315}{5250000} := \frac{3 \times 1^5}{5 \times 2 \times 5000+0}$$

$$1672. \quad \frac{316}{1185} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 18 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{316}{11850} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 18 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{316}{118500} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 18 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{316}{1185000} := \frac{(3+1) \times 6}{1 \times 18 \times 5000}$$

$$1676. \quad \frac{316}{395} := \frac{3 \times 16}{(3+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{316}{3950} := \frac{3 \times 16}{(3+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{316}{39500} := \frac{3 \times 16}{(3+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{316}{395000} := \frac{3 \times 16}{(3+9) \times 5000}$$

$$1677. \quad \frac{316}{632} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 6}{6 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{316}{6320} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 6}{6 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{316}{63200} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 6}{6 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{316}{632000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 6}{6 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$1682. \quad \frac{318}{1378} := \frac{3 \times 18}{1 \times 3 \times 78}$$

$$\frac{318}{13780} := \frac{3 \times 18}{1 \times 3 \times 780}$$

$$\frac{318}{137800} := \frac{3 \times 18}{1 \times 3 \times 7800}$$

$$\frac{318}{1378000} := \frac{3 \times 18}{1 \times 3 \times 78000}$$

$$1687. \quad \frac{318}{795} := \frac{(3+1) \times 8}{(7+9) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{318}{7950} := \frac{(3+1) \times 8}{(7+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{318}{79500} := \frac{(3+1) \times 8}{(7+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{318}{795000} := \frac{(3+1) \times 8}{(7+9) \times 5000}$$

$$1678. \quad \frac{317}{1268} := \frac{3 \times (1+7)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{317}{12680} := \frac{3 \times (1+7)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{317}{126800} := \frac{3 \times (1+7)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{317}{1268000} := \frac{3 \times (1+7)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$1683. \quad \frac{318}{1749} := \frac{3+1+8}{17+49}$$

$$\frac{318}{17649} := \frac{3+1+8}{17+649}$$

$$\frac{318}{176649} := \frac{3+1+8}{17+6649}$$

$$\frac{318}{1766649} := \frac{3+1+8}{17+66649}$$

$$1688. \quad \frac{319}{1276} := \frac{3 \times 19}{(1+2) \times 76}$$

$$\frac{319}{12760} := \frac{3 \times 19}{(1+2) \times 760}$$

$$\frac{319}{127600} := \frac{3 \times 19}{(1+2) \times 7600}$$

$$\frac{319}{1276000} := \frac{3 \times 19}{(1+2) \times 76000}$$

$$1679. \quad \frac{318}{1166} := \frac{3+18}{11+66}$$

$$\frac{318}{11766} := \frac{3+18}{11+766}$$

$$\frac{318}{117766} := \frac{3+18}{11+7766}$$

$$\frac{318}{1177766} := \frac{3+18}{11+77766}$$

$$1684. \quad \frac{318}{424} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{4 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{318}{4240} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{4 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{318}{42400} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{4 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{318}{424000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{4 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

$$1689. \quad \frac{319}{1276} := \frac{3+19}{12+76}$$

$$\frac{319}{12876} := \frac{3+19}{12+876}$$

$$\frac{319}{128876} := \frac{3+19}{12+8876}$$

$$\frac{319}{1288876} := \frac{3+19}{12+88876}$$

$$1680. \quad \frac{318}{1272} := \frac{3 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 72}$$

$$\frac{318}{12720} := \frac{3 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 720}$$

$$\frac{318}{127200} := \frac{3 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{318}{1272000} := \frac{3 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 72000}$$

$$1685. \quad \frac{318}{636} := \frac{3 \times 18}{6 \times 3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{318}{6360} := \frac{3 \times 18}{6 \times 3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{318}{63600} := \frac{3 \times 18}{6 \times 3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{318}{636000} := \frac{3 \times 18}{6 \times 3 \times 6000}$$

$$1690. \quad \frac{319}{638} := \frac{(3+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{319}{6380} := \frac{(3+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{319}{63800} := \frac{(3+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{319}{638000} := \frac{(3+1) \times 9}{(6+3) \times 8000}$$

$$1681. \quad \frac{318}{1325} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 25}$$

$$\frac{318}{13250} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 250}$$

$$\frac{318}{132500} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{318}{1325000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{(1+3) \times 25000}$$

$$1686. \quad \frac{318}{742} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times 4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{318}{7420} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times 4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{318}{74200} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times 4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{318}{742000} := \frac{3 \times 1 \times 8}{7 \times 4 \times 2000}$$

$$1691. \quad \frac{319}{638} := \frac{3+19}{6+38}$$

$$\frac{319}{6438} := \frac{3+19}{6+438}$$

$$\frac{319}{64438} := \frac{3+19}{6+4438}$$

$$\frac{319}{644438} := \frac{3+19}{6+44438}$$

$$1692. \quad \frac{319}{957} := \frac{3+19}{9+57}$$

$$\frac{319}{9657} := \frac{3+19}{9+657}$$

$$\frac{319}{96657} := \frac{3+19}{9+6657}$$

$$\frac{319}{96657} := \frac{3+19}{9+66657}$$

$$1697. \quad \frac{321}{535} := \frac{3+21}{(5+3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{321}{5350} := \frac{3+21}{(5+3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{321}{53500} := \frac{3+21}{(5+3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{321}{535000} := \frac{3+21}{(5+3) \times 5000}$$

$$1701. \quad \frac{322}{1012} := \frac{3+2^2}{10+12}$$

$$\frac{322}{10212} := \frac{3+2^2}{10+212}$$

$$\frac{322}{102212} := \frac{3+2^2}{10+2212}$$

$$\frac{322}{1022212} := \frac{3+2^2}{10+22212}$$

$$1693. \quad \frac{320}{704} := \frac{3+2+0}{7+04}$$

$$\frac{320}{7104} := \frac{3+2+0}{7+104}$$

$$\frac{320}{71104} := \frac{3+2+0}{7+1104}$$

$$\frac{320}{711104} := \frac{3+2+0}{7+11104}$$

$$1698. \quad \frac{321}{642} := \frac{3+21}{6 \times 4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{321}{6420} := \frac{3+21}{6 \times 4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{321}{64200} := \frac{3+21}{6 \times 4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{321}{642000} := \frac{3+21}{6 \times 4 \times 2000}$$

$$1702. \quad \frac{322}{1127} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 2}{(1+1+2) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{322}{11270} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 2}{(1+1+2) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{322}{112700} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 2}{(1+1+2) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{322}{1127000} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 2}{(1+1+2) \times 7000}$$

$$1694. \quad \frac{321}{1177} := \frac{3+21}{11+77}$$

$$\frac{321}{11877} := \frac{3+21}{11+877}$$

$$\frac{321}{118877} := \frac{3+21}{11+8877}$$

$$\frac{321}{1188877} := \frac{3+21}{11+88877}$$

$$1699. \quad \frac{321}{8560} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{8 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{321}{85600} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{8 \times 5 \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{321}{856000} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{8 \times 5 \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{321}{8560000} := \frac{3^2 \times 1}{8 \times 5 \times 6000 + 0}$$

$$1703. \quad \frac{322}{1288} := \frac{32+2}{(1+2 \times 8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{322}{12880} := \frac{32+2}{(1+2 \times 8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{322}{128800} := \frac{32+2}{(1+2 \times 8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{322}{1288000} := \frac{32+2}{(1+2 \times 8) \times 8000}$$

$$1695. \quad \frac{321}{1284} := \frac{3^2+1}{(1 \times 2+8) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{321}{12840} := \frac{3^2+1}{(1 \times 2+8) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{321}{128400} := \frac{3^2+1}{(1 \times 2+8) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{321}{1284000} := \frac{3^2+1}{(1 \times 2+8) \times 4000}$$

$$1700. \quad \frac{322}{1012} := \frac{3+2^2}{(10+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{322}{10120} := \frac{3+2^2}{(10+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{322}{101200} := \frac{3+2^2}{(10+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{322}{1012000} := \frac{3+2^2}{(10+1) \times 2000}$$

$$1704. \quad \frac{322}{1449} := \frac{32+2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{322}{14490} := \frac{32+2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{322}{144900} := \frac{32+2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{322}{1449000} := \frac{32+2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9000}$$

$$1696. \quad \frac{321}{1391} := \frac{3 \times 21}{1 \times 3 \times 91}$$

$$\frac{321}{13910} := \frac{3 \times 21}{1 \times 3 \times 910}$$

$$\frac{321}{139100} := \frac{3 \times 21}{1 \times 3 \times 9100}$$

$$\frac{321}{1391000} := \frac{3 \times 21}{1 \times 3 \times 91000}$$

$$1705. \quad \frac{322}{483} := \frac{32 \times 2}{4 \times 8 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{322}{4830} := \frac{32 \times 2}{4 \times 8 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{322}{48300} := \frac{32 \times 2}{4 \times 8 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{322}{483000} := \frac{32 \times 2}{4 \times 8 \times 3000}$$

1706.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{322}{506} &:= \frac{3+2^2}{5+06} \\ \frac{322}{5106} &:= \frac{3+2^2}{5+106} \\ \frac{322}{51106} &:= \frac{3+2^2}{5+1106} \\ \frac{322}{511106} &:= \frac{3+2^2}{5+11106} \end{aligned}$$

1711.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1188} &:= \frac{3+24}{11+88} \\ \frac{324}{11988} &:= \frac{3+24}{11+988} \\ \frac{324}{119988} &:= \frac{3+24}{11+9988} \end{aligned}$$

1716.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1440} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\ \frac{324}{14400} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\ \frac{324}{144000} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\ \frac{324}{1440000} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 4 \times 40000} \end{aligned}$$

1707.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1080} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 080} \\ \frac{324}{10800} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 0800} \\ \frac{324}{108000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 08000} \\ \frac{324}{1080000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 080000} \end{aligned}$$

1712.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1215} &:= \frac{3 \times 2^4}{12 \times 15} \\ \frac{324}{12150} &:= \frac{3 \times 2^4}{12 \times 150} \\ \frac{324}{121500} &:= \frac{3 \times 2^4}{12 \times 1500} \\ \frac{324}{1215000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2^4}{12 \times 15000} \end{aligned}$$

1717.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1782} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{17+82} \\ \frac{324}{17982} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{17+982} \\ \frac{324}{179982} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{17+9982} \end{aligned}$$

1708.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1125} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 125} \\ \frac{324}{11250} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 1250} \\ \frac{324}{112500} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 12500} \\ \frac{324}{1125000} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 125000} \end{aligned}$$

1713.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1296} &:= \frac{3+24}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\ \frac{324}{12960} &:= \frac{3+24}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\ \frac{324}{129600} &:= \frac{3+24}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\ \frac{324}{1296000} &:= \frac{3+24}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1718.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{432} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{4 \times 3 \times 2} \\ \frac{324}{4320} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{4 \times 3 \times 20} \\ \frac{324}{43200} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{4 \times 3 \times 200} \\ \frac{324}{432000} &:= \frac{3 \times (2+4)}{4 \times 3 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1709.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1188} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 88} \\ \frac{324}{11880} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 880} \\ \frac{324}{118800} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 8800} \\ \frac{324}{1188000} &:= \frac{3 \times 2 \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 88000} \end{aligned}$$

1714.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1350} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\ \frac{324}{13500} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\ \frac{324}{135000} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1719.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{585} &:= \frac{32+4}{(5+8) \times 5} \\ \frac{324}{5850} &:= \frac{32+4}{(5+8) \times 50} \\ \frac{324}{58500} &:= \frac{32+4}{(5+8) \times 500} \\ \frac{324}{585000} &:= \frac{32+4}{(5+8) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1710.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1197} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\ \frac{324}{11970} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\ \frac{324}{119700} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\ \frac{324}{1197000} &:= \frac{32+4}{1 \times 19 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

1715.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{1368} &:= \frac{32+4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\ \frac{324}{13680} &:= \frac{32+4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80} \\ \frac{324}{136800} &:= \frac{32+4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800} \\ \frac{324}{1368000} &:= \frac{32+4}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1720.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{324}{729} &:= \frac{32+4}{(7+2) \times 9} \\ \frac{324}{7290} &:= \frac{32+4}{(7+2) \times 90} \\ \frac{324}{72900} &:= \frac{32+4}{(7+2) \times 900} \\ \frac{324}{729000} &:= \frac{32+4}{(7+2) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1721. \quad \frac{324}{7560} := \frac{3+2+4}{7 \times 5 \times 6+0}$$

$$\frac{324}{75600} := \frac{3+2+4}{7 \times 5 \times 60+0}$$

$$\frac{324}{756000} := \frac{3+2+4}{7 \times 5 \times 600+0}$$

$$\frac{324}{7560000} := \frac{3+2+4}{7 \times 5 \times 6000+0}$$

$$1726. \quad \frac{325}{1300} := \frac{3 \times 25}{1 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{325}{13000} := \frac{3 \times 25}{1 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{325}{130000} := \frac{3 \times 25}{1 \times 30000}$$

$$\frac{325}{1300000} := \frac{3 \times 25}{1 \times 300000}$$

$$1731. \quad \frac{325}{5875} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(5 \times 8+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{58750} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(5 \times 8+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{325}{587500} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(5 \times 8+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{325}{5875000} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(5 \times 8+7) \times 5000}$$

$$1722. \quad \frac{324}{864} := \frac{3 \times 24}{8 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{324}{8640} := \frac{3 \times 24}{8 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{324}{86400} := \frac{3 \times 24}{8 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{324}{864000} := \frac{3 \times 24}{8 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

$$1727. \quad \frac{325}{1375} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{13750} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{325}{137500} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{325}{1375000} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(1+3+7) \times 5000}$$

$$1732. \quad \frac{325}{624} := \frac{3 \times 25}{6 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{325}{6240} := \frac{3 \times 25}{6 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{325}{62400} := \frac{3 \times 25}{6 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{325}{624000} := \frac{3 \times 25}{6 \times 24000}$$

$$1723. \quad \frac{325}{1144} := \frac{(1+1) \times 44}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{11440} := \frac{(1+1) \times 440}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{114400} := \frac{(1+1) \times 4400}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{1144000} := \frac{(1+1) \times 44000}{(3+2) \times 5}$$

$$1728. \quad \frac{325}{1430} := \frac{3+2+5}{1+43+0}$$

$$\frac{325}{14300} := \frac{3+2+5}{1+443+0}$$

$$\frac{325}{143000} := \frac{3+2+5}{1+4443+0}$$

$$\frac{325}{1430000} := \frac{3+2+5}{1+44443+0}$$

$$1733. \quad \frac{325}{715} := \frac{3+2+5}{7+15}$$

$$\frac{325}{7215} := \frac{3+2+5}{7+215}$$

$$\frac{325}{72215} := \frac{3+2+5}{7+2215}$$

$$\frac{325}{722215} := \frac{3+2+5}{7+22215}$$

$$1724. \quad \frac{325}{1248} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 48}$$

$$\frac{325}{12480} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 480}$$

$$\frac{325}{124800} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 4800}$$

$$\frac{325}{1248000} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}$$

$$1729. \quad \frac{325}{18875} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(18 \times 8+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{325}{188750} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(18 \times 8+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{325}{1887500} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(18 \times 8+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{325}{18875000} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{(18 \times 8+7) \times 5000}$$

$$1734. \quad \frac{325}{825} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+25}$$

$$\frac{325}{8325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+325}$$

$$\frac{325}{83325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+3325}$$

$$\frac{325}{833325} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{8+33325}$$

$$1725. \quad \frac{325}{1250} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{1^2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{325}{12500} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{1^2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{325}{125000} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{1^2 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{325}{1250000} := \frac{3+2 \times 5}{1^2 \times 50000}$$

$$1730. \quad \frac{325}{429} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{4+29}$$

$$\frac{325}{4329} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{4+329}$$

$$\frac{325}{43329} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{4+3329}$$

$$\frac{325}{433329} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{4+33329}$$

$$1735. \quad \frac{325}{858} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+58}$$

$$\frac{325}{8658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+658}$$

$$\frac{325}{86658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+6658}$$

$$\frac{325}{866658} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{8+66658}$$

$$1736. \quad \frac{325}{936} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(9+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{325}{9360} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(9+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{325}{93600} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(9+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{325}{936000} := \frac{(3+2) \times 5}{(9+3) \times 6000}$$

$$1741. \quad \frac{327}{1199} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 1 \times 99}$$

$$\frac{327}{11990} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 1 \times 990}$$

$$\frac{327}{119900} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900}$$

$$\frac{327}{1199000} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}$$

$$1746. \quad \frac{328}{369} := \frac{3^2 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{328}{3690} := \frac{3^2 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{328}{36900} := \frac{3^2 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{328}{369000} := \frac{3^2 \times 8}{(3+6) \times 9000}$$

$$1737. \quad \frac{326}{1304} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{1 \times 30 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{326}{13040} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{1 \times 30 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{326}{130400} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{1 \times 30 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{326}{1304000} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{1 \times 30 \times 4000}$$

$$1742. \quad \frac{327}{545} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{(5+4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{327}{5450} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{(5+4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{327}{54500} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{(5+4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{327}{545000} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{(5+4) \times 5000}$$

$$1747. \quad \frac{328}{451} := \frac{32+8}{4+51}$$

$$\frac{328}{4551} := \frac{32+8}{4+551}$$

$$\frac{328}{45551} := \frac{32+8}{4+5551}$$

$$\frac{328}{455551} := \frac{32+8}{4+55551}$$

$$1738. \quad \frac{326}{489} := \frac{3 \times 2^6}{4 \times 8 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{326}{4890} := \frac{3 \times 2^6}{4 \times 8 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{326}{48900} := \frac{3 \times 2^6}{4 \times 8 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{326}{489000} := \frac{3 \times 2^6}{4 \times 8 \times 9000}$$

$$1743. \quad \frac{327}{6540} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{65 \times 4 + 0}$$

$$\frac{327}{65400} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{65 \times 40 + 0}$$

$$\frac{327}{654000} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{65 \times 400 + 0}$$

$$\frac{327}{6540000} := \frac{3 \times 2 + 7}{65 \times 4000 + 0}$$

$$1748. \quad \frac{328}{492} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{328}{4920} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{328}{49200} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{328}{492000} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{4 \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$1739. \quad \frac{326}{652} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{6 \times 5 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{326}{6520} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{6 \times 5 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{326}{65200} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{6 \times 5 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{326}{652000} := \frac{(3+2) \times 6}{6 \times 5 \times 2000}$$

$$1744. \quad \frac{327}{872} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 7}{8 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{327}{8720} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 7}{8 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{327}{87200} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 7}{8 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{327}{872000} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 7}{8 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$1740. \quad \frac{327}{1090} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 090}$$

$$\frac{327}{10900} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 0900}$$

$$\frac{327}{109000} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 09000}$$

$$\frac{327}{1090000} := \frac{3 \times (2+7)}{1 \times 090000}$$

$$1745. \quad \frac{328}{1435} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{14 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{328}{14350} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{14 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{328}{143500} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{14 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{328}{1435000} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{14 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$1749. \quad \frac{328}{615} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 15}$$

$$\frac{328}{6150} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 150}$$

$$\frac{328}{61500} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 1500}$$

$$\frac{328}{615000} := \frac{3 \times 2 \times 8}{6 \times 15000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1750. \quad & \frac{329}{1034} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+34} \\
 & \frac{329}{10434} := \frac{3+2+9}{10+434} \\
 & \frac{104434}{329} := \frac{10+4434}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{1044434}{329} := \frac{10+44434}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{1044434}{1044434} := \frac{10+44434}{10+44434}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1755. \quad & \frac{329}{423} := \frac{3+2+9}{(4+2) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{329}{4230} := \frac{3+2+9}{(4+2) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{42300}{329} := \frac{(4+2) \times 300}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{423000}{329} := \frac{(4+2) \times 3000}{3+2+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1760. \quad & \frac{331}{993} := \frac{3^{3+1}}{9 \times 9 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{331}{9930} := \frac{3^{3+1}}{9 \times 9 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{331}{99300} := \frac{3^{3+1}}{9 \times 9 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{331}{993000} := \frac{3^{3+1}}{9 \times 9 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1751. \quad & \frac{329}{1175} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{329}{11750} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{117500}{329} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 7500}{3+2 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{1175000}{329} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 75000}{3+2 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1756. \quad & \frac{329}{517} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+17} \\
 & \frac{329}{5217} := \frac{3+2+9}{5+217} \\
 & \frac{52217}{329} := \frac{5+2217}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{522217}{329} := \frac{5+22217}{3+2+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1761. \quad & \frac{332}{1245} := \frac{3+3+2}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{332}{12450} := \frac{3+3+2}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{332}{124500} := \frac{3+3+2}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{332}{1245000} := \frac{3+3+2}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1752. \quad & \frac{329}{1269} := \frac{3+2+9}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{329}{12690} := \frac{3+2+9}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{126900}{329} := \frac{1^2 \times 6 \times 900}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{1269000}{329} := \frac{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000}{3+2+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1757. \quad & \frac{330}{1155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+15+5} \\
 & \frac{330}{12155} := \frac{3+3+0}{1+215+5} \\
 & \frac{122155}{330} := \frac{1+2215+5}{3+3+0} \\
 & \frac{1222155}{330} := \frac{1+22215+5}{3+3+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1762. \quad & \frac{332}{1328} := \frac{33 \times 2}{(1+32) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{332}{13280} := \frac{33 \times 2}{(1+32) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{332}{132800} := \frac{33 \times 2}{(1+32) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{332}{1328000} := \frac{33 \times 2}{(1+32) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1753. \quad & \frac{329}{1316} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{(13+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{329}{13160} := \frac{3+2 \times 9}{(13+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{131600}{329} := \frac{(13+1) \times 600}{3+2 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{1316000}{329} := \frac{(13+1) \times 6000}{3+2 \times 9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1758. \quad & \frac{330}{605} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+05} \\
 & \frac{330}{6105} := \frac{3+3+0}{6+105} \\
 & \frac{61105}{330} := \frac{6+1105}{3+3+0} \\
 & \frac{611105}{330} := \frac{6+11105}{3+3+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1763. \quad & \frac{332}{1826} := \frac{3+3+2}{18+26} \\
 & \frac{332}{18426} := \frac{3+3+2}{18+426} \\
 & \frac{184426}{332} := \frac{18+4426}{3+3+2} \\
 & \frac{1844426}{332} := \frac{18+44426}{3+3+2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1754. \quad & \frac{329}{1551} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+51} \\
 & \frac{329}{15651} := \frac{3+2+9}{15+651} \\
 & \frac{156651}{329} := \frac{15+6651}{3+2+9} \\
 & \frac{1566651}{329} := \frac{15+66651}{3+2+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1759. \quad & \frac{331}{662} := \frac{3 \times (3+1)}{(6+6) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{331}{6620} := \frac{3 \times (3+1)}{(6+6) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{66200}{331} := \frac{(6+6) \times 200}{3 \times (3+1)} \\
 & \frac{662000}{331} := \frac{(6+6) \times 2000}{3 \times (3+1)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1764. \quad & \frac{332}{830} := \frac{3 \times 32}{8 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{332}{8300} := \frac{3 \times 32}{8 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{332}{83000} := \frac{3 \times 32}{8 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{332}{830000} := \frac{3 \times 32}{8 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

1765.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{332}{913} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+13} \\ \frac{332}{9213} &:= \frac{3+3+2}{9+213} \\ \frac{92213}{332} &:= \frac{9+2213}{3+3+2} \\ \frac{92213}{922213} &:= \frac{9+22213}{9+22213} \end{aligned}$$

1770.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1295} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 3}{(12+9) \times 5} \\ \frac{333}{12950} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 3}{(12+9) \times 50} \\ \frac{333}{129500} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 3}{(12+9) \times 500} \\ \frac{333}{1295000} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 3}{(12+9) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1775.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{814} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+14} \\ \frac{333}{8214} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{8+214} \\ \frac{82214}{333} &:= \frac{8+2214}{3+3+3} \\ \frac{82214}{822214} &:= \frac{8+22214}{8+22214} \end{aligned}$$

1766.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{332}{996} &:= \frac{(3+3)^2}{(9+9) \times 6} \\ \frac{332}{9960} &:= \frac{(3+3)^2}{(9+9) \times 60} \\ \frac{332}{99600} &:= \frac{(3+3)^2}{(9+9) \times 600} \\ \frac{332}{996000} &:= \frac{(3+3)^2}{(9+9) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1771.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1369} &:= \frac{3 \times 3^3}{(1+36) \times 9} \\ \frac{333}{13690} &:= \frac{3 \times 3^3}{(1+36) \times 90} \\ \frac{333}{136900} &:= \frac{3 \times 3^3}{(1+36) \times 900} \\ \frac{333}{1369000} &:= \frac{3 \times 3^3}{(1+36) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

1776.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{334}{1336} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 36} \\ \frac{334}{13360} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 360} \\ \frac{334}{133600} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 3600} \\ \frac{334}{1336000} &:= \frac{3 \times 3 \times 4}{(1+3) \times 36000} \end{aligned}$$

1767.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1184} &:= \frac{3 \times 33}{11 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{333}{11840} &:= \frac{3 \times 33}{11 \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{333}{118400} &:= \frac{3 \times 33}{11 \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{333}{1184000} &:= \frac{3 \times 33}{11 \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1772.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1480} &:= \frac{3 \times (3+3)}{1^4 \times 80} \\ \frac{333}{14800} &:= \frac{3 \times (3+3)}{1^4 \times 800} \\ \frac{333}{148000} &:= \frac{3 \times (3+3)}{1^4 \times 8000} \\ \frac{333}{1480000} &:= \frac{3 \times (3+3)}{1^4 \times 80000} \end{aligned}$$

1777.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{334}{1837} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+37} \\ \frac{334}{18537} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+537} \\ \frac{334}{185537} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+5537} \\ \frac{334}{1855537} &:= \frac{3+3+4}{18+55537} \end{aligned}$$

1768.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1221} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+21} \\ \frac{333}{12321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+321} \\ \frac{333}{123321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+3321} \\ \frac{333}{1233321} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{12+33321} \end{aligned}$$

1773.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{407} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+07} \\ \frac{333}{4107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+107} \\ \frac{333}{41107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+1107} \\ \frac{333}{411107} &:= \frac{3+3+3}{4+11107} \end{aligned}$$

1769.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{1258} &:= \frac{3+33}{(12+5) \times 8} \\ \frac{333}{12580} &:= \frac{3+33}{(12+5) \times 80} \\ \frac{333}{125800} &:= \frac{3+33}{(12+5) \times 800} \\ \frac{333}{1258000} &:= \frac{3+33}{(12+5) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1774.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{333}{666} &:= \frac{3+33}{(6+6) \times 6} \\ \frac{333}{6660} &:= \frac{3+33}{(6+6) \times 60} \\ \frac{333}{66600} &:= \frac{3+33}{(6+6) \times 600} \\ \frac{333}{666000} &:= \frac{3+33}{(6+6) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1778.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{335}{1340} &:= \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 40} \\ \frac{335}{13400} &:= \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 400} \\ \frac{335}{134000} &:= \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 4000} \\ \frac{335}{1340000} &:= \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 40000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1779. \quad \frac{335}{536} := \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{(5+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{335}{5360} := \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{(5+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{335}{53600} := \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{(5+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{335}{536000} := \frac{(3+3) \times 5}{(5+3) \times 6000}$$

$$1784. \quad \frac{336}{1280} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{1^2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{336}{12800} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{1^2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{336}{128000} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{1^2 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{336}{1280000} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{1^2 \times 80000}$$

$$1789. \quad \frac{336}{616} := \frac{3+3+6}{6+16}$$

$$\frac{336}{6216} := \frac{3+3+6}{6+216}$$

$$\frac{336}{62216} := \frac{3+3+6}{6+2216}$$

$$\frac{336}{622216} := \frac{3+3+6}{6+22216}$$

$$1780. \quad \frac{336}{1056} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+56}$$

$$\frac{336}{10656} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+656}$$

$$\frac{336}{106656} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+6656}$$

$$\frac{336}{1066656} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{10+66656}$$

$$1785. \quad \frac{336}{1344} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{336}{13440} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{336}{134400} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{336}{1344000} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$1790. \quad \frac{336}{896} := \frac{3^3 \times 6}{8 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{336}{8960} := \frac{3^3 \times 6}{8 \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{336}{89600} := \frac{3^3 \times 6}{8 \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{336}{896000} := \frac{3^3 \times 6}{8 \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$1781. \quad \frac{336}{1120} := \frac{(3+3) \times 6}{1 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{336}{11200} := \frac{(3+3) \times 6}{1 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{336}{112000} := \frac{(3+3) \times 6}{1 \times 12000}$$

$$\frac{336}{1120000} := \frac{(3+3) \times 6}{1 \times 120000}$$

$$1786. \quad \frac{336}{14848} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{336}{148480} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{336}{1484800} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{336}{14848000} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{(14 \times 8 + 4) \times 8000}$$

$$1791. \quad \frac{336}{924} := \frac{3+3+6}{9+24}$$

$$\frac{336}{9324} := \frac{3+3+6}{9+324}$$

$$\frac{336}{93324} := \frac{3+3+6}{9+3324}$$

$$\frac{336}{933324} := \frac{3+3+6}{9+33324}$$

$$1782. \quad \frac{336}{1176} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{336}{11760} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{336}{117600} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{336}{1176000} := \frac{3+3+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

$$1787. \quad \frac{336}{1584} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+84}$$

$$\frac{336}{15984} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+984}$$

$$\frac{336}{159984} := \frac{3+3 \times 6}{15+9984}$$

$$1792. \quad \frac{337}{1348} := \frac{3+3 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{337}{13480} := \frac{3+3 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{337}{134800} := \frac{3+3 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{337}{1348000} := \frac{3+3 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$1783. \quad \frac{336}{1232} := \frac{3+3+6}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{336}{12432} := \frac{3+3+6}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{336}{124432} := \frac{3+3+6}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{336}{1244432} := \frac{3+3+6}{12+44432}$$

$$1788. \quad \frac{336}{1848} := \frac{3+3+6}{18+48}$$

$$\frac{336}{18648} := \frac{3+3+6}{18+648}$$

$$\frac{336}{186648} := \frac{3+3+6}{18+6648}$$

$$\frac{336}{1866648} := \frac{3+3+6}{18+66648}$$

$$1793. \quad \frac{339}{1130} := \frac{(3 \times 3) + 9}{(1+1) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{339}{11300} := \frac{(3 \times 3) + 9}{(1+1) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{339}{113000} := \frac{(3 \times 3) + 9}{(1+1) \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{339}{1130000} := \frac{(3 \times 3) + 9}{(1+1) \times 30000}$$

1794.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{339}{1243} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+43} \\ \frac{339}{12543} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+543} \\ \frac{339}{125543} &:= \frac{3+3+9}{12+5543} \\ \frac{125543}{339} &:= \frac{12+5543}{3+3+9} \\ \frac{125543}{125543} &:= \frac{12+5543}{12+5543} \end{aligned}$$

1799.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{341}{1395} &:= \frac{3+41}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5} \\ \frac{341}{13950} &:= \frac{3+41}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50} \\ \frac{341}{139500} &:= \frac{3+41}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500} \\ \frac{341}{1395000} &:= \frac{3+41}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1804.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1140} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 40} \\ \frac{342}{11400} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 400} \\ \frac{342}{114000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 4000} \\ \frac{342}{1140000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+1) \times 40000} \end{aligned}$$

1795.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{339}{1356} &:= \frac{3+39}{1 \times 3 \times 56} \\ \frac{339}{13560} &:= \frac{3+39}{1 \times 3 \times 560} \\ \frac{339}{135600} &:= \frac{3+39}{1 \times 3 \times 5600} \\ \frac{339}{1356000} &:= \frac{3+39}{1 \times 3 \times 56000} \end{aligned}$$

1800.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{341}{682} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+82} \\ \frac{341}{6882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+882} \\ \frac{341}{68882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+8882} \\ \frac{341}{688882} &:= \frac{3+41}{6+88882} \end{aligned}$$

1805.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1152} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2} \\ \frac{342}{11520} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1)^5 \times 20} \\ \frac{342}{115200} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1)^5 \times 200} \\ \frac{342}{1152000} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1796.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{339}{452} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 9}{4 \times 5 \times 2} \\ \frac{339}{4520} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 9}{4 \times 5 \times 20} \\ \frac{339}{45200} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 9}{4 \times 5 \times 200} \\ \frac{339}{452000} &:= \frac{3+3 \times 9}{4 \times 5 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1801.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1026} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(10+2) \times 6} \\ \frac{342}{10260} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(10+2) \times 60} \\ \frac{342}{102600} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(10+2) \times 600} \\ \frac{342}{1026000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{(10+2) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1806.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{11592} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1+5) \times 92} \\ \frac{342}{115920} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1+5) \times 920} \\ \frac{342}{1159200} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1+5) \times 9200} \\ \frac{342}{11592000} &:= \frac{3+4^2}{(1+1+5) \times 92000} \end{aligned}$$

1797.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{341}{1023} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{(10+2) \times 3} \\ \frac{341}{10230} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{(10+2) \times 30} \\ \frac{341}{102300} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{(10+2) \times 300} \\ \frac{341}{1023000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 1}{(10+2) \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

1802.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1045} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+45} \\ \frac{342}{10545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+545} \\ \frac{342}{105545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+5545} \\ \frac{342}{1055545} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{10+55545} \end{aligned}$$

1798.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{341}{1364} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 1}{(1^3+6) \times 40} \\ \frac{341}{13640} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 1}{(1^3+6) \times 400} \\ \frac{341}{136400} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 1}{(1^3+6) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1803.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1064} &:= \frac{3+4+2}{(1+06) \times 4} \\ \frac{342}{10640} &:= \frac{3+4+2}{(1+06) \times 40} \\ \frac{342}{106400} &:= \frac{3+4+2}{(1+06) \times 400} \\ \frac{342}{1064000} &:= \frac{3+4+2}{(1+06) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1807.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{342}{1197} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\ \frac{342}{11970} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\ \frac{342}{119700} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\ \frac{342}{1197000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

$$1808. \quad \frac{342}{1216} := \frac{3+4+2}{1 \times 2 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{342}{12160} := \frac{3+4+2}{1 \times 2 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{342}{121600} := \frac{3+4+2}{1 \times 2 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{342}{1216000} := \frac{3+4+2}{1 \times 2 \times 16000}$$

$$1812. \quad \frac{342}{1296} := \frac{3+4^2}{(1+2+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{342}{12960} := \frac{3+4^2}{(1+2+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{342}{129600} := \frac{3+4^2}{(1+2+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{342}{1296000} := \frac{3+4^2}{(1+2+9) \times 6000}$$

$$1816. \quad \frac{342}{1463} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+63}$$

$$\frac{342}{14763} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+763}$$

$$\frac{342}{147763} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+7763}$$

$$\frac{342}{1477763} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{14+77763}$$

$$1809. \quad \frac{342}{1254} := \frac{34+2}{(1+2^5) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{342}{12540} := \frac{34+2}{(1+2^5) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{342}{125400} := \frac{34+2}{(1+2^5) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{342}{1254000} := \frac{34+2}{(1+2^5) \times 4000}$$

$$1813. \quad \frac{342}{12996} := \frac{3 \times 4^2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 96}$$

$$\frac{342}{129960} := \frac{3 \times 4^2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 960}$$

$$\frac{342}{1299600} := \frac{3 \times 4^2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 9600}$$

$$\frac{342}{12996000} := \frac{3 \times 4^2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 96000}$$

$$1817. \quad \frac{342}{1672} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{16+72}$$

$$\frac{342}{16872} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{16+872}$$

$$\frac{342}{168872} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{16+8872}$$

$$\frac{342}{1688872} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{16+88872}$$

$$1810. \quad \frac{342}{1254} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+54}$$

$$\frac{342}{12654} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+654}$$

$$\frac{342}{126654} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+6654}$$

$$\frac{342}{1266654} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{12+66654}$$

$$1814. \quad \frac{342}{1368} := \frac{34 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 68}$$

$$\frac{342}{13680} := \frac{34 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 680}$$

$$\frac{342}{136800} := \frac{34 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 6800}$$

$$\frac{342}{1368000} := \frac{34 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 68000}$$

$$1818. \quad \frac{342}{1881} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{18+81}$$

$$\frac{342}{18981} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{18+981}$$

$$\frac{342}{189981} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{18+9981}$$

$$\frac{342}{1899981} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{18+99981}$$

$$1811. \quad \frac{342}{1296} := \frac{3+4^2}{(1+2+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{342}{12960} := \frac{3+(4^2)}{(1+2+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{342}{129600} := \frac{3+(4^2)}{(1+2+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{342}{1296000} := \frac{3+(4^2)}{(1+2+9) \times 6000}$$

$$1815. \quad \frac{342}{1425} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{342}{14250} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{342}{142500} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{342}{1425000} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 2}{1 \times 4 \times 25000}$$

$$1819. \quad \frac{342}{418} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{4+18}$$

$$\frac{342}{4218} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{4+218}$$

$$\frac{342}{42218} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{4+2218}$$

$$\frac{342}{422218} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{4+22218}$$

$$1820. \quad \frac{342}{432} := \frac{3+4^2}{4 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{342}{4320} := \frac{3+4^2}{4 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{342}{43200} := \frac{3+4^2}{4 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{342}{432000} := \frac{3+4^2}{4 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

1821.

$$\frac{342}{4560} := \frac{3+4+2}{4 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{342}{45600} := \frac{3+4+2}{4 \times 5 \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{342}{456000} := \frac{3+4+2}{4 \times 5 \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{342}{4560000} := \frac{3+4+2}{4 \times 5 \times 6000 + 0}$$

1822.

$$\frac{342}{494} := \frac{34+2}{(4+9) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{342}{4940} := \frac{34+2}{(4+9) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{342}{49400} := \frac{34+2}{(4+9) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{342}{494000} := \frac{34+2}{(4+9) \times 4000}$$

1823.

$$\frac{342}{627} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{6+27}$$

$$\frac{342}{6327} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{6+327}$$

$$\frac{342}{63327} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{6+3327}$$

$$\frac{342}{633327} := \frac{3 \times (4+2)}{6+33327}$$

1824.

$$\frac{342}{950} := \frac{3^4 \times 2}{9 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{342}{9500} := \frac{3^4 \times 2}{9 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{342}{95000} := \frac{3^4 \times 2}{9 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{342}{950000} := \frac{3^4 \times 2}{9 \times 50000}$$

1825.

$$\frac{343}{1225} := \frac{3^4+3}{12 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{343}{12250} := \frac{3^4+3}{12 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{343}{122500} := \frac{3^4+3}{12 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{343}{1225000} := \frac{3^4+3}{12 \times 25000}$$

1826.

$$\frac{343}{1285} := \frac{(3+4)^3}{(1+2^8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{343}{12850} := \frac{(3+4)^3}{(1+2^8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{343}{128500} := \frac{(3+4)^3}{(1+2^8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{343}{1285000} := \frac{(3+4)^3}{(1+2^8) \times 5000}$$

1827.

$$\frac{343}{1568} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(1+5+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{343}{15680} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(1+5+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{343}{156800} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(1+5+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{343}{1568000} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(1+5+6) \times 8000}$$

1828.

$$\frac{343}{392} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(3+9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{343}{3920} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(3+9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{343}{39200} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(3+9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{343}{392000} := \frac{3 \times (4+3)}{(3+9) \times 2000}$$

1829.

$$\frac{344}{1075} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 075}$$

$$\frac{344}{10750} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 0750}$$

$$\frac{344}{107500} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 07500}$$

$$\frac{344}{1075000} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 075000}$$

1830.

$$\frac{344}{1204} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(1+20) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{344}{12040} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(1+20) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{344}{120400} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(1+20) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{344}{1204000} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(1+20) \times 4000}$$

1831.

$$\frac{344}{1290} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{344}{12900} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{344}{129000} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{344}{1290000} := \frac{3 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 90000}$$

1832.

$$\frac{344}{1376} := \frac{3+4 \times 4}{1^3 \times 76}$$

$$\frac{344}{13760} := \frac{3+4 \times 4}{1^3 \times 760}$$

$$\frac{344}{137600} := \frac{3+4 \times 4}{1^3 \times 7600}$$

$$\frac{344}{1376000} := \frac{3+4 \times 4}{1^3 \times 76000}$$

1833.

$$\frac{344}{516} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(5+1) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{344}{5160} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(5+1) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{344}{51600} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(5+1) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{344}{516000} := \frac{3 \times (4+4)}{(5+1) \times 6000}$$

1834.

$$\frac{345}{1242} := \frac{(3+4) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 42}$$

$$\frac{345}{12420} := \frac{(3+4) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 420}$$

$$\frac{345}{124200} := \frac{(3+4) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 4200}$$

$$\frac{345}{1242000} := \frac{(3+4) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 42000}$$

1835.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{1288} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 28 \times 8} \\ \frac{345}{12880} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 28 \times 80} \\ \frac{345}{128800} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 28 \times 800} \\ \frac{345}{1288000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 28 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1840.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{480} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{4 \times 8 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{4800} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{4 \times 80 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{48000} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{4 \times 800 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{480000} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{4 \times 8000 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

1845.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{347}{1388} &:= \frac{3+47}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 8} \\ \frac{347}{13880} &:= \frac{3+47}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 80} \\ \frac{347}{138800} &:= \frac{3+47}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 800} \\ \frac{347}{1388000} &:= \frac{3+47}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1836.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{1380} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 80} \\ \frac{345}{13800} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 800} \\ \frac{345}{138000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 8000} \\ \frac{345}{1380000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 80000} \end{aligned}$$

1841.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{525} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{(5+2) \times 5} \\ \frac{345}{5250} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{(5+2) \times 50} \\ \frac{345}{52500} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{(5+2) \times 500} \\ \frac{345}{525000} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{(5+2) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

1846.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{348}{1160} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 60} \\ \frac{348}{11600} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 600} \\ \frac{348}{116000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 6000} \\ \frac{348}{1160000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 60000} \end{aligned}$$

1837.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{1470} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14 \times 7 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{14700} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14 \times 70 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{147000} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14 \times 700 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{1470000} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14 \times 7000 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

1842.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{690} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+5)}{6 \times 9 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{6900} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+5)}{6 \times 90 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{69000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+5)}{6 \times 900 + 0} \\ \frac{345}{690000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+5)}{6 \times 9000 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

1847.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{348}{1392} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(1+39) \times 2} \\ \frac{348}{13920} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(1+39) \times 20} \\ \frac{348}{139200} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(1+39) \times 200} \\ \frac{348}{1392000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(1+39) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

1838.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{1485} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14+85} \\ \frac{345}{14985} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14+985} \\ \frac{345}{149985} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14+9985} \\ \frac{345}{1499985} &:= \frac{3+4 \times 5}{14+99985} \end{aligned}$$

1843.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{346}{1384} &:= \frac{3 \times 46}{138 \times 4} \\ \frac{346}{13840} &:= \frac{3 \times 46}{138 \times 40} \\ \frac{346}{138400} &:= \frac{3 \times 46}{138 \times 400} \\ \frac{346}{1384000} &:= \frac{3 \times 46}{138 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

1848.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{348}{783} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(7+8) \times 3} \\ \frac{348}{7830} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(7+8) \times 30} \\ \frac{348}{78300} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(7+8) \times 300} \\ \frac{348}{783000} &:= \frac{3 \times 4 + 8}{(7+8) \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

1839.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{345}{368} &:= \frac{3 \times 45}{3 \times 6 \times 8} \\ \frac{345}{3680} &:= \frac{3 \times 45}{3 \times 6 \times 80} \\ \frac{345}{36800} &:= \frac{3 \times 45}{3 \times 6 \times 800} \\ \frac{345}{368000} &:= \frac{3 \times 45}{3 \times 6 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

1844.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{346}{519} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times 1 \times 9} \\ \frac{346}{5190} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times 1 \times 90} \\ \frac{346}{51900} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times 1 \times 900} \\ \frac{346}{519000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+6)}{5 \times 1 \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

1849.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{348}{986} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(9+8) \times 6} \\ \frac{348}{9860} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(9+8) \times 60} \\ \frac{348}{98600} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(9+8) \times 600} \\ \frac{348}{986000} &:= \frac{3 \times (4+8)}{(9+8) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

1850.

$$\frac{351}{1053} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{(10+5) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{351}{10530} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{(10+5) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{351}{105300} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{(10+5) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{351}{1053000} := \frac{3 \times 5 \times 1}{(10+5) \times 3000}$$

1855.

$$\frac{351}{12675} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 26 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{351}{126750} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 26 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{351}{1267500} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 26 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{351}{12675000} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 26 \times 75000}$$

1860.

$$\frac{351}{416} := \frac{3+51}{4 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{351}{4160} := \frac{3+51}{4 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{351}{41600} := \frac{3+51}{4 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{351}{416000} := \frac{3+51}{4 \times 16000}$$

1851.

$$\frac{351}{1144} := \frac{3+51}{11 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{351}{11440} := \frac{3+51}{11 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{351}{114400} := \frac{3+51}{11 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{351}{1144000} := \frac{3+51}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

1856.

$$\frac{351}{1352} := \frac{3+51}{(1+3) \times 52}$$

$$\frac{351}{13520} := \frac{3+51}{(1+3) \times 520}$$

$$\frac{351}{135200} := \frac{3+51}{(1+3) \times 5200}$$

$$\frac{351}{1352000} := \frac{3+51}{(1+3) \times 52000}$$

1861.

$$\frac{351}{624} := \frac{3 \times (5+1)}{(6+2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{351}{6240} := \frac{3 \times (5+1)}{(6+2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{351}{62400} := \frac{3 \times (5+1)}{(6+2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{351}{624000} := \frac{3 \times (5+1)}{(6+2) \times 4000}$$

1852.

$$\frac{351}{1248} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 24 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{351}{12480} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 24 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{351}{124800} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 24 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{351}{1248000} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 24 \times 8000}$$

1857.

$$\frac{351}{1365} := \frac{3+5+1}{(1^3+6) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{351}{13650} := \frac{3+5+1}{(1^3+6) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{351}{136500} := \frac{3+5+1}{(1^3+6) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{351}{1365000} := \frac{3+5+1}{(1^3+6) \times 5000}$$

1862.

$$\frac{351}{637} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{63 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{351}{6370} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{63 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{351}{63700} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{63 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{351}{637000} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{63 \times 7000}$$

1853.

$$\frac{351}{12558} := \frac{35+1}{(1+2^5 \times 5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{351}{125580} := \frac{35+1}{(1+2^5 \times 5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{351}{1255800} := \frac{35+1}{(1+2^5 \times 5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{351}{12558000} := \frac{35+1}{(1+2^5 \times 5) \times 8000}$$

1858.

$$\frac{351}{1456} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{351}{14560} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{351}{145600} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{351}{1456000} := \frac{3+51}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}$$

1863.

$$\frac{351}{975} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{9 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{351}{9750} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{9 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{351}{97500} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{9 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{351}{975000} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{9 \times 75000}$$

1854.

$$\frac{351}{12636} := \frac{35+1}{12 \times 6 \times 3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{351}{126360} := \frac{35+1}{12 \times 6 \times 3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{351}{1263600} := \frac{35+1}{12 \times 6 \times 3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{351}{12636000} := \frac{35+1}{12 \times 6 \times 3 \times 6000}$$

1859.

$$\frac{351}{390} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{3 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{351}{3900} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{3 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{351}{39000} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{3 \times 9000}$$

$$\frac{351}{390000} := \frac{3^5 \times 1}{3 \times 90000}$$

$$1864. \quad \frac{352}{1056} := \frac{3+5+2}{1 \times 05 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{352}{10560} := \frac{3+5+2}{1 \times 05 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{352}{105600} := \frac{3+5+2}{1 \times 05 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{352}{1056000} := \frac{3+5+2}{1 \times 05 \times 6000}$$

$$1865. \quad \frac{352}{1221} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{1+221}$$

$$\frac{352}{12221} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{1+2221}$$

$$\frac{352}{122221} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{1+22221}$$

$$\frac{352}{1222221} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{1+222221}$$

$$1866. \quad \frac{352}{1320} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{352}{13200} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{352}{132000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{352}{1320000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 20000}$$

$$1867. \quad \frac{352}{1408} := \frac{3+5+2}{(1+4) \times 08}$$

$$\frac{352}{14080} := \frac{3+5+2}{(1+4) \times 080}$$

$$\frac{352}{140800} := \frac{3+5+2}{(1+4) \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{352}{1408000} := \frac{3+5+2}{(1+4) \times 08000}$$

$$1868. \quad \frac{352}{363} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{3+63}$$

$$\frac{352}{3663} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{3+663}$$

$$\frac{352}{36663} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{3+6663}$$

$$\frac{352}{366663} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{3+66663}$$

$$1869. \quad \frac{352}{396} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{(3+9) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{352}{3960} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{(3+9) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{352}{39600} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{(3+9) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{352}{396000} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{(3+9) \times 6000}$$

$$1870. \quad \frac{352}{484} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{4+84}$$

$$\frac{352}{4884} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{4+884}$$

$$\frac{352}{48884} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{4+8884}$$

$$\frac{352}{488884} := \frac{(3+5)^2}{4+88884}$$

$$1871. \quad \frac{352}{550} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{5 \times 5 + 0}$$

$$\frac{352}{5500} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{5 \times 50 + 0}$$

$$\frac{352}{55000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{5 \times 500 + 0}$$

$$\frac{352}{550000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 2}{5 \times 5000 + 0}$$

$$1872. \quad \frac{354}{590} := \frac{3 \times (5+4)}{5 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\frac{354}{5900} := \frac{3 \times (5+4)}{5 \times 90 + 0}$$

$$\frac{354}{59000} := \frac{3 \times (5+4)}{5 \times 900 + 0}$$

$$\frac{354}{590000} := \frac{3 \times (5+4)}{5 \times 9000 + 0}$$

$$1873. \quad \frac{354}{885} := \frac{(3+5) \times 4}{(8+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{354}{8850} := \frac{(3+5) \times 4}{(8+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{354}{88500} := \frac{(3+5) \times 4}{(8+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{354}{885000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 4}{(8+8) \times 5000}$$

$$1874. \quad \frac{355}{1278} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{355}{12780} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{355}{127800} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{355}{1278000} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 2 + 7) \times 8000}$$

$$1875. \quad \frac{355}{1420} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{355}{14200} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{355}{142000} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 4 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{355}{1420000} := \frac{3 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 4 \times 20000}$$

$$1876. \quad \frac{355}{1491} := \frac{3 \times (5+5)}{14 \times 9 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{355}{14910} := \frac{3 \times (5+5)}{14 \times 9 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{355}{149100} := \frac{3 \times (5+5)}{14 \times 9 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{355}{1491000} := \frac{3 \times (5+5)}{14 \times 9 \times 1000}$$

$$1877. \quad \frac{355}{426} := \frac{35+5}{4 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{355}{4260} := \frac{35+5}{4 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{355}{42600} := \frac{35+5}{4 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{355}{426000} := \frac{35+5}{4 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1878. \quad & \frac{355}{5680} := \frac{3+5 \times 5}{56 \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{56800} := \frac{3+5 \times 5}{56 \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{568000} := \frac{3+5 \times 5}{56 \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{5680000} := \frac{3+5 \times 5}{56 \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1883. \quad & \frac{357}{1428} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{357}{14280} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{357}{142800} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{357}{1428000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{14 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1888. \quad & \frac{357}{612} := \frac{35+7}{6 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{357}{6120} := \frac{35+7}{6 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{357}{61200} := \frac{35+7}{6 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{357}{612000} := \frac{35+7}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1879. \quad & \frac{355}{6390} := \frac{3+5+5}{6 \times 439 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{63900} := \frac{3+5+5}{6 \times 4390 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{639000} := \frac{3+5+5}{6 \times 43900 + 0} \\
 & \frac{355}{6390000} := \frac{3+5+5}{6 \times 439000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1884. \quad & \frac{357}{1734} := \frac{35+7}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{357}{17340} := \frac{35+7}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{357}{173400} := \frac{35+7}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{357}{1734000} := \frac{35+7}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1889. \quad & \frac{357}{748} := \frac{35+7}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{357}{7480} := \frac{35+7}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{357}{74800} := \frac{35+7}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{357}{748000} := \frac{35+7}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1880. \quad & \frac{355}{781} := \frac{35+5}{7+81} \\
 & \frac{355}{7881} := \frac{35+5}{7+881} \\
 & \frac{355}{78881} := \frac{35+5}{7+8881} \\
 & \frac{355}{788881} := \frac{35+5}{7+88881}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1885. \quad & \frac{357}{17374} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{357}{173740} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{357}{1737400} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{357}{17374000} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1890. \quad & \frac{357}{816} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 16} \\
 & \frac{357}{8160} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{357}{81600} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{357}{816000} := \frac{(3+5) \times 7}{8 \times 16000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1881. \quad & \frac{357}{1275} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{357}{12750} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{357}{127500} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{357}{1275000} := \frac{35+7}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1886. \quad & \frac{357}{561} := \frac{35+7}{5+61} \\
 & \frac{357}{5661} := \frac{35+7}{5+661} \\
 & \frac{357}{56661} := \frac{35+7}{5+6661} \\
 & \frac{357}{566661} := \frac{35+7}{5+66661}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1891. \quad & \frac{361}{10545} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{10 + 545} \\
 & \frac{361}{105450} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{10 + 5450} \\
 & \frac{361}{1054500} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{10 + 54500}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1882. \quad & \frac{357}{1326} := \frac{35+7}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{357}{13260} := \frac{35+7}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{357}{132600} := \frac{35+7}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{357}{1326000} := \frac{35+7}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1887. \quad & \frac{357}{5950} := \frac{35+7}{(5+9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{357}{59500} := \frac{35+7}{(5+9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{357}{595000} := \frac{35+7}{(5+9) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{357}{5950000} := \frac{35+7}{(5+9) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1892. \quad & \frac{361}{1083} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(10+8) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{361}{10830} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(10+8) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{361}{108300} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(10+8) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{361}{1083000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(10+8) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1893. \quad & \frac{361}{1197} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{361}{11970} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{361}{119700} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{361}{1197000} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1898. \quad & \frac{361}{627} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 27} \\
 & \frac{361}{6327} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 327} \\
 & \frac{361}{63327} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 3327} \\
 & \frac{361}{633327} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{6 + 33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1903. \quad & \frac{362}{1448} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(14 + 4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{362}{14480} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(14 + 4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{362}{144800} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(14 + 4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{362}{1448000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(14 + 4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1894. \quad & \frac{361}{1368} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{361}{13680} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{361}{136800} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{361}{1368000} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1899. \quad & \frac{361}{722} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 1}{(7 + 2) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{361}{7220} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 1}{(7 + 2) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{361}{72200} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 1}{(7 + 2) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{361}{722000} := \frac{3 + 6 \times 1}{(7 + 2) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1904. \quad & \frac{362}{724} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(7 + 2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{362}{7240} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(7 + 2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{362}{72400} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(7 + 2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{362}{724000} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{(7 + 2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1895. \quad & \frac{361}{1444} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(14 + 4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{361}{14440} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(14 + 4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{361}{144400} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(14 + 4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{361}{1444000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 1}{(14 + 4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1900. \quad & \frac{361}{836} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 36} \\
 & \frac{361}{8436} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 436} \\
 & \frac{361}{84436} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 4436} \\
 & \frac{361}{844436} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{8 + 44436}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1905. \quad & \frac{362}{905} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{9 \times 05} \\
 & \frac{362}{9050} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{9 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{362}{90500} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{9 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{362}{905000} := \frac{(3 + 6) \times 2}{9 \times 05000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1896. \quad & \frac{361}{1463} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 63} \\
 & \frac{361}{14763} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 763} \\
 & \frac{361}{147763} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 7763} \\
 & \frac{361}{1477763} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{14 + 77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1901. \quad & \frac{362}{1086} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(10 + 8) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{362}{10860} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(10 + 8) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{362}{108600} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(10 + 8) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{362}{1086000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 2}{(10 + 8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1906. \quad & \frac{363}{1089} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 3}{(10 + 8) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{363}{10890} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 3}{(10 + 8) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{363}{108900} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 3}{(10 + 8) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{363}{1089000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 3}{(10 + 8) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1897. \quad & \frac{361}{1672} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 72} \\
 & \frac{361}{16872} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 872} \\
 & \frac{361}{168872} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 8872} \\
 & \frac{361}{1688872} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 1}{16 + 88872}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1902. \quad & \frac{362}{1267} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 2)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{362}{12670} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 2)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{362}{126700} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 2)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{362}{1267000} := \frac{3 \times (6 + 2)}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1907. \quad & \frac{363}{1221} := \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 221} \\
 & \frac{363}{12221} := \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 2221} \\
 & \frac{363}{122221} := \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 22221} \\
 & \frac{363}{1222221} := \frac{3 + 63}{1 + 222221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1908. \quad & \frac{363}{1331} := \frac{3+6+3}{13+31} \\
 & \frac{363}{13431} := \frac{3+6+3}{13+431} \\
 & \frac{363}{134431} := \frac{3+6+3}{13+4431} \\
 & \frac{363}{1344431} := \frac{3+6+3}{13+44431}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1913. \quad & \frac{364}{1232} := \frac{3+6+4}{12+32} \\
 & \frac{364}{12432} := \frac{3+6+4}{12+432} \\
 & \frac{364}{124432} := \frac{3+6+4}{12+4432} \\
 & \frac{364}{1244432} := \frac{3+6+4}{12+44432}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1918. \quad & \frac{364}{616} := \frac{3+6+4}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{364}{6216} := \frac{3+6+4}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{364}{62216} := \frac{3+6+4}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{364}{622216} := \frac{3+6+4}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1909. \quad & \frac{363}{484} := \frac{3+63}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{363}{4884} := \frac{3+63}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{363}{48884} := \frac{3+63}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{363}{488884} := \frac{3+63}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1914. \quad & \frac{364}{1344} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{364}{13440} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{364}{134400} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{364}{1344000} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1919. \quad & \frac{364}{637} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 3 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{364}{6370} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 3 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{364}{63700} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 3 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{364}{637000} := \frac{3 \times 6 \times 4}{6 \times 3 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1910. \quad & \frac{363}{726} := \frac{3 \times (6+3)}{(7+2) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{363}{7260} := \frac{3 \times (6+3)}{(7+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{363}{72600} := \frac{3 \times (6+3)}{(7+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{363}{726000} := \frac{3 \times (6+3)}{(7+2) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1915. \quad & \frac{364}{1456} := \frac{3 \times (6+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{364}{14560} := \frac{3 \times (6+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{364}{145600} := \frac{3 \times (6+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{364}{1456000} := \frac{3 \times (6+4)}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1920. \quad & \frac{364}{728} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(7+2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{364}{7280} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(7+2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{364}{72800} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(7+2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{364}{728000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(7+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1911. \quad & \frac{364}{1120} := \frac{3+6+4}{(1+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{364}{11200} := \frac{3+6+4}{(1+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{364}{112000} := \frac{3+6+4}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{364}{1120000} := \frac{3+6+4}{(1+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1916. \quad & \frac{364}{455} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(4+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{364}{4550} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(4+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{364}{45500} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(4+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{364}{455000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(4+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1912. \quad & \frac{364}{1176} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{364}{11760} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{364}{117600} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{364}{1176000} := \frac{3+6+4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1917. \quad & \frac{364}{546} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{364}{5460} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{364}{54600} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{364}{546000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(5+4) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1921. \quad & \frac{364}{819} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{364}{8190} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{364}{81900} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{364}{819000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1922. \quad & \frac{364}{910} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{364}{9100} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{364}{91000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{9 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{364}{910000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 4}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1927. \quad & \frac{366}{427} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(4+2) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{366}{4270} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(4+2) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{366}{42700} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(4+2) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{366}{427000} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(4+2) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1932. \quad & \frac{366}{976} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(9+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{366}{9760} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(9+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{366}{97600} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(9+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{366}{976000} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{(9+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1923. \quad & \frac{364}{924} := \frac{3+6+4}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{364}{9324} := \frac{3+6+4}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{364}{93324} := \frac{3+6+4}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{364}{933324} := \frac{3+6+4}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1928. \quad & \frac{366}{549} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{(5+4) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{366}{5490} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{(5+4) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{366}{54900} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{(5+4) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{366}{549000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{(5+4) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1933. \quad & \frac{368}{1472} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{368}{14720} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{368}{147200} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{368}{1472000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1924. \quad & \frac{366}{1098} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 09 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{366}{10980} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 09 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{366}{109800} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 09 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{366}{1098000} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 09 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1929. \quad & \frac{366}{610} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{366}{6100} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{366}{61000} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{366}{610000} := \frac{3 \times (6+6)}{6 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1934. \quad & \frac{368}{690} := \frac{36 \times 8}{6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{368}{6900} := \frac{36 \times 8}{6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{368}{69000} := \frac{36 \times 8}{6 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{368}{690000} := \frac{36 \times 8}{6 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1925. \quad & \frac{366}{1342} := \frac{3+6+6}{13+42} \\
 & \frac{366}{13542} := \frac{3+6+6}{13+542} \\
 & \frac{366}{135542} := \frac{3+6+6}{13+5542} \\
 & \frac{366}{1355542} := \frac{3+6+6}{13+55542}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1930. \quad & \frac{366}{671} := \frac{36+6}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{366}{6771} := \frac{36+6}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{366}{67771} := \frac{36+6}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{366}{677771} := \frac{36+6}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1935. \quad & \frac{368}{920} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{9 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{368}{9200} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{9 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{368}{92000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{9 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{368}{920000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 8}{9 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1926. \quad & \frac{366}{1464} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{366}{14640} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{366}{146400} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{366}{1464000} := \frac{3 \times 6 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1931. \quad & \frac{366}{915} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{9 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{366}{9150} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{9 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{366}{91500} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{9 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{366}{915000} := \frac{(3+6) \times 6}{9 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1936. \quad & \frac{369}{1230} := \frac{3+6+9}{1 \times 2 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{369}{12300} := \frac{3+6+9}{1 \times 2 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{369}{123000} := \frac{3+6+9}{1 \times 2 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{369}{1230000} := \frac{3+6+9}{1 \times 2 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1937. \quad & \frac{369}{1312} := \frac{3+6+9}{(1+31) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{369}{13120} := \frac{3+6+9}{(1+31) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{369}{131200} := \frac{3+6+9}{(1+31) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{369}{1312000} := \frac{3+6+9}{(1+31) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1942. \quad & \frac{369}{820} := \frac{3+69}{8 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{369}{8200} := \frac{3+69}{8 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{369}{82000} := \frac{3+69}{8 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{369}{820000} := \frac{3+69}{8 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1947. \quad & \frac{371}{1113} := \frac{3+7+1}{1 \times 11 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{371}{11130} := \frac{3+7+1}{1 \times 11 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{371}{111300} := \frac{3+7+1}{1 \times 11 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{371}{1113000} := \frac{3+7+1}{1 \times 11 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1938. \quad & \frac{369}{1353} := \frac{3+6+9}{13+53} \\
 & \frac{369}{13653} := \frac{3+6+9}{13+653} \\
 & \frac{369}{136653} := \frac{3+6+9}{13+6653} \\
 & \frac{369}{1366653} := \frac{3+6+9}{13+66653}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1943. \quad & \frac{370}{1221} := \frac{3+7+0}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{370}{12321} := \frac{3+7+0}{12+321} \\
 & \frac{370}{123321} := \frac{3+7+0}{12+3321} \\
 & \frac{370}{1233321} := \frac{3+7+0}{12+33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1948. \quad & \frac{371}{1166} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 66} \\
 & \frac{371}{11660} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 660} \\
 & \frac{371}{116600} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{371}{1166000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1939. \quad & \frac{369}{1435} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{(1+4) \times 35} \\
 & \frac{369}{14350} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{(1+4) \times 350} \\
 & \frac{369}{143500} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{369}{1435000} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{(1+4) \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1944. \quad & \frac{370}{407} := \frac{3+7+0}{4+07} \\
 & \frac{370}{4107} := \frac{3+7+0}{4+107} \\
 & \frac{370}{41107} := \frac{3+7+0}{4+1107} \\
 & \frac{370}{411107} := \frac{3+7+0}{4+11107}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1949. \quad & \frac{371}{1272} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^2 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{371}{12720} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^2 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{371}{127200} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^2 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{371}{1272000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^2 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1940. \quad & \frac{369}{1476} := \frac{3+69}{(1+47) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{369}{14760} := \frac{3+69}{(1+47) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{369}{147600} := \frac{3+69}{(1+47) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{369}{1476000} := \frac{3+69}{(1+47) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1945. \quad & \frac{370}{814} := \frac{3+7+0}{8+14} \\
 & \frac{370}{8214} := \frac{3+7+0}{8+214} \\
 & \frac{370}{82214} := \frac{3+7+0}{8+2214} \\
 & \frac{370}{822214} := \frac{3+7+0}{8+22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1950. \quad & \frac{371}{1325} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{371}{13250} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{371}{132500} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{371}{1325000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 3 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1941. \quad & \frac{369}{451} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+51} \\
 & \frac{369}{4551} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+551} \\
 & \frac{369}{45551} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+5551} \\
 & \frac{369}{455551} := \frac{3 \times (6+9)}{4+55551}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1946. \quad & \frac{371}{1060} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{371}{10600} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{371}{106000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 06000} \\
 & \frac{371}{1060000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1 \times 060000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1951. \quad & \frac{371}{1378} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^3 \times 78} \\
 & \frac{371}{13780} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^3 \times 780} \\
 & \frac{371}{137800} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^3 \times 7800} \\
 & \frac{371}{1378000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^3 \times 78000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1952. \quad \frac{371}{1484} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^4 \times 84}$$

$$\frac{371}{14840} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^4 \times 840}$$

$$\frac{371}{148400} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^4 \times 8400}$$

$$\frac{371}{1484000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{1^4 \times 84000}$$

$$1957. \quad \frac{372}{1395} := \frac{3 + 7^2}{1 \times 39 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{372}{13950} := \frac{3 + 7^2}{1 \times 39 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{372}{139500} := \frac{3 + 7^2}{1 \times 39 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{372}{1395000} := \frac{3 + 7^2}{1 \times 39 \times 5000}$$

$$1962. \quad \frac{375}{17875} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{178750} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{1787500} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{17875000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(17 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}$$

$$1953. \quad \frac{371}{424} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{(4 + 2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{371}{4240} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{(4 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{371}{42400} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{(4 + 2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{371}{424000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 1}{(4 + 2) \times 4000}$$

$$1958. \quad \frac{373}{1492} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 3}{14 \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{373}{14920} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 3}{14 \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{373}{149200} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 3}{14 \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{373}{1492000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 3}{14 \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$1963. \quad \frac{375}{18375} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{183750} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{1837500} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{18375000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(18 + 3) \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$1954. \quad \frac{371}{742} := \frac{3 + 71}{74 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{371}{7420} := \frac{3 + 71}{74 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{371}{74200} := \frac{3 + 71}{74 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{371}{742000} := \frac{3 + 71}{74 \times 2000}$$

$$1959. \quad \frac{375}{1250} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{1^2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{12500} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{1^2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{125000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{1^2 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{375}{1250000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{1^2 \times 50000}$$

$$1964. \quad \frac{375}{1875} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{18750} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{187500} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{1875000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 \times 8 + 7) \times 5000}$$

$$1955. \quad \frac{372}{1023} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{10 + 23}$$

$$\frac{372}{10323} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{10 + 323}$$

$$\frac{372}{103323} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{10 + 3323}$$

$$\frac{372}{1033323} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{10 + 33323}$$

$$1960. \quad \frac{375}{1625} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{16250} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{162500} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{1625000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{(1 + 6 \times 2) \times 5000}$$

$$1965. \quad \frac{375}{625} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5)}{6 \times 2 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{6250} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5)}{6 \times 2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{62500} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5)}{6 \times 2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{625000} := \frac{3 \times (7 + 5)}{6 \times 2 \times 5000}$$

$$1956. \quad \frac{372}{1240} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{1^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{372}{12400} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{1^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{372}{124000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{1^2 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{372}{1240000} := \frac{3 + 7 + 2}{1^2 \times 40000}$$

$$1961. \quad \frac{375}{16275} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 5}{1 \times 62 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{375}{162750} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 5}{1 \times 62 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{375}{1627500} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 5}{1 \times 62 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{375}{16275000} := \frac{(3 + 7) \times 5}{1 \times 62 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

$$1966. \quad \frac{375}{825} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{8 + 25}$$

$$\frac{375}{8325} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{8 + 325}$$

$$\frac{375}{83325} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{8 + 3325}$$

$$\frac{375}{833325} := \frac{3 + 7 + 5}{8 + 33325}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1967. \quad & \frac{376}{1034} := \frac{3+7+6}{10+34} \\
 & \frac{376}{10434} := \frac{3+7+6}{10+434} \\
 & \frac{376}{104434} := \frac{3+7+6}{10+4434} \\
 & \frac{376}{1044434} := \frac{3+7+6}{10+44434}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1972. \quad & \frac{377}{1160} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{377}{11600} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{377}{116000} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 16000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1977. \quad & \frac{378}{1050} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{378}{10500} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{378}{105000} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 05000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1968. \quad & \frac{376}{1269} := \frac{3+7+6}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{376}{12690} := \frac{3+7+6}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{376}{126900} := \frac{3+7+6}{1^2 \times 6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{376}{1269000} := \frac{3+7+6}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1973. \quad & \frac{377}{1421} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{14^2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{377}{14210} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{14^2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{377}{142100} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{14^2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{377}{1421000} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{14^2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1978. \quad & \frac{378}{1155} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 1 \times 55} \\
 & \frac{378}{11550} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 1 \times 550} \\
 & \frac{378}{115500} := \frac{3+7+8}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1969. \quad & \frac{376}{1551} := \frac{3+7+6}{15+51} \\
 & \frac{376}{15651} := \frac{3+7+6}{15+651} \\
 & \frac{376}{156651} := \frac{3+7+6}{15+6651} \\
 & \frac{376}{1566651} := \frac{3+7+6}{15+66651}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1974. \quad & \frac{377}{1450} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{377}{14500} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{377}{145000} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1979. \quad & \frac{378}{1260} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{378}{12600} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{378}{126000} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1970. \quad & \frac{376}{423} := \frac{3+7+6}{(4+2) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{376}{4230} := \frac{3+7+6}{(4+2) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{376}{42300} := \frac{3+7+6}{(4+2) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{376}{423000} := \frac{3+7+6}{(4+2) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1975. \quad & \frac{377}{435} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{4 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{377}{4350} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{4 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{377}{43500} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{4 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{377}{435000} := \frac{3+7 \times 7}{4 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1980. \quad & \frac{378}{1302} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{378}{13020} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{378}{130200} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{378}{1302000} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1971. \quad & \frac{376}{517} := \frac{3+7+6}{5+17} \\
 & \frac{376}{5217} := \frac{3+7+6}{5+217} \\
 & \frac{376}{52217} := \frac{3+7+6}{5+2217} \\
 & \frac{376}{522217} := \frac{3+7+6}{5+22217}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1976. \quad & \frac{377}{754} := \frac{(3+7) \times 7}{7 \times 5 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{377}{7540} := \frac{(3+7) \times 7}{7 \times 5 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{377}{75400} := \frac{(3+7) \times 7}{7 \times 5 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{377}{754000} := \frac{(3+7) \times 7}{7 \times 5 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1981. \quad & \frac{378}{1344} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{378}{13440} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{378}{134400} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{378}{1344000} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1982. \quad & \frac{378}{1365} := \frac{3 \times 78}{13 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{378}{13650} := \frac{3 \times 78}{13 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{378}{136500} := \frac{3 \times 78}{13 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{378}{1365000} := \frac{3 \times 78}{13 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1987. \quad & \frac{378}{648} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{6 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{378}{6480} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{6 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{378}{64800} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{6 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{378}{648000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{6 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1992. \quad & \frac{382}{764} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7+6) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{382}{7640} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7+6) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{382}{76400} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7+6) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{382}{764000} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 2}{(7+6) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1983. \quad & \frac{378}{1386} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1 \times 3+8) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{378}{13860} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1 \times 3+8) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{378}{138600} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1 \times 3+8) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{378}{1386000} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1 \times 3+8) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1988. \quad & \frac{378}{924} := \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{378}{9240} := \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{378}{92400} := \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{378}{924000} := \frac{3+7+8}{(9+2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1993. \quad & \frac{382}{9550} := \frac{3+8 \times 2}{95 \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \frac{382}{95500} := \frac{3+8 \times 2}{95 \times 50 + 0} \\
 & \frac{382}{955000} := \frac{3+8 \times 2}{95 \times 500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{382}{9550000} := \frac{3+8 \times 2}{95 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1984. \quad & \frac{378}{1470} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^4 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{378}{14700} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^4 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{378}{147000} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^4 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{378}{1470000} := \frac{3+7+8}{1^4 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1989. \quad & \frac{379}{758} := \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(7+5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{379}{7580} := \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(7+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{379}{75800} := \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(7+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{379}{758000} := \frac{3 \times (7+9)}{(7+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1994. \quad & \frac{384}{1332} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+332} \\
 & \frac{384}{13332} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+3332} \\
 & \frac{384}{133332} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+33332} \\
 & \frac{384}{1333332} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{1+333332}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1985. \quad & \frac{378}{1512} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5) \times 12} \\
 & \frac{378}{15120} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5) \times 120} \\
 & \frac{378}{151200} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5) \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{378}{1512000} := \frac{3+7+8}{(1+5) \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1990. \quad & \frac{381}{635} := \frac{3 \times (8+1)}{(6+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{381}{6350} := \frac{3 \times (8+1)}{(6+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{381}{63500} := \frac{3 \times (8+1)}{(6+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{381}{635000} := \frac{3 \times (8+1)}{(6+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1995. \quad & \frac{384}{396} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+96} \\
 & \frac{384}{3996} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+996} \\
 & \frac{384}{39996} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+9996} \\
 & \frac{384}{399996} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 4}{3+99996}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1986. \quad & \frac{378}{450} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{378}{4500} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{378}{45000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{378}{450000} := \frac{3 \times 7 \times 8}{4 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1991. \quad & \frac{382}{1146} := \frac{3 \times (8+2)}{(1+14) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{382}{11460} := \frac{3 \times (8+2)}{(1+14) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{382}{114600} := \frac{3 \times (8+2)}{(1+14) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{382}{1146000} := \frac{3 \times (8+2)}{(1+14) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1996. \quad & \frac{385}{1232} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 5}{12 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{385}{12320} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 5}{12 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{385}{123200} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 5}{12 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{385}{1232000} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 5}{12 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

1997.

$$\frac{385}{1260} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{385}{12600} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{385}{126000} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{385}{1260000} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(1+2) \times 60000}$$

2002.

$$\frac{386}{965} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 6}{(9+6) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{386}{9650} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 6}{(9+6) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{386}{96500} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 6}{(9+6) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{386}{965000} := \frac{3 \times 8 + 6}{(9+6) \times 5000}$$

2007.

$$\frac{392}{1120} := \frac{3+9+2}{(1+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{392}{11200} := \frac{3+9+2}{(1+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{392}{112000} := \frac{3+9+2}{(1+1) \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{392}{1120000} := \frac{3+9+2}{(1+1) \times 20000}$$

1998.

$$\frac{385}{448} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(4+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{385}{4480} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(4+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{385}{44800} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(4+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{385}{448000} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{(4+4) \times 8000}$$

2003.

$$\frac{388}{1164} := \frac{(3+8) \times 8}{11 \times 6 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{388}{11640} := \frac{(3+8) \times 8}{11 \times 6 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{388}{116400} := \frac{(3+8) \times 8}{11 \times 6 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{388}{1164000} := \frac{(3+8) \times 8}{11 \times 6 \times 4000}$$

2008.

$$\frac{392}{1176} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{392}{11760} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{392}{117600} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{392}{1176000} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

1999.

$$\frac{385}{462} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+62}$$

$$\frac{385}{4662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+662}$$

$$\frac{385}{46662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+6662}$$

$$\frac{385}{466662} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{4+66662}$$

2004.

$$\frac{388}{485} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 8}{48 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{388}{4850} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 8}{48 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{388}{48500} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 8}{48 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{388}{485000} := \frac{3 \times 8 \times 8}{48 \times 5000}$$

2009.

$$\frac{392}{1225} := \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+2) \times 25}$$

$$\frac{392}{12250} := \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+2) \times 250}$$

$$\frac{392}{122500} := \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+2) \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{392}{1225000} := \frac{(3+9) \times 2}{(1+2) \times 25000}$$

2000.

$$\frac{385}{693} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+93}$$

$$\frac{385}{6993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+993}$$

$$\frac{385}{69993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+9993}$$

$$\frac{385}{699993} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{6+99993}$$

2005.

$$\frac{390}{1365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+36+5}$$

$$\frac{390}{14365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+436+5}$$

$$\frac{390}{144365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+4436+5}$$

$$\frac{390}{1444365} := \frac{3+9+0}{1+44436+5}$$

2010.

$$\frac{392}{1232} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{392}{12432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{392}{124432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{392}{1244432} := \frac{3+9+2}{12+44432}$$

2001.

$$\frac{385}{735} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{7 \times 3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{385}{7350} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{7 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{385}{73500} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{7 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{385}{735000} := \frac{(3+8) \times 5}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

2006.

$$\frac{390}{715} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+15}$$

$$\frac{390}{7215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+215}$$

$$\frac{390}{72215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+2215}$$

$$\frac{390}{722215} := \frac{3+9+0}{7+22215}$$

2011.

$$\frac{392}{1344} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{392}{13440} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{392}{134400} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{392}{1344000} := \frac{3+9+2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2012. \quad & \frac{392}{1512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+51+2} \\
 & \frac{392}{15512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+551+2} \\
 & \frac{392}{155512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+5551+2} \\
 & \frac{392}{1555512} := \frac{3+9+2}{1+55551+2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2017. \quad & \frac{393}{917} := \frac{3+9 \times 3}{(9+1) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{393}{9170} := \frac{3+9 \times 3}{(9+1) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{393}{91700} := \frac{3+9 \times 3}{(9+1) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{393}{917000} := \frac{3+9 \times 3}{(9+1) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2022. \quad & \frac{396}{1452} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+52} \\
 & \frac{396}{14652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+652} \\
 & \frac{396}{146652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+6652} \\
 & \frac{396}{1466652} := \frac{3+9+6}{14+66652}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2013. \quad & \frac{392}{616} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{392}{6216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{392}{62216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{392}{622216} := \frac{3+9+2}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2018. \quad & \frac{396}{1221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{396}{12221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{396}{122221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+22221} \\
 & \frac{396}{1222221} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{1+222221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2023. \quad & \frac{396}{484} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+84} \\
 & \frac{396}{4884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+884} \\
 & \frac{396}{48884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+8884} \\
 & \frac{396}{488884} := \frac{(3+9) \times 6}{4+88884}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2014. \quad & \frac{393}{1048} := \frac{3+9+3}{(1+04) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{393}{10480} := \frac{3+9+3}{(1+04) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{393}{104800} := \frac{3+9+3}{(1+04) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{393}{1048000} := \frac{3+9+3}{(1+04) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2019. \quad & \frac{396}{1296} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{396}{12960} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{396}{129600} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{396}{1296000} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2024. \quad & \frac{396}{550} := \frac{3+9+6}{5 \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \frac{396}{5500} := \frac{3+9+6}{5 \times 50 + 0} \\
 & \frac{396}{55000} := \frac{3+9+6}{5 \times 500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{396}{550000} := \frac{3+9+6}{5 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2015. \quad & \frac{393}{1179} := \frac{39+3}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{393}{11790} := \frac{39+3}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{393}{117900} := \frac{39+3}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{393}{1179000} := \frac{39+3}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2020. \quad & \frac{396}{1320} := \frac{3+9+6}{1 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{396}{13200} := \frac{3+9+6}{1 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{396}{132000} := \frac{3+9+6}{1 \times 3 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{396}{1320000} := \frac{3+9+6}{1 \times 3 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2025. \quad & \frac{396}{726} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+26} \\
 & \frac{396}{7326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+326} \\
 & \frac{396}{73326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+3326} \\
 & \frac{396}{733326} := \frac{3+9+6}{7+33326}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2016. \quad & \frac{393}{1441} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+41} \\
 & \frac{393}{14541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+541} \\
 & \frac{393}{145541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+5541} \\
 & \frac{393}{1455541} := \frac{3+9+3}{14+55541}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2021. \quad & \frac{396}{1332} := \frac{3+96}{1+332} \\
 & \frac{396}{13332} := \frac{3+96}{1+3332} \\
 & \frac{396}{133332} := \frac{3+96}{1+33332} \\
 & \frac{396}{1333332} := \frac{3+96}{1+333332}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2026. \quad & \frac{396}{880} := \frac{3 \times 96}{8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{396}{8800} := \frac{3 \times 96}{8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{396}{88000} := \frac{3 \times 96}{8 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{396}{880000} := \frac{3 \times 96}{8 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2027. \quad & \frac{399}{1045} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{399}{10545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{399}{105545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{399}{1055545} := \frac{3+9+9}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2032. \quad & \frac{399}{418} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+18} \\
 & \frac{399}{4218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+218} \\
 & \frac{399}{42218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+2218} \\
 & \frac{399}{422218} := \frac{3+9+9}{4+22218}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2037. \quad & \frac{402}{1206} := \frac{4+0 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 06} \\
 & \frac{402}{12060} := \frac{4+0 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{402}{120600} := \frac{4+0 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{402}{1206000} := \frac{4+0 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 06000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2028. \quad & \frac{399}{1197} := \frac{3+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{399}{11970} := \frac{3+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{399}{119700} := \frac{3+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{399}{1197000} := \frac{3+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2033. \quad & \frac{399}{627} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{399}{6327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{399}{63327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{399}{633327} := \frac{3+9+9}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2038. \quad & \frac{402}{1407} := \frac{40 \times 2}{1 \times 40 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{402}{14070} := \frac{40 \times 2}{1 \times 40 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{402}{140700} := \frac{40 \times 2}{1 \times 40 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{402}{1407000} := \frac{40 \times 2}{1 \times 40 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2029. \quad & \frac{399}{1330} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(1+3) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{399}{13300} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(1+3) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{399}{133000} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(1+3) \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{399}{1330000} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(1+3) \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2034. \quad & \frac{399}{665} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(6+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{399}{6650} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(6+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{399}{66500} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(6+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{399}{665000} := \frac{3 \times 9 + 9}{(6+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2039. \quad & \frac{402}{804} := \frac{4^{02}}{8 \times 04} \\
 & \frac{402}{8040} := \frac{4^{02}}{8 \times 040} \\
 & \frac{402}{80400} := \frac{4^{02}}{8 \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{402}{804000} := \frac{4^{02}}{8 \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2030. \quad & \frac{399}{1368} := \frac{3+9 \times 9}{1 \times 36 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{399}{13680} := \frac{3+9 \times 9}{1 \times 36 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{399}{136800} := \frac{3+9 \times 9}{1 \times 36 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{399}{1368000} := \frac{3+9 \times 9}{1 \times 36 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2035. \quad & \frac{399}{836} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+36} \\
 & \frac{399}{8436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+436} \\
 & \frac{399}{84436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+4436} \\
 & \frac{399}{844436} := \frac{3+9+9}{8+44436}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2040. \quad & \frac{404}{1010} := \frac{4+0 \times 4}{1 \times (010)} \\
 & \frac{404}{10100} := \frac{4+0 \times 4}{1 \times (0100)} \\
 & \frac{404}{101000} := \frac{4+0 \times 4}{1 \times (01000)} \\
 & \frac{404}{1010000} := \frac{4+0 \times 4}{1 \times (010000)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2031. \quad & \frac{399}{1463} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{399}{14763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{399}{147763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{399}{1477763} := \frac{3+9+9}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2036. \quad & \frac{402}{1072} := \frac{4+02}{(1+07) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{402}{10720} := \frac{4+02}{(1+07) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{402}{107200} := \frac{4+02}{(1+07) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{402}{1072000} := \frac{4+02}{(1+07) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2041. \quad & \frac{404}{1111} := \frac{40+4}{11 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{404}{11110} := \frac{40+4}{11 \times 110} \\
 & \frac{404}{111100} := \frac{40+4}{11 \times 1100} \\
 & \frac{404}{1111000} := \frac{40+4}{11 \times 11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2042.

$$\frac{404}{1111} := \frac{4+04}{11+11}$$

$$\frac{404}{11211} := \frac{4+04}{11+211}$$

$$\frac{404}{112211} := \frac{4+04}{11+2211}$$

$$\frac{404}{1122211} := \frac{4+04}{11+22211}$$

2047.

$$\frac{405}{1134} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1+13) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{405}{11340} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1+13) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{405}{113400} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1+13) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{405}{1134000} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1+13) \times 4000}$$

2052.

$$\frac{405}{1440} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{405}{14400} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{405}{144000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{405}{1440000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}$$

2043.

$$\frac{404}{1212} := \frac{4+04}{1 \times 2 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{404}{12120} := \frac{4+04}{1 \times 2 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{404}{121200} := \frac{4+04}{1 \times 2 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{404}{1212000} := \frac{4+04}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}$$

2048.

$$\frac{405}{1197} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 19 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{405}{11970} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 19 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{405}{119700} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 19 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{405}{1197000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}$$

2053.

$$\frac{405}{1458} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{405}{14580} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{405}{145800} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{405}{1458000} := \frac{4 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 8000}$$

2044.

$$\frac{404}{1313} := \frac{4 \times 04}{(1+3) \times 13}$$

$$\frac{404}{13130} := \frac{4 \times 04}{(1+3) \times 130}$$

$$\frac{404}{131300} := \frac{4 \times 04}{(1+3) \times 1300}$$

$$\frac{404}{1313000} := \frac{4 \times 04}{(1+3) \times 13000}$$

2049.

$$\frac{405}{1215} := \frac{4 \times 05}{12 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{405}{12150} := \frac{4 \times 05}{12 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{405}{121500} := \frac{4 \times 05}{12 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{405}{1215000} := \frac{4 \times 05}{12 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

2054.

$$\frac{405}{1485} := \frac{40+5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{405}{14850} := \frac{40+5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{405}{148500} := \frac{40+5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{405}{1485000} := \frac{40+5}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}$$

2045.

$$\frac{404}{1414} := \frac{4 \times 04}{1 \times 4 \times 14}$$

$$\frac{404}{14140} := \frac{4 \times 04}{1 \times 4 \times 140}$$

$$\frac{404}{141400} := \frac{4 \times 04}{1 \times 4 \times 1400}$$

$$\frac{404}{1414000} := \frac{4 \times 04}{1 \times 4 \times 14000}$$

2050.

$$\frac{405}{1350} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{405}{13500} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{405}{135000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{405}{1350000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}$$

2055.

$$\frac{405}{1575} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{405}{15750} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{405}{157500} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{405}{1575000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

2046.

$$\frac{405}{1125} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 125}$$

$$\frac{405}{11250} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 1250}$$

$$\frac{405}{112500} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 12500}$$

$$\frac{405}{1125000} := \frac{40+5}{1 \times 125000}$$

2051.

$$\frac{405}{1368} := \frac{40+5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{405}{13680} := \frac{40+5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{405}{136800} := \frac{40+5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{405}{1368000} := \frac{40+5}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

2056.

$$\frac{405}{5850} := \frac{40+5}{(5+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{405}{58500} := \frac{40+5}{(5+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{405}{585000} := \frac{40+5}{(5+8) \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{405}{5850000} := \frac{40+5}{(5+8) \times 50000}$$

2057.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{405}{729} &:= \frac{40+5}{(7+2) \times 9} \\ \frac{405}{7290} &:= \frac{40+5}{(7+2) \times 90} \\ \frac{405}{72900} &:= \frac{40+5}{(7+2) \times 900} \\ \frac{405}{729000} &:= \frac{40+5}{(7+2) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2062.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{407}{1221} &:= \frac{4+07}{12+21} \\ \frac{407}{12321} &:= \frac{4+07}{12+321} \\ \frac{407}{123321} &:= \frac{4+07}{12+3321} \\ \frac{407}{1233321} &:= \frac{4+07}{12+33321} \end{aligned}$$

2067.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1292} &:= \frac{4+08}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2} \\ \frac{408}{12920} &:= \frac{4+08}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20} \\ \frac{408}{129200} &:= \frac{4+08}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200} \\ \frac{408}{1292000} &:= \frac{4+08}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2058.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{405}{891} &:= \frac{40+5}{8+91} \\ \frac{405}{8991} &:= \frac{40+5}{8+991} \\ \frac{405}{89991} &:= \frac{40+5}{8+9991} \\ \frac{405}{899991} &:= \frac{40+5}{8+99991} \end{aligned}$$

2063.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{407}{1480} &:= \frac{4+07}{(1+4) \times 8+0} \\ \frac{407}{14800} &:= \frac{4+07}{(1+4) \times 80+0} \\ \frac{407}{148000} &:= \frac{4+07}{(1+4) \times 800+0} \\ \frac{407}{1480000} &:= \frac{4+07}{(1+4) \times 8000+0} \end{aligned}$$

2068.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1326} &:= \frac{40+8}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\ \frac{408}{13260} &:= \frac{40+8}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \frac{408}{132600} &:= \frac{40+8}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\ \frac{408}{1326000} &:= \frac{40+8}{13 \times 2 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2059.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{406}{1015} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 6}{(1+01) \times 5} \\ \frac{406}{10150} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 6}{(1+01) \times 50} \\ \frac{406}{101500} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 6}{(1+01) \times 500} \\ \frac{406}{1015000} &:= \frac{4+0 \times 6}{(1+01) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2064.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1122} &:= \frac{4+08}{11+22} \\ \frac{408}{11322} &:= \frac{4+08}{11+322} \\ \frac{408}{113322} &:= \frac{4+08}{11+3322} \\ \frac{408}{1133322} &:= \frac{4+08}{11+33322} \end{aligned}$$

2069.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1428} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{1 \times 4 \times 28} \\ \frac{408}{14280} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{1 \times 4 \times 280} \\ \frac{408}{142800} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{1 \times 4 \times 2800} \\ \frac{408}{1428000} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{1 \times 4 \times 28000} \end{aligned}$$

2060.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{406}{1421} &:= \frac{4 \times 06}{1 \times 4 \times 21} \\ \frac{406}{14210} &:= \frac{4 \times 06}{1 \times 4 \times 210} \\ \frac{406}{142100} &:= \frac{4 \times 06}{1 \times 4 \times 2100} \\ \frac{406}{1421000} &:= \frac{4 \times 06}{1 \times 4 \times 21000} \end{aligned}$$

2065.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1224} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{12 \times 2 \times 4} \\ \frac{408}{12240} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{12 \times 2 \times 40} \\ \frac{408}{122400} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{12 \times 2 \times 400} \\ \frac{408}{1224000} &:= \frac{4 \times 08}{12 \times 2 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2070.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1734} &:= \frac{40+8}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\ \frac{408}{17340} &:= \frac{40+8}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\ \frac{408}{173400} &:= \frac{40+8}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\ \frac{408}{1734000} &:= \frac{40+8}{17 \times 3 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2061.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{407}{1184} &:= \frac{4+07}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{407}{11840} &:= \frac{4+07}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{407}{118400} &:= \frac{4+07}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{407}{1184000} &:= \frac{4+07}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2066.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{1275} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\ \frac{408}{12750} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\ \frac{408}{127500} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\ \frac{408}{1275000} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 2 \times 75000} \end{aligned}$$

2071.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{408}{17374} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\ \frac{408}{173740} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\ \frac{408}{1737400} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\ \frac{408}{17374000} &:= \frac{40+8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2072. \quad & \frac{408}{561} := \frac{40+8}{5+61} \\
 & \frac{408}{5661} := \frac{40+8}{5+661} \\
 & \frac{408}{56661} := \frac{40+8}{5+6661} \\
 & \frac{408}{566661} := \frac{40+8}{5+66661}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2077. \quad & \frac{408}{952} := \frac{4+08}{(9+5) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{408}{9520} := \frac{4+08}{(9+5) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{408}{95200} := \frac{4+08}{(9+5) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{408}{952000} := \frac{4+08}{(9+5) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2082. \quad & \frac{411}{1507} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+07} \\
 & \frac{411}{15207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+207} \\
 & \frac{411}{152207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+2207} \\
 & \frac{411}{1522207} := \frac{4+1+1}{15+22207}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2073. \quad & \frac{408}{595} := \frac{40+8}{(5+9) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{408}{5950} := \frac{40+8}{(5+9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{408}{59500} := \frac{40+8}{(5+9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{408}{595000} := \frac{40+8}{(5+9) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2078. \quad & \frac{409}{818} := \frac{4 \times 09}{(8+1) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{409}{8180} := \frac{4 \times 09}{(8+1) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{409}{81800} := \frac{4 \times 09}{(8+1) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{409}{818000} := \frac{4 \times 09}{(8+1) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2083. \quad & \frac{411}{685} := \frac{41+1}{(6+8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{411}{6850} := \frac{41+1}{(6+8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{411}{68500} := \frac{41+1}{(6+8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{411}{685000} := \frac{41+1}{(6+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2074. \quad & \frac{408}{612} := \frac{40+8}{6 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{408}{6120} := \frac{40+8}{6 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{408}{61200} := \frac{40+8}{6 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{408}{612000} := \frac{40+8}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2079. \quad & \frac{410}{1804} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+04} \\
 & \frac{410}{18204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+204} \\
 & \frac{410}{182204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+2204} \\
 & \frac{410}{1822204} := \frac{4+1+0}{18+22204}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2084. \quad & \frac{411}{822} := \frac{4^{1+1}}{8 \times 2 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{411}{8220} := \frac{4^{1+1}}{8 \times 2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{411}{82200} := \frac{4^{1+1}}{8 \times 2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{411}{822000} := \frac{4^{1+1}}{8 \times 2 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2075. \quad & \frac{408}{748} := \frac{40+8}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{408}{7480} := \frac{40+8}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{408}{74800} := \frac{40+8}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{408}{748000} := \frac{40+8}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2080. \quad & \frac{410}{902} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+02} \\
 & \frac{410}{9102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+102} \\
 & \frac{410}{91102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+1102} \\
 & \frac{410}{911102} := \frac{4+1+0}{9+11102}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2085. \quad & \frac{412}{1030} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 030} \\
 & \frac{412}{10300} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 0300} \\
 & \frac{412}{103000} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 03000} \\
 & \frac{412}{1030000} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 030000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2076. \quad & \frac{408}{918} := \frac{4 \times 08}{9 \times 1 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{408}{9180} := \frac{4 \times 08}{9 \times 1 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{408}{91800} := \frac{4 \times 08}{9 \times 1 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{408}{918000} := \frac{4 \times 08}{9 \times 1 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2081. \quad & \frac{411}{1233} := \frac{4+1+1}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{411}{12330} := \frac{4+1+1}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{411}{123300} := \frac{4+1+1}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{411}{1233000} := \frac{4+1+1}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2086. \quad & \frac{412}{1133} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 33} \\
 & \frac{412}{11330} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 330} \\
 & \frac{412}{113300} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 3300} \\
 & \frac{412}{1133000} := \frac{4 \times (1+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 33000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2087. \quad & \frac{412}{1133} := \frac{4+12}{11+33} \\
 & \frac{412}{11433} := \frac{4+12}{11+433} \\
 & \frac{114433}{412} := \frac{11+4433}{4+12} \\
 & \frac{114433}{412} := \frac{11+4433}{4+12} \\
 & \frac{1144433}{412} := \frac{11+44433}{4+12} \\
 & \frac{1144433}{1144433} := \frac{11+44433}{11+44433}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2092. \quad & \frac{413}{1239} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^2+3) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{413}{12390} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^2+3) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{413}{123900} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^2+3) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{413}{1239000} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 3}{(1^2+3) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2097. \quad & \frac{414}{1242} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{414}{12420} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{414}{124200} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{414}{1242000} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2088. \quad & \frac{412}{1236} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+23) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{412}{12360} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+23) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{412}{123600} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+23) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{412}{1236000} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+23) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2093. \quad & \frac{414}{1012} := \frac{4+1+4}{(10+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{414}{10120} := \frac{4+1+4}{(10+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{414}{101200} := \frac{4+1+4}{(10+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{414}{1012000} := \frac{4+1+4}{(10+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2098. \quad & \frac{414}{506} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+06} \\
 & \frac{414}{5106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+106} \\
 & \frac{414}{51106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+1106} \\
 & \frac{414}{511106} := \frac{4+1+4}{5+11106}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2089. \quad & \frac{412}{1339} := \frac{4 \times 12}{13 \times (3+9)} \\
 & \frac{412}{13390} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+3) \times 390} \\
 & \frac{412}{133900} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+3) \times 3900} \\
 & \frac{412}{1339000} := \frac{4 \times 12}{(1+3) \times 39000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2094. \quad & \frac{414}{1035} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+03) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{414}{10350} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+03) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{414}{103500} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+03) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{414}{1035000} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{(1+03) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2099. \quad & \frac{414}{621} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{6 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{414}{6210} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{6 \times 2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{414}{62100} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{6 \times 2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{414}{621000} := \frac{4+1 \times 4}{6 \times 2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2090. \quad & \frac{412}{1442} := \frac{4 \times 12}{1 \times 4 \times 42} \\
 & \frac{412}{14420} := \frac{4 \times 12}{1 \times 4 \times 420} \\
 & \frac{412}{144200} := \frac{4 \times 12}{1 \times 4 \times 4200} \\
 & \frac{412}{1442000} := \frac{4 \times 12}{1 \times 4 \times 42000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2095. \quad & \frac{414}{1150} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{414}{11500} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{414}{115000} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 1 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{414}{1150000} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2100. \quad & \frac{414}{828} := \frac{4^{1 \times 4}}{8^2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{414}{8280} := \frac{4^{1 \times 4}}{8^2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{414}{82800} := \frac{4^{1 \times 4}}{8^2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{414}{828000} := \frac{4^{1 \times 4}}{8^2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2091. \quad & \frac{412}{721} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 2}{7 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{412}{7210} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 2}{7 \times 2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{412}{72100} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 2}{7 \times 2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{412}{721000} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 2}{7 \times 2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2096. \quad & \frac{414}{1173} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{414}{11730} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{414}{117300} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{414}{1173000} := \frac{4+14}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2101. \quad & \frac{415}{1162} := \frac{4+1^5}{(1 \times 1+6) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{415}{11620} := \frac{4+1^5}{(1 \times 1+6) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{415}{116200} := \frac{4+1^5}{(1 \times 1+6) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{415}{1162000} := \frac{4+1^5}{(1 \times 1+6) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2106. \quad & \frac{415}{913} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+13} \\
 & \frac{415}{9213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+213} \\
 & \frac{415}{92213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+2213} \\
 & \frac{415}{922213} := \frac{4+1+5}{9+22213}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2111. \quad & \frac{416}{1456} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{416}{14560} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{416}{145600} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{416}{1456000} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2102. \quad & \frac{415}{1245} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{415}{12450} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{415}{124500} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{415}{1245000} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2107. \quad & \frac{416}{1144} := \frac{4 \times 16}{11 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{416}{11440} := \frac{4 \times 16}{11 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{416}{114400} := \frac{4 \times 16}{11 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{416}{1144000} := \frac{4 \times 16}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2112. \quad & \frac{416}{728} := \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{416}{7280} := \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{416}{72800} := \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{416}{728000} := \frac{4 \times 16}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2103. \quad & \frac{415}{1328} := \frac{4+1^5}{1^3 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{415}{13280} := \frac{4+1^5}{1^3 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{415}{132800} := \frac{4+1^5}{1^3 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{415}{1328000} := \frac{4+1^5}{1^3 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2108. \quad & \frac{416}{1144} := \frac{4+16}{11+44} \\
 & \frac{416}{11544} := \frac{4+16}{11+544} \\
 & \frac{416}{115544} := \frac{4+16}{11+5544} \\
 & \frac{416}{1155544} := \frac{4+16}{11+55544}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2113. \quad & \frac{416}{832} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{416}{8320} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{416}{83200} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{416}{832000} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 6}{8 \times 3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2104. \quad & \frac{415}{1826} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+26} \\
 & \frac{415}{18426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+426} \\
 & \frac{415}{184426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+4426} \\
 & \frac{415}{1844426} := \frac{4+1+5}{18+44426}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2109. \quad & \frac{416}{1248} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 24 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{416}{12480} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 24 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{416}{124800} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 24 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{416}{1248000} := \frac{4 \times 16}{1 \times 24 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2114. \quad & \frac{417}{1251} := \frac{4+1 \times 7}{(1+2^5) \times 1} \\
 & \frac{417}{12510} := \frac{4+1 \times 7}{(1+2^5) \times 10} \\
 & \frac{417}{125100} := \frac{4+1 \times 7}{(1+2^5) \times 100} \\
 & \frac{417}{1251000} := \frac{4+1 \times 7}{(1+2^5) \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2105. \quad & \frac{412}{5150} := \frac{4+1 \times 2}{5 \times 15+0} \\
 & \frac{412}{51500} := \frac{4+1 \times 2}{5 \times 150+0} \\
 & \frac{412}{515000} := \frac{4+1 \times 2}{5 \times 1500+0} \\
 & \frac{412}{5150000} := \frac{4+1 \times 2}{5 \times 15000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2110. \quad & \frac{416}{1352} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 52} \\
 & \frac{416}{13520} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 520} \\
 & \frac{416}{135200} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 5200} \\
 & \frac{416}{1352000} := \frac{4 \times 16}{(1+3) \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2115. \quad & \frac{417}{1529} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+29} \\
 & \frac{417}{15429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+429} \\
 & \frac{417}{154429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+4429} \\
 & \frac{417}{1544429} := \frac{4+1+7}{15+44429}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2116. \quad & \frac{418}{1045} := \frac{4+18}{10+45} \\
 & \frac{418}{10545} := \frac{4+18}{10+545} \\
 & \frac{418}{105545} := \frac{4+18}{10+5545} \\
 & \frac{418}{1055545} := \frac{4+18}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2121. \quad & \frac{418}{1463} := \frac{4 \times 18}{1 \times 4 \times 63} \\
 & \frac{418}{14630} := \frac{4 \times 18}{1 \times 4 \times 630} \\
 & \frac{418}{146300} := \frac{4 \times 18}{1 \times 4 \times 6300}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2126. \quad & \frac{418}{627} := \frac{4+18}{6+27} \\
 & \frac{418}{6327} := \frac{4+18}{6+327} \\
 & \frac{418}{63327} := \frac{4+18}{6+3327} \\
 & \frac{418}{633327} := \frac{4+18}{6+33327}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2117. \quad & \frac{418}{1197} := \frac{4+18}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{418}{11970} := \frac{4+18}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{418}{119700} := \frac{4+18}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{418}{1197000} := \frac{4+18}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2122. \quad & \frac{418}{1463} := \frac{4+18}{14+63} \\
 & \frac{418}{14763} := \frac{4+18}{14+763} \\
 & \frac{418}{147763} := \frac{4+18}{14+7763} \\
 & \frac{418}{1477763} := \frac{4+18}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2127. \quad & \frac{418}{836} := \frac{4 \times 18}{8 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{418}{8360} := \frac{4 \times 18}{8 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{418}{83600} := \frac{4 \times 18}{8 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{418}{836000} := \frac{4 \times 18}{8 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2118. \quad & \frac{418}{1254} := \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 54} \\
 & \frac{418}{12540} := \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 540} \\
 & \frac{418}{125400} := \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 5400} \\
 & \frac{418}{1254000} := \frac{4 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 54000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2123. \quad & \frac{418}{1672} := \frac{4+18}{16+72} \\
 & \frac{418}{16872} := \frac{4+18}{16+872} \\
 & \frac{418}{168872} := \frac{4+18}{16+8872} \\
 & \frac{418}{1688872} := \frac{4+18}{16+88872}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2128. \quad & \frac{418}{836} := \frac{4+18}{8+36} \\
 & \frac{418}{8436} := \frac{4+18}{8+436} \\
 & \frac{418}{84436} := \frac{4+18}{8+4436} \\
 & \frac{418}{844436} := \frac{4+18}{8+44436}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2119. \quad & \frac{418}{1254} := \frac{4+18}{12+54} \\
 & \frac{418}{12654} := \frac{4+18}{12+654} \\
 & \frac{418}{126654} := \frac{4+18}{12+6654} \\
 & \frac{418}{1266654} := \frac{4+18}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2124. \quad & \frac{418}{1881} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8}{18 \times 8 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{418}{18810} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8}{18 \times 8 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{418}{188100} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8}{18 \times 8 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{418}{1881000} := \frac{4 \times 1 \times 8}{18 \times 8 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2129. \quad & \frac{419}{1257} := \frac{4+1+9}{(1^2+5) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{419}{12570} := \frac{4+1+9}{(1^2+5) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{419}{125700} := \frac{4+1+9}{(1^2+5) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{419}{1257000} := \frac{4+1+9}{(1^2+5) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2120. \quad & \frac{418}{1368} := \frac{4+18}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{418}{13680} := \frac{4+18}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{418}{136800} := \frac{4+18}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{418}{1368000} := \frac{4+18}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2125. \quad & \frac{418}{1881} := \frac{4+18}{18+81} \\
 & \frac{418}{18981} := \frac{4+18}{18+981} \\
 & \frac{418}{189981} := \frac{4+18}{18+9981}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2130. \quad & \frac{420}{1155} := \frac{4+20}{11+55} \\
 & \frac{420}{11655} := \frac{4+20}{11+655} \\
 & \frac{420}{116655} := \frac{4+20}{11+6655}
 \end{aligned}$$

2131.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{420}{1225} &:= \frac{4+20}{(12+2) \times 5} \\ \frac{420}{12250} &:= \frac{4+20}{(12+2) \times 50} \\ \frac{420}{122500} &:= \frac{4+20}{(12+2) \times 500} \\ \frac{420}{1225000} &:= \frac{4+20}{(12+2) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2136.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{422}{633} &:= \frac{(4+2)^2}{6 \times 3 \times 3} \\ \frac{422}{6330} &:= \frac{(4+2)^2}{6 \times 3 \times 30} \\ \frac{422}{63300} &:= \frac{(4+2)^2}{6 \times 3 \times 300} \\ \frac{422}{633000} &:= \frac{(4+2)^2}{6 \times 3 \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

2141.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1269} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9} \\ \frac{423}{12690} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90} \\ \frac{423}{126900} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{1^2 \times 6 \times 900} \\ \frac{423}{1269000} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2132.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{421}{1263} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 3} \\ \frac{421}{12630} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 30} \\ \frac{421}{126300} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 300} \\ \frac{421}{1263000} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 1}{1^2 \times 6 \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

2137.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{422}{844} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2)^2}{8 \times 4 \times 4} \\ \frac{422}{8440} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2)^2}{8 \times 4 \times 40} \\ \frac{422}{84400} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2)^2}{8 \times 4 \times 400} \\ \frac{422}{844000} &:= \frac{(4 \times 2)^2}{8 \times 4 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2142.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1316} &:= \frac{4+23}{(13+1) \times 6} \\ \frac{423}{13160} &:= \frac{4+23}{(13+1) \times 60} \\ \frac{423}{131600} &:= \frac{4+23}{(13+1) \times 600} \\ \frac{423}{1316000} &:= \frac{4+23}{(13+1) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2133.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{421}{842} &:= \frac{4 \times 21}{84 \times 2} \\ \frac{421}{8420} &:= \frac{4 \times 21}{84 \times 20} \\ \frac{421}{84200} &:= \frac{4 \times 21}{84 \times 200} \\ \frac{421}{842000} &:= \frac{4 \times 21}{84 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2138.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1034} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+34} \\ \frac{423}{10434} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+434} \\ \frac{423}{104434} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+4434} \\ \frac{423}{1044434} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{10+44434} \end{aligned}$$

2143.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1410} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 10} \\ \frac{423}{14100} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 100} \\ \frac{423}{141000} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 1000} \\ \frac{423}{1410000} &:= \frac{4+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

2134.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{422}{1266} &:= \frac{42+2}{1 \times 2 \times 66} \\ \frac{422}{12660} &:= \frac{42+2}{1 \times 2 \times 660} \\ \frac{422}{126600} &:= \frac{42+2}{1 \times 2 \times 6600} \\ \frac{422}{1266000} &:= \frac{42+2}{1 \times 2 \times 66000} \end{aligned}$$

2139.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1128} &:= \frac{4^2 \times 3}{1 \times 128} \\ \frac{423}{11280} &:= \frac{4^2 \times 3}{1 \times 1280} \\ \frac{423}{112800} &:= \frac{4^2 \times 3}{1 \times 12800} \\ \frac{423}{1128000} &:= \frac{4^2 \times 3}{1 \times 128000} \end{aligned}$$

2144.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1551} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+51} \\ \frac{423}{15651} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+651} \\ \frac{423}{156651} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+6651} \\ \frac{423}{1566651} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{15+66651} \end{aligned}$$

2135.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{422}{1477} &:= \frac{4 \times 22}{1 \times 4 \times 77} \\ \frac{422}{14770} &:= \frac{4 \times 22}{1 \times 4 \times 770} \\ \frac{422}{147700} &:= \frac{4 \times 22}{1 \times 4 \times 7700} \\ \frac{422}{1477000} &:= \frac{4 \times 22}{1 \times 4 \times 77000} \end{aligned}$$

2140.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{1175} &:= \frac{4+23}{1 \times 1 \times 75} \\ \frac{423}{11750} &:= \frac{4+23}{1 \times 1 \times 750} \\ \frac{423}{117500} &:= \frac{4+23}{1 \times 1 \times 7500} \\ \frac{423}{1175000} &:= \frac{4+23}{1 \times 1 \times 75000} \end{aligned}$$

2145.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{517} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+17} \\ \frac{423}{5217} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+217} \\ \frac{423}{52217} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+2217} \\ \frac{423}{522217} &:= \frac{(4+2) \times 3}{5+22217} \end{aligned}$$

2150.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1166} &:= \frac{4+24}{11+66} \\ \frac{424}{11766} &:= \frac{4+24}{11+766} \\ \frac{424}{117766} &:= \frac{4+24}{11+7766} \end{aligned}$$

2155.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{530} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 4}{5 \times 3+0} \\ \frac{424}{5300} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 4}{5 \times 30+0} \\ \frac{424}{53000} &:= \frac{4+2 \times 4}{5 \times 300+0} \end{aligned}$$

2146.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{5640} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{5 \times 64+0} \\ \frac{423}{56400} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{5 \times 6400+0} \\ \frac{423}{564000} &:= \frac{4 \times 2 \times 3}{5 \times 64000+0} \end{aligned}$$

2151.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1272} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1^2 \times 72} \\ \frac{424}{12720} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1^2 \times 720} \\ \frac{424}{127200} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1^2 \times 7200} \end{aligned}$$

2156.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{583} &:= \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5+83} \\ \frac{424}{5883} &:= \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5+883} \\ \frac{424}{58883} &:= \frac{4 \times 2^4}{5+8883} \end{aligned}$$

2147.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{423}{987} &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times 8 \times 7} \\ \frac{423}{9870} &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times 8 \times 70} \\ \frac{423}{98700} &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times 8 \times 700} \\ \frac{423}{987000} &:= \frac{(4+2)^3}{9 \times 8 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

2152.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1325} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 25} \\ \frac{424}{13250} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 250} \\ \frac{424}{132500} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 2500} \end{aligned}$$

2157.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{742} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 42} \\ \frac{424}{7420} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 420} \\ \frac{424}{74200} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 4200} \end{aligned}$$

2148.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1060} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 060} \\ \frac{424}{10600} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 0600} \\ \frac{424}{106000} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 06000} \end{aligned}$$

2153.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1378} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{(1+3) \times 78} \\ \frac{424}{13780} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{(1+3) \times 780} \\ \frac{424}{137800} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{(1+3) \times 7800} \end{aligned}$$

2158.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{795} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 9 \times 5} \\ \frac{424}{7950} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 9 \times 50} \\ \frac{424}{79500} &:= \frac{42 \times 4}{7 \times 9 \times 500} \end{aligned}$$

2149.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1166} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 66} \\ \frac{424}{11660} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 660} \\ \frac{424}{116600} &:= \frac{4 \times (2+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 6600} \end{aligned}$$

2154.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{424}{1484} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{1 \times 4 \times 84} \\ \frac{424}{14840} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{1 \times 4 \times 840} \\ \frac{424}{148400} &:= \frac{4 \times 24}{1 \times 4 \times 8400} \end{aligned}$$

2159.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{425}{1224} &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{12 \times 24} \\ \frac{425}{12240} &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{12 \times 240} \\ \frac{425}{122400} &:= \frac{4 \times 25}{12 \times 2400} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2160. \quad & \frac{425}{12750} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{12 \times 75 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{127500} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{12 \times 750 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{1275000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{12 \times 7500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{12750000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{12 \times 75000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2165. \quad & \frac{426}{1491} := \frac{(4+2) \times 6}{14 \times 9 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{426}{14910} := \frac{(4+2) \times 6}{14 \times 9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{426}{149100} := \frac{(4+2) \times 6}{14 \times 9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{426}{1491000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 6}{14 \times 9 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2170. \quad & \frac{428}{1177} := \frac{4+28}{11+77} \\
 & \frac{428}{11877} := \frac{4+28}{11+877} \\
 & \frac{428}{118877} := \frac{4+28}{11+8877} \\
 & \frac{428}{1188877} := \frac{4+28}{11+88877}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2161. \quad & \frac{425}{1428} := \frac{4 \times 25}{1 \times 42 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{425}{14280} := \frac{4 \times 25}{1 \times 42 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{425}{142800} := \frac{4 \times 25}{1 \times 42 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{425}{1428000} := \frac{4 \times 25}{1 \times 42 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2166. \quad & \frac{426}{781} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 6}{7+81} \\
 & \frac{426}{7881} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 6}{7+881} \\
 & \frac{426}{78881} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 6}{7+8881} \\
 & \frac{426}{788881} := \frac{4 \times 2 \times 6}{7+88881}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2171. \quad & \frac{428}{1391} := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1+3) \times 91} \\
 & \frac{428}{13910} := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1+3) \times 910} \\
 & \frac{428}{139100} := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1+3) \times 9100} \\
 & \frac{428}{1391000} := \frac{4 \times 28}{(1+3) \times 91000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2162. \quad & \frac{425}{680} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{6 \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{6800} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{6 \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{68000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{6 \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{425}{680000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 5}{6 \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2167. \quad & \frac{427}{610} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{6 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{427}{6100} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{6 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{427}{61000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{6 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{427}{610000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{6 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2172. \quad & \frac{428}{535} := \frac{4+28}{(5+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{428}{5350} := \frac{4+28}{(5+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{428}{53500} := \frac{4+28}{(5+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{428}{535000} := \frac{4+28}{(5+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2163. \quad & \frac{426}{1065} := \frac{4+2+6}{1 \times 06 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{426}{10650} := \frac{4+2+6}{1 \times 06 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{426}{106500} := \frac{4+2+6}{1 \times 06 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{426}{1065000} := \frac{4+2+6}{1 \times 06 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2168. \quad & \frac{427}{671} := \frac{42+7}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{427}{6771} := \frac{42+7}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{427}{67771} := \frac{42+7}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{427}{677771} := \frac{42+7}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2173. \quad & \frac{428}{642} := \frac{4+28}{6 \times 4 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{428}{6420} := \frac{4+28}{6 \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{428}{64200} := \frac{4+28}{6 \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{428}{642000} := \frac{4+28}{6 \times 4 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2164. \quad & \frac{426}{1420} := \frac{4+26}{(1+4) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{426}{14200} := \frac{4+26}{(1+4) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{426}{142000} := \frac{4+26}{(1+4) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{426}{1420000} := \frac{4+26}{(1+4) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2169. \quad & \frac{427}{976} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{(9+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{427}{9760} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{(9+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{427}{97600} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{(9+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{427}{976000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 7}{(9+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2174. \quad & \frac{428}{963} := \frac{4^2 \times 8}{96 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{428}{9630} := \frac{4^2 \times 8}{96 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{428}{96300} := \frac{4^2 \times 8}{96 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{428}{963000} := \frac{4^2 \times 8}{96 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2175. \quad & \frac{429}{1144} := \frac{(4+2) \times 9}{1 \times 144} \\
 & \frac{429}{11440} := \frac{(4+2) \times 9}{1 \times 1440} \\
 & \frac{429}{114400} := \frac{(4+2) \times 9}{1 \times 14400} \\
 & \frac{429}{1144000} := \frac{(4+2) \times 9}{1 \times 144000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2180. \quad & \frac{431}{1293} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(1+2+9) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{431}{12930} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(1+2+9) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{431}{129300} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(1+2+9) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{431}{1293000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 1}{(1+2+9) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2185. \quad & \frac{432}{648} := \frac{4 \times 32}{6 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{432}{6480} := \frac{4 \times 32}{6 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{432}{64800} := \frac{4 \times 32}{6 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{432}{648000} := \frac{4 \times 32}{6 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2176. \quad & \frac{429}{1248} := \frac{4+2 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{429}{12480} := \frac{4+2 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{429}{124800} := \frac{4+2 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{429}{1248000} := \frac{4+2 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2181. \quad & \frac{432}{1152} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{432}{11520} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(1+1)^5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{432}{115200} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(1+1)^5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{432}{1152000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 2}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2186. \quad & \frac{433}{1299} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 3}{(1+2+9) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{433}{12990} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 3}{(1+2+9) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{433}{129900} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 3}{(1+2+9) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{433}{1299000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 3}{(1+2+9) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2177. \quad & \frac{429}{1287} := \frac{4+29}{12+87} \\
 & \frac{429}{12987} := \frac{4+29}{12+987} \\
 & \frac{429}{129987} := \frac{4+29}{12+9987} \\
 & \frac{429}{1299987} := \frac{4+29}{12+99987}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2182. \quad & \frac{432}{1188} := \frac{4+32}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{432}{11988} := \frac{4+32}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{432}{119988} := \frac{4+32}{11+9988} \\
 & \frac{432}{1199988} := \frac{4+32}{11+99988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2187. \quad & \frac{434}{1116} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1+11) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{434}{11160} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1+11) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{434}{111600} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1+11) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{434}{1116000} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1+11) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2178. \quad & \frac{429}{624} := \frac{4+29}{6 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{429}{6240} := \frac{4+29}{6 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{429}{62400} := \frac{4+29}{6 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{429}{624000} := \frac{4+29}{6 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2183. \quad & \frac{432}{1296} := \frac{4+32}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{432}{12960} := \frac{4+32}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{432}{129600} := \frac{4+32}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{432}{1296000} := \frac{4+32}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2188. \quad & \frac{434}{1240} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{434}{12400} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{434}{124000} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{434}{1240000} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2179. \quad & \frac{429}{858} := \frac{4+29}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{429}{8658} := \frac{4+29}{8+658} \\
 & \frac{429}{86658} := \frac{4+29}{8+6658} \\
 & \frac{429}{866658} := \frac{4+29}{8+66658}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2184. \quad & \frac{432}{1344} := \frac{4+3+2}{(1 \times 3+4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{432}{13440} := \frac{4+3+2}{(1 \times 3+4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{432}{134400} := \frac{4+3+2}{(1 \times 3+4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{432}{1344000} := \frac{4+3+2}{(1 \times 3+4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2189. \quad & \frac{434}{1488} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{434}{14880} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{434}{148800} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{434}{1488000} := \frac{4 \times (3+4)}{(1 \times 4+8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2190. \quad & \frac{435}{1160} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{435}{11600} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{435}{116000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 16000} \\
 & \frac{435}{1160000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 160000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2195. \quad & \frac{436}{1199} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\
 & \frac{436}{11990} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\
 & \frac{436}{119900} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\
 & \frac{436}{1199000} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2200. \quad & \frac{438}{1095} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+09) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{438}{10950} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+09) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{438}{109500} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+09) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{438}{1095000} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 8}{(1+09) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2191. \quad & \frac{435}{1218} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{435}{12180} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{435}{121800} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{435}{1218000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 21 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2196. \quad & \frac{436}{545} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{(5+4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{436}{5450} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{(5+4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{436}{54500} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{(5+4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{436}{545000} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{(5+4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2201. \quad & \frac{438}{1168} := \frac{43+8}{(1+16) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{438}{11680} := \frac{43+8}{(1+16) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{438}{116800} := \frac{43+8}{(1+16) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{438}{1168000} := \frac{43+8}{(1+16) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2192. \quad & \frac{435}{1421} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{14^2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{435}{14210} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{14^2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{435}{142100} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{14^2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{435}{1421000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{14^2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2197. \quad & \frac{436}{763} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{7 \times 6 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{436}{7630} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{7 \times 6 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{436}{76300} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{7 \times 6 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{436}{763000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 6}{7 \times 6 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2202. \quad & \frac{438}{1460} := \frac{4^3+8}{1 \times 4 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{438}{14600} := \frac{4^3+8}{1 \times 4 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{438}{146000} := \frac{4^3+8}{1 \times 4 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{438}{1460000} := \frac{4^3+8}{1 \times 4 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2193. \quad & \frac{435}{1450} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{435}{14500} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{435}{145000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{435}{1450000} := \frac{4 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2198. \quad & \frac{437}{1150} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{437}{11500} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{437}{115000} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 1 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{437}{1150000} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2203. \quad & \frac{440}{1155} := \frac{4+4+0}{1+15+5} \\
 & \frac{440}{12155} := \frac{4+4+0}{1+215+5} \\
 & \frac{440}{122155} := \frac{4+4+0}{1+2215+5} \\
 & \frac{440}{1222155} := \frac{4+4+0}{1+22215+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2194. \quad & \frac{436}{1090} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{436}{10900} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{436}{109000} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{436}{1090000} := \frac{4 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2199. \quad & \frac{437}{1173} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{437}{11730} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{437}{117300} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{437}{1173000} := \frac{4 \times 3 + 7}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2204. \quad & \frac{440}{1815} := \frac{4+4+0}{18+15} \\
 & \frac{440}{18315} := \frac{4+4+0}{18+315} \\
 & \frac{440}{183315} := \frac{4+4+0}{18+3315} \\
 & \frac{440}{1833315} := \frac{4+4+0}{18+33315}
 \end{aligned}$$

2205.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{440}{605} &:= \frac{4+4+0}{6+05} \\ \frac{440}{6105} &:= \frac{4+4+0}{6+105} \\ \frac{440}{61105} &:= \frac{4+4+0}{6+1105} \\ \frac{440}{611105} &:= \frac{4+4+0}{6+11105} \end{aligned}$$

2206.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{441}{1225} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{(1+2^2) \times 5} \\ \frac{441}{12250} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{(1+2^2) \times 50} \\ \frac{441}{122500} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{(1+2^2) \times 500} \\ \frac{441}{1225000} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{(1+2^2) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2207.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{441}{1323} &:= \frac{4+4 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 2 \times 3} \\ \frac{441}{13230} &:= \frac{4+4 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 2 \times 30} \\ \frac{441}{132300} &:= \frac{4+4 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 2 \times 300} \\ \frac{441}{1323000} &:= \frac{4+4 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 2 \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

2208.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{441}{1617} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{16+17} \\ \frac{441}{16317} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{16+317} \\ \frac{441}{163317} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{16+3317} \\ \frac{441}{1633317} &:= \frac{4+4+1}{16+33317} \end{aligned}$$

2209.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{441}{882} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 1}{(8+8) \times 2} \\ \frac{441}{8820} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 1}{(8+8) \times 20} \\ \frac{441}{88200} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 1}{(8+8) \times 200} \\ \frac{441}{882000} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 1}{(8+8) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2210.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{442}{1105} &:= \frac{4+4^2}{1 \times 10 \times 5} \\ \frac{442}{11050} &:= \frac{4+4^2}{1 \times 10 \times 50} \\ \frac{442}{110500} &:= \frac{4+4^2}{1 \times 10 \times 500} \\ \frac{442}{1105000} &:= \frac{4+4^2}{1 \times 10 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2211.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{442}{663} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+2)}{(6+6) \times 3} \\ \frac{442}{6630} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+2)}{(6+6) \times 30} \\ \frac{442}{66300} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+2)}{(6+6) \times 300} \\ \frac{442}{663000} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+2)}{(6+6) \times 3000} \end{aligned}$$

2212.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{442}{884} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 2}{(8+8) \times 4} \\ \frac{442}{8840} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 2}{(8+8) \times 40} \\ \frac{442}{88400} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 2}{(8+8) \times 400} \\ \frac{442}{884000} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 2}{(8+8) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2213.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{443}{1329} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+3)^2 \times 9} \\ \frac{443}{13290} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+3)^2 \times 90} \\ \frac{443}{132900} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+3)^2 \times 900} \\ \frac{443}{1329000} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+3)^2 \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2214.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{443}{886} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(8+8) \times 6} \\ \frac{443}{8860} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(8+8) \times 60} \\ \frac{443}{88600} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(8+8) \times 600} \\ \frac{443}{886000} &:= \frac{4 \times 4 \times 3}{(8+8) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2215.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{444}{1184} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{444}{11840} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{444}{118400} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{444}{1184000} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2216.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{444}{1221} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{12+21} \\ \frac{444}{12321} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{12+321} \\ \frac{444}{123321} &:= \frac{4+4+4}{12+3321} \end{aligned}$$

2217.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{444}{1258} &:= \frac{4+44}{(12+5) \times 8} \\ \frac{444}{12580} &:= \frac{4+44}{(12+5) \times 80} \\ \frac{444}{125800} &:= \frac{4+44}{(12+5) \times 800} \\ \frac{444}{1258000} &:= \frac{4+44}{(12+5) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2218.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{444}{1332} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 32} \\ \frac{444}{13320} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 320} \\ \frac{444}{133200} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 3200} \\ \frac{444}{1332000} &:= \frac{4 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 32000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2219. \quad & \frac{444}{1480} := \frac{4+4+4}{(1+4) \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{444}{14800} := \frac{4+4+4}{(1+4) \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{444}{148000} := \frac{4+4+4}{(1+4) \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{444}{1480000} := \frac{4+4+4}{(1+4) \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2224. \quad & \frac{446}{1115} := \frac{(4 \times 4)+6}{1 \times 11 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{446}{11150} := \frac{(4 \times 4)+6}{1 \times 11 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{446}{111500} := \frac{(4 \times 4)+6}{1 \times 11 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{446}{1115000} := \frac{(4 \times 4)+6}{1 \times 11 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2229. \quad & \frac{448}{1176} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{448}{11760} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{448}{117600} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{448}{1176000} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2220. \quad & \frac{444}{666} := \frac{4+44}{(6+6) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{444}{6660} := \frac{4+44}{(6+6) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{444}{66600} := \frac{4+44}{(6+6) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{444}{666000} := \frac{4+44}{(6+6) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2225. \quad & \frac{447}{1192} := \frac{4+4+7}{(1+19) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{447}{11920} := \frac{4+4+7}{(1+19) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{447}{119200} := \frac{4+4+7}{(1+19) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{447}{1192000} := \frac{4+4+7}{(1+19) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2230. \quad & \frac{448}{1260} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{448}{12600} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{448}{126000} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+2) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{448}{1260000} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+2) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2221. \quad & \frac{444}{814} := \frac{4+4+4}{8+14} \\
 & \frac{444}{8214} := \frac{4+4+4}{8+214} \\
 & \frac{444}{82214} := \frac{4+4+4}{8+2214} \\
 & \frac{444}{822214} := \frac{4+4+4}{8+22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2226. \quad & \frac{447}{1639} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+39} \\
 & \frac{447}{16539} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+539} \\
 & \frac{447}{165539} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+5539} \\
 & \frac{447}{1655539} := \frac{4+4+7}{16+55539}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2231. \quad & \frac{448}{1344} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{448}{13440} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{448}{134400} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{448}{1344000} := \frac{4+4+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2222. \quad & \frac{444}{888} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 4}{(8+8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{444}{8880} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 4}{(8+8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{444}{88800} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 4}{(8+8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{444}{888000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 4}{(8+8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2227. \quad & \frac{447}{894} := \frac{(4 \times 4)^7}{8^9 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{447}{8940} := \frac{(4 \times 4)^7}{8^9 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{447}{89400} := \frac{(4 \times 4)^7}{8^9 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{447}{894000} := \frac{(4 \times 4)^7}{8^9 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2223. \quad & \frac{445}{979} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+79} \\
 & \frac{445}{9879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+879} \\
 & \frac{445}{98879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+8879} \\
 & \frac{445}{988879} := \frac{(4+4) \times 5}{9+88879}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2228. \quad & \frac{448}{1120} := \frac{4+4+8}{(1+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{448}{11200} := \frac{4+4+8}{(1+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{448}{112000} := \frac{4+4+8}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{448}{1120000} := \frac{4+4+8}{(1+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2232. \quad & \frac{448}{1365} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{13 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{448}{13650} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{13 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{448}{136500} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{13 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{448}{1365000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{13 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2233. \quad & \frac{448}{1400} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{448}{14000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{448}{140000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 40000} \\
 & \frac{448}{1400000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{1 \times 400000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2238. \quad & \frac{448}{560} := \frac{4 \times 4 + 8}{5 \times 6 + 0} \\
 & \frac{448}{5600} := \frac{4 \times 4 + 8}{5 \times 60 + 0} \\
 & \frac{448}{56000} := \frac{4 \times 4 + 8}{5 \times 600 + 0} \\
 & \frac{448}{560000} := \frac{4 \times 4 + 8}{5 \times 6000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2243. \quad & \frac{451}{1353} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{451}{13530} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{451}{135300} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{451}{1353000} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 1}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2234. \quad & \frac{448}{14336} := \frac{4 + 4 \times 8}{1 \times 4^3 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{448}{143360} := \frac{4 + 4 \times 8}{1 \times 4^3 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{448}{1433600} := \frac{4 + 4 \times 8}{1 \times 4^3 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{448}{14336000} := \frac{4 + 4 \times 8}{1 \times 4^3 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2239. \quad & \frac{448}{616} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{6 + 16} \\
 & \frac{448}{6216} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{6 + 216} \\
 & \frac{448}{62216} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{6 + 2216} \\
 & \frac{448}{622216} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{6 + 22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2244. \quad & \frac{451}{1435} := \frac{4 + 51}{(1+4) \times 35} \\
 & \frac{451}{14350} := \frac{4 + 51}{(1+4) \times 350} \\
 & \frac{451}{143500} := \frac{4 + 51}{(1+4) \times 3500} \\
 & \frac{451}{1435000} := \frac{4 + 51}{(1+4) \times 35000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2235. \quad & \frac{448}{1848} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{448}{18480} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{448}{184800} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{448}{1848000} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{(1+8 \times 4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2240. \quad & \frac{448}{630} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{6 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{448}{6300} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{6 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{448}{63000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{6 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{448}{630000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{6 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2245. \quad & \frac{451}{902} := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{9 \times 02} \\
 & \frac{451}{9020} := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{9 \times 020} \\
 & \frac{451}{90200} := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{9 \times 0200} \\
 & \frac{451}{902000} := \frac{4 + 5 \times 1}{9 \times 02000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2236. \quad & \frac{448}{1848} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{18 + 48} \\
 & \frac{448}{18648} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{18 + 648} \\
 & \frac{448}{186648} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{18 + 6648} \\
 & \frac{448}{1866648} := \frac{4 + 4 + 8}{18 + 66648}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2241. \quad & \frac{448}{693} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6 + 93} \\
 & \frac{448}{6993} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6 + 993} \\
 & \frac{448}{69993} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6 + 9993} \\
 & \frac{448}{699993} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{6 + 99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2246. \quad & \frac{452}{1356} := \frac{4 + 52}{1 \times 3 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{452}{13560} := \frac{4 + 52}{1 \times 3 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{452}{135600} := \frac{4 + 52}{1 \times 3 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{452}{1356000} := \frac{4 + 52}{1 \times 3 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2237. \quad & \frac{448}{462} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4 + 62} \\
 & \frac{448}{4662} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4 + 662} \\
 & \frac{448}{46662} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4 + 6662} \\
 & \frac{448}{466662} := \frac{(4+4) \times 8}{4 + 66662}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2242. \quad & \frac{448}{784} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{448}{7840} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{448}{78400} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{448}{784000} := \frac{4 \times 4 \times 8}{7 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2247. \quad & \frac{452}{904} := \frac{(4+5) \times 2}{9 \times 04} \\
 & \frac{452}{9040} := \frac{(4+5) \times 2}{9 \times 040} \\
 & \frac{452}{90400} := \frac{(4+5) \times 2}{9 \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{452}{904000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 2}{9 \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2248. \quad & \frac{453}{1208} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 20 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{453}{12080} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 20 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{453}{120800} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 20 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{453}{1208000} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 20 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2253. \quad & \frac{455}{1274} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+27) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{455}{12740} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+27) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{455}{127400} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+27) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{455}{1274000} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+27) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2258. \quad & \frac{455}{819} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{8 \times 1 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{455}{8190} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{8 \times 1 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{455}{81900} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{8 \times 1 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{455}{819000} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{8 \times 1 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2249. \quad & \frac{453}{1359} := \frac{45+3}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{453}{13590} := \frac{45+3}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{453}{135900} := \frac{45+3}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{453}{1359000} := \frac{45+3}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2254. \quad & \frac{455}{1365} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{455}{13650} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{455}{136500} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{455}{1365000} := \frac{4 \times (5+5)}{(1+3) \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2259. \quad & \frac{455}{910} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{455}{9100} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{455}{91000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{9 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{455}{910000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2250. \quad & \frac{453}{906} := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{9 \times 06} \\
 & \frac{453}{9060} := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{9 \times 060} \\
 & \frac{453}{90600} := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{9 \times 0600} \\
 & \frac{453}{906000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 3}{9 \times 06000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2255. \quad & \frac{455}{546} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 4 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{455}{5460} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 4 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{455}{54600} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 4 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{455}{546000} := \frac{4 \times 5 \times 5}{5 \times 4 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2260. \quad & \frac{456}{912} := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{456}{9120} := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{456}{91200} := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{456}{912000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 6}{9 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2251. \quad & \frac{454}{1362} := \frac{4+5 \times 4}{1 \times 36 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{454}{13620} := \frac{4+5 \times 4}{1 \times 36 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{454}{136200} := \frac{4+5 \times 4}{1 \times 36 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{454}{1362000} := \frac{4+5 \times 4}{1 \times 36 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2256. \quad & \frac{455}{637} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(6+3) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{455}{6370} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(6+3) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{455}{63700} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(6+3) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{455}{637000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(6+3) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2261. \quad & \frac{457}{914} := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{9 \times 14} \\
 & \frac{457}{9140} := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{9 \times 140} \\
 & \frac{457}{91400} := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{9 \times 1400} \\
 & \frac{457}{914000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 7}{9 \times 14000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2252. \quad & \frac{454}{908} := \frac{4 \times (5+4)}{9 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{454}{9080} := \frac{4 \times (5+4)}{9 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{454}{90800} := \frac{4 \times (5+4)}{9 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{454}{908000} := \frac{4 \times (5+4)}{9 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2257. \quad & \frac{455}{728} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(7+2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{455}{7280} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(7+2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{455}{72800} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(7+2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{455}{728000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 5}{(7+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2262. \quad & \frac{458}{1145} := \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 14 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{458}{11450} := \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 14 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{458}{114500} := \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 14 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{458}{1145000} := \frac{4 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 14 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2263.

$$\frac{458}{916} := \frac{(4+5) \times 8}{9 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{458}{9160} := \frac{(4+5) \times 8}{9 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{458}{91600} := \frac{(4+5) \times 8}{9 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{458}{916000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 8}{9 \times 16000}$$

2268.

$$\frac{459}{1360} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{459}{13600} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{459}{136000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+3) \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{459}{1360000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+3) \times 60000}$$

2273.

$$\frac{459}{17374} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{459}{173740} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{459}{1737400} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{459}{17374000} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}$$

2264.

$$\frac{459}{1122} := \frac{4+5+9}{11 \times 2 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{459}{11220} := \frac{4+5+9}{11 \times 2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{459}{112200} := \frac{4+5+9}{11 \times 2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{459}{1122000} := \frac{4+5+9}{11 \times 2 \times 2000}$$

2269.

$$\frac{459}{1377} := \frac{4+5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{459}{13770} := \frac{4+5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{459}{137700} := \frac{4+5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{459}{1377000} := \frac{4+5 \times 9}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 7000}$$

2274.

$$\frac{459}{561} := \frac{45+9}{5+61}$$

$$\frac{459}{5661} := \frac{45+9}{5+661}$$

$$\frac{459}{56661} := \frac{45+9}{5+6661}$$

$$\frac{459}{566661} := \frac{45+9}{5+66661}$$

2265.

$$\frac{459}{1224} := \frac{4+5+9}{1 \times 2 \times 24}$$

$$\frac{459}{12240} := \frac{4+5+9}{1 \times 2 \times 240}$$

$$\frac{459}{122400} := \frac{4+5+9}{1 \times 2 \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{459}{1224000} := \frac{4+5+9}{1 \times 2 \times 24000}$$

2270.

$$\frac{459}{1428} := \frac{4+5+9}{(1+4+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{459}{14280} := \frac{4+5+9}{(1+4+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{459}{142800} := \frac{4+5+9}{(1+4+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{459}{1428000} := \frac{4+5+9}{(1+4+2) \times 8000}$$

2275.

$$\frac{459}{595} := \frac{45+9}{5 \times (9+5)}$$

$$\frac{459}{5950} := \frac{45+9}{(5+9) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{459}{59500} := \frac{45+9}{(5+9) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{459}{595000} := \frac{45+9}{(5+9) \times 5000}$$

2266.

$$\frac{459}{1275} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 2 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{459}{12750} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 2 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{459}{127500} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 2 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{459}{1275000} := \frac{45+9}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}$$

2271.

$$\frac{459}{1479} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{459}{14790} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{459}{147900} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{459}{1479000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{(1+4 \times 7) \times 9000}$$

2276.

$$\frac{459}{612} := \frac{45+9}{6 \times 12}$$

$$\frac{459}{6120} := \frac{45+9}{6 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{459}{61200} := \frac{45+9}{6 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{459}{612000} := \frac{45+9}{6 \times 12000}$$

2267.

$$\frac{459}{1326} := \frac{45+9}{13 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{459}{13260} := \frac{45+9}{13 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{459}{132600} := \frac{45+9}{13 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{459}{1326000} := \frac{45+9}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

2272.

$$\frac{459}{1734} := \frac{45+9}{17 \times 3 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{459}{17340} := \frac{45+9}{17 \times 3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{459}{173400} := \frac{45+9}{17 \times 3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{459}{1734000} := \frac{45+9}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}$$

2277.

$$\frac{459}{714} := \frac{4+5+9}{7 \times 1 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{459}{7140} := \frac{4+5+9}{7 \times 1 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{459}{71400} := \frac{4+5+9}{7 \times 1 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{459}{714000} := \frac{4+5+9}{7 \times 1 \times 4000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2278. \quad & \frac{459}{748} := \frac{45+9}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{459}{7480} := \frac{45+9}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{459}{74800} := \frac{45+9}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{459}{748000} := \frac{45+9}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2283. \quad & \frac{462}{1155} := \frac{4 \times (6+2)}{(1+15) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{462}{11550} := \frac{4 \times (6+2)}{(1+15) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{462}{115500} := \frac{4 \times (6+2)}{(1+15) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{462}{1155000} := \frac{4 \times (6+2)}{(1+15) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2288. \quad & \frac{462}{735} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{462}{7350} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{462}{73500} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{462}{735000} := \frac{4+62}{7 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2279. \quad & \frac{459}{918} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{9 \times 18} \\
 & \frac{459}{9180} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{9 \times 180} \\
 & \frac{459}{91800} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{9 \times 1800} \\
 & \frac{459}{918000} := \frac{(4+5) \times 9}{9 \times 18000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2284. \quad & \frac{462}{1232} := \frac{4 \times 6^2}{12 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{462}{12320} := \frac{4 \times 6^2}{12 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{462}{123200} := \frac{4 \times 6^2}{12 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{462}{1232000} := \frac{4 \times 6^2}{12 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2289. \quad & \frac{465}{1023} := \frac{4+6+5}{10+23} \\
 & \frac{465}{10323} := \frac{4+6+5}{10+323} \\
 & \frac{465}{103323} := \frac{4+6+5}{10+3323} \\
 & \frac{465}{1033323} := \frac{4+6+5}{10+33323}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2280. \quad & \frac{460}{1012} := \frac{4+6+0}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{460}{10212} := \frac{4+6+0}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{460}{102212} := \frac{4+6+0}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{460}{1022212} := \frac{4+6+0}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2285. \quad & \frac{462}{1260} := \frac{4+62}{(1+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{462}{12600} := \frac{4+62}{(1+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{462}{126000} := \frac{4+62}{(1+2) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{462}{1260000} := \frac{4+62}{(1+2) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2290. \quad & \frac{465}{1240} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{465}{12400} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{465}{124000} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{465}{1240000} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2281. \quad & \frac{460}{506} := \frac{4+6+0}{5+06} \\
 & \frac{460}{5106} := \frac{4+6+0}{5+106} \\
 & \frac{460}{51106} := \frac{4+6+0}{5+1106} \\
 & \frac{460}{511106} := \frac{4+6+0}{5+11106}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2286. \quad & \frac{462}{1365} := \frac{4+62}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{462}{13650} := \frac{4+62}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{462}{136500} := \frac{4+62}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{462}{1365000} := \frac{4+62}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2291. \quad & \frac{465}{1395} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^3 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{465}{13950} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^3 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{465}{139500} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^3 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{465}{1395000} := \frac{4+6+5}{1^3 \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2282. \quad & \frac{461}{922} := \frac{4+6+1}{(9+2) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{461}{9220} := \frac{4+6+1}{(9+2) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{461}{92200} := \frac{4+6+1}{(9+2) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{461}{922000} := \frac{4+6+1}{(9+2) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2287. \quad & \frac{462}{693} := \frac{4+62}{6+93} \\
 & \frac{462}{6993} := \frac{4+62}{6+993} \\
 & \frac{462}{69993} := \frac{4+62}{6+9993} \\
 & \frac{462}{699993} := \frac{4+62}{6+99993}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2292. \quad & \frac{465}{1488} := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 48 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{465}{14880} := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 48 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{465}{148800} := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 48 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{465}{1488000} := \frac{4 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 48 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{466}{932} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 \times 6}{9 \times 32} \\
 \frac{466}{9320} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 \times 6}{9 \times 320} \\
 \frac{466}{93200} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 \times 6}{9 \times 3200} \\
 \frac{466}{932000} &:= \frac{4 \times 6 \times 6}{9 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1197} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 \frac{468}{11970} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 \frac{468}{119700} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 \frac{468}{1197000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1440} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 \frac{468}{14400} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 \frac{468}{144000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\
 \frac{468}{1440000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1040} &:= \frac{4 + 6 + 8}{1 \times 040} \\
 \frac{468}{10400} &:= \frac{4 + 6 + 8}{1 \times 0400} \\
 \frac{468}{104000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 + 8}{1 \times 04000} \\
 \frac{468}{1040000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 + 8}{1 \times 040000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1248} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 24 \times 8} \\
 \frac{468}{12480} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 24 \times 80} \\
 \frac{468}{124800} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 24 \times 800} \\
 \frac{468}{1248000} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 24 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1456} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 4 \times 56} \\
 \frac{468}{14560} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 4 \times 560} \\
 \frac{468}{145600} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 4 \times 5600} \\
 \frac{468}{1456000} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1125} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 125} \\
 \frac{468}{11250} &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times 8)}{1 \times 1250} \\
 \frac{468}{112500} &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times 8)}{1 \times 12500} \\
 \frac{468}{1125000} &:= \frac{4 + (6 \times 8)}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1350} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 \frac{468}{13500} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 \frac{468}{135000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 \frac{468}{1350000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1485} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 + 4 \times 8} \times 5 \\
 \frac{468}{14850} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 + 4 \times 8} \times 50 \\
 \frac{468}{148500} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 + 4 \times 8} \times 500 \\
 \frac{468}{1485000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{1 + 4 \times 8} \times 5000
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1144} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{11 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 \frac{468}{11440} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{11 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 \frac{468}{114400} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{11 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 \frac{468}{1144000} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1352} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 52} \\
 \frac{468}{13520} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 520} \\
 \frac{468}{135200} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 5200} \\
 \frac{468}{1352000} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{1 \times 3 \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{676} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{(6 + 7) \times 6} \\
 \frac{468}{6760} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{(6 + 7) \times 60} \\
 \frac{468}{67600} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{(6 + 7) \times 600} \\
 \frac{468}{676000} &:= \frac{46 + 8}{(6 + 7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1170} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 8)}{(1 + 1) \times 70} \\
 \frac{468}{11700} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 8)}{(1 + 1) \times 700} \\
 \frac{468}{117000} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 8)}{(1 + 1) \times 7000} \\
 \frac{468}{1170000} &:= \frac{4 \times (6 + 8)}{(1 + 1) \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{1368} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 \frac{468}{13680} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 \frac{468}{136800} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 \frac{468}{1368000} &:= \frac{4 + 6 \times 8}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{468}{728} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{7 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 \frac{468}{7280} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{7 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 \frac{468}{72800} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{7 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 \frac{468}{728000} &:= \frac{4 + 68}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2308.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{468}{729} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(7+2) \times 9} \\ \frac{468}{7290} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(7+2) \times 90} \\ \frac{468}{72900} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(7+2) \times 900} \\ \frac{468}{729000} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{(7+2) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2309.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{468}{891} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{8+91} \\ \frac{468}{8991} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{8+991} \\ \frac{468}{89991} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{8+9991} \\ \frac{468}{899991} &:= \frac{4+6 \times 8}{8+99991} \end{aligned}$$

2310.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{471}{1727} &:= \frac{4+7+1}{17+27} \\ \frac{471}{17427} &:= \frac{4+7+1}{17+427} \\ \frac{471}{174427} &:= \frac{4+7+1}{17+4427} \\ \frac{471}{1744427} &:= \frac{4+7+1}{17+44427} \end{aligned}$$

2311.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{471}{628} &:= \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 8} \\ \frac{471}{6280} &:= \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 80} \\ \frac{471}{62800} &:= \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 800} \\ \frac{471}{628000} &:= \frac{47+1}{(6+2) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2312.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{472}{1416} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 2}{(14+1) \times 6} \\ \frac{472}{14160} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 2}{(14+1) \times 60} \\ \frac{472}{141600} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 2}{(14+1) \times 600} \\ \frac{472}{1416000} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 + 2}{(14+1) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2313.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{472}{1475} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 5} \\ \frac{472}{14750} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 50} \\ \frac{472}{147500} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 500} \\ \frac{472}{1475000} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2314.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{472}{590} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+2)}{5 \times 9 + 0} \\ \frac{472}{5900} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+2)}{5 \times 90 + 0} \\ \frac{472}{59000} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+2)}{5 \times 900 + 0} \\ \frac{472}{590000} &:= \frac{4 \times (7+2)}{5 \times 9000 + 0} \end{aligned}$$

2315.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{472}{767} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(7+6) \times 7} \\ \frac{472}{7670} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(7+6) \times 70} \\ \frac{472}{76700} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(7+6) \times 700} \\ \frac{472}{767000} &:= \frac{4 \times 7 \times 2}{(7+6) \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

2316.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{473}{1290} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{1^2 \times 90} \\ \frac{473}{12900} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{1^2 \times 900} \\ \frac{473}{129000} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{1^2 \times 9000} \\ \frac{473}{1290000} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{1^2 \times 90000} \end{aligned}$$

2317.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{473}{516} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{(5+1) \times 6} \\ \frac{473}{5160} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{(5+1) \times 60} \\ \frac{473}{51600} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{(5+1) \times 600} \\ \frac{473}{516000} &:= \frac{(4+7) \times 3}{(5+1) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2318.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{474}{1185} &:= \frac{4+7 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 5} \\ \frac{474}{11850} &:= \frac{4+7 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 50} \\ \frac{474}{118500} &:= \frac{4+7 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 500} \\ \frac{474}{1185000} &:= \frac{4+7 \times 4}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2319.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{474}{1738} &:= \frac{4+7+4}{17+38} \\ \frac{474}{17538} &:= \frac{4+7+4}{17+538} \\ \frac{474}{175538} &:= \frac{4+7+4}{17+5538} \\ \frac{474}{1755538} &:= \frac{4+7+4}{17+55538} \end{aligned}$$

2320.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{475}{798} &:= \frac{4 \times 75}{7 \times 9 \times 8} \\ \frac{475}{7980} &:= \frac{4 \times 75}{7 \times 9 \times 80} \\ \frac{475}{79800} &:= \frac{4 \times 75}{7 \times 9 \times 800} \\ \frac{475}{798000} &:= \frac{4 \times 75}{7 \times 9 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2321.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{476}{1120} &:= \frac{4+7+6}{(1+1) \times 20} \\ \frac{476}{11200} &:= \frac{4+7+6}{(1+1) \times 200} \\ \frac{476}{112000} &:= \frac{4+7+6}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\ \frac{476}{1120000} &:= \frac{4+7+6}{(1+1) \times 20000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2322. \quad & \frac{476}{1176} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{476}{11760} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{476}{117600} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{476}{1176000} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2327. \quad & \frac{477}{1125} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{477}{11250} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{477}{112500} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 12500}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2332. \quad & \frac{477}{1378} := \frac{4+77}{1 \times 3 \times 78} \\
 & \frac{477}{13780} := \frac{4+77}{1 \times 3 \times 780} \\
 & \frac{477}{137800} := \frac{4+77}{1 \times 3 \times 7800}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2323. \quad & \frac{476}{1344} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{476}{13440} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{476}{134400} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{476}{1344000} := \frac{4+7+6}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2328. \quad & \frac{477}{1197} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{477}{11970} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{477}{119700} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{477}{1197000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2333. \quad & \frac{477}{1440} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{477}{14400} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{477}{144000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2324. \quad & \frac{476}{1848} := \frac{4+7+6}{18+48} \\
 & \frac{476}{18648} := \frac{4+7+6}{18+648} \\
 & \frac{476}{186648} := \frac{4+7+6}{18+6648} \\
 & \frac{476}{1866648} := \frac{4+7+6}{18+66648}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2329. \quad & \frac{477}{1325} := \frac{4+7+7}{(1+3^2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{477}{13250} := \frac{4+7+7}{(1+3^2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{477}{132500} := \frac{4+7+7}{(1+3^2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{477}{1325000} := \frac{4+7+7}{(1+3^2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2334. \quad & \frac{477}{1485} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{477}{14850} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{477}{148500} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{477}{1485000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2325. \quad & \frac{476}{616} := \frac{4+7+6}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{476}{6216} := \frac{4+7+6}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{476}{62216} := \frac{4+7+6}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{476}{622216} := \frac{4+7+6}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2330. \quad & \frac{477}{1350} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{477}{13500} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{477}{135000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2335. \quad & \frac{477}{1749} := \frac{4+7+7}{17+49} \\
 & \frac{477}{17649} := \frac{4+7+7}{17+649} \\
 & \frac{477}{176649} := \frac{4+7+7}{17+6649} \\
 & \frac{477}{1766649} := \frac{4+7+7}{17+66649}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2326. \quad & \frac{476}{924} := \frac{4+7+6}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{476}{9324} := \frac{4+7+6}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{476}{93324} := \frac{4+7+6}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{476}{933324} := \frac{4+7+6}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2331. \quad & \frac{477}{1368} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{477}{13680} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{477}{136800} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{477}{1368000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2336. \quad & \frac{477}{585} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(5+8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{477}{5850} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(5+8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{477}{58500} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(5+8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{477}{585000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(5+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2337. \quad & \frac{477}{636} := \frac{4+77}{6 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{477}{6360} := \frac{4+77}{6 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{477}{63600} := \frac{4+77}{6 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{477}{636000} := \frac{4+77}{6 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2342. \quad & \frac{479}{958} := \frac{47+9}{(9+5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{479}{9580} := \frac{47+9}{(9+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{479}{95800} := \frac{47+9}{(9+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{479}{958000} := \frac{47+9}{(9+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2347. \quad & \frac{482}{1446} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{482}{14460} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{482}{144600} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{482}{1446000} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 2}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2338. \quad & \frac{477}{729} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(7+2) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{477}{7290} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(7+2) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{477}{72900} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(7+2) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{477}{729000} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{(7+2) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2343. \quad & \frac{480}{1485} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{14 + 85} \\
 & \frac{480}{14985} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{14 + 985} \\
 & \frac{480}{149985} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{14 + 9985} \\
 & \frac{480}{1499985} := \frac{4 \times 8 + 0}{14 + 99985}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2348. \quad & \frac{482}{723} := \frac{(4+8)^2}{72 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{482}{7230} := \frac{(4+8)^2}{72 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{482}{72300} := \frac{(4+8)^2}{72 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{482}{723000} := \frac{(4+8)^2}{72 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2339. \quad & \frac{477}{848} := \frac{47+7}{(8+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{477}{8480} := \frac{47+7}{(8+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{477}{84800} := \frac{47+7}{(8+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{477}{848000} := \frac{47+7}{(8+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2344. \quad & \frac{481}{1221} := \frac{4+8+1}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{481}{12321} := \frac{4+8+1}{12+321} \\
 & \frac{481}{123321} := \frac{4+8+1}{12+3321} \\
 & \frac{481}{1233321} := \frac{4+8+1}{12+33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2349. \quad & \frac{483}{1127} := \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{1 \times 12 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{483}{11270} := \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{1 \times 12 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{483}{112700} := \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{1 \times 12 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{483}{1127000} := \frac{(4+8) \times 3}{1 \times 12 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2340. \quad & \frac{477}{891} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{8+91} \\
 & \frac{477}{8991} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{8+991} \\
 & \frac{477}{89991} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{8+9991} \\
 & \frac{477}{899991} := \frac{4+7 \times 7}{8+99991}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2345. \quad & \frac{481}{814} := \frac{4+8+1}{8+14} \\
 & \frac{481}{8214} := \frac{4+8+1}{8+214} \\
 & \frac{481}{82214} := \frac{4+8+1}{8+2214} \\
 & \frac{481}{822214} := \frac{4+8+1}{8+22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2341. \quad & \frac{478}{1195} := \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{478}{11950} := \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{478}{119500} := \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{478}{1195000} := \frac{4 \times 7 + 8}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2346. \quad & \frac{482}{1205} := \frac{4 \times (8+2)}{1 \times 20 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{482}{12050} := \frac{4 \times (8+2)}{1 \times 20 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{482}{120500} := \frac{4 \times (8+2)}{1 \times 20 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{482}{1205000} := \frac{4 \times (8+2)}{1 \times 20 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2350. \quad & \frac{483}{1288} := \frac{4+83}{(1+28) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{483}{12880} := \frac{4+83}{(1+28) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{483}{128800} := \frac{4+83}{(1+28) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{483}{1288000} := \frac{4+83}{(1+28) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2351. \quad & \frac{483}{1380} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{1^3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{483}{13800} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{1^3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{483}{138000} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{1^3 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{483}{1380000} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{1^3 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2356. \quad & \frac{484}{1221} := \frac{4+84}{1+221} \\
 & \frac{484}{12221} := \frac{4+84}{1+2221} \\
 & \frac{484}{122221} := \frac{4+84}{1+22221} \\
 & \frac{484}{1222221} := \frac{4+84}{1+222221}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2361. \quad & \frac{486}{1188} := \frac{48 \times 6}{11 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{486}{11880} := \frac{48 \times 6}{11 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{486}{118800} := \frac{48 \times 6}{11 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{486}{1188000} := \frac{48 \times 6}{11 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2352. \quad & \frac{483}{1449} := \frac{48+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{483}{14490} := \frac{48+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{483}{144900} := \frac{48+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{483}{1449000} := \frac{48+3}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2357. \quad & \frac{484}{1331} := \frac{4+8+4}{13+31} \\
 & \frac{484}{13431} := \frac{4+8+4}{13+431} \\
 & \frac{484}{134431} := \frac{4+8+4}{13+4431} \\
 & \frac{484}{1344431} := \frac{4+8+4}{13+44431}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2362. \quad & \frac{486}{1197} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{486}{11970} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{486}{119700} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{486}{1197000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2353. \quad & \frac{483}{621} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{483}{6210} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{483}{62100} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{483}{621000} := \frac{4+8 \times 3}{6^2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2358. \quad & \frac{484}{726} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{484}{7260} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{484}{72600} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{484}{726000} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(7+2) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2363. \quad & \frac{486}{1215} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{12 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{486}{12150} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{12 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{486}{121500} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{12 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{486}{1215000} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{12 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2354. \quad & \frac{484}{1089} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(1+08) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{484}{10890} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(1+08) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{484}{108900} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(1+08) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{484}{1089000} := \frac{4+8 \times 4}{(1+08) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2359. \quad & \frac{484}{847} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 4}{8 \times 4 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{484}{8470} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 4}{8 \times 4 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{484}{84700} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 4}{8 \times 4 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{484}{847000} := \frac{4 \times 8 \times 4}{8 \times 4 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2364. \quad & \frac{486}{1296} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{486}{12960} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{486}{129600} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{486}{1296000} := \frac{(4+8) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2355. \quad & \frac{484}{1210} := \frac{4 \times (8+4)}{12 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{484}{12100} := \frac{4 \times (8+4)}{12 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{484}{121000} := \frac{4 \times (8+4)}{12 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{484}{1210000} := \frac{4 \times (8+4)}{12 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2360. \quad & \frac{486}{1125} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{486}{11250} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{486}{112500} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{486}{1125000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2365. \quad & \frac{486}{1350} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{486}{13500} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{486}{135000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{486}{1350000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2366. \quad & \frac{486}{1368} := \frac{48+6}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{486}{13680} := \frac{48+6}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{486}{136800} := \frac{48+6}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{486}{1368000} := \frac{48+6}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2371. \quad & \frac{486}{5670} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 6 \times 7+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{56700} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 6 \times 70+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{567000} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 6 \times 700+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{5670000} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 6 \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2376. \quad & \frac{488}{1220} := \frac{(4+8) \times 8}{12 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{488}{12200} := \frac{(4+8) \times 8}{12 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{488}{122000} := \frac{(4+8) \times 8}{12 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{488}{1220000} := \frac{(4+8) \times 8}{12 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2367. \quad & \frac{486}{1440} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{486}{14400} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{486}{144000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{486}{1440000} := \frac{48+6}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2372. \quad & \frac{486}{585} := \frac{48+6}{(5+8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{486}{5850} := \frac{48+6}{(5+8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{486}{58500} := \frac{48+6}{(5+8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{486}{585000} := \frac{48+6}{(5+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2377. \quad & \frac{488}{1464} := \frac{4 \times 8+8}{(1+4) \times 6 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{488}{14640} := \frac{4 \times 8+8}{(1+4) \times 6 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{488}{146400} := \frac{4 \times 8+8}{(1+4) \times 6 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{488}{1464000} := \frac{4 \times 8+8}{(1+4) \times 6 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2368. \quad & \frac{486}{1458} := \frac{4 \times (8+6)}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{486}{14580} := \frac{4 \times (8+6)}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{486}{145800} := \frac{4 \times (8+6)}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{486}{1458000} := \frac{4 \times (8+6)}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2373. \quad & \frac{486}{729} := \frac{48+6}{(7+2) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{486}{7290} := \frac{48+6}{(7+2) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{486}{72900} := \frac{48+6}{(7+2) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{486}{729000} := \frac{48+6}{(7+2) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2378. \quad & \frac{488}{671} := \frac{48+8}{6+71} \\
 & \frac{488}{6771} := \frac{48+8}{6+771} \\
 & \frac{488}{67771} := \frac{48+8}{6+7771} \\
 & \frac{488}{677771} := \frac{48+8}{6+77771}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2369. \quad & \frac{486}{1485} := \frac{48+6}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{486}{14850} := \frac{48+6}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{486}{148500} := \frac{48+6}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{486}{1485000} := \frac{48+6}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2374. \quad & \frac{486}{864} := \frac{48 \times 6}{8 \times 64} \\
 & \frac{486}{8640} := \frac{48 \times 6}{8 \times 640} \\
 & \frac{486}{86400} := \frac{48 \times 6}{8 \times 6400} \\
 & \frac{486}{864000} := \frac{48 \times 6}{8 \times 64000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2379. \quad & \frac{492}{1435} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{14 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{492}{14350} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{14 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{492}{143500} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{14 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{492}{1435000} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{14 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2370. \quad & \frac{486}{540} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 4+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{5400} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 40+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{54000} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 400+0} \\
 & \frac{486}{540000} := \frac{4+8+6}{5 \times 4000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2375. \quad & \frac{486}{891} := \frac{48+6}{8+91} \\
 & \frac{486}{8991} := \frac{48+6}{8+991} \\
 & \frac{486}{89991} := \frac{48+6}{8+9991} \\
 & \frac{486}{899991} := \frac{48+6}{8+99991}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2380. \quad & \frac{492}{615} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 15} \\
 & \frac{492}{6150} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 150} \\
 & \frac{492}{61500} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{492}{615000} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 2}{6 \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2381. \quad \frac{492}{820} := \frac{4+92}{8 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{492}{8200} := \frac{4+92}{8 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{492}{82000} := \frac{4+92}{8 \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{492}{820000} := \frac{4+92}{8 \times 20000}$$

$$2386. \quad \frac{495}{1375} := \frac{4+9+5}{(1 \times 3+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{495}{13750} := \frac{4+9+5}{(1 \times 3+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{495}{137500} := \frac{4+9+5}{(1 \times 3+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{495}{1375000} := \frac{4+9+5}{(1 \times 3+7) \times 5000}$$

$$2391. \quad \frac{498}{664} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 8}{6 \times 64}$$

$$\frac{498}{6640} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 8}{6 \times 640}$$

$$\frac{498}{66400} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 8}{6 \times 6400}$$

$$\frac{498}{664000} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 8}{6 \times 64000}$$

$$2382. \quad \frac{494}{1197} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{494}{11970} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{494}{119700} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{494}{1197000} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7000}$$

$$2387. \quad \frac{495}{1675} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 67 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{495}{16750} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 67 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{495}{167500} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 67 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{495}{1675000} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 67 \times 5000}$$

$$2392. \quad \frac{499}{998} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{499}{9980} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{499}{99800} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{499}{998000} := \frac{4 \times 9 \times 9}{9 \times 9 \times 8000}$$

$$2383. \quad \frac{494}{1254} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{494}{12540} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{494}{125400} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{494}{1254000} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 4000}$$

$$2388. \quad \frac{495}{16975} := \frac{4+95}{(1+6) \times 97 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{495}{169750} := \frac{4+95}{(1+6) \times 97 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{495}{1697500} := \frac{4+95}{(1+6) \times 97 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{495}{16975000} := \frac{4+95}{(1+6) \times 97 \times 5000}$$

$$2393. \quad \frac{501}{18537} := \frac{5^{01}}{1^8 \times 5 \times 37}$$

$$\frac{501}{185370} := \frac{5^{01}}{1^8 \times 5 \times 370}$$

$$\frac{501}{1853700} := \frac{5^{01}}{1^8 \times 5 \times 3700}$$

$$\frac{501}{18537000} := \frac{5^{01}}{1^8 \times 5 \times 37000}$$

$$2384. \quad \frac{494}{1368} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{494}{13680} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{494}{136800} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{494}{1368000} := \frac{4 \times (9+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8000}$$

$$2389. \quad \frac{497}{1278} := \frac{(4+9) \times 7}{(1+2) \times 78}$$

$$\frac{497}{12780} := \frac{(4+9) \times 7}{(1+2) \times 780}$$

$$\frac{497}{127800} := \frac{(4+9) \times 7}{(1+2) \times 7800}$$

$$\frac{497}{1278000} := \frac{(4+9) \times 7}{(1+2) \times 78000}$$

$$2385. \quad \frac{495}{1250} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{495}{12500} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{495}{125000} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 25000}$$

$$\frac{495}{1250000} := \frac{4+95}{1 \times 250000}$$

$$2390. \quad \frac{497}{781} := \frac{49+7}{7+81}$$

$$\frac{497}{7881} := \frac{49+7}{7+881}$$

$$\frac{497}{78881} := \frac{49+7}{7+8881}$$

$$\frac{497}{788881} := \frac{49+7}{7+88881}$$

$$2394. \quad \frac{502}{1255} := \frac{5 \times 02}{1^2 \times 5 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{502}{12550} := \frac{5 \times 02}{1^2 \times 5 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{502}{125500} := \frac{5 \times 02}{1^2 \times 5 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{502}{1255000} := \frac{5 \times 02}{1^2 \times 5 \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2395. \quad & \frac{502}{7530} := \frac{5+02}{7 \times 5 \times 3+0} \\
 & \frac{502}{75300} := \frac{5+02}{7 \times 5 \times 30+0} \\
 & \frac{502}{753000} := \frac{5+02}{7 \times 5 \times 300+0} \\
 & \frac{502}{7530000} := \frac{5+02}{7 \times 5 \times 3000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2400. \quad & \frac{505}{1212} := \frac{5+05}{1 \times 2 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{505}{12120} := \frac{5+05}{1 \times 2 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{505}{121200} := \frac{5+05}{1 \times 2 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{505}{1212000} := \frac{5+05}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2405. \quad & \frac{507}{1352} := \frac{5+07}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{507}{13520} := \frac{5+07}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{507}{135200} := \frac{5+07}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{507}{1352000} := \frac{5+07}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2396. \quad & \frac{504}{1120} := \frac{50+4}{1 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{504}{11200} := \frac{50+4}{1 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{504}{112000} := \frac{50+4}{1 \times 12000} \\
 & \frac{504}{1120000} := \frac{50+4}{1 \times 120000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2401. \quad & \frac{505}{1313} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1^3 \times 13} \\
 & \frac{505}{13130} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1^3 \times 130} \\
 & \frac{505}{131300} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1^3 \times 1300} \\
 & \frac{505}{1313000} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1^3 \times 13000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2406. \quad & \frac{510}{1122} := \frac{5+10}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{510}{11322} := \frac{5+10}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{510}{113322} := \frac{5+10}{11+3322} \\
 & \frac{510}{1133322} := \frac{5+10}{11+33322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2397. \quad & \frac{505}{1010} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 010} \\
 & \frac{505}{10100} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 0100} \\
 & \frac{505}{101000} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 01000} \\
 & \frac{505}{1010000} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 010000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2402. \quad & \frac{505}{1414} := \frac{5 \times 05}{(1+4) \times 14} \\
 & \frac{505}{14140} := \frac{5 \times 05}{(1+4) \times 140} \\
 & \frac{505}{141400} := \frac{5 \times 05}{(1+4) \times 1400} \\
 & \frac{505}{1414000} := \frac{5 \times 05}{(1+4) \times 14000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2407. \quad & \frac{511}{1168} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+1^6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{511}{11680} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+1^6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{511}{116800} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+1^6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{511}{1168000} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+1^6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2398. \quad & \frac{505}{1111} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{505}{11110} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 110} \\
 & \frac{505}{111100} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 1100} \\
 & \frac{505}{1111000} := \frac{5+0 \times 5}{1 \times 1 \times 11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2403. \quad & \frac{506}{1012} := \frac{5+06}{(10+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{506}{10120} := \frac{5+06}{(10+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{506}{101200} := \frac{5+06}{(10+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{506}{1012000} := \frac{5+06}{(10+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2408. \quad & \frac{511}{1241} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+2^4) \times 1} \\
 & \frac{511}{12410} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+2^4) \times 10} \\
 & \frac{511}{124100} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+2^4) \times 100} \\
 & \frac{511}{1241000} := \frac{5+1+1}{(1+2^4) \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2399. \quad & \frac{505}{1111} := \frac{5+05}{11+11} \\
 & \frac{505}{11211} := \frac{5+05}{11+211} \\
 & \frac{505}{112211} := \frac{5+05}{11+2211} \\
 & \frac{505}{1122211} := \frac{5+05}{11+22211}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2404. \quad & \frac{506}{1012} := \frac{5+06}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{506}{10212} := \frac{5+06}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{506}{102212} := \frac{5+06}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{506}{1022212} := \frac{5+06}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2409. \quad & \frac{511}{1606} := \frac{5+1+1}{16+06} \\
 & \frac{511}{16206} := \frac{5+1+1}{16+206} \\
 & \frac{511}{162206} := \frac{5+1+1}{16+2206} \\
 & \frac{511}{1622206} := \frac{5+1+1}{16+22206}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2410. \quad \frac{512}{1024} := \frac{(5+1) \times 2}{1 \times 024}$$

$$\frac{512}{10240} := \frac{(5+1) \times 2}{1 \times 0240}$$

$$\frac{512}{102400} := \frac{(5+1) \times 2}{1 \times 024000}$$

$$2415. \quad \frac{513}{1368} := \frac{51+3}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{513}{13680} := \frac{51+3}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{513}{136800} := \frac{51+3}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 800}$$

$$2420. \quad \frac{515}{1133} := \frac{5+15}{11+33}$$

$$\frac{515}{11433} := \frac{5+15}{11+433}$$

$$\frac{515}{114433} := \frac{5+15}{11+4433}$$

$$2411. \quad \frac{512}{704} := \frac{5+1+2}{7+04}$$

$$\frac{512}{7104} := \frac{5+1+2}{7+104}$$

$$\frac{512}{71104} := \frac{5+1+2}{7+1104}$$

$$\frac{512}{711104} := \frac{5+1+2}{7+11104}$$

$$2416. \quad \frac{513}{1425} := \frac{51 \times 3}{1 \times 425}$$

$$\frac{513}{14250} := \frac{51 \times 3}{1 \times 4250}$$

$$\frac{513}{142500} := \frac{51 \times 3}{1 \times 425000}$$

$$2421. \quad \frac{515}{1236} := \frac{5+15}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{515}{12360} := \frac{5+15}{1 \times 2^3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{515}{123600} := \frac{5+15}{1 \times 2^3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{515}{1236000} := \frac{5+15}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6000}$$

$$2412. \quad \frac{513}{1026} := \frac{5+1^3}{1 \times 02 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{513}{10260} := \frac{5+1^3}{1 \times 02 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{513}{102600} := \frac{5+1^3}{1 \times 02 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{513}{1026000} := \frac{5+1^3}{1 \times 02 \times 6000}$$

$$2417. \quad \frac{513}{1482} := \frac{5+1+3}{(1+4+8) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{513}{14820} := \frac{5+1+3}{(1+4+8) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{513}{148200} := \frac{5+1+3}{(1+4+8) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{513}{1482000} := \frac{5+1+3}{(1+4+8) \times 2000}$$

$$2422. \quad \frac{515}{1442} := \frac{5 \times 15}{(1+4) \times 42}$$

$$\frac{515}{14420} := \frac{5 \times 15}{(1+4) \times 420}$$

$$\frac{515}{144200} := \frac{5 \times 15}{(1+4) \times 4200}$$

$$\frac{515}{1442000} := \frac{5 \times 15}{(1+4) \times 42000}$$

$$2413. \quad \frac{513}{1197} := \frac{51+3}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{513}{11970} := \frac{51+3}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{513}{119700} := \frac{51+3}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{513}{1197000} := \frac{51+3}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7000}$$

$$2418. \quad \frac{514}{1285} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4}{(1 \times 2 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{514}{12850} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4}{(1 \times 2 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{514}{128500} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4}{(1 \times 2 + 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{514}{1285000} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 4}{(1 \times 2 + 8) \times 5000}$$

$$2414. \quad \frac{513}{1254} := \frac{5+13}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{513}{12540} := \frac{5+13}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{513}{125400} := \frac{5+13}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{513}{1254000} := \frac{5+13}{(1+2 \times 5) \times 4000}$$

$$2419. \quad \frac{515}{1133} := \frac{5 \times (1+5)}{(1+1) \times 33}$$

$$\frac{515}{11330} := \frac{5 \times (1+5)}{(1+1) \times 330}$$

$$\frac{515}{113300} := \frac{5 \times (1+5)}{(1+1) \times 3300}$$

$$\frac{515}{1133000} := \frac{5 \times (1+5)}{(1+1) \times 33000}$$

$$2423. \quad \frac{515}{721} := \frac{5+1 \times 5}{7 \times 2 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{515}{7210} := \frac{5+1 \times 5}{7 \times 2 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{515}{72100} := \frac{5+1 \times 5}{7 \times 2 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{515}{721000} := \frac{5+1 \times 5}{7 \times 2 \times 1000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2424. \quad & \frac{515}{824} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 5}{(8+2) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{515}{8240} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 5}{(8+2) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{515}{82400} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 5}{(8+2) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{515}{824000} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 5}{(8+2) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2429. \quad & \frac{516}{946} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9+46} \\
 & \frac{516}{9546} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9+546} \\
 & \frac{516}{95546} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{9+5546}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2434. \quad & \frac{517}{1551} := \frac{5+17}{15+51} \\
 & \frac{517}{15651} := \frac{5+17}{15+651} \\
 & \frac{517}{156651} := \frac{5+17}{15+6651}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2425. \quad & \frac{516}{1032} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{10 \times 3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{516}{10320} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{10 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{516}{103200} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{10 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{516}{1032000} := \frac{5 \times 1 \times 6}{10 \times 3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2430. \quad & \frac{517}{1034} := \frac{5+1^7}{1 \times 03 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{517}{10340} := \frac{5+1^7}{1 \times 03 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{517}{103400} := \frac{5+1^7}{1 \times 03 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{517}{1034000} := \frac{5+1^7}{1 \times 03 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2435. \quad & \frac{518}{1036} := \frac{5 \times 18}{10 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{518}{10360} := \frac{5 \times 18}{10 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{518}{103600} := \frac{5 \times 18}{10 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{518}{1036000} := \frac{5 \times 18}{10 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2426. \quad & \frac{516}{1075} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1 \times 075} \\
 & \frac{516}{10750} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1 \times 0750} \\
 & \frac{516}{107500} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1 \times 07500} \\
 & \frac{516}{1075000} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1 \times 075000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2431. \quad & \frac{517}{1034} := \frac{5+17}{10+34} \\
 & \frac{517}{10434} := \frac{5+17}{10+434} \\
 & \frac{517}{104434} := \frac{5+17}{10+4434}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2436. \quad & \frac{518}{1184} := \frac{5+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{518}{11840} := \frac{5+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{518}{118400} := \frac{5+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{518}{1184000} := \frac{5+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2427. \quad & \frac{516}{1204} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{(1+20) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{516}{12040} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{(1+20) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{516}{120400} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{(1+20) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{516}{1204000} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{(1+20) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2432. \quad & \frac{517}{1269} := \frac{5+17}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{517}{12690} := \frac{5+17}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{517}{126900} := \frac{5+17}{1^2 \times 6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{517}{1269000} := \frac{5+17}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2437. \quad & \frac{518}{1221} := \frac{5+1+8}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{518}{12321} := \frac{5+1+8}{12+321} \\
 & \frac{518}{123321} := \frac{5+1+8}{12+3321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2428. \quad & \frac{516}{1290} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1^2 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{516}{12900} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1^2 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{516}{129000} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1^2 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{516}{1290000} := \frac{(5+1) \times 6}{1^2 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2433. \quad & \frac{517}{1551} := \frac{5 \times 17}{1 \times 5 \times 51} \\
 & \frac{517}{15510} := \frac{5 \times 17}{1 \times 5 \times 510} \\
 & \frac{517}{155100} := \frac{5 \times 17}{1 \times 5 \times 5100} \\
 & \frac{517}{1551000} := \frac{5 \times 17}{1 \times 5 \times 51000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2438. \quad & \frac{518}{12950} := \frac{5+1^8}{(1+29) \times 5+0} \\
 & \frac{518}{129500} := \frac{5+1^8}{(1+29) \times 50+0} \\
 & \frac{518}{1295000} := \frac{5+1^8}{(1+29) \times 500+0} \\
 & \frac{518}{12950000} := \frac{5+1^8}{(1+29) \times 5000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2439. \quad \frac{518}{1480} := \frac{5+1+8}{(1+4) \times 8+0}$$

$$\frac{518}{14800} := \frac{5+1+8}{(1+4) \times 80+0}$$

$$\frac{518}{148000} := \frac{5+1+8}{(1+4) \times 800+0}$$

$$\frac{518}{1480000} := \frac{5+1+8}{(1+4) \times 8000+0}$$

$$2444. \quad \frac{522}{1392} := \frac{5+22}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{522}{13920} := \frac{5+22}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{522}{139200} := \frac{5+22}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{522}{1392000} := \frac{5+22}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2000}$$

$$2449. \quad \frac{524}{917} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+1) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{524}{9170} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+1) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{524}{91700} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+1) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{524}{917000} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+1) \times 7000}$$

$$2440. \quad \frac{518}{814} := \frac{5+1+8}{8+14}$$

$$\frac{518}{8214} := \frac{5+1+8}{8+214}$$

$$\frac{518}{82214} := \frac{5+1+8}{8+2214}$$

$$\frac{518}{822214} := \frac{5+1+8}{8+22214}$$

$$2445. \quad \frac{522}{1450} := \frac{5+2^2}{(1+4) \times 5+0}$$

$$\frac{522}{14500} := \frac{5+2^2}{(1+4) \times 50+0}$$

$$\frac{522}{145000} := \frac{5+2^2}{(1+4) \times 500+0}$$

$$\frac{522}{1450000} := \frac{5+2^2}{(1+4) \times 5000+0}$$

$$2450. \quad \frac{525}{1155} := \frac{5 \times 25}{11 \times 5 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{525}{11550} := \frac{5 \times 25}{11 \times 5 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{525}{115500} := \frac{5 \times 25}{11 \times 5 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{525}{1155000} := \frac{5 \times 25}{11 \times 5 \times 5000}$$

$$2441. \quad \frac{519}{1903} := \frac{5+1^9}{19+03}$$

$$\frac{519}{19203} := \frac{5+1^9}{19+203}$$

$$\frac{519}{192203} := \frac{5+1^9}{19+2203}$$

$$\frac{519}{1922203} := \frac{5+1^9}{19+22203}$$

$$2446. \quad \frac{524}{1048} := \frac{52+4}{(10+4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{524}{10480} := \frac{52+4}{(10+4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{524}{104800} := \frac{52+4}{(10+4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{524}{1048000} := \frac{52+4}{(10+4) \times 8000}$$

$$2451. \quad \frac{525}{1155} := \frac{5+25}{11+55}$$

$$\frac{525}{11655} := \frac{5+25}{11+655}$$

$$\frac{525}{116655} := \frac{5+25}{11+6655}$$

$$\frac{525}{1166655} := \frac{5+25}{11+66655}$$

$$2442. \quad \frac{520}{1144} := \frac{5+20}{11+44}$$

$$\frac{520}{11544} := \frac{5+20}{11+544}$$

$$\frac{520}{115544} := \frac{5+20}{11+544}$$

$$\frac{520}{1155544} := \frac{5+20}{11+544}$$

$$2447. \quad \frac{524}{1179} := \frac{(5+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9}$$

$$\frac{524}{11790} := \frac{(5+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 90}$$

$$\frac{524}{117900} := \frac{(5+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 900}$$

$$\frac{524}{1179000} := \frac{(5+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9000}$$

$$2443. \quad \frac{522}{1160} := \frac{5+22}{1 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{522}{11600} := \frac{5+22}{1 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{522}{116000} := \frac{5+22}{1 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{522}{1160000} := \frac{5+22}{1 \times 1 \times 60000}$$

$$2448. \quad \frac{524}{655} := \frac{5 \times 24}{6 \times 5 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{524}{6550} := \frac{5 \times 24}{6 \times 5 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{524}{65500} := \frac{5 \times 24}{6 \times 5 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{524}{655000} := \frac{5 \times 24}{6 \times 5 \times 5000}$$

$$2452. \quad \frac{525}{1225} := \frac{5+25}{(12+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{525}{12250} := \frac{5+25}{(12+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{525}{122500} := \frac{5+25}{(12+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{525}{1225000} := \frac{5+25}{(12+2) \times 5000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2453. \quad & \frac{525}{1260} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{525}{12600} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{525}{126000} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{525}{1260000} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2458. \quad & \frac{525}{14875} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{(1+(4+8) \times 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{525}{148750} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{(1+(4+8) \times 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{525}{1487500} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{(1+(4+8) \times 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{525}{14875000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{(1+(4+8) \times 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2463. \quad & \frac{527}{1240} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{527}{12400} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{527}{124000} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{527}{1240000} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2454. \quad & \frac{525}{13650} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{13 \times 6 \times 5 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{136500} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{13 \times 6 \times 50 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{1365000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{13 \times 6 \times 500 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{13650000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{13 \times 6 \times 5000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2459. \quad & \frac{525}{1575} := \frac{5 \times 25}{1 \times 5 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{525}{15750} := \frac{5 \times 25}{1 \times 5 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{525}{157500} := \frac{5 \times 25}{1 \times 5 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{525}{1575000} := \frac{5 \times 25}{1 \times 5 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2464. \quad & \frac{527}{13950} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^3 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{527}{139500} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^3 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{527}{1395000} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^3 \times 9 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{527}{13950000} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{1^3 \times 9 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2455. \quad & \frac{525}{1400} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{1 \times 40 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{14000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{1 \times 400 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{140000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{1 \times 4000 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{1400000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{1 \times 40000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2460. \quad & \frac{525}{630} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{6 \times 3 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{6300} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{6 \times 30 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{63000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{6 \times 300 + 0} \\
 & \frac{525}{630000} := \frac{5+2 \times 5}{6 \times 3000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2465. \quad & \frac{528}{1056} := \frac{5+2+8}{1 \times 05 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{528}{10560} := \frac{5+2+8}{1 \times 05 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{528}{105600} := \frac{5+2+8}{1 \times 05 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{528}{1056000} := \frac{5+2+8}{1 \times 05 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2456. \quad & \frac{525}{1428} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(1+4^2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{525}{14280} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(1+4^2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{525}{142800} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(1+4^2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{525}{1428000} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(1+4^2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2461. \quad & \frac{525}{756} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(7+5) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{525}{7560} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(7+5) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{525}{75600} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(7+5) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{525}{756000} := \frac{5 \times 2 \times 5}{(7+5) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2466. \quad & \frac{528}{1056} := \frac{5+28}{10+56} \\
 & \frac{528}{10656} := \frac{5+28}{10+656} \\
 & \frac{528}{106656} := \frac{5+28}{10+6656} \\
 & \frac{528}{1066656} := \frac{5+28}{10+66656}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2457. \quad & \frac{525}{14700} := \frac{525}{(1+4) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{525}{147000} := \frac{525}{(1+4) \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{525}{1470000} := \frac{525}{(1+4) \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2462. \quad & \frac{525}{1470} := \frac{5 \times 25}{(1+4) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{527}{1023} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 23} \\
 & \frac{527}{10323} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 323} \\
 & \frac{527}{103323} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 3323} \\
 & \frac{527}{1033323} := \frac{5 \times 2 + 7}{10 + 33323}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2467. \quad & \frac{528}{1280} := \frac{5+28}{1^2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{528}{12800} := \frac{5+28}{1^2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{528}{128000} := \frac{5+28}{1^2 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{528}{1280000} := \frac{5+28}{1^2 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2468. \quad \frac{528}{1408} := \frac{5+2+8}{(1+4+0) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{528}{14080} := \frac{5+2+8}{(1+4+0) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{528}{140800} := \frac{5+2+8}{(1+4+0) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{528}{1408000} := \frac{5+2+8}{(1+4+0) \times 8000}$$

$$2473. \quad \frac{530}{1166} := \frac{5+30}{11+66}$$

$$\frac{530}{11766} := \frac{5+30}{11+766}$$

$$\frac{530}{117766} := \frac{5+30}{11+7766}$$

$$2478. \quad \frac{532}{1064} := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+06) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{532}{10640} := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+06) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{532}{106400} := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+06) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{532}{1064000} := \frac{5+3^2}{(1+06) \times 4000}$$

$$2469. \quad \frac{528}{14976} := \frac{5+28}{(149+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{528}{149760} := \frac{5+28}{(149+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{528}{1497600} := \frac{5+28}{(149+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{528}{14976000} := \frac{5+28}{(149+7) \times 6000}$$

$$2474. \quad \frac{531}{1062} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 1}{(10+6) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{531}{10620} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 1}{(10+6) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{531}{106200} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 1}{(10+6) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{531}{1062000} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 1}{(10+6) \times 2000}$$

$$2479. \quad \frac{532}{1216} := \frac{5+3^2}{1 \times 2 \times 16}$$

$$\frac{532}{12160} := \frac{5+3^2}{1 \times 2 \times 160}$$

$$\frac{532}{121600} := \frac{5+3^2}{1 \times 2 \times 1600}$$

$$\frac{532}{1216000} := \frac{5+3^2}{1 \times 2 \times 16000}$$

$$2470. \quad \frac{528}{1584} := \frac{5+28}{15+84}$$

$$\frac{528}{15984} := \frac{5+28}{15+984}$$

$$\frac{528}{159984} := \frac{5+28}{15+9984}$$

$$2475. \quad \frac{531}{1180} := \frac{5+31}{1 \times 1 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{531}{11800} := \frac{5+31}{1 \times 1 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{531}{118000} := \frac{5+31}{1 \times 1 \times 8000}$$

$$2480. \quad \frac{533}{1066} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 3}{1 \times 06 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{533}{10660} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 3}{1 \times 06 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{533}{106600} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 3}{1 \times 06 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{533}{1066000} := \frac{5 \times 3 + 3}{1 \times 06 \times 6000}$$

$$2471. \quad \frac{528}{704} := \frac{5+2 \times 8}{7 \times 04}$$

$$\frac{528}{7040} := \frac{5+2 \times 8}{7 \times 040}$$

$$\frac{528}{70400} := \frac{5+2 \times 8}{7 \times 0400}$$

$$\frac{528}{704000} := \frac{5+2 \times 8}{7 \times 04000}$$

$$2476. \quad \frac{531}{1298} := \frac{5+31}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{531}{12980} := \frac{5+31}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{531}{129800} := \frac{5+31}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{531}{1298000} := \frac{5+31}{(1 \times 2 + 9) \times 8000}$$

$$2481. \quad \frac{534}{1335} := \frac{5+3+4}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{534}{13350} := \frac{5+3+4}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{534}{133500} := \frac{5+3+4}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{534}{1335000} := \frac{5+3+4}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 5000}$$

$$2472. \quad \frac{529}{1150} := \frac{5+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{529}{11500} := \frac{5+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{529}{115000} := \frac{5+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{529}{1150000} := \frac{5+2 \times 9}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}$$

$$2477. \quad \frac{531}{1416} := \frac{5+3+1}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{531}{14160} := \frac{5+3+1}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{531}{141600} := \frac{5+3+1}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{531}{1416000} := \frac{5+3+1}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2482. \quad & \frac{534}{1424} := \frac{5+3+4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{534}{14240} := \frac{5+3+4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{534}{142400} := \frac{5+3+4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{534}{1424000} := \frac{5+3+4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2487. \quad & \frac{536}{1340} := \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{536}{13400} := \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{536}{134000} := \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{536}{1340000} := \frac{(5+3) \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2491. \quad & \frac{540}{1188} := \frac{5+40}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{540}{11988} := \frac{5+40}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{540}{119988} := \frac{5+40}{11+9988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2483. \quad & \frac{534}{712} := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{534}{7120} := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{534}{71200} := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{534}{712000} := \frac{5+3+4}{(7+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2488. \quad & \frac{537}{1432} := \frac{53+7}{(1+4) \times 32} \\
 & \frac{537}{14320} := \frac{53+7}{(1+4) \times 320} \\
 & \frac{537}{143200} := \frac{53+7}{(1+4) \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{537}{1432000} := \frac{53+7}{(1+4) \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2492. \quad & \frac{541}{1082} := \frac{5+4 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{541}{10820} := \frac{5+4 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{541}{108200} := \frac{5+4 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{541}{1082000} := \frac{5+4 \times 1}{(1+08) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2484. \quad & \frac{535}{1177} := \frac{5+35}{11+77} \\
 & \frac{535}{11877} := \frac{5+35}{11+877} \\
 & \frac{535}{118877} := \frac{5+35}{11+8877} \\
 & \frac{535}{1188877} := \frac{5+35}{11+88877}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2489. \quad & \frac{539}{1078} := \frac{5+3 \times 9}{(1+07) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{539}{10780} := \frac{5+3 \times 9}{(1+07) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{539}{107800} := \frac{5+3 \times 9}{(1+07) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{539}{1078000} := \frac{5+3 \times 9}{(1+07) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2493. \quad & \frac{542}{1084} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(1+08) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{542}{10840} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(1+08) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{542}{108400} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(1+08) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{542}{1084000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(1+08) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2485. \quad & \frac{535}{12840} := \frac{5+35}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{535}{128400} := \frac{5+35}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{535}{1284000} := \frac{5+35}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2490. \quad & \frac{539}{10878} := \frac{5+39}{10+878} \\
 & \frac{539}{108878} := \frac{5+39}{10+8878} \\
 & \frac{539}{1088878} := \frac{5+39}{10+88878}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2494. \quad & \frac{542}{1355} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{542}{13550} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{542}{135500} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{542}{1355000} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 2}{(1+3) \times 5 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2486. \quad & \frac{535}{6420} := \frac{5+35}{6 \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{535}{64200} := \frac{5+35}{6 \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{535}{642000} := \frac{5+35}{6 \times 4 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{535}{6420000} := \frac{5+35}{6 \times 4 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2495. \quad & \frac{542}{813} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{542}{8130} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{542}{81300} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{542}{813000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 2}{(8+1) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2496. \quad & \frac{543}{1086} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{543}{10860} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{543}{108600} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{543}{1086000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+08) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2501. \quad & \frac{544}{748} := \frac{5 \times (4+4)}{7+48} \\
 & \frac{544}{7548} := \frac{5 \times (4+4)}{7+548} \\
 & \frac{544}{75548} := \frac{5 \times (4+4)}{7+5548} \\
 & \frac{544}{755548} := \frac{5 \times (4+4)}{7+55548}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2506. \quad & \frac{546}{1050} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{546}{10500} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{546}{105000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 05000} \\
 & \frac{546}{1050000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 050000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2497. \quad & \frac{543}{1267} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{543}{12670} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{543}{126700} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{543}{1267000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{(1+2+6) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2502. \quad & \frac{544}{816} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{544}{8160} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{544}{81600} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{544}{816000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(8+1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2507. \quad & \frac{546}{1155} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 55} \\
 & \frac{546}{11550} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 550} \\
 & \frac{546}{115500} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 5500} \\
 & \frac{546}{1155000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2498. \quad & \frac{543}{1448} := \frac{5+43}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{543}{14480} := \frac{5+43}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{543}{144800} := \frac{5+43}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{543}{1448000} := \frac{5+43}{1 \times 4 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2503. \quad & \frac{545}{1090} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{545}{10900} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{545}{109000} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{545}{1090000} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2508. \quad & \frac{546}{1260} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{546}{12600} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{546}{126000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{546}{1260000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2499. \quad & \frac{543}{905} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{9 \times 05} \\
 & \frac{543}{9050} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{9 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{543}{90500} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{9 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{543}{905000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 3}{9 \times 05000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2504. \quad & \frac{545}{1199} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\
 & \frac{545}{11990} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\
 & \frac{545}{119900} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\
 & \frac{545}{1199000} := \frac{5 \times (4+5)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2509. \quad & \frac{546}{1302} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{546}{13020} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{546}{130200} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{546}{1302000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2500. \quad & \frac{544}{1088} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(1+08) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{544}{10880} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(1+08) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{544}{108800} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(1+08) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{544}{1088000} := \frac{(5+4) \times 4}{(1+08) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2505. \quad & \frac{545}{1308} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 30 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{545}{13080} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 30 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{545}{130800} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 30 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{545}{1308000} := \frac{5 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 30 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2510. \quad & \frac{546}{1344} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{546}{13440} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{546}{134400} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{546}{1344000} := \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2511.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{1365} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^3 \times 65} \\ \frac{546}{13650} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^3 \times 650} \\ \frac{546}{136500} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^3 \times 6500} \\ \frac{546}{1365000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^3 \times 65000} \end{aligned}$$

2516.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{819} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 9} \\ \frac{546}{8190} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 90} \\ \frac{546}{81900} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 900} \\ \frac{546}{819000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(8+1) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2521.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{1220} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times 2 \times 2} \\ \frac{549}{12200} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times 2 \times 20} \\ \frac{549}{122000} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times 2 \times 200} \\ \frac{549}{1220000} &:= \frac{5+4+9}{1 \times 2 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2512.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{1386} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6} \\ \frac{546}{13860} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60} \\ \frac{546}{138600} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600} \\ \frac{546}{1386000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2517.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{910} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{9 \times 10} \\ \frac{546}{9100} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{9 \times 100} \\ \frac{546}{91000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{9 \times 1000} \\ \frac{546}{910000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{9 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

2522.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{610} &:= \frac{5+49}{6 \times 10} \\ \frac{549}{6100} &:= \frac{5+49}{6 \times 100} \\ \frac{549}{61000} &:= \frac{5+49}{6 \times 1000} \\ \frac{549}{610000} &:= \frac{5+49}{6 \times 10000} \end{aligned}$$

2513.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{1470} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^4 \times 70} \\ \frac{546}{14700} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^4 \times 700} \\ \frac{546}{147000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^4 \times 7000} \\ \frac{546}{1470000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{1^4 \times 70000} \end{aligned}$$

2518.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{924} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(9+2) \times 4} \\ \frac{546}{9240} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(9+2) \times 40} \\ \frac{546}{92400} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(9+2) \times 400} \\ \frac{546}{924000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 6}{(9+2) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2514.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{637} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(6+3) \times 7} \\ \frac{546}{6370} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(6+3) \times 70} \\ \frac{546}{63700} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(6+3) \times 700} \\ \frac{546}{637000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(6+3) \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

2519.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{548}{1370} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 8}{1^3 \times 70} \\ \frac{548}{13700} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 8}{1^3 \times 700} \\ \frac{548}{137000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 8}{1^3 \times 7000} \\ \frac{548}{1370000} &:= \frac{5 \times 4 + 8}{1^3 \times 70000} \end{aligned}$$

2523.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{671} &:= \frac{54+9}{6+71} \\ \frac{549}{6771} &:= \frac{54+9}{6+771} \\ \frac{549}{67771} &:= \frac{54+9}{6+7771} \\ \frac{549}{677771} &:= \frac{54+9}{6+77771} \end{aligned}$$

2515.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{546}{728} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 8} \\ \frac{546}{7280} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 80} \\ \frac{546}{72800} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 800} \\ \frac{546}{728000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 6}{(7+2) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2520.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{548}{959} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 8}{(9+5) \times 9} \\ \frac{548}{9590} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 8}{(9+5) \times 90} \\ \frac{548}{95900} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 8}{(9+5) \times 900} \\ \frac{548}{959000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 8}{(9+5) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2524.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{915} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 9}{9 \times 15} \\ \frac{549}{9150} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 9}{9 \times 150} \\ \frac{549}{91500} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 9}{9 \times 1500} \\ \frac{549}{915000} &:= \frac{(5+4) \times 9}{9 \times 15000} \end{aligned}$$

2525.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{549}{976} &:= \frac{5+49}{(9+7) \times 6} \\ \frac{549}{9760} &:= \frac{5+49}{(9+7) \times 60} \\ \frac{549}{97600} &:= \frac{5+49}{(9+7) \times 600} \\ \frac{549}{976000} &:= \frac{5+49}{(9+7) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2530.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{552}{1012} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{(10+1) \times 2} \\ \frac{552}{10120} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{(10+1) \times 20} \\ \frac{552}{101200} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{(10+1) \times 200} \\ \frac{552}{1012000} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{(10+1) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2535.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{553}{1264} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 3}{1^2 \times 64} \\ \frac{553}{12640} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 3}{1^2 \times 640} \\ \frac{553}{126400} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 3}{1^2 \times 6400} \\ \frac{553}{1264000} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 3}{1^2 \times 64000} \end{aligned}$$

2526.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{550}{1155} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{1+15+5} \\ \frac{550}{12155} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{1+215+5} \\ \frac{550}{122155} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{1+2215+5} \\ \frac{550}{1222155} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{1+22215+5} \end{aligned}$$

2531.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{552}{1012} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{10+12} \\ \frac{552}{10212} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{10+212} \\ \frac{552}{102212} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{10+2212} \\ \frac{552}{1022212} &:= \frac{5+5+2}{10+22212} \end{aligned}$$

2536.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{554}{1108} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 8} \\ \frac{554}{11080} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 80} \\ \frac{554}{110800} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 800} \\ \frac{554}{1108000} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2527.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{550}{605} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{6+05} \\ \frac{550}{6105} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{6+105} \\ \frac{550}{61105} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{6+1105} \\ \frac{550}{611105} &:= \frac{5+5+0}{6+11105} \end{aligned}$$

2532.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{552}{1104} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 2}{1 \times 10 \times 4} \\ \frac{552}{11040} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 2}{1 \times 10 \times 40} \\ \frac{552}{110400} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 2}{1 \times 10 \times 400} \\ \frac{552}{1104000} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 2}{1 \times 10 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2537.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{555}{1184} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 5}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{555}{11840} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 5}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{555}{118400} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 5}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{555}{1184000} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 5}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2528.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{550}{726} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 26} \\ \frac{550}{7326} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 326} \\ \frac{550}{73326} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 3326} \\ \frac{550}{733326} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 0}{7 + 33326} \end{aligned}$$

2533.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{552}{1472} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 2}{1^4 \times 72} \\ \frac{552}{14720} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 2}{1^4 \times 720} \\ \frac{552}{147200} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 2}{1^4 \times 7200} \\ \frac{552}{1472000} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 2}{1^4 \times 72000} \end{aligned}$$

2538.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{555}{1221} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{12+21} \\ \frac{555}{12321} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{12+321} \\ \frac{555}{123321} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{12+3321} \\ \frac{555}{1233321} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{12+33321} \end{aligned}$$

2529.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{551}{1102} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 2} \\ \frac{551}{11020} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 20} \\ \frac{551}{110200} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 200} \\ \frac{551}{1102000} &:= \frac{5+5 \times 1}{1 \times 10 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2534.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{553}{1106} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 3}{1 \times 10 \times 6} \\ \frac{553}{11060} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 3}{1 \times 10 \times 60} \\ \frac{553}{110600} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 3}{1 \times 10 \times 600} \\ \frac{553}{1106000} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 3}{1 \times 10 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2539.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{555}{1258} &:= \frac{5+55}{(12+5) \times 8} \\ \frac{555}{12580} &:= \frac{5+55}{(12+5) \times 80} \\ \frac{555}{125800} &:= \frac{5+55}{(12+5) \times 800} \\ \frac{555}{1258000} &:= \frac{5+55}{(12+5) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2540.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{555}{814} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{8+14} \\ \frac{555}{8214} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{8+214} \\ \frac{555}{82214} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{8+2214} \\ \frac{555}{822214} &:= \frac{5+5+5}{8+22214} \end{aligned}$$

2546.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{558}{1395} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 5} \\ \frac{558}{13950} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 50} \\ \frac{558}{139500} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 500} \\ \frac{558}{1395000} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2551.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1224} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^2 \times 24} \\ \frac{561}{12240} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^2 \times 240} \\ \frac{561}{122400} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^2 \times 2400} \\ \frac{561}{1224000} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^2 \times 24000} \end{aligned}$$

2541.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{556}{1529} &:= \frac{5+5+6}{15+29} \\ \frac{556}{15429} &:= \frac{5+5+6}{15+429} \\ \frac{556}{154429} &:= \frac{5+5+6}{15+4429} \\ \frac{556}{1544429} &:= \frac{5+5+6}{15+44429} \end{aligned}$$

2547.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{558}{1488} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1^4 \times 88} \\ \frac{558}{14880} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1^4 \times 880} \\ \frac{558}{148800} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1^4 \times 8800} \\ \frac{558}{1488000} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1^4 \times 88000} \end{aligned}$$

2552.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1275} &:= \frac{5+61}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\ \frac{561}{12750} &:= \frac{5+61}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\ \frac{561}{127500} &:= \frac{5+61}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\ \frac{561}{1275000} &:= \frac{5+61}{1 \times 2 \times 75000} \end{aligned}$$

2542.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{556}{695} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 6}{(6+9) \times 5} \\ \frac{556}{6950} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 6}{(6+9) \times 50} \\ \frac{556}{69500} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 6}{(6+9) \times 500} \\ \frac{556}{695000} &:= \frac{(5+5) \times 6}{(6+9) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2548.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{558}{744} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{(7+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{558}{7440} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{(7+4) \times 40} \\ \frac{558}{74400} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{(7+4) \times 400} \\ \frac{558}{744000} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{(7+4) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2553.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1326} &:= \frac{5+61}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\ \frac{561}{13260} &:= \frac{5+61}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \frac{561}{132600} &:= \frac{5+61}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\ \frac{561}{1326000} &:= \frac{5+61}{13 \times 2 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2543.

2544.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{558}{1116} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 11 \times 6} \\ \frac{558}{11160} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 11 \times 60} \\ \frac{558}{111600} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 11 \times 600} \\ \frac{558}{1116000} &:= \frac{5 \times 5 + 8}{1 \times 11 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2549.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1020} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 020} \\ \frac{561}{10200} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 0200} \\ \frac{561}{102000} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 02000} \\ \frac{561}{1020000} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 020000} \end{aligned}$$

2545.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{558}{1240} &:= \frac{5+5+8}{1^2 \times 40} \\ \frac{558}{12400} &:= \frac{5+5+8}{1^2 \times 400} \\ \frac{558}{124000} &:= \frac{5+5+8}{1^2 \times 4000} \\ \frac{558}{1240000} &:= \frac{5+5+8}{1^2 \times 40000} \end{aligned}$$

2550.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1122} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 22} \\ \frac{561}{11220} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 220} \\ \frac{561}{112200} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 2200} \\ \frac{561}{1122000} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1 \times 1 \times 22000} \end{aligned}$$

2554.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{561}{1428} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^4 \times 28} \\ \frac{561}{14280} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^4 \times 280} \\ \frac{561}{142800} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^4 \times 2800} \\ \frac{561}{1428000} &:= \frac{5+6 \times 1}{1^4 \times 28000} \end{aligned}$$

$$2555. \quad \frac{565}{1356} := \frac{5+65}{1 \times 3 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{565}{13560} := \frac{5+65}{1 \times 3 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{565}{135600} := \frac{5+65}{1 \times 3 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{565}{1356000} := \frac{5+65}{1 \times 3 \times 56000}$$

$$2560. \quad \frac{567}{1197} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 19 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{567}{11970} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 19 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{567}{119700} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 19 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{567}{1197000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}$$

$$2565. \quad \frac{567}{585} := \frac{56+7}{(5+8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{567}{5850} := \frac{56+7}{(5+8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{567}{58500} := \frac{56+7}{(5+8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{567}{585000} := \frac{56+7}{(5+8) \times 5000}$$

$$2556. \quad \frac{565}{678} := \frac{56 \times 5}{6 \times 7 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{565}{6780} := \frac{56 \times 5}{6 \times 7 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{565}{67800} := \frac{56 \times 5}{6 \times 7 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{565}{678000} := \frac{56 \times 5}{6 \times 7 \times 8000}$$

$$2561. \quad \frac{567}{1350} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{567}{13500} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{567}{135000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{567}{1350000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}$$

$$2566. \quad \frac{567}{891} := \frac{56+7}{8+91}$$

$$\frac{567}{8910} := \frac{56+7}{8+910}$$

$$\frac{567}{89100} := \frac{56+7}{8+9100}$$

$$\frac{567}{891000} := \frac{56+7}{8+91000}$$

$$2557. \quad \frac{566}{1132} := \frac{(5+6) \times 6}{1 \times 132}$$

$$\frac{566}{11320} := \frac{(5+6) \times 6}{1 \times 1320}$$

$$\frac{566}{113200} := \frac{(5+6) \times 6}{1 \times 13200}$$

$$\frac{566}{1132000} := \frac{(5+6) \times 6}{1 \times 132000}$$

$$2562. \quad \frac{567}{1368} := \frac{56+7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{567}{13680} := \frac{56+7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{567}{136800} := \frac{56+7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{567}{1368000} := \frac{56+7}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

$$2567. \quad \frac{568}{781} := \frac{56+8}{7+81}$$

$$\frac{568}{7810} := \frac{56+8}{7+810}$$

$$\frac{568}{78100} := \frac{56+8}{7+8100}$$

$$\frac{568}{781000} := \frac{56+8}{7+81000}$$

$$2558. \quad \frac{567}{1125} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 125}$$

$$\frac{567}{11250} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 1250}$$

$$\frac{567}{112500} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 12500}$$

$$\frac{567}{1125000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 125000}$$

$$2563. \quad \frac{567}{1440} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{567}{14400} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{567}{144000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{567}{1440000} := \frac{56+7}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}$$

$$2568. \quad \frac{569}{1138} := \frac{5+6+9}{(1+1+3) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{569}{11380} := \frac{5+6+9}{(1+1+3) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{569}{113800} := \frac{5+6+9}{(1+1+3) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{569}{1138000} := \frac{5+6+9}{(1+1+3) \times 8000}$$

$$2559. \quad \frac{567}{11592} := \frac{5+67}{(1+15) \times 92}$$

$$\frac{567}{115920} := \frac{5+67}{(1+15) \times 920}$$

$$\frac{567}{1159200} := \frac{5+67}{(1+15) \times 9200}$$

$$\frac{567}{11592000} := \frac{5+67}{(1+15) \times 92000}$$

$$2564. \quad \frac{567}{1485} := \frac{56+7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{567}{14850} := \frac{56+7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{567}{148500} := \frac{56+7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{567}{1485000} := \frac{56+7}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}$$

$$2569. \quad \frac{573}{1146} := \frac{5+7+3}{(1 \times 1+4) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{573}{11460} := \frac{5+7+3}{(1 \times 1+4) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{573}{114600} := \frac{5+7+3}{(1 \times 1+4) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{573}{1146000} := \frac{5+7+3}{(1 \times 1+4) \times 6000}$$

$$2570. \quad \frac{573}{1337} := \frac{(5+7) \times 3}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{573}{13370} := \frac{(5+7) \times 3}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{573}{133700} := \frac{(5+7) \times 3}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{573}{1337000} := \frac{(5+7) \times 3}{(1+3) \times 3 \times 7000}$$

$$2575. \quad \frac{576}{1296} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{576}{12960} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{576}{129600} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{576}{1296000} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$2580. \quad \frac{580}{1276} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 76}$$

$$\frac{580}{12876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 876}$$

$$\frac{580}{128876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 8876}$$

$$\frac{580}{1288876} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{12 + 88876}$$

$$2571. \quad \frac{574}{1025} := \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{10 \times 25}$$

$$\frac{574}{10250} := \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{10 \times 250}$$

$$\frac{574}{102500} := \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{10 \times 2500}$$

$$\frac{574}{1025000} := \frac{5 \times 7 \times 4}{10 \times 25000}$$

$$2576. \quad \frac{576}{672} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{576}{6720} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{576}{67200} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{576}{672000} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{6 \times 7 \times 2000}$$

$$2581. \quad \frac{580}{638} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 38}$$

$$\frac{580}{6438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 438}$$

$$\frac{580}{64438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 4438}$$

$$\frac{580}{644438} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{6 + 44438}$$

$$2572. \quad \frac{574}{1148} := \frac{5+7+4}{1 \times 1 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{574}{11480} := \frac{5+7+4}{1 \times 1 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{574}{114800} := \frac{5+7+4}{1 \times 1 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{574}{1148000} := \frac{5+7+4}{1 \times 1 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$2577. \quad \frac{576}{792} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+92}$$

$$\frac{576}{7992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+992}$$

$$\frac{576}{79992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+9992}$$

$$\frac{576}{799992} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{7+99992}$$

$$2582. \quad \frac{580}{957} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 57}$$

$$\frac{580}{9657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 657}$$

$$\frac{580}{96657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 6657}$$

$$\frac{580}{966657} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 0}{9 + 66657}$$

$$2573. \quad \frac{574}{14350} := \frac{5+7+4}{(1+4+3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{574}{143500} := \frac{5+7+4}{(1+4+3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{574}{1435000} := \frac{5+7+4}{(1+4+3) \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{574}{14350000} := \frac{5+7+4}{(1+4+3) \times 50000}$$

$$2578. \quad \frac{577}{1154} := \frac{5+7 \times 7}{(1+1) \times 54}$$

$$\frac{577}{11540} := \frac{5+7 \times 7}{(1+1) \times 540}$$

$$\frac{577}{115400} := \frac{5+7 \times 7}{(1+1) \times 5400}$$

$$\frac{577}{1154000} := \frac{5+7 \times 7}{(1+1) \times 54000}$$

$$2583. \quad \frac{581}{1826} := \frac{5+8+1}{18+26}$$

$$\frac{581}{18426} := \frac{5+8+1}{18+426}$$

$$\frac{581}{184426} := \frac{5+8+1}{18+4426}$$

$$\frac{581}{1844426} := \frac{5+8+1}{18+44426}$$

$$2574. \quad \frac{576}{1280} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{576}{12800} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{576}{128000} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$\frac{576}{1280000} := \frac{(5+7) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 80000}$$

$$2579. \quad \frac{579}{772} := \frac{5+7+9}{(7+7) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{579}{7720} := \frac{5+7+9}{(7+7) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{579}{77200} := \frac{5+7+9}{(7+7) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{579}{772000} := \frac{5+7+9}{(7+7) \times 2000}$$

$$2584. \quad \frac{581}{913} := \frac{5+8+1}{9+13}$$

$$\frac{581}{9213} := \frac{5+8+1}{9+213}$$

$$\frac{581}{92213} := \frac{5+8+1}{9+2213}$$

$$\frac{581}{922213} := \frac{5+8+1}{9+22213}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2585. \quad & \frac{582}{1455} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(1 + 4 \times 5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{582}{14550} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(1 + 4 \times 5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{582}{145500} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(1 + 4 \times 5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{582}{1455000} := \frac{5 \times 8 + 2}{(1 + 4 \times 5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2590. \quad & \frac{585}{1287} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 87} \\
 & \frac{585}{12987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 987} \\
 & \frac{585}{129987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 9987} \\
 & \frac{585}{1299987} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{12 + 99987}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2595. \quad & \frac{585}{1456} := \frac{5 + 85}{1 \times 4 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{585}{14560} := \frac{5 + 85}{1 \times 4 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{585}{145600} := \frac{5 + 85}{1 \times 4 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{585}{1456000} := \frac{5 + 85}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2586. \quad & \frac{584}{876} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 4)}{(8 + 7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{584}{8760} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 4)}{(8 + 7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{584}{87600} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 4)}{(8 + 7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{584}{876000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 4)}{(8 + 7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2591. \quad & \frac{585}{1350} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{585}{13500} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{585}{135000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{585}{1350000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2596. \quad & \frac{585}{1485} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{585}{14850} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{585}{148500} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{585}{1485000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2587. \quad & \frac{585}{1125} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{585}{11250} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{585}{112500} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{585}{1125000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2592. \quad & \frac{585}{1352} := \frac{5 + 85}{(1 + 3) \times 52} \\
 & \frac{585}{13520} := \frac{5 + 85}{(1 + 3) \times 520} \\
 & \frac{585}{135200} := \frac{5 + 85}{(1 + 3) \times 5200} \\
 & \frac{585}{1352000} := \frac{5 + 85}{(1 + 3) \times 52000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2597. \quad & \frac{585}{624} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{6 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{585}{6240} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{6 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{585}{62400} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{6 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{585}{624000} := \frac{5 + 8 \times 5}{6 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2588. \quad & \frac{585}{1144} := \frac{5 + 85}{11 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{585}{11440} := \frac{5 + 85}{11 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{585}{114400} := \frac{5 + 85}{11 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{585}{1144000} := \frac{5 + 85}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2593. \quad & \frac{585}{1368} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{585}{13680} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{585}{136800} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{585}{1368000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2598. \quad & \frac{585}{715} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 15} \\
 & \frac{585}{7215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 215} \\
 & \frac{585}{72215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 2215} \\
 & \frac{585}{722215} := \frac{5 + 8 + 5}{7 + 22215}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2589. \quad & \frac{585}{1197} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{585}{11970} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{585}{119700} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{585}{1197000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2594. \quad & \frac{585}{1440} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{585}{14400} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{585}{144000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{585}{1440000} := \frac{5 \times (8 + 5)}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2599. \quad & \frac{585}{728} := \frac{5 + 85}{7 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{585}{7280} := \frac{5 + 85}{7 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{585}{72800} := \frac{5 + 85}{7 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{585}{728000} := \frac{5 + 85}{7 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2600. \quad & \frac{585}{729} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{(7+2) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{585}{7290} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{(7+2) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{585}{72900} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{(7+2) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{585}{729000} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{(7+2) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2605. \quad & \frac{588}{1176} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{588}{11760} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{588}{117600} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{588}{1176000} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2610. \quad & \frac{588}{924} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{588}{9324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{588}{93324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{588}{933324} := \frac{5+8+8}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2601. \quad & \frac{585}{858} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{585}{8658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+658} \\
 & \frac{585}{86658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+6658} \\
 & \frac{585}{866658} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{8+66658}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2606. \quad & \frac{588}{1232} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+32} \\
 & \frac{588}{12432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+432} \\
 & \frac{588}{124432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+4432} \\
 & \frac{588}{1244432} := \frac{5+8+8}{12+44432}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2611. \quad & \frac{592}{1184} := \frac{5+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{592}{11840} := \frac{5+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{592}{118400} := \frac{5+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{592}{1184000} := \frac{5+9+2}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2602. \quad & \frac{585}{891} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+91} \\
 & \frac{585}{8991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+991} \\
 & \frac{585}{89991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+9991} \\
 & \frac{585}{899991} := \frac{5 \times (8+5)}{8+99991}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2607. \quad & \frac{588}{1344} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{588}{13440} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{588}{134400} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{588}{1344000} := \frac{5+8+8}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2612. \quad & \frac{592}{1221} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{592}{12321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+321} \\
 & \frac{592}{123321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+3321} \\
 & \frac{592}{1233321} := \frac{5+9+2}{12+33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2603. \quad & \frac{585}{936} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{(9+3) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{585}{9360} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{(9+3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{585}{93600} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{(9+3) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{585}{936000} := \frac{5+8 \times 5}{(9+3) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2608. \quad & \frac{588}{1848} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+48} \\
 & \frac{588}{18648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+648} \\
 & \frac{588}{186648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+6648} \\
 & \frac{588}{1866648} := \frac{5+8+8}{18+66648}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2613. \quad & \frac{592}{1480} := \frac{5+9+2}{(1+4) \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{592}{14800} := \frac{5+9+2}{(1+4) \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{592}{148000} := \frac{5+9+2}{(1+4) \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{592}{1480000} := \frac{5+9+2}{(1+4) \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2604. \quad & \frac{588}{1120} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{(1+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{588}{11200} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{(1+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{588}{112000} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{588}{1120000} := \frac{5+(8+8)}{(1+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2609. \quad & \frac{588}{616} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+16} \\
 & \frac{588}{6216} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+216} \\
 & \frac{588}{62216} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+2216} \\
 & \frac{588}{622216} := \frac{5+8+8}{6+22216}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2614. \quad & \frac{592}{814} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+14} \\
 & \frac{592}{8214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+214} \\
 & \frac{592}{82214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+2214} \\
 & \frac{592}{822214} := \frac{5+9+2}{8+22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2615. \quad & \frac{593}{1186} := \frac{5 \times 9 + 3}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{593}{11860} := \frac{5 \times 9 + 3}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{593}{118600} := \frac{5 \times 9 + 3}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{593}{1186000} := \frac{5 \times 9 + 3}{(1+1) \times 8 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2620. \quad & \frac{595}{1326} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{595}{13260} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{595}{132600} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{595}{1326000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2625. \quad & \frac{596}{1192} := \frac{5+9+6}{(1+19) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{596}{11920} := \frac{5+9+6}{(1+19) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{596}{119200} := \frac{5+9+6}{(1+19) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{596}{1192000} := \frac{5+9+6}{(1+19) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2616. \quad & \frac{594}{1155} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1+1+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{594}{11550} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1+1+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{594}{115500} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1+1+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{594}{1155000} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1+1+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2621. \quad & \frac{595}{1734} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{595}{17340} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{595}{173400} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{595}{1734000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{17 \times 3 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2626. \quad & \frac{596}{1639} := \frac{5+9+6}{16+39} \\
 & \frac{596}{16539} := \frac{5+9+6}{16+539} \\
 & \frac{596}{165539} := \frac{5+9+6}{16+5539}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2617. \quad & \frac{594}{1200} := \frac{5+94}{1 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{594}{12000} := \frac{5+94}{1 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{594}{120000} := \frac{5+94}{1 \times 20000} \\
 & \frac{594}{1200000} := \frac{5+94}{1 \times 200000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2622. \quad & \frac{595}{17374} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{595}{173740} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{595}{1737400} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{595}{17374000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2627. \quad & \frac{602}{1204} := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 04} \\
 & \frac{602}{12040} := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 040} \\
 & \frac{602}{120400} := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{602}{1204000} := \frac{6+0 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2618. \quad & \frac{594}{1485} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1^4+8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{594}{14850} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1^4+8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{594}{148500} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1^4+8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{594}{1485000} := \frac{5+9+4}{(1^4+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2623. \quad & \frac{595}{612} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{6 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{595}{6120} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{6 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{595}{61200} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{6 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{595}{612000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{6 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2619. \quad & \frac{595}{1275} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{595}{12750} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{595}{127500} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{595}{1275000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2624. \quad & \frac{595}{748} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{(7+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{595}{7480} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{(7+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{595}{74800} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{(7+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{595}{748000} := \frac{5 \times (9+5)}{(7+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2628. \quad & \frac{603}{1072} := \frac{6+03}{(1+07) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{603}{10720} := \frac{6+03}{(1+07) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{603}{107200} := \frac{6+03}{(1+07) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{603}{1072000} := \frac{6+03}{(1+07) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2629. \quad \frac{603}{1206} := \frac{6+0 \times 3}{1 \times 2 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{603}{12060} := \frac{6+0 \times 3}{1 \times 2 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{603}{120600} := \frac{6+0 \times 3}{1 \times 2 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{603}{1206000} := \frac{6+0 \times 3}{1 \times 2 \times 06000}$$

$$2634. \quad \frac{605}{1815} := \frac{6+05}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{605}{18315} := \frac{6+05}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{605}{183315} := \frac{6+05}{18+3315}$$

$$2639. \quad \frac{606}{1313} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1^3 \times 13}$$

$$\frac{606}{13130} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1^3 \times 130}$$

$$\frac{606}{131300} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1^3 \times 1300}$$

$$\frac{606}{1313000} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1^3 \times 13000}$$

$$2630. \quad \frac{603}{1340} := \frac{6 \times 03}{1^3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{603}{13400} := \frac{6 \times 03}{1^3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{603}{134000} := \frac{6 \times 03}{1^3 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{603}{1340000} := \frac{6 \times 03}{1^3 \times 40000}$$

$$2635. \quad \frac{606}{1010} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1 \times 010}$$

$$\frac{606}{10100} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1 \times 0100}$$

$$\frac{606}{101000} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1 \times 01000}$$

$$\frac{606}{1010000} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{1 \times 010000}$$

$$2640. \quad \frac{606}{1414} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{14 \times 1^4}$$

$$\frac{606}{14140} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{14 \times 140}$$

$$\frac{606}{141400} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{14 \times 1400}$$

$$\frac{606}{1414000} := \frac{6+0 \times 6}{14 \times 14000}$$

$$2631. \quad \frac{603}{1474} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{603}{14740} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{603}{147400} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{603}{1474000} := \frac{6 \times 03}{(1 \times 4 + 7) \times 4000}$$

$$2636. \quad \frac{606}{1111} := \frac{60+6}{11 \times 11}$$

$$\frac{606}{11110} := \frac{60+6}{11 \times 110}$$

$$\frac{606}{111100} := \frac{60+6}{11 \times 1100}$$

$$\frac{606}{1111000} := \frac{60+6}{11 \times 11000}$$

$$2641. \quad \frac{609}{1015} := \frac{6+0 \times 9}{(1+01) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{609}{10150} := \frac{6+0 \times 9}{(1+01) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{609}{101500} := \frac{6+0 \times 9}{(1+01) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{609}{1015000} := \frac{6+0 \times 9}{(1+01) \times 5000}$$

$$2632. \quad \frac{604}{1359} := \frac{60+4}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{604}{13590} := \frac{60+4}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{604}{135900} := \frac{60+4}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{604}{1359000} := \frac{60+4}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9000}$$

$$2637. \quad \frac{606}{1111} := \frac{6+06}{11+11}$$

$$\frac{606}{11211} := \frac{6+06}{11+211}$$

$$\frac{606}{112211} := \frac{6+06}{11+2211}$$

$$\frac{606}{1122211} := \frac{6+06}{11+22211}$$

$$2642. \quad \frac{611}{1222} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 2 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{611}{12220} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 2 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{611}{122200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 2 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{611}{1222000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 1}{(1+2) \times 2 \times 2000}$$

$$2633. \quad \frac{605}{1210} := \frac{6+0 \times 5}{12 \times 1 + 0}$$

$$\frac{605}{12100} := \frac{6+0 \times 5}{12 \times 10 + 0}$$

$$\frac{605}{121000} := \frac{6+0 \times 5}{12 \times 100 + 0}$$

$$\frac{605}{1210000} := \frac{6+0 \times 5}{12 \times 1000 + 0}$$

$$2638. \quad \frac{606}{1212} := \frac{6+06}{1 \times (2 \times 12)}$$

$$\frac{606}{12120} := \frac{6+06}{1 \times 2 \times 120}$$

$$\frac{606}{121200} := \frac{6+06}{1 \times 2 \times 1200}$$

$$\frac{606}{1212000} := \frac{6+06}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}$$

$$2643. \quad \frac{612}{1020} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 020}$$

$$\frac{612}{10200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 0200}$$

$$\frac{612}{102000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 02000}$$

$$\frac{612}{1020000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 020000}$$

2644.

$$\frac{612}{1088} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{1 \times 08 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{612}{10880} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{1 \times 08 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{612}{108800} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{1 \times 08 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{612}{1088000} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{1 \times 08 \times 8000}$$

2649.

$$\frac{612}{1292} := \frac{6 + 12}{(1 + 2 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{612}{12920} := \frac{6 + 12}{(1 + 2 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{612}{129200} := \frac{6 + 12}{(1 + 2 \times 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{612}{1292000} := \frac{6 + 12}{(1 + 2 \times 9) \times 2000}$$

2654.

$$\frac{612}{17374} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{612}{173740} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{612}{1737400} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{612}{17374000} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000}$$

2645.

$$\frac{612}{1122} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 22}$$

$$\frac{612}{11220} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 220}$$

$$\frac{612}{112200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 2200}$$

$$\frac{612}{1122000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 22000}$$

2650.

$$\frac{612}{1326} := \frac{6 \times 12}{13 \times 2 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{612}{13260} := \frac{6 \times 12}{13 \times 2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{612}{132600} := \frac{6 \times 12}{13 \times 2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{612}{1326000} := \frac{6 \times 12}{13 \times 2 \times 6000}$$

2655.

$$\frac{612}{748} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7 + 4) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{612}{7480} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7 + 4) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{612}{74800} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7 + 4) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{612}{748000} := \frac{6 \times 12}{(7 + 4) \times 8000}$$

2646.

$$\frac{612}{1122} := \frac{6 + 12}{11 + 22}$$

$$\frac{612}{11322} := \frac{6 + 12}{11 + 322}$$

$$\frac{612}{113322} := \frac{6 + 12}{11 + 3322}$$

$$\frac{612}{1133322} := \frac{6 + 12}{11 + 33322}$$

2651.

$$\frac{612}{1428} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^4 \times 28}$$

$$\frac{612}{14280} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^4 \times 280}$$

$$\frac{612}{142800} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^4 \times 2800}$$

$$\frac{612}{1428000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^4 \times 28000}$$

2656.

$$\frac{612}{816} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{8 \times 1 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{612}{8160} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{8 \times 1 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{612}{81600} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{8 \times 1 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{612}{816000} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}$$

2647.

$$\frac{612}{1224} := \frac{6 + 1 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{612}{12240} := \frac{6 + 1 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{612}{122400} := \frac{6 + 1 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{612}{1224000} := \frac{6 + 1 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

2652.

$$\frac{612}{1445} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{612}{14450} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{612}{144500} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{612}{1445000} := \frac{6^{1 \times 2}}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5000}$$

2648.

$$\frac{612}{1275} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{612}{12750} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{612}{127500} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{612}{1275000} := \frac{6 \times 12}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}$$

2653.

$$\frac{612}{1734} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^7 \times 34}$$

$$\frac{612}{17340} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^7 \times 340}$$

$$\frac{612}{173400} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^7 \times 3400}$$

$$\frac{612}{1734000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 2}{1^7 \times 34000}$$

2657.

$$\frac{612}{952} := \frac{6 + 12}{(9 + 5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{612}{9520} := \frac{6 + 12}{(9 + 5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{612}{95200} := \frac{6 + 12}{(9 + 5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{612}{952000} := \frac{6 + 12}{(9 + 5) \times 2000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2658. \quad & \frac{614}{1228} := \frac{(6+1) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 28} \\
 & \frac{614}{12280} := \frac{(6+1) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 280} \\
 & \frac{614}{122800} := \frac{(6+1) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 2800} \\
 & \frac{614}{1228000} := \frac{(6+1) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 28000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2663. \quad & \frac{615}{1435} := \frac{6 \times 15}{14 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{615}{14350} := \frac{6 \times 15}{14 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{615}{143500} := \frac{6 \times 15}{14 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{615}{1435000} := \frac{6 \times 15}{14 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2668. \quad & \frac{616}{1232} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 6}{12 \times 3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{616}{12320} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 6}{12 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{616}{123200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 6}{12 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{616}{1232000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 6}{12 \times 3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2659. \quad & \frac{615}{1025} := \frac{6 \times 1^5}{1 \times 02 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{615}{10250} := \frac{6 \times 1^5}{1 \times 02 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{615}{102500} := \frac{6 \times 1^5}{1 \times 02 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{615}{1025000} := \frac{6 \times 1^5}{1 \times 02 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2664. \quad & \frac{615}{1476} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+4+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{615}{14760} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+4+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{615}{147600} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+4+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{615}{1476000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+4+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2669. \quad & \frac{616}{1232} := \frac{6+16}{12+32} \\
 & \frac{616}{12432} := \frac{6+16}{12+432} \\
 & \frac{616}{124432} := \frac{6+16}{12+4432} \\
 & \frac{616}{1244432} := \frac{6+16}{12+44432}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2660. \quad & \frac{615}{1230} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{615}{12300} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{615}{123000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{615}{1230000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 2 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2665. \quad & \frac{615}{820} := \frac{6+1+5}{8 \times 2+0} \\
 & \frac{615}{8200} := \frac{6+1+5}{8 \times 20+0} \\
 & \frac{615}{82000} := \frac{6+1+5}{8 \times 200+0} \\
 & \frac{615}{820000} := \frac{6+1+5}{8 \times 2000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2670. \quad & \frac{616}{1344} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{616}{13440} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{616}{134400} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{616}{1344000} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2661. \quad & \frac{615}{1312} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+31) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{615}{13120} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+31) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{615}{131200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+31) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{615}{1312000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+31) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2666. \quad & \frac{616}{1120} := \frac{6+16}{(1+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{616}{11200} := \frac{6+16}{(1+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{616}{112000} := \frac{6+16}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{616}{1120000} := \frac{6+16}{(1+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2671. \quad & \frac{616}{13728} := \frac{6 \times (1+6)}{13 \times (7+2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{616}{137280} := \frac{6 \times (1+6)}{13 \times (7+2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{616}{1372800} := \frac{6 \times (1+6)}{13 \times (7+2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{616}{13728000} := \frac{6 \times (1+6)}{13 \times (7+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2662. \quad & \frac{615}{1353} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13+53} \\
 & \frac{615}{13653} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13+653} \\
 & \frac{615}{136653} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13+6653} \\
 & \frac{615}{1366653} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 5}{13+66653}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2667. \quad & \frac{616}{1176} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{616}{11760} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{616}{117600} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{616}{1176000} := \frac{6+16}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2672. \quad & \frac{616}{924} := \frac{6+16}{9+24} \\
 & \frac{616}{9324} := \frac{6+16}{9+324} \\
 & \frac{616}{93324} := \frac{6+16}{9+3324} \\
 & \frac{616}{933324} := \frac{6+16}{9+33324}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2673. \quad & \frac{617}{1234} := \frac{6+1+7}{(1+2 \times 3) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{617}{12340} := \frac{6+1+7}{(1+2 \times 3) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{617}{123400} := \frac{6+1+7}{(1+2 \times 3) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{617}{1234000} := \frac{6+1+7}{(1+2 \times 3) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2678. \quad & \frac{618}{1442} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{14 \times 4 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{618}{14420} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{14 \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{618}{144200} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{14 \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{618}{1442000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{14 \times 4 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2683. \quad & \frac{621}{1150} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{621}{11500} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{621}{115000} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 1 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{621}{1150000} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2674. \quad & \frac{618}{1133} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{11 \times 3 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{618}{11330} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{11 \times 3 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{618}{113300} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{11 \times 3 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{618}{1133000} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{11 \times 3 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2679. \quad & \frac{618}{824} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{8 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{618}{8240} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{8 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{618}{82400} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{8 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{618}{824000} := \frac{6 \times 1 \times 8}{8 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2684. \quad & \frac{621}{1173} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{621}{11730} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{621}{117300} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{621}{1173000} := \frac{6+21}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2675. \quad & \frac{618}{1133} := \frac{6+18}{11+33} \\
 & \frac{618}{11433} := \frac{6+18}{11+433} \\
 & \frac{618}{114433} := \frac{6+18}{11+4433} \\
 & \frac{618}{1144433} := \frac{6+18}{11+44433}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2680. \quad & \frac{619}{1238} := \frac{6 \times (1+9)}{(12+3) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{619}{12380} := \frac{6 \times (1+9)}{(12+3) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{619}{123800} := \frac{6 \times (1+9)}{(12+3) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{619}{1238000} := \frac{6 \times (1+9)}{(12+3) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2685. \quad & \frac{621}{1242} := \frac{6+2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{621}{12420} := \frac{6+2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{621}{124200} := \frac{6+2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{621}{1242000} := \frac{6+2 \times 1}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2676. \quad & \frac{618}{1236} := \frac{61+8}{1 \times 23 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{618}{12360} := \frac{61+8}{1 \times 23 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{618}{123600} := \frac{61+8}{1 \times 23 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{618}{1236000} := \frac{61+8}{1 \times 23 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2681. \quad & \frac{620}{1705} := \frac{6+2+0}{17+05} \\
 & \frac{620}{17205} := \frac{6+2+0}{17+205} \\
 & \frac{620}{172205} := \frac{6+2+0}{17+2205}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2686. \quad & \frac{621}{1380} := \frac{6^2 \times 1}{1^3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{621}{13800} := \frac{(6^2 \times 1)}{1^3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{621}{138000} := \frac{(6^2 \times 1)}{1^3 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{621}{1380000} := \frac{(6^2 \times 1)}{1^3 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2677. \quad & \frac{618}{1339} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 39} \\
 & \frac{618}{13390} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 390} \\
 & \frac{618}{133900} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 3900} \\
 & \frac{618}{1339000} := \frac{6 \times (1+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 39000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2682. \quad & \frac{621}{1035} := \frac{6+2+1}{1 \times 03 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{621}{10350} := \frac{6+2+1}{1 \times 03 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{621}{103500} := \frac{6+2+1}{1 \times 03 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{621}{1035000} := \frac{6+2+1}{1 \times 03 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2687. \quad & \frac{621}{1449} := \frac{6^{2+1}}{14 \times 4 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{621}{14490} := \frac{6^{2+1}}{14 \times 4 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{621}{144900} := \frac{6^{2+1}}{14 \times 4 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{621}{1449000} := \frac{6^{2+1}}{14 \times 4 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2688.

$$\frac{621}{7659} := \frac{6+21}{(7+6 \times 5) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{621}{76590} := \frac{6+21}{(7+6 \times 5) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{621}{765900} := \frac{6+21}{(7+6 \times 5) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{621}{7659000} := \frac{6+21}{(7+6 \times 5) \times 9000}$$

2693.

$$\frac{623}{712} := \frac{6+2^3}{(7+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{623}{7120} := \frac{6+2^3}{(7+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{623}{71200} := \frac{6+2^3}{(7+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{623}{712000} := \frac{6+2^3}{(7+1) \times 2000}$$

2698.

$$\frac{624}{1352} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{(1+3) \times 52}$$

$$\frac{624}{13520} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{(1+3) \times 520}$$

$$\frac{624}{135200} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{(1+3) \times 5200}$$

$$\frac{624}{1352000} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{(1+3) \times 52000}$$

2689.

$$\frac{622}{1244} := \frac{(6+2) \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{622}{12440} := \frac{(6+2) \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{622}{124400} := \frac{(6+2) \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{622}{1244000} := \frac{(6+2) \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

2694.

$$\frac{624}{1144} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{11 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{624}{11440} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{11 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{624}{114400} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{11 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{624}{1144000} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

2699.

$$\frac{624}{1365} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{(1^3 + 6) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{624}{13650} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{(1^3 + 6) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{624}{136500} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{(1^3 + 6) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{624}{1365000} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{(1^3 + 6) \times 5000}$$

2690.

$$\frac{623}{1246} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{623}{12460} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{623}{124600} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{623}{1246000} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 4 \times 6000}$$

2695.

$$\frac{624}{1248} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{1^2 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{624}{12480} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{1^2 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{624}{124800} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{1^2 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{624}{1248000} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 4}{1^2 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

2700.

$$\frac{624}{1456} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{1 \times 4 \times 56}$$

$$\frac{624}{14560} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{1 \times 4 \times 560}$$

$$\frac{624}{145600} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{1 \times 4 \times 5600}$$

$$\frac{624}{1456000} := \frac{6 \times 2^4}{1 \times 4 \times 56000}$$

2691.

$$\frac{623}{1335} := \frac{6+2^3}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{623}{13350} := \frac{6+2^3}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{623}{133500} := \frac{6+2^3}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{623}{1335000} := \frac{6+2^3}{(1 \times 3 + 3) \times 5000}$$

2696.

$$\frac{624}{1287} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 87}$$

$$\frac{624}{12987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 987}$$

$$\frac{624}{129987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 9987}$$

$$\frac{624}{1299987} := \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{12 + 99987}$$

2692.

$$\frac{623}{1424} := \frac{6+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{623}{14240} := \frac{6+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{623}{142400} := \frac{6+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{623}{1424000} := \frac{6+2^3}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 4000}$$

2697.

$$\frac{624}{1300} := \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{624}{13000} := \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{624}{130000} := \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 30000}$$

$$\frac{624}{1300000} := \frac{6 \times 24}{1 \times 300000}$$

2701.

$$\frac{624}{832} := \frac{6 \times (2+4)}{8 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{624}{8320} := \frac{6 \times (2+4)}{8 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{624}{83200} := \frac{6 \times (2+4)}{8 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{624}{832000} := \frac{6 \times (2+4)}{8 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{624}{858} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 58} \\
 \frac{624}{8658} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 658} \\
 \frac{624}{86658} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 6658} \\
 \frac{624}{86658} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{8 + 66658}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1045} &:= \frac{6+2+7}{(1+04) \times 5} \\
 \frac{627}{10450} &:= \frac{6+2+7}{(1+04) \times 50} \\
 \frac{627}{104500} &:= \frac{6+2+7}{(1+04) \times 500} \\
 \frac{627}{1045000} &:= \frac{6+2+7}{(1+04) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1254} &:= \frac{6+27}{12+54} \\
 \frac{627}{12654} &:= \frac{6+27}{12+654} \\
 \frac{627}{126654} &:= \frac{6+27}{12+6654} \\
 \frac{627}{1266654} &:= \frac{6+27}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{624}{936} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+3) \times 6} \\
 \frac{624}{9360} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+3) \times 60} \\
 \frac{624}{93600} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+3) \times 600} \\
 \frac{624}{936000} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 4}{(9+3) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1045} &:= \frac{6+27}{10+45} \\
 \frac{627}{10545} &:= \frac{6+27}{10+545} \\
 \frac{627}{105545} &:= \frac{6+27}{10+5545} \\
 \frac{627}{1055545} &:= \frac{6+27}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1368} &:= \frac{6+27}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8} \\
 \frac{627}{13680} &:= \frac{6+27}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80} \\
 \frac{627}{136800} &:= \frac{6+27}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800} \\
 \frac{627}{1368000} &:= \frac{6+27}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{625}{1375} &:= \frac{(6+2) \times 5}{13+75} \\
 \frac{625}{13875} &:= \frac{(6+2) \times 5}{13+875} \\
 \frac{625}{138875} &:= \frac{(6+2) \times 5}{13+8875} \\
 \frac{625}{1388875} &:= \frac{(6+2) \times 5}{13+88875}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1155} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1+1+5) \times 5} \\
 \frac{627}{11550} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1+1+5) \times 50} \\
 \frac{627}{115500} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1+1+5) \times 500} \\
 \frac{627}{1155000} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1+1+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1463} &:= \frac{6+27}{14+63} \\
 \frac{627}{14763} &:= \frac{6+27}{14+763} \\
 \frac{627}{147763} &:= \frac{6+27}{14+7763} \\
 \frac{627}{1477763} &:= \frac{6+27}{14+77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{626}{1252} &:= \frac{6+26}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2} \\
 \frac{626}{12520} &:= \frac{6+26}{1 \times 2^5 \times 20} \\
 \frac{626}{125200} &:= \frac{6+26}{1 \times 2^5 \times 200} \\
 \frac{626}{1252000} &:= \frac{6+26}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1197} &:= \frac{6+27}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 \frac{627}{11970} &:= \frac{6+27}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 \frac{627}{119700} &:= \frac{6+27}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 \frac{627}{1197000} &:= \frac{6+27}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1485} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1^4+8) \times 5} \\
 \frac{627}{14850} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1^4+8) \times 50} \\
 \frac{627}{148500} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1^4+8) \times 500} \\
 \frac{627}{1485000} &:= \frac{6 \times 2+7}{(1^4+8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{626}{939} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 6}{(9+3) \times 9} \\
 \frac{626}{9390} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 6}{(9+3) \times 90} \\
 \frac{626}{93900} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 6}{(9+3) \times 900} \\
 \frac{626}{939000} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 6}{(9+3) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{627}{1254} &:= \frac{6+2 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 5 \times 4} \\
 \frac{627}{12540} &:= \frac{6+2 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 5 \times 40} \\
 \frac{627}{125400} &:= \frac{6+2 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 5 \times 400} \\
 \frac{627}{1254000} &:= \frac{6+2 \times 7}{1 \times 2 \times 5 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{628}{1256} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times 2^5 \times 6} \\
 \frac{628}{12560} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times 2^5 \times 60} \\
 \frac{628}{125600} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times 2^5 \times 600} \\
 \frac{628}{1256000} &:= \frac{6 \times 2 \times 8}{1 \times 2^5 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2717. \quad \frac{628}{1413} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{(14 + 1) \times 3}$$

$$\frac{628}{14130} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{(14 + 1) \times 30}$$

$$\frac{628}{141300} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{(14 + 1) \times 300}$$

$$\frac{628}{1413000} := \frac{6 \times 2 + 8}{(14 + 1) \times 3000}$$

$$2722. \quad \frac{629}{1258} := \frac{6 + 2 \times 9}{(1^2 + 5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{629}{12580} := \frac{6 + 2 \times 9}{(1^2 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{629}{125800} := \frac{6 + 2 \times 9}{(1^2 + 5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{629}{1258000} := \frac{6 + 2 \times 9}{(1^2 + 5) \times 8000}$$

$$2727. \quad \frac{632}{1738} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17 + 38}$$

$$\frac{632}{17538} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17 + 538}$$

$$\frac{632}{175538} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 2}{17 + 5538}$$

$$2718. \quad \frac{628}{1727} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 27}$$

$$\frac{628}{17427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 427}$$

$$\frac{628}{174427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 4427}$$

$$\frac{628}{1744427} := \frac{6 + 2 + 8}{17 + 44427}$$

$$2723. \quad \frac{629}{1480} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(1 + 4) \times 8 + 0}$$

$$\frac{629}{14800} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(1 + 4) \times 80 + 0}$$

$$\frac{629}{148000} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(1 + 4) \times 800 + 0}$$

$$\frac{629}{1480000} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{(1 + 4) \times 8000 + 0}$$

$$2728. \quad \frac{632}{948} := \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times 4 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{632}{9480} := \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times 4 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{632}{94800} := \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times 4 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{632}{948000} := \frac{6 \times 32}{9 \times 4 \times 8000}$$

$$2719. \quad \frac{628}{785} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 8)}{(7 + 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{628}{7850} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 8)}{(7 + 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{628}{78500} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 8)}{(7 + 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{628}{785000} := \frac{6 \times (2 + 8)}{(7 + 8) \times 5000}$$

$$2724. \quad \frac{630}{1155} := \frac{6 + 30}{11 + 55}$$

$$\frac{630}{11655} := \frac{6 + 30}{11 + 655}$$

$$\frac{630}{116655} := \frac{6 + 30}{11 + 6655}$$

$$\frac{630}{1166655} := \frac{6 + 30}{11 + 66655}$$

$$2729. \quad \frac{633}{1055} := \frac{6 + 3 \times 3}{1 \times 05 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{633}{10550} := \frac{6 + 3 \times 3}{1 \times 05 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{633}{105500} := \frac{6 + 3 \times 3}{1 \times 05 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{633}{1055000} := \frac{6 + 3 \times 3}{1 \times 05 \times 5000}$$

$$2720. \quad \frac{629}{1184} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{629}{11840} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{629}{118400} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{629}{1184000} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

$$2725. \quad \frac{631}{1262} := \frac{63 + 1}{1 \times 2^6 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{631}{12620} := \frac{63 + 1}{1 \times 2^6 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{631}{126200} := \frac{63 + 1}{1 \times 2^6 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{631}{1262000} := \frac{63 + 1}{1 \times 2^6 \times 2000}$$

$$2730. \quad \frac{633}{1266} := \frac{63 + 3}{1 \times 2 \times 66}$$

$$\frac{633}{12660} := \frac{63 + 3}{1 \times 2 \times 660}$$

$$\frac{633}{126600} := \frac{63 + 3}{1 \times 2 \times 6600}$$

$$\frac{633}{1266000} := \frac{63 + 3}{1 \times 2 \times 66000}$$

$$2721. \quad \frac{629}{1221} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{12 + 21}$$

$$\frac{629}{12321} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{12 + 321}$$

$$\frac{629}{123321} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{12 + 3321}$$

$$\frac{629}{1233321} := \frac{6 + 2 + 9}{12 + 33321}$$

$$2726. \quad \frac{632}{1264} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 2}{(12 + 6) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{632}{12640} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 2}{(12 + 6) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{632}{126400} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 2}{(12 + 6) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{632}{1264000} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 2}{(12 + 6) \times 4000}$$

$$2731. \quad \frac{633}{1477} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 3}{1^4 \times 7 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{633}{14770} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 3}{1^4 \times 7 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{633}{147700} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 3}{1^4 \times 7 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{633}{1477000} := \frac{6 \times 3 + 3}{1^4 \times 7 \times 7000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2732. \quad & \frac{633}{844} := \frac{6 \times (3+3)}{(8+4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{633}{8440} := \frac{6 \times (3+3)}{(8+4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{633}{84400} := \frac{6 \times (3+3)}{(8+4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{633}{844000} := \frac{6 \times (3+3)}{(8+4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2737. \quad & \frac{636}{1325} := \frac{6+3 \times 6}{(1+3^2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{636}{13250} := \frac{6+3 \times 6}{(1+3^2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{636}{132500} := \frac{6+3 \times 6}{(1+3^2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{636}{1325000} := \frac{6+3 \times 6}{(1+3^2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2742. \quad & \frac{637}{975} := \frac{63 \times 7}{9 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{637}{9750} := \frac{63 \times 7}{9 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{637}{97500} := \frac{63 \times 7}{9 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{637}{975000} := \frac{63 \times 7}{9 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2733. \quad & \frac{634}{1268} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4}{(12+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{634}{12680} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4}{(12+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{634}{126800} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4}{(12+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{634}{1268000} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 4}{(12+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2738. \quad & \frac{636}{1378} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 78} \\
 & \frac{636}{13780} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 780} \\
 & \frac{636}{137800} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 7800} \\
 & \frac{636}{1378000} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 78000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2743. \quad & \frac{638}{1160} := \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(1+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{638}{11600} := \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(1+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{638}{116000} := \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(1+1) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{638}{1160000} := \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(1+1) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2734. \quad & \frac{636}{1166} := \frac{6 \times 36}{11 \times 6 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{636}{11660} := \frac{6 \times 36}{11 \times 6 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{636}{116600} := \frac{6 \times 36}{11 \times 6 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{636}{1166000} := \frac{6 \times 36}{11 \times 6 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2739. \quad & \frac{637}{1274} := \frac{6+3+7}{(1^2+7) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{637}{12740} := \frac{6+3+7}{(1^2+7) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{637}{127400} := \frac{6+3+7}{(1^2+7) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{637}{1274000} := \frac{6+3+7}{(1^2+7) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2744. \quad & \frac{638}{1276} := \frac{6+3 \times 8}{(1+2+7) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{638}{12760} := \frac{6+3 \times 8}{(1+2+7) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{638}{127600} := \frac{6+3 \times 8}{(1+2+7) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{638}{1276000} := \frac{6+3 \times 8}{(1+2+7) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2735. \quad & \frac{636}{1166} := \frac{6+36}{11+66} \\
 & \frac{636}{11766} := \frac{6+36}{11+766} \\
 & \frac{636}{117766} := \frac{6+36}{11+7766} \\
 & \frac{636}{1177766} := \frac{6+36}{11+77766}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2740. \quad & \frac{637}{819} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{637}{8190} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{637}{81900} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{637}{819000} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{(8+1) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2736. \quad & \frac{636}{1272} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 72} \\
 & \frac{636}{12720} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 720} \\
 & \frac{636}{127200} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{636}{1272000} := \frac{6 \times 3 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2741. \quad & \frac{637}{910} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{637}{9100} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{637}{91000} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{9 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{637}{910000} := \frac{(6+3) \times 7}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2745. \quad & \frac{638}{1276} := \frac{6+38}{12+76} \\
 & \frac{638}{12876} := \frac{6+38}{12+876} \\
 & \frac{638}{128876} := \frac{6+38}{12+8876} \\
 & \frac{638}{1288876} := \frac{6+38}{12+88876}
 \end{aligned}$$

2746.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{638}{957} &:= \frac{6+38}{9+57} \\ \frac{638}{9657} &:= \frac{6+38}{9+657} \\ \frac{638}{96657} &:= \frac{6+38}{9+6657} \\ \frac{96657}{638} &:= \frac{9+6657}{6+38} \\ \frac{96657}{96657} &:= \frac{9+66657}{9+66657} \end{aligned}$$

2751.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{639}{781} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+81} \\ \frac{639}{7881} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+881} \\ \frac{639}{78881} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+9)}{7+8881} \\ \frac{78881}{639} &:= \frac{7+8881}{6 \times (3+9)} \\ \frac{78881}{78881} &:= \frac{7+88881}{7+88881} \end{aligned}$$

2756.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1012} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{(10+1) \times 2} \\ \frac{644}{10120} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{(10+1) \times 20} \\ \frac{644}{101200} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{(10+1) \times 200} \\ \frac{101200}{644} &:= \frac{(10+1) \times 200}{6+4+4} \\ \frac{1012000}{644} &:= \frac{(10+1) \times 2000}{6+4+4} \end{aligned}$$

2747.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{638}{986} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(9+8) \times 6} \\ \frac{638}{9860} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(9+8) \times 60} \\ \frac{638}{98600} &:= \frac{6 \times (3+8)}{(9+8) \times 600} \\ \frac{98600}{638} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 600}{6 \times (3+8)} \\ \frac{986000}{638} &:= \frac{(9+8) \times 6000}{6 \times (3+8)} \end{aligned}$$

2752.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{640}{704} &:= \frac{6+4+0}{7+04} \\ \frac{640}{7104} &:= \frac{6+4+0}{7+104} \\ \frac{640}{71104} &:= \frac{6+4+0}{7+1104} \\ \frac{71104}{640} &:= \frac{7+1104}{6+4+0} \\ \frac{711104}{640} &:= \frac{7+11104}{6+4+0} \end{aligned}$$

2757.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1012} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+12} \\ \frac{644}{10212} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+212} \\ \frac{644}{102212} &:= \frac{6+4+4}{10+2212} \\ \frac{102212}{644} &:= \frac{10+2212}{6+4+4} \\ \frac{1022212}{644} &:= \frac{10+22212}{6+4+4} \end{aligned}$$

2748.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{639}{1065} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{1 \times 06 \times 5} \\ \frac{639}{10650} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{1 \times 06 \times 50} \\ \frac{639}{106500} &:= \frac{6+3+9}{1 \times 06 \times 500} \\ \frac{106500}{639} &:= \frac{1 \times 06 \times 500}{6+3+9} \\ \frac{1065000}{639} &:= \frac{1 \times 06 \times 5000}{6+3+9} \end{aligned}$$

2753.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{642}{1177} &:= \frac{6+42}{11+77} \\ \frac{642}{11877} &:= \frac{6+42}{11+877} \\ \frac{642}{118877} &:= \frac{6+42}{11+8877} \\ \frac{118877}{642} &:= \frac{11+8877}{6+42} \\ \frac{1188877}{642} &:= \frac{11+88877}{6+42} \end{aligned}$$

2758.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1127} &:= \frac{6 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 12 \times 7} \\ \frac{644}{11270} &:= \frac{6 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 12 \times 70} \\ \frac{644}{112700} &:= \frac{6 \times (4+4)}{1 \times 12 \times 700} \\ \frac{112700}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 700}{6 \times (4+4)} \\ \frac{1127000}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 7000}{6 \times (4+4)} \end{aligned}$$

2749.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{639}{1136} &:= \frac{6 \times 3+9}{(1+1)^3 \times 6} \\ \frac{639}{11360} &:= \frac{6 \times 3+9}{(1+1)^3 \times 60} \\ \frac{639}{113600} &:= \frac{6 \times 3+9}{(1+1)^3 \times 600} \\ \frac{113600}{639} &:= \frac{(1+1)^3 \times 600}{6 \times 3+9} \\ \frac{1136000}{639} &:= \frac{(1+1)^3 \times 6000}{6 \times 3+9} \end{aligned}$$

2754.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{642}{1284} &:= \frac{6+42}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{642}{12840} &:= \frac{6+42}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{642}{128400} &:= \frac{6+42}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{128400}{642} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 8 \times 400}{6+42} \\ \frac{1284000}{642} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 8 \times 4000}{6+42} \end{aligned}$$

2759.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1150} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 50} \\ \frac{644}{11500} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 500} \\ \frac{644}{115000} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 1 \times 5000} \\ \frac{115000}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 1 \times 5000}{6 \times 4+4} \\ \frac{1150000}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 1 \times 50000}{6 \times 4+4} \end{aligned}$$

2750.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{639}{1420} &:= \frac{6+39}{(1+4) \times 20} \\ \frac{639}{14200} &:= \frac{6+39}{(1+4) \times 200} \\ \frac{639}{142000} &:= \frac{6+39}{(1+4) \times 2000} \\ \frac{142000}{639} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 2000}{6+39} \\ \frac{1420000}{639} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 20000}{6+39} \end{aligned}$$

2755.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{643}{1286} &:= \frac{6 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 6} \\ \frac{643}{12860} &:= \frac{6 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 60} \\ \frac{643}{128600} &:= \frac{6 \times 4 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 600} \\ \frac{128600}{643} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 8 \times 600}{6 \times 4 \times 3} \\ \frac{1286000}{643} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 8 \times 6000}{6 \times 4 \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

2760.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{644}{1173} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\ \frac{644}{11730} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\ \frac{644}{117300} &:= \frac{6 \times 4+4}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\ \frac{117300}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 17 \times 300}{6 \times 4+4} \\ \frac{1173000}{644} &:= \frac{1 \times 17 \times 3000}{6 \times 4+4} \end{aligned}$$

$$2761. \quad \frac{644}{1288} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{644}{12880} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{644}{128800} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{644}{1288000} := \frac{6 \times 4 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 8000}$$

$$2766. \quad \frac{648}{1125} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 125}$$

$$\frac{648}{11250} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 1250}$$

$$\frac{648}{112500} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 12500}$$

$$2771. \quad \frac{648}{1296} := \frac{6+48}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{648}{12960} := \frac{6+48}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{648}{129600} := \frac{6+48}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{648}{1296000} := \frac{6+48}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}$$

$$2762. \quad \frac{644}{1449} := \frac{64+4}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{644}{14490} := \frac{64+4}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{644}{144900} := \frac{64+4}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{644}{1449000} := \frac{64+4}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9000}$$

$$2767. \quad \frac{648}{1134} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1+13) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{648}{11340} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1+13) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{648}{113400} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1+13) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{648}{1134000} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{(1+13) \times 4000}$$

$$2772. \quad \frac{648}{1350} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{648}{13500} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{648}{135000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{648}{1350000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}$$

$$2763. \quad \frac{645}{1075} := \frac{6+45}{(10+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{645}{10750} := \frac{6+45}{(10+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{645}{107500} := \frac{6+45}{(10+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{645}{1075000} := \frac{6+45}{(10+7) \times 5000}$$

$$2768. \quad \frac{648}{1152} := \frac{6+4+8}{(1+15) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{648}{11520} := \frac{6+4+8}{(1+15) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{648}{115200} := \frac{6+4+8}{(1+15) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{648}{1152000} := \frac{6+4+8}{(1+15) \times 2000}$$

$$2773. \quad \frac{648}{1368} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{648}{13680} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{648}{136800} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{648}{1368000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

$$2764. \quad \frac{645}{1290} := \frac{6 \times (4+5)}{12 \times 9 + 0}$$

$$\frac{645}{12900} := \frac{6 \times (4+5)}{12 \times 90 + 0}$$

$$\frac{645}{129000} := \frac{6 \times (4+5)}{12 \times 900 + 0}$$

$$\frac{645}{1290000} := \frac{6 \times (4+5)}{12 \times 9000 + 0}$$

$$2769. \quad \frac{648}{1197} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 7}$$

$$\frac{648}{11970} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{648}{119700} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{648}{1197000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}$$

$$2774. \quad \frac{648}{1440} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{648}{14400} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{648}{144000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{648}{1440000} := \frac{6 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}$$

$$2765. \quad \frac{645}{1419} := \frac{6+4+5}{14+19}$$

$$\frac{645}{14319} := \frac{6+4+5}{14+319}$$

$$\frac{645}{143319} := \frac{6+4+5}{14+3319}$$

$$\frac{645}{1433319} := \frac{6+4+5}{14+33319}$$

$$2770. \quad \frac{648}{1215} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{12 \times 1 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{648}{12150} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{12 \times 1 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{648}{121500} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{12 \times 1 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{648}{1215000} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{12 \times 1 \times 5000}$$

$$2775. \quad \frac{648}{1458} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times (4 + 5) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{648}{14580} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times (4 + 5) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{648}{145800} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times (4 + 5) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{648}{1458000} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 8}{1 \times (4 + 5) \times 8000}$$

$$2780. \quad \frac{649}{1475} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{1^4 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{649}{14750} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{1^4 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{649}{147500} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{1^4 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{649}{1475000} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{1^4 \times 75000}$$

$$2785. \quad \frac{651}{1344} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{651}{13440} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{651}{134400} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{651}{1344000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 + 3) \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$2776. \quad \frac{648}{1485} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{648}{14850} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{648}{148500} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{648}{1485000} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5000}$$

$$2781. \quad \frac{651}{1050} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 050}$$

$$\frac{651}{10500} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 0500}$$

$$\frac{651}{105000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 05000}$$

$$\frac{651}{1050000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 050000}$$

$$2786. \quad \frac{651}{1365} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{651}{13650} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{651}{136500} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{651}{1365000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^3 \times 65000}$$

$$2777. \quad \frac{648}{729} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(7 + 2) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{648}{7290} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(7 + 2) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{648}{72900} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(7 + 2) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{648}{729000} := \frac{6 \times (4 + 8)}{(7 + 2) \times 9000}$$

$$2782. \quad \frac{651}{1155} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 55}$$

$$\frac{651}{11550} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 550}$$

$$\frac{651}{115500} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 5500}$$

$$\frac{651}{1155000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}$$

$$2787. \quad \frac{651}{1386} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{651}{13860} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{651}{138600} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{651}{1386000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 6000}$$

$$2778. \quad \frac{648}{7560} := \frac{6 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 5 \times 6 + 0}$$

$$\frac{648}{75600} := \frac{6 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 5 \times 60 + 0}$$

$$\frac{648}{756000} := \frac{6 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 5 \times 600 + 0}$$

$$\frac{648}{7560000} := \frac{6 + 4 + 8}{7 \times 5 \times 6000 + 0}$$

$$2783. \quad \frac{651}{1260} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^2 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{651}{12600} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^2 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{651}{126000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^2 \times 6000}$$

$$\frac{651}{1260000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^2 \times 60000}$$

$$2788. \quad \frac{651}{1470} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{651}{14700} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{651}{147000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{651}{1470000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{1^4 \times 70000}$$

$$2779. \quad \frac{649}{1239} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{649}{12390} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{649}{123900} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{649}{1239000} := \frac{6 \times 4 + 9}{(1 + 2 \times 3) \times 9000}$$

$$2784. \quad \frac{651}{1302} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 30 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{651}{13020} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 30 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{651}{130200} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 30 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{651}{1302000} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 1}{1 \times 30 \times 2000}$$

$$2789. \quad \frac{651}{924} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(9 + 2) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{651}{9240} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(9 + 2) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{651}{92400} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(9 + 2) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{651}{924000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 1}{(9 + 2) \times 4000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2790. \quad & \frac{652}{1304} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{1 \times 30 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{652}{13040} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{1 \times 30 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{652}{130400} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{1 \times 30 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{652}{1304000} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 2}{1 \times 30 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2795. \quad & \frac{654}{1308} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4}{1 \times 30 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{654}{13080} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4}{1 \times 30 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{654}{130800} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4}{1 \times 30 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{654}{1308000} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 4}{1 \times 30 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2800. \quad & \frac{662}{1324} := \frac{6 \times (6+2)}{(1+3) \times 24} \\
 & \frac{662}{13240} := \frac{6 \times (6+2)}{(1+3) \times 240} \\
 & \frac{662}{132400} := \frac{6 \times (6+2)}{(1+3) \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{662}{1324000} := \frac{6 \times (6+2)}{(1+3) \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2791. \quad & \frac{652}{815} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 2}{8 \times 1 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{652}{8150} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 2}{8 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{652}{81500} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 2}{8 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{652}{815000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 2}{8 \times 1 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2796. \quad & \frac{655}{1048} := \frac{65+5}{(10+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{655}{10480} := \frac{65+5}{(10+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{655}{104800} := \frac{65+5}{(10+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{655}{1048000} := \frac{65+5}{(10+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2801. \quad & \frac{663}{1088} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 08 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{663}{10880} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 08 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{663}{108800} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 08 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{663}{1088000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 08 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2792. \quad & \frac{653}{1306} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 30 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{653}{13060} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 30 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{653}{130600} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 30 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{653}{1306000} := \frac{6 \times 5 \times 3}{1 \times 30 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2797. \quad & \frac{655}{1179} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{655}{11790} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{655}{117900} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{655}{1179000} := \frac{6 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2802. \quad & \frac{663}{1224} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2) \times 24} \\
 & \frac{663}{12240} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2) \times 240} \\
 & \frac{663}{122400} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2) \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{663}{1224000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2) \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2793. \quad & \frac{654}{1090} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{654}{10900} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{654}{109000} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{654}{1090000} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2798. \quad & \frac{657}{1168} := \frac{6 \times (5+7)}{1 \times 16 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{657}{11680} := \frac{6 \times (5+7)}{1 \times 16 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{657}{116800} := \frac{6 \times (5+7)}{1 \times 16 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{657}{1168000} := \frac{6 \times (5+7)}{1 \times 16 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2803. \quad & \frac{663}{1275} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{663}{12750} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{663}{127500} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{663}{1275000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2794. \quad & \frac{654}{1199} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\
 & \frac{654}{11990} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\
 & \frac{654}{119900} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\
 & \frac{654}{1199000} := \frac{6 \times (5+4)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2799. \quad & \frac{659}{1318} := \frac{6 + (5+9)}{(1+3+1) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{659}{13180} := \frac{6 + (5+9)}{(1+3+1) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{659}{131800} := \frac{6 + (5+9)}{(1+3+1) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{659}{1318000} := \frac{6 + (5+9)}{(1+3+1) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2804. \quad & \frac{663}{1326} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 3 \times 26} \\
 & \frac{663}{13260} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 3 \times 260} \\
 & \frac{663}{132600} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 3 \times 2600} \\
 & \frac{663}{1326000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{1 \times 3 \times 26000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2805. \quad & \frac{663}{1445} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{663}{14450} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{663}{144500} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{(1 + 4 \times 4) \times 500}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2810. \quad & \frac{664}{913} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{9 + 13} \\
 & \frac{664}{9213} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{9 + 213} \\
 & \frac{664}{92213} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{9 + 2213} \\
 & \frac{664}{922213} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{9 + 22213}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2815. \quad & \frac{666}{814} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{666}{8214} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{8 + 214} \\
 & \frac{666}{82214} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{8 + 2214} \\
 & \frac{666}{822214} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{8 + 22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2806. \quad & \frac{663}{1683} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16 + 83} \\
 & \frac{663}{16983} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16 + 983} \\
 & \frac{663}{169983} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16 + 9983} \\
 & \frac{663}{1699983} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{16 + 99983}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2811. \quad & \frac{665}{1330} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{665}{13300} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{665}{133000} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{665}{1330000} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 5}{(1 + 3) \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2816. \quad & \frac{668}{1837} := \frac{6 + 6 + 8}{18 + 37} \\
 & \frac{668}{18537} := \frac{6 + 6 + 8}{18 + 537} \\
 & \frac{668}{185537} := \frac{6 + 6 + 8}{18 + 5537} \\
 & \frac{668}{1855537} := \frac{6 + 6 + 8}{18 + 55537}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2807. \quad & \frac{663}{816} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{8 \times 1 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{663}{8160} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{8 \times 1 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{663}{81600} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{8 \times 1 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{663}{816000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 3}{8 \times 1 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2812. \quad & \frac{666}{1184} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{666}{11840} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{666}{118400} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{666}{1184000} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2817. \quad & \frac{668}{835} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 8}{8 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{668}{8350} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 8}{8 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{668}{83500} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 8}{8 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{668}{835000} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 8}{8 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2808. \quad & \frac{664}{1328} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 4}{(1 + 3^2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{664}{13280} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 4}{(1 + 3^2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{664}{132800} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 4}{(1 + 3^2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{664}{1328000} := \frac{6 \times 6 + 4}{(1 + 3^2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2813. \quad & \frac{666}{1221} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{12 + 21} \\
 & \frac{666}{12321} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{12 + 321} \\
 & \frac{666}{123321} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{12 + 3321} \\
 & \frac{666}{1233321} := \frac{6 + 6 + 6}{12 + 33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2818. \quad & \frac{669}{1338} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{1 \times 3^3 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{669}{13380} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{1 \times 3^3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{669}{133800} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{1 \times 3^3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{669}{1338000} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{1 \times 3^3 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2809. \quad & \frac{664}{1826} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{18 + 26} \\
 & \frac{664}{18426} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{18 + 426} \\
 & \frac{664}{184426} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{18 + 4426} \\
 & \frac{664}{1844426} := \frac{6 + 6 + 4}{18 + 44426}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2814. \quad & \frac{666}{1480} := \frac{6 \times 6 \times 6}{1 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{666}{14800} := \frac{6 \times 6 \times 6}{1 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{666}{148000} := \frac{6 \times 6 \times 6}{1 \times 48000} \\
 & \frac{666}{1480000} := \frac{6 \times 6 \times 6}{1 \times 480000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2819. \quad & \frac{669}{892} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{669}{8920} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{669}{89200} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{669}{892000} := \frac{(6 + 6) \times 9}{8 \times 9 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2820.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{671}{1342} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 2} \\ \frac{671}{13420} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 20} \\ \frac{671}{134200} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 200} \\ \frac{671}{1342000} &:= \frac{6+7 \times 1}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2825.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{768} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{7 \times 6 \times 8} \\ \frac{672}{7680} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{7 \times 6 \times 80} \\ \frac{672}{76800} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{7 \times 6 \times 800} \\ \frac{672}{768000} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{7 \times 6 \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2830.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{675}{1470} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{14 \times 70} \\ \frac{675}{14700} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{14 \times 700} \\ \frac{675}{147000} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{14 \times 7000} \\ \frac{675}{1470000} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{14 \times 70000} \end{aligned}$$

2821.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{1280} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 80} \\ \frac{672}{12800} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 800} \\ \frac{672}{128000} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 8000} \\ \frac{672}{1280000} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 80000} \end{aligned}$$

2826.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{792} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+92} \\ \frac{672}{7992} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+992} \\ \frac{672}{79992} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+9992} \\ \frac{672}{799992} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{7+99992} \end{aligned}$$

2831.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{675}{972} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{9 \times 72} \\ \frac{675}{9720} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{9 \times 720} \\ \frac{675}{97200} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{9 \times 7200} \\ \frac{675}{972000} &:= \frac{6 \times 75}{9 \times 72000} \end{aligned}$$

2822.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{1296} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6} \\ \frac{672}{12960} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 60} \\ \frac{672}{129600} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 600} \\ \frac{672}{1296000} &:= \frac{6 \times 7 \times 2}{(1+2) \times 9 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2827.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{673}{1346} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 3}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 6} \\ \frac{673}{13460} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 3}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 60} \\ \frac{673}{134600} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 3}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 600} \\ \frac{673}{1346000} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 3}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2832.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{676}{1248} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{(1+2) \times 48} \\ \frac{676}{12480} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{(1+2) \times 480} \\ \frac{676}{124800} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{(1+2) \times 4800} \\ \frac{676}{1248000} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{(1+2) \times 48000} \end{aligned}$$

2823.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{1344} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 2}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 4} \\ \frac{672}{13440} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 2}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 40} \\ \frac{672}{134400} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 2}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 400} \\ \frac{672}{1344000} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 2}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2828.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{674}{1348} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 4}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 8} \\ \frac{674}{13480} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 4}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 80} \\ \frac{674}{134800} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 4}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 800} \\ \frac{674}{1348000} &:= \frac{(6+7) \times 4}{(1+3 \times 4) \times 8000} \end{aligned}$$

2824.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{672}{1776} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+776} \\ \frac{672}{17776} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+7776} \\ \frac{672}{177776} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+77776} \\ \frac{672}{1777776} &:= \frac{6 \times 7^2}{1+777776} \end{aligned}$$

2829.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{675}{1250} &:= \frac{6+75}{(1+2) \times 50} \\ \frac{675}{12500} &:= \frac{6+75}{(1+2) \times 500} \\ \frac{675}{125000} &:= \frac{6+75}{(1+2) \times 5000} \\ \frac{675}{1250000} &:= \frac{6+75}{(1+2) \times 50000} \end{aligned}$$

2833.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{676}{1352} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 3 \times 52} \\ \frac{676}{13520} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 3 \times 520} \\ \frac{676}{135200} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 3 \times 5200} \\ \frac{676}{1352000} &:= \frac{6 \times (7+6)}{1 \times 3 \times 52000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2834. \quad & \frac{676}{845} := \frac{6+7 \times 6}{(8+4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{676}{8450} := \frac{6+7 \times 6}{(8+4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{676}{84500} := \frac{6+7 \times 6}{(8+4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{676}{845000} := \frac{6+7 \times 6}{(8+4) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2839. \quad & \frac{682}{1240} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{1^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{682}{12400} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{1^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{682}{124000} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{1^2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{682}{1240000} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{1^2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2844. \quad & \frac{684}{1152} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{((1+1)^5) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{684}{11520} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+1)^5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{684}{115200} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+1)^5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{684}{1152000} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+1)^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2835. \quad & \frac{678}{791} := \frac{6 \times 7^8}{7^9 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{678}{7910} := \frac{6 \times 7^8}{7^9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{678}{79100} := \frac{6 \times 7^8}{7^9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{678}{791000} := \frac{6 \times 7^8}{7^9 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2840. \quad & \frac{682}{1364} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 64} \\
 & \frac{682}{13640} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 640} \\
 & \frac{682}{136400} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 6400} \\
 & \frac{682}{1364000} := \frac{6 \times 8 \times 2}{1 \times 3 \times 64000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2845. \quad & \frac{684}{1197} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{684}{11970} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{684}{119700} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{684}{1197000} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+1) \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2836. \quad & \frac{681}{1135} := \frac{6+8+1}{(1+1+3) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{681}{11350} := \frac{6+8+1}{(1+1+3) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{681}{113500} := \frac{6+8+1}{(1+1+3) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{681}{1135000} := \frac{6+8+1}{(1+1+3) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2841. \quad & \frac{682}{1395} := \frac{6+82}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{682}{13950} := \frac{6+82}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{682}{139500} := \frac{6+82}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{682}{1395000} := \frac{6+82}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2846. \quad & \frac{684}{1216} := \frac{6+8+4}{1 \times 2 \times 16} \\
 & \frac{684}{12160} := \frac{6+8+4}{1 \times 2 \times 160} \\
 & \frac{684}{121600} := \frac{6+8+4}{1 \times 2 \times 1600} \\
 & \frac{684}{1216000} := \frac{6+8+4}{1 \times 2 \times 16000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2837. \quad & \frac{681}{908} := \frac{6 \times (8+1)}{9 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{681}{9080} := \frac{6 \times (8+1)}{9 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{681}{90800} := \frac{6 \times (8+1)}{9 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{681}{908000} := \frac{6 \times (8+1)}{9 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2842. \quad & \frac{682}{868} := \frac{6+82}{(8+6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{682}{8680} := \frac{6+82}{(8+6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{682}{86800} := \frac{6+82}{(8+6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{682}{868000} := \frac{6+82}{(8+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2838. \quad & \frac{682}{1023} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+23} \\
 & \frac{682}{10323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+323} \\
 & \frac{682}{103323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+3323} \\
 & \frac{682}{1033323} := \frac{6+8 \times 2}{10+33323}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2843. \quad & \frac{684}{1064} := \frac{6+8+4}{(1+06) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{684}{10640} := \frac{6+8+4}{(1+06) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{684}{106400} := \frac{6+8+4}{(1+06) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{684}{1064000} := \frac{6+8+4}{(1+06) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2847. \quad & \frac{684}{1254} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{684}{12540} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{684}{125400} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{684}{1254000} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{(1+2^5) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2848. \quad & \frac{684}{1296} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+2+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{684}{12960} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+2+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{684}{129600} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+2+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{684}{1296000} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{(1+2+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2853. \quad & \frac{688}{1290} := \frac{6 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{688}{12900} := \frac{6 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{688}{129000} := \frac{6 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{688}{1290000} := \frac{6 \times (8+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2858. \quad & \frac{690}{1518} := \frac{6+9+0}{15+18} \\
 & \frac{690}{15318} := \frac{6+9+0}{15+318} \\
 & \frac{690}{153318} := \frac{6+9+0}{15+3318} \\
 & \frac{690}{1533318} := \frac{6+9+0}{15+33318}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2849. \quad & \frac{684}{1368} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{684}{13680} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{684}{136800} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{684}{1368000} := \frac{6 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 3 \times 6 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2854. \quad & \frac{689}{1166} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 66} \\
 & \frac{689}{11660} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 660} \\
 & \frac{689}{116600} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{689}{1166000} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(1+1) \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2859. \quad & \frac{692}{1384} := \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{692}{13840} := \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{692}{138400} := \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{692}{1384000} := \frac{6+9 \times 2}{(1+3+8) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2850. \quad & \frac{684}{1782} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{17+82} \\
 & \frac{684}{17982} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{17+982} \\
 & \frac{684}{179982} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{17+9982} \\
 & \frac{684}{1799982} := \frac{6+8 \times 4}{17+99982}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2855. \quad & \frac{689}{1272} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{689}{12720} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{689}{127200} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{689}{1272000} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{1 \times 2 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2860. \quad & \frac{692}{865} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 2}{(8+6) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{692}{8650} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 2}{(8+6) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{692}{86500} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 2}{(8+6) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{692}{865000} := \frac{6 \times 9 + 2}{(8+6) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2851. \quad & \frac{684}{855} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 4}{(8+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{684}{8550} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 4}{(8+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{684}{85500} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 4}{(8+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{684}{855000} := \frac{6 \times 8 + 4}{(8+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2856. \quad & \frac{689}{848} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(8+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{689}{8480} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(8+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{689}{84800} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(8+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{689}{848000} := \frac{6+8 \times 9}{(8+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2861. \quad & \frac{693}{1050} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{693}{10500} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{693}{105000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1 \times 05000} \\
 & \frac{693}{1050000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1 \times 050000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2852. \quad & \frac{686}{1372} := \frac{6+8+6}{(13+7) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{686}{13720} := \frac{6+8+6}{(13+7) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{686}{137200} := \frac{6+8+6}{(13+7) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{686}{1372000} := \frac{6+8+6}{(13+7) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2857. \quad & \frac{690}{1012} := \frac{6+9+0}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{690}{10212} := \frac{6+9+0}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{690}{102212} := \frac{6+9+0}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{690}{1022212} := \frac{6+9+0}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2862. \quad & \frac{693}{1232} := \frac{6+9+3}{1^2 \times 32} \\
 & \frac{693}{12320} := \frac{6+9+3}{1^2 \times 320} \\
 & \frac{693}{123200} := \frac{6+9+3}{1^2 \times 3200} \\
 & \frac{693}{1232000} := \frac{6+9+3}{1^2 \times 32000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2863. \quad & \frac{693}{1260} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{693}{12600} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{693}{126000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{693}{1260000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2868. \quad & \frac{693}{1470} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^4 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{693}{14700} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^4 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{693}{147000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^4 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{693}{1470000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{1^4 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2873. \quad & \frac{699}{1398} := \frac{6 \times (9+9)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{699}{13980} := \frac{6 \times (9+9)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{699}{139800} := \frac{6 \times (9+9)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{699}{1398000} := \frac{6 \times (9+9)}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2864. \quad & \frac{693}{1302} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{693}{13020} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{693}{130200} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{693}{1302000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2869. \quad & \frac{693}{924} := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 3}{9 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{693}{9240} := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 3}{9 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{693}{92400} := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 3}{9 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{693}{924000} := \frac{6 \times 9 \times 3}{9 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2874. \quad & \frac{702}{1248} := \frac{70+2}{1 \times 2^4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{702}{12480} := \frac{70+2}{1 \times 2^4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{702}{124800} := \frac{70+2}{1 \times 2^4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{702}{1248000} := \frac{70+2}{1 \times 2^4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2865. \quad & \frac{693}{1344} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{693}{13440} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{693}{134400} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{693}{1344000} := \frac{6+9 \times 3}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2870. \quad & \frac{694}{1388} := \frac{6+94}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{694}{13880} := \frac{6+94}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{694}{138800} := \frac{6+94}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{694}{1388000} := \frac{6+94}{(1+3 \times 8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2875. \quad & \frac{705}{1128} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1+1) \times 28} \\
 & \frac{705}{11280} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1+1) \times 280} \\
 & \frac{705}{112800} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1+1) \times 2800} \\
 & \frac{705}{1128000} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1+1) \times 28000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2866. \quad & \frac{693}{1365} := \frac{6+93}{1 \times 3 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{693}{13650} := \frac{6+93}{1 \times 3 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{693}{136500} := \frac{6+93}{1 \times 3 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{693}{1365000} := \frac{6+93}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2871. \quad & \frac{695}{1529} := \frac{6+9+5}{15+29} \\
 & \frac{695}{15429} := \frac{6+9+5}{15+429} \\
 & \frac{695}{154429} := \frac{6+9+5}{15+4429} \\
 & \frac{695}{1544429} := \frac{6+9+5}{15+44429}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2876. \quad & \frac{705}{1269} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1^2+6) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{705}{12690} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1^2+6) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{705}{126900} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1^2+6) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{705}{1269000} := \frac{7 \times 05}{(1^2+6) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2867. \quad & \frac{693}{1386} := \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{693}{13860} := \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{693}{138600} := \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{693}{1386000} := \frac{6 \times (9+3)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2872. \quad & \frac{698}{1396} := \frac{(6+9) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{698}{13960} := \frac{(6+9) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{698}{139600} := \frac{(6+9) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{698}{1396000} := \frac{(6+9) \times 8}{(1+39) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2877. \quad & \frac{705}{1410} := \frac{7+0 \times 5}{14 \times 1+0} \\
 & \frac{705}{14100} := \frac{7+0 \times 5}{14 \times 10+0} \\
 & \frac{705}{141000} := \frac{7+0 \times 5}{14 \times 100+0} \\
 & \frac{705}{1410000} := \frac{7+0 \times 5}{14 \times 1000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2878. \quad & \frac{706}{1412} := \frac{7 \times 06}{(1+41) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{706}{14120} := \frac{7 \times 06}{(1+41) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{706}{141200} := \frac{7 \times 06}{(1+41) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{706}{1412000} := \frac{7 \times 06}{(1+41) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883. \quad & \frac{707}{1313} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^3 \times 13} \\
 & \frac{707}{13130} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^3 \times 130} \\
 & \frac{707}{131300} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^3 \times 1300} \\
 & \frac{707}{1313000} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^3 \times 13000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2888. \quad & \frac{712}{1424} := \frac{7 \times 12}{1 \times 42 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{712}{14240} := \frac{7 \times 12}{1 \times 42 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{712}{142400} := \frac{7 \times 12}{1 \times 42 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{712}{1424000} := \frac{7 \times 12}{1 \times 42 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2879. \quad & \frac{707}{1010} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1 \times 010} \\
 & \frac{707}{10100} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1 \times 0100} \\
 & \frac{707}{101000} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1 \times 01000} \\
 & \frac{707}{1010000} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1 \times 010000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2884. \quad & \frac{707}{1414} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^4 \times 14} \\
 & \frac{707}{14140} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^4 \times 140} \\
 & \frac{707}{141400} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^4 \times 1400} \\
 & \frac{707}{1414000} := \frac{7+0 \times 7}{1^4 \times 14000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2889. \quad & \frac{712}{979} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+79} \\
 & \frac{712}{9879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+879} \\
 & \frac{712}{98879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+8879} \\
 & \frac{712}{988879} := \frac{(7+1)^2}{9+88879}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2880. \quad & \frac{707}{1111} := \frac{70+7}{11 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{707}{11110} := \frac{70+7}{11 \times 110} \\
 & \frac{707}{111100} := \frac{70+7}{11 \times 1100} \\
 & \frac{707}{1111000} := \frac{70+7}{11 \times 11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2885. \quad & \frac{708}{1416} := \frac{7+08}{(1+4 \times 1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{708}{14160} := \frac{7+08}{(1+4 \times 1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{708}{141600} := \frac{7+08}{(1+4 \times 1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{708}{1416000} := \frac{7+08}{(1+4 \times 1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2890. \quad & \frac{714}{1122} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{11 \times 2 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{714}{11220} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{11 \times 2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{714}{112200} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{11 \times 2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{714}{1122000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{11 \times 2 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2881. \quad & \frac{707}{1111} := \frac{7+07}{11+11} \\
 & \frac{707}{11211} := \frac{7+07}{11+211} \\
 & \frac{707}{112211} := \frac{7+07}{11+2211} \\
 & \frac{707}{1122211} := \frac{7+07}{11+22211}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2886. \quad & \frac{709}{1418} := \frac{7+09}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{709}{14180} := \frac{7+09}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{709}{141800} := \frac{7+09}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{709}{1418000} := \frac{7+09}{1 \times 4 \times 1 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2891. \quad & \frac{714}{1122} := \frac{7+14}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{714}{11322} := \frac{7+14}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{714}{113322} := \frac{7+14}{11+3322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2882. \quad & \frac{707}{1212} := \frac{7+07}{1 \times 2 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{707}{12120} := \frac{7+07}{1 \times 2 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{707}{121200} := \frac{7+07}{1 \times 2 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{707}{1212000} := \frac{7+07}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2887. \quad & \frac{712}{1335} := \frac{7+1^2}{1^3 \times 3 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{712}{13350} := \frac{7+1^2}{1^3 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{712}{133500} := \frac{7+1^2}{1^3 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{712}{1335000} := \frac{7+1^2}{1^3 \times 3 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2892. \quad & \frac{714}{1224} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 24} \\
 & \frac{714}{12240} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 240} \\
 & \frac{714}{122400} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 2400} \\
 & \frac{714}{1224000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 24000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2893. \quad \frac{714}{1275} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{714}{12750} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{714}{127500} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{714}{1275000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 4}{(1+2+7) \times 5000}$$

$$2898. \quad \frac{715}{1144} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{715}{11440} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{715}{114400} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{715}{1144000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 4000}$$

$$2903. \quad \frac{716}{1432} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 6}{14 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{716}{14320} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 6}{14 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{716}{143200} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 6}{14 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{716}{1432000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 6}{14 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

$$2894. \quad \frac{714}{1292} := \frac{7+14}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{714}{12920} := \frac{7+14}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{714}{129200} := \frac{7+14}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{714}{1292000} := \frac{7+14}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}$$

$$2899. \quad \frac{715}{12375} := \frac{7+1+5}{1^2 \times 3 \times 75}$$

$$\frac{715}{123750} := \frac{7+1+5}{1^2 \times 3 \times 750}$$

$$\frac{715}{1237500} := \frac{7+1+5}{1^2 \times 3 \times 7500}$$

$$\frac{715}{12375000} := \frac{7+1+5}{1^2 \times 3 \times 75000}$$

$$2904. \quad \frac{717}{1434} := \frac{7+17}{1 \times 4 \times 3 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{717}{14340} := \frac{7+17}{1 \times 4 \times 3 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{717}{143400} := \frac{7+17}{1 \times 4 \times 3 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{717}{1434000} := \frac{7+17}{1 \times 4 \times 3 \times 4000}$$

$$2895. \quad \frac{714}{1309} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+09}$$

$$\frac{714}{13209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+209}$$

$$\frac{714}{132209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+2209}$$

$$\frac{714}{1322209} := \frac{7+1+4}{13+22209}$$

$$2900. \quad \frac{715}{1287} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{(1^2+8) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{715}{12870} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{(1^2+8) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{715}{128700} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{(1^2+8) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{715}{1287000} := \frac{7 \times 1 \times 5}{(1^2+8) \times 7000}$$

$$2905. \quad \frac{718}{1436} := \frac{7 \times 18}{14 \times 3 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{718}{14360} := \frac{7 \times 18}{14 \times 3 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{718}{143600} := \frac{7 \times 18}{14 \times 3 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{718}{1436000} := \frac{7 \times 18}{14 \times 3 \times 6000}$$

$$2896. \quad \frac{714}{1428} := \frac{(7+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{714}{14280} := \frac{(7+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{714}{142800} := \frac{(7+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{714}{1428000} := \frac{(7+1) \times 4}{1 \times 4 \times 2 \times 8000}$$

$$2901. \quad \frac{715}{1573} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+73}$$

$$\frac{715}{15873} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+873}$$

$$\frac{715}{158873} := \frac{(7+1) \times 5}{15+8873}$$

$$2906. \quad \frac{719}{1438} := \frac{7+1 \times 9}{(1^4+3) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{719}{14380} := \frac{7+1 \times 9}{(1^4+3) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{719}{143800} := \frac{7+1 \times 9}{(1^4+3) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{719}{1438000} := \frac{7+1 \times 9}{(1^4+3) \times 8000}$$

$$2897. \quad \frac{714}{952} := \frac{7+14}{(9+5) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{714}{9520} := \frac{7+14}{(9+5) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{714}{95200} := \frac{7+14}{(9+5) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{714}{952000} := \frac{7+14}{(9+5) \times 2000}$$

$$2902. \quad \frac{715}{1815} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{715}{18315} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{715}{183315} := \frac{7+1+5}{18+3315}$$

$$2907. \quad \frac{721}{1030} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 030}$$

$$\frac{721}{10300} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 0300}$$

$$\frac{721}{103000} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 03000}$$

$$\frac{721}{1030000} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 030000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2908. \quad & \frac{721}{1133} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 33} \\
 & \frac{721}{11330} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 330} \\
 & \frac{721}{113300} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 3300} \\
 & \frac{721}{1133000} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 1 \times 33000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2913. \quad & \frac{722}{1444} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{722}{14440} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{722}{144400} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{722}{1444000} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2918. \quad & \frac{726}{1320} := \frac{7 + 26}{1 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{726}{13200} := \frac{7 + 26}{1 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{726}{132000} := \frac{7 + 26}{1 \times 3 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{726}{1320000} := \frac{7 + 26}{1 \times 3 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2909. \quad & \frac{721}{1133} := \frac{7 + 21}{11 + 33} \\
 & \frac{721}{11433} := \frac{7 + 21}{11 + 433} \\
 & \frac{721}{114433} := \frac{7 + 21}{11 + 4433} \\
 & \frac{721}{1144433} := \frac{7 + 21}{11 + 44433}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2914. \quad & \frac{723}{1446} := \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{1^4 \times 4 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{723}{14460} := \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{1^4 \times 4 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{723}{144600} := \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{1^4 \times 4 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{723}{1446000} := \frac{7 + 2 + 3}{1^4 \times 4 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2919. \quad & \frac{726}{1452} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{726}{14520} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{726}{145200} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{726}{1452000} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 6}{1 \times 4 \times 5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2910. \quad & \frac{721}{1236} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{721}{12360} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{721}{123600} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{721}{1236000} := \frac{7 \times (2+1)}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2915. \quad & \frac{724}{1267} := \frac{72 \times 4}{12 \times 6 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{724}{12670} := \frac{72 \times 4}{12 \times 6 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{724}{126700} := \frac{72 \times 4}{12 \times 6 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{724}{1267000} := \frac{72 \times 4}{12 \times 6 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2920. \quad & \frac{726}{1452} := \frac{7 + 26}{14 + 52} \\
 & \frac{726}{14652} := \frac{7 + 26}{14 + 652} \\
 & \frac{726}{146652} := \frac{7 + 26}{14 + 6652} \\
 & \frac{726}{1466652} := \frac{7 + 26}{14 + 66652}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2911. \quad & \frac{721}{1442} := \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(1 + 4 + 4) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{721}{14420} := \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(1 + 4 + 4) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{721}{144200} := \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(1 + 4 + 4) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{721}{1442000} := \frac{7 + 2 \times 1}{(1 + 4 + 4) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2916. \quad & \frac{724}{905} := \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{9 \times 05} \\
 & \frac{724}{9050} := \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{9 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{724}{90500} := \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{9 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{724}{905000} := \frac{(7+2) \times 4}{9 \times 05000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2921. \quad & \frac{727}{1454} := \frac{7 + 2^7}{(1 + 4) \times 54} \\
 & \frac{727}{14540} := \frac{7 + 2^7}{(1 + 4) \times 540} \\
 & \frac{727}{145400} := \frac{7 + 2^7}{(1 + 4) \times 5400} \\
 & \frac{727}{1454000} := \frac{7 + 2^7}{(1 + 4) \times 54000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2912. \quad & \frac{722}{1083} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{1 \times 08 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{722}{10830} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{1 \times 08 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{722}{108300} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{1 \times 08 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{722}{1083000} := \frac{7 \times 2 + 2}{1 \times 08 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2917. \quad & \frac{726}{1089} := \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{(1+08) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{726}{10890} := \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{(1+08) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{726}{108900} := \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{(1+08) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{726}{1089000} := \frac{(7+2) \times 6}{(1+08) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2922. \quad & \frac{728}{1144} := \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{11 \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{728}{11440} := \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{11 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{728}{114400} := \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{11 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{728}{1144000} := \frac{7 \times 2 \times 8}{11 \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2923. \quad & \frac{728}{1144} := \frac{7+28}{11+44} \\
 & \frac{728}{728} := \frac{7+28}{7+28} \\
 & \frac{11544}{728} := \frac{11+544}{7+28} \\
 & \frac{115544}{728} := \frac{11+5544}{7+28} \\
 & \frac{1155544}{728} := \frac{11+55544}{7+28}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2928. \quad & \frac{729}{1134} := \frac{7+29}{(1+13) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{729}{729} := \frac{7+29}{7+29} \\
 & \frac{11340}{729} := \frac{(1+13) \times 40}{7+29} \\
 & \frac{113400}{729} := \frac{(1+13) \times 400}{7+29} \\
 & \frac{1134000}{729} := \frac{(1+13) \times 4000}{7+29}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2933. \quad & \frac{729}{1368} := \frac{72+9}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{729}{729} := \frac{72+9}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{13680}{729} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{136800}{729} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{1368000}{729} := \frac{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}{72+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2924. \quad & \frac{728}{1352} := \frac{7 \times (2+8)}{13 \times 5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{728}{728} := \frac{7 \times (2+8)}{7 \times (2+8)} \\
 & \frac{13520}{728} := \frac{13 \times 5 \times 20}{7 \times (2+8)} \\
 & \frac{135200}{728} := \frac{13 \times 5 \times 200}{7 \times (2+8)} \\
 & \frac{1352000}{728} := \frac{13 \times 5 \times 2000}{7 \times (2+8)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2929. \quad & \frac{729}{1197} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{729}{729} := \frac{72+9}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{11970}{729} := \frac{1 \times 19 \times 70}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{119700}{729} := \frac{1 \times 19 \times 700}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{1197000}{729} := \frac{1 \times 19 \times 7000}{72+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2934. \quad & \frac{729}{1440} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{729}{729} := \frac{72+9}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{14400}{729} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 400}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{144000}{729} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 4000}{72+9} \\
 & \frac{1440000}{729} := \frac{1 \times 4 \times 40000}{72+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2925. \quad & \frac{728}{819} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(8+1) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{728}{8190} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(8+1) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{728}{81900} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(8+1) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{728}{819000} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{(8+1) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2930. \quad & \frac{729}{1215} := \frac{7+29}{12 \times 1 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{729}{12150} := \frac{7+29}{12 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{729}{121500} := \frac{7+29}{12 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{729}{1215000} := \frac{7+29}{12 \times 1 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2935. \quad & \frac{729}{1458} := \frac{7+29}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{729}{14580} := \frac{7+29}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{729}{145800} := \frac{7+29}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{729}{1458000} := \frac{7+29}{(1 \times 4 + 5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2926. \quad & \frac{728}{910} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{9 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{728}{9100} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{9 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{728}{91000} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{9 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{728}{910000} := \frac{(7+2) \times 8}{9 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2931. \quad & \frac{729}{1296} := \frac{72 \times 9}{12 \times 96} \\
 & \frac{729}{12960} := \frac{72 \times 9}{12 \times 960} \\
 & \frac{729}{129600} := \frac{72 \times 9}{12 \times 9600} \\
 & \frac{729}{1296000} := \frac{72 \times 9}{12 \times 96000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2936. \quad & \frac{729}{1485} := \frac{72+9}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{729}{14850} := \frac{72+9}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{729}{148500} := \frac{72+9}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{729}{1485000} := \frac{72+9}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2927. \quad & \frac{729}{1125} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{729}{11250} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{729}{112500} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{729}{1125000} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2932. \quad & \frac{729}{1350} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{729}{13500} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{729}{135000} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{729}{1350000} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2937. \quad & \frac{729}{1575} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{729}{15750} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{729}{157500} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{729}{1575000} := \frac{72+9}{1 \times 5 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2938. \quad & \frac{729}{15795} := \frac{7+2+9}{(15+7 \times 9) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{729}{157950} := \frac{7+2+9}{(15+7 \times 9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{729}{1579500} := \frac{7+2+9}{(15+7 \times 9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{729}{15795000} := \frac{7+2+9}{(15+7 \times 9) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2943. \quad & \frac{731}{1887} := \frac{7^3+1}{1+887} \\
 & \frac{731}{18887} := \frac{7^3+1}{1+8887} \\
 & \frac{731}{188887} := \frac{7^3+1}{1+88887} \\
 & \frac{731}{1888887} := \frac{7^3+1}{1+888887}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2948. \quad & \frac{735}{1155} := \frac{7+35}{11+55} \\
 & \frac{735}{11655} := \frac{7+35}{11+655} \\
 & \frac{735}{116655} := \frac{7+35}{11+6655} \\
 & \frac{735}{1166655} := \frac{7+35}{11+66655}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2939. \quad & \frac{729}{891} := \frac{72+9}{8+91} \\
 & \frac{729}{8991} := \frac{72+9}{8+991} \\
 & \frac{729}{89991} := \frac{72+9}{8+9991} \\
 & \frac{729}{899991} := \frac{72+9}{8+99991}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2944. \quad & \frac{731}{850} := \frac{7^3+1}{8 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{731}{8500} := \frac{7^3+1}{8 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{731}{85000} := \frac{7^3+1}{8 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{731}{850000} := \frac{7^3+1}{8 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2949. \quad & \frac{735}{1225} := \frac{7+35}{(12+2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{735}{12250} := \frac{7+35}{(12+2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{735}{122500} := \frac{7+35}{(12+2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{735}{1225000} := \frac{7+35}{(12+2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2940. \quad & \frac{730}{803} := \frac{7+3+0}{8+03} \\
 & \frac{730}{8103} := \frac{7+3+0}{8+103} \\
 & \frac{730}{81103} := \frac{7+3+0}{8+1103} \\
 & \frac{730}{811103} := \frac{7+3+0}{8+11103}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2945. \quad & \frac{732}{1220} := \frac{7+3+2}{1^2 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{732}{12200} := \frac{7+3+2}{1^2 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{732}{122000} := \frac{7+3+2}{1^2 \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{732}{1220000} := \frac{7+3+2}{1^2 \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2950. \quad & \frac{735}{1260} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{735}{12600} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{735}{126000} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{735}{1260000} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2941. \quad & \frac{731}{1224} := \frac{7^3+1}{12^2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{731}{12240} := \frac{7^3+1}{12^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{731}{122400} := \frac{7^3+1}{12^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{731}{1224000} := \frac{7^3+1}{12^2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2946. \quad & \frac{732}{1281} := \frac{7+3^2}{1 \times 28 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{732}{12810} := \frac{7+3^2}{1 \times 28 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{732}{128100} := \frac{7+3^2}{1 \times 28 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{732}{1281000} := \frac{7+3^2}{1 \times 28 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2942. \quad & \frac{731}{1462} := \frac{7+3+1}{(1+4+6) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{731}{14620} := \frac{7+3+1}{(1+4+6) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{731}{146200} := \frac{7+3+1}{(1+4+6) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{731}{1462000} := \frac{7+3+1}{(1+4+6) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2947. \quad & \frac{732}{1464} := \frac{(7+3) \times 2}{(1 \times 4+6) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{732}{14640} := \frac{(7+3) \times 2}{(1 \times 4+6) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{732}{146400} := \frac{(7+3) \times 2}{(1 \times 4+6) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{732}{1464000} := \frac{(7+3) \times 2}{(1 \times 4+6) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2951. \quad & \frac{735}{1323} := \frac{7+3+5}{1 \times 3^2 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{735}{13230} := \frac{7+3+5}{1 \times 3^2 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{735}{132300} := \frac{7+3+5}{1 \times 3^2 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{735}{1323000} := \frac{7+3+5}{1 \times 3^2 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$2952. \quad \frac{735}{1365} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 65}$$

$$\frac{735}{13650} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 650}$$

$$\frac{735}{136500} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{735}{1365000} := \frac{7 \times 3 \times 5}{1 \times 3 \times 65000}$$

$$2957. \quad \frac{736}{1285} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+2^8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{736}{12850} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+2^8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{736}{128500} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+2^8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{736}{1285000} := \frac{7+3^6}{(1+2^8) \times 5000}$$

$$2962. \quad \frac{742}{1060} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{742}{10600} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{742}{106000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 06000}$$

$$\frac{742}{1060000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 060000}$$

$$2953. \quad \frac{735}{1617} := \frac{7+3+5}{16+17}$$

$$\frac{735}{16317} := \frac{7+3+5}{16+317}$$

$$\frac{735}{163317} := \frac{7+3+5}{16+3317}$$

$$\frac{735}{1633317} := \frac{7+3+5}{16+33317}$$

$$2958. \quad \frac{737}{1206} := \frac{7+37}{12 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{737}{12060} := \frac{7+37}{12 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{737}{120600} := \frac{7+37}{12 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{737}{1206000} := \frac{7+37}{12 \times 06000}$$

$$2963. \quad \frac{742}{1113} := \frac{(7+4) \times 2}{1 \times 11 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{742}{11130} := \frac{(7+4) \times 2}{1 \times 11 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{742}{111300} := \frac{(7+4) \times 2}{1 \times 11 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{742}{1113000} := \frac{(7+4) \times 2}{1 \times 11 \times 3000}$$

$$2954. \quad \frac{735}{1680} := \frac{7 \times 35}{(1+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{735}{16800} := \frac{7 \times 35}{(1+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{735}{168000} := \frac{7 \times 35}{(1+6) \times 8000}$$

$$2959. \quad \frac{738}{1025} := \frac{7+3+8}{1 \times 025}$$

$$\frac{738}{10250} := \frac{7+3+8}{1 \times 0250}$$

$$\frac{738}{102500} := \frac{7+3+8}{1 \times 02500}$$

$$2964. \quad \frac{742}{1166} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 66}$$

$$\frac{742}{11660} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 660}$$

$$\frac{742}{116600} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 6600}$$

$$\frac{742}{1166000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 66000}$$

$$2955. \quad \frac{736}{1012} := \frac{7+3+6}{(10+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{736}{10120} := \frac{7+3+6}{(10+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{736}{101200} := \frac{7+3+6}{(10+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{736}{1012000} := \frac{7+3+6}{(10+1) \times 2000}$$

$$2960. \quad \frac{738}{1230} := \frac{7+3+8}{1^2 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{738}{12300} := \frac{7+3+8}{1^2 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{738}{123000} := \frac{7+3+8}{1^2 \times 3000}$$

$$\frac{738}{1230000} := \frac{7+3+8}{1^2 \times 30000}$$

$$2965. \quad \frac{742}{1166} := \frac{7+42}{11+66}$$

$$\frac{742}{11766} := \frac{7+42}{11+766}$$

$$\frac{742}{117766} := \frac{7+42}{11+7766}$$

$$2956. \quad \frac{736}{1012} := \frac{7+3+6}{10+12}$$

$$\frac{736}{10212} := \frac{7+3+6}{10+212}$$

$$\frac{736}{102212} := \frac{7+3+6}{10+2212}$$

$$\frac{736}{1022212} := \frac{7+3+6}{10+22212}$$

$$2961. \quad \frac{738}{1435} := \frac{7+3+8}{(1 \times 4+3) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{738}{14350} := \frac{7+3+8}{(1 \times 4+3) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{738}{143500} := \frac{7+3+8}{(1 \times 4+3) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{738}{1435000} := \frac{7+3+8}{(1 \times 4+3) \times 5000}$$

$$2966. \quad \frac{742}{1272} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^2 \times 72}$$

$$\frac{742}{12720} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^2 \times 720}$$

$$\frac{742}{127200} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^2 \times 7200}$$

$$\frac{742}{1272000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^2 \times 72000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2967. \quad & \frac{742}{1325} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 3 \times 25} \\
 & \frac{742}{13250} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 3 \times 250} \\
 & \frac{742}{132500} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 3 \times 2500} \\
 & \frac{742}{1325000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 3 \times 25000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2972. \quad & \frac{744}{1395} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{744}{13950} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{744}{139500} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{744}{1395000} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{(1 \times 3 + 9) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2977. \quad & \frac{747}{1826} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+26} \\
 & \frac{747}{18426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+426} \\
 & \frac{747}{184426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+4426} \\
 & \frac{747}{1844426} := \frac{7+4+7}{18+44426}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2968. \quad & \frac{742}{1378} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^3 \times 78} \\
 & \frac{742}{13780} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^3 \times 780} \\
 & \frac{742}{137800} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^3 \times 7800} \\
 & \frac{742}{1378000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^3 \times 78000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2973. \quad & \frac{744}{1488} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{1^4 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{744}{14880} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{1^4 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{744}{148800} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{1^4 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{744}{1488000} := \frac{7 \times 4 + 4}{1^4 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2978. \quad & \frac{742}{1166} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 66} \\
 & \frac{742}{11660} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 660} \\
 & \frac{742}{116600} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{742}{1166000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2969. \quad & \frac{742}{1484} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^4 \times 84} \\
 & \frac{742}{14840} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^4 \times 840} \\
 & \frac{742}{148400} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^4 \times 8400} \\
 & \frac{742}{1484000} := \frac{7 \times (4+2)}{1^4 \times 84000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2974. \quad & \frac{745}{1490} := \frac{7 \times (4+5)}{14 \times 9 + 0} \\
 & \frac{745}{14900} := \frac{7 \times (4+5)}{14 \times 90 + 0} \\
 & \frac{745}{149000} := \frac{7 \times (4+5)}{14 \times 900 + 0} \\
 & \frac{745}{1490000} := \frac{7 \times (4+5)}{14 \times 9000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2979. \quad & \frac{747}{913} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+13} \\
 & \frac{747}{9213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+213} \\
 & \frac{747}{92213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+2213} \\
 & \frac{747}{922213} := \frac{7+4+7}{9+22213}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2970. \quad & \frac{742}{795} := \frac{7 \times 42}{7 \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{742}{7950} := \frac{7 \times 42}{7 \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{742}{79500} := \frac{7 \times 42}{7 \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{742}{795000} := \frac{7 \times 42}{7 \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2975. \quad & \frac{746}{1119} := \frac{(7+4) \times 6}{1 \times 11 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{746}{11190} := \frac{(7+4) \times 6}{1 \times 11 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{746}{111900} := \frac{(7+4) \times 6}{1 \times 11 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{746}{1119000} := \frac{(7+4) \times 6}{1 \times 11 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2980. \quad & \frac{747}{996} := \frac{74+7}{(9+9) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{747}{9960} := \frac{74+7}{(9+9) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{747}{99600} := \frac{74+7}{(9+9) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{747}{996000} := \frac{74+7}{(9+9) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2971. \quad & \frac{744}{1116} := \frac{(7+4) \times 4}{1 \times 11 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{744}{11160} := \frac{(7+4) \times 4}{1 \times 11 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{744}{111600} := \frac{(7+4) \times 4}{1 \times 11 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{744}{1116000} := \frac{(7+4) \times 4}{1 \times 11 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2976. \quad & \frac{747}{1245} := \frac{7+47}{1 \times 2 \times 45} \\
 & \frac{747}{12450} := \frac{7+47}{1 \times 2 \times 450} \\
 & \frac{747}{124500} := \frac{7+47}{1 \times 2 \times 4500} \\
 & \frac{747}{1245000} := \frac{7+47}{1 \times 2 \times 45000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2981. \quad & \frac{748}{1275} := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{748}{12750} := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{748}{127500} := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{748}{1275000} := \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

2982.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{748}{1326} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 6} \\ \frac{748}{13260} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 60} \\ \frac{748}{132600} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 600} \\ \frac{748}{1326000} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{13 \times 2 \times 6000} \end{aligned}$$

2987.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{749}{1284} &:= \frac{7+49}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 4} \\ \frac{749}{12840} &:= \frac{7+49}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 40} \\ \frac{749}{128400} &:= \frac{7+49}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 400} \\ \frac{749}{1284000} &:= \frac{7+49}{(1+2) \times 8 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2992.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{754}{1392} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2} \\ \frac{754}{13920} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 20} \\ \frac{754}{139200} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 200} \\ \frac{754}{1392000} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 2000} \end{aligned}$$

2983.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{748}{1734} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{17 \times 3 \times 4} \\ \frac{748}{17340} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{17 \times 3 \times 40} \\ \frac{748}{173400} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{17 \times 3 \times 400} \\ \frac{748}{1734000} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{17 \times 3 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2988.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{752}{1034} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{10+34} \\ \frac{752}{10434} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{10+434} \\ \frac{752}{104434} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{10+4434} \\ \frac{752}{1044434} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{10+44434} \end{aligned}$$

2993.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{755}{1208} &:= \frac{(7+5) \times 5}{12 \times 08} \\ \frac{755}{12080} &:= \frac{(7+5) \times 5}{12 \times 080} \\ \frac{755}{120800} &:= \frac{(7+5) \times 5}{12 \times 0800} \\ \frac{755}{1208000} &:= \frac{(7+5) \times 5}{12 \times 08000} \end{aligned}$$

2984.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{748}{17374} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4} \\ \frac{748}{173740} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 40} \\ \frac{748}{1737400} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 400} \\ \frac{748}{17374000} &:= \frac{(7+4) \times 8}{1 \times 73 \times 7 \times 4000} \end{aligned}$$

2989.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{752}{1269} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9} \\ \frac{752}{12690} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{1^2 \times 6 \times 90} \\ \frac{752}{126900} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{1^2 \times 6 \times 900} \\ \frac{752}{1269000} &:= \frac{7+5^2}{1^2 \times 6 \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2994.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{755}{1359} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 3 + 5) \times 9} \\ \frac{755}{13590} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 3 + 5) \times 90} \\ \frac{755}{135900} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 3 + 5) \times 900} \\ \frac{755}{1359000} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 5}{(1 \times 3 + 5) \times 9000} \end{aligned}$$

2985.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{749}{1177} &:= \frac{7 \times 49}{11 \times 7 \times 7} \\ \frac{749}{11770} &:= \frac{7 \times 49}{11 \times 7 \times 70} \\ \frac{749}{117700} &:= \frac{7 \times 49}{11 \times 7 \times 700} \\ \frac{749}{1177000} &:= \frac{7 \times 49}{11 \times 7 \times 7000} \end{aligned}$$

2990.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{753}{1255} &:= \frac{75+3}{(1+25) \times 5} \\ \frac{753}{12550} &:= \frac{75+3}{(1+25) \times 50} \\ \frac{753}{125500} &:= \frac{75+3}{(1+25) \times 500} \\ \frac{753}{1255000} &:= \frac{75+3}{(1+25) \times 5000} \end{aligned}$$

2986.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{749}{1177} &:= \frac{7+49}{11+77} \\ \frac{749}{11877} &:= \frac{7+49}{11+877} \\ \frac{749}{118877} &:= \frac{7+49}{11+8877} \\ \frac{749}{1188877} &:= \frac{7+49}{11+88877} \end{aligned}$$

2991.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{754}{1160} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{1 \times 1 \times 60} \\ \frac{754}{11600} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{1 \times 1 \times 600} \\ \frac{754}{116000} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{1 \times 1 \times 6000} \\ \frac{754}{1160000} &:= \frac{7 \times 5 + 4}{1 \times 1 \times 60000} \end{aligned}$$

2995.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{756}{1120} &:= \frac{75+6}{1 \times 120} \\ \frac{756}{11200} &:= \frac{75+6}{1 \times 1200} \\ \frac{756}{112000} &:= \frac{75+6}{1 \times 12000} \\ \frac{756}{1120000} &:= \frac{75+6}{1 \times 120000} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2996. \quad & \frac{756}{1155} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 55} \\
 & \frac{756}{11550} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 550} \\
 & \frac{756}{115500} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 5500} \\
 & \frac{756}{1155000} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 55000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3001. \quad & \frac{756}{1428} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{756}{14280} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{756}{142800} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{756}{1428000} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{(1+4^2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3006. \quad & \frac{762}{1397} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{(13+9) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{762}{13970} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{(13+9) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{762}{139700} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{(13+9) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{762}{1397000} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{(13+9) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2997. \quad & \frac{756}{1188} := \frac{7+56}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{756}{11988} := \frac{7+56}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{756}{119988} := \frac{7+56}{11+9988} \\
 & \frac{756}{1199988} := \frac{7+56}{11+99988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3002. \quad & \frac{756}{1470} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+4) \times 7+0} \\
 & \frac{756}{14700} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+4) \times 70+0} \\
 & \frac{756}{147000} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+4) \times 700+0} \\
 & \frac{756}{1470000} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+4) \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3007. \quad & \frac{763}{1090} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{763}{10900} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{763}{109000} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{763}{1090000} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2998. \quad & \frac{756}{1260} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{756}{12600} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{756}{126000} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{756}{1260000} := \frac{(7+5) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3003. \quad & \frac{759}{1150} := \frac{7+59}{(1+1) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{759}{11500} := \frac{7+59}{(1+1) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{759}{115000} := \frac{7+59}{(1+1) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{759}{1150000} := \frac{7+59}{(1+1) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3008. \quad & \frac{763}{1199} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\
 & \frac{763}{11990} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\
 & \frac{763}{119900} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\
 & \frac{763}{1199000} := \frac{7 \times (6+3)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2999. \quad & \frac{756}{1296} := \frac{7+56}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{756}{12960} := \frac{7+56}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{756}{129600} := \frac{7+56}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{756}{1296000} := \frac{7+56}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3004. \quad & \frac{759}{1380} := \frac{7 \times 5+9}{1^3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{759}{13800} := \frac{7 \times 5+9}{1^3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{759}{138000} := \frac{7 \times 5+9}{1^3 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{759}{1380000} := \frac{7 \times 5+9}{1^3 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3009. \quad & \frac{765}{1275} := \frac{76+5}{1 \times 27 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{765}{12750} := \frac{76+5}{1 \times 27 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{765}{127500} := \frac{76+5}{1 \times 27 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{765}{1275000} := \frac{76+5}{1 \times 27 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3000. \quad & \frac{756}{1344} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+3+4) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{756}{13440} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+3+4) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{756}{134400} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+3+4) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{756}{1344000} := \frac{7+5+6}{(1+3+4) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3005. \quad & \frac{762}{1270} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{762}{12700} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{762}{127000} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{762}{1270000} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3010. \quad & \frac{765}{1428} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 28} \\
 & \frac{765}{14280} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 280} \\
 & \frac{765}{142800} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 2800} \\
 & \frac{765}{1428000} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 5}{14 \times 28000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3011. \quad & \frac{766}{1149} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 6}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{766}{11490} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 6}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{766}{114900} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 6}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{766}{1149000} := \frac{7 \times 6 + 6}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3016. \quad & \frac{774}{1419} := \frac{7+7+4}{14+19} \\
 & \frac{774}{14319} := \frac{7+7+4}{14+319} \\
 & \frac{774}{143319} := \frac{7+7+4}{14+3319} \\
 & \frac{774}{1433319} := \frac{7+7+4}{14+33319}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3021. \quad & \frac{777}{814} := \frac{7+7+7}{8+14} \\
 & \frac{777}{8214} := \frac{7+7+7}{8+214} \\
 & \frac{777}{82214} := \frac{7+7+7}{8+2214} \\
 & \frac{777}{822214} := \frac{7+7+7}{8+22214}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3012. \quad & \frac{767}{1475} := \frac{7 \times (6+7)}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{767}{14750} := \frac{7 \times (6+7)}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{767}{147500} := \frac{7 \times (6+7)}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{767}{1475000} := \frac{7 \times (6+7)}{(1+4) \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3017. \quad & \frac{777}{1184} := \frac{7+7+7}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{777}{11840} := \frac{7+7+7}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{777}{118400} := \frac{7+7+7}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{777}{1184000} := \frac{7+7+7}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3022. \quad & \frac{782}{1012} := \frac{7+8+2}{(10+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{782}{10120} := \frac{7+8+2}{(10+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{782}{101200} := \frac{7+8+2}{(10+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{782}{1012000} := \frac{7+8+2}{(10+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3013. \quad & \frac{768}{1776} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1+776} \\
 & \frac{768}{17776} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1+7776} \\
 & \frac{768}{177776} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1+77776} \\
 & \frac{768}{1777776} := \frac{7 \times 6 \times 8}{1+777776}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3018. \quad & \frac{777}{1221} := \frac{7+7+7}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{777}{12321} := \frac{7+7+7}{12+321} \\
 & \frac{777}{123321} := \frac{7+7+7}{12+3321} \\
 & \frac{777}{1233321} := \frac{7+7+7}{12+33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3023. \quad & \frac{782}{1012} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{782}{10212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{782}{102212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{782}{1022212} := \frac{7+8+2}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3014. \quad & \frac{770}{1155} := \frac{7+7+0}{1+15+5} \\
 & \frac{770}{12155} := \frac{7+7+0}{1+215+5} \\
 & \frac{770}{122155} := \frac{7+7+0}{1+2215+5} \\
 & \frac{770}{1222155} := \frac{7+7+0}{1+22215+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3019. \quad & \frac{777}{1258} := \frac{7+77}{(12+5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{777}{12580} := \frac{7+77}{(12+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{777}{125800} := \frac{7+77}{(12+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{777}{1258000} := \frac{7+77}{(12+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3024. \quad & \frac{782}{1122} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{782}{11322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{782}{113322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+3322} \\
 & \frac{782}{1133322} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{11+33322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3015. \quad & \frac{770}{1815} := \frac{7+7+0}{18+15} \\
 & \frac{770}{18315} := \frac{7+7+0}{18+315} \\
 & \frac{770}{183315} := \frac{7+7+0}{18+3315} \\
 & \frac{770}{1833315} := \frac{7+7+0}{18+33315}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3020. \quad & \frac{777}{1480} := \frac{7+7+7}{(1+4) \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{777}{14800} := \frac{7+7+7}{(1+4) \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{777}{148000} := \frac{7+7+7}{(1+4) \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{777}{1480000} := \frac{7+7+7}{(1+4) \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3025. \quad & \frac{782}{1224} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{782}{12240} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{782}{122400} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{782}{1224000} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3026. \quad & \frac{782}{1292} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{782}{12920} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{782}{129200} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{782}{1292000} := \frac{7+8 \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3031. \quad & \frac{784}{1280} := \frac{7 \times 84}{12 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{784}{12800} := \frac{7 \times 84}{12 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{784}{128000} := \frac{7 \times 84}{12 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{784}{1280000} := \frac{7 \times 84}{12 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3036. \quad & \frac{791}{1356} := \frac{7+91}{1 \times 3 \times 56} \\
 & \frac{791}{13560} := \frac{7+91}{1 \times 3 \times 560} \\
 & \frac{791}{135600} := \frac{7+91}{1 \times 3 \times 5600} \\
 & \frac{791}{1356000} := \frac{7+91}{1 \times 3 \times 56000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3027. \quad & \frac{783}{1160} := \frac{78+3}{(1+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{783}{11600} := \frac{78+3}{(1+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{783}{116000} := \frac{78+3}{(1+1) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{783}{1160000} := \frac{78+3}{(1+1) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3032. \quad & \frac{784}{1365} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{784}{13650} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{784}{136500} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{784}{1365000} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{13 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3037. \quad & \frac{792}{1125} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{792}{11250} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{792}{112500} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{792}{1125000} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3028. \quad & \frac{783}{1305} := \frac{7+83}{1 \times 30 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{783}{13050} := \frac{7+83}{1 \times 30 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{783}{130500} := \frac{7+83}{1 \times 30 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{783}{1305000} := \frac{7+83}{1 \times 30 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3033. \quad & \frac{784}{1400} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{784}{14000} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{784}{140000} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 40000} \\
 & \frac{784}{1400000} := \frac{7 \times 8 \times 4}{1 \times 400000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3038. \quad & \frac{792}{1280} := \frac{7+92}{1 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{792}{12800} := \frac{7+92}{1 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{792}{128000} := \frac{7+92}{1 \times 2 \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{792}{1280000} := \frac{7+92}{1 \times 2 \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3029. \quad & \frac{783}{1392} := \frac{(7+8) \times 3}{(1+39) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{783}{13920} := \frac{(7+8) \times 3}{(1+39) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{783}{139200} := \frac{(7+8) \times 3}{(1+39) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{783}{1392000} := \frac{(7+8) \times 3}{(1+39) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3034. \quad & \frac{785}{1727} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+27} \\
 & \frac{785}{17427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+427} \\
 & \frac{785}{174427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+4427} \\
 & \frac{785}{1744427} := \frac{7+8+5}{17+44427}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3039. \quad & \frac{792}{1350} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{792}{13500} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{792}{135000} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{792}{1350000} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3030. \quad & \frac{784}{1120} := \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{784}{11200} := \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{784}{112000} := \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 12000} \\
 & \frac{784}{1120000} := \frac{7 \times (8+4)}{1 \times 120000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3035. \quad & \frac{789}{1315} := \frac{7+89}{(1+31) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{789}{13150} := \frac{7+89}{(1+31) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{789}{131500} := \frac{7+89}{(1+31) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{789}{1315000} := \frac{7+89}{(1+31) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

3040.

$$\frac{792}{1368} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{792}{13680} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{792}{136800} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{792}{1368000} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+3 \times 6) \times 8000}$$

3044.

$$\frac{792}{891} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+91}$$

$$\frac{792}{8991} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+991}$$

$$\frac{792}{89991} := \frac{7+9^2}{8+9991}$$

3049.

$$\frac{804}{1072} := \frac{8+04}{(1+07) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{804}{10720} := \frac{8+04}{(1+07) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{804}{107200} := \frac{8+04}{(1+07) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{804}{1072000} := \frac{8+04}{(1+07) \times 2000}$$

3041.

$$\frac{792}{1408} := \frac{7+9+2}{1 \times 4 \times 08}$$

$$\frac{792}{14080} := \frac{7+9+2}{1 \times 4 \times 080}$$

$$\frac{792}{140800} := \frac{7+9+2}{1 \times 4 \times 0800}$$

$$\frac{792}{1408000} := \frac{7+9+2}{1 \times 4 \times 08000}$$

3045.

$$\frac{795}{1325} := \frac{7+9+5}{(1+3 \times 2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{795}{13250} := \frac{7+9+5}{(1+3 \times 2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{795}{132500} := \frac{7+9+5}{(1+3 \times 2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{795}{1325000} := \frac{7+9+5}{(1+3 \times 2) \times 5000}$$

3050.

$$\frac{804}{1206} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 06}$$

$$\frac{804}{12060} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 060}$$

$$\frac{804}{120600} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 0600}$$

$$\frac{804}{1206000} := \frac{8+0 \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 06000}$$

3042.

$$\frac{792}{1440} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{792}{14400} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{792}{144000} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

$$\frac{792}{1440000} := \frac{7+9^2}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}$$

3046.

$$\frac{798}{1368} := \frac{7 \times (9+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 68}$$

$$\frac{798}{13680} := \frac{7 \times (9+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 680}$$

$$\frac{798}{136800} := \frac{7 \times (9+8)}{1 \times 3 \times 6800}$$

3051.

$$\frac{804}{14874} := \frac{8 \times 04}{1^4 \times 8 \times 74}$$

$$\frac{804}{148740} := \frac{8 \times 04}{1^4 \times 8 \times 740}$$

$$\frac{804}{1487400} := \frac{8 \times 04}{1^4 \times 8 \times 7400}$$

3047.

$$\frac{801}{1335} := \frac{80+1}{1 \times 3^3 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{801}{13350} := \frac{80+1}{1 \times 3^3 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{801}{133500} := \frac{80+1}{1 \times 3^3 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{801}{1335000} := \frac{80+1}{1 \times 3^3 \times 5000}$$

3052.

$$\frac{805}{1288} := \frac{8 \times 05}{1^2 \times 8 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{805}{12880} := \frac{8 \times 05}{1^2 \times 8 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{805}{128800} := \frac{8 \times 05}{1^2 \times 8 \times 800}$$

$$\frac{805}{1288000} := \frac{8 \times 05}{1^2 \times 8 \times 8000}$$

3043.

$$\frac{792}{1485} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{792}{14850} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{792}{148500} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{792}{1485000} := \frac{7+9^2}{(1+4 \times 8) \times 5000}$$

3048.

$$\frac{803}{1241} := \frac{8+03}{(1+2^4) \times 1}$$

$$\frac{803}{12410} := \frac{8+03}{(1+2^4) \times 10}$$

$$\frac{803}{124100} := \frac{8+03}{(1+2^4) \times 100}$$

$$\frac{803}{1241000} := \frac{8+03}{(1+2^4) \times 1000}$$

3053.

$$\frac{805}{1449} := \frac{8 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{805}{14490} := \frac{8 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{805}{144900} := \frac{8 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{805}{1449000} := \frac{8 \times 05}{(1 \times 4 + 4) \times 9000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3054. \quad & \frac{805}{1771} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17 + 71} \\
 & \frac{805}{17871} := \frac{8 \times 05}{17 + 871} \\
 & \frac{178871}{805} := \frac{17 + 8871}{8 \times 05} \\
 & \frac{178871}{178871} := \frac{17 + 88871}{17 + 88871}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3059. \quad & \frac{808}{1212} := \frac{8 + 08}{1 \times 2 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{12120}{808} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 120}{8 + 08} \\
 & \frac{121200}{808} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 1200}{8 + 08} \\
 & \frac{1212000}{808} := \frac{1 \times 2 \times 12000}{8 + 08}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3064. \quad & \frac{813}{1084} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 3}{1 \times 08 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{813}{10840} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 3}{1 \times 08 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{108400}{813} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 400}{8 \times 1 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{1084000}{813} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 4000}{8 \times 1 \times 3}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3055. \quad & \frac{807}{1345} := \frac{8 + 07}{(1^3 + 4) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{13450}{807} := \frac{(1^3 + 4) \times 50}{8 + 07} \\
 & \frac{134500}{807} := \frac{(1^3 + 4) \times 500}{8 + 07} \\
 & \frac{1345000}{807} := \frac{(1^3 + 4) \times 5000}{8 + 07}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3060. \quad & \frac{808}{1313} := \frac{8 + 0 \times 8}{1^3 \times 13} \\
 & \frac{13130}{808} := \frac{1^3 \times 130}{8 + 0 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{131300}{808} := \frac{1^3 \times 1300}{8 + 0 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{1313000}{808} := \frac{1^3 \times 13000}{8 + 0 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3065. \quad & \frac{814}{1184} := \frac{8 + 14}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{11840}{814} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{118400}{814} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{1184000}{814} := \frac{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}{8 + 14}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3056. \quad & \frac{808}{1010} := \frac{8 + 0 \times 8}{1 \times 010} \\
 & \frac{808}{10100} := \frac{8 + 0 \times 8}{1 \times 0100} \\
 & \frac{101000}{808} := \frac{1 \times 01000}{8 + 0 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{1010000}{808} := \frac{1 \times 010000}{8 + 0 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3061. \quad & \frac{808}{1414} := \frac{8 + 0 \times 8}{1^4 \times 14} \\
 & \frac{14140}{808} := \frac{1^4 \times 140}{8 + 0 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{141400}{808} := \frac{1^4 \times 1400}{8 + 0 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{1414000}{808} := \frac{1^4 \times 14000}{8 + 0 \times 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3066. \quad & \frac{814}{1221} := \frac{8 + 14}{12 + 21} \\
 & \frac{12321}{814} := \frac{12 + 321}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{123321}{814} := \frac{12 + 3321}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{1233321}{814} := \frac{12 + 33321}{8 + 14}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3057. \quad & \frac{808}{1111} := \frac{80 + 8}{11 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{11110}{808} := \frac{11 \times 110}{80 + 8} \\
 & \frac{111100}{808} := \frac{11 \times 1100}{80 + 8} \\
 & \frac{1111000}{808} := \frac{11 \times 11000}{80 + 8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3062. \quad & \frac{812}{1015} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{(1 + 01) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{812}{10150} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{(1 + 01) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{812}{101500} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{(1 + 01) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{812}{1015000} := \frac{8 \times 1^2}{(1 + 01) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3067. \quad & \frac{814}{1480} := \frac{8 + 14}{(1 + 4) \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{814}{14800} := \frac{8 + 14}{(1 + 4) \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{148000}{814} := \frac{(1 + 4) \times 800 + 0}{8 + 14} \\
 & \frac{1480000}{814} := \frac{(1 + 4) \times 8000 + 0}{8 + 14}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3058. \quad & \frac{808}{1111} := \frac{8 + 08}{11 + 11} \\
 & \frac{11211}{808} := \frac{11 + 211}{8 + 08} \\
 & \frac{112211}{808} := \frac{11 + 2211}{8 + 08} \\
 & \frac{1122211}{808} := \frac{11 + 22211}{8 + 08}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3063. \quad & \frac{812}{1421} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{14 \times 2 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{812}{14210} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{14 \times 2 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{812}{142100} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{14 \times 2 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{812}{1421000} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 2}{14 \times 2 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3068. \quad & \frac{816}{1088} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 08 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{816}{10880} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 08 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{108800}{816} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 800}{8 \times 1 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{1088000}{816} := \frac{1 \times 08 \times 8000}{8 \times 1 \times 6}
 \end{aligned}$$

3069.

$$\frac{816}{1122} := \frac{8+16}{11+22}$$

$$\frac{816}{11322} := \frac{8+16}{11+322}$$

$$\frac{816}{113322} := \frac{8+16}{11+3322}$$

3074.

$$\frac{816}{1428} := \frac{8 \times 16}{14 \times 2 \times 8}$$

$$\frac{816}{14280} := \frac{8 \times 16}{14 \times 2 \times 80}$$

$$\frac{816}{142800} := \frac{8 \times 16}{14 \times 2 \times 800}$$

3079.

$$\frac{819}{910} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{9 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{819}{9100} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{9 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{819}{91000} := \frac{(8+1) \times 9}{9 \times 1000}$$

3070.

$$\frac{816}{1224} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 24}$$

$$\frac{816}{12240} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 240}$$

$$\frac{816}{122400} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 2400}$$

$$\frac{816}{1224000} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2) \times 24000}$$

3075.

$$\frac{816}{1445} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{816}{14450} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{816}{144500} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{816}{1445000} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 5000}$$

3080.

$$\frac{820}{1804} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+04}$$

$$\frac{820}{18204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+204}$$

$$\frac{820}{182204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+2204}$$

$$\frac{820}{1822204} := \frac{8+2+0}{18+22204}$$

3071.

$$\frac{816}{1275} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{816}{12750} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{816}{127500} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{816}{1275000} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{(1+2 \times 7) \times 5000}$$

3076.

$$\frac{816}{1683} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16+83}$$

$$\frac{816}{16983} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16+983}$$

$$\frac{816}{169983} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16+9983}$$

$$\frac{816}{1699983} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{16+99983}$$

3081.

$$\frac{820}{902} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+02}$$

$$\frac{820}{9102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+102}$$

$$\frac{820}{91102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+1102}$$

$$\frac{820}{911102} := \frac{8+2+0}{9+11102}$$

3072.

$$\frac{816}{1292} := \frac{8+16}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{816}{12920} := \frac{8+16}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{816}{129200} := \frac{8+16}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{816}{1292000} := \frac{8+16}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}$$

3077.

$$\frac{819}{1001} := \frac{8+1^9}{10+01}$$

$$\frac{819}{10101} := \frac{8+1^9}{10+101}$$

$$\frac{819}{101101} := \frac{8+1^9}{10+1101}$$

$$\frac{819}{1011101} := \frac{8+1^9}{10+11101}$$

3082.

$$\frac{822}{1233} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3}$$

$$\frac{822}{12330} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 30}$$

$$\frac{822}{123300} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 300}$$

$$\frac{822}{1233000} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3000}$$

3073.

$$\frac{816}{1326} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 26}$$

$$\frac{816}{13260} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 260}$$

$$\frac{816}{132600} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 2600}$$

$$\frac{816}{1326000} := \frac{8 \times 1 \times 6}{1 \times 3 \times 26000}$$

3078.

$$\frac{819}{1365} := \frac{8+1+9}{1^3 \times 6 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{819}{13650} := \frac{8+1+9}{1^3 \times 6 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{819}{136500} := \frac{8+1+9}{1^3 \times 6 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{819}{1365000} := \frac{8+1+9}{1^3 \times 6 \times 5000}$$

3083.

$$\frac{822}{1507} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+07}$$

$$\frac{822}{15207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+207}$$

$$\frac{822}{152207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+2207}$$

$$\frac{822}{1522207} := \frac{8+2 \times 2}{15+22207}$$

3084.

$$\frac{824}{1030} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 030}$$

$$\frac{824}{10300} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 0300}$$

$$\frac{824}{103000} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 03000}$$

$$\frac{824}{1030000} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 030000}$$

3088.

$$\frac{824}{1339} := \frac{8+2^4}{1^3 \times 39}$$

$$\frac{824}{13390} := \frac{8+2^4}{1^3 \times 390}$$

$$\frac{824}{133900} := \frac{8+2^4}{1^3 \times 3900}$$

$$\frac{824}{1339000} := \frac{8+2^4}{1^3 \times 39000}$$

3093.

$$\frac{825}{15875} := \frac{8+25}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{825}{158750} := \frac{8+25}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{825}{1587500} := \frac{8+25}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{825}{15875000} := \frac{8+25}{(15 \times 8+7) \times 5000}$$

3085.

$$\frac{824}{1133} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 1 \times 33}$$

$$\frac{824}{11330} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 1 \times 330}$$

$$\frac{824}{113300} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 1 \times 3300}$$

$$\frac{824}{1133000} := \frac{8+2^4}{1 \times 1 \times 33000}$$

3089.

$$\frac{824}{1442} := \frac{8 \times 2 \times 4}{14 \times 4 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{824}{14420} := \frac{8 \times 2 \times 4}{14 \times 4 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{824}{144200} := \frac{8 \times 2 \times 4}{14 \times 4 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{824}{1442000} := \frac{8 \times 2 \times 4}{14 \times 4 \times 2000}$$

3094.

$$\frac{825}{17325} := \frac{8+2+5}{1 \times 7 \times 3^2 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{825}{173250} := \frac{8+2+5}{1 \times 7 \times 3^2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{825}{1732500} := \frac{8+2+5}{1 \times 7 \times 3^2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{825}{17325000} := \frac{8+2+5}{1 \times 7 \times 3^2 \times 5000}$$

3086.

$$\frac{824}{1133} := \frac{8+24}{11+33}$$

$$\frac{824}{11433} := \frac{8+24}{11+433}$$

$$\frac{824}{114433} := \frac{8+24}{11+4433}$$

$$\frac{824}{1144433} := \frac{8+24}{11+44433}$$

3090.

$$\frac{825}{1188} := \frac{(8+2) \times 5}{(1 \times 1+8) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{825}{11880} := \frac{(8+2) \times 5}{(1 \times 1+8) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{825}{118800} := \frac{(8+2) \times 5}{(1 \times 1+8) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{825}{1188000} := \frac{(8+2) \times 5}{(1 \times 1+8) \times 8000}$$

3095.

$$\frac{825}{1815} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+15}$$

$$\frac{825}{18315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+315}$$

$$\frac{825}{183315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+3315}$$

$$\frac{825}{1833315} := \frac{8+2+5}{18+33315}$$

3087.

$$\frac{824}{1236} := \frac{8+2+4}{(1 \times 2+3) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{824}{12360} := \frac{8+2+4}{(1 \times 2+3) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{824}{123600} := \frac{8+2+4}{(1 \times 2+3) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{824}{1236000} := \frac{8+2+4}{(1 \times 2+3) \times 6000}$$

3091.

$$\frac{825}{1250} := \frac{8+25}{1^2 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{825}{12500} := \frac{8+25}{1^2 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{825}{125000} := \frac{8+25}{1^2 \times 5000}$$

$$\frac{825}{1250000} := \frac{8+25}{1^2 \times 50000}$$

3096.

$$\frac{828}{1012} := \frac{8+2+8}{(10+1) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{828}{10120} := \frac{8+2+8}{(10+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{828}{101200} := \frac{8+2+8}{(10+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{828}{1012000} := \frac{8+2+8}{(10+1) \times 2000}$$

3092.

$$\frac{825}{1375} := \frac{8 \times 2+5}{1^3 \times 7 \times 5}$$

$$\frac{825}{13750} := \frac{8 \times 2+5}{1^3 \times 7 \times 50}$$

$$\frac{825}{137500} := \frac{8 \times 2+5}{1^3 \times 7 \times 500}$$

$$\frac{825}{1375000} := \frac{8 \times 2+5}{1^3 \times 7 \times 5000}$$

3097.

$$\frac{828}{1012} := \frac{8+2+8}{10+12}$$

$$\frac{828}{10212} := \frac{8+2+8}{10+212}$$

$$\frac{828}{102212} := \frac{8+2+8}{10+2212}$$

$$\frac{828}{1022212} := \frac{8+2+8}{10+22212}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{828}{1150} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 1 \times 50} \\
 \frac{828}{11500} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 1 \times 500} \\
 \frac{828}{115000} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 1 \times 5000} \\
 \frac{828}{1150000} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 1 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{833}{1225} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{(1+2 \times 2) \times 5} \\
 \frac{833}{12250} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{(1+2 \times 2) \times 50} \\
 \frac{833}{122500} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{(1+2 \times 2) \times 500} \\
 \frac{833}{1225000} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{(1+2 \times 2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1197} &:= \frac{8+36}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 \frac{836}{11970} &:= \frac{8+36}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 \frac{836}{119700} &:= \frac{8+36}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 \frac{836}{1197000} &:= \frac{8+36}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{828}{1173} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 17 \times 3} \\
 \frac{828}{11730} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 17 \times 30} \\
 \frac{828}{117300} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 17 \times 300} \\
 \frac{828}{1173000} &:= \frac{8+28}{1 \times 17 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{833}{1323} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{1 \times 3^2 \times 3} \\
 \frac{833}{13230} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{1 \times 3^2 \times 30} \\
 \frac{833}{132300} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{1 \times 3^2 \times 300} \\
 \frac{833}{1323000} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{1 \times 3^2 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1254} &:= \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 2 \times 54} \\
 \frac{836}{12540} &:= \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 2 \times 540} \\
 \frac{836}{125400} &:= \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 2 \times 5400} \\
 \frac{836}{1254000} &:= \frac{8 \times (3+6)}{1 \times 2 \times 54000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{832}{1248} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{12 \times 4 \times 8} \\
 \frac{832}{12480} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{12 \times 4 \times 80} \\
 \frac{832}{124800} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{12 \times 4 \times 800} \\
 \frac{832}{1248000} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{12 \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{833}{1428} &:= \frac{8+3+3}{(1^4+2) \times 8} \\
 \frac{833}{14280} &:= \frac{8+3+3}{(1^4+2) \times 80} \\
 \frac{833}{142800} &:= \frac{8+3+3}{(1^4+2) \times 800} \\
 \frac{833}{1428000} &:= \frac{8+3+3}{(1^4+2) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1254} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+54} \\
 \frac{836}{12654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+654} \\
 \frac{836}{126654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+6654} \\
 \frac{836}{1266654} &:= \frac{8+36}{12+66654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{832}{1443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+443} \\
 \frac{832}{14443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+4443} \\
 \frac{832}{144443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+44443} \\
 \frac{832}{1444443} &:= \frac{8 \times 32}{1+444443}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{833}{1617} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+17} \\
 \frac{833}{16317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+317} \\
 \frac{833}{163317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+3317} \\
 \frac{833}{1633317} &:= \frac{8+3 \times 3}{16+33317}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1368} &:= \frac{8+36}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8} \\
 \frac{836}{13680} &:= \frac{8+36}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 80} \\
 \frac{836}{136800} &:= \frac{8+36}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 800} \\
 \frac{836}{1368000} &:= \frac{8+36}{(1 \times 3+6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{832}{1456} &:= \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 6} \\
 \frac{832}{14560} &:= \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 60} \\
 \frac{832}{145600} &:= \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 600} \\
 \frac{832}{1456000} &:= \frac{8 \times 3^2}{(1+4 \times 5) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1045} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+45} \\
 \frac{836}{10545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+545} \\
 \frac{836}{105545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+5545} \\
 \frac{836}{1055545} &:= \frac{8+36}{10+55545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{836}{1463} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 63} \\
 \frac{836}{14630} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 630} \\
 \frac{836}{146300} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 6300} \\
 \frac{836}{1463000} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 \times 6}{1 \times 4 \times 63000}
 \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned} \frac{836}{1463} &:= \frac{8+36}{14+63} \\ \frac{836}{836} &:= \frac{8+36}{8+36} \\ \frac{14763}{836} &:= \frac{14+763}{8+36} \\ \frac{147763}{836} &:= \frac{14+7763}{8+36} \\ \frac{147763}{836} &:= \frac{14+7763}{8+36} \\ \frac{1477763}{836} &:= \frac{14+77763}{8+36} \end{aligned}$$

3118.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{837}{14880} &:= \frac{8+3+7}{(1+4) \times 8 \times 8 + 0} \\ \frac{837}{837} &:= \frac{8+3+7}{8+3+7} \\ \frac{148800}{837} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 8 \times 80 + 0}{8+3+7} \\ \frac{1488000}{837} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 8 \times 800 + 0}{8+3+7} \\ \frac{14880000}{837} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 8 \times 8000 + 0}{8+3+7} \end{aligned}$$

3123.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{844}{1055} &:= \frac{8+4 \times 4}{(1+05) \times 5} \\ \frac{844}{844} &:= \frac{8+4 \times 4}{8+4 \times 4} \\ \frac{10550}{844} &:= \frac{(1+05) \times 50}{8+4 \times 4} \\ \frac{105500}{844} &:= \frac{(1+05) \times 500}{8+4 \times 4} \\ \frac{1055000}{844} &:= \frac{(1+05) \times 5000}{8+4 \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

3114.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{836}{1672} &:= \frac{8+36}{16+72} \\ \frac{836}{836} &:= \frac{8+36}{8+36} \\ \frac{16872}{836} &:= \frac{16+872}{8+36} \\ \frac{168872}{836} &:= \frac{16+8872}{8+36} \\ \frac{168872}{836} &:= \frac{16+8872}{8+36} \\ \frac{1688872}{836} &:= \frac{16+88872}{8+36} \end{aligned}$$

3119.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{840}{1155} &:= \frac{8+40}{11+55} \\ \frac{840}{840} &:= \frac{8+40}{8+40} \\ \frac{11655}{840} &:= \frac{11+655}{8+40} \\ \frac{116655}{840} &:= \frac{11+6655}{8+40} \\ \frac{116655}{840} &:= \frac{11+6655}{8+40} \end{aligned}$$

3124.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{844}{1266} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 4}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 6} \\ \frac{844}{844} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 4}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{12660}{844} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 60}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{126600}{844} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 600}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{1266000}{844} &:= \frac{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 6000}{(8+4) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

3115.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{836}{8455} &:= \frac{8+36}{(84+5) \times 5} \\ \frac{836}{836} &:= \frac{8+36}{8+36} \\ \frac{84550}{836} &:= \frac{(84+5) \times 50}{8+36} \\ \frac{845500}{836} &:= \frac{(84+5) \times 500}{8+36} \\ \frac{8455000}{836} &:= \frac{(84+5) \times 5000}{8+36} \end{aligned}$$

3120.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{842}{1263} &:= \frac{8 \times 4^2}{1 \times 2^6 \times 3} \\ \frac{842}{842} &:= \frac{8 \times 4^2}{8 \times 4^2} \\ \frac{12630}{842} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^6 \times 30}{8 \times 4^2} \\ \frac{126300}{842} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^6 \times 300}{8 \times 4^2} \\ \frac{1263000}{842} &:= \frac{1 \times 2^6 \times 3000}{8 \times 4^2} \end{aligned}$$

3125.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{844}{1477} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 4}{(1+4+7) \times 7} \\ \frac{844}{844} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 4}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{14770}{844} &:= \frac{(1+4+7) \times 70}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{147700}{844} &:= \frac{(1+4+7) \times 700}{(8+4) \times 4} \\ \frac{1477000}{844} &:= \frac{(1+4+7) \times 7000}{(8+4) \times 4} \end{aligned}$$

3116.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{837}{1215} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{(1+2) \times 15} \\ \frac{837}{837} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{12150}{837} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 150}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{121500}{837} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 1500}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{1215000}{837} &:= \frac{(1+2) \times 15000}{8 \times 3 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

3121.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{843}{1124} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 3}{1 \times 12 \times 4} \\ \frac{843}{843} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 3}{(8+4) \times 3} \\ \frac{11240}{843} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 40}{(8+4) \times 3} \\ \frac{112400}{843} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 400}{(8+4) \times 3} \\ \frac{1124000}{843} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 4000}{(8+4) \times 3} \end{aligned}$$

3117.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{837}{1350} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{1^3 \times 50} \\ \frac{837}{837} &:= \frac{8 \times 3 + 7}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{13500}{837} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 500}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{135000}{837} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 5000}{8 \times 3 + 7} \\ \frac{1350000}{837} &:= \frac{1^3 \times 50000}{8 \times 3 + 7} \end{aligned}$$

3122.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{843}{1405} &:= \frac{8+4+3}{(1+4) \times 05} \\ \frac{843}{843} &:= \frac{8+4+3}{8+4+3} \\ \frac{14050}{843} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 050}{8+4+3} \\ \frac{140500}{843} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 0500}{8+4+3} \\ \frac{1405000}{843} &:= \frac{(1+4) \times 05000}{8+4+3} \end{aligned}$$

3126.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{846}{1128} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{1 \times 12 \times 8} \\ \frac{846}{846} &:= \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{(8+4) \times 6} \\ \frac{11280}{846} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 80}{(8+4) \times 6} \\ \frac{112800}{846} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 800}{(8+4) \times 6} \\ \frac{1128000}{846} &:= \frac{1 \times 12 \times 8000}{(8+4) \times 6} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3127. \quad & \frac{846}{1175} := \frac{8+46}{1 \times 1 \times 75} \\
 & \frac{846}{11750} := \frac{8+46}{1 \times 1 \times 750} \\
 & \frac{846}{117500} := \frac{8+46}{1 \times 1 \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{846}{1175000} := \frac{8+46}{1 \times 1 \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3132. \quad & \frac{847}{1386} := \frac{8 \times (4+7)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{847}{13860} := \frac{8 \times (4+7)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{847}{138600} := \frac{8 \times (4+7)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{847}{1386000} := \frac{8 \times (4+7)}{1 \times 3 \times 8 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3137. \quad & \frac{849}{1132} := \frac{8+4+9}{(1+13) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{849}{11320} := \frac{8+4+9}{(1+13) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{849}{113200} := \frac{8+4+9}{(1+13) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{849}{1132000} := \frac{8+4+9}{(1+13) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3128. \quad & \frac{846}{1269} := \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{846}{12690} := \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{846}{126900} := \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{846}{1269000} := \frac{(8+4) \times 6}{1 \times 2 \times 6 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3133. \quad & \frac{848}{1166} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 66} \\
 & \frac{848}{11660} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 660} \\
 & \frac{848}{116600} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 6600} \\
 & \frac{848}{1166000} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{(1+1) \times 66000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3138. \quad & \frac{850}{1887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+887} \\
 & \frac{850}{18887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+8887} \\
 & \frac{850}{188887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+88887} \\
 & \frac{850}{1888887} := \frac{8 \times 50}{1+888887}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3129. \quad & \frac{846}{1316} := \frac{8+46}{(13+1) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{846}{13160} := \frac{8+46}{(13+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{846}{131600} := \frac{8+46}{(13+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{846}{1316000} := \frac{8+46}{(13+1) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3134. \quad & \frac{848}{1166} := \frac{8+48}{11+66} \\
 & \frac{848}{11766} := \frac{8+48}{11+766} \\
 & \frac{848}{117766} := \frac{8+48}{11+7766} \\
 & \frac{848}{1177766} := \frac{8+48}{11+77766}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3139. \quad & \frac{850}{935} := \frac{8 \times 5+0}{9+35} \\
 & \frac{850}{9435} := \frac{8 \times 5+0}{9+435} \\
 & \frac{850}{94435} := \frac{8 \times 5+0}{9+4435} \\
 & \frac{850}{944435} := \frac{8 \times 5+0}{9+44435}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3130. \quad & \frac{847}{1155} := \frac{8+47}{1 \times 15 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{847}{11550} := \frac{8+47}{1 \times 15 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{847}{115500} := \frac{8+47}{1 \times 15 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{847}{1155000} := \frac{8+47}{1 \times 15 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3135. \quad & \frac{848}{1272} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 72} \\
 & \frac{848}{12720} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 720} \\
 & \frac{848}{127200} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{848}{1272000} := \frac{8 \times (4+8)}{1 \times 2 \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3140. \quad & \frac{852}{1420} := \frac{8+52}{(1+4) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{852}{14200} := \frac{8+52}{(1+4) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{852}{142000} := \frac{8+52}{(1+4) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{852}{1420000} := \frac{8+52}{(1+4) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3131. \quad & \frac{847}{1210} := \frac{(8+4) \times 7}{12 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{847}{12100} := \frac{(8+4) \times 7}{12 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{847}{121000} := \frac{(8+4) \times 7}{12 \times 1000} \\
 & \frac{847}{1210000} := \frac{(8+4) \times 7}{12 \times 10000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3136. \quad & \frac{848}{1484} := \frac{84 \times 8}{14 \times 84} \\
 & \frac{848}{14840} := \frac{84 \times 8}{14 \times 840} \\
 & \frac{848}{148400} := \frac{84 \times 8}{14 \times 8400} \\
 & \frac{848}{1484000} := \frac{84 \times 8}{14 \times 84000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3141. \quad & \frac{852}{14910} := \frac{(8+5) \times 2}{(1+4) \times 91+0} \\
 & \frac{852}{149100} := \frac{(8+5) \times 2}{(1+4) \times 910+0} \\
 & \frac{852}{1491000} := \frac{(8+5) \times 2}{(1+4) \times 9100+0} \\
 & \frac{852}{14910000} := \frac{(8+5) \times 2}{(1+4) \times 91000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3142. \quad & \frac{852}{1562} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 62} \\
 & \frac{852}{15762} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 2}{15 + 762} \\
 & \frac{157762}{852} := \frac{15 + 7762}{8 \times 5 + 2} \\
 & \frac{157762}{157762} := \frac{15 + 7762}{15 + 7762}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3147. \quad & \frac{855}{1254} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 54} \\
 & \frac{855}{12654} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{12 + 654} \\
 & \frac{126654}{855} := \frac{12 + 6654}{8 \times 5 + 5} \\
 & \frac{126654}{126654} := \frac{12 + 6654}{12 + 6654}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3152. \quad & \frac{856}{1177} := \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 77} \\
 & \frac{856}{11877} := \frac{8 + 56}{11 + 877} \\
 & \frac{118877}{856} := \frac{11 + 8877}{8 + 56} \\
 & \frac{118877}{118877} := \frac{11 + 8877}{11 + 8877}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3143. \quad & \frac{855}{1045} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 45} \\
 & \frac{855}{10545} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{10 + 545} \\
 & \frac{105545}{855} := \frac{10 + 5545}{8 \times 5 + 5} \\
 & \frac{105545}{105545} := \frac{10 + 5545}{10 + 5545}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3148. \quad & \frac{855}{1425} := \frac{8 + 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 2) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{855}{14250} := \frac{8 + 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 2) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{855}{142500} := \frac{8 + 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 2) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{855}{1425000} := \frac{8 + 5 + 5}{(1 \times 4 + 2) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3153. \quad & \frac{856}{1284} := \frac{8 + 56}{(1 + 2) \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{856}{12840} := \frac{8 + 56}{(1 + 2) \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{856}{128400} := \frac{8 + 56}{(1 + 2) \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{856}{1284000} := \frac{8 + 56}{(1 + 2) \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3144. \quad & \frac{855}{1140} := \frac{8 + 5 \times 5}{11 \times 4 + 0} \\
 & \frac{855}{11400} := \frac{8 + 5 \times 5}{11 \times 40 + 0} \\
 & \frac{855}{114000} := \frac{8 + 5 \times 5}{11 \times 400 + 0} \\
 & \frac{855}{1140000} := \frac{8 + 5 \times 5}{11 \times 4000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3149. \quad & \frac{855}{1463} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 63} \\
 & \frac{855}{14763} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 763} \\
 & \frac{855}{147763} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 7763} \\
 & \frac{855}{1477763} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{14 + 77763}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3154. \quad & \frac{858}{1144} := \frac{8 + 58}{(1 + 1) \times 44} \\
 & \frac{858}{11440} := \frac{8 + 58}{(1 + 1) \times 440} \\
 & \frac{858}{114400} := \frac{8 + 58}{(1 + 1) \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{858}{1144000} := \frac{8 + 58}{(1 + 1) \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3145. \quad & \frac{855}{1197} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{855}{11970} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{855}{119700} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{855}{1197000} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{1 \times 1 \times 9 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3150. \quad & \frac{855}{1672} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 72} \\
 & \frac{855}{16872} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 872} \\
 & \frac{855}{168872} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 8872} \\
 & \frac{855}{1688872} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{16 + 88872}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3155. \quad & \frac{858}{1188} := \frac{8 \times (5 + 8)}{1 \times 18 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{858}{11880} := \frac{8 \times (5 + 8)}{1 \times 18 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{858}{118800} := \frac{8 \times (5 + 8)}{1 \times 18 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{858}{1188000} := \frac{8 \times (5 + 8)}{1 \times 18 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3146. \quad & \frac{855}{1254} := \frac{85 + 5}{(1 + 2^5) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{855}{12540} := \frac{85 + 5}{(1 + 2^5) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{855}{125400} := \frac{85 + 5}{(1 + 2^5) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{855}{1254000} := \frac{85 + 5}{(1 + 2^5) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3151. \quad & \frac{855}{1881} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 81} \\
 & \frac{855}{18981} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 981} \\
 & \frac{855}{189981} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 9981} \\
 & \frac{855}{1899981} := \frac{8 \times 5 + 5}{18 + 99981}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3156. \quad & \frac{858}{1248} := \frac{8 + 58}{1 \times 2 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{858}{12480} := \frac{8 + 58}{1 \times 2 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{858}{124800} := \frac{8 + 58}{1 \times 2 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{858}{1248000} := \frac{8 + 58}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3157. \quad & \frac{858}{1287} := \frac{8+58}{12+87} \\
 & \frac{858}{12987} := \frac{8+58}{12+987} \\
 & \frac{12987}{858} := \frac{12+987}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{129987}{858} := \frac{12+9987}{8+58} \\
 & \frac{129987}{129987} := \frac{12+9987}{12+9987}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3162. \quad & \frac{864}{1215} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 15} \\
 & \frac{864}{12150} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 150} \\
 & \frac{864}{121500} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 1500} \\
 & \frac{864}{1215000} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{(1+2) \times 15000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3167. \quad & \frac{866}{1299} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 6}{1^2 \times 9 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{866}{12990} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 6}{1^2 \times 9 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{866}{129900} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 6}{1^2 \times 9 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{866}{1299000} := \frac{8 \times 6 + 6}{1^2 \times 9 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3158. \quad & \frac{861}{1148} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{861}{11480} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{861}{114800} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{861}{1148000} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 1}{(1+1) \times 4 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3163. \quad & \frac{864}{1296} := \frac{8+64}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{864}{12960} := \frac{8+64}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{864}{129600} := \frac{8+64}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{864}{1296000} := \frac{8+64}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3168. \quad & \frac{868}{1240} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{868}{12400} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{868}{124000} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{868}{1240000} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{1 \times 2 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3159. \quad & \frac{862}{1293} := \frac{8+6 \times 2}{(1^2+9) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{862}{12930} := \frac{8+6 \times 2}{(1^2+9) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{862}{129300} := \frac{8+6 \times 2}{(1^2+9) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{862}{1293000} := \frac{8+6 \times 2}{(1^2+9) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3164. \quad & \frac{864}{1344} := \frac{86+4}{(1+34) \times 4} \\
 & \frac{864}{13440} := \frac{86+4}{(1+34) \times 40} \\
 & \frac{864}{134400} := \frac{86+4}{(1+34) \times 400} \\
 & \frac{864}{1344000} := \frac{86+4}{(1+34) \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3169. \quad & \frac{868}{1395} := \frac{8 \times (6+8)}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{868}{13950} := \frac{8 \times (6+8)}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{868}{139500} := \frac{8 \times (6+8)}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{868}{1395000} := \frac{8 \times (6+8)}{(1+3) \times 9 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3160. \quad & \frac{864}{1188} := \frac{8 \times 64}{11 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{864}{11880} := \frac{8 \times 64}{11 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{864}{118800} := \frac{8 \times 64}{11 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{864}{1188000} := \frac{8 \times 64}{11 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3165. \quad & \frac{864}{1350} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{1^3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{864}{13500} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{1^3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{864}{135000} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{1^3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{864}{1350000} := \frac{8+6 \times 4}{1^3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3170. \quad & \frac{868}{1488} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{868}{14880} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{868}{148800} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{868}{1488000} := \frac{8+6 \times 8}{(1 \times 4 + 8) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3161. \quad & \frac{864}{1188} := \frac{8+64}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{864}{11988} := \frac{8+64}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{864}{119988} := \frac{8+64}{11+9988} \\
 & \frac{864}{1199988} := \frac{8+64}{11+99988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3166. \quad & \frac{865}{1384} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 384} \\
 & \frac{865}{13840} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 3840} \\
 & \frac{865}{138400} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 38400} \\
 & \frac{865}{1384000} := \frac{8 \times 6 \times 5}{1 \times 384000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3171. \quad & \frac{872}{1090} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{872}{10900} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{872}{109000} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{872}{1090000} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3172. \quad & \frac{872}{1199} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 99} \\
 & \frac{872}{11990} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 990} \\
 & \frac{872}{119900} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 9900} \\
 & \frac{872}{1199000} := \frac{8 \times (7+2)}{1 \times 1 \times 99000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3177. \quad & \frac{874}{1012} := \frac{8+7+4}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{874}{10212} := \frac{8+7+4}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{874}{102212} := \frac{8+7+4}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{874}{1022212} := \frac{8+7+4}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3182. \quad & \frac{884}{1105} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{884}{11050} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{884}{110500} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{884}{1105000} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{1 \times 10 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3173. \quad & \frac{873}{1261} := \frac{8+7+3}{1 \times 26 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{873}{12610} := \frac{8+7+3}{1 \times 26 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{873}{126100} := \frac{8+7+3}{1 \times 26 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{873}{1261000} := \frac{8+7+3}{1 \times 26 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3178. \quad & \frac{880}{1155} := \frac{8+8+0}{1+15+5} \\
 & \frac{880}{12155} := \frac{8+8+0}{1+215+5} \\
 & \frac{880}{122155} := \frac{8+8+0}{1+2215+5} \\
 & \frac{880}{1222155} := \frac{8+8+0}{1+22215+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3183. \quad & \frac{884}{1144} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{(1+1) \times 44} \\
 & \frac{884}{11440} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{(1+1) \times 440} \\
 & \frac{884}{114400} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{(1+1) \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{884}{1144000} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{(1+1) \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3174. \quad & \frac{873}{13580} := \frac{8+(7+3)}{1 \times 35 \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{873}{135800} := \frac{8+(7+3)}{1 \times 35 \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{873}{1358000} := \frac{8+(7+3)}{1 \times 35 \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{873}{13580000} := \frac{8+(7+3)}{1 \times 35 \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3179. \quad & \frac{880}{1815} := \frac{8+8+0}{18+15} \\
 & \frac{880}{18315} := \frac{8+(8+0)}{18+315} \\
 & \frac{880}{183315} := \frac{8+(8+0)}{18+3315} \\
 & \frac{880}{1833315} := \frac{8+(8+0)}{18+33315}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3184. \quad & \frac{884}{1248} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{1 \times 2 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{884}{12480} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{1 \times 2 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{884}{124800} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{1 \times 2 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{884}{1248000} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3175. \quad & \frac{873}{1455} := \frac{8+7+3}{(1^4+5) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{873}{14550} := \frac{8+7+3}{(1^4+5) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{873}{145500} := \frac{8+7+3}{(1^4+5) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{873}{1455000} := \frac{8+7+3}{(1^4+5) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3180. \quad & \frac{882}{1078} := \frac{8+8^2}{10+78} \\
 & \frac{882}{10878} := \frac{8+8^2}{10+878} \\
 & \frac{882}{108878} := \frac{8+8^2}{10+8878} \\
 & \frac{882}{1088878} := \frac{8+8^2}{10+88878}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3185. \quad & \frac{884}{1287} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12+87} \\
 & \frac{884}{12987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12+987} \\
 & \frac{884}{129987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12+9987} \\
 & \frac{884}{1299987} := \frac{8 \times 8 + 4}{12+99987}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3176. \quad & \frac{874}{10120} := \frac{8+7+4}{(10+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{874}{101200} := \frac{8+7+4}{(10+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{874}{1012000} := \frac{8+7+4}{(10+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{874}{10120000} := \frac{8+7+4}{(10+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3181. \quad & \frac{882}{1617} := \frac{8+8+2}{16+17} \\
 & \frac{882}{16317} := \frac{8+8+2}{16+317} \\
 & \frac{882}{163317} := \frac{8+8+2}{16+3317} \\
 & \frac{882}{1633317} := \frac{8+8+2}{16+33317}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3186. \quad & \frac{884}{1326} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{(1+3^2) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{884}{13260} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{(1+3^2) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{884}{132600} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{(1+3^2) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{884}{1326000} := \frac{8+8 \times 4}{(1+3^2) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3187. \quad & \frac{884}{936} := \frac{(8 \times 8) + 4}{(9 + 3) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{884}{9360} := \frac{(8 \times 8) + 4}{(9 + 3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{884}{93600} := \frac{(8 \times 8) + 4}{(9 + 3) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{884}{936000} := \frac{(8 \times 8) + 4}{(9 + 3) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3192. \quad & \frac{888}{1258} := \frac{8 + 88}{(12 + 5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{888}{12580} := \frac{8 + 88}{(12 + 5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{888}{125800} := \frac{8 + 88}{(12 + 5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{888}{1258000} := \frac{8 + 88}{(12 + 5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3197. \quad & \frac{891}{1350} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 3 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{891}{13500} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 3 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{891}{135000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 3 \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{891}{1350000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 3 \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3188. \quad & \frac{885}{1475} := \frac{8 + 8 + 5}{1^4 \times 7 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{885}{14750} := \frac{8 + 8 + 5}{1^4 \times 7 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{885}{147500} := \frac{8 + 8 + 5}{1^4 \times 7 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{885}{1475000} := \frac{8 + 8 + 5}{1^4 \times 7 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3193. \quad & \frac{888}{1295} := \frac{8 + 8 \times 8}{(12 + 9) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{888}{12950} := \frac{8 + 8 \times 8}{(12 + 9) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{888}{129500} := \frac{8 + 8 \times 8}{(12 + 9) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{888}{1295000} := \frac{8 + 8 \times 8}{(12 + 9) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3198. \quad & \frac{891}{1368} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{891}{13680} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{891}{136800} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{891}{1368000} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 3 \times 6) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3189. \quad & \frac{886}{1329} := \frac{(8 + 8) \times 6}{(1 + 3)^2 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{886}{13290} := \frac{(8 + 8) \times 6}{(1 + 3)^2 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{886}{132900} := \frac{(8 + 8) \times 6}{(1 + 3)^2 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{886}{1329000} := \frac{(8 + 8) \times 6}{(1 + 3)^2 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3194. \quad & \frac{888}{1480} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{(1 + 4) \times 8 + 0} \\
 & \frac{888}{14800} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{(1 + 4) \times 80 + 0} \\
 & \frac{888}{148000} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{(1 + 4) \times 800 + 0} \\
 & \frac{888}{1480000} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{(1 + 4) \times 8000 + 0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3199. \quad & \frac{891}{1440} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{891}{14400} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{891}{144000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 4 \times 4000} \\
 & \frac{891}{1440000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 4 \times 40000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3190. \quad & \frac{888}{1184} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{888}{11840} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{888}{118400} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{888}{1184000} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3195. \quad & \frac{891}{1125} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 125} \\
 & \frac{891}{11250} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 1250} \\
 & \frac{891}{112500} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 12500} \\
 & \frac{891}{1125000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 125000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3200. \quad & \frac{891}{1485} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5} \\
 & \frac{891}{14850} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{891}{148500} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{891}{1485000} := \frac{8 + 91}{(1 + 4 \times 8) \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3191. \quad & \frac{888}{1221} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 21} \\
 & \frac{888}{12321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 321} \\
 & \frac{888}{123321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 3321} \\
 & \frac{888}{1233321} := \frac{8 + 8 + 8}{12 + 33321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3196. \quad & \frac{891}{1197} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 19 \times 7} \\
 & \frac{891}{11970} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 19 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{891}{119700} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 19 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{891}{1197000} := \frac{8 + 91}{1 \times 19 \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3201. \quad & \frac{892}{1338} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 2}{1 \times 3^3 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{892}{13380} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 2}{1 \times 3^3 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{892}{133800} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 2}{1 \times 3^3 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{892}{1338000} := \frac{8 \times 9 \times 2}{1 \times 3^3 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3202. \quad & \frac{902}{1353} := \frac{9 \times 02}{(1+3+5) \times 3} \\
 & \frac{902}{13530} := \frac{9 \times 02}{(1+3+5) \times 30} \\
 & \frac{902}{135300} := \frac{9 \times 02}{(1+3+5) \times 300} \\
 & \frac{902}{1353000} := \frac{9 \times 02}{(1+3+5) \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3207. \quad & \frac{905}{1448} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+4+4) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{905}{14480} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+4+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{905}{144800} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+4+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{905}{1448000} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+4+4) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3212. \quad & \frac{909}{1111} := \frac{9+09}{11+11} \\
 & \frac{909}{11211} := \frac{9+09}{11+211} \\
 & \frac{909}{112211} := \frac{9+09}{11+2211} \\
 & \frac{909}{1122211} := \frac{9+09}{11+22211}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3203. \quad & \frac{902}{1804} := \frac{9+02}{18+04} \\
 & \frac{902}{18204} := \frac{9+02}{18+204} \\
 & \frac{902}{182204} := \frac{9+02}{18+2204} \\
 & \frac{902}{1822204} := \frac{9+02}{18+22204}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3208. \quad & \frac{906}{10570} := \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(10+5) \times 7+0} \\
 & \frac{906}{105700} := \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(10+5) \times 70+0} \\
 & \frac{906}{1057000} := \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(10+5) \times 700+0} \\
 & \frac{906}{10570000} := \frac{9+0 \times 6}{(10+5) \times 7000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3213. \quad & \frac{909}{1212} := \frac{9+09}{1 \times 2 \times 12} \\
 & \frac{909}{12120} := \frac{9+09}{1 \times 2 \times 120} \\
 & \frac{909}{121200} := \frac{9+09}{1 \times 2 \times 1200} \\
 & \frac{909}{1212000} := \frac{9+09}{1 \times 2 \times 12000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3204. \quad & \frac{903}{1204} := \frac{9+0 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 04} \\
 & \frac{903}{12040} := \frac{9+0 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 040} \\
 & \frac{903}{120400} := \frac{9+0 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 0400} \\
 & \frac{903}{1204000} := \frac{9+0 \times 3}{(1+2) \times 04000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3209. \quad & \frac{906}{1359} := \frac{90+6}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{906}{13590} := \frac{90+6}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{906}{135900} := \frac{90+6}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{906}{1359000} := \frac{90+6}{(1+3 \times 5) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3214. \quad & \frac{909}{1313} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^3 \times 13} \\
 & \frac{909}{13130} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^3 \times 130} \\
 & \frac{909}{131300} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^3 \times 1300} \\
 & \frac{909}{1313000} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^3 \times 13000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3205. \quad & \frac{905}{1086} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+08) \times 6} \\
 & \frac{905}{10860} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+08) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{905}{108600} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+08) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{905}{1086000} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+08) \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3210. \quad & \frac{909}{1010} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1 \times 010} \\
 & \frac{909}{10100} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1 \times 0100} \\
 & \frac{909}{101000} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1 \times 01000} \\
 & \frac{909}{1010000} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1 \times 010000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3215. \quad & \frac{909}{1414} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^4 \times 14} \\
 & \frac{909}{14140} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^4 \times 140} \\
 & \frac{909}{141400} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^4 \times 1400} \\
 & \frac{909}{1414000} := \frac{9+0 \times 9}{1^4 \times 14000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3206. \quad & \frac{905}{1267} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+2+6) \times 7} \\
 & \frac{905}{12670} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+2+6) \times 70} \\
 & \frac{905}{126700} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+2+6) \times 700} \\
 & \frac{905}{1267000} := \frac{9 \times 05}{(1+2+6) \times 7000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3211. \quad & \frac{909}{1111} := \frac{90+9}{11 \times 11} \\
 & \frac{909}{11110} := \frac{90+9}{11 \times 110} \\
 & \frac{909}{111100} := \frac{90+9}{11 \times 1100} \\
 & \frac{909}{1111000} := \frac{90+9}{11 \times 11000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3216. \quad & \frac{910}{1001} := \frac{9+1+0}{10+01} \\
 & \frac{910}{10101} := \frac{9+1+0}{10+101} \\
 & \frac{910}{101101} := \frac{9+1+0}{10+1101} \\
 & \frac{910}{1011101} := \frac{9+1+0}{10+11101}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3217. \quad & \frac{912}{1216} := \frac{9 \times 1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{912}{12160} := \frac{9 \times 1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{912}{121600} := \frac{9 \times 1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{912}{1216000} := \frac{9 \times 1^2}{1 \times 2 \times 1 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3222. \quad & \frac{917}{10480} := \frac{91+7}{(10+4) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{917}{104800} := \frac{91+7}{(10+4) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{917}{1048000} := \frac{91+7}{(10+4) \times 8000} \\
 & \frac{917}{10480000} := \frac{91+7}{(10+4) \times 80000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3227. \quad & \frac{918}{1224} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{12 \times 2 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{918}{12240} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{12 \times 2 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{918}{122400} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{12 \times 2 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{918}{1224000} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{12 \times 2 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3218. \quad & \frac{913}{12450} := \frac{9+13}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 50} \\
 & \frac{913}{124500} := \frac{9+13}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 500} \\
 & \frac{913}{1245000} := \frac{9+13}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 5000} \\
 & \frac{913}{12450000} := \frac{9+13}{(1 \times 2+4) \times 50000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3223. \quad & \frac{917}{1179} := \frac{91+7}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{917}{11790} := \frac{91+7}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{917}{117900} := \frac{91+7}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{917}{1179000} := \frac{91+7}{(1+1) \times 7 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3228. \quad & \frac{918}{1275} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 75} \\
 & \frac{918}{12750} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 750} \\
 & \frac{918}{127500} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 7500} \\
 & \frac{918}{1275000} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+2) \times 75000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3219. \quad & \frac{913}{1826} := \frac{9+13}{18+26} \\
 & \frac{913}{18426} := \frac{9+13}{18+426} \\
 & \frac{913}{184426} := \frac{9+13}{18+4426} \\
 & \frac{913}{1844426} := \frac{9+13}{18+44426}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3224. \quad & \frac{918}{1020} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 020} \\
 & \frac{918}{10200} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 0200} \\
 & \frac{918}{102000} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 02000} \\
 & \frac{918}{1020000} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 020000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3229. \quad & \frac{918}{1292} := \frac{9+18}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{918}{12920} := \frac{9+18}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{918}{129200} := \frac{9+18}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{918}{1292000} := \frac{9+18}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3220. \quad & \frac{914}{1371} := \frac{9+1+4}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{914}{13710} := \frac{9+1+4}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{914}{137100} := \frac{9+1+4}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{914}{1371000} := \frac{9+1+4}{1 \times 3 \times 7 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3225. \quad & \frac{918}{1122} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 22} \\
 & \frac{918}{11220} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 220} \\
 & \frac{918}{112200} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 2200} \\
 & \frac{918}{1122000} := \frac{9+1+8}{1 \times 1 \times 22000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3221. \quad & \frac{915}{1220} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{915}{12200} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{915}{122000} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{915}{1220000} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 5}{(1+2) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3226. \quad & \frac{918}{1122} := \frac{9+18}{11+22} \\
 & \frac{918}{11322} := \frac{9+18}{11+322} \\
 & \frac{918}{113322} := \frac{9+18}{11+3322} \\
 & \frac{918}{1133322} := \frac{9+18}{11+33322}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3230. \quad & \frac{918}{1360} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+3) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{918}{13600} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+3) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{918}{136000} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+3) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{918}{1360000} := \frac{9 \times 18}{(1+3) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3231. \quad & \frac{918}{1428} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 28} \\
 & \frac{918}{14280} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 280} \\
 & \frac{918}{142800} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 2800} \\
 & \frac{918}{1428000} := \frac{9 \times 1 \times 8}{1 \times 4 \times 28000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3236. \quad & \frac{924}{1120} := \frac{9+24}{(1+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{924}{11200} := \frac{9+24}{(1+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{924}{112000} := \frac{9+24}{(1+1) \times 2000} \\
 & \frac{924}{1120000} := \frac{9+24}{(1+1) \times 20000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3241. \quad & \frac{924}{1260} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^2 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{924}{12600} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^2 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{924}{126000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^2 \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{924}{1260000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^2 \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3232. \quad & \frac{918}{952} := \frac{9+18}{(9+5) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{918}{9520} := \frac{9+18}{(9+5) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{918}{95200} := \frac{9+18}{(9+5) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{918}{952000} := \frac{9+18}{(9+5) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3237. \quad & \frac{924}{1155} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 55} \\
 & \frac{924}{11550} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 550} \\
 & \frac{924}{115500} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 5500} \\
 & \frac{924}{1155000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 1 \times 55000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3242. \quad & \frac{924}{1302} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+30) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{924}{13020} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+30) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{924}{130200} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+30) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{924}{1302000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+30) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3233. \quad & \frac{918}{9792} := \frac{9+18}{9 \times (7+9) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{918}{97920} := \frac{9+18}{9 \times (7+9) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{918}{979200} := \frac{9+18}{9 \times (7+9) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{918}{9792000} := \frac{9+18}{9 \times (7+9) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3238. \quad & \frac{924}{1176} := \frac{9+24}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{924}{11760} := \frac{9+24}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{924}{117600} := \frac{9+24}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{924}{1176000} := \frac{9+24}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3243. \quad & \frac{924}{1344} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{924}{13440} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{924}{134400} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{924}{1344000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{(1+3) \times 4 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3234. \quad & \frac{921}{1228} := \frac{9+2+1}{1^2 \times 2 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{921}{12280} := \frac{9+2+1}{1^2 \times 2 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{921}{122800} := \frac{9+2+1}{1^2 \times 2 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{921}{1228000} := \frac{9+2+1}{1^2 \times 2 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3239. \quad & \frac{924}{1232} := \frac{9 \times (2+4)}{12 \times 3 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{924}{12320} := \frac{9 \times (2+4)}{12 \times 3 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{924}{123200} := \frac{9 \times (2+4)}{12 \times 3 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{924}{1232000} := \frac{9 \times (2+4)}{12 \times 3 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3244. \quad & \frac{924}{1365} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 65} \\
 & \frac{924}{13650} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 650} \\
 & \frac{924}{136500} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 6500} \\
 & \frac{924}{1365000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^3 \times 65000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3235. \quad & \frac{924}{1050} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 050} \\
 & \frac{924}{10500} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 0500} \\
 & \frac{924}{105000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 05000} \\
 & \frac{924}{1050000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1 \times 050000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3240. \quad & \frac{924}{1232} := \frac{9+24}{12+32} \\
 & \frac{924}{12432} := \frac{9+24}{12+432} \\
 & \frac{924}{124432} := \frac{9+24}{12+4432} \\
 & \frac{924}{1244432} := \frac{9+24}{12+44432}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3245. \quad & \frac{924}{1470} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^4 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{924}{14700} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^4 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{924}{147000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^4 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{924}{1470000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 4}{1^4 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3246. \quad & \frac{925}{1369} := \frac{9 \times 25}{(1+36) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{925}{13690} := \frac{9 \times 25}{(1+36) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{925}{136900} := \frac{9 \times 25}{(1+36) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{925}{1369000} := \frac{9 \times 25}{(1+36) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3251. \quad & \frac{927}{1339} := \frac{9 \times 27}{13 \times 3 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{927}{13390} := \frac{9 \times 27}{13 \times 3 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{927}{133900} := \frac{9 \times 27}{13 \times 3 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{927}{1339000} := \frac{9 \times 27}{13 \times 3 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3256. \quad & \frac{936}{1144} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 44} \\
 & \frac{936}{11440} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 440} \\
 & \frac{936}{114400} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 4400} \\
 & \frac{936}{1144000} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 44000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3247. \quad & \frac{926}{1389} := \frac{(9+2) \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{926}{13890} := \frac{(9+2) \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{926}{138900} := \frac{(9+2) \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{926}{1389000} := \frac{(9+2) \times 6}{(1 \times 3 + 8) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3252. \quad & \frac{930}{1705} := \frac{9+3+0}{17+05} \\
 & \frac{930}{17205} := \frac{9+3+0}{17+205} \\
 & \frac{930}{172205} := \frac{9+3+0}{17+2205} \\
 & \frac{930}{1722205} := \frac{9+3+0}{17+22205}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3257. \quad & \frac{936}{1248} := \frac{9 \times 3 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 48} \\
 & \frac{936}{12480} := \frac{9 \times 3 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 480} \\
 & \frac{936}{124800} := \frac{9 \times 3 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{936}{1248000} := \frac{9 \times 3 + 6}{1 \times 2 \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3248. \quad & \frac{927}{1133} := \frac{9 \times (2+7)}{11 \times 3 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{927}{11330} := \frac{9 \times (2+7)}{11 \times 3 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{927}{113300} := \frac{9 \times (2+7)}{11 \times 3 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{927}{1133000} := \frac{9 \times (2+7)}{11 \times 3 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3253. \quad & \frac{932}{1165} := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 5} \\
 & \frac{932}{11650} := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 50} \\
 & \frac{932}{116500} := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 500} \\
 & \frac{932}{1165000} := \frac{(9+3) \times 2}{1 \times 1 \times 6 \times 5000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3258. \quad & \frac{936}{1287} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+87} \\
 & \frac{936}{12987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+987} \\
 & \frac{936}{129987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+9987} \\
 & \frac{936}{1299987} := \frac{(9+3) \times 6}{12+99987}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3249. \quad & \frac{927}{1133} := \frac{9+27}{11+33} \\
 & \frac{927}{11433} := \frac{9+27}{11+433} \\
 & \frac{927}{114433} := \frac{9+27}{11+4433} \\
 & \frac{927}{1144433} := \frac{9+27}{11+44433}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3254. \quad & \frac{932}{1398} := \frac{(9+3)^2}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{932}{13980} := \frac{(9+3)^2}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{932}{139800} := \frac{(9+3)^2}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{932}{1398000} := \frac{(9+3)^2}{1 \times 3 \times 9 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3259. \quad & \frac{936}{1872} := \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 72} \\
 & \frac{936}{18720} := \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 720} \\
 & \frac{936}{187200} := \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 7200} \\
 & \frac{936}{1872000} := \frac{9 \times 36}{(1+8) \times 72000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3250. \quad & \frac{927}{1236} := \frac{9+27}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{927}{12360} := \frac{9+27}{1 \times 2^3 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{927}{123600} := \frac{9+27}{1 \times 2^3 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{927}{1236000} := \frac{9+27}{1 \times 2^3 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3255. \quad & \frac{935}{1815} := \frac{9+3+5}{18+15} \\
 & \frac{935}{18315} := \frac{9+3+5}{18+315} \\
 & \frac{935}{183315} := \frac{9+3+5}{18+3315} \\
 & \frac{935}{1833315} := \frac{9+3+5}{18+33315}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3260. \quad & \frac{939}{1252} := \frac{9+39}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2} \\
 & \frac{939}{12520} := \frac{9+39}{1 \times 2^5 \times 20} \\
 & \frac{939}{125200} := \frac{9+39}{1 \times 2^5 \times 200} \\
 & \frac{939}{1252000} := \frac{9+39}{1 \times 2^5 \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

3261.

$$\frac{942}{1256} := \frac{9 \times 4^2}{1 \times 2^5 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{942}{12560} := \frac{9 \times 4^2}{1 \times 2^5 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{942}{125600} := \frac{9 \times 4^2}{1 \times 2^5 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{942}{1256000} := \frac{9 \times 4^2}{1 \times 2^5 \times 6000}$$

3266.

$$\frac{945}{1470} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 70}$$

$$\frac{945}{14700} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 700}$$

$$\frac{945}{147000} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 7000}$$

$$\frac{945}{1470000} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{1 \times 4 \times 70000}$$

3271.

$$\frac{951}{1268} := \frac{9 \times (5+1)}{(1+2+6) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{951}{12680} := \frac{9 \times (5+1)}{(1+2+6) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{951}{126800} := \frac{9 \times (5+1)}{(1+2+6) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{951}{1268000} := \frac{9 \times (5+1)}{(1+2+6) \times 8000}$$

3262.

$$\frac{944}{1180} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 180}$$

$$\frac{944}{11800} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 1800}$$

$$\frac{944}{118000} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 18000}$$

$$\frac{944}{1180000} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 4}{1 \times 180000}$$

3267.

$$\frac{946}{1032} := \frac{9+46}{10 \times 3 \times 2}$$

$$\frac{946}{10320} := \frac{9+46}{10 \times 3 \times 20}$$

$$\frac{946}{103200} := \frac{9+46}{10 \times 3 \times 200}$$

$$\frac{946}{1032000} := \frac{9+46}{10 \times 3 \times 2000}$$

3272.

$$\frac{952}{1088} := \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{(1+08) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{952}{10880} := \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{(1+08) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{952}{108800} := \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{(1+08) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{952}{1088000} := \frac{9 \times (5+2)}{(1+08) \times 8000}$$

3263.

$$\frac{945}{1155} := \frac{9+45}{11+55}$$

$$\frac{945}{11655} := \frac{9+45}{11+655}$$

$$\frac{945}{116655} := \frac{9+45}{11+6655}$$

$$\frac{945}{1166655} := \frac{9+45}{11+66655}$$

3268.

$$\frac{946}{1376} := \frac{9+4 \times 6}{(1^3+7) \times 6}$$

$$\frac{946}{13760} := \frac{9+4 \times 6}{(1^3+7) \times 60}$$

$$\frac{946}{137600} := \frac{9+4 \times 6}{(1^3+7) \times 600}$$

$$\frac{946}{1376000} := \frac{9+4 \times 6}{(1^3+7) \times 6000}$$

3273.

$$\frac{952}{1120} := \frac{9+5^2}{(1+1) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{952}{11200} := \frac{9+5^2}{(1+1) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{952}{112000} := \frac{9+5^2}{(1+1) \times 2000}$$

$$\frac{952}{1120000} := \frac{9+5^2}{(1+1) \times 20000}$$

3264.

$$\frac{945}{12600} := \frac{9+45}{12 \times 60+0}$$

$$\frac{945}{126000} := \frac{9+45}{12 \times 600+0}$$

$$\frac{945}{1260000} := \frac{9+45}{12 \times 6000+0}$$

3269.

$$\frac{946}{1419} := \frac{9 \times (4+6)}{(14+1) \times 9}$$

$$\frac{946}{14190} := \frac{9 \times (4+6)}{(14+1) \times 90}$$

$$\frac{946}{141900} := \frac{9 \times (4+6)}{(14+1) \times 900}$$

$$\frac{946}{1419000} := \frac{9 \times (4+6)}{(14+1) \times 9000}$$

3265.

$$\frac{945}{1365} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 65}$$

$$\frac{945}{13650} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 650}$$

$$\frac{945}{136500} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 6500}$$

$$\frac{945}{1365000} := \frac{9 \times 4 \times 5}{(1+3) \times 65000}$$

3270.

$$\frac{948}{1264} := \frac{9+4+8}{(1^2+6) \times 4}$$

$$\frac{948}{12640} := \frac{9+4+8}{(1^2+6) \times 40}$$

$$\frac{948}{126400} := \frac{9+4+8}{(1^2+6) \times 400}$$

$$\frac{948}{1264000} := \frac{9+4+8}{(1^2+6) \times 4000}$$

3274.

$$\frac{952}{1122} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+22}$$

$$\frac{952}{11322} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+322}$$

$$\frac{952}{113322} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{11+3322}$$

3275.

$$\frac{952}{1176} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{952}{11760} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{952}{117600} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{952}{1176000} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 1 \times 7 \times 6000}$$

3276.

$$\frac{952}{1224} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{952}{12240} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{952}{122400} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{952}{1224000} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2)^2 \times 4000}$$

3277.

$$\frac{952}{1232} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+32}$$

$$\frac{952}{12432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+432}$$

$$\frac{952}{124432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+4432}$$

$$\frac{952}{1244432} := \frac{9+5^2}{12+44432}$$

3278.

$$\frac{952}{1292} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2}$$

$$\frac{952}{12920} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 20}$$

$$\frac{952}{129200} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 200}$$

$$\frac{952}{1292000} := \frac{(9+5) \times 2}{(1+2 \times 9) \times 2000}$$

3279.

$$\frac{952}{1309} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+09}$$

$$\frac{952}{13209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+209}$$

$$\frac{952}{132209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+2209}$$

$$\frac{952}{1322209} := \frac{9+5+2}{13+22209}$$

3280.

$$\frac{952}{1344} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{952}{13440} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{952}{134400} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{952}{1344000} := \frac{9+5^2}{1 \times 3 \times 4 \times 4000}$$

3281.

$$\frac{952}{1428} := \frac{9+5+2}{(1^4+2) \times 8}$$

$$\frac{952}{14280} := \frac{9+5+2}{(1^4+2) \times 80}$$

$$\frac{952}{142800} := \frac{9+5+2}{(1^4+2) \times 800}$$

$$\frac{952}{1428000} := \frac{9+5+2}{(1^4+2) \times 8000}$$

3282.

$$\frac{954}{1325} := \frac{9+5+4}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 5}$$

$$\frac{954}{13250} := \frac{9+5+4}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 50}$$

$$\frac{954}{132500} := \frac{9+5+4}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 500}$$

$$\frac{954}{1325000} := \frac{9+5+4}{(1 \times 3+2) \times 5000}$$

3283.

$$\frac{955}{1146} := \frac{(9+5) \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 6}$$

$$\frac{955}{11460} := \frac{(9+5) \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 60}$$

$$\frac{955}{114600} := \frac{(9+5) \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 600}$$

$$\frac{955}{1146000} := \frac{(9+5) \times 5}{1 \times 14 \times 6000}$$

3284.

$$\frac{955}{1337} := \frac{9 \times 5+5}{(1+3 \times 3) \times 7}$$

$$\frac{955}{13370} := \frac{9 \times 5+5}{(1+3 \times 3) \times 70}$$

$$\frac{955}{133700} := \frac{9 \times 5+5}{(1+3 \times 3) \times 700}$$

$$\frac{955}{1337000} := \frac{9 \times 5+5}{(1+3 \times 3) \times 7000}$$

3285.

$$\frac{957}{1276} := \frac{9+57}{12+76}$$

$$\frac{957}{12876} := \frac{9+57}{12+876}$$

$$\frac{957}{128876} := \frac{9+57}{12+8876}$$

$$\frac{957}{1288876} := \frac{9+57}{12+88876}$$

3286.

$$\frac{963}{1177} := \frac{9+63}{11+77}$$

$$\frac{963}{11877} := \frac{9+63}{11+877}$$

$$\frac{963}{118877} := \frac{9+63}{11+8877}$$

$$\frac{963}{1188877} := \frac{9+63}{11+88877}$$

3287.

$$\frac{963}{1284} := \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 4}$$

$$\frac{963}{12840} := \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 40}$$

$$\frac{963}{128400} := \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 400}$$

$$\frac{963}{1284000} := \frac{96 \times 3}{12 \times 8 \times 4000}$$

3288.

$$\frac{963}{1391} := \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{13 \times 9 \times 1}$$

$$\frac{963}{13910} := \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{13 \times 9 \times 10}$$

$$\frac{963}{139100} := \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{13 \times 9 \times 100}$$

$$\frac{963}{1391000} := \frac{9 \times (6+3)}{13 \times 9 \times 1000}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3289. \quad & \frac{966}{1012} := \frac{9+6+6}{(10+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{966}{10120} := \frac{9+6+6}{(10+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{966}{101200} := \frac{9+6+6}{(10+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{966}{1012000} := \frac{9+6+6}{(10+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3294. \quad & \frac{968}{1408} := \frac{9+68}{14 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{968}{14080} := \frac{9+68}{14 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{968}{140800} := \frac{9+68}{14 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{968}{1408000} := \frac{9+68}{14 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3299. \quad & \frac{973}{1251} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+2)^5 \times 1} \\
 & \frac{973}{12510} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+2)^5 \times 10} \\
 & \frac{973}{125100} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+2)^5 \times 100} \\
 & \frac{973}{1251000} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{(1+2)^5 \times 1000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3290. \quad & \frac{966}{1012} := \frac{9+6+6}{10+12} \\
 & \frac{966}{10212} := \frac{9+6+6}{10+212} \\
 & \frac{966}{102212} := \frac{9+6+6}{10+2212} \\
 & \frac{966}{1022212} := \frac{9+6+6}{10+22212}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3295. \quad & \frac{972}{1188} := \frac{9+72}{11+88} \\
 & \frac{972}{11988} := \frac{9+72}{11+988} \\
 & \frac{972}{119988} := \frac{9+72}{11+9988}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3300. \quad & \frac{973}{1390} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 3 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{973}{13900} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 3 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{973}{139000} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 3 \times 9000} \\
 & \frac{973}{1390000} := \frac{9 \times 7 \times 3}{1 \times 3 \times 90000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3291. \quad & \frac{966}{1242} := \frac{9+6+6}{1+24+2} \\
 & \frac{966}{12742} := \frac{9+6+6}{1+274+2} \\
 & \frac{966}{127742} := \frac{9+6+6}{1+2774+2} \\
 & \frac{966}{1277742} := \frac{9+6+6}{1+27774+2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3296. \quad & \frac{972}{1296} := \frac{9+72}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{972}{12960} := \frac{9+72}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{972}{129600} := \frac{9+72}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{972}{1296000} := \frac{9+72}{1 \times 2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3301. \quad & \frac{981}{1090} := \frac{9 \times (8+1)}{1 \times 090} \\
 & \frac{981}{10900} := \frac{9 \times (8+1)}{1 \times 0900} \\
 & \frac{981}{109000} := \frac{9 \times (8+1)}{1 \times 09000} \\
 & \frac{981}{1090000} := \frac{9 \times (8+1)}{1 \times 090000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3292. \quad & \frac{966}{1288} := \frac{96 \times 6}{12 \times 8 \times 8} \\
 & \frac{966}{12880} := \frac{96 \times 6}{12 \times 8 \times 80} \\
 & \frac{966}{128800} := \frac{96 \times 6}{12 \times 8 \times 800} \\
 & \frac{966}{1288000} := \frac{96 \times 6}{12 \times 8 \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3297. \quad & \frac{972}{1458} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{972}{14580} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{972}{145800} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{972}{1458000} := \frac{(9+7) \times 2}{(1^4+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3302. \quad & \frac{981}{1199} := \frac{9 \times 81}{11 \times 9 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{981}{11990} := \frac{9 \times 81}{11 \times 9 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{981}{119900} := \frac{9 \times 81}{11 \times 9 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{981}{1199000} := \frac{9 \times 81}{11 \times 9 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3293. \quad & \frac{966}{1449} := \frac{96+6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9} \\
 & \frac{966}{14490} := \frac{96+6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 90} \\
 & \frac{966}{144900} := \frac{96+6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 900} \\
 & \frac{966}{1449000} := \frac{96+6}{(1+4 \times 4) \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3298. \quad & \frac{972}{1470} := \frac{9 \times 72}{14 \times 70} \\
 & \frac{972}{14700} := \frac{9 \times 72}{14 \times 700} \\
 & \frac{972}{147000} := \frac{9 \times 72}{14 \times 7000} \\
 & \frac{972}{1470000} := \frac{9 \times 72}{14 \times 70000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3303. \quad & \frac{981}{1308} := \frac{9+8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 08} \\
 & \frac{981}{13080} := \frac{9+8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 080} \\
 & \frac{981}{130800} := \frac{9+8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 0800} \\
 & \frac{981}{1308000} := \frac{9+8+1}{1 \times 3 \times 08000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3304. \quad & \frac{982}{1473} := \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times 7 \times 3} \\
 & \frac{982}{14730} := \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times 7 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{982}{147300} := \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times 7 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{982}{1473000} := \frac{98 \times 2}{14 \times 7 \times 3000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3309. \quad & \frac{984}{1476} := \frac{98 \times 4}{14 \times 7 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{984}{14760} := \frac{98 \times 4}{14 \times 7 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{984}{147600} := \frac{98 \times 4}{14 \times 7 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{984}{1476000} := \frac{98 \times 4}{14 \times 7 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3314. \quad & \frac{990}{1815} := \frac{9+9+0}{18+15} \\
 & \frac{990}{18315} := \frac{9+9+0}{18+315} \\
 & \frac{990}{183315} := \frac{9+9+0}{18+3315} \\
 & \frac{990}{1833315} := \frac{9+9+0}{18+33315}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3305. \quad & \frac{984}{1230} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{12 \times 30} \\
 & \frac{984}{12300} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{12 \times 300} \\
 & \frac{984}{123000} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{12 \times 3000} \\
 & \frac{984}{1230000} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{12 \times 30000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3310. \quad & \frac{986}{1160} := \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 60} \\
 & \frac{986}{11600} := \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 600} \\
 & \frac{986}{116000} := \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 6000} \\
 & \frac{986}{1160000} := \frac{(9+8) \times 6}{(1+1) \times 60000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3315. \quad & \frac{993}{1324} := \frac{9 \times 9 \times 3}{1 \times 324} \\
 & \frac{993}{13240} := \frac{9 \times 9 \times 3}{1 \times 3240} \\
 & \frac{993}{132400} := \frac{9 \times 9 \times 3}{1 \times 32400} \\
 & \frac{993}{1324000} := \frac{9 \times 9 \times 3}{1 \times 324000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3306. \quad & \frac{984}{1296} := \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1^2 \times 9 \times 6} \\
 & \frac{984}{12960} := \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1^2 \times 9 \times 60} \\
 & \frac{984}{129600} := \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1^2 \times 9 \times 600} \\
 & \frac{984}{1296000} := \frac{9+8 \times 4}{1^2 \times 9 \times 6000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3311. \quad & \frac{986}{1479} := \frac{98 \times 6}{14 \times 7 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{986}{14790} := \frac{98 \times 6}{14 \times 7 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{986}{147900} := \frac{98 \times 6}{14 \times 7 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{986}{1479000} := \frac{98 \times 6}{14 \times 7 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3316. \quad & \frac{996}{1245} := \frac{(9+9) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 45} \\
 & \frac{996}{12450} := \frac{(9+9) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 450} \\
 & \frac{996}{124500} := \frac{(9+9) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 4500} \\
 & \frac{996}{1245000} := \frac{(9+9) \times 6}{(1+2) \times 45000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3307. \quad & \frac{984}{1312} := \frac{9+8+4}{(13+1) \times 2} \\
 & \frac{984}{13120} := \frac{9+8+4}{(13+1) \times 20} \\
 & \frac{984}{131200} := \frac{9+8+4}{(13+1) \times 200} \\
 & \frac{984}{1312000} := \frac{9+8+4}{(13+1) \times 2000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3312. \quad & \frac{987}{1269} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 7}{12 \times 6 \times 9} \\
 & \frac{987}{12690} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 7}{12 \times 6 \times 90} \\
 & \frac{987}{126900} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 7}{12 \times 6 \times 900} \\
 & \frac{987}{1269000} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 7}{12 \times 6 \times 9000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3317. \quad & \frac{996}{1826} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+26} \\
 & \frac{996}{18426} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+426} \\
 & \frac{996}{184426} := \frac{9+9+6}{18+4426}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3308. \quad & \frac{984}{13448} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{(1+3^4) \times 48} \\
 & \frac{984}{134480} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{(1+3^4) \times 480} \\
 & \frac{984}{1344800} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{(1+3^4) \times 4800} \\
 & \frac{984}{13448000} := \frac{9 \times 8 \times 4}{(1+3^4) \times 48000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3313. \quad & \frac{990}{1155} := \frac{9+9+0}{1+15+5} \\
 & \frac{990}{12155} := \frac{9+9+0}{1+215+5} \\
 & \frac{990}{122155} := \frac{9+9+0}{1+2215+5} \\
 & \frac{990}{1222155} := \frac{9+9+0}{1+22215+5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3318. \quad & \frac{999}{1184} := \frac{9+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4} \\
 & \frac{999}{11840} := \frac{9+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 40} \\
 & \frac{999}{118400} := \frac{9+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 400} \\
 & \frac{999}{1184000} := \frac{9+9+9}{1 \times 1 \times 8 \times 4000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3319. \quad & \frac{999}{1221} := \frac{9+9+9}{12+21} \\
 & \frac{999}{999} := \frac{9+9+9}{9+9+9} \\
 & \frac{12321}{999} := \frac{12+321}{9+9+9} \\
 & \frac{123321}{999} := \frac{12+3321}{9+9+9} \\
 & \frac{1233321}{999} := \frac{12+33321}{9+9+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3320. \quad & \frac{999}{1258} := \frac{9+99}{(12+5) \times 8} \\
 & \frac{999}{12580} := \frac{9+99}{(12+5) \times 80} \\
 & \frac{999}{125800} := \frac{9+99}{(12+5) \times 800} \\
 & \frac{999}{1258000} := \frac{9+99}{(12+5) \times 8000}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3321. \quad & \frac{999}{1480} := \frac{9+9+9}{(1+4) \times 8+0} \\
 & \frac{999}{14800} := \frac{9+9+9}{(1+4) \times 80+0} \\
 & \frac{999}{148000} := \frac{9+9+9}{(1+4) \times 800+0} \\
 & \frac{999}{1480000} := \frac{9+9+9}{(1+4) \times 8000+0}
 \end{aligned}$$

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